

NONLOCAL EQUATIONS AND
APPLICATIONS

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A MATHEMATICIAN'S DECLARATION

This PhD thesis is the result of four years of research at the University of Western Australia under the invaluable supervision of my mentors and friends Prof. Serena Dipierro and Prof. Enrico Valdinoci. This work collects all the articles that I wrote during my candidature as a PhD student, with the precious help and guidance of my supervisors and of my esteemed collaborators Prof. Simon Blatt, Prof. Alberto Farina, Prof. Julian Scheuer and Prof. Armin Schikorra.

Now, before diving into the realm of nonlocality, I wish to share some thoughts which are the consequence of my academic experience.

In the process of submitting this thesis for the title of Doctor of Philosophy at the aforementioned institution I came to a discouraging realization regarding the nature of academia for a young mathematician like myself. Indeed, I had to recognize the existence of a duality in the figure of the modern researcher; a duality caused by the incompatibility of the ethical principles necessary to a fruitful collaboration between mathematicians, with the still, sterile, deeply rotten and declining bureaucracy imposed by the very same institutions which promote themselves as oases of knowledge and uncorrupted exchange of ideas.

On one hand, as researchers it is our duty to stand by the highest moral values which are so critical for the thriving of the scientific community, such as trust and respect in the framework of collaboration.

On the other hand, sometimes these values clash with the rules imposed on us by our institutions, rules that are the result of an approximative and destructive approach to regulation and are prompted by a poorly organized centralized system.

Instead of promoting a dialogue between the many departments of an institution and the legislative bodies of the latter, with the noble purpose of creating *ad hoc* regulations which take into account the different needs of different research fields, the universities blindly enforce the same legislation upon the different schools.

This phenomenon inevitably leads to injustice.

The first people impacted by the inequities resulting from this dysfunctional system are students and young researchers, who are not guaranteed an efficient collaborative environment, which is instead corrupted by the influence of a short-sighted bureaucracy.

In my personal experience this takes the form of an “author declaration”, enforced by these bodies and imposed by my institution, consisting of a dry statement regarding the specific contribution of the PhD candidate on the co-authored work in the thesis, completely incompatible with the type of creative process characteristic of a mathematical collaboration. In the wise words of some people who have been working in the field for much longer than I did:

True collaboration is more than the sum of individual contributions. It is a shared intellectual journey, marked by spontaneous insights, long hours of discussions, mutual challenges, repeated failures, rare but precious successes, and the kind of collective creativity that cannot be neatly partitioned. In mathematics, as in the arts, the value of a work often lies not in who contributed what, but in how the ideas came together. True collaboration only thrives in an environment of mutual trust, where all participants feel free to explore ideas, take intellectual risks, and support one another. In such a setting, assigning credit in a fractional or hierarchical manner may not only be misleading, but may also discourage the open exchange that fuels creativity.

For how relatable these words might sound to colleagues and illustrious exponents of the scientific community, they have no value to the distant and narrow mind of the bureaucratic body of my institution, which on the other hand forces me to present a document, which is detrimental to me just as much to my colleagues and to my future collaborations, as part of the institutional submission requirements.

I refuse to be subject to such a dull, ignorant and brute display of power, and I cannot accept to include such a document in this thesis. For this reason, regardless of the document I will have to submit to my university, I consider this to be my real PhD thesis, the real result of sincere scientific curiosity and sustained collaborative effort.

SIGNATURE:

Giovanni Giacomini

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INTRODUCTION

In this thesis we deal with a series of mathematical models and problems related to *nonlocal partial differential equations*. While “nonlocality” occurs in several fields of mathematics, the topic treated in this manuscript focuses on integro-differential equations of fractional types. Recently, these equations have gained the interest of the scientific community thanks to their aptness to describe a wide range of real-world phenomena.

The prototypical example of elliptic nonlocal operator is the *fractional Laplacian*, given by

$$(-\Delta)^s u(x) := c_{n,s} P.V. \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{u(x) - u(y)}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy$$

where *P.V.* stands for “principal value”, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $c_{n,s} > 0$ is a suitable normalizing constant. It is possible to interpret nonlocal operators as a generalization of classical differential operator, e.g. as $s \rightarrow 1$ then $(-\Delta)^s \rightarrow -\Delta$ see for instance [AV19].

A key feature of nonlocal PDEs is their ability to capture long-range interactions, making them particularly suitable to describe systems where the effect of components far away from each others is appreciable. In this regard, nonlocal PDEs often naturally arise as a by-product of the use of stochastic processes.

In the prototypical example of the fractional Laplacian, it can be showed that $(-\Delta)^s$ is the generator of a stochastic process known as *subordinate Brownian motion*, see e.g. [Boc49]. The idea is to consider the classical Brownian motion and introduce a random choice of the time t through what is known as *s-stable subordinator*, see e.g. [KSVc12; SSVc06].

The nonlocal parabolic PDE associated to such a process is known as the *fractional heat equation*, and takes the form

$$\partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) \quad \text{for } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Such an equation is a valid alternative to the classical heat equation when one aims at describing phenomena of anomalous diffusion. Indeed, the solution to such an equation decays as an inverse power law at infinity, in clear contrast with the fast exponential decay typical of the classical heat kernel.

This thesis is split into four parts. In Part I, we treat the biological theory of the *Lévy flight foraging hypothesis*. This conjecture challenges the paradigm of classical Brownian motion as preferred random strategy performed by animals in search of food, i.e. foragers, and instead suggests that foragers diffuse according to a scale-free fractal-like pattern, see for instance [Sim+08; Hum+10; Hum+12; HWS13].

In Chapter 2, we consider a forager diffusing via a fractional heat equation in the real line and we introduce several efficiency functionals whose optimality is discussed in relation to the Lévy exponent of the evolution equation.

Several biological scenarios, such as a target close to the forager, a sparse environment, a target located away from the forager and two targets are specifically taken into account.

The optimal strategies of each of these configurations are here analyzed explicitly also with the aid of some special functions of classical flavor and the results are confronted with the existing paradigms of the Lévy foraging hypothesis.

Interestingly, one discovers bifurcation phenomena in which a sudden switch occurs between an optimal (but somehow unreliable) Lévy foraging pattern of inverse square law type and a less ideal (but somehow more secure) classical Brownian motion strategy.

Additionally, optimal foraging strategies can be detected in the vicinity of the Brownian one even in cases in which the Brownian one is pessimizing an efficiency functional.

In Chapters 3 and 4 we provide a comprehensive approach to the spectral fractional heat equation that combines purely analytic and probabilistic perspectives. Furthermore, we give two new results on the monotonicity properties of the spectral fractional heat diffusion with respect to the fractional parameter.

The first result deals with the spectral fractional heat kernel, evaluated at the initial singularity. The second result considers the probability for the corresponding stochastic process of being confined in a subregion of the domain.

In both results, the monotonicity property depends on the size of the first non-zero eigenvalue.

The case of homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions is addressed in detail in Chapter 3, while Neumann boundary conditions are treated in Chapter 4.

In Chapter 5 we investigate the problem of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis in an ecological niche described by a bounded region of space, with either absorbing or reflecting boundary conditions.

To this end, we consider a forager diffusing according to a fractional heat equation in a bounded domain and we define several efficiency functionals whose optimality is discussed in relation to the fractional exponent $s \in (0, 1)$ of the diffusive equation.

Such equation is taken to be the spectral fractional heat equation (with Dirichlet or Neumann boundary conditions).

We analyze the biological scenarios in which a target is close to the forager. In particular, for all the efficiency functionals considered here, we show that if the target is close enough to the forager, then the most rewarding search strategy will be in a small neighborhood of $s = 0$.

Interestingly, we show that $s = 0$ is a global pessimizer for some of the efficiency functionals. From this, together with the aforementioned optimality results, we deduce that the most rewarding strategy can be unsafe or unreliable in practice, given its proximity with the pessimizing exponent, thus the forager may opt for a less performant, but safer, hunting method.

Interestingly, the biological literature has already collected several pieces of evidence of foragers diffusing with very low Lévy exponents, often in relation with a high energetic content of the prey. It is thereby suggestive to relate these patterns with a high-risk/high-gain strategy, in which the forager adopts a potentially very profitable, but also potentially completely unrewarding, strategy due to the high value of the possible outcome.

The case of a forager diffusing in the whole space is also considered, and it is treated in Chapter 6. There, we analyze the searching strategies of a forager diffusing in \mathbb{R}^n via an equation of fractional type. Specifically, the diffusion of the forager

is regulated by a Lévy flight whose exponent can be chosen in order to optimize a suitable foraging efficiency functional. Here, the dimension n is arbitrary. We notice that an example of fractional diffusion in the whole space was already considered in Chapter 2 when $n = 1$.

Furthermore, we show that the exponent $s = 0$ corresponding to the limit case of heavy-tailed Lévy flights is a pessimizer for the efficiency functional. On the other hand, we prove that, in situations of biological interest, one finds the most rewarding strategies arbitrarily close to $s = 0$. The combination of these results gives that the most rewarding searching option may turn out to be unfeasible, or at least unreliable, in practice, since small perturbations of the optimal searching exponent lead to pessimal patterns.

The cases analyzed specifically are those of a target located in the proximity of the forager and that of sparse prey modeled by a target infinitely far from the initial position of the seeker. The efficiency functionals taken into account are either of pointwise type (in which the predator and the prey are modeled by moving points) and of set-dependent type (in which the predator and the prey correspond to regions of space with uniform density, thus modeling also the case of a sight range of the biological individuals involved).

In Chapter 7, we consider the case of a stationary prey in a given region of space.

In particular, we show that if the prey is uniformly distributed, then the best possible strategy for the forager is to be stationary and uniformly distributed in the same region.

However, in several biological settings, foragers cannot be completely stationary, therefore we investigate the best seeking strategy for Lévy foragers in terms of the corresponding Lévy exponent. In this case, we show that the best strategy depends on the region size in which the prey is located: large regions exhibit optimal seeking strategies close to Gaussian random walks, while small regions favour Lévy foragers with small fractional exponent.

We also consider optimal strategies in view of the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey. When this distribution is supported in a suitable volume, then the foraging efficiency functional is monotone increasing with respect to the Lévy exponent and accordingly the optimal strategy is given by the Gaussian dispersal. If instead the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is

supported in the complement of a suitable volume, then the foraging efficiency functional is monotone decreasing with respect to the Lévy exponent and therefore the optimal strategy is given by a null fractional exponent (which in turn corresponds, from a biological standpoint, to a strategy of “ambush” type).

In Chapter 8, we apply the model developed in Chapter 7 to the case of foragers with finite lifetime (i.e., foragers which need to eat a certain amount of food in a given time, otherwise they die).

Specifically, we consider the case in which the initial distribution of the forager coincides with a stationary distribution of the targets and we determine the optimal Lévy exponent for the associated efficiency functional.

Namely, we show that if the Fourier transform of the prey distribution is supported in a sufficiently small ball, then the optimizer is given by a Gaussian dispersal, and if instead the Fourier transform of the prey distribution is supported in the complement of a suitable ball, then the ballistic diffusion provides an optimizer (precise conditions for the uniqueness of these optimizers are also given).

In Part II, we introduce the concept of nonlocal Willmore energy of a surface $\partial E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, which is defined as the L^p -norm of the fractional mean curvature of ∂E . Then, we discuss the existence of minimizers in the class of boundaries of convex sets for the critical and subcritical case.

In Chapter 10 we investigate surfaces with bounded L^p -norm of the fractional mean curvature, a quantity we shall refer to as *fractional Willmore-type functional*. In the subcritical case and under convexity assumptions we show how this Willmore-functional controls local parametrization, and conclude as consequences lower Ahlfors-regularity, a weak Michael-Simon type inequality, and an application to stability.

In Chapter 11, we consider the scaling-invariant nonlocal Willmore energy. Our main result is the existence of minimizers in the class of convex C^1 -curves. Also, by mean of the Maximum Principle, we use a barrier to show that convex curves that are not C^1 have infinite energy.

In Part III, we prove density estimates for minimizers of a nonlocal variational functional characterized by a double-well potential with slow growth from its minima.

More precisely, in Chapter 13 we provide density estimates for level sets of min-

minimizers of the energy

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx$$

where $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$ and W is a double-well potential with polynomial growth $m \in [p, +\infty)$ from the minima.

These kinds of potentials are “degenerate”, since they detach “slowly” from the minima, therefore they provide additional difficulties if one wishes to determine the relative sizes of the “layers” and the “pure phases”. To overcome these challenges, we introduce new barriers allowing us to rely on the fractional Sobolev inequality and on a suitable iteration method.

The proofs presented in Chapter 13 are robust enough to consider the case of quasilinear nonlocal equations driven by the fractional p -Laplacian, but our results are new even for the case $p = 2$.

In Chapter 14 we provide density estimates for a class of functions which includes all the minimizers of the energy

$$\mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := (1 - s) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \right) + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

where $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and W is a double-well potential with polynomial growth $m \in [p, +\infty)$ from the minima.

Moreover, making use of a Γ -convergence result for \mathcal{E}_s^p as $s \rightarrow 1$, we obtain density estimates for the minimizers of the limit energy functional, which takes the form

$$\mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{K_{n,p}}{2p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^p + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

for a suitable $K_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$.

In Part IV, we prove a geometrical algorithm to explicitly write the solution of a Dirichlet problem for s -harmonic maps in balls.

We provide a fractional counterpart of the classical results by Schwarz and Malmheden on harmonic functions. From that we obtain a representation formula for s -harmonic functions as a linear superposition of weighted classical harmonic

functions which also entails a new proof of the fractional Harnack inequality. This proof also leads to optimal constants for the fractional Harnack inequality in the ball.

PART I

NONLOCAL DIFFUSION AND FORAGING
THEORY

1

INTRODUCTION TO PART I

Foraging theory (see e.g. [SK86b]) is a cross-disciplinary topic of investigation that gathers together researchers from different areas (such as biologists, ethologists, physicists, statisticians, computer scientists, mathematicians, etc.). It is commonly accepted that the variety of environmental and biological situations in nature have led over time to highly efficient foraging strategies.

In general, the precise determination of optimal foraging strategies depends in a very complex way on a large number of parameters; furthermore, the collection and analysis of empirical data are typically challenging tasks, also open to controversial interpretations due to the use of different mathematical models or even due to spurious information (see e.g. [Edw+07]).

A rather consolidated attempt to understand and classify different foraging strategies according to the evolution of the distribution of the searchers lies in the so-called Lévy flight foraging hypothesis. Namely, rather than diffusing in analogy to the classical Brownian motion, empirical evidence has often backed the hypothesis that animals move according to a scale-free fractal-like pattern similar to the one produced by long-jump random walks of Lévy type possibly to avoid being trapped in a search of food confined in a narrow region beyond sensory range and to reduce the chances of intensively revisiting immediate surrounding areas in environments of scarce resources (see e.g. [Sim+08; Hum+10; Hum+12; HWS13] for empirical evidence for such biological Lévy flights).

Therefore, Lévy flights seem to be a better search strategy when the source of food is scarce and sparsely distributed and there is a large area to be covered in order to succeed in the hunt.

The aim of Chapters 2-8 is to build a mathematical model to test the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis in the framework of nonlocal diffusion and under different environmental scenarios.

In particular, we will consider the case of a forager diffusing either in the whole space \mathbb{R}^n or in a bounded domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$. Due to the nonlocal nature of the problem, these two situations require the use of different operators inducing the diffusion. For this reason we will treat them separately, see Section 1.1 for the diffusion in bounded domains and Section 1.2 for the diffusion in \mathbb{R}^n .

More precisely, to describe the diffusion of the forager we will make use of a *fractional heat equation* of the form

$$\partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) \quad \text{for } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$$

where $s \in (0, 1)$ and $(-\Delta)^s$ is either the *fractional Laplacian*, if the diffusion occurs in $\Omega = \mathbb{R}^n$, or, if Ω is a bounded domain, the *spectral fractional Laplacian*, see e.g. [AV19] for further details on these operators.

The choice for such a diffusion equation relies on the fact that the density associated to a forager performing long-jump random walks of Lévy type converges to the solution of a fractional heat equation in the continuum limit of the time and space step approaching zero. See for instance Section 4.3 in [AV19] and Section 2.1 in [BV16] for a heuristic explanation of this fact.

Furthermore, to test the hypothesis, we will build efficiency functionals, which depend on the distribution of the forager, on the distribution of the targets and on the time span of the hunt. The idea is to first consider a foraging success functional, which, roughly speaking, will be taken to be proportional to the encounter rate between the forager and the target. Also, to assure that our model is biologically feasible, we will compare this quantity, which is advantageous for the forager, with some quantities which instead provide a penalization for the forager. In this way we obtain efficiency functionals which somehow account for the rate of hunting success for the predator versus the effort needed.

1.1 Main results in bounded domains - Chapters 3, 4 and 5

The problem of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis in an ecological niche is treated in Chapter 5. The region of space in which the diffusion occurs is described by some bounded domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, with either absorbing or reflecting boundary conditions.

The mathematical setting that we consider here goes as follows. We model a forager moving in some bounded region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ through a spectral fractional diffusion with either Dirichlet or Neumann homogeneous boundary conditions. The domain Ω where the diffusion occurs can be seen as an ecological niche where the forager is confined (the Dirichlet condition corresponding to the case in which the forager is killed at the boundary of the niche, and the Neumann datum corresponding e.g. to fences that prevent the forager to exit the niche).

Specifically, the probability density $u = u(t, x)$ of the forager satisfies the diffusive equation

$$\partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) \quad \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega,$$

with either Dirichlet or Neumann homogeneous boundary conditions.

Here above s is a fractional parameter in $(0, 1)$ and the operator $(-\Delta)^s$ represents the spectral fractional Laplacian, see e.g. Sections 2.3 and 4.3 in [AV19] for the basics of this operator.

More specifically, as detailed in Chapter 3, for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $y \in \Omega$ the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation starting at y reads as

$$(1.1) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ u(t, x) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \Omega. \end{cases}$$

where the last equation is meant in the sense of measure (see the comment after equation (3.10)).

Analogously, as treated in Chapter 4, for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $y \in \Omega$, the Neumann

spectral fractional heat equation starting at y , can be written as

$$(1.2) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu}(t, x) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \Omega, \end{cases}$$

where the last equation is always meant in the sense of measure.

For a detailed introductions to the operators $(-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s$ and $(-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s$ see Section 3.2 and 4.2 respectively in Chapters 3 and 4.

In what follows we adopt the subscript $*$ to denote that the quantity considered can refer to either the Dirichlet or Neumann problem.

The choice of a spectral fractional Laplacian is motivated by its stochastic interpretation. Indeed, in Theorem 3.19, Proposition 3.21 and Theorem 4.15, Proposition 4.17 respectively in Chapters 3 and 4, we show that the fundamental solution to equation (1.1) and (1.2), which will be denoted by $r_*^s(t, x, y)$, is the transition density of a stochastic process known as *subordinate Brownian motion*.

To be more precise, the stochastic process induced by the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian, is known as the *subordinate killed Brownian motion*. Roughly speaking, such a process is built from the the process generated by the Dirichlet Laplacian, known as killed Brownian motion, by introducing a random choice of time via a procedure called *subordination* (see [Boc49]).

Analogously, the stochastic process whose transition density is the solution to (1.2) is obtained by subordinating the process known as reflecting Brownian motion.

The random choice of time in the aforementioned subordination process is mediate through a stochastic process known as *s-stable subordinator*, see e.g. Definition 3.17 in Chapter 3. The *s-stable subordinator* admits a density, see equation (5.31) in Chapter 5, which decays at infinity as an inverse power law of degree $1 + s$, see Lemma 5.18 in Chapter 5. In particular, from this asymptotic, we deduce that, roughly speaking, the fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1)$ determines the probability with which the random choice of time in the Brownian motion is either characterized by very large times, for s close to 0, or for smaller times, for s close to 1. For further details see Chapters 3, 4 and Section 5.2 in Chapter 5.

For what concerns the targets, we assume that they are scattered in Ω according to a distribution $p(t, x)$, where $(t, x) \in [0, +\infty) \times \Omega$.

In order to measure the effectiveness of a foraging strategy, we consider different functionals which account for the rate of hunting “success” for the predator versus the “effort” needed.

We consider, as an initial measure of the success of the hunting strategy of the predator, a *foraging success functional* which accounts for the random encounters between the forager following the anomalous diffusion in equations in (1.1) and (1.2) and the targets.

More precisely, if Y_* is the subordinate Brownian motion associated with the transition density r_*^s , then, the quantity

$$\mathbb{E}[p(t, Y_t) | Y_0 = y] := \int_{\Omega} r_*^s(t, \xi, y) p(t, \xi) d\xi$$

coincides with the expected density of encounters between a target and the forager at the time $t > 0$, assuming that the search started at $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Since we are interested in the overall result over some time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$, the foraging success functional takes the form

$$(1.3) \quad \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} r_*^s(t, x, y) p(t, x) dx dt.$$

To obtain an efficiency functional, we compare this quantity with some other quantities of biological significance that instead provide a penalization for the seeker. Here, we will consider as penalization quantities the *time* T , the *average distance traveled by the forager* $l_*^y(s, T)$ after a time T and the *mean square displacement* $\mathcal{A}_*^y(s, T)$ after a time T .

More explicitly, the average distance traveled by the forager at time $T \in (0, +\infty)$ is given by

$$l_*^y(s, T) := \int_0^T \mathbb{E}_y^s[|Y_{*,t}|] dt = \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\zeta - y| r_*^s(t, \zeta, y) d\zeta dt.$$

Similarly, the mean square displacement is given by

$$\mathcal{A}_*^y(s, T) := \int_0^T \mathbb{E}_y^s[|Y_{*,t}|^2] dt = \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\zeta - y|^2 r_*^s(t, \zeta, y) d\zeta dt.$$

As a special case of target distribution $p(t, \xi)$, we consider the situation in which there is only one target located at $x \in \Omega$. In this case, the distribution $p(t, \xi)$ reduces

to the Dirac's delta $\delta_x(\xi)$ and the foraging success functional in (1.3) will be denoted by

$$\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) = \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} r_*^s(t, \zeta, y) \delta_x(\zeta) d\zeta dt = \int_0^T r_*^s(t, x, y) dt.$$

In Chapter 5, we focus on the optimal foraging strategy according to the following efficiency functionals:

$$(1.4) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{1,*}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T)}{T}, & \mathcal{E}_{2,*}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T)}{I_*^y(s, T)} \\ \text{and } \mathcal{E}_{3,*}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T)}{\mathcal{A}_*^y(s, T)} \end{aligned}$$

In addition to the functionals in (1.4), we consider the following set-dependent functionals. Here, the exact initial positions of target and forager are replaced by uniform densities in two subregions of Ω . Namely, we assume that the targets are distributed in Ω according to

$$p(t, x) := \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}(x)}{|\Omega_1|},$$

for some measurable set $\Omega_1 \subset \Omega$, where χ_{Ω_1} is the characteristic function of Ω_1 and $|\Omega_1|$ denotes the Lebesgue measure of Ω_1 .

The forager diffusing via the spectral fractional heat equation is initially uniformly distributed in some measurable set $\Omega_2 \subset \Omega$ and therefore, its density in $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ is given by

$$f_*^s(t, x) := \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_2} r_*^s(t, x, y) dy,$$

see e.g. Lemmas 3.27 and 4.23 respectively in Chapters 3 and 4.

With this notation, the *set-dependent forager success functional* takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} f_*^s(t, x) p(t, x) dx dt \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} r_*^s(t, x, y) dx dy dt. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, in this framework, the average distance traveled by the forager and the mean square displacement are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{l}_*^{\Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| f_*^s(t, \xi) d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega \times \Omega_2} |\xi - y| r_*^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dy dt \\ \text{and } \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_*^{\Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y|^2 f_*^s(t, \xi) d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega \times \Omega_2} |\xi - y|^2 r_*^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dy dt.\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, with these set-dependent foraging success functional and penalization quantities, we define the *set-dependent efficiency functionals* as

$$(1.5) \quad \begin{aligned}\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,*}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T)}{T}, & \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,*}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T)}{\tilde{l}_*^{\Omega_2}(s, T)} \\ \text{and } \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,*}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T)}{\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_*^{\Omega_2}(s, T)}.\end{aligned}$$

Now that we have established the mathematical framework needed to discuss the foraging hypothesis in bounded domains, we are ready to state the main results contained in Chapter 5.

First, we show that for each $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$, satisfying $x \neq y$, the first Dirichlet functional $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T)$ attains its infimum at $s = 0$. Moreover, we show that the Dirichlet functionals in (5.6) admit a finite limit for $s \searrow 0$, as far as $x \neq y$.

Theorem 1.1 (Theorem 5.6 in Chapter 5). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, for every $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$ with $x \neq y$, it holds that

$$(1.6) \quad \inf_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = 0.$$

Moreover, we have that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{3,D}^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty).$$

The following two theorems are the most important results of Chapter 5:

Theorem 1.2 (Theorem 5.7 in Chapter 5). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $\delta = \delta_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x \in B_\delta(y) \setminus \{y\}$ it holds that

$$\sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{1, D}^{x, y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1, D}^{x, y}\left(s_{x, y, T}^{(1)}, T\right) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x, y, T}^{(1)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Moreover, for each $j \in \{2, 3\}$ it holds that

$$(1.7) \quad \mathcal{E}_{j, D}^{x, y}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{j, D}^{x, y}(s, T).$$

Moreover, an analogous situation holds true also for the Neumann functionals in (1.4):

Theorem 1.3 (Theorem 5.8 in Chapter 5). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $\delta = \delta_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x \in B_\delta(y) \setminus \{y\}$ and for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ it holds that

$$\sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{j, N}^{x, y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{j, N}^{x, y}\left(s_{x, y, T}^{(j)}, T\right) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x, y, T}^{(j)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Therefore, from Theorems 1.2 and 1.3 we deduce that if the initial position of the forager approaches the position of the target, the fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1)$ maximizing the functionals in (1.3) converges to 0.

We notice that, as detailed in Remark 5.9 in Chapter 5, on the one hand, Theorem 1.1 establishes that $s = 0$ is a global minimizer for $\mathcal{E}_{1, D}$. On the other hand, if $s_{x, y, T}^{(1)}$ is a maximizer of $\mathcal{E}_{1, D}^{x, y}(\cdot, T)$, then from Theorem 1.2 we evince that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow y} s_{x, y, T}^{(1)} = 0.$$

This means that as x approaches y , the maximizer of the functional $\mathcal{E}_{1, D}^{x, y}$ converges to $s = 0$, which is a global minimizer. Therefore, a small perturbation of $s_{x, y, T}^{(1)}$ can lead to very small values for $\mathcal{E}_{1, D}$, making such choice of the most rewarding fractional exponent quite unreliable.

Things turn out to be different for $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{3,D}^{x,y}$. Indeed, see equation (1.7), for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, if x and y are close enough, then

$$\mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}(s, T),$$

so that $s = 0$ in these two cases is “almost” a maximizer. Roughly speaking, we can say that the functionals $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{3,D}$ present more reliable optimal configurations than $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$.

In Remark 5.10 in Chapter 5 we provide an interpretation of the unreliability of the optimizer as a high-risk/high-reward strategy. Indeed, in [Wea+14] it has been observed that the case $s = 0$ occurs when some marine predators aim at preys with a high-energy content. In this way, one can think that the high gain prospected by the energy content of the prey may serve as a mitigation of the chance of failure entailed by a very beneficial, but risky, strategy.

One may wonder whether the unreliability of the most rewarding strategies is specific of a forager confined in a bounded region and a nearby prey. As showed in Chapter 6, this is not the case. Indeed, we will prove that the same result holds for a predator diffusing in the whole space and also for a prey located arbitrarily far from the predator. We will discuss this in the following section.

We now focus our analysis on the set dependent functionals in (1.5).

The following result can be considered as the set-dependent counterpart of Theorem 1.1.

Theorem 1.4 (Theorem 5.14 in Chapter 5). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and smooth and disjoint sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$, it holds that

$$(1.8) \quad \inf_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = 0.$$

Moreover, we have that

$$(1.9) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty).$$

In Theorems 1.2 and 1.3 we have established that the Neumann and Dirichlet functionals in (1.4) have a common feature. Indeed, if the prey location $x \in \Omega$ is in

a sufficiently small neighborhood of the forager starting position $y \in \Omega$, then $\mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{j,N}^{x,y}$ attain their maximum for some value close to $s = 0$.

This characteristic is somewhat preserved if we consider the set-dependent functionals in (1.5). Indeed, we can show that if Ω_1, Ω_2 are close enough (in a sense that will be made precise later), then also for the functionals in (1.5) a strongly nonlocal search strategy will be preferred.

Before stating the precise results we fix some notation. For each $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $r \in (0, +\infty)$ we denote

$$r_y B := \{r(x - y) + y \quad \text{s.t. } x \in B\}.$$

Theorem 1.5 (Theorem 5.15 in Chapter 5). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $r = r_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for any smooth and disjoint sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_r(y)$ it holds that

$$(1.10) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)}, T \right) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Moreover, let $K \Subset \Omega$ be star-shaped with respect to some $y \in K$. Then, for all $j \in \{2, 3\}$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, there exists some $r = r_{\varepsilon, K, T, \Omega}$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset r_y K$ are smooth and disjoint it holds that

$$(1.11) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T).$$

As a consequence of Theorems 1.4 and 1.5 we can deduce that the most rewarding strategy may not be the safest, similarly to what happens for the functional $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$. Also, a result analogous to Theorem 1.3 holds true when considering the Neumann functionals in (1.5).

Theorem 1.6 (Theorem 5.16 in Chapter 5). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $r = r_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for any smooth and disjoint sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_r(y)$ and for each $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ it holds that

$$(1.12) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(j)}, T \right) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(j)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

1.2 Main results in \mathbb{R}^n - Chapters 2, 6, 7 and 8

In Chapters 2, 6, 7 and 8 we study the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis when the forager diffuses in the whole space \mathbb{R}^n .

To start with, one needs to define an energy that quantifies the success of the hunt in relation to the distribution of foragers, denoted by $u(t, x)$, and of preys, denoted by $p(t, x)$. Here, $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the space variable and $t \in [0, +\infty)$ denotes the time variable.

The *foraging success functional* accounting for the random encounters of foragers and preys over a time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$ takes the form

$$(1.13) \quad \mathcal{F}_0(u, p, T) := \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u(t, x) p(t, x) dx dt.$$

To build a feasible efficiency functional, we will compare this quantity, which is advantageous for the forager, with the inverse of the time span T , namely

$$(1.14) \quad \mathcal{F}(u, p, T) := \frac{1}{T} \mathcal{F}_0(u, p, T).$$

We notice that the choice of taking the average over the time span is based on the ansatz that for a searching strategy to be efficient, it is important not only to ensure a foraging success for the predator, but also to do so as quickly as possible.

The main objective in these chapters is to maximize the quantity in (1.14) for some fixed $p(t, x)$ in a suitably chosen class of densities $u(t, x)$. From a biological standpoint this corresponds to maximise the encounter rate between forager and prey by choosing an optimal search strategy, or density, for the forager $u(t, x)$.

In Chapters 2 and 6, the diffusion considered for the forager is that modeled by the fractional heat equation,

$$(1.15) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^n. \end{cases}$$

When $s = 1$, the operator $-(-\Delta)^s$ reduces to the standard Laplacian (i.e., the sum of pure second derivatives). Instead, when $s \in (0, 1)$ the fractional Laplacian is defined as

$$-(-\Delta)^s u(x) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{u(x+y) + u(x-y) - 2u(x)}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy,$$

up to a normalizing constant that we disregard for simplicity (see e.g. [AV19] and the references therein for the basics of the fractional Laplace operator).

Analogously to the spectral case, the solution to (1.15) is the transition density of the stochastic process called *subordinate Brownian motion*, see e.g. [KSVc12; SSVc06].

We assume that the forager may tune the fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1]$ in order to maximize the convenience of the corresponding hunting strategy. In this context, we recall that $s = 1$ in (6.2) corresponds to the classical diffusion pattern induced by the Brownian motion, while $s \in (0, 1)$ is related to an anomalous diffusion produced by the corresponding Lévy flight, see e.g. Section 4 in [AV19] and the references therein.

We denote by $G^s(t, x, y)$ the solution to (6.2). In our model, $G^s(t, x, y)$ describes the forager's distribution at time $t \in (0, +\infty)$ with respect to the spatial position $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The point $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ identifies the initial position of the forager (indeed, as customary, the notation δ_y in (6.2) represents the Dirac delta distribution centred at y).

It is important to observe that the energy in (1.14) with $u(t, x) := G^s(t, x, y)$ has a precise stochastic interpretation. Indeed, as detailed in Section 6.2 of Chapter 6, if we denote by X the subordinate Brownian motion associated with the transition density G^s , the quantity

$$(1.16) \quad \mathbb{E}[p(t, X_t), X_0 = y] := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, \xi, y) p(t, \xi) d\xi$$

coincides with expected density of encounters between the target and the forager at time $t > 0$, assuming that the search started at $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$. As a result, the efficiency functional in (1.14), in this case coincides with the average over the time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$ of the expected density in (1.16).

If we assume that the target is stationary, i.e. it remains at a given point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for all times, we have that $p(t, \xi) = \delta_x(\xi)$, and the efficiency functional in (1.14) reduces to

$$(1.17) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(G^s(\cdot, \cdot, y), \delta_x, T) &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, \xi, y) \delta_x(\xi) d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T G^s(t, x, y) dt. \end{aligned}$$

For the sake of notation, for every $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $s \in (0, 1]$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$ we adopt the notation

$$\mathcal{F}(G^s(\cdot, \cdot, y), \delta_x, T) =: \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T).$$

Furthermore, we will also consider the scenario in which the precise locations of the seeker and the prey are replaced by uniform distributions in subregions of \mathbb{R}^n . More precisely, given some measurable and bounded sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, we denote by $u_{\Omega_2}^s(t, x)$ the solution to the equation

$$(1.18) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n \\ u(0, x) = \frac{\chi_{\Omega_2}(x)}{|\Omega_2|} & \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^n, \end{cases}$$

and we assume that the target is uniformly distributed in Ω_1 , namely

$$p(t, \xi) := \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}(\xi)}{|\Omega_1|}.$$

With this choice, the efficiency functional in (1.14) can be rewritten as the *set-dependent efficiency functional*

$$(1.19) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}\left(u_{\Omega_2}^s, \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}}{|\Omega_1|}, T\right) &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u_{\Omega_2}^s(t, \xi) \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}(\xi)}{|\Omega_1|} d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}(\xi)}{|\Omega_1|} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, z, \xi) \frac{\chi_{\Omega_2}(z)}{|\Omega_2|} dz d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{T|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} G^s(t, x, y) dx dy dt. \end{aligned}$$

In such a framework, for the sake of notation, we denote

$$\mathcal{F}\left(u_{\Omega_2}^s, \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}}{|\Omega_1|}, T\right) =: \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T).$$

From a biological standpoint we observe that $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ is proportional to the integral over the time $t \in (0, T)$ of the expected number of encounters at t for a forager starting the search in the region Ω_2 and a prey spread in Ω_1 , with uniform distributions.

Now that we have defined the mathematical setting we use throughout the Chapters 2, 6, 7 and 8, we are ready to discuss the main results.

In Chapter 2 we analyze the one dimensional case. More precisely, for $n = 1$, we define several efficiency functionals. These are built by comparing the quantity in (1.13), which is advantageous for the forager, with quantities of interests which instead provide a penalization for the seeker's strategy, such as the time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$ or the average distance walked by the forager, see equations (2.7) and (2.8) in Chapter 2. The corresponding efficiency functionals thus compare, the outcome of the forager's hunt with the effort required to implement it.

Furthermore, several biological environments are considered, such as the one of a target close to the initial position of the predator, of a sparse distribution of targets or a remotely located target. Mathematically, this corresponds to suitably choosing the target density $p(t, \xi)$ in (1.13) to model each of these scenarios.

By doing so, we obtain the efficiency functionals in equations (2.15), (2.23) and (2.30) in Chapter 2.

Our objective was to understand which Lévy exponent optimizes, or pessimizes, a given efficiency functional for a given distribution of targets.

Our findings show that the *theoretical optimality* of an exponent has to be confronted with the *practical reliability* of the corresponding hunting strategy, since we pointed out the occurrence of *bifurcation phenomena* depending on the environmental parameters in which a sudden switch takes place between a theoretically optimal exponent and a less ideal, but more secure, foraging procedure.

In particular, optimal exponents can be located arbitrarily close to pessimal ones, making the practical choice of the hunting strategy a delicate balance between a striving for maximum success and a more conservative attitude to prioritize safety, see e.g. (2.17).

In Chapter 6, we show that such a phenomenon, where the optimal exponent gets arbitrarily close to a pessimizer, can be observed also in higher dimension. Hence, from now on we will assume that $n \geq 1$.

To formally discuss this behaviour, in analogy with what we showed in Theorem 1.1 equation (1.6), we begin by stating that independently from the starting position of the forager $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, of the prey location $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (as far as $x \neq y$) and of the time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$, the strategy $s = 0$ is a global minimizer for $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(\cdot, T)$:

Theorem 1.7 (Theorem 6.2 in Chapter 6). *Let $(x, y, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$ such that $x \neq y$. Then,*

$$\inf_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = 0.$$

We now focus on the optimal pattern. In particular, some general results are obtained in terms of asymptotic analysis.

First, we show that as the prey location gets closer and closer to the initial position of the forager the fractional parameter maximizing the efficiency functional approaches the value $s = 0$.

Theorem 1.8 (Theorem 6.3 in Chapter 6). *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $r = r_{\varepsilon, n, T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| \in (0, r)$ it holds that*

$$\sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Now, we focus our attention on the case of sparse targets. More precisely, we show that when the target diverges towards infinity, the most rewarding strategy converges to the value $s = 0$.

Theorem 1.9 (Theorem 6.6 in Chapter 6). *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $R = R_{\varepsilon, n, T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| > R$ it holds that*

$$(1.20) \quad \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

In Theorems 1.8 and 1.9 we showed that as the forager is getting closer or further from them prey location, the optimizer for \mathcal{E} is converging to $s = 0$.

However, we notice that the case $s = 0$ is a minimizer, as pointed out in Theorem 1.7.

This situation clearly shows that in cases of biological interest the most rewarding strategy (i.e. the one maximizing an efficiency functional) can result to be unsafe (because dangerously close to strategies that instead pessimize the efficiency functional). From the mathematical viewpoint, this phenomenon is described by an efficiency functional which develops a global maximizer in a small neighborhood of a global minimizer.

From the biological point of view, the diffusion models related to $s = 0$ have often appeared in both theoretical analyses, see e.g. [Vis+99; VRDL08; San+04] and experimental data, see e.g. [Hum+12; SRP07; RF+04; ABM04].

Furthermore, it has been suggested in [Wea+14] that the case $s = 0$ is closely related to “ambush” strategies by predators and to a high energy content of the targets. It is suggestive to relate this high-energy content of the targets and the high-risk strategy related to $s = 0$: in a sense, one can imagine that a forager may not be discouraged by the fact that the most rewarding strategy can be dangerously close to the pessimizer precisely when the target is also highly rewarding. The adoption of an optimal strategy close to $s = 0$ would then correspond to a *high-risk/high-gain* situation, in which the expectation of the forager is that the hunt’s gain will be so high to compensate for the risk of failure.

Now we consider the set-dependent efficiency functional introduced in (1.19). In the case where Ω_1 and Ω_2 are disjoint and regular enough, we observe that a result analogous to the one given in Theorem 1.7 holds true.

Theorem 1.10 (Theorem 6.12 in Chapter 6). *Let $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and disjoint. Then, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that*

$$\inf_{s \in (0,1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = 0.$$

Now, we address the results related to the optimization of the set-dependent efficiency functional. Specifically, we establish results in line with Theorems 1.8 and 1.9 by replacing the pointwise functional in (1.17) with the set-dependent functional defined in (1.19). More precisely, we show that *if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are close enough, or sufficiently far away from each other, then the maximizer of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ is in some small neighborhood of $s = 0$* . The formal statements are the following ones:

Theorem 1.11 (Theorem 6.13 in Chapter 6). *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $r = r_{\varepsilon, n, T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are smooth, disjoint and such that $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_r(x_0)$ for some $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$, it holds that*

$$\sup_{s \in (0,1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Theorem 1.12 (Theorem 6.14 in Chapter 6). *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $R = R_{\varepsilon, n, T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfy*

$$\inf_{\substack{x \in \Omega_1 \\ y \in \Omega_2}} |x - y| \geq R,$$

then it holds that

$$\sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

The situation described for Theorem 1.8 and 1.9 carries over for the case of set-dependent efficiency functionals: namely, from Theorems 1.10, 1.11 and 1.12 we can evince that the most rewarding strategy for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ is unreliable, developing pessimizers and optimizers arbitrarily close to each other, both when the average locations of predators and targets are close and when they are far away.

In the framework of set-dependent efficiency functionals, a natural question is whether stationary foragers would better fit stationary preys with uniform distributions sharing the same region.

In Chapter 7 we discuss this problem, and we provide a positive answer, according to Theorem 1.13 below. Before stating it, we observe that when $s = 0$, equation (1.15) reduces to $\partial_t u = -u$ and $u(0, x) = \delta_y(x)$, and the formal solution takes the form $e^{-t} \delta(y - x)$.

Theorem 1.13 (Theorem 7.1 in Chapter 7). *Let $\Omega_2, \tilde{\Omega}_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and suppose that $\Omega_1 \subset \Omega_2$. Then, for every $s \in [0, 1]$ it holds that*

$$\mathcal{F} \left(\frac{\chi_{\Omega_2}}{|\Omega_2|}, \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}}{|\Omega_1|}, T \right) \geq \mathcal{E}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T),$$

where \mathcal{F} has been defined in (1.14).

Theorem 1.13 raises the natural question of what the best diffusive forager is; this is also a relevant biological question, since some biological foragers cannot be stationary.

In the next result we prove that the best diffusive search strategy (in terms of the most appropriate choice of s) heavily depends on the size of the domain.

To discuss this, given $r > 0$, we consider the dilation by a factor r of the region Ω , namely

$$\Omega_r := \{rx \text{ s.t. } x \in \Omega\}.$$

Our result states that for each region Ω we can find some time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and a dilation Ω_r for some large $r \in (1, +\infty)$, such that $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_r, \Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ is strictly increasing. The biological intuition for this result is that short range dispersal strategies maintain the foragers close to the prey, with a possible error localized near the boundary of the region, and a large dilation makes this boundary region more negligible with respect to the bulk of the domain.

Moreover, we show that by considering instead a small dilation Ω_r , for some $r \in (0, 1)$, then $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_r, \Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ is strictly decreasing. The biological intuition for this being that, if the distribution of prey occurs in a very small region, then any dispersal strategy would move the forager away from the prey, making it more convenient for the seeker to adopt an extreme strategy which maintains it, as much as possible, at the initial position, possibly at the risk of being quickly pushed towards infinity, since in any case small displacement would be sufficient to miss the prey.

Theorem 1.14 (Theorem 7.2 in Chapter 7). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, measurable and strictly convex. Then, there exists some $r_\Omega \in (1, +\infty)$ such that*

$$(1.21) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_r, \Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \quad \text{is strictly increasing in } s \in (0, 1),$$

for each $r \in (r_\Omega, +\infty)$ and $T \in [r^2, +\infty)$.

Furthermore, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ there exists some $r_{\Omega, T} \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$(1.22) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_r, \Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \quad \text{is strictly decreasing in } s \in (0, \frac{n}{2}] \cap (0, 1),$$

for each $r \in (0, r_{\Omega, T})$.

Also, if $n = 1$, for each $\sigma \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ there exist some $T_\sigma \in (1, +\infty)$ and $\tilde{r}_\Omega \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$(1.23) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_r, \Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \quad \text{is strictly increasing in } s \in (\sigma, 1),$$

for each $T \in (T_\sigma, +\infty)$ and $r \in (0, \tilde{r}_\Omega)$.

From a biological standpoint, it is also interesting to consider the case of a stationary prey which is not uniformly distributed and a diffusive forager that aims at optimizing its searching strategy. In this case, we consider a stationary distribution of prey $p \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and a diffusive forager with initial distribution equal to the prey. Thus, the distribution of forager is a probability density satisfying

$$(1.24) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = p(x). \end{cases}$$

We will denote by u_p the solution of (1.24). Thus, we have:

Theorem 1.15 (Theorem 7.5 in Chapter 7). *The foraging success functional (1.13) associated with a forager diffusing as in (1.24) has the form*

$$\int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi dt.$$

In particular, if the Fourier transform of p is supported in the ball of radius $\frac{1}{2\pi}$, then this efficiency functional is monotone strictly increasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by the Gaussian dispersal $s = 1$.

If instead the Fourier transform of p is supported in the complement of the ball of radius $\frac{1}{2\pi}$, then this efficiency functional is monotone strictly decreasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by $s = 0$.

We notice that, roughly speaking, distributions whose Fourier transform are supported close to the origin present “mild oscillations”, while the ones whose Fourier transform has support reaching towards infinity present “wilder oscillations”. Thus, the statement in Theorem 1.15, suggests that when $p(x)$ has mild oscillation, the classical random walk is better than ant fractional diffusion. On the other hand, when $p(x)$ has wild oscillations the fractional parameter $s = 0$ is the optimizer.

We can also interpret the results stated in Theorem 1.15 in light of Theorem 1.14, according to the relation between the Fourier transform of the characteristic function of a set Ω and its size, see the comment after Theorem 7.5 in Chapter 7.

It would be also interesting to consider more general cases of the above results, in which an active interaction between the forager and the prey takes place.

In Chapter 8, we consider the case of a forager with a finite lifetime (that is, it can forage only for a finite time, since if it does not eat any food for a given time interval, then it dies).

To formalize this idea, we need to define a new efficiency functional which can model such a scenario. First, we adopt the following notation. For every $T \in (0, +\infty)$, $p \in {}^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$ we denote by

$$\mathcal{F}_0(u_p, p, T) =: E(s, T)$$

where \mathcal{F}_0 has been defined in (1.13) and u_p is the solution to (1.24).

Also, it is convenient to introduce the extended natural numbers $\bar{\mathbb{N}} := \mathbb{N} \cup \{\infty\}$, where ∞ denotes a maximum element for the naturals. In particular, we have that $j + \infty = \infty + j = \infty$ for every $j \in \bar{\mathbb{N}}$ and $\infty - j = \infty$ for every $j \in \mathbb{N}$. In this way, we can present the case of finite and infinite (but countable) lifespans in a unified framework.

For this, we consider $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty\}$, an ordered set of lifespans $\{T_i\}_{i \in \{1, \dots, k\}}$ such that $0 < T_i < T_{i+1}$ and $\{c_i\}_{i \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}}$ with $c_i > 0$ for every $i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$. Also, if $k = \infty$, we make the assumption that

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} T_i = T_\infty = +\infty.$$

We suppose that the forager dies at time T_j for some $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ if $E(s, T_j) < c_j$, while if $E(s, T_j) \geq c_j$ the forager survives and can look for food till time T_{k+1} .

In this situation, the efficiency functional for this forager can be written for every $s \in I$ as

$$\mathcal{E}(s) := \begin{cases} E(s, T_j) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\} \text{ and } E(s, T_j) < c_j, \\ E(s, T_k) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}. \end{cases}$$

Note that in this setting the forager cannot modify the Lévy exponent s for all the duration of its life.

Without loss of generality, we can suppose from now on that the surviving thresholds are monotone, consistently with the biological idea that the total food threshold at a subsequent foraging time is higher than the ones at previous times. Namely, without loss of generality, we will assume that

$$c_{j+1} \geq c_j,$$

thanks to the following observation:

Lemma 1.16 (Lemma 8.2 in Chapter 8). *Let $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty\}$, $\tilde{c}_j := \max\{c_1, \dots, c_j\}$ with $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ and for every $s \in I$*

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}(s) := \begin{cases} E(s, T_j) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq \tilde{c}_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\} \text{ and } E(s, T_j) < \tilde{c}_j, \\ E(s, T_k) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq \tilde{c}_i \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}. \end{cases}$$

Then, $\tilde{\mathcal{E}} = \mathcal{E}$.

Then the main result of Chapter 8 goes as follows:

Theorem 1.17 (Theorem 8.3 in Chapter 8). *Let $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty\}$. We have the following dichotomy:*

- *either there exists $s_\star \in I$ such that $E(s_\star, T_i) \geq c_i$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$, in which case*

$$\sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_{k-1}} E(s, T_k),$$

where

$$I_{k-1} := \{s \in I \text{ s.t. } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}\},$$

- *or there exists $j_\star \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ such that¹ if $s \in I$ and $E(s, T_i) \geq c_i$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, k-1\} \cap [1, j_\star - 1]$, then necessarily $E(s, T_{j_\star}) < c_{j_\star}$, and the set*

$$I_{j_\star} := \{s \in I \text{ s.t. } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k-1\} \cap [1, j_\star - 1]\}$$

is nonempty.

In this case,

$$\sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_{j_\star}} E(s, T_{j_\star}).$$

In general, for many thresholds and time spans, the explicit analysis of the maximizers of Theorem 1.17 could be quite involved. There are however special cases in which explicit maximizers can be obtained, see e.g. Theorem 8.4, Corollary 8.5 and Theorem 8.6 in Chapter 8.

¹As customary, we use the notation $[1, j_\star - 1] = \emptyset$ when $j_\star = 1$, and in this case the requirement on i becomes void. For instance, if $j_\star = 1$, then $I_{j_\star} = I$.

2

EFFICIENCY FUNCTIONALS FOR THE LÉVY FLIGHT FORAGING HYPOTHESIS

We consider a forager diffusing via a fractional heat equation and we introduce several efficiency functionals whose optimality is discussed in relation to the Lévy exponent of the evolution equation.

Several biological scenarios, such as a target close to the forager, a sparse environment, a target located away from the forager and two targets are specifically taken into account.

The optimal strategies of each of these configurations are here analyzed explicitly also with the aid of some special functions of classical flavor and the results are confronted with the existing paradigms of the Lévy foraging hypothesis.

Interestingly, one discovers bifurcation phenomena in which a sudden switch occurs between an optimal (but somehow unreliable) Lévy foraging pattern of inverse square law type and a less ideal (but somehow more secure) classical Brownian motion strategy.

Additionally, optimal foraging strategies can be detected in the vicinity of the Brownian one even in cases in which the Brownian one is pessimizing an efficiency functional.

2.1 Introduction

Foraging theory (see e.g. [SK86b]) is a fascinating, important and cross-disciplinary topic of investigation that gathers together researchers from different areas (such as

biologists, ethologists, physicists, statisticians, computer scientists, mathematicians, etc.). It is commonly accepted that the broad variety of environmental and biological situations in nature and the Darwinistic evolution through natural selection have led over time to highly efficient foraging strategies see e.g. [Bar+05] (it is however under an intense debate whether Lévy type patterns in animal searches are an evolutionary stable and well consolidated outcome [Hum+12] or they are produced by innate composite correlated random walks [Ben07; Rey14]; under investigation is also the role of particular distribution of resources for the emergence of foraging patterns, see e.g. [Boy+06]; it is also debatable that natural selection alone can always optimize a specific parameter in complex environments, see e.g. [Gra87; PO87]).

In general, the precise determination of optimal foraging strategies depends in a very complex way on a large number of parameters (such as the density and mobility of the preys and of the searchers and the mutable environmental conditions); furthermore, the collection and analysis of empirical data are typically challenging tasks, also open to controversial interpretations due to the use of different mathematical models or even due to spurious information (see e.g. [Edw+07]).

A rather consolidated attempt to understand and classify different foraging strategies according to the evolution of the distribution of the searchers lies in the so-called Lévy flight foraging hypothesis. Namely, rather than diffusing in analogy to the classical Brownian motion, empirical evidence has often backed the hypothesis that animals move according to a scale-free fractal-like pattern similar to the one produced by long-jump random walks of Lévy type, possibly to avoid being trapped in a search of food confined in a narrow region beyond sensory range and to reduce the chances of intensively revisiting immediate surrounding areas in environments of scarce resources (see e.g. [Sim+08; Hum+10; Hum+12; HWS13] for empirical evidence for such biological Lévy flights). Phenomena related to Lévy flights are attracting increasing interest and they seem to possess some kind of universality, occurring also in situations different from animal foraging and including, among the others, human settlements and travels, see [Ber+05; BHG06; BLG07; GHB08; Rai+14; Rey+18] and also [GK21a] for related virtual reconstructions. Lévy patterns also emerge in dynamical models as a non-Gaussian transport related to chaos, see e.g. [ASZ91; SZK93].

Several studies have exploited tools from mathematical analysis and statistical

mechanics to validate the hypothesis that Lévy flights confer a significant advantage for foragers, see [Vis+99; Bar+02; Vis+02; Rap+09]. Typically, to confirm the Lévy flights optimality, structural assumptions on the environment, on the searcher and on the target are taken, such as: the foraging should be of non-destructive type (that is, once a target has been foraged, it has to reappear infinitely fast); after foraging, the seeker starts a new flight “infinitely close” to the previous target; the searcher moves rapidly relative to the target; the target density is low; the forager does not keep memory of previous encounters; the forager has inadequate information on the area to patrol and on the target location, etc. Of course, all these characteristics provide a highly simplified representations of real foragers, yet conceptual simplifications (rather than trivializations) are often very advantageous to advance and consolidate the knowledge on a complex topic. As a matter of fact, due to the difficulty of the analytical setting (and also to mimic situations of biological interest), to develop a mathematical theory of foraging related to the Lévy flight hypothesis it is often necessary to introduce additional parameters (such as a “direct vision distance” of the predator, see page 912 in [Vis+99]) and approximations (see e.g. equations (2) and (5) in [Vis+99]). In general, in spite of several quite strong and convincing attempts to completely deduce the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis from prime principles, several important details have generated debate, see e.g. [PCM14; Lev+20; Bul+21; Lev+21] and also [JPE11] for a review of several controversial aspects of the Lévy foraging hypothesis.

In this chapter, we consider the optimal foraging strategies in several situations of biological interest, such as:

- the case in which a single target is located in the proximity of the forager’s burrow,
- the case in which targets are sparsely distributed,
- the case in which a single target is located far away from the forager’s burrow,
- the case in which there are two targets, one close and one far from the forager’s burrow.

The optimal strategies of each of these configurations will be analyzed in light of new efficiency functionals relying also on methods from mathematical analysis and with the aid of some classical special functions.

A few comments are in order to highlight some of the main structural differences between our approach and the rather abundant existing literature on optimal animal foraging. On the one hand, the models considered here share with the existing literature several common traits, such as the assumption that the forager has no memory about the targets previously hit and that the prey has no awareness of the strategy and the movement of the predator. On the other hand, our models present significant differences with the existing literature for at least the following features:

- the forager does not restart its strategy after hitting each single target (instead, the seeker diffuses according to a Lévy type of diffusive equation, and this feature happens to be consistent with the setting of some of the existing literature, see equation (1) in [PCM14]; similar, but different, space-fractional equations in biological environment have also been considered in view of the Caputo derivative, see equation (2.1) in [Val+17]),
- no additional parameter related to direct vision is taken into account, no a-priori bound on step lengths is imposed, no truncation of the power law distribution is assumed (with the advantage of not endowing the problem with auxiliary and sometimes arbitrary parameters; as a counterpart of these technical and conceptual simplifications, the diffusions corresponding to infinite mean displacements are ruled out as infinite overshooting and this feature happens to be consistent with the setting of some of the existing literature, see e.g. the discussion after formula (2) in [PCM14]),
- we will take into account time averages of foraging success (though some integrals over time were previously considered, such as in the cumulative probability in equation (6) of [PCM14], we will specialize our analysis in detecting different optimal strategies according to the different time scales involved in the seeking process, rather than simply considering the foraging outcome at a given time),

- we will analyze in detail the role played by possibly different normalizing constants appearing when linking probabilistic models to analytical ones (typically, these constants depend¹ on the fractional exponent s , hence they may play a significant role when the objective is to optimize in s and, in general, they cannot be light-heartedly disregarded),
- we will find solutions in closed form, relying only on elementary special functions (and, since these functions, such as the Euler Gamma Function and the Riemann Zeta Function, are widely studied and already carefully implemented in all mathematical softwares, in our approach no expensive or advanced numerical simulations are needed),
- we introduce a number of new efficiency functionals whose optimization can be explicitly discussed (these functionals are inspired by, but somewhat different from, the mean first passage time adopted in [Vis+99] – in this way, we also avoid any overlap with some controversial details in the contemporary literature such as in [Lev+20; Bul+21; Lev+21]).

Though the arguments developed here essentially carry over to the multi-dimensional case, for the sake of simplicity (and following a consolidated tradition in mathematical biology, see e.g. [Bul+01; PCM14]), we stick here to dimension 1. The multi-dimensional case will be treated in Chapters 3-8, also taking into account new sets of structural parameters according to the geometry of the space and of the diffusive process.

Also, we focus here on the case of stationary targets (the case of mobile preys possibly with different velocities will be accounted for in a forthcoming work).

¹In terms of optimization strategies, we think it would have been beneficial, for instance, to discuss more extensively the possible dependences on μ (corresponding to $1 + 2s$ here) in the right hand sides of equation (5) in [Vis+99] and equation (11) in [Rap+09], as well as the constant C in equation (4) of [Rap+09]. The explanation for the pseudo mean squared displacements in the right hand side of equation (10) of [Rap+09] could have also benefitted from further details on the possible dependence of δ and α (the latter corresponding to $2s$ here).

<i>Notation Table</i>	
Fourier Transform of f	$\widehat{f}(\xi) := \mathcal{F}f(\xi) := \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(x)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx$
Fourier Antitransform of g	$\check{g}(x) := \mathcal{F}^{-1}g(x) := \int_{\mathbb{R}} g(\xi)e^{2\pi i x \xi} d\xi$
Poisson Summation Formula	$\sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} f(x+k) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \widehat{f}(k) e^{2\pi i x k}$
Dirac Delta Function at x_0	δ_{x_0}
Integral of a continuous function ϕ against the Dirac Delta	$\int_{\mathbb{R}} \phi(x)\delta_{x_0}(x) dx := \phi(x_0)$
Fractional parameter	$s \in (0, 1)$
Fractional Laplacian of u	$(-\Delta)^s u := \mathcal{F}^{-1}(2\pi\xi ^{2s}\widehat{u})$
Gamma Function ($z \in \mathbb{C}, \Re(z) > 0$)	$\Gamma(z) := \int_0^{+\infty} \vartheta^{z-1} e^{-\vartheta} d\vartheta$
Euler-Mascheroni constant	$\gamma := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\ln n + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \right) = 0.5772156\dots$
Digamma Function	$\psi(z) := \frac{d}{dz} \ln(\Gamma(z)) = \frac{\Gamma'(z)}{\Gamma(z)}$
Riemann Zeta Function ($z \in \mathbb{C}, \Re(z) > 1$)	$\zeta(z) := \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{j^z}$

The results obtained will detect the optimal exponent s corresponding to the most efficient foraging strategy (according to the different possible efficiency functionals). Several interesting patterns will arise. Quite often, optimal strategies are obtained in nature either by Lévy flights modeled on the inverse square law, or by the classical Brownian motion, or by some intermediate fractional values. In our discussion, all these three patterns will clearly arise and suitable bifurcation of optimal strategies will occur in dependence of the environmental parameters.

For instance, varying the time in which the search occurs or the sparseness of the targets, the optimality of the inverse square law may be lost in favor of a classical Gaussian strategy (or viceversa), and in some cases optimal values are found arbitrarily close to pessimal ones (and, conversely, pessimal values arbitrarily close to optimal ones). We think that this is a very interesting phenomenon, underlying the fact that the theoretical optimality of the strategy by itself might be not the main information to take into account for efficient search algorithms, since less ideal

strategies might produce more consistent results and prove themselves to be more reliable and viable in concrete situations.

In some circumstances, we will also detect optimal fractional values of intermediate type between the inverse square law and the Gaussian. In all cases, we will develop explicit (and somewhat “elegant”) representations of the efficiency functional that we introduce, thus allowing simple and effective analytic manipulations. As a byproduct, many of the environmental bifurcation parameters will be computed exactly.

The rest of the chapter is organized as follows. In the forthcoming Section 2.2, we introduce our mathematical setting adopted in this chapter, modeled on a forager randomly diffusing through a nonlocal heat equation and immobile targets with different types of distributions (see also the Notation Table for the list of the main mathematical objects and notations utilized in this chapter). The different biological scenarios corresponding to these distributions of resources will be discussed in Section 2.3, where several efficient functionals will be optimized with respect to the diffusion exponent. The results obtained will be also compared with the existing literature related to the Lévy foraging hypothesis.

2.2 Mathematical setting

We introduce now the formal mathematical setting we work with. The setting is modeled on the fractional heat equation and goes as follows.

Let $\kappa > 0$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $u(x, t)$ be the solution² of

$$(2.1) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u = -\kappa^{2s} (-\Delta)^s u & \text{in } \mathbb{R} \times (0, +\infty), \\ u(x, 0) = \delta_0(x). \end{cases}$$

By taking the Fourier Transform of this relation,

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t \hat{u} = -|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s} \hat{u} & \text{in } \mathbb{R} \times (0, +\infty), \\ \hat{u}(x, 0) = 1. \end{cases}$$

²In several occurrences in the existing literature, the Lévy exponent in biological contexts is denoted by μ . With respect to our notation, it holds that $\mu = 1 + 2s$.

Therefore

$$(2.2) \quad \widehat{u}(\xi, t) = \exp(-|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s}t) \quad \text{and} \quad u(x, t) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\left(\exp(-|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s}t)\right).$$

It is possible that the similarity (and the difference) between the expression for \widehat{u} in (2.2) and the standard Gaussian (corresponding to $s = 1$) were one of the inspiring motivations for Lévy's approach to the Central Limit Theorem in presence of infinite moments, see equation (7) in [SZK93].

We observe that, by scaling,

$$(2.3) \quad \begin{aligned} u(x, t) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \exp(-|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s}t + 2\pi i x \xi) d\xi \\ &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \exp(-|2\pi\kappa\eta|^{2s} + 2\pi i t^{-\frac{1}{2s}} x \eta) d\eta \\ &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \mathcal{F}^{-1}\left(\exp(-|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s})\right) \left(\frac{x}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} u\left(\frac{x}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}}, 1\right). \end{aligned}$$

In addition (see e.g. formula (2.30) in [AV19]),

$$(2.4) \quad 0 \leq u(x, 1) \leq \frac{C_{s,\kappa}}{1 + |x|^{1+2s}},$$

for some $C_{s,\kappa} > 0$ depending only on s and κ .

It is also useful to recall that, according to formula (6) of [Pól23],

$$(2.5) \quad \begin{aligned} \lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} |x|^{1+2s} u(x, t) &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} |x|^{1+2s} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s}t} \cos(2\pi x \xi) d\xi \\ &= 2 \lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} |x|^{1+2s} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-(2\pi\kappa\xi)^{2s}t} \cos(2\pi x \xi) d\xi \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi \kappa t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} |x|^{1+2s} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\vartheta^{2s}} \cos\left(\frac{x\vartheta}{\kappa t^{\frac{1}{2s}}}\right) d\vartheta \\ &= \frac{\kappa^{2s} t}{\pi} \lim_{y \rightarrow \pm\infty} |y|^{1+2s} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\vartheta^{2s}} \cos(y\vartheta) d\vartheta \\ &= \frac{\kappa^{2s} t \Gamma(1 + 2s) \sin(\pi s)}{\pi}, \end{aligned}$$

where the substitutions $\vartheta := 2\pi\kappa\xi t^{\frac{1}{2s}}$ and $y := \frac{x}{\kappa t^{\frac{1}{2s}}}$ have been used.

2.3 Description of the optimal strategies in different frameworks

We introduce here the notion of value functional related to the foraging success that we aim at optimizing with respect to the parameter s .

Given a distribution of targets $p(x, t)$, the *foraging success functional* will be taken as proportional to the encounters between seekers and preys over time and therefore, given $T > 0$, it takes the form

$$(2.6) \quad \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} p(x, t) u(x, t) dx dt.$$

We will compare this quantity, which is advantageous for the forager, with several quantities of interest which instead provide a penalization for the seeker's strategy. These terms will be *time* (thus, we will consider the amount of targets met over the time span T), a *renormalization of time* that takes into account, in some sense, the trajectory performed at a discrete level by a corresponding Lévy walker (as presented in (2.7) below), and the *average distance from the origin* (that is the distance of the forager "from home", as discussed in (2.8) below).

To present the renormalization of time, we let $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ and we recall (see e.g. formula (4.6) in [AV19]) that the mean excursion for each time step of a discrete Lévy walker is proportional to the spacial step by a factor of the form

$$\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{j^{2s}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{j^{1+2s}}} = \frac{\zeta(2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)}.$$

Though one cannot really consider this as the distance traveled by the Lévy walker in the unit of time (due to the nonlinear dependence between space and time variables in long-jump random processes), it is suggestive to consider a possible renormalization of time of the form

$$(2.7) \quad \bar{\ell}(s, T) := \frac{T \zeta(2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)}.$$

As for the distance between the forager and its burrow (located at the origin), we consider the average displacement for $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ given by

$$(2.8) \quad \ell(s, T) := \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} |x| u(x, t) dx dt.$$

We observe that this is a natural quantity to take into consideration as a penalization for long excursions to account for the forager's need to return to home. Related (but different) displacement functions were taken into account in equation (1) of [GK21a]. A variant of this approach (that will be accounted for in a forthcoming work) consists in considering pseudo mean displacements as in equation (10) of [Rap+09], possibly also including different normalization constants.

We also recall that the quantity in (2.8) can be computed by using the Fourier Transform for generalized functions (see Section 3.3 in Chapter II of [GS64] for the main results on this topic and Section 3.9 in Chapter I of [GS64] for the setting of the notation related to generalized functions). Indeed, from³ equation (2) on page 194 of [GS64] we know that

$$\mathcal{F}(|x|) = -\frac{1}{2\pi^2 |\xi|^2}$$

and therefore, by Plancherel Theorem, (2.2) and the substitution $y := (2\pi\kappa\xi)^{2s}t$,

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} |x| u(x, t) dx dt &= \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} |x| (u(x, t) - \delta_0(x)) dx dt \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\pi^2} \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} \frac{\widehat{u}(\xi, t) - 1}{|\xi|^2} d\xi dt \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\pi^2} \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} \frac{\exp(-|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s}t) - 1}{|\xi|^2} d\xi dt \\ &= -\frac{1}{\pi^2} \iint_{(0, +\infty) \times (0, T)} \frac{\exp(-(2\pi\kappa\xi)^{2s}t) - 1}{\xi^2} d\xi dt \\ &= -\frac{\kappa}{\pi s} \iint_{(0, +\infty) \times (0, T)} t^{\frac{1}{2s}} (e^{-y} - 1) y^{-\frac{1}{2s}-1} dy dt. \end{aligned}$$

³We stress that the notation of [GS64] for the Fourier Transform chooses a different normalization than the one here, by defining

$$\tilde{\mathcal{F}}f(\xi) := \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(x) e^{ix\xi} dx = \mathcal{F}f\left(-\frac{\xi}{2\pi}\right),$$

see formula (1) on page 153 in [GS64].

In this way we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ell(s, T) &= -\frac{2\kappa T^{\frac{1+2s}{2s}}}{\pi(1+2s)} \int_0^{+\infty} (e^{-y} - 1) y^{-\frac{1}{2s}-1} dy \\
 &= \frac{4\kappa s T^{\frac{1+2s}{2s}}}{\pi(1+2s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \left[\frac{d}{dy} \left(\frac{e^{-y} - 1}{y^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \right) + \frac{e^{-y}}{y^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \right] dy \\
 (2.9) \quad &= \frac{4\kappa s T^{\frac{1+2s}{2s}}}{\pi(1+2s)} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-y} y^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}-1} dy \\
 &= \frac{4\kappa s T^{\frac{1+2s}{2s}}}{\pi(1+2s)} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

One of the main goals of this chapter is to consider, as efficiency functional for the forager, the ratio between (2.6) and either the time T , or the quantity in (2.7), or that in (2.8). We stress that while T is obviously well defined⁴ for all $s \in (0, 1)$, the quantities in (2.7) and (2.8) are finite only when $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ (formally, they can be defined to be equal to $+\infty$ when $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$). The reduction of the analysis of foraging strategies in the range $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ has been also performed elsewhere in the literature, see e.g. the discussion after formula (2) in [PCM14] or formula (35) in [ASZ91] (it is however interesting to pursue also different approaches to incorporate conveniently modified situations in which the average jump distance is infinite, but possibly incorporating waiting times between subsequent jumps, see e.g. [MW65; SKW82; SWK87] and pages 34–35 in [SZK93]).

We will also distinguish two cases of interest according to the diffusion coefficient κ in (2.1). Namely, we will consider the standard case in which $\kappa = 1$ (this is a classical normalization choice, see e.g. formula (1) in [PCM14]), as well as the case in which κ depends on s via the relation

$$(2.10) \quad \kappa = \left(-\frac{\cos(\pi s)\Gamma(-2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2s}} =: \kappa_s.$$

This form of the diffusion coefficient is the one emerging in the formal passage to the continuous limit of a random Lévy walker in the discrete lattice $h\mathbb{Z}$ for time

⁴In any case, in what follows we will restrict our analysis to the range $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$. This is due to the fact that the utility functions that we will define in (2.15), and thus in (2.30), are properly defined only in this range (the functionals in (2.23) could instead more generally be defined in a larger range of s).

steps $\tau = h^{2s}$, since, in this setting,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u(x, t + \tau) - u(x, t)}{\tau} &= \left(\sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}} \frac{1}{|k|^{1+2s}} \right)^{-1} \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}} \frac{u(x + hk, t) - u(x, t)}{h^{2s} |k|^{1+2s}} \\ &= \left(2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{1+2s}} \right)^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{u(x + hk, t) + u(x - hk, t) - 2u(x, t)}{h^{2s} k^{1+2s}} \\ &\simeq \frac{1}{2\zeta(1+2s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{u(x+y, t) + u(x-y, t) - 2u(x, t)}{y^{1+2s}} dy, \end{aligned}$$

where we have approximated a Riemann sum with the corresponding integral. Thus setting $v_{y,t}(x) := u(x+y, t)$, and noticing that

$$\widehat{v}_{y,t}(\xi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} u(x+y, t) e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx = e^{2\pi i y \xi} \int_{\mathbb{R}} u(z, t) e^{-2\pi i z \xi} dz = e^{2\pi i y \xi} \widehat{u}(\xi, t),$$

we see that, in the formal limit,

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u(x, t) &= \frac{1}{2\zeta(1+2s)} \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{e^{2\pi i y \xi} + e^{-2\pi i y \xi} - 2}{y^{1+2s}} dy \widehat{u}(\xi, t) \right) \\ &= -\frac{1}{\zeta(1+2s)} \mathcal{F}^{-1} \left(\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1 - \cos(2\pi y \xi)}{y^{1+2s}} dy \widehat{u}(\xi, t) \right) \\ &= -\frac{(2\pi)^{2s}}{\zeta(1+2s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1 - \cos z}{z^{1+2s}} dz \mathcal{F}^{-1} (|\xi|^{2s} \widehat{u}(\xi, t)) \\ &= \frac{\cos(\pi s) \Gamma(-2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \mathcal{F}^{-1} (|2\pi \xi|^{2s} \widehat{u}(\xi, t)) \\ &= \frac{\cos(\pi s) \Gamma(-2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} (-\Delta)^s u(x, t) \end{aligned}$$

see e.g. the appendix in [Coc+22] for the computation of the latter constant (which is negative), and this justifies (2.10).

Moreover, using the functional equation (40.5) in [Rad73] (and, as customary, adopting the notation that extends the Riemann Zeta Function by analytic continuation), we can simplify the expression for κ_s in (2.10) and get

$$(2.11) \quad \kappa_s = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(-\frac{1}{2\zeta(-2s)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2s}}.$$

Single prey at the origin

We now consider the case of a single target located at the origin. In this case, the distribution of prey can be written as

$$p_0(x) = \delta_0(x).$$

We observe that, by (2.2),

$$(2.12) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}} p_0(x)u(x, t) dx = u(0, t) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\widehat{u}(\cdot, t))(0, t) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \exp(-|2\pi\kappa\xi|^{2s}t) d\xi \\ = 2 \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-(2\pi\kappa\xi)^{2s}t) d\xi.$$

Also, making use of the change of variable $\vartheta := (2\pi\kappa\xi)^{2s}t$, we see that

$$(2.13) \quad 2 \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-(2\pi\kappa\xi)^{2s}t) d\xi = \frac{1}{2\pi\kappa s t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \int_0^{+\infty} \vartheta^{\frac{1}{2s}-1} e^{-\vartheta} d\vartheta = \frac{1}{2\pi\kappa s t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right).$$

Thus, in the notation of (2.6), using (2.12) and (2.13), the foraging success functional for a single target located at the origin takes the form, for $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$,

$$(2.14) \quad \Phi_0(s; \kappa, T) := \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} p_0(x)u(x, t) dx dt = \int_0^T \frac{1}{2\pi\kappa s t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right) dt \\ = \frac{T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}}}{\pi\kappa(2s-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right),$$

and takes value equal to $+\infty$ when $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$. Hence, recalling (2.7), (2.9) and (2.11), we consider the utility functionals defined for $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ given by

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.15) \quad \mathcal{E}_1(s; T) &:= \frac{\Phi_0(s; 1, T)}{T} = \frac{1}{\pi T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right), \\
\mathcal{E}_2(s; T) &:= \frac{\Phi_0(s; \kappa_s, T)}{T} = \frac{2(-2\zeta(-2s))^{\frac{1}{2s}}}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right), \\
\mathcal{E}_3(s; T) &:= \frac{\Phi_0(s; 1, T)}{\bar{\ell}(s, T)} = \frac{\zeta(1+2s)}{\pi T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1) \zeta(2s)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right), \\
\mathcal{E}_4(s; T) &:= \frac{\Phi_0(s; \kappa_s, T)}{\bar{\ell}(s, T)} = \frac{\zeta(1+2s) 2(-2\zeta(-2s))^{\frac{1}{2s}}}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1) \zeta(2s)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right), \\
\mathcal{E}_5(s; T) &:= \frac{\Phi_0(s; 1, T)}{\ell(s, T)} = \frac{(1+2s) \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right)}{4s(2s-1) T^{\frac{1}{s}} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)} \\
\text{and } \mathcal{E}_6(s; T) &:= \frac{\Phi_0(s; \kappa_s, T)}{\ell(s, T)} = \frac{\pi^2(-2\zeta(-2s))^{\frac{1}{s}} (1+2s) \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right)}{s(2s-1) T^{\frac{1}{s}} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)}.
\end{aligned}$$

We observe that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 1/2} \mathcal{E}_1(s; T) = +\infty,$$

therefore, for every $T > 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.16) \quad &\text{the supremum of the utility functional } \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right) \mapsto \mathcal{E}_1(s; T) \\
&\text{is uniquely attained at } s = \frac{1}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

We recall that the value $s = \frac{1}{2}$ occurs often in optimal foraging problems, as an ideal balance between intensive search and longer (hence energetically more expensive) movements, both in terms of real world data (such as for atlantic cods, see e.g. Figure 1d in [Sim+08], jackals, see e.g. [Atk+02], wandering albatrosses, see e.g. Figure 1 in [HWS13], deers, see e.g. Figure 2(a) in [MBH02], bees, see [Rey+07a], fruit flies, see [RF07], and also Amazonian farmers searching for nuts, see Figure 3(b.09) in [Rey+18], etc.) and of theoretical optimization (see [Vis+99; Bul+01]). Interestingly, it also occurs in patterns generated by human ecology (such as distances

Figure 2.1: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_1(s; T)$ for $T = 10^j$, $j \in \{0, \dots, 5\}$.

between campsites, see Figure 1 in [BLG07]). With respect to these data, the statement in (2.16) can be seen as a confirmation of the most common paradigm in the Lévy foraging hypothesis. On the other hand, the qualitative behaviour of $\mathcal{E}_1(s; T)$ changes dramatically for large intervals of time: indeed, as hinted by Figure 2.1

(that plots $\mathcal{E}_1(\cdot; T)$ for $T \in \{1, 10, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5\}$), we have that

(2.17) for large T , the utility functional $\left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right) \mapsto \mathcal{E}_1(s; T)$ has a unique minimum at some point s_T such that

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} s_T = \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_1(s_T; T) = 0.$$

This is an interesting phenomenon, showing that the optimality at $s = \frac{1}{2}$ may become “unstable” and depends on the time span in which the phenomenon is observed, allowing a sudden switch between the optimal (but somehow unreliable) Lévy foraging pattern and the less ideal (but somehow more secure) classical Brownian motion strategy.

It is suggestive to compare this phenomenon to other occurrences in which Lévy flights with $s = \frac{1}{2}$ should theoretically provide the optimal seeking strategy but they coexist with another possible notion of foraging optimization related to Brownian walks, see e.g. the end of page 9 in [Bul+01].

Figure 2.2: Plot of $x \mapsto u(x, 1)$ with $\kappa = 1$ corresponding to $s = \frac{1}{2}$ (in magenta) and to $s = 1$ (in blue).

A heuristic explanation for the statement in (2.17) can be given in terms of the behaviour of the function u (with $\kappa = 1$) at the origin and at infinity in dependence

of the parameter s . Indeed, while the usual paradigm is to relate small values of s to long excursions of the traveller, this general notion has sometimes to be revised according to the specific mathematical model taken into account in the diffusive strategy of the forager, since, on the one hand, solutions of equation (2.1) corresponding to lower values of s do present a fatter tail distribution, but, on the other hand, due to the loss of the regularizing effect of the diffusive operator for small s , they also present a more prominent mass at the origin: see e.g. Figure 2.2 in which one can compare solutions at time $t = 1$ corresponding to $s = \frac{1}{2}$ and $s = 1$. Thus, the balance of these two apparently contrasting features may provide advantageous foragers' strategies for small values of s also in presence of proximate preys (not due to the long range excursion induced by the fat tail of the distribution, but rather due to the distribution peak at the origin produced by the less regularizing effect of a lower order operator). With respect to this observation, in view of the scaling properties of the equation (see (2.3)), the prominent role of the peak at the origin occurs for small times, while it becomes less significant for larger times. This somehow explains why the Lévy flights corresponding to $s = \frac{1}{2}$ are, in principle, more favorable than the classical Brownian motion, but this effect may become less relevant and rather insecure for very long time spans. It is suggestive to investigate whether the interplay between optimal but unstable strategies with suboptimal but safer ones may play a role in the appearance in nature of composite correlated random walks and in the biological approximation of Lévy walks as an innate composite correlated random walks, see [Ben07; Rey14].

It is also interesting to compare with biological situations in which a predominance of classical random walks coexists with patterns close to a theoretical optimum of $s = \frac{1}{2}$, see e.g. Figure 4 in [Hay+12].

We stress that the phenomenon described in (2.17) relies on the ideal assumption that the target is modelled as a “material point” (thus any arbitrarily small diffusion of the forager misses the resource) and is a byproduct of a memory-less search strategy (see e.g. [GM13] for a discussion of memory-enhanced foraging strategies).

The statement in (2.17) can be checked analytically as detailed in Appendix 2.4.

Figure 2.3: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_2(s; T)$ for $T = 10^j$, $j \in \{1, 4, 8, 16\}$.

We also have that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 1/2} \mathcal{E}_2(s; T) = +\infty$$

and, in view of the divergence of the Gamma Functions at negative integers,

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} \mathcal{E}_2(s; T) = 0.$$

These equations show that, for every $T > 0$

(2.18)

the supremum of the utility functional $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \mapsto \mathcal{E}_2(s; T)$ is uniquely attained at $s = \frac{1}{2}$ and the infimum is uniquely attained at $s = 1$,

which in turn suggests a very strong advantage for the Lévy strategy compared to the Poisson one. On the other hand, for long time spans, the pattern in (2.18) shows a significant instability, as sketched in Figure 2.3, which depicts the map $\mathcal{E}_2(\cdot; T)$ for

$T \in \{10, 10^4, 10^8, 10^{16}\}$. As a result,

$$(2.19) \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{for large } T, \text{ the utility functional } \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right) \mapsto \mathcal{E}_2(s; T) \\ & \text{has a local minimum at some point } s_T \text{ such that} \\ & \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} s_T = \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_2(s_T; T) = 0, \\ & \text{and a local maximum at some point } S_T \text{ such that } \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} S_T = 1. \end{aligned}$$

The statement in (2.19) can be checked analytically as detailed in Appendix 2.4.

Interesting patterns having a theoretical (but unstable for large time) optimum at $s = \frac{1}{2}$ with a stabilizing option at $s = 1$ are exhibited by the utility functionals \mathcal{E}_5 and \mathcal{E}_6 : see Figure 2.4 for the sketch of $\mathcal{E}_5(\cdot; T)$ (notice the pattern change between $T = 1.1$ and $T = 1.5$ and the development of an interior maximum at $T = 1.3$) and Figure 2.5 for the sketch of $\mathcal{E}_6(\cdot; T)$. We also stress that, for a given T , the values of \mathcal{E}_5 and \mathcal{E}_6 remain finite (differently from the cases of \mathcal{E}_1 and \mathcal{E}_2).

The cases of the utility functionals \mathcal{E}_3 and \mathcal{E}_4 are instead surprisingly different. Indeed, Figure 2.6 hints that \mathcal{E}_3 is monotone decreasing with a supremum at $s = \frac{1}{2}$ when $T \leq 1.5$, but then its monotonicity behavior changes when $T \geq 1.6$ and develops a supremum at $s = 1$ when $T \geq 1.7$. In this case, even the theoretical optimality at $s = \frac{1}{2}$ is lost for large times and additionally the switch between Lévy and Poisson optimal strategy occurs with a rather abrupt transition with respect to the parameter T .

The functional \mathcal{E}_4 exhibits a different and interesting pattern, as highlighted in Figure 2.7: in this case the system shows a sudden change of optimality occurring between $T = 2$ and $T = 3$: it appears indeed that the Lévy foraging for $s = \frac{1}{2}$ is optimal when $T \leq 2$, but when $T \geq 3$ a new optimal strategy for a different

Figure 2.4: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_5(s; T)$ for $T \in \{1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.5, 5, 10\}$.

fractional exponent s arises (with this new optimal exponent moving towards $s = 1$ as T becomes large).

As a matter of fact, we can detect analytically this bifurcation phenomenon and find an explicit value for the critical T by the following analytic argument. We use the notation $\varepsilon := 2s - 1$ according to which we have that

$$(2s - 1)\zeta(2s) = \varepsilon\zeta(1 + \varepsilon) = 1 + \gamma\varepsilon + o(\varepsilon)$$

Figure 2.5: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_6(s; T)$ for $T \in \{1, 1.5, 2, 5, 10, 10^3, 10^9, 10^{13}\}$.

and therefore

$$\mathcal{E}_4(s; T) = \frac{2\zeta(2+\varepsilon)(-2\zeta(-\varepsilon-1))^{\frac{1}{1+\varepsilon}}}{T^{\frac{1}{1+\varepsilon}}(1+\varepsilon\gamma+o(\varepsilon))} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{1+\varepsilon}\right)$$

Figure 2.6: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_3(s; T)$ for $T \in \{1, 1.5, 1.6, 1.7, 1.8, 10\}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{2(\zeta(2) + \zeta'(2)\varepsilon + o(\varepsilon))(-2\zeta(-1) + 2\zeta'(-1)\varepsilon + o(\varepsilon))^{\frac{1}{1+\varepsilon}}}{(T - T \ln T \varepsilon + o(\varepsilon))(1 + \gamma\varepsilon + o(\varepsilon))} \times \\
&\times (1 + \gamma\varepsilon + o(\varepsilon)) \\
&= 2 \left(\frac{\pi^2}{6} + \zeta'(2)\varepsilon + o(\varepsilon) \right) \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6} \ln 6 \varepsilon + 2\zeta'(-1)\varepsilon + o(\varepsilon) \right) \times \\
&\times \left(\frac{1}{T} + \frac{\ln T}{T} \varepsilon + o(\varepsilon) \right) + o(\varepsilon) \\
&= \frac{\pi^2}{18T} + 2\varepsilon \left(\frac{\pi^2}{36T} \ln T + \frac{\pi^2}{36T} \ln 6 + \frac{\pi^2}{3T} \zeta'(-1) + \frac{\zeta'(2)}{6T} \right) + o(\varepsilon)
\end{aligned}$$

This yields that

$$\frac{9T}{\pi^2} \frac{d\mathcal{E}_4}{ds} \left(\frac{1}{2}; T \right) = \ln T + \ln 6 + 12\zeta'(-1) + \frac{6}{\pi^2} \zeta'(2)$$

and this quantity is positive (respectively, negative) when $T > T_*$ (respectively, when $T < T_*$), where

$$T_* := \exp \left(-\ln 6 - 12\zeta'(-1) - \frac{6}{\pi^2} \zeta'(2) \right) = 2.145248182\dots$$

and, as a result, when $T > T_*$ the inverse square law $s = \frac{1}{2}$ cannot maximize \mathcal{E}_4 and values of s even slightly larger than $\frac{1}{2}$ provide greater values of such an efficiency functional.

Preys on a sparse lattice

Now we take into consideration a set of targets displayed in the lattice $\lambda\mathbb{Z}$, for some $\lambda > 0$, and we consider the asymptotics related to large values of λ , corresponding to the case of sparse preys. To this end, we consider the target distribution

$$p(x) := \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \delta_{\lambda k}(x).$$

We observe that

$$(2.20) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}} p(x) u(x, t) dx = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} u(\lambda k, t) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} u_\lambda(k, t)$$

where

$$u_\lambda(x, t) := u(\lambda x, t).$$

By (2.3) and (2.4),

$$(2.21) \quad \begin{aligned} (1 + |x|^{1+2s}) |u_\lambda(x, t)| &= (1 + |x|^{1+2s}) |u(\lambda x, t)| = \frac{1 + |x|^{1+2s}}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} u \left(\frac{\lambda x}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}}, 1 \right) \\ &\leq \frac{C (1 + |x|^{1+2s})}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}} \left(1 + \left| \frac{\lambda x}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} \right|^{1+2s} \right)} \leq C_{s, \lambda, t}, \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.7: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_4(s; T)$ for $T \in \{0.1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 100, 1000\}$.

for some $C_{s,\lambda,t} \in (0, +\infty)$.

Moreover, by (2.2),

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{u}_\lambda(\xi, t) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} u(\lambda x, t) e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_{\mathbb{R}} u(y, t) e^{-2\pi i \lambda^{-1} y \xi} dy \\ &= \frac{1}{\lambda} \widehat{u}\left(\frac{\xi}{\lambda}, t\right) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \exp\left(-\frac{|2\pi \kappa \xi|^{2s} t}{\lambda^{2s}}\right)\end{aligned}$$

and accordingly

$$(1 + |\xi|^{1+2s}) |\widehat{u}_\lambda(\xi, t)| = \frac{1 + |\xi|^{1+2s}}{\lambda} \exp\left(-\frac{|2\pi \kappa \xi|^{2s} t}{\lambda^{2s}}\right) \leq \widetilde{C}_{s, \lambda, t},$$

for some $\widetilde{C}_{s, \lambda, t} \in (0, +\infty)$.

In view of this estimate and (2.21), for a given $t > 0$ we can use the Poisson Summation Formula on u_λ (see e.g. formula (4.4.2) and Theorem 4.4.2 in [Pin02]) and, in light of (2.20), conclude that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} p(x) u(x, t) dx = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} u_\lambda(k) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \widehat{u}_\lambda(k) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \exp\left(-\frac{|2\pi k|^{2s} t}{\lambda^{2s}}\right).$$

For large λ , we can consider the latter term as a Riemann sum, therefore, using polar coordinates,

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} p(x) u(x, t) dx \simeq \int_{\mathbb{R}} \exp(-|2\pi y|^{2s} t) dy = 2 \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-(2\pi \rho)^{2s} t) d\rho.$$

Thus, recalling (2.6), (2.13) and (2.14), we can consider, for large λ , the foraging success functional

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(s) &:= \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0, T)} p(x) u(x, t) dx dt \simeq \frac{1}{2\pi s} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right) \int_0^T \frac{dt}{t^{\frac{1}{2s}}} = \frac{T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}}}{\pi(2s-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right) \\ &= \Phi_0(s; 1, T).\end{aligned}$$

The case of a sparse distribution of targets is therefore reduced to that of a single prey at the origin and, since the optimizers discussed in Section 2.3 were isolated and nondegenerate, the analysis provided in Section 2.3 for a single prey gives asymptotic information to the case of sparsely distributed targets when λ is sufficiently large.

Remote single prey

Now we consider the case of a single target located far away from the initial position of the seeker. For this, given $L > 0$, let

$$p_L(x) := \delta_L(x).$$

For $T > 0$, in view of (2.6), we consider the foraging success functional

$$\Phi_{L,T}(s; \kappa) := \iint_{\mathbb{R} \times (0,T)} p_L(x) u(x, t) dx dt = \int_0^T u(L, t) dt$$

By (2.5), for large L ,

$$L^{1+2s} \Phi_{L,T}(s; \kappa) \simeq \int_0^T \frac{\kappa^{2s} t \Gamma(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{\pi} dt = \frac{\kappa^{2s} T^2 \Gamma(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{2\pi}.$$

Thus, in the lines of (2.15), we set

$$\tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; \kappa) := \frac{\kappa^{2s} T^2 \Gamma(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{2\pi L^{1+2s}},$$

we notice that

$$(2.22) \quad \Phi_{L,T}(s; \kappa) \simeq \tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; \kappa)$$

for large L , and we discuss the optimization of the utility functionals⁵

(2.23)

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; 1)}{T} = \frac{T \Gamma(1 + 2s) \sin(\pi s)}{2\pi L^{1+2s}}, \\ \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; \kappa_s)}{T} = -\frac{T\Gamma(-2s) \Gamma(1 + 2s) \sin(2\pi s)}{4\pi L^{1+2s} \zeta(1 + 2s)} \\ &= \frac{T}{4L^{1+2s} \zeta(1 + 2s)}, \\ \mathcal{G}_3(s; L, T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; 1)}{\bar{\ell}(s, T)} = \frac{T \zeta(1 + 2s) \Gamma(1 + 2s) \sin(\pi s)}{2\pi L^{1+2s} \zeta(2s)}, \\ \mathcal{G}_4(s; L, T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; \kappa_s)}{\bar{\ell}(s, T)} = -\frac{T \Gamma(-2s) \Gamma(1 + 2s) \sin(2\pi s)}{4\pi L^{1+2s} \zeta(2s)} \\ &= \frac{T}{4L^{1+2s} \zeta(2s)},\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{G}_5(s; L, T) := \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; 1)}{\ell(s, T)} = \frac{T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}} \Gamma(2 + 2s) \sin(\pi s)}{8L^{1+2s} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)}$$

and
$$\mathcal{G}_6(s; L, T) := \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_{L,T}(s; \kappa_s)}{\ell(s, T)} = \left(\frac{-1}{2^{1+2s}\pi^{2s}\zeta(-2s)}\right)^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}} \frac{T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}} \Gamma(2 + 2s) \sin(\pi s)}{8L^{1+2s} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)}.$$

We point out that the final time T does not play any role in the optimization in s of the value functionals \mathcal{G}_1 , \mathcal{G}_2 , \mathcal{G}_3 and \mathcal{G}_4 in (2.23). We also stress that the biological meaning of the efficiency functionals in (2.23) only occurs for large values of $L > 0$, due to the asymptotics in (2.22), nevertheless it is interesting to study those functionals for all values of L also to detect bifurcation phenomena with respect to this parameter that depend only on the final analytic formulation and not on their initial construction.

We also observe that, differently from the functionals in (2.15), the ones defined in (2.23) can be continuously extended in $(0, \frac{1}{2}]$. Nevertheless, among them only \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 admit non negative values for $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$. Since the functionals in (2.23) lose their physical meaning for negative values, when studying the optimal search strat-

⁵The final expressions for \mathcal{G}_2 and \mathcal{G}_4 are due to Euler's reflection formula

$$\Gamma(1 - z)\Gamma(z) = \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi z)} \quad \text{for all } z \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}.$$

egy we will take into account the fractional parameter s in the whole interval $(0, 1)$ only when studying \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 .

Figure 2.8: Plot of $(0, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T)$ (say, when $T = 1$) for $L = 10^j$, with $j \in \{-3, \dots, 2\}$.

A plot of \mathcal{G}_1 is given in Figure 2.8, where one can appreciate that for small values of L the optimal exponent is close (but not equal) to 1 (consistently with the idea that if the prey is close to the starting point of the predator the best seeking strategy

is close to that of local type), while for large values of L the maximum is provided by a value of s close to zero. This is in agreement with the idea that if the prey is far away from the forager's starting position, then the optimal search strategy has a strong nonlocal component. More precisely, we have that

$$(2.24) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{if } L \text{ is large enough, the optimal foraging strategy for } \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) \\ &\text{is uniquely attained at some } s_L \text{ such that } \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L = 0. \end{aligned}$$

This can be proved analytically, see Appendix 2.4. From the plots provided in Figure 2.8, we see that $s = 0$ is a global minimum for \mathcal{G}_1 . Nevertheless, as stated in (2.24), for L large enough \mathcal{G}_1 admits a unique maximum $s_L \in (0, 1)$ such that $s_L \searrow 0$ for $L \rightarrow +\infty$. Thus, the global maximum s_L approaches the global minimum $s = 0$ as L gets larger and larger. We can summarize this phenomenon, by saying that the optimal search strategy for \mathcal{G}_1 is unstable. Namely, a slight deviation from the optimal value s_L can lead to very small values for \mathcal{G}_1 .

The functionals that we take into account to model the environmental scenario of a remote single prey are obtained using the approximation provided in (2.22). For this reason, we cannot rule out a priori that the aforementioned instability result is a consequence of this approximation and instead it does occur if we consider the original functional

$$(2.25) \quad \frac{\Phi_{L,T}(s; 1)}{T}.$$

In Chapter 6, we will address this problem and we will show that this instability result does hold true also for the non approximated efficiency functional in (2.25), provided that L is large enough. We will also show that this unstable behaviour is true in a multidimensional framework.

The functional \mathcal{G}_2 also shows an interesting bifurcation diagram plotted in Figure 2.9: also in this framework preys located close to the origin favor local diffusive strategies (optimized in this case for $s = 1$) and when L becomes larger an larger the optimal exponent moves to the left till becomes $s = 0$. Analogously to the

Figure 2.9: Plot of $(0, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T)$ (say, when $T = 1$) for $L \in \{1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.5, 2, 10\}$.

functional $\mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T)$, we can show that

$$(2.26) \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{if } L \text{ is large enough, the optimal foraging strategy for } \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) \\ & \text{is uniquely attained at some } s_L \text{ such that } \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The claim in (2.24) is proved analytically in Appendix 2.4. Note that also in this case we have the same instability of the optimal search strategy that we already observed for \mathcal{G}_1 .

The similarities and differences between Figures 2.8 and 2.9 highlight how different normalization choices in the model can affect optimal strategies: note indeed that the only difference between \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 lies in the way the diffusion coefficient κ is modeled on the basis of the underlying random process. The sensitivity of the optimization strategies with respect to these normalizing constants seems to be not investigated in the current literature and it produces in Figures 2.8 and 2.9 a different outcome on the optimality of the Gaussian exponent $s = 1$; this interesting difference is induced by the analytical observation that $\mathcal{G}_1(1; L, T) = 0 < \mathcal{G}_2(1; L, T)$.

Figure 2.10: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{G}_3(s; L, T)$ for $T = 1$ and $L = 10^j$, $j \in \{0, \dots, 5\}$.

As for the functional \mathcal{G}_3 , plots for different values of L are given in Figure 2.10. Interestingly, on the one hand, both the inverse square law $s = \frac{1}{2}$ and the Gaussian law $s = 1$ are minima for the functional for every T and L ; on the other hand, for very sparse targets (corresponding to large values of L),

(2.27)

the optimal foraging strategy for $\mathcal{G}_3(s; L, T)$ is uniquely attained at some s_L

such that $\lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L = \frac{1}{2}$.

This can also be proved analytically, see Appendix 2.4.

The graph of the functional \mathcal{G}_4 is instead plotted in Figure 2.11: notice that for $L \leq 1.7$ this functional is increasing and attains its maximum for the Gaussian strategy $s = 1$, but for $L \geq 2$ the functional \mathcal{G}_4 develops an interior maximum. More precisely, as proved analytically in Appendix 2.4, setting

$$(2.28) \quad L^* := \exp\left(-\frac{\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)}\right) = 1.768198\dots$$

we have that

(2.29)

if $L \leq L^*$ the optimal foraging strategy for $\mathcal{G}_4(s; L, T)$ is uniquely attained at $s = 1$,

while if $L > L^*$ the optimal foraging strategy for $\mathcal{G}_4(s; L, T)$ is uniquely attained

at some $s_L \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right)$ such that $\lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L = \frac{1}{2}$.

Therefore, for larger and larger values of $L > L^*$, the optimal strategy for \mathcal{G}_4 is getting closer and closer to the inverse power law distribution induced by $s = \frac{1}{2}$.

The cases of \mathcal{G}_5 and \mathcal{G}_6 are quite sophisticated, since their optimization strategies depend both on the final time T and on the scantness of the targets modeled by L . In the special situation in which $L = T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s(1+2s)}}$ these value functionals do not depend on L and T and they are plotted in Figures 2.12 and 2.13, respectively.

Figure 2.11: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{G}_4(s; L, T)$ for $T = 1$ and $L \in \{1.7, 2, 4, 10, 100, 10000\}$.

In particular, it appears that when $L = T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s(1+2s)}}$ the functional \mathcal{G}_5 is maximized in proximity of $s = 0.80261\dots$ and \mathcal{G}_6 in proximity of $s = 0.861187\dots$: in spite of the rather arbitrary choice relating T and L in Figures 2.12 and 2.13, it is suggestive to compare these optimal intermediate values between the inverse square power law distribution and the Gaussian one with the ones observed experimentally for some blue sharks (see e.g. Figure 1b in [Hum+10] which would correspond to $s = 0.73$), basking sharks and bigeye tunas (see e.g. Figures 1b and 1c in [Sim+08] which would

Figure 2.12: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{G}_5(s; L, T)$ for $L = T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s(1+2s)}}$.

Figure 2.13: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{G}_6(s; L, T)$ for $L = T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s(1+2s)}}$.

correspond to $s = 0.7$). See also the red curves in Figures 2, 4 and 6 of [PCM14] (which corresponds to $s \simeq 0.75$). It is also interesting to compare these values with the simulation data of some swarm dynamics (corresponding to $s = 0.745$, see Figure 3 in [RO16]). Of course, we are not aiming here at precisely reconstructing the bartumeus2005animaltative results arising in specific real-world experiments, but we think it is an interesting feature that even the very simplified situation that we describe may lead to optimal values of s which are somewhat intermediate between $s = \frac{1}{2}$ and $s = 1$.

Prey at the origin and remote prey

We now consider the case of two targets, one located “at home” at the origin and another far away at a given distance $L > 0$. This corresponds to a prey distribution

of the form

$$p_{0,L}(x) := \delta_0(x) + \delta_L(x).$$

Since the foraging success functional in (2.6) is linear with respect to the target distribution, the analysis of this case reduces to the superposition of the value functionals introduced in (2.15) and (2.23): thus, in the above notation, we define

$$(2.30) \quad \mathcal{H}_j(s; L, T) := \mathcal{E}_j(s; T) + \mathcal{G}_j(s; L, T) \quad \text{for } j \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$$

and we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}_1(s; L, T) &= \frac{1}{\pi T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right) + \frac{T \Gamma(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{2\pi L^{1+2s}}, \\ \mathcal{H}_2(s; L, T) &= \frac{2(-2\zeta(-2s))^{\frac{1}{2s}}}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right) + \frac{T}{4L^{1+2s} \zeta(1+2s)}, \\ \mathcal{H}_3(s; L, T) &= \frac{\zeta(1+2s)}{\pi T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1) \zeta(2s)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right) + \frac{T \zeta(1+2s) \Gamma(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{2\pi L^{1+2s} \zeta(2s)}, \\ \mathcal{H}_4(s; L, T) &= \frac{\zeta(1+2s) 2(-2\zeta(-2s))^{\frac{1}{2s}}}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1) \zeta(2s)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right) + \frac{T}{4L^{1+2s} \zeta(2s)}, \\ \mathcal{H}_5(s; L, T) &= \frac{(1+2s) \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right)}{4s(2s-1) T^{\frac{1}{s}} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)} + \frac{T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}} \Gamma(2+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{8L^{1+2s} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)} \\ \text{and } \mathcal{H}_6(s; L, T) &= \frac{\pi^2(-2\zeta(-2s))^{\frac{1}{s}} (1+2s) \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right)}{s(2s-1) T^{\frac{1}{s}} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)} \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{-1}{2^{1+2s} \pi^{2s} \zeta(-2s)} \right)^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}} \frac{T^{\frac{2s-1}{2s}} \Gamma(2+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{8L^{1+2s} \Gamma\left(\frac{2s-1}{2s}\right)}. \end{aligned}$$

We point out that in all the above value functionals, the second term becomes predominant for large values of T , hence the long time analysis for \mathcal{H}_j boils down to the one developed for \mathcal{G}_j in Section 2.3 (this is consistent with the idea that for long times the forager has drifted away from its initial location). Similarly, small values of T reduce the analysis of \mathcal{H}_j to the one developed for \mathcal{E}_j in Section 2.3 (consistently with the ansatz that for small times the forager will exploit the targets in the vicinity of its burrow).

Instead, when $T = 1$ both the terms in \mathcal{H}_j contribute to the optimization of \mathcal{H}_j and the corresponding plots (when also $L = 1$) are given in Figure 2.14, showing an optimal foraging strategy corresponding to $s = \frac{1}{2}$ in these specific situations.

Figure 2.14: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{H}_j(s; L, T)$ for $T = 1 = L$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$.

2.4 Appendices

Analytical verification of (2.17)

Let

$$(2.31) \quad c(s; T) := \frac{1}{2\pi T^{\frac{1}{2s}} (2s-1)^2 s^2} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right)$$

and notice that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.32) \quad \frac{d}{ds}c(s; T) &= \left(\frac{\ln T}{2s^2} - \frac{4}{2s-1} - \frac{2}{s} \right) c(s; T) - \frac{1}{4\pi T^{\frac{1}{2s}}(2s-1)^2 s^4} \Gamma' \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \\
 &= \left(\frac{\ln T}{2s^2} - \frac{4}{2s-1} - \frac{2}{s} - \frac{1}{2s^2} \psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) c(s; T).
 \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, by (2.15),

$$(2.33) \quad \mathcal{E}_1(s; T) = 2s^2(2s-1) c(s; T)$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.34) \quad \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{E}_1(s; T) &= (4s(2s-1) + 4s^2) c(s; T) + 2s^2(2s-1) \frac{d}{ds}c(s; T) \\
 &= \left((2s-1) \ln T - 4s^2 - (2s-1) \psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) c(s; T).
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we define

$$(2.35) \quad Z(x) := \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{k+x} - \frac{1}{k} \right)$$

and (see Chapter 10 in [Bon17]) we find that

$$(2.36) \quad \psi(x) = -\gamma - \frac{1}{x} - \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{1}{k+x} - \frac{1}{k} \right) = -\gamma - \frac{1}{x} - Z(x).$$

Accordingly, we can rewrite equation (2.34) as

$$(2.37) \quad \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{E}_1(s; T) = \left((2s-1) \ln T + (2s-1)\gamma - 2s + (2s-1) Z \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) c(s; T).$$

Moreover, since $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$, we have that $\frac{1}{2s} \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ and therefore, for each $k \geq 1$,

$$\frac{1}{k + \frac{1}{2s}} - \frac{1}{k} \geq \frac{1}{k+1} - \frac{1}{k} = -\frac{1}{k(k+1)} \geq -\frac{1}{k^2}.$$

As a result,

$$(2.38) \quad -1 < -\frac{\pi^2}{12} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} \leq \frac{1}{2} Z \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \leq 0.$$

We now define the function

$$(2.39) \quad f(s) := \left((2s-1) \ln T + (2s-1)\gamma - 2s - 2(2s-1) \right) c(s; T)$$

and we deduce from (2.37) and (2.38) that

$$(2.40) \quad f(s) \leq \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{E}_1(s; T).$$

For T large enough such that $\ln T + \gamma \geq 3$, let

$$(2.41) \quad \bar{s}_T := \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\ln T + \gamma - 2}{\ln T + \gamma - 3} \right)$$

and observe that

$$(2.42) \quad f(s) \geq 0 \text{ if and only if } s \in (\bar{s}_T, 1).$$

Recalling (2.15), we observe that

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}} \mathcal{E}_1(s, T) = +\infty.$$

This limit together with (2.42) and (2.40) imply that

$$(2.43) \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{the map } \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1 \right) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_1(s; T) \text{ attains its minimum somewhere} \\ & \text{in the interval } \left(\frac{1}{2}, \bar{s}_T \right). \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, by (2.32) and (2.34),

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d^2}{ds^2} \mathcal{E}_1(s; T) \\ &= \left(2 \ln T - 8s - 2\psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) + \frac{2s-1}{2s^2} \psi' \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) c(s; T) \\ & \quad + \left((2s-1) \ln T - 4s^2 - (2s-1)\psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \frac{d}{ds} c(s; T) \\ &= \left[\left(2 \ln T - 8s - 2\psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) + \frac{2s-1}{2s^2} \psi' \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left((2s-1) \ln T - 4s^2 - (2s-1)\psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \right] \times \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \times \left(\frac{\ln T}{2s^2} - \frac{4}{2s-1} - \frac{2}{s} - \frac{1}{2s^2} \psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \Big] c(s; T) \\ & \geq \left[\frac{(2s-1) \ln^2 T}{2s^2} - \left(4 + \frac{2(2s-1)}{s} + \frac{2s-1}{s^2} \psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \ln T + \frac{16s^2}{2s-1} - C \right] c(s; T) \end{aligned}$$

for some $C > 0$ independent on T .

Hence, setting $A := \frac{\sqrt{2s-1} \ln T}{\sqrt{2}s}$ and $B := \frac{4s}{\sqrt{2s-1}}$, and noticing that

$$4\sqrt{2} \ln T = 2AB \leq A^2 + B^2 = \frac{(2s-1) \ln^2 T}{2s^2} + \frac{16s^2}{2s-1},$$

we conclude that

$$(2.44) \quad \frac{d^2}{ds^2} \mathcal{E}_1(s; T) \geq \left[\left(4\sqrt{2} - 4 - \frac{2(2s-1)}{s} - \frac{2s-1}{s^2} \psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \ln T - C \right] c(s; T).$$

Now, recalling (2.36) and (2.38),

$$\begin{aligned} & 4\sqrt{2} - 4 - \frac{2(2s-1)}{s} - \frac{2s-1}{s^2} \psi \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \\ & = 4\sqrt{2} - 4 - \frac{2(2s-1)}{s} + \frac{2s-1}{s^2} \left(\gamma + 2s + Z \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \\ & = 4\sqrt{2} - 4 + \frac{2s-1}{s^2} \left(\gamma + Z \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \\ & \geq 4\sqrt{2} - 4 - \frac{2s-1}{s^2} (2 - \gamma) \\ & \geq 4\sqrt{2} - 4 - 2 + \gamma, \end{aligned}$$

which is strictly positive.

This observation and (2.44) entail that \mathcal{E}_1 is strictly convex for large T , and consequently, the minimum in (2.43) is attained at a unique point that we denote by s_T . Since

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \bar{s}_T = \frac{1}{2},$$

we thus obtain from (2.43) that

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} s_T = \frac{1}{2},$$

which concludes the analytical proof of (2.17).

Analytical verification of (2.19)

We point out that

$$(2.45) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 1/2} \mathcal{E}_2(s; T) = +\infty,$$

since the denominator in the definition of \mathcal{E}_2 in (2.15) vanishes. Moreover, since the Riemann Zeta Function vanishes at the negative even integers (different from -1), we note that $\zeta(-2) = 0$, whence

$$(2.46) \quad \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \mathcal{E}_2(s; T) = 0.$$

Also, in light of (2.15), we can rewrite $\mathcal{E}_2(s; T)$ as

$$\mathcal{E}_2(s; T) = 2\pi(h(s))^{\frac{1}{2s}} \mathcal{E}_1(s, T),$$

where we have defined $h(s) := -2\zeta(-2s) > 0$ for each $s \in (1/2, 1)$.

We remark⁶ that, if $s \in (1/2, 1)$,

$$h(s) = 2^{1-2s} \pi^{-2s-1} \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(1+2s) \zeta(1+2s) \in \left(0, \frac{\Gamma(3) \zeta(2)}{\pi^2}\right] = \left(0, \frac{1}{3}\right]$$

and therefore

$$(2.47) \quad \ln(h(s)) \leq \ln \frac{1}{3} < 0.$$

Also,

$$(2.48) \quad h'(s) = 2^{1-2s} \pi^{-2s-1} \Gamma(1+2s) \left[2 \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1+2s) + \zeta(1+2s) \left(\pi \cos(\pi s) + 2 \sin(\pi s) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln 2 - \ln \pi) \right) \right].$$

We recall that

$$\psi(1+2s) - \ln 2 - \ln \pi \leq \psi(3) - \ln 2 - \ln \pi = -0.9150927\dots$$

⁶Here we are using the Riemann's Functional Equation

$$\zeta(z) = 2^z \pi^{z-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{2}\right) \Gamma(1-z) \zeta(1-z).$$

and therefore we infer from (2.48) that

$$\begin{aligned} h'(s) &\leq 2^{1-2s}\pi^{-2s-1}\Gamma(1+2s)\left[2\sin(\pi s)\zeta'(1+2s)+\pi\zeta(1+2s)\cos(\pi s)\right] \\ &\leq 2^{1-2s}\pi^{-2s}\Gamma(1+2s)\zeta(1+2s)\cos(\pi s). \end{aligned}$$

Since the latter term is nonpositive for $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, and actually strictly negative when $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, the observations above yield that $h' < 0$ in $(\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ and more precisely, for all $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$,

$$(2.49) \quad -C_1 < h'(s) < -C_2,$$

where C_1 and C_2 are positive constants.

We now compute the derivative with respect to s of $\mathcal{E}_2(s; T)$ and get

$$\frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{E}_2(s; T) = 2\pi \left[\frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{E}_1(s, T)(h(s))^{\frac{1}{2s}} + \mathcal{E}_1(s, T)(h(s))^{\frac{1}{2s}} \left(-\frac{1}{2s^2} \ln(h(s)) + \frac{1}{2s} \frac{h'(s)}{h(s)} \right) \right].$$

Hence, from equations (2.33) and (2.37) we deduce that

$$(2.50) \quad \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{E}_2(s; T) = 2\pi c(s; T)(h(s))^{\frac{1-2s}{2s}} \left(P(s, T) h(s) - (2s-1) \ln(h(s)) h(s) + s(2s-1) h'(s) \right),$$

where

$$P(s, T) := (2s-1) \ln T + (2s-1)\gamma - 2s + (2s-1) Z \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right)$$

and c and Z are as defined in (2.31) and (2.35), respectively.

Now, using (2.38) and (2.39), we observe that

$$\begin{aligned} P(s, T) &= (2s-1) \ln T + (2s-1)\gamma - 2s + (2s-1) Z \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \\ &= (2s-1) \ln T + (2s-1)\gamma - 2s - 2(2s-1) + (2s-1) \left(2 + Z \left(\frac{1}{2s} \right) \right) \\ &\geq (2s-1) \ln T + (2s-1)\gamma - 2s - 2(2s-1) \\ &= \frac{f(s)}{c(s; T)}. \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence, owing also to (2.47), (2.49) and (2.50) we find that

$$(2.51) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{E}_2(s; T) &\geq 2\pi c(s; T) (h(s))^{\frac{1-2s}{2s}} \left(\frac{f(s) h(s)}{c(s; T)} + s(2s-1) h'(s) \right) \\ &\geq 2\pi c(s; T) (h(s))^{\frac{1-2s}{2s}} \left(\frac{f(s) h(s)}{c(s; T)} - s(2s-1)C_1 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, by (2.42) and the fact that $h(s)$ is decreasing, we get that for all $s \in (\bar{s}_T, \frac{3}{4})$,

$$(2.52) \quad 2\pi c(s; T) h(s)^{\frac{1-2s}{2s}} \left(\frac{f(s) h(3/4)}{c(s; T)} - s(2s-1)C_1 \right) \leq \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{E}_2(s; T)$$

where \bar{s}_T is as defined in (2.41). Now we set

$$\hat{s}_T := \bar{s}_T + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{s(2s-1)C_1}{h(3/4)(\ln T - 3 + \gamma)} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\ln T - 2 + \gamma + s(2s-1)C_1/h(3/4)}{\ln T - 3 + \gamma} \right).$$

Hence, recalling again (2.39) and assuming T conveniently large, for all $s \in (\hat{s}_T, \frac{3}{4})$,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{f(s)h(3/4)}{c(s; T)} - s(2s-1)C_1 &= h(3/4) \left((2s-1) \ln T + (2s-1)\gamma - 2s - 2(2s-1) \right) \\ &\quad - s(2s-1)C_1 \\ &= 2s h(3/4) \left(\ln T + \gamma - 3 \right) + h(3/4) \left(-\ln T - \gamma + 2 \right) \\ &\quad - s(2s-1)C_1 \\ &> 2\hat{s}_T h(3/4) \left(\ln T + \gamma - 3 \right) + h(3/4) \left(-\ln T - \gamma + 2 \right) \\ &\quad - s(2s-1)C_1 \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Plugging this information into (2.52) we find that, for large T , the function $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_2(s; T)$ is strictly increasing in $(\hat{s}_T, \frac{3}{4})$ and in view of (2.45) we obtain that this function possesses a local minimum $s_T \in (\frac{1}{2}, \hat{s}_T]$ and (recalling also (2.46)) a local maximum $S_T \in [\frac{3}{4}, 1)$. Since \hat{s}_T converges to $\frac{1}{2}$ as $T \rightarrow +\infty$, we also obtain that $s_T \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}$ as $T \rightarrow +\infty$.

Accordingly, to complete the proof of (2.19), it only remains to check that $S_T \rightarrow 1$ as $T \rightarrow +\infty$. To this end, we note that, by (2.39) and (2.51),

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{1}{2\pi c(S_T; T) h(S_T)^{\frac{1-2S_T}{2S_T}}} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{E}_2(S_T; T) \geq \frac{f(S_T) h(S_T)}{c(S_T; T)} - S_T(2S_T-1)C_1 \\ &= h(S_T) \left((2S_T-1) \ln T + (2S_T-1)\gamma - 2S_T - 2(2S_T-1) \right) \\ &\quad - S_T(2S_T-1)C_1 \\ &\geq h(S_T) \frac{\ln T}{2} - C_2 - C_3 h(S_T), \end{aligned}$$

for some constants $C_2, C_3 > 0$.

For this reason,

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{C_2}{h(S_T)} + C_3 \geq \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\ln T}{2} = +\infty,$$

whence

$$0 = \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} h(S_T) = \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} -2\zeta(-2s_T).$$

Since the only zero of the Riemann Zeta Function in $[-2, -1]$ occurs at -2 , we thereby infer that $-2s_T \rightarrow -2$, and thus $s_T \rightarrow 1$, as $T \rightarrow +\infty$. With this, we have concluded the analytical verification of (2.19).

Analytical verification of (2.24)

We compute that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) &= \frac{T}{2\pi} \left[\frac{2\Gamma'(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) + \pi\Gamma(1+2s) \cos(\pi s) - 2\Gamma(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \ln L}{L^{1+2s}} \right], \\ &= \frac{T\Gamma(1+2s)}{\pi L^{1+2s}} \left[\sin(\pi s) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L) + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

For L large enough, we define

$$s_L^{(-)} := \frac{1}{8 \ln L}$$

and we notice that

$$(2.53) \quad \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L^{(-)} = 0.$$

Also, if L is sufficiently large, using (2.36) (and noticing that $Z(1+2s) < 0$), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\pi L^{1+2s}}{T\Gamma(1+2s)} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) &> \sin(\pi s) \left(-\gamma - \frac{1}{1+2s} - \ln L \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \\ &\geq -2 \sin(\pi s) \ln L + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \\ &\geq -2\pi s \ln L + \frac{\pi}{4} \\ &\geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

for all $s \in \left(0, s_L^{(-)} \right]$.

Analogously, we define

$$(2.54) \quad s_L^{(+)} := \frac{2}{3(\ln L - \psi(3))},$$

and note that also in this case we have that

$$(2.55) \quad \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L^{(+)} = 0.$$

Now, we notice that if L is sufficiently large and $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$,

$$\frac{\pi L^{1+2s}}{T\Gamma(1+2s)} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) \leq -\frac{\sin(\pi s)}{2} \ln L + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) < 0.$$

If instead $s \in [s_L^{(+)}, \frac{1}{2})$,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\pi L^{1+2s}}{T\Gamma(1+2s)} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) &< \sin(\pi s)(\psi(3) - \ln L) + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \\ &\leq -\sin(\pi s)(\ln L - \psi(3)) + \frac{\pi}{2} \\ &\leq -\sin(\pi s_L^{(+)})(\ln L - \psi(3)) + \frac{\pi}{2} \\ &\leq -\frac{3\pi s_L^{(+)}}{4}(\ln L - \psi(3)) + \frac{\pi}{2} \\ &\leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

In conclusion, if L is large enough and $s \in [s_L^{(+)}, 1)$ we have that

$$\frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) < 0.$$

Therefore, from these considerations we conclude that

$$(2.56) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{there exists at least one critical point for } \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) \\ &\text{and all the critical points of } \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) \text{ are located in } (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)}). \end{aligned}$$

Now, we show that if L is large enough, then

$$(2.57) \quad \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) \text{ is strictly decreasing in } (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)}).$$

To prove it, if L is large enough, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{d^2}{ds^2} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) \\
 = & \frac{2T\Gamma(1+2s)}{\pi L^{1+2s}} \left(\sin(\pi s) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L) + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \right) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L) \\
 & + \frac{T\Gamma(1+2s)}{\pi L^{1+2s}} \left(\pi \cos(\pi s) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L) + 2 \sin(\pi s) \psi'(1+2s) - \frac{\pi^2}{2} \sin(\pi s) \right) \\
 = & \frac{2T\Gamma(1+2s)}{\pi L^{1+2s}} \left(\sin(\pi s) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L) + \pi \cos(\pi s) \right) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L) \\
 & + \frac{T\Gamma(1+2s)}{\pi L^{1+2s}} \left(2 \sin(\pi s) \psi'(1+2s) - \frac{\pi^2}{2} \sin(\pi s) \right) \\
 \leq & \frac{2T\Gamma(1+2s)}{L^{1+2s}} \left(s (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L - \pi) + 1 \right) (\psi(1+2s) - \ln L) \\
 & + \frac{2T\Gamma(1+2s)}{\pi L^{1+2s}} \sin(\pi s) \psi'(1+2s).
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we observe that if $s \in (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)})$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 s(\ln L - \psi(1+2s) + \pi) - 1 & \leq \frac{2}{3(\ln L - \psi(3))} (\ln L - \psi(1+2s) + \pi) - 1 \\
 & = \frac{2}{3} + \frac{2(\psi(3) - \psi(1+2s) + \pi)}{3(\ln L - \psi(3))} - 1 \\
 & = -\frac{1}{3} + \frac{2(\psi(3) - \psi(1+2s) + \pi)}{3(\ln L - \psi(3))} \\
 & \leq -\frac{1}{6},
 \end{aligned}$$

as long as L is taken sufficiently large.

Moreover, since $\psi(1+2s)$ is increasing for $s \in (0, 1)$, if L is sufficiently large, we have that, for all $s \in (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)})$,

$$\sin(\pi s) \psi'(1+2s) \leq \pi s \psi'(1+2s) \leq \pi s_L^{(+)} \psi'(1+2s).$$

Thus, using these pieces of information, we conclude that, if L is large enough, for every $s \in (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)})$,

$$\frac{d^2}{ds^2} \mathcal{G}_1(s; L, T) \leq -\frac{T\Gamma(1+2s)}{3L^{1+2s}} (\ln L - \psi(1+2s)) + \frac{2T\Gamma(1+2s)}{L^{1+2s}} s_L^{(+)} \psi'(1+2s)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -\frac{T\Gamma(1+2s)}{3L^{1+2s}}(\ln L - \psi(1+2s) - 6s_L^{(+)}\psi'(1+2s)) \\
&= -\frac{T\Gamma(1+2s)}{3L^{1+2s}}\left(\ln L - \psi(1+2s) - \frac{4\psi'(1+2s)}{\ln L - \psi(3)}\right) \\
&< 0.
\end{aligned}$$

This establishes the claim in (2.57).

Now, the claim in (2.24) follows from (2.56), (2.57) and the limits in (2.53) and (2.55).

Analytical verification of (2.26)

We compute that

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) &= -\frac{T}{4}\left[\frac{2\ln L}{L^{1+2s}\zeta(1+2s)} + \frac{2\zeta'(1+2s)}{L^{1+2s}\zeta^2(1+2s)}\right] \\
&= -\frac{T}{2L^{1+2s}\zeta(1+2s)}\left[\ln L + \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)}\right].
\end{aligned}$$

The Riemann zeta function ζ is a meromorphic function with pole at $z = 1$. We also recall that near $z = 1$ the derivative of the Riemann Zeta Function has the Laurent expansion

$$(2.58) \quad \frac{\zeta'(z)}{\zeta(z)} = -\frac{1}{z-1} + \gamma + O(z-1),$$

see e.g. page 481 in [Cho95]. This leads to the expression

$$(2.59) \quad \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} = -\frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + O(2s)$$

and to the existence of some constant $C \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(2.60) \quad \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \geq -\frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + Cs,$$

for all $s \in (0, 1)$. We point out that we can assume without loss of generality that $C \in (-\infty, 0]$.

Therefore, if we define

$$s_L^{(+)} := \frac{1}{2(\ln L + \gamma + C)},$$

we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.61) \quad \frac{2L^{1+2s}\zeta(1+2s)}{T} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) &= - \left[\ln L + \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \right] \\
 &\leq - \left(\ln L - \frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + Cs \right) \\
 &< - \left(\ln L - \frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + C \right) \\
 &\leq 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

for all $s \in [s_L^{(+)}, 1)$.

We notice also that

$$(2.62) \quad \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L^{(+)} = 0.$$

Analogously, thanks to the expansion in (2.59), we obtain the existence of some $\tilde{C} \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(2.63) \quad \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \leq -\frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + \tilde{C}s,$$

for all $s \in (0, 1)$. Without loss of generality, we can suppose that $\tilde{C} \in [0, +\infty)$.

Thus, if we define

$$s_L^{(-)} := \frac{1}{2(\ln L + \gamma + \tilde{C})},$$

we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.64) \quad \frac{2L^{1+2s}\zeta(1+2s)}{T} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) &= - \left[\ln L + \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \right] \\
 &\geq - \left(\ln L - \frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + \tilde{C}s \right) \\
 &> - \left(\ln L - \frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + \tilde{C} \right) \\
 &\geq 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

for all $s \in (0, s_L^{(-)}]$.

We also observe that

$$(2.65) \quad \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L^{(-)} = 0.$$

From (2.61) and (2.64) we deduce that

$$(2.66) \quad \begin{aligned} & \text{there exists at least one critical point for } \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) \\ & \text{and all the critical points of } \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) \text{ are located in } (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)}). \end{aligned}$$

We now show that, for all L large enough,

$$(2.67) \quad \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) \text{ is strictly decreasing in } (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)}).$$

To prove it, using (2.63) we estimate the derivative

$$(2.68) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{d^2}{ds^2} \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) &= \frac{T}{\zeta(1+2s)L^{1+2s}} \left[\ln L + \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \right]^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{T}{\zeta(1+2s)L^{1+2s}} \left[\frac{\zeta''(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} - \frac{(\zeta'(1+2s))^2}{\zeta^2(1+2s)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Now we notice that

$$(2.69) \quad \left| \ln L + \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \right| \leq \ln L - \frac{1}{2s} + \gamma + \max\{\tilde{C}, -C\}s,$$

thanks to (2.60) and (2.63).

Moreover, by the definitions of $s_L^{(-)}$ and $s_L^{(+)}$, we have that

$$\frac{1}{2(\ln L + \gamma + \tilde{C})} < s < \frac{1}{2(\ln L + \gamma + C)},$$

which gives that

$$\left| \ln L - \frac{1}{2s} + \gamma \right| \leq \max\{\tilde{C}, -C\}.$$

From this and (2.69), we deduce that

$$(2.70) \quad \left| \ln L + \frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \right| \leq \max\{\tilde{C}, -C\}(1+s).$$

Additionally, differentiating the Laurent expansion in (2.58),

$$(2.71) \quad \frac{\zeta''(z)}{\zeta(z)} - \left(\frac{\zeta'(z)}{\zeta(z)} \right)^2 = \frac{d}{dz} \frac{\zeta'(z)}{\zeta(z)} = \frac{1}{(z-1)^2} + O(1),$$

which leads to the existence of some constant $\hat{C} \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(2.72) \quad \frac{\zeta''(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} - \left(\frac{\zeta'(1+2s)}{\zeta(1+2s)} \right)^2 \geq \frac{1}{(2s)^2} + \hat{C},$$

for all $s \in (0, 1)$.

Using (2.70) and (2.72) into (2.68), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d^2}{ds^2} \mathcal{G}_2(s; L, T) \\ & \leq \frac{T}{\zeta(1+2s)L^{1+2s}} \left[(\max\{\tilde{C}, -C\})^2 (1+s)^2 - \frac{1}{(2s)^2} - \hat{C} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{T}{\zeta(1+2s)L^{1+2s}} \left[(\max\{\tilde{C}, -C\})^2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{2(\ln L + \gamma + C)} \right)^2 - (\ln L + \gamma + C)^2 - \hat{C} \right], \end{aligned}$$

for all $s \in (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)})$.

Thus, if L is sufficiently large, we obtain (2.67).

Therefore, claim (2.26) follows from (2.66), (2.67) and the limits in (2.62) and (2.65).

Analytical verification of (2.27)

We observe that

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{P}(s; L, T) \\ & := \frac{\pi L^{1+2s} \zeta(2s)}{T\Gamma(1+2s)} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_3(s; L, T) \\ & = \zeta(1+2s) \left(-\ln L \sin(\pi s) + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) + \sin(\pi s) \psi(1+2s) \right) + \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1+2s) \\ & \quad - \frac{\zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \end{aligned}$$

and the positivity of the derivative of \mathcal{G}_3 is equivalent to the positivity of \mathcal{P} .

Let also

$$\mathcal{Q}(s) := \zeta(1+2s) \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) + \sin(\pi s) \psi(1+2s) \right) + \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1+2s)$$

and note that $\sup_{s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)} |\mathcal{Q}(s)| \leq C$ for some $C > 0$; in addition,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}(s; L, T) & = -\zeta(1+2s) \ln L \sin(\pi s) - \frac{\zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} + \mathcal{Q}(s) \\ & = -\zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \left(\ln L + \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \right) + \mathcal{Q}(s) \end{aligned}$$

$$= -\zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \left(\ln L - \frac{1}{2s-1} \right) + \tilde{\mathcal{Q}}(s),$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}(s) := \mathcal{Q}(s) - \zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \left(\frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} + \frac{1}{2s-1} \right).$$

We stress that $\sup_{s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)} |\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}(s)| \leq \tilde{C}$ for some $\tilde{C} > 0$, thanks to (2.58).

Let now

$$\varepsilon_L := \frac{1}{\sqrt{\ln L}} \quad \text{and} \quad s_L^{(\pm)} := \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1 \pm \varepsilon_L}{2 \ln L}.$$

We notice that

$$(2.73) \quad \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} \varepsilon_L = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L^{(\pm)} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Also, when $s \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, s_L^{(-)} \right]$, we have that

$$2s - 1 \leq 2s_L^{(-)} - 1 = \frac{1 - \varepsilon_L}{\ln L}$$

and, as a result, for large L ,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}(s; L, T) &\geq \zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \left(-\ln L + \frac{\ln L}{1 - \varepsilon_L} \right) - \tilde{C} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_L \ln L \zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{1 - \varepsilon_L} - \tilde{C} \\ &\geq \frac{\sqrt{\ln L} \zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{2} - \tilde{C} \\ &\geq \frac{\sqrt{\ln L} \zeta(3)}{4} - \tilde{C} \\ &> 0. \end{aligned}$$

Instead, when $s \in \left[s_L^{(+)}, 1 \right)$,

$$2s - 1 \geq 2s_L^{(+)} - 1 = \frac{1 + \varepsilon_L}{\ln L},$$

which entails that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}(s; L, T) &\leq \zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s) \left(-\ln L + \frac{\ln L}{1 + \varepsilon_L} \right) + \tilde{\mathcal{Q}}(s) \\ &\leq -\frac{\varepsilon_L \ln L \zeta(1+2s) \sin(\pi s)}{1 + \varepsilon_L} + \mathcal{Q}(s) + C_1 \sin(\pi s) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq -\frac{\sqrt{\ln L} \zeta(3) \sin(\pi s)}{1 + \varepsilon_L} + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \zeta(1 + 2s) + C_2 \sin(\pi s) \\
 &= -\sin(\pi s) \left(\frac{\sqrt{\ln L} \zeta(3)}{1 + \varepsilon_L} - C_2 \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \zeta(1 + 2s) \\
 &\leq -\sin(\pi s) \left(\frac{\sqrt{\ln L} \zeta(3)}{2} - C_2 \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \cos(\pi s) \zeta(1 + 2s) \\
 &< 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

where C_1 and C_2 are suitable positive constants.

From these considerations, it follows that there exists at least one zero for \mathcal{P} and all the zeros of \mathcal{P} are located in $(s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)})$. As a consequence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.74) \quad &\text{there exists at least a critical point for } \mathcal{G}_3 \\
 &\text{and all the critical points of } \mathcal{G}_3 \text{ are located in } (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)}).
 \end{aligned}$$

We now show that

$$(2.75) \quad \mathcal{P} \text{ is strictly decreasing in } (s_L^{(-)}, s_L^{(+)}).$$

For this, we calculate that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.76) \quad &\frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{P}(s; L, T) = \ln L \left(-2 \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1 + 2s) - \pi \zeta(1 + 2s) \cos(\pi s) \right) \\
 &\quad + \pi \cos(\pi s) \left[2 \zeta'(1 + 2s) + \zeta(1 + 2s) \left(\psi(1 + 2s) - \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \right) \right] \\
 &\quad + 2 \sin(\pi s) \left[\zeta''(1 + 2s) + \zeta'(1 + 2s) \left(\psi(1 + 2s) - \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \quad \left. + \zeta(1 + 2s) \left(-\frac{\zeta''(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} + \left(\frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \right)^2 + \psi'(1 + 2s) - \pi^2 \right) \right] \\
 &\leq \ln L \left(-2 \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1 + 2s) - \pi \zeta(1 + 2s) \cos(\pi s) \right) \\
 &\quad - \pi \cos(\pi s) \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} - 2 \sin(\pi s) \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \\
 &\quad + \zeta(1 + 2s) \left(-\frac{\zeta''(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} + \left(\frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \right)^2 \right) + C_3
 \end{aligned}$$

for some constant $C_3 > 0$.

Plugging (2.71) into (2.76) we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{P}(s; L, T) &\leq \ln L \left(-2 \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1+2s) - \pi \zeta(1+2s) \cos(\pi s) \right) \\ &\quad - \pi \cos(\pi s) \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} - 2 \sin(\pi s) \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} - \frac{\zeta(1+2s)}{(2s-1)^2} + C_4 \end{aligned}$$

for some constant $C_4 > 0$. Thus, since $\zeta' \leq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} (2.77) \quad \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{P}(s; L, T) &\leq \ln L \left(-2 \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1+2s) - \pi \zeta(1+2s) \cos(\pi s) \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{2\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} - \frac{\zeta(1+2s)}{(2s-1)^2} + C_4 \\ &\leq \ln L \left(-2 \sin(\pi s) \zeta'(1+2s) - \pi \zeta(1+2s) \cos(\pi s) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{2}{2s-1} - \frac{\zeta(1+2s)}{(2s-1)^2} + C_5 \end{aligned}$$

for some $C_5 > 0$, where (2.58) has been used once again.

Moreover, if $s \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, s_L^{(+)}\right]$, then, for large L ,

$$2s-1 \leq \frac{1+\varepsilon_L}{\ln L} \leq \frac{2}{\ln L}$$

and therefore we deduce from (2.77) that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{P}(s; L, T) &\leq \frac{C_6}{2s-1} - \frac{\zeta(1+2s)}{(2s-1)^2} \leq \frac{1}{2s-1} \left(C_6 - \frac{\zeta(3)}{2s-1} \right) \\ &\leq -\frac{1}{2s-1} \left(\frac{\zeta(3)}{2s_L^{(+)}-1} - C_6 \right) \leq -\frac{1}{2s-1} \left(\frac{\zeta(3) \ln L}{2} - C_6 \right) < 0, \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof of (2.75).

The desired claim in (2.27) now follows combining (2.74) and (2.75) with the second limit in (2.73).

Analytical verification of (2.29)

We start by computing the derivative of \mathcal{G}_4 with respect to s , and we get that

$$(2.78) \quad \frac{d}{ds}\mathcal{G}_4(s, T, L) = -\frac{T}{2L^{1+2s} \zeta(2s)} \left(\ln L + \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)} \right).$$

Now we observe that, for $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$, the function

$$m(s) := \frac{\zeta'(2s)}{\zeta(2s)}$$

is negative and strictly increasing. Furthermore, from (2.58) we infer that

$$(2.79) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 1/2} m(s) = -\infty.$$

Now, in light of (2.78),

$$(2.80) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_4(s, T, L) > 0 & \text{ if and only if } \ln L + m(s) < 0, \\ & \text{ and thus if and only if } L < \exp(-m(s)). \end{aligned}$$

Also, from (2.28) and the monotonicity of the function m , for each $L \leq L^*$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ we have that

$$\exp(-m(s)) > \exp(-m(1)) = L^* \geq L,$$

and therefore we deduce from (2.80) that

$$(2.81)$$

when $L \leq L^*$ the supremum of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{G}_4(s; L, T)$ is uniquely attained at $s = 1$.

If instead $L > L^*$, using (2.79) we see that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 1/2} \exp(-m(s)) = +\infty > L$$

$$\text{and } \lim_{s \nearrow 1} \exp(-m(s)) = \exp(-m(1)) = L^* < L.$$

This and the strict monotonicity of m yield that for each $L > L^*$ there exists a unique $s_L \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ such that

$$(2.82) \quad \frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_4(s_L, L, T) = 0,$$

with $\frac{d}{ds} \mathcal{G}_4(s, L, T) > 0$ if and only if $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, s_L)$, namely s_L is the unique maximum for $\mathcal{G}_4(s, L, T)$ when $L > L^*$.

From these observations and (2.81), in order to complete the analytical proof of (2.29), it is only left to show that

$$(2.83) \quad \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} s_L = \frac{1}{2}.$$

To this end, equations (2.78) and (2.82) give that

$$0 = \ln L + m(s_L),$$

which leads to

$$(2.84) \quad +\infty = \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} \ln L = - \lim_{L \rightarrow +\infty} m(s_L).$$

Since the only pole of $m(s)$ at $[\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ occurs in $s = \frac{1}{2}$, then we obtain (2.83), as desired.

Conclusions

In this article we have introduced several efficiency functionals accounting for different foraging strategies of a predator (for simplicity, in a one-dimensional environment). The foraging strategies rely on the possible adoption of a different Lévy exponent for the diffusion of the predator. The corresponding efficiency functionals thus compare, roughly speaking, the outcome of the forager's hunt with the effort required to implement it and our objective was to understand, in different scenarios, which Lévy exponent optimizes, or pessimizes, a given efficiency functional for a given distribution of targets.

Several biological environments have been considered, such as the ones of a target close to the initial position of the predator, of a sparse distribution of targets, of a remotely located target, etc.

The optimal exponents correspond to different hunting strategies, driven by either classical or anomalous types of diffusion: specifically, one can compare the classical diffusion induced by Brownian motion and the one obtained by an inverse square law distribution. Our findings show that the *theoretical optimality* of an exponent has to be confronted with the *practical reliability* of the corresponding hunting strategy, since we pointed out the occurrence of *bifurcation phenomena* depending

on the environmental parameters in which a sudden switch takes place between a theoretically optimal exponent and a less ideal, but more secure, foraging procedure. In particular, optimal exponents can be located arbitrarily close to pessimal ones, making the practical choice of the hunting strategy a delicate balance between a striving for maximum success and a more conservative attitude to prioritize safety.

Cases of intermediate optimal exponents, balancing between purely Gaussian and Lévy distributions, have also been detected.

We kept our analysis as simple as possible, by removing additional parameters in the model such as the possibility of restarting the strategy after each hit and the distinction between random relocation and direct finite-range vision. Also, we did not introduce any additional a-priori bound on the length of the forager's journey and no additional truncation on the power law distributions has been added into the model. Furthermore, the efficiency functionals did not account just for a single foraging success but rather for its time average.

In our computation, a significant role is also played by the possibly different normalization constants involved in probabilistic and analytical models. The results obtained present explicit solutions in closed form which utilize only elementary special functions (in particular, no expensive numerical simulations were needed and the results are not affected by truncations or discretizations).

3

DIFFUSIVE PROCESSES MODELED ON THE SPECTRAL FRACTIONAL LAPLACIAN WITH DIRICHLET BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

In this chapter we provide a comprehensive approach to the spectral fractional heat equation that combines purely analytic and probabilistic perspectives.

Furthermore, we give two new results on the monotonicity properties of the spectral fractional heat diffusion with respect to the fractional parameter.

The first result deals with the spectral fractional heat kernel, evaluated at the initial singularity. The second result considers the probability for the corresponding stochastic process of being confined in a subregion of the domain.

In both results, the monotonicity property depends on the size of the first non-zero eigenvalue.

The case of homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions are addressed in detail here. Neumann boundary conditions will be taken into account in Chapter 4.

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter we consider the heat equation driven by the spectral fractional Laplacian with Dirichlet data (see Chapter 4 for the case of Neumann data), and we ob-

tain two original results concerning the monotonicity properties of the corresponding heat kernel with respect to the fractional parameter. In doing so, we revisit the analytic and probabilistic framework related to the fractional diffusion of spectral type, providing a unified and essentially self-contained setting.

To introduce these results at a colloquial level, we will denote by $r^s(t, x, y)$ the solution of the spectral fractional heat equation at time $t > 0$ evaluated at a point $x \in \Omega$, with initial condition at time $t = 0$ given by a Dirac delta function concentrated at a given point $y \in \Omega$.

For our purposes, Ω is an open, connected and bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^n with smooth boundary, which allows us to expand functions in $L^2(\Omega)$ through a basis of eigenfunctions. The action of the fractional diffusive operator is therefore modelled through a power of the corresponding eigenvalues and the superscript s in the notation $r^s(t, x, y)$ refers to the fractional power $s \in (0, 1]$ that we take into account. More specifically, the power $s = 1$ would correspond to the classical Laplacian and thus to the classical heat kernel and the eigenfunctions and eigenvalues are considered here to be with homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions (and to be completely explicitly, the corresponding fractional diffusion kernel will be thereby denoted by $r_D^s(t, x, x)$); the case of homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions will be addressed in Chapter 4 (in which case, for the sake of clarity, the corresponding fractional diffusion kernel will be denoted by $r_N^s(t, x, x)$).

The rigorous details related to these types of fractional diffusion with Dirichlet data will be presented in Sections 3.2 (see Chapter 4 for the corresponding case of Neumann conditions). For the moment, we stick to the notation $r^s(t, x, y)$ to represent the corresponding heat kernel, either with Dirichlet or Neumann condition, so to state some of the results with a common notation.

In this setting, our first original contribution focuses on the monotonicity of the function $r^s(t, x, x)$ with respect to the fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1]$, for given $t \in (0, +\infty)$ and $x \in \Omega$.

This question has a concrete meaning since the function $r^s(t, x, x)$ measures the amount of heat remaining at time t precisely at the point corresponding to the initial heat singularity: roughly speaking, the larger this function is, the more persistent the “memory of the initial singularity” is, while the smaller this function is, the easier for the system to “discharge the initial singularity” away from its original location.

Interestingly, our result shows that the monotonicity of the spectral fractional heat kernel $r^s(t, x, x)$ with respect to the fractional parameter s depends on the geometry of the domain Ω encoded by the first non-zero eigenvalue. While the precise result will be provided in Theorem 3.10, we can anticipate their statements as follows:

Theorem 3.1. *If the first non-zero eigenvalue is bigger than or equal to 1, then the fractional heat kernel $r^s(t, x, x)$ is monotone decreasing in s .*

If instead the first non-zero eigenvalue is strictly less than 1, then for every $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ there exists some $T > 0$ such that for each $t > T$

$$r^{s_0}(t, x, x) < r^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

Additional comments relating the physical aspects of the fractional diffusion with the specific geometry of the domains considered will be provided after Theorem 3.11 here (and Theorem 4.12 in Chapter 4 for the Neumann case), once the formal mathematical setting has been fully developed.

The second original result that we present in this chapter deals with the conditional probability for the stochastic process corresponding to the fractional heat equation to remain confined in a subregion Ω' of Ω . Roughly speaking, and for the moment surfing over the technical complications of a precise notation (which will be detailed in the forthcoming Section 3.2 for the Dirichlet data case and in Section 4.2 of Chapter 4 for the Neumann data case), one could denote by Y_t the stochastic process corresponding to the spectral fractional diffusion (indices related to the boundary conditions can be added to be more specific, but here we aim at comprising both Dirichlet and Neumann data in a unified notation, for the sake of simplicity). Thus, one can also denote by \mathbb{P}^s the probability notion related to such a process and one looks at the conditional probability for the stochastic process to lie in the subregion Ω' at time t , given that the initial location of the process was also in Ω' . Denoting this conditional probability by $\mathbb{P}^s(Y_t \in \Omega' | Y_0 \in \Omega')$, we obtain:

Theorem 3.2. *If the first non-zero eigenvalue is bigger than or equal to 1, then the conditional probability $\mathbb{P}^s(Y_t \in \Omega' | Y_0 \in \Omega')$ is monotone decreasing in s .*

If instead the first non-zero eigenvalue is strictly less than 1, then for every $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ there exists some $T > 0$ such that for each $t > T$

$$\mathbb{P}^{s_0}(Y_t \in \Omega' | Y_0 \in \Omega') < \mathbb{P}^{s_1}(Y_t \in \Omega' | Y_0 \in \Omega').$$

A precise version of this result will be given in Theorem 3.11.

Theorems 4.1 and 4.2 (or, better to say, their rigorous formulation in Theorems 3.10 and 3.11) will be exploited in Chapter 5 related to foraging models and hunting strategies in the study of animal behavior.

Moreover, giving a detailed formulation of these original results and providing thorough proofs of them offered us the occasion in this chapter to provide an exhaustive analytic presentation of the spectral fractional Laplacian and its connections with the heat equation. Additionally, in this chapter, the probabilistic methods are reviewed and compared to the analytic ones, providing a somewhat unified setting.

We also mention that the reason for which we focus here on the spectral version of the fractional Laplacian (rather than on other fractional possibilities appearing in the literature) consists mainly in its facility of dealing with different boundary conditions at the same time and in a rather natural way. For example, Dirichlet conditions for the integral (instead of spectral) fractional Laplacian need to be assigned in the whole complement of the domain, making practical computations sometimes complicated. Even more importantly, Neumann conditions for the integral fractional Laplacian pop up at least in two different formulations, compare e.g. [FJ15] with [DROV17]: while one of these formulations has a clean geometric meaning, it appears to be often unfeasible from the point of view of variational methods; on the other hand, the other formulation does seem to be more amenable in terms of functional analysis and possesses a neat probabilistic interpretation (see [DV21]), but its global setting as an integral prescription in the complement of the domain makes often explicit calculations quite unpractical.

The spectral formulation of the fractional problem presents instead the advantage of offering a natural way to encode different sorts of boundary conditions into a setting which is easy to introduce and structurally consistent with classical functional analysis. The price to pay for this convenience is however that the probabilistic setting related to the spectral fractional Laplacian is somewhat more sophisticated

and possibly less transparent to non-specialists: to compensate for this disadvantage we try to offer in this chapter a setting which is as accessible as possible to a broad community of readers.

To provide the reader with a glimpse of the conceptual structure of this chapter, in conjunction with Chapter 4 in which the Neumann case is treated, we give the following flowchart:

In further detail, this chapter is organized as follows.

In Section 3.2 we introduce the precise mathematical framework that will be used throughout the chapter, and state the main results that will be proved (see Chapter 4 for the Neumann counterpart). Here we define the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation and we state the theorems regarding the existence, regularity and uniqueness of the solution to these systems of equations (see Theorem 3.8). Moreover, we provide a Maximum Principle (Theorem 3.9).

At the end of Section 3.2 we present the original results of this article. Specifically, in Theorem 3.10, we give a precise statement of Theorem 4.1 for the Dirichlet case. Analogously, in Theorem 3.11, we rephrase Theorem 4.2 with a detailed probabilistic notation for the Dirichlet case. See Chapter 4 for analogous results in the Neumann setting.

Section 3.3 is devoted to the proof of the main results. More specifically, in Section 3.3 we provide a presentation of the stochastic process associated to the kernel r_D^s , which will be called subordinate killed Brownian motion, while in Section 3.3 we prove through analytical arguments that this kernel is the unique solution to the

Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation (3.10), giving thus a proof of Theorems 3.8 and 3.9. Finally, in Section 3.3 we prove Theorems 3.10 and 3.11.

Some of the arguments presented here also exploit a few auxiliary results of general interest that are collected, for the facility of the reader, in the appendix of Chapter 4.

3.2 The Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation

To introduce the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation we need to define the *Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian*. We take a bounded, open and connected set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ with smooth boundary and an orthonormal basis $\{\phi_k\}_k$ of $L^2(\Omega)$ satisfying

$$(3.1) \quad \begin{cases} -\Delta \phi_k = \lambda_k \phi_k & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \phi_k \in H_0^1(\Omega), \end{cases}$$

where the values $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 < \lambda_3 \dots$ are the eigenvalues of the Laplace operator with homogeneous Dirichlet datum on the boundary of the domain (see for instance [Eva10, Section 6.5]). In particular, since Ω has smooth boundary, the eigenfunctions ϕ_k are all $C^\infty(\overline{\Omega})$ (namely, they are differentiable as many times as one wishes and their derivatives of any order are uniformly continuous in Ω).

Let us now consider a function $u(t, x)$, with $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$, such that $u(t, \cdot) \in L^2(\Omega)$. Then we can write the $L^2(\Omega)$ decomposition of $u(t, \cdot)$ in eigenfunctions as

$$(3.2) \quad u(t, x) = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} u_k(t) \phi_k(x), \quad \text{with} \quad u_k(t) := \int_{\Omega} u(t, y) \phi_k(y) dy,$$

where the convergence of the series in (3.2) is meant with respect to the $L^2(\Omega)$ -norm.

Definition 3.3. Let $s \in (0, 1)$. We define the *Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian* as

$$(3.3) \quad \begin{aligned} &(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s : H_D^{2s}(\Omega) \subset L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega) \\ &u \longmapsto (-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s u := \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} u_k \lambda_k^s \phi_k \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(3.4) \quad H_D^{2s}(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in L^2(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} u_k^2 \lambda_k^{2s} < +\infty \right\}.$$

We stress that the ‘‘Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian’’ in (3.3) is different from the ‘‘integral fractional Laplacian’’ and from the ‘‘regional fractional Laplacian’’ that have been also widely studied in the recent literature: see e.g. [AV19] and the references therein for similarities and differences between these fractional operators.

From now on, we denote by $p_D^\Omega(t, x, y)$ the ‘‘fundamental solution’’ of the heat equation in Ω with homogeneous Dirichlet condition corresponding to an initial heat density concentrated at the point $y \in \Omega$, namely $p_D^\Omega(t, x, y)$ is the solution of

$$(3.5) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = \Delta u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ u(t, x) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \Omega. \end{cases}$$

The function p_D^Ω is often referred to with the name of *classical Dirichlet heat kernel in Ω* .

The following result is a consequence of Theorem 1 and Theorem 9 in [Itô57], together with Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4 and Lemma 3.25 in Section 3.3 (to be precise, we also mention that the uniqueness in the space $C^1((0, +\infty), H_0^1(\Omega))$ can be proved with the exact same approach used to show uniqueness for the system of equations (3.10) as stated in Theorem 3.8).

Theorem 3.4. *Let Ω be open, connected, bounded and smooth. Let us define the function*

$$(3.6) \quad p_D^\Omega : (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ (t, x, y) \mapsto p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) := \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k).$$

Then, for each $y \in \Omega$ the function $p_D^\Omega(\cdot, \cdot, y)$ is the unique solution to (3.5) in $C^1((0, +\infty), H_0^1(\Omega))$. Moreover, $p_D^\Omega \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$.

We also recall a Maximum Principle for the Dirichlet heat kernel:

Theorem 3.5 (See Theorem 10.3 in [Bre11]). *Let Ω be open, bounded, connected and with smooth boundary. For each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $(t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ we have that*

$$(3.7) \quad \min \left\{ 0, \inf_{\Omega} f \right\} \leq \int_{\Omega} p_D^{\Omega}(t, x, y) f(x) dx \leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}.$$

It is also useful to recall that, utilizing the classical Dirichlet heat kernel, one can equivalently express the spectral fractional Laplacian via the integration against a suitable kernel, plus a linear term of order zero. The precise details of this statement go as follows:

Proposition 3.6 (See [SVc03] and [AD17]). *Let $u \in H_D^{2s}(\Omega)$. Then, for almost every $x \in \Omega$,*

$$(3.8) \quad (-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s u(x) = P.V. \int_{\Omega} [u(x) - u(y)] J_D(x, y) dy + K_D(x) u(x),$$

where

$$(3.9) \quad \begin{aligned} J_D(x, y) &:= \frac{s}{\Gamma(1-s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^{\Omega}(t, x, y) \frac{dt}{t^{1+s}} \\ \text{and } K_D(x) &:= \frac{s}{\Gamma(1-s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \left(1 - \int_{\Omega} p_D^{\Omega}(t, x, y) dy \right) \frac{dt}{t^{1+s}}. \end{aligned}$$

The right-hand side of (3.8) is defined for each $x \in \Omega$ if $u \in C^{2s+\varepsilon}(\Omega) \cap L^1(\Omega, \delta(x) dx)$ for some $\varepsilon > 0$, where $\delta(x) := \text{dist}(x, \partial\Omega)$.

The functions J_D and K_D in (3.9) are called respectively the *jumping kernel* and *killing measure*. The killing measure has a probability interpretation that relates it to the lifetime of the stochastic process generated by the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian (see Remark 3.22).

As customary, the notation “P.V.” in (3.8) stands for “the principal value sense” and it means that the integral is intended up to the removal of a ball around its singularity in the limit sense, that is

$$P.V. \int_{\Omega} [u(x) - u(y)] J_D(x, y) dy := \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\Omega \setminus B_{\varepsilon}(x)} [u(x) - u(y)] J_D(x, y) dy.$$

Equation (3.8) can be quite useful in practice: for instance, it leads to the following Maximum Principle for $(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s$:

Lemma 3.7 (See Lemma 9 in [Aba16]). *Let $\varepsilon > 0$ and $u \in C_{loc}^{2s+\varepsilon}(\Omega) \cap L^1(\Omega, \delta(x) dx)$ be such that*

$$\begin{aligned} & (-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s u(x) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in \Omega \\ \text{and} \quad & \liminf_{\Omega \ni x \rightarrow p} u(x) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } p \in \partial\Omega, \end{aligned}$$

where $(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s$ is given as in (3.8). Then, $u(x) \geq 0$ for all $x \in \Omega$.

For each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $y \in \Omega$ the *Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation* starting at y reads as

$$(3.10) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ u(t, x) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \Omega. \end{cases}$$

The last equation is meant in the sense of measure: more precisely, defining

$$(3.11) \quad C_0(\Omega) := \{f \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \text{ s.t. } f(x) = 0 \text{ for all } x \in \partial\Omega\},$$

the last line in (3.10) means that, for each $f \in C_0(\Omega)$,

$$(3.12) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\Omega} u(t, x) f(x) dx = f(y).$$

No confusion should arise between the space $C_0(\Omega)$ introduced in (3.11) and the more standard space $C_c(\Omega)$, which is the space of continuous functions in $\bar{\Omega}$ whose support is contained in Ω : in particular, with this notation, we have that $C_c(\Omega) \subsetneq C_0(\Omega)$.

In this setting, one has the following basic structural results:

Theorem 3.8 (Existence, Uniqueness and Regularity of the solution to (3.10)). *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, connected and with smooth boundary. If we set*

$$(3.13) \quad \begin{aligned} & r_D^s : (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ & (t, x, y) \mapsto r_D^s(t, x, y) := \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s), \end{aligned}$$

then for each $y \in \Omega$ the function $r_D^s(\cdot, \cdot, y)$ is the unique solution to (3.10) in $C^1((0, +\infty), H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$. Moreover, $r_D^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$.

We will refer to r_D^s as the *Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel*. Using the Maximum Principle for the classical heat kernel in equation (3.7) one can prove its fractional counterpart. More precisely we state that:

Theorem 3.9 (Maximum Principle). *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, connected and with smooth boundary. For each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $(t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ we have that*

$$(3.14) \quad \min \left\{ 0, \inf_{\Omega} f \right\} \leq \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx \leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}.$$

Theorems 3.8 and 3.9 will be proven in Section 3.3. Additionally, we will establish in the forthcoming Theorem 3.19 and Proposition 3.21 that $r_D^s(\cdot, \cdot, y)$ is the *transition density* in Ω of the aforementioned subordinate killed Brownian motion, which will be denoted by $Y_{D,y}^{\Omega} = (\mathfrak{S}, \{\mathcal{P}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P}, \{Y_{D,t}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_{D,y}^s)$. A detailed construction for this stochastic process with its main properties is contained in Section 3.3. This means that $r_D^s(t, x, y)$ represents the density of probability that the process starting at $y \in \Omega$ will be in the position $x \in \Omega$ at a time $t > 0$. Therefore, the probability $\mathbb{P}_{D,y}^s(Y_{D,t}^{\Omega} \in \Omega')$ of finding the process $Y_{D,y}^{\Omega}$ starting at $y \in \Omega$ in some subset Ω' at a time $t > 0$ is

$$(3.15) \quad \mathbb{P}_{D,y}^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega') = \int_{\Omega'} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx.$$

We now point out one effect of subordination on the killed Brownian motion and a direct link between the geometry of the domain and the notion of probability set forth in equation (3.16). In particular, one can define the conditional probability

$$(3.16) \quad \mathbb{P}_D^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega'' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega') := \frac{1}{|\Omega'|} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega''} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx dy,$$

for each $\Omega', \Omega'' \subset \Omega$, where Ω' has positive measure. The probability in equation (3.16) is the probability of being in a set Ω'' at some time $t > 0$ starting the process from a set Ω' .

The relation between the geometry of the domain and this conditional probability is stated in the next theorems, which are the main results of this chapter. Their statements detect the monotonicity properties in the fractional parameter s in relation to the diffusive process induced by the Dirichlet fractional Laplacian. Interestingly, these monotonicity properties differ according to the size of the first Dirichlet eigenvalue of the Laplacian. The precise results that we have go as follows:

Theorem 3.10. *Let $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ and $x \in \Omega$.*

(i) *If $\lambda_1 \geq 1$, then for each $t > 0$ it holds that*

$$(3.17) \quad r_D^{s_0}(t, x, x) > r_D^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

(ii) *If $\lambda_1 < 1$, then there exists some $T > 0$, depending on x , s_0 and s_1 , such that for each $t > T$*

$$(3.18) \quad r_D^{s_0}(t, x, x) < r_D^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

Theorem 3.11. *Let $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ and $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ measurable with positive measure.*

(i) *If $\lambda_1 \geq 1$, then for each $t > 0$ it holds that*

$$(3.19) \quad \mathbb{P}_D^{s_0}(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega') > \mathbb{P}_D^{s_1}(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega').$$

(ii) *If $\lambda_1 < 1$, then there exists some $T > 0$, depending on Ω' , s_0 and s_1 , such that for each $t > T$*

$$(3.20) \quad \mathbb{P}_D^{s_0}(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega') < \mathbb{P}_D^{s_1}(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega').$$

Theorems 3.10 and 3.11 will be proven in Section 3.3. The relation between the inequalities (3.17)-(3.20) and the geometry of the domain is encoded into the first eigenvalue λ_1 . As a matter of fact it is well known that the first eigenvalue of the Dirichlet Laplacian is strictly related to the volume of the domain and (under convexity assumptions) to its perimeter (see [GN13] and references therein). Nevertheless, the volume of the domain is not the only geometrical feature of the domain that plays some role on the estimation of the first eigenvalue.

To make this observation clear, for a general bounded domain Ω , we have the following upper and lower bound (see formulas (4.9) and (4.12) in [GN13])

$$(3.21) \quad \left(\frac{v_n}{|\Omega|} \right)^{\frac{2}{n}} \beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}^2 \leq \lambda_1 \leq \left(\frac{\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}}{\rho} \right)^2,$$

where $\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}$ is the first positive zero of the Bessel function $\mathcal{J}_{\frac{n}{2}-1}$, v_n the Lebesgue measure of the unit ball in \mathbb{R}^n and

$$(3.22) \quad \rho := \max_{x \in \Omega} \min_{y \in \partial\Omega} |x - y|$$

is the *inradius* of Ω , namely the radius of the largest ball inscribed in Ω .

As a consequence of (3.21), one sees that if the domain Ω has a small enough measure, then $\lambda_1 \geq 1$, and therefore the monotonicity properties in (3.17) and (3.19) hold true. In the case of equation (3.19) this means that, for a small domain, in the sense of measure, for lower values of $s \in (0, 1)$ the probability of getting out of any starting set Ω' at any time t is lower.

This phenomenon is consistent with the heuristic idea that lower values of s correspond to a “less regular” solution of the fractional heat equation, therefore, for lower values of s , if we focus our attention only to the vicinity of the original source, a relatively large proportion of the mass of the solution tends to remain confined for quite a long time near its initial location.

While it is tempting to consider this situation as an occurrence of “slow diffusion”, a pinch of salt is needed when trying to make these considerations consistent, also in view of the following observation.

If the largest ball B_ρ inscribed in Ω is large enough, then thanks to the right hand side inequality in (3.21) we infer that $\lambda_1 < 1$. In this case, we have that if we choose $0 < s_0 < s_1 < 1$ and $\Omega' \subset \Omega$, then there exists some $T > 0$ such that for all $t > T$ the probability $\mathbb{P}^{s_0}(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega')$ that $Y_{D,t}$ will be in the starting set Ω' is smaller than the probability $\mathbb{P}^{s_1}(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega')$.

This phenomenon is also consistent with the heuristic idea that lower values of s correspond to a “fat tail” probability of jumping far away from the original location: in this sense, if the inradius is sufficiently large, thus allowing these long jumps to occur, the long time behavior of the solution will exhibit this sort of “fast diffusion”.

From these comments it should now be clear that the distinction between “slow” and “fast” diffusion is possibly more delicate than what it may seem at a first glance and it cannot be reduced merely to quantitative considerations about the fractional exponent of the equation (since, in light of the above comments, small fractional exponents can exhibit both “slow” and “fast” diffusion with respect to Dirichlet

boundary conditions, and the size and shape of the domain may play an essential role in selecting the appropriate phenomenon in different situations).

Note that in the scenario where Ω has very large Lebesgue measure, but is narrow enough so that ρ is sufficiently small, inequality (3.21) does not give us a suitable upper or lower bound in order to apply Theorem 3.11. Nevertheless, there are other inequalities available relating the first eigenvalue of the Laplacian to the geometric properties of the domain Ω .

For instance, if the domain Ω is convex, then one can make the right-hand side in (3.21) more precise. In particular (see equation (4.14) in [GN13]) we have that

$$(3.23) \quad \lambda_1 \leq \beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}^2 \frac{H^{n-1}(\partial\Omega)}{n \rho |\Omega|},$$

where H^{n-1} denotes, as usual, the $(n-1)$ -dimensional Hausdorff measure.

Remark 3.12. We observe that, for convex sets, the upper bound for λ_1 in (3.23) is sharper than that in (3.21). This is due to the geometrically interesting fact that, for convex sets,

$$(3.24) \quad \rho H^{n-1}(\partial\Omega) \leq n |\Omega|.$$

To check this, up to a translation, we can assume that

$$(3.25) \quad B_\rho \subseteq \Omega.$$

Thus, we recall that, given $x \in \partial\Omega$, if $\nu(x)$ is the unit exterior normal of Ω at x , then

$$(3.26) \quad x \cdot \nu(x) \geq \rho.$$

This is possibly a classical inequality in convex geometry (see e.g. [BM20]), but we present its simple proof for the convenience of the reader. Let $y \in \overline{\Omega}$. By convexity, we know that $\overline{\Omega}$ is contained in its supporting halfspace at x , namely

$$\overline{\Omega} \subseteq \{z \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ s.t. } (z-x) \cdot \nu(x) \leq 0\},$$

hence $(y-x) \cdot \nu(x) \leq 0$. In particular, recalling (3.25) and choosing $y := \rho\nu(x) \in \overline{B_\rho} \subseteq \overline{\Omega}$, we obtain that

$$\rho = \rho\nu(x) \cdot \nu(x) = y \cdot \nu(x) \leq x \cdot \nu(x)$$

and this proves (3.26).

From (3.26) we deduce that

$$n |\Omega| = \int_{\Omega} \operatorname{div}(x) dx = \int_{\partial\Omega} x \cdot \nu(x) dH^{n-1}(x) \geq \rho H^{n-1}(\partial\Omega),$$

and this proves (3.24), as desired.

Figure 3.1: *The set described in Example 3.13.*

Example 3.13. To better appreciate the improvement provided by (3.23) for convex sets with respect to the general case in (3.21) and to recognize the effect of this improvement in the setting of Theorems 3.10 and 3.11, we provide here an elementary example of a convex set Ω such that

$$(3.27) \quad \beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}^2 \frac{H^{n-1}(\partial\Omega)}{n \rho |\Omega|} < 1 < \left(\frac{\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}}{\rho} \right)^2.$$

In particular, for this set, we infer from (3.23) that $\lambda_1 < 1$, therefore the claims in (ii) of Theorems 3.10 and 3.11 hold true: but we stress that (3.21) would have not guaranteed this, therefore this example showcases that inequality (3.21), only relying on the measure of a domain and on the inradius, does not provide optimal information on convex sets and instead other geometrical features play a decisive role in the estimation of λ_1 , which is in turn crucial to detect the diffusivity properties of the spectral heat kernels according to Theorems 3.10 and 3.11.

Let us now construct an example of a convex set satisfying (3.27). The existence of sets with this property is somewhat a general fact (see e.g. the formula in display below (2.1) in [BM20]), but we present an elementary example to keep the discussion as simple as possible. The example that we construct is with boundary of class $C^{1,1}$, but one can also regularize the boundary and obtain a smooth set by exploiting this example.

The example that we present is the following. We pick $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, to be conveniently chosen below. We let $h > 0$, $\rho := (1 - \varepsilon)\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}$ and

$$\Omega := \bigcup_{\tau \in (-h/2, h/2)} B_\rho(0, \dots, 0, \tau).$$

See Figure 3.1 for a sketch of this set in \mathbb{R}^3 . We point out that

$$\left(\frac{\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}}{\rho}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}}{(1-\varepsilon)\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{(1-\varepsilon)^2} > 1,$$

therefore it only remains to check the first inequality in (3.27).

To this end, we denote by v_n the n -dimensional Lebesgue measure of the unit ball in \mathbb{R}^n and by a_{n-1} the $(n-1)$ -dimensional surface area of the boundary of the unit ball in \mathbb{R}^n . It is well known (see e.g. [DV24, equation (1.2.6)]) that

$$v_n = \frac{a_{n-1}}{n}.$$

We observe that Ω consists of two halfballs of radius ρ glued on the top and on the bottom of a cylinder of height h , therefore

$$|\Omega| = |B_\rho| + h\rho^{n-1}v_{n-1} = \rho^n v_n + h\rho^{n-1}v_{n-1}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} H^{n-1}(\partial\Omega) &= H^{n-1}(\partial B_\rho) + h\rho^{n-2}a_{n-2} \\ &= \rho^{n-1}a_{n-1} + h\rho^{n-2}a_{n-2} \\ &= n\rho^{n-1}v_n + (n-1)h\rho^{n-2}v_{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence,

$$\beta_{\frac{n}{2}-1,1}^2 \frac{H^{n-1}(\partial\Omega)}{n\rho|\Omega|} = \left(\frac{\rho}{(1-\varepsilon)}\right)^2 \frac{n\rho^{n-1}v_n + (n-1)h\rho^{n-2}v_{n-1}}{n\rho(\rho^n v_n + h\rho^{n-1}v_{n-1})}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1-\varepsilon)^2} \frac{n\rho v_n + (n-1)h v_{n-1}}{n\rho v_n + n h v_{n-1}}.$$

Hence, since

$$\frac{n\rho v_n + (n-1)h v_{n-1}}{n\rho v_n + n h v_{n-1}} < 1,$$

we deduce that, if ε is small enough, possibly in dependence of ρ and n , then also

$$\frac{1}{(1-\varepsilon)^2} \frac{n\rho v_n + (n-1)h v_{n-1}}{n\rho v_n + n h v_{n-1}} < 1.$$

The proof of (3.27) is thereby complete.

3.3 The spectral fractional heat equation with Dirichlet boundary conditions

In this section we study the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation (3.10) from a probabilistic and analytic point of view.

Section 3.3 introduces some background on a stochastic process called the subordinate killed Brownian motion. More precisely, we show that the transition density of this process coincides with the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel r_D^s given in equation (3.13).

Section 3.3 is devoted to the analytical study of the solution to the system of equations (3.10). Here we prove Theorems 3.8 and 3.9. The first result states that the unique solution to (3.10) is the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel r_D^s , while Theorem 3.9 is a Maximum Principle for the spectral fractional heat equation with Dirichlet boundary conditions.

In Section 3.3 we prove two new results, namely Theorems 3.10 and 3.11, which give us some interesting monotonicity properties (with respect to the parameter s) of the kernel r_D^s and the conditional probability given in equation (3.16).

From the killed Brownian motion to the subordinate killed Brownian motion

In this section we present a brief and self-contained construction of the subordinate killed Brownian motion, which is a stochastic process built from the killed Brow-

nian motion by introducing a random choice of the time via a procedure called subordination (see [Boc49]). The detailed construction of such a process is given in Theorem 3.19. More precisely, in Theorem 3.19 and Proposition 3.21 we prove that the transition density associated with this stochastic process is the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel r_D^s defined in equation (3.13). Further details on this subject can be found for instance in [SSVc12].

Now we recall some basic facts related to the notion of Killed Brownian process. Roughly speaking, the gist is that when the particle leaves the reference set Ω , it is placed into a “cemetery” where it remains forever.

To formalize this heuristic idea, we let

$$(3.28) \quad X := (\mathfrak{S}, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \{\mathbb{P}_x\}_{x \in \Omega})$$

be a family of classical n -dimensional Brownian motions in \mathbb{R}^n starting at $x \in \Omega$, namely

$$\mathbb{P}_x(X_0 = x) = 1.$$

For a definition of Brownian motion see for instance [Bal17]; in practice, in (3.28) one can consider $\mathfrak{S} = C([0, +\infty), \mathbb{R}^n)$ and $X_t(\omega) = \omega(t)$ for each $\omega \in \mathfrak{S}$ and $t \geq 0$.

Let us now recall the notion of *first exit time* random variable $\tau_\Omega := \inf\{t : X_t \notin \Omega\}$, and¹ a point $\partial \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \overline{\Omega}$.

Theorem 3.14 (See Theorems 2.2 and 2.4 in [CZ95]). *Let Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected and $x \in \Omega$. Consider the process $X_{D,x} := (\mathfrak{S}, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \{X_t^\Omega\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_x)$, where the random variable $X_t^\Omega : \mathfrak{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is defined by*

$$X_t^\Omega := \begin{cases} X_t & \text{if } t < \tau_\Omega, \\ \partial & \text{if } t \geq \tau_\Omega. \end{cases}$$

Then, the process $X_{D,x}$ is a Markov process and for each Lebesgue measurable set $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ and $t > 0$ it holds that

$$(3.29) \quad \mathbb{P}_x(X_t^\Omega \in \Omega') = \int_{\Omega'} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) dy.$$

¹The point ∂ is often called the “cemetery” of the stochastic process. Using “ ∂ ” to denote the cemetery is a typical notation in the literature, hence we stick to it. No confusion should arise with the boundary of a set (as a matter of fact, the two notations somewhat coincide for a classical Brownian motion, in the sense that the cemetery in this case can be seen as the boundary of the domain, with all points identified into a single one).

Definition 3.15. Let $x \in \Omega$.

The Markov process $X_{D,x} := (\mathfrak{G}, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \{X_t^\Omega\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_x)$ as defined in Theorem 3.14 is called killed Brownian motion.

In view of Theorem 3.14, the semigroup $\{T_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ associated with $X_{D,x}$ is

$$T_t f(x) := \int_{\Omega} f(y) p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) dy = \mathbb{E}_x[f(X_t^\Omega)],$$

for each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$. Note that we are using the term “transition density” for $p_D^\Omega(t, x, y)$ even though p_D^Ω is just the part of the transition density concentrated in Ω , which is not the whole state space, that is instead $\Omega \cup \{\partial\}$. Furthermore, for each $x \in \Omega$,

$$(3.30) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \mathbb{P}(X_t^\Omega \in \Omega) = \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) dy = 0,$$

see e.g. [CZ95, Chapter 2]. From a physical point of view, the result in (3.30) highlights that the process will eventually reach the boundary of Ω and will therefore be constrained in ∂ , or, in other terms, it will be killed.

The *generator* of the killed Brownian motion coincides with the Dirichlet Laplacian, namely

$$\frac{d}{dt} T_t f|_{t=0} = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{T_t f - f}{t} = \Delta_\Omega f$$

for each $f \in H_0^1(\Omega)$.

We now frame the notion of Brownian motion into a more general concept, according to the following classical framework:

Definition 3.16 (Lévy processes). Let $(\tilde{D}, \mathcal{B}, \mathbb{P})$ be a probability space. Then, we say that the stochastic process $X = (\tilde{D}, \mathcal{B}, \{\mathcal{B}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P})$ is a Lévy process if:

- 1) $\mathbb{P}(X_0 = 0) = 1$;
- 2) for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 \leq t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_{n+1}$, the random variables $(X_{t_{j+1}} - X_{t_j}, 1 \leq j \leq n)$ are independent, and also $X_{t_{j+1}} - X_{t_j}$ and $X_{t_{j+1}-t_j} - X_0$ are identically distributed for each $1 \leq j \leq n$;
- 3) X is stochastically continuous, namely for each $a > 0$ and for all $s \geq 0$ it holds

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow s} \mathbb{P}(|X_t - X_s| > a) = 0.$$

The Brownian motion is the prototype example of Lévy process, see for instance [App09].

We now recall the notion of s -stable subordinator. In a nutshell, a Lévy process is a subordinator if its realization is increasing as a function of time. Also, a subordinator is stable when its Laplace transform reduces to an exponential function of a power, as made precise through the following setting:

Definition 3.17 (s -stable subordinator). Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mathfrak{S}_1 := C([0, +\infty), [0, +\infty))$.

We say that a Lévy process

$$(3.31) \quad S = (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathcal{G}, \{S_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s)$$

is an s -stable subordinator if the following properties are satisfied:

- 1) $S_t(\omega)$ is an increasing function of $t > 0$ for each $\omega \in \mathfrak{S}_1$;
- 2) for each $\lambda > 0$

$$(3.32) \quad \tilde{\mathbb{E}}^s[\exp(-\lambda S_t)] := \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-x\lambda) \mu_t^s(dx) = \exp(-t\lambda^s),$$

where μ_t^s is the law associated with the random variable S_t , namely

$$(3.33) \quad \tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(S_t \in A) = \mu_t^s(A)$$

for each Borel subset $A \subset [0, +\infty)$.

Some comments are in order about the reason behind the name of s -stability in Definition 3.17. While the parameter s obviously refers to the exponent in (3.32), the notion of stability refers to the fact that

$$(3.34) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{if } \overline{S}_t \text{ and } \underline{S}_t \text{ are independent and satisfy (3.32),} \\ &\text{then } \tilde{S}_t := \overline{S}_{t/2} + \underline{S}_{t/2} \text{ satisfies (3.32) as well.} \end{aligned}$$

To check this, we recall that the probability density $\tilde{\mu}_t^s$ of \tilde{S}_t satisfies the condition

$$\int_0^{+\infty} f(z) \tilde{\mu}_t^s(dz) = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} f(x+y) \overline{\mu}_{t/2}^s(dx) \underline{\mu}_{t/2}^s(dy)$$

for each f which is Borel measurable, where $\bar{\mu}_{t/2}^s$ and $\underline{\mu}_{t/2}^s$ are the corresponding probability densities respectively for $\bar{S}_{t/2}$ and $\underline{S}_{t/2}$. Therefore, we obtain that for each $\lambda > 0$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda x} \tilde{\mu}_t^s(dx) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda(x+y)} \bar{\mu}_{t/2}^s(dx) \underline{\mu}_{t/2}^s(dy) \\
 (3.35) \qquad &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda x} e^{-\lambda y} \bar{\mu}_{t/2}^s(dx) \underline{\mu}_{t/2}^s(dy) \\
 &= e^{-\lambda^s t/2} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda x} \underline{\mu}_{t/2}^s(dy) \\
 &= e^{-\lambda^s t},
 \end{aligned}$$

which confirms (3.34).

Remark 3.18. We also remark that the density μ_t^s of a s -stable subordinator is absolutely continuous with respect to the Lebesgue measure for each $s \in (0, 1)$. As a matter of fact, see for instance Proposition 3.1 in [KV18], if we call

$$\mu_t^s(l) := \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) du \quad \text{for all } l > 0,$$

then, $\mu_t^s \in L^1((0, +\infty))$ for each $t > 0$ and $s \in (0, 1)$, and also for each Borel subset $A \subset [0, +\infty)$ it holds that

$$\mu_t^s(A) = \int_A \mu_t^s(l) dl.$$

Since the absolute continuity with respect to the Lebesgue measure is not needed in this chapter, we will keep using the notation

$$\mu_t^s(A) = \int_A \mu_t^s(dl),$$

for each Borel subset $A \subset [0, +\infty)$.

Now we introduce the subordinate killed Brownian motion through the operation of subordination, which was first introduced by Bochner in [Boc49]. Roughly speaking, in this framework subordination determines a random choice of the time t through the s -stable subordinator S , providing in this way a new process (a formalization of this concept will be given in equation (3.36) here below). In the following result we recall a classical formula for the transition density of this subordinate process, which will be called *subordinate killed Brownian motion*. The formula is given

in (3.37) and we provide here a detailed analytic proof for the convenience of the reader.

Theorem 3.19. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, Ω be open, bounded smooth and connected. Furthermore, let $S = (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathcal{G}, \{S_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s)$ be an s -stable subordinator and $X_{D,x} := (\mathfrak{S}, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \{X_t^\Omega\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_x)$ be a killed Brownian motion as in Definition 3.15.*

Let us define the family of stochastic processes

$$(3.36) \quad \begin{aligned} Y_D^\Omega &:= (\mathfrak{S} \times \mathfrak{S}_1, \{\mathcal{F}_t \times \mathcal{G}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{G}, \{Y_{D,t}\}_{t \geq 0}, \{\mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s\}_{x \in \Omega}) \\ \text{and} \quad Y_{D,t}(\omega, \omega_1) &:= X_{S_t(\omega_1)}^\Omega(\omega), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s := \mathbb{P}_x \times \tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s$.

Then, for each $x \in \Omega$ the stochastic process $Y_{D,x}^\Omega$ is a Markov process. Moreover, for each Lebesgue measurable subset $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ we have that

$$(3.37) \quad \mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega') = \int_{\Omega'} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(dl) dy.$$

Proof. The process $Y_{D,x}^\Omega$ is a Markov process (see for instance [Bou84]). Thus, we only have to prove formula (3.37). Let $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ and $t > 0$, then we see that

$$(3.38) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega') &= \mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s(\{(\omega, \omega_1) \in \mathfrak{S} \times \mathfrak{S}_1 \text{ s.t. } X_{S_t(\omega_1)}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \\ &= \int_{\mathfrak{S}_1} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{S} \text{ s.t. } X_{S_t(\omega_1)}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) d\tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(\omega_1). \end{aligned}$$

Now we consider $h > 0$ and define the following quantities

$$(3.39) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_k(h) &:= \int_{\{S_t(\omega_1) \in [kh, (k+1)h]\}} \left(\mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{S} \text{ s.t. } X_{S_t(\omega_1)}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{S} \text{ s.t. } X_{kh}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \right) d\tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(\omega_1) \\ \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}_k(h) &:= \int_{kh}^{(k+1)h} \left(\mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{S} \text{ s.t. } X_{kh}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{S} \text{ s.t. } X_l(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \right) \mu_t^s(l) dl. \end{aligned}$$

With the notation in (3.39), we observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{\mathfrak{G}_1} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{G} \text{ s.t. } X_{S_t(\omega_1)}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) d\tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(\omega_1) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{\{S_t(\omega_1) \in [kh, (k+1)h)\}} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{G} \text{ s.t. } X_{S_t(\omega_1)}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) d\tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(\omega_1) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{\{S_t(\omega_1) \in [kh, (k+1)h)\}} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{G} \text{ s.t. } X_{kh}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) d\tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(\omega_1) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{I}_k(h) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{G} \text{ s.t. } X_{kh}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \int_{\{S_t(\omega_1) \in [kh, (k+1)h)\}} d\tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(\omega_1) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{I}_k(h) \\
 (3.40) \quad &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{G} \text{ s.t. } X_{kh}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(S_t(\omega_1) \in [kh, (k+1)h)) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{I}_k(h) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{G} \text{ s.t. } X_{kh}(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \int_{kh}^{(k+1)h} \mu_t^s(dl) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{I}_k(h) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{kh}^{(k+1)h} \mathbb{P}_x(\{\omega \in \mathfrak{G} \text{ s.t. } X_l(\omega) \in \Omega'\}) \mu_t^s(dl) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{J}_k(h) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{I}_k(h) \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\Omega'} p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) dy \mu_t^s(dl) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{J}_k(h) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{I}_k(h).
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we note that since $\mathbb{P}_x(A) \leq 1$ for each $A \in \mathcal{F}$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 (3.41) \quad & \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \|\mathcal{I}_k(h)\|_{L^\infty((0, +\infty))} \leq \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{\{S_t(\omega_1) \in [kh, (k+1)h)\}} d\tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s(\omega_1) = 1 \\
 \text{and} \quad & \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \|\mathcal{J}_k(h)\|_{L^\infty((0, +\infty))} \leq \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{kh}^{(k+1)h} \mu_t^s(l) dl = 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, using (3.29) and the regularity of p_D^Ω stated in Theorem 3.4 one gets that for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$

$$(3.42) \quad \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{I}_k(h) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{J}_k(h) = 0.$$

By equations (3.41) and (3.42) we deduce that

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{I}_k(h) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \mathcal{J}_k(h) = 0.$$

Therefore, using the identity in (3.38) and taking the limit for $h \rightarrow 0$ in (3.40) we find that

$$(3.43) \quad \mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega') = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\Omega'} p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) dy \mu_t^s(dl).$$

Hence we have proved formula (3.37), which concludes the proof of Theorem 3.19. \square

According to Theorem 3.19, we can give the following:

Definition 3.20 (Subordinate killed Brownian motion, see [SVc03]). For each $x \in \Omega$ the process

$$Y_{D,x}^\Omega := (\mathfrak{G} \times \mathfrak{G}_1, \{\mathcal{F}_t \times \mathcal{G}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{G}, \{Y_{D,t}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s)$$

defined in Theorem 3.19 is called *subordinate killed Brownian motion* starting at x and it is given by

$$(3.44) \quad Y_{D,t}(\omega, \omega_1) = \begin{cases} X_{S_t(\omega_1)}^\Omega(\omega) & \text{if } S_t(\omega_1) < \tau_\Omega(\omega), \\ \partial & \text{if } S_t(\omega_1) \geq \tau_\Omega(\omega). \end{cases}$$

Now we show that the transition density of the subordinate killed Brownian motion coincides with the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel r_D^s defined in equation (3.13).

Proposition 3.21. *Let $r_D^s : (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be as in equation (3.13). Then,*

$$(3.45) \quad r_D^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(dl)$$

for all $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$.

Proof. Thanks to Theorem 3.4 we have that

$$p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k).$$

Using this and equation (3.32) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, t) \mu_t^s(dl) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-l\lambda_k) \mu_t^s(dl) \\
 (3.46) \qquad &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-l\lambda_k) \mu_t^s(dl) \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \\
 &= r_D^s(t, x, y).
 \end{aligned}$$

The identity between the first and second line in (3.46) is guaranteed by the Dominated Convergence Theorem, which can be applied thanks to equation (40) in Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28 of the appendix of Chapter 4. \square

As a straightforward consequence of Theorem 3.19 and Proposition 3.21, the transition density associated with the subordinate killed Brownian motion coincides with the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel given in equation (3.13). Therefore,

$$\mathbb{P}_{D,x}^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega') = \int_{\Omega'} r_D^s(t, x, y) dy$$

and accordingly

$$(3.47) \qquad \mathbb{P}_D^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega'' | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega') = \frac{1}{|\Omega'|} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega''} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx dy,$$

as anticipated in equation (3.16). The term $|\Omega'|^{-1}$ in equation (3.47) is a normalizing factor, and it is introduced so that $\mathbb{P}^s(\cdot | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega')$ is actually a probability in $\mathfrak{S} \times \mathfrak{S}_1$. Clearly, since the state space is not Ω (but $\Omega \cup \{\partial\}$), for $t > 0$ we have $\mathbb{P}^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega') < 1$. By defining

$$\mathbb{P}_D^s(Y_{D,t} \in \partial | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega') := 1 - \mathbb{P}_D^s(Y_{D,t} \in \Omega | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega'),$$

we deduce that $\mathbb{P}^s(\cdot | Y_{D,0} \in \Omega')$ is a probability with state space $\Omega \cup \{\partial\}$.

In equation (3.8) of Proposition 3.6 we have stated that the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian admits an integral representation. In that expression, a zero order term K_D , called the “killing measure”, is present. In the following remark we point out its relation with the subordinate killed Brownian motion.

Remark 3.22. For each $x \in \Omega$ there is a connection between the killing measure $K_D(x)$ computed in x and the rapidity with which the process $Y_{D,x}^\Omega$ exits the domain Ω . More specifically, we have the identity (see Lemma 3.1 in [SVc03])

$$K_D(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-s)} \mathbb{E}_x(\tau_\Omega^{-s}).$$

In particular this means that a subordinate killed process with low values for the exit time τ_Ω will have a greater “killing component”. In this sense the killing measure keeps track of the killing rate.

From Proposition 3.21 we also obtain that:

Proposition 3.23. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Y_D^Ω as in Definition 3.20. The semigroup associated with Y_D^Ω*

$$(3.48) \quad \begin{aligned} R_t : L^2(\Omega) &\rightarrow L^2(\Omega) \\ f &\mapsto R_t f(x) := \int_\Omega f(y) r_D^s(t, x, y) dy, \end{aligned}$$

satisfies

$$\|R_t f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} < \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}.$$

Proof. We can rewrite (3.48) as

$$(3.49) \quad \begin{aligned} R_t f(x) &= \int_\Omega f(y) r_D^s(t, x, y) dy \\ &= \int_\Omega \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(y) \phi_k(x) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) f(y) dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \int_\Omega \phi_k(y) f(y) dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k(x) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \end{aligned}$$

for each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$. The identity between the second and third line is due to the bounds for the eigenfunctions given in Proposition 4.27, and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4, together with the Dominated Convergence Theorem. Hence,

we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \|R_t f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &= \left\| \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) f_k \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k^2 \exp(-2\lambda_k^s t) < \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k^2 = \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}, \end{aligned}$$

as desired. \square

As well known, the generator associated with the killed Brownian motion is the Dirichlet Laplacian (see e.g. [CZ95, Theorem 2.13]). Now we show a similar result for the subordinate killed Brownian motion, namely that the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian in (3.3) is the generator of Y_D^Ω .

Proposition 3.24. *The generator of the process Y_D^Ω is given by equation (3.3). Namely, for each $f \in H_D^{2s}(\Omega)$,*

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{R_t f - f}{t} = -(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s f,$$

where the convergence is meant in $L^2(\Omega)$.

Proof. We will prove the statement first for the eigenfunctions of the Laplacian, and then by density for all $f \in H_D^{2s}(\Omega)$. Let ϕ_k be as in equation (4.40). Then we have that for each $x \in \Omega$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{R_t \phi_k(x) - \phi_k(x)}{t} &= \frac{1}{t} \left(\int_{\Omega} \phi_k(y) r_D^s(t, x, y) dy - \phi_k(x) \right) \\ (3.50) \quad &= \frac{1}{t} \left(\int_{\Omega} \phi_k(y) \sum_{j=1}^{+\infty} \phi_j(x) \phi_j(y) \exp(-t\lambda_j^s) dy - \phi_k(x) \right) \\ &= \phi_k(x) \left(\frac{\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1}{t} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Let now $f \in H_D^{2s}(\Omega)$, and consider its $L^2(\Omega)$ decomposition $f = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k$. Given $\varepsilon > 0$, we pick $N \in \mathbb{N}$ sufficiently large such that

$$\left\| f - \sum_{k=1}^N f_k \phi_k \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \varepsilon.$$

Thus, owing to Proposition 3.23,

$$\left\| R_t f - \sum_{k=1}^N f_k R_t \phi_k \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = \left\| R_t \left(f - \sum_{k=1}^N f_k \phi_k \right) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \varepsilon.$$

This gives that

$$R_t f = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k R_t \phi_k,$$

where the convergence is intended in $L^2(\Omega)$.

Since $f \in H_D^{2s}(\Omega)$, we have that $(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s f \in L^2(\Omega)$, hence

$$(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s f = \sum_{k=1}^N \lambda_k^s f_k \phi_k.$$

As a consequence, by (3.50),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{R_t f - f}{t} + (-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s f &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \left(\frac{R_t \phi_k - \phi_k}{t} + \lambda_k^s \phi_k \right) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k \left(\frac{\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1}{t} + \lambda_k \right). \end{aligned}$$

This gives that

$$\left\| \frac{R_t f - f}{t} + (-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s f \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k^2 \left(\frac{\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1}{t} + \lambda_k^s \right)^2.$$

We observe that $-\lambda_k^s \leq \frac{\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1}{t} < 0$ for each $t > 0$, which means that

$$\sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left\| f_k^2 \left(\frac{\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1}{t} \right)^2 \right\|_{L^\infty(0,+\infty)} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k^2 \lambda_k^{2s} < +\infty,$$

where the last inequality is due to the fact that $f \in H_D^{2s}(\Omega)$.

Therefore,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \left\| \frac{R_t f - f}{t} + (-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s f \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} f_k^2 \left(\frac{\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1}{t} + \lambda_k^s \right)^2 = 0,$$

as desired. □

Existence, Uniqueness and Maximum Principle for the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation

We now focus on the existence, uniqueness and regularity of the solution to the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation (3.10) and on a Maximum Principle for its solution, addressing the proofs of Theorems 3.8 and 3.9.

To start with, the following result establishes the regularity of the kernel r_D^s , which will be later proved to be the solution to (3.10).

Lemma 3.25. *Let $s \in (0, 1]$ and Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected. Then, $r_D^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \overline{\Omega} \times \overline{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$.*

Proof. Consider the truncated series

$$(3.51) \quad S_M(t, x, y) := \sum_{k=1}^M \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s)$$

and $(t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$.

Owing to Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4, we see that

$$\sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} |\phi_k(y)|^2 \exp(-2t\lambda_k^s) \leq c_{m_0, \Omega, 0}^2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{2\alpha(m_0)} \exp(-2t\lambda_k^s) < +\infty,$$

and therefore

$$(3.52) \quad \begin{aligned} S_M(t, \cdot, y) \text{ converges to } r_{D,y}^s(t, \cdot) := r_D^s(t, \cdot, y) \\ \text{in } L^2(\Omega) \text{ for each } (t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega. \end{aligned}$$

From the $L^2(\Omega)$ convergence of the series we obtain, possibly up to a subsequence, that $S_M(t, \cdot, y)$ is converging a.e. to $r_{D,y}^s(t, \cdot)$ in Ω .

Using the estimates in (4.42) and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|\phi_k(\cdot) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s)\|_{C^r(\overline{\Omega})} \\ \leq c_{m_r, \Omega, r} c_{m_0, \Omega, 0} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{\alpha(m_0) + \alpha(m_r)} \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) < +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

This gives that $S_M(t, \cdot, y)$ is converging in $C^r(\bar{\Omega})$ to $r_D^s(t, \cdot, y)$ for each $r \in \mathbb{N}$. From this, we conclude that $r_D^s(t, \cdot, y) \in C^\infty(\bar{\Omega})$, and since r_D^s is symmetric in the last two variables, we have that $r_D^s(t, \cdot, \cdot) \in C^\infty(\bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $t \in (0, +\infty)$.

The next step is to show that $r_D^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$. Given $(x, y) \in \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega}$ and $\varepsilon > 0$, we note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|D^\gamma \phi_k(x) D^\beta \phi_k(y) \frac{d^r}{dt^r} \exp(-t\lambda_k^s)\|_{C^0([\varepsilon, +\infty))} \\ & \leq \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|\phi_k\|_{C^{|\gamma|}(\bar{\Omega})} \|\phi_k\|_{C^{|\beta|}(\bar{\Omega})} \|\exp(-t\lambda_k^s)\|_{C^r([\varepsilon, +\infty))} (\lambda_k^s)^r \\ & \leq c_{m_{|\gamma|}, \Omega, |\gamma|} c_{m_{|\beta|}, \Omega, |\beta|} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{\alpha(m_{|\gamma|}) + \alpha(m_{|\beta|}) + rs} \exp(-\varepsilon \lambda_k^s) \\ & < +\infty \end{aligned}$$

for each multindex $\beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{N}^n$ and $r \in \mathbb{N}$. In particular, this estimate gives that

$$\frac{d^r}{dt^r} D^\gamma D^\beta S_M \rightarrow \frac{d^r}{dt^r} D^\gamma D^\beta r_D^s \quad \text{for } M \rightarrow +\infty$$

in $C^0([\varepsilon, +\infty))$, leading to $r_D^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for any $\varepsilon > 0$. □

Now we prove that r_D^s is a solution to the first two equations in (3.10). The proof of the fact that r_D^s solves also the third equation in (3.10) and that the solution is unique can be found at the end of this section (see the proof of Theorem 3.8).

Lemma 3.26. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected. Then, for each $y \in \Omega$ the function $r_{D,y}^s(t, x) := r_D^s(t, x, y)$ is a solution to the first and second equation in (3.10).*

Proof. First we show that $r_{D,y}^s$ solves the first equation in (3.10). For this, we observe that Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4 yield that we can differentiate with respect to t inside the sum, and thus

$$\partial_t r_{D,y}^s(t, x) = - \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \lambda_k^s \exp(-t \lambda_k^s) = -(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s r_{D,y}^s(t, x),$$

which proves that $r_{D,y}^s$ solves the first equation in (3.10).

Furthermore, we recall the uniform convergence of the series $S_M(t, \cdot, y)$ in Ω for each $(t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ to $r_{D,y}^s(t, \cdot)$, as given by (3.52). Since $\phi_k(x) = 0$ for each $x \in \partial\Omega$ and $k \geq 1$, then we get that also $r_{D,y}^s(t, x) = 0$ for each $x \in \partial\Omega$. These observations show that $r_{D,y}^s$ solves also the second equation in (3.10), and this concludes the proof of Lemma 3.26. \square

We now state and prove a technical result that will be useful later in order to prove the Maximum Principle stated in Theorem 3.9. More specifically, we will obtain a continuity with respect to the initial data (see the forthcoming equation (3.54)) which will be used to prove that r_D^s satisfies the third equation in (3.10) (as stated in Theorem 3.8 below).

Lemma 3.27. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected. For each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ the function $R_t f$ defined in (3.48) is the unique solution in $C([0, +\infty), L^2(\Omega)) \cap C^1((0, +\infty), H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$ to the system of equations*

$$(3.53) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, y) = -(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s u(t, y) & \text{for all } (t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ u(t, y) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, y) = f(y) & \text{for all } y \in \Omega. \end{cases}$$

The last equation in (3.53) is meant as

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \|u(t, y) - f(y)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = 0.$$

Furthermore, for each $\varepsilon > 0$, it holds that $R_t f(y) \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega})$. Moreover, if $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$, then

$$(3.54) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \|R_t f(y) - f(y)\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} = 0.$$

Proof. Let $f \in L^2(\Omega)$. First we show that $R_t f$ satisfies the first equation in (3.53). By Lemma 3.25 we have that $r_D^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$. From this regularity result one easily deduces that $R_t f(y) \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$. In view of (3.49), we know that

$$(3.55) \quad R_t f(y) = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s).$$

Using Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28 from the appendix of Chapter 4, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t R_t f(y) &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k(y) \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \\ &= - \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^s f_k \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) = -(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s R_t f(y). \end{aligned}$$

This proves that $R_t f$ satisfies the first equation in (3.53).

Also the second equation in (3.53) is satisfied by $R_t f$. Indeed, thanks to Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4, for each $t > 0$ the series on the right-hand side of (3.55) converges uniformly in $y \in \Omega$, and since the ϕ_k 's are all vanishing on $\partial\Omega$, we can conclude that the second equation in (3.53) holds true.

Now we verify that $R_t f$ satisfies the last equation in (3.53). Using (3.55) and the fact that $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\Omega} |R_t f(y) - f(y)|^2 dy &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} (\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1)^2 f_k^2 = 0 \\ (3.56) \qquad \qquad \qquad &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} (\exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - 1)^2 f_k^2 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we have proved that $R_t f$ satisfies also the third equation in (3.53). Now, from the fact that $R_t f(y) \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$ together with equations (3.56) and (3.55) we deduce that $R_t f(y) \in C([0, +\infty), L^2(\Omega)) \cap C^1((0, +\infty), H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$. Therefore, we have proved that $R_t f$ is a solution to (3.53) in the space $C([0, +\infty), L^2(\Omega)) \cap C^1((0, +\infty), H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$.

Let us now discuss the uniqueness of the solution of (3.53). It is showed by using the monotonicity² of the operator $(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s$. In particular suppose that $g(t, y) \in$

²An operator $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subset H \rightarrow H$ is said *monotone* if $(Av, v) \geq 0$ for each $v \in \mathcal{D}(A)$, where $(H, (\cdot, \cdot))$ is an Hilbert space. For further details see [Bre11].

$C([0, +\infty), L^2(\Omega)) \cap C^1((0, +\infty), H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$ is another solution to (3.53), then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega} |R_t f(y) - g(t, y)|^2 dy \\ &= \frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega} (R_t f(y) - g(t, y)) (R_t f(y) - g(t, y)) dy \\ &= - \int_{\Omega} (-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s (R_t f(y) - g(t, y)) (R_t f(y) - g(t, y)) dy \\ &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the function $\kappa(t) := \|R_t f(y) - g(t, y)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2$ is positive, decreasing, continuous and by hypothesis $\kappa(0) = 0$. This implies that $\kappa(t) = 0$ for each $t > 0$, which means that $R_t f(y) = g(t, y)$ for each $t \in (0, +\infty)$ and for almost every $y \in \Omega$.

We now prove the limit in equation (3.54). Let $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$. For this, we note that, by Proposition 4.30 in the appendix of Chapter 4,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|f_k \phi_k\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \|(1 - \exp(-t\lambda_k^s))\|_{L^\infty([0, +\infty))} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|f_k \phi_k\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} < +\infty.$$

Therefore, using (3.55) we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \|R_t f - f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \left\| \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f_k \phi_k \right\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \\ (3.57) \quad &\leq \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|f_k \phi_k\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} (1 - \exp(-t\lambda_k^s)) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|f_k \phi_k\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} (1 - \exp(-t\lambda_k^s)) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

The proof of the desired result is thereby complete. \square

Now we are ready to prove the Maximum Principle for the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation (3.10) as stated in Theorem 3.9. With a rather standard method in parabolic PDEs, in the following proof we use an argument based on the Maximum Principle for the operator $(-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s$.

Alternatively, Theorem 3.9 can be proved by making use of the probabilistic framework developed in Section 3.3. More specifically, one can deduce the two-sided inequality in (4.56) from the Maximum Principle for the classical Dirichlet

heat equation and formula (3.45). A proof of Theorem 3.9 using the probabilistic approach can be found in the appendix of Chapter 4.

Instead, here we present a purely analytical proof which does not require any probability result.

Proof of Theorem 3.9. We focus on the proof of the right-hand side inequality in (4.56). Let us first assume that $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ (the general case will then be treated by using an approximation argument). By Lemma 3.27 we know that $R_t f(y) =: f(t, y) \in C([0, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega}) \cap C^\infty([\delta, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\delta > 0$. Let us call $K := \max\{0, \sup_\Omega f\}$, and assume by contradiction that there exists $(t^*, y^*) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ such that

$$f(t^*, y^*) > K.$$

We define a new function $W(t, y) := f(t^*, y^*) - \varepsilon - f(t, y)$, where $\varepsilon > 0$ is a constant satisfying

$$(3.58) \quad \varepsilon < \inf_\Omega (f(t^*, y^*) - f(x)).$$

Note that $W(t, y) \in C([0, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega}) \cap C^\infty([\delta, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\delta > 0$. Then, we observe that

$$W(0, y) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad W(t^*, y^*) < 0,$$

and therefore there exists a point $(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ such that

$$(3.59) \quad \begin{aligned} W(t, y) &> 0 \quad \text{for all } (t, y) \in [0, \tilde{t}) \times \Omega, \\ W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) &= 0 \quad \text{and} \quad W(\tilde{t}, y) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in \Omega. \end{aligned}$$

In particular this means that

$$\partial_t W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \leq 0.$$

Moreover, using the Maximum Principle for $(-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s$ given in Lemma 3.7 and the fact that \tilde{y} is a minimum for $W(\tilde{t}, \cdot)$, we deduce that

$$(-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \leq 0.$$

Therefore, we get

$$\partial_t W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) + (-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \leq 0.$$

On the other hand, using the fact that $f(t, y)$ is a solution to the first equation in (3.53) (as established by Lemma 3.27) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) + (-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) &= -\partial_t f(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) + (-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s (f(t^*, y^*) - \varepsilon) - (-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s f(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \\ &= (-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s (f(t^*, y^*) - \varepsilon) > 0, \end{aligned}$$

providing a contradiction. This completes the proof of the right-hand side inequality in (4.56) when $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$.

We now prove the right-hand side inequality in (4.56) when $f \in L^2(\Omega)$. To do so let us first observe that

$$(3.60) \quad r_D^s(t, x, y) \geq 0 \text{ for each } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

Indeed, if by contradiction there exist (t_0, x_0, y_0) such that $r_D^s(t_0, x_0, y_0) < 0$, then by continuity there exists a neighbourhood V_{x_0} of x_0 such that

$$r_D^s(t_0, \cdot, y_0)|_{V_{x_0}} < 0.$$

Now, given a function $g \in C_c^\infty(V_{x_0})$ such that $g \geq 0$, we define

$$g(t, y) := \int_{V_{x_0}} r_D^s(t, x, y) g(x) dx$$

and we see that

$$g(t_0, y_0) = \int_{V_{x_0}} r_D^s(t_0, x, y_0) g(x) dx < 0.$$

On the other hand, $g(t, y)$ is the solution to (3.53) with initial condition $g(x)$, and therefore $g(t, x) \geq 0$ for each $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$, thus providing the desired contradiction and establishing (3.60).

Let us now consider a sequence of invading compact sets $K_n \subset \Omega$, namely $\cup_{k=1}^{+\infty} K_n = \Omega$, and $K_n \subset K_{n+1}$ for each n , and a sequence of smooth functions $f_n \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ such that $f_n|_{K_n} = 1$ and $0 \leq f_n \leq 1$. Then for each $(t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ we have that

$$\int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f_n(x) dx,$$

where the identity is guaranteed by the Dominated Convergence Theorem.

Furthermore, notice that, for each n ,

$$\int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f_n(x) dx \leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f_n \right\} = 1.$$

These observations give that

$$(3.61) \quad \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx \leq 1.$$

Therefore, if $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, y) &= \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx \\ &\leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\} \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx \leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

and this proves the right-hand side inequality of (4.56) when $f \in L^2(\Omega)$.

The left-hand side inequality of (4.56) can be proved analogously. \square

For the sake of completeness, we now improve the statement in (3.60) by showing the strict positivity of the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel r_D^s .

Corollary 3.28. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected. Then, for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$ it holds that*

$$r_D^s(t, x, y) > 0.$$

Proof. We recall (3.60) and we argue by contradiction supposing that there exists some $(t_0, x_0, y_0) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$ such that $r_D^s(t_0, x_0, y_0) = 0$. Then, using (3.8) and Lemma 3.26 we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t r_D^s(t_0, x_0, y_0) &= -(-\Delta)_{D, \Omega}^s r_D^s(t_0, x_0, y_0) \\ &= - \int_{\Omega} (0 - r_D^s(t_0, x, y_0)) J_D(x_0, x) dx > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the function $t \mapsto r_D^s(t, x_0, y_0)$ is strictly increasing in t in a neighbourhood of t_0 .

Since $r_D^s(t_0, x_0, y_0) = 0$, we conclude that there exists some $t < t_0$ such that $r_D^s(t, x_0, y_0) < 0$, which is in contradiction with (3.60). \square

As a consequence of Corollary 3.28 we establish that $R_t : C_0(\Omega) \rightarrow C_0(\Omega)$ is continuous with Lipschitz constant 1. This continuity result will be fundamental when proving that $r_D^s(t, x, y)$ solves also the third equation in (3.10).

Corollary 3.29. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be open, bounded, smooth and connected. Then,*

$$\begin{aligned} R_t : C_0(\Omega) &\rightarrow C_0(\Omega) \\ f &\longmapsto R_t f \end{aligned}$$

satisfies

$$(3.62) \quad \|R_t f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \leq \|f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)}.$$

Proof. From Corollary 3.28 and inequality (3.61) we obtain that

$$|R_t f(y)| = \left| \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx \right| \leq \|f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx \leq \|f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)},$$

for every $y \in \Omega$. Taking the maximum in $y \in \Omega$ of both sides we get (3.62), as desired. \square

Now we address the proof of Theorem 3.8.

Proof of Theorem 3.8. In Lemma 3.25 we already proved that $r_D^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$. Moreover, thanks to Lemma 3.26 we know that $r_{D,y}^s$ is a solution to the first and second equation in (3.10). It is left to show that it satisfies the third equation, and that is unique in $C^1((0, +\infty), H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$. Let us first prove that $r_D^s(\cdot, \cdot, y)$ satisfies the third equation in (3.10).

Let $f \in C_0(\Omega)$ and consider a sequence of smooth functions $\{f_n\}_n \subset C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ such that f_n converges uniformly in Ω to f . Then we have that for each $y \in \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} &|R_t f(y) - f(y)| \\ &\leq |R_t f(y) - R_t f_n(y)| + |R_t f_n(y) - f_n(y)| + |f_n(y) - f(y)| \\ &\leq \|R_t f - R_t f_n\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} + \|R_t f_n - f_n\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} + \|f_n - f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)}. \end{aligned}$$

Given $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $N_\varepsilon \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n \geq N_\varepsilon$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$ it holds $\|f_n - f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} < \varepsilon$. Thanks to Corollary 3.29 we know that $R_t : C_0(\Omega) \rightarrow C_0(\Omega)$ is continuous, and therefore if $n \geq N_\varepsilon$ we get that

$$\|R_t f - R_t f_n\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \leq \|f_n - f\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} < \varepsilon.$$

Given $n \geq N_\varepsilon$, thanks to equation (3.54), we have that for each $t > 0$ small enough it holds $\|R_t f_n - f_n\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} < \varepsilon$. Therefore, we have just proved that for each $f \in C_0(\Omega)$ and $y \in \Omega$ it holds that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx = f(y),$$

which establishes that the function $r_{D,y}^s(t, x) := r_D^s(t, x)$ satisfies also the third equation in (3.10). Note that $r_{D,y}^s(t, x) \in C^1((0, +\infty); H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$. Indeed, in view of Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4, combined with equation (3.4), we have that for each $\delta > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{2s} \phi_k(y)^2 \|\exp(-2t\lambda_k^s)\|_{L^\infty((\delta, +\infty))} < +\infty \\ \text{and} \quad & \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{2s} \phi_k(y)^2 \left\| \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-2t\lambda_k^s) \right\|_{L^\infty((\delta, +\infty))} < +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Now that we have showed that $r_{D,y}^s \in C^1((0, +\infty); H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$ is a solution to (3.10), let us prove that it is unique in $C^1((0, +\infty); H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$. Suppose by contradiction that there exists, for some $y \in \Omega$, a map $v_y(t, x)$ that satisfies equations (3.10) and such that $v_y(t, x) \in C^1((0, +\infty), H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$.

Then, we can write

$$v_y(t, x) = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} c_k(t, y) \phi_k(x),$$

where $c_k(t, y) \in C^1((0, +\infty))$ as a consequence of the hypothesis $v_y(t, x) \in C^1((0, +\infty); H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$. Since v_y is a solution to the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation (3.10) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{d}{dt} c_k(t, y) \phi_k(x) &= \partial_t v_y(t, x) \\ &= -(-\Delta)_{D,\Omega}^s v_y(t, x) = -\sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^s c_k(t, y) \phi_k(x), \end{aligned}$$

from which we deduce that $c_k(t, y) = m_{k,y} \exp(-t\lambda_k^s)$, for some constant $m_{k,y}$ to be specified.

Since $v_y(t, x)$ satisfies the third equation in (3.10) we finally get that for each $k \geq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_k(y) &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\Omega} v_y(t, x) \phi_k(x) dx \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\Omega} \sum_{j=1}^{+\infty} m_{j,y} \exp(-t\lambda_j^s) \phi_j(x) \phi_k(x) dx \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} m_{k,y} \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \\ &= m_{k,y}, \end{aligned}$$

and therefore $v_y(t, x) = r_{D,y}(t, x)$, which proves that the solution to (3.10) in $C^1((0, +\infty); H_D^{2s}(\Omega))$ is unique. This last step concludes the proof of Theorem 3.8. \square

Proof of Theorems 3.10 and 3.11

In this section we prove Theorems 3.10 and 3.11. We begin by pointing out that (3.45) means that $r_D^s(t, x, y)$ is equal to the probability that S_t has values in the infinitesimal interval dl , times the density of probability $p_D^\Omega(l, x, y)$ that a point starting at y , following a killed Brownian motion, will be in the position x at a time l , integrated over all possible values of l . Therefore, the action of subordination introduces a random s -dependent choice of the time in which we consider the classical Dirichlet heat kernel, so that $r_D^s(t, x, y)$ results in a time-weighted superposition of $p_D^\Omega(l, x, y)$.

In Theorems 3.10 and 3.11 we analyze the monotonicity with respect to s of the fractional Dirichlet heat kernel r_D^s on the diagonal, and the monotonicity of the conditional probability in equation (3.47) when $\Omega'' = \Omega'$.

Proof of Theorems 3.10 and 3.11. First we show point (i) of Theorems 3.10 and 3.11. We take the derivative of $r_D^s(t, x, y)$ with respect to s , which gives us

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} r_D^s(t, x, y) &= \frac{d}{ds} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \\ (3.63) \qquad &= -t \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k). \end{aligned}$$

Note that we can differentiate inside the sum thanks to Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4.

Therefore, if we take the integral over $\Omega' \times \Omega'$ of both sides of (3.63) we get

$$(3.64) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx dy &= \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} \frac{d}{ds} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx dy \\ &= -t \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} c_{k, \Omega'}^2 \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k), \end{aligned}$$

where we have defined $c_{k, \Omega'} := \int_{\Omega'} \phi_k(x) dx$. The first identity in (3.64) is a consequence of Proposition 4.27, and Lemma 4.28 in the appendix of Chapter 4, combined with the Dominated Convergence Theorem.

Therefore, if $\lambda_1 \geq 1$, the last term in (3.64) is strictly negative, and this implies (i) of Theorem 3.11.

Moreover, if $x = y \in \Omega$, then from (3.63) we also have that

$$r_D^{s_0}(t, x, x) > r_D^{s_1}(t, x, x),$$

for each $t \in (0, +\infty)$, and $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$, which proves point (i) of Theorem 3.10.

Let us now focus on the proof of point (ii) of Theorems 3.10 and 3.11. If $\lambda_1 < 1$, then from (3.64) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{\exp(t\lambda_1^s)}{t} \left(\frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx dy \right) \\ &= c_{1, \Omega'}^2 \lambda_1^s |\ln(\lambda_1)| - \sum_{k=2}^{+\infty} c_{k, \Omega'}^2 \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k). \end{aligned}$$

Since the first eigenfunction is strictly positive, see for instance [Eva10], recalling also the classical estimates on the Dirichlet eigenvalues (see e.g. equation (4.48) in the appendix of Chapter 4), the above computation yields that $c_{1, \Omega'} > 0$.

We claim that for each $t > 0$ large enough (depending on s and Ω') we get

$$(3.65) \quad \frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx dy > 0.$$

Indeed, using Hölder's inequality and the fact that for each $k \geq 1$ the ϕ_k 's are normalized in $L^2(\Omega)$, we obtain

$$c_{k, \Omega'}^2 = \left(\int_{\Omega'} \phi_k(x) dx \right)^2 \leq \left(\left(\int_{\Omega'} \phi_k(x)^2 dx \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} |\Omega'|^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)^2 \leq |\Omega'|.$$

Thus, we can employ this last inequality to obtain the bound

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\exp(t\lambda_1^s)}{t} \left(\frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_D^s(t, x, y) dx dy \right) \\
 (3.66) \quad & = c_{1, \Omega'}^2 \lambda_1^s |\ln(\lambda_1)| - \sum_{k=2}^{+\infty} c_{k, \Omega'}^2 \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k) \\
 & \geq c_{1, \Omega'}^2 \lambda_1^s |\ln(\lambda_1)| - |\Omega'| \sum_{k=k''}^{+\infty} \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $k'' = \min \{k \geq 1 \text{ s.t. } \lambda_k \geq 1\}$.

Also, thanks to equation (4.48) in the appendix of Chapter 4, we can apply Lemma 7 in that appendix to the last series in (3.66) with $a_k = \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k)$ and $b_k = (\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)$, and deduce that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} |\Omega'| \sum_{k=k''}^{+\infty} \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k) = 0.$$

By combining this limit with the inequality in (3.66) we conclude the proof of the claim in (3.65).

Therefore, as a consequence of (3.65), if we fix $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$, there exists some $T > 0$ depending on s_0, s_1 and Ω' such that for each $t > T$

$$\int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_D^{s_0}(t, x, y) dx dy < \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_D^{s_1}(t, x, y) dx dy.$$

This concludes the proof of point (ii) of Theorem 3.11.

Point (ii) of Theorem 3.10 is proved similarly. To show it, we note that from equation (3.63), we obtain that if $x = y \in \Omega$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\exp(t\lambda_1)}{t} \frac{d}{ds} r_D^s(t, x, x) \\
 & = \phi_1(x)^2 \lambda_1^s |\ln \lambda_1| - \sum_{k=2}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x)^2 \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k).
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, thanks to this last identity and Proposition 4.27 in the appendix of Chapter 4 we deduce the lower bound

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\exp(t\lambda_1)}{t} \frac{d}{ds} r_D^s(t, x, x) \\
 (3.67) \quad & \geq \phi_1(x)^2 \lambda_1^s |\ln \lambda_1| - \sum_{k=k''}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{2\alpha(m_0)} \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $k'' = \min \{k \geq 1 \text{ s.t. } \lambda_k \geq 1\}$.

Therefore, thanks to equation (4.48) in the appendix of Chapter 4, we can apply Lemma 4.29 in that appendix to the last series in (3.67) with $a_k = \lambda_k^{2\alpha(m_0)+s} \ln(\lambda_k)$ and $b_k = (\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)$, and obtain that

$$(3.68) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{k=k''}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{2\alpha(m_0)} \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \lambda_k^s \ln(\lambda_k) = 0.$$

By this limit and (3.67) we prove that for each $t > 0$ large enough, depending on $s \in (0, 1]$ and $x \in \Omega$ we get

$$\frac{d}{ds} r_D^s(t, x, x) > 0.$$

Hence, if we fix some $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ and $x \in \Omega$ there exists some $T' > 0$ depending on s_0, s_1 and x such that for each $t > T'$

$$(3.69) \quad r_D^{s_0}(t, x, x) < r_D^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

This proves point (ii) of Theorem 3.10. □

4

DIFFUSIVE PROCESSES MODELED ON THE SPECTRAL FRACTIONAL LAPLACIAN WITH NEUMANN BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

In this chapter we provide a comprehensive approach to the spectral fractional heat equation that combines purely analytic and probabilistic perspectives.

Furthermore, we give two new results on the monotonicity properties of the spectral fractional heat diffusion with respect to the fractional parameter.

The first result deals with the spectral fractional heat kernel, evaluated at the initial singularity. The second result considers the probability for the corresponding stochastic process of being confined in a subregion of the domain.

In both results, the monotonicity property depends on the size of the first non-zero eigenvalue.

The case of homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions are addressed in detail here. Dirichlet boundary conditions are taken into account in Chapter 3.

4.1 Introduction

In Chapter 3, the following results have been put forth for anomalous diffusion driven by the spectral fractional Laplacian with Dirichlet data:

Theorem 4.1. *If the first non-zero eigenvalue is bigger than or equal to 1, then the fractional heat kernel $r^s(t, x, x)$ is monotone decreasing in s .*

If instead the first non-zero eigenvalue is strictly less than 1, then for every $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ there exists some $T > 0$ such that for each $t > T$

$$r^{s_0}(t, x, x) < r^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

Theorem 4.2. *If the first non-zero eigenvalue is bigger than or equal to 1, then the conditional probability $\mathbb{P}^s(Y_t \in \Omega' | Y_0 \in \Omega')$ is monotone decreasing in s .*

If instead the first non-zero eigenvalue is strictly less than 1, then for every $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ there exists some $T > 0$ such that for each $t > T$

$$\mathbb{P}^{s_0}(Y_t \in \Omega' | Y_0 \in \Omega') < \mathbb{P}^{s_1}(Y_t \in \Omega' | Y_0 \in \Omega').$$

The goal of this chapter is to establish the same results for the Neumann case (in which case, a subscript “ N ” will be added to the notation to stress when the setting is specifically addressing the Neumann boundary conditions).

The plan of this chapter is the following. In Section 4.2 we introduce the precise mathematical framework that will be used throughout this chapter and state the main results that will be proved. Here we define the Neumann spectral fractional heat equation and we state the theorems regarding the existence, regularity and uniqueness of the solution to these systems of equations (see Theorem 4.9). Moreover, we provide a Maximum Principle (see Theorem 4.10).

Then, in Theorem 4.11, we give a precise statement of Theorem 4.1 for the Neumann case and in Theorem 4.12 we rephrase Theorem 4.2 with a detailed probabilistic notation for the Neumann case.

Moreover, in Section 4.3 we introduce the main properties concerning the stochastic process associated with the Neumann kernel r_N^s , which will be called subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion. Section 4.3 is devoted to an analytical approach to the Neumann spectral fractional heat equation (4.8). Here we prove Theorems 4.9 and 4.10, and therefore that the kernel r_N^s is the unique solution to the Neumann spectral fractional heat equation (4.8). The proofs of the original results for the Neumann case (Theorems 4.11 and 4.12) are given in detail in Section 4.3.

The arguments rely also on some basic auxiliary result that are collected, for the facility of the reader, in the appendix of this chapter.

4.2 The Neumann spectral fractional heat equation

Now we deal with the counterpart of the spectral fractional heat equation presented in Section 3.2 of Chapter 3 when the boundary data are of Neumann, rather than Dirichlet, type. Most of the main features are in common between the Dirichlet and the Neumann case, since the functional analysis setting can be efficiently translated from one framework into another. However, for clarity and completeness, we provide explicitly the technical details in the Neumann case as well. For this, we proceed as follows.

We consider an orthonormal basis $\{\psi_k\}_k$ of $L^2(\Omega)$ satisfying

$$(4.1) \quad \begin{cases} -\Delta\psi_k = \mu_k\psi_k & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial\psi_k}{\partial\nu} = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases}$$

where the values $0 = \mu_0 < \mu_1 \leq \mu_2 \leq \mu_3 \dots$ are the eigenvalues of the Laplace operator with a Neumann homogeneous boundary condition. In principle, the boundary condition in (4.1) should be intended in the weak sense (see e.g. page 296 in [Bre11]), but, since the boundary of Ω is assumed to be smooth, the eigenfunctions ψ_k belong to $C^\infty(\bar{\Omega})$ and (4.1) makes sense in the classical case.

Note also that the eigenfunction associated with the eigenvalue μ_0 is just the constant function normalized in $L^2(\Omega)$. If $u(t, x)$ with $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ is such that $u(t, \cdot) \in L^2(\Omega)$, then

$$u(t, x) = \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} u_k(t) \psi_k(x), \quad \text{with} \quad u_k(t) := \int_{\Omega} u(t, y) \psi_k(y) dy.$$

In line with the setting provided in Definition 3.3 of Chapter 3 for the Dirichlet case, we can thus introduce a fractional Neumann framework as follows:

Definition 4.3. Let $s \in (0, 1)$. We define the Neumann spectral fractional Laplacian as

$$(4.2) \quad \begin{aligned} (-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s &: H_N^{2s}(\Omega) \subset L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega) \\ u &\longmapsto (-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s u := \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} u_k \mu_k^s \psi_k, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(4.3) \quad H_N^{2s}(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in L^2(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} u_k^2 \mu_k^{2s} < +\infty \right\}.$$

We observe that the space $H_N^{2s}(\Omega)$ introduced in (4.3) here coincides with the space $H_D^{2s}(\Omega)$ introduced in equation (3.4) of Chapter 3 for the Dirichlet case, except that the weights used here are the Neumann eigenvalues of the Laplacian, instead of the Dirichlet ones.

It is also useful to consider the classical “fundamental solution” of the heat equation with homogeneous Neumann condition, that is the solution of

$$(4.4) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = \Delta u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu}(t, x) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \Omega \end{cases}$$

where $\nu(x)$ is the outward pointing normal to $\partial\Omega$ at the point $x \in \partial\Omega$, and the last equation is meant in the sense of measure. The solution of (4.4) will be denoted by $p_N^\Omega(t, x, y)$ and it is often referred to with the name of *classical Neumann heat kernel in Ω* .

In what follows we denote by

$$W_N^{1,2}(\Omega) := \left\{ f \in W^{1,2}(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } \frac{\partial f}{\partial \nu} = 0 \right\}.$$

Theorem 1.1 and equation (2.4) in [Hsu84] together with Lemma 4.28 in the appendix and Lemma 4.20 in Section 4.3 (with the clarification that the uniqueness in the space $C^1((0, +\infty), W_N^{1,2}(\Omega))$ can be proved with the exact same approach used to show uniqueness for the system of equations (4.8) as stated in Theorem 4.9) give us the following result:

Theorem 4.4. *Let Ω be open, connected, bounded and smooth. Let us define the function*

$$(4.5) \quad \begin{aligned} p_N^\Omega &: (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ (t, x, y) &\mapsto p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) := \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k). \end{aligned}$$

Then, for each $y \in \Omega$ the function $p_N^\Omega(\cdot, \cdot, y)$ is the unique solution to

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = \Delta u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ u(t, x) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \Omega. \end{cases}$$

in $C^1((0, +\infty), W_N^{1,2}(\Omega))$.

Moreover, $p_N^\Omega \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$.

The following Maximum Principle is a straightforward consequence of Theorem 1.2 in [Hsu84].

Theorem 4.5. *Let Ω be open, bounded, connected and with smooth boundary. For each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $(t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ we have that*

$$\min \left\{ 0, \inf_{\Omega} f \right\} \leq \int_{\Omega} p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) f(x) dx \leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}.$$

In agreement with Proposition 3.6, of Chapter 3 for the Dirichlet case, one can give an equivalent definition for the Neumann spectral fractional Laplacian by exploiting an integral operator built via a jumping kernel of Neumann type. The explicit details go as follows:

Proposition 4.6 (See [AV19]). *Let $u \in H_N^{2s}(\Omega)$. Then,*

$$(4.6) \quad (-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s u(x) = P.V. \int_{\Omega} [u(x) - u(y)] J_N(x, y) dy$$

for almost every $x \in \Omega$, where

$$(4.7) \quad J_N(x, y) := \frac{s}{\Gamma(1-s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) \frac{dt}{t^{1+s}}.$$

The right-hand side of (4.6) is well defined for each $x \in \Omega$ if $u \in C_{loc}^{2s+\varepsilon}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ for some $\varepsilon > 0$.

The function in (4.7) is called *Neumann jumping kernel*.

Remark 4.7. An interesting structural difference between equation (3.8) in Chapter 3 and equation (4.6) here consists in the fact that the latter does not present

any additional zero order term (equivalently, the Neumann type “killing measure” vanishes identically). Indeed, suppose that there exists some $k : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that for each $u \in H_N^{2s}(\Omega)$ one has

$$(-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s u(x) = \int_{\Omega} [u(x) - u(y)] J_N(x, y) dy + k(x) u(x)$$

for almost $x \in \Omega$. Then, since $1 \in H_N^{2s}(\Omega)$, we would have thanks to (4.2) that

$$0 = (-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s 1(x) = \int_{\Omega} (1 - 1) J_N(x, y) dy + k(x) = 0 + k(x).$$

Moreover, one obtains the following Maximum Principle for the Neumann spectral fractional Laplacian, which can be seen as the Neumann counterpart of Lemma 3.7 in Chapter 3:

Lemma 4.8. *Let $\varepsilon > 0$, $u \in C_{loc}^{2s+\varepsilon}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ be non-constant and $x^* \in \Omega$ such that $u(x^*) = \inf_{\Omega} u(x)$. Then it holds that*

$$(-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s u(x^*) < 0.$$

Now, for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $y \in \Omega$, we consider the *Neumann spectral fractional heat equation* starting at y , which reads as

$$(4.8) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu}(t, x) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, x) = \delta_y(x) & \text{for all } x \in \Omega. \end{cases}$$

As customary, the last equation is meant in the sense of measure, see equation (3.12) in Chapter 3. In Section 4.3 we will establish the following two basic results:

Theorem 4.9 (Existence, Uniqueness and Regularity of the solution to (4.8)). *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, connected and with smooth boundary. If we set*

$$(4.9) \quad \begin{aligned} r_N^s : (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ (t, x, y) &\mapsto r_N^s(t, x, y) := \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k^s). \end{aligned}$$

then for each $y \in \Omega$ the function $r_N^s(\cdot, \cdot, y)$ is the unique solution to (4.8) in $C^1((0, +\infty), H_N^{2s}(\Omega))$. Moreover, $r_N^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega} \times \bar{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$.

We call r_N^s the *Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel*.

Theorem 4.10 (Maximum Principle). *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, connected and with smooth boundary. For each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $(t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ we have that*

$$(4.10) \quad \min \left\{ 0, \inf_{\Omega} f \right\} \leq \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx \leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}.$$

Later on (see Theorem 4.15 and Proposition 4.17) we will also prove that $r_N^s(\cdot, \cdot, y)$ is the *transition density* of the aforementioned subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion, which will be denoted by

$$Y_{N,y}^{\Omega} = (\mathfrak{G}, \{\mathcal{P}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P}, \{Y_{N,t}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_{N,y}^s)$$

A detailed presentation of this stochastic process is contained in Section 4.3. In this setting, $r_N^s(t, x, y)$ represents the density of probability that the process starting at $y \in \Omega$ will occupy the position $x \in \Omega$ at a time $t > 0$. Therefore, the probability $\mathbb{P}_{N,y}^s$ of finding the process $Y_{N,t}^{\Omega}$ starting at $y \in \Omega$ in some subset $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ at a time $t \in (0, +\infty)$ is

$$(4.11) \quad \mathbb{P}_{N,y}^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega') := \int_{\Omega'} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx.$$

Additionally (see Lemma 4.22) we will establish that the transition density $r_N^s(t, \cdot, y)$ has $L^1(\Omega)$ -norm that is constantly equal to 1 for each t (and $y \in \Omega$). This property is in agreement with the fact that the process, once it reaches the boundary of Ω , gets reflected. Indeed, this reflection property encodes the main difference between the killed motion, corresponding to an equation with homogeneous Dirichlet boundary data, and the reflected motion, which produces a homogeneous Neumann condition.

We now showcase two results which can be seen as the counterpart of Theorems 3.10 and 3.11 in Chapter 3 for the Neumann case that we treat here. To this end, assuming that a starting point $y \in \Omega$ is chosen uniformly in Ω , one defines the conditional probability

$$(4.12) \quad \mathbb{P}_N^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega'' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega') = \frac{1}{|\Omega'|} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega''} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy,$$

for each $\Omega', \Omega'' \subset \Omega$, where Ω' has positive measure. Note that $\mathbb{P}^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega'' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega')$ is the probability of being in the set Ω'' at a time $t > 0$ starting from a set Ω' at $t = 0$ and following the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion.

Given $\Omega' \subset \Omega$, we also define $\mu_{k(\Omega')}$ as the first non-zero eigenvalue associated with an eigenfunction satisfying

$$(4.13) \quad \int_{\Omega'} \psi_k(x) dx \neq 0.$$

Moreover, for each $x \in \Omega$ we denote with $\mu_{k(x)}$ the first non-zero eigenvalue associated with an eigenfunction satisfying

$$(4.14) \quad \psi_k(x) \neq 0.$$

The existence of $\mu_{k(\Omega')}$ and $\mu_{k(x)}$ is straightforward (see Proposition 4.26 for details). With this notation, we have the following two results, which will be proven in Section 4.3:

Theorem 4.11. *Let $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$ and $x \in \Omega$.*

(i) *If $\mu_{k(x)} \geq 1$, then for each $t > 0$ it holds*

$$(4.15) \quad r_N^{s_0}(t, x, x) > r_N^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

(ii) *If $\mu_{k(x)} < 1$, then there exists some $T > 0$, depending on s_0, s_1 and x , such that for each $t > T$*

$$(4.16) \quad r_N^{s_0}(t, x, x) < r_N^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

Theorem 4.12. *Let $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$, $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ measurable with positive measure.*

(i) *If $\mu_{k(\Omega')} \geq 1$, then for each $t > 0$ we have*

$$(4.17) \quad \mathbb{P}_N^{s_0}(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega') > \mathbb{P}_N^{s_1}(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega').$$

(ii) *If $\mu_{k(\Omega')} < 1$, then there exists some $T > 0$, depending on s_0, s_1 and Ω' , such that for each $t > T$*

$$(4.18) \quad \mathbb{P}_N^{s_0}(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega') < \mathbb{P}_N^{s_1}(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega').$$

Similarly to Theorems 3.10 and 3.11 in Chapter 3, also Theorems 4.11 and 4.12 here relate the local behavior of the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion to the geometry of the domain, through the Neumann eigenvalues. However, differently from the Dirichlet case, the first eigenfunction μ_0 does not play any role in Theorems 4.11 and 4.12 concerning the behavior of $\mathbb{P}^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega')$ in relation to s , since obviously $\mu_0 = 0$ and therefore a finer investigation is needed. Interestingly, as stated in Theorems 4.11 and 4.12, the essential ingredient in this setting becomes the first eigenvalue μ_k with $k \neq 0$ whose corresponding eigenfunction has either non-zero average in Ω' (as detailed in (4.13), corresponding to the statement in Theorem 4.11) or non-zero value at the point (as specified in (4.14), in correspondence with Theorem 4.12).

We stress that, by construction, in (4.13) and (4.14) we have that $k(\Omega') \geq 1$ and $k(x) \geq 1$, respectively. Therefore, $\mu_1 \leq \mu_{k(\Omega')}$ and $\mu_1 \leq \mu_{k(x)}$. Accordingly, if $\mu_1 \geq 1$ we get that also $\mu_{k(\Omega')} \geq 1$ and $\mu_{k(x)} \geq 1$. For this reason, a simple consequence of Theorems 4.11 and 4.12 is that if $\mu_1 \geq 1$ then the monotonicity claims with respect to the fractional parameter stated in (4.15) and (4.17) hold true.

It is therefore desirable to have explicit lower bounds on μ_1 in order to conveniently apply point (i) in Theorems 4.11 and 4.12. To this end, we recall that, if Ω is convex, one has that

$$\mu_1 \geq \frac{\pi^2}{\delta^2},$$

where we have denoted by

$$\delta := \max_{x,y \in \partial\Omega} |x - y|,$$

see [PW60, equation (1.9)]. Thus, if Ω is convex and its diameter δ is smaller than π , it follows that $\mu_{k(x)}, \mu_{k(\Omega')} \geq 1$, which in turns gives the validity of (4.15) and (4.17).

When $\mu_1 < 1$, it could still be possible that (4.15) and (4.17) hold true and therefore in this case a finer analysis is needed to detect the size of $\mu_{k(\Omega')}$ and $\mu_{k(x)}$ respectively. To this end, we recall (see [Krö92]) that, for all $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$,

$$\mu_k \leq \left(\frac{n+2}{2} \right)^{\frac{2}{n}} \frac{4\pi^2 k^{2/n}}{(v_n |\Omega|)^{\frac{2}{n}}},$$

where v_n is the Lebesgue measure of the unit ball in \mathbb{R}^n . In particular, if the measure of Ω is large enough with respect to either $k(x)$ or $k(\Omega)$, one can deduce from the above inequality that either $\mu_{k(x)} < 1$ or $\mu_{k(\Omega)} < 1$, which permits to conclude that point (ii) in either Theorem 4.11 and 4.12 hold true in this case.

4.3 The spectral fractional heat equation with Neumann boundary conditions

In this section we provide an analytical and probabilistic exposition on the Neumann spectral fractional heat equation (4.8).

Section 4.3 is dedicated to the introduction of the stochastic process called the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion. We show that the transition density of this process is the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel r_N^s given in equation (4.9).

In Section 4.3 we propose an analytical study of the solution to the system of equations (4.8). Specifically, we prove Theorems 4.9 and 4.10. The first result states that the unique solution to (4.8) is the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel r_N^s , while Theorem 4.10 is a Maximum Principle for the spectral fractional heat equation with Neumann boundary conditions.

Section 4.3 consists in the proof of the original Theorems 4.11 and 4.12. These results provide some insight on the monotonicity properties (with respect to the parameter s) of the Neumann heat kernel r_N^s and the conditional probability introduced in equation (4.12).

From the standard reflecting Brownian motion to the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion

In this section, through a suitable modification of the setting introduced in Section 3.3 of Chapter 3, we will construct the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion. This stochastic process is obtained by starting from the standard reflecting Brownian motion via the introduction of a random choice of time. This type of procedure belongs to a class of operations between Markov processes which takes

the name of subordination (see [Boc49]). We give a more detailed presentation on the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion in Theorem 4.15 below. More precisely, in Theorem 4.15 and Proposition 4.17 we will show that the transition density associated with this stochastic process is the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel r_N^s given in equation (4.9).

We now briefly recall the main properties of the standard reflecting Brownian motion. There are different ways of defining a standard reflecting Brownian motion, and they all lead to the same Markov process. There exists a broad literature treating this problem, see e.g. [LS84; Fuk67; BH90; DI08]. In this chapter we will follow the more analytic approach to define this stochastic process, namely by first constructing a transition density starting from a system of parabolic PDEs. In particular the main definitions and procedures here follow [Hsu84]. We now reconsider the Neumann heat kernel $p_N^\Omega(t, x, y)$ introduced in (4.5). As stated in Theorem 4.4, we can write the heat kernel as the $L^2(\Omega)$ expansion in eigenfunctions

$$(4.19) \quad p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) = \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k).$$

Let us denote by $\mathfrak{S} = C([0, +\infty), \Omega)$. Then, we have the following result (see [Hsu84]).

Theorem 4.13. *Let $y \in \Omega$.*

There exists a Markov process $X_N^\Omega = (\mathfrak{S}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}_t, \{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_y)$ such that for each $t > 0$ and $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ it holds

$$(4.20) \quad \mathbb{P}_y(X_t \in \Omega') = \int_{\Omega'} p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) dx.$$

Definition 4.14. *Let $y \in \Omega$.*

A stochastic process $X_{N,y}^\Omega = (\mathfrak{S}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{F}_t, \{X_t^\Omega\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_y)$ is defined as a standard reflecting Brownian motion starting at $y \in \Omega$ if its transition density satisfies the equations in (4.4).

In view of Theorem 4.13, the semigroup N_t associated with $X_{N,x}$ is

$$N_t f(x) := \int_{\Omega} p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) f(y) dy = \mathbb{E}_x[f(X_t^\Omega)],$$

for each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$. Therefore, the *generator* of the standard reflecting Brownian motion coincides with Neumann Laplacian, namely

$$\frac{d}{dt} N_t f|_{t=0} = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{N_t f - f}{t} = \Delta_{N,\Omega} f,$$

for each $f \in W_N^{1,2}(\Omega)$.

We observe (see [Hsu84]) that for each $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$

$$(4.21) \quad \mathbb{P}_y(X_t \in \Omega) = \int_{\Omega} p_N^{\Omega}(t, x, y) dy = 1.$$

We mention that this is a consequence of the fact that the first eigenvalue of the Neumann Laplacian is zero. In particular, the identity in (4.21) highlights the fact that the process is restricted to Ω and cannot escape the domain. Note that this is in contrast with the behavior of the killed Brownian motion, which was instead eventually doomed to be confined in the cemetery ∂ (see equation (3.30) in Chapter 3).

In the following result we build the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion, by introducing in the previously discussed standard reflecting Brownian motion a random choice of the time. More specifically, we will assume that such a choice follows the motion of a s -stable subordinator (see Definition 3.17 in Chapter 3). The proof of the next result is analogous to the one of Theorem 3.19 in Chapter 3 and therefore will be omitted.

Theorem 4.15. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, $S = (\mathfrak{G}_1, \mathcal{G}, \{S_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s)$ be an s -stable subordinator and $X_{N,x} := (\mathfrak{G}, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \{X_t^{\Omega}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_x)$ be a standard reflecting Brownian motion as in Definition 4.14. Let us define the family of stochastic processes*

$$(4.22) \quad Y_N^{\Omega} := (\mathfrak{G} \times \mathfrak{G}_1, \{\mathcal{F}_t \times \mathcal{G}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{G}, \{Y_{N,t}\}_{t \geq 0}, \{\mathbb{P}_{N,y}^s\}_{y \in \Omega})$$

and $Y_{N,t}(\omega, \omega_1) := X_{S_t(\omega_1)}(\omega)$

where $\mathbb{P}_{N,y}^s := \mathbb{P}_y \times \tilde{\mathbb{P}}^s$. Then, for each $x \in \Omega$ the stochastic process $Y_{N,x}^{\Omega}$ is a Markov process. Moreover, for each Lebesgue measurable set $\Omega' \subset \Omega$,

$$(4.23) \quad \mathbb{P}_{N,y}^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega') = \int_{\Omega'} \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^{\Omega}(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(dl) dy.$$

Definition 4.16 (Subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion). For each $x \in \Omega$, the process

$$Y_{N,x}^\Omega := (\mathfrak{G} \times \mathfrak{G}_1, \{\mathcal{F}_t \times \mathcal{G}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{G}, \{Y_{N,t}\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathbb{P}_{N,x}^s)$$

defined in Theorem 4.15 is called *subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion* starting at x .

Now we show that the transition density of the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion coincides with the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel r_N^s defined in equation (4.9).

Proposition 4.17. *Let $r_N^s : (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be as in equation (4.9). Then,*

$$(4.24) \quad r_N^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(dl) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

Proof. Thanks to Theorem 4.4 we have that

$$p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) = \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k).$$

Also,

$$\tilde{\mathbb{E}}^s[\exp(-\lambda S_t)] := \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-x\lambda) \mu_t^s(dx) = \exp(-t\lambda^s),$$

see equation (3.32) in Chapter 3.

Hence, we conclude that

$$(4.25) \quad \begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, t) \mu_t^s(dl) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-l\mu_k) \mu_t^s(dl) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-l\mu_k) \mu_t^s(dl) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \\ &= r_N^s(t, x, y). \end{aligned}$$

The identity between the first and second line in (4.25) is guaranteed by the Dominated Convergence Theorem, which can be applied thanks to Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28. □

Thanks to Theorem 4.15 and Proposition 4.17, the transition density associated with the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion is the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel r_N^s given in equation (4.9). Hence, we can consider the probability function

$$\mathbb{P}_{N,x}^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega') = \int_{\Omega'} r_N^s(t, x, y) dy.$$

Similarly to what we have done in Section 3.3 of Chapter 3, we can also take into account the conditional probability

$$(4.26) \quad \mathbb{P}_N^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega' | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega'') := \frac{1}{|\Omega''|} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega''} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy.$$

Note that in this case the state space coincide with Ω , and thus $\mathbb{P}^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega | Y_{N,0} \in \Omega'') = 1$ for each $t > 0$. This last observation follows from the fact that for each $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$

$$\mathbb{P}_{N,x}^s(Y_{N,t} \in \Omega) = \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, x, y) dy = 1,$$

thanks to (4.21) and (4.24). An alternative analytical proof of this fact will be given in Lemma 4.22.

Another consequence of Theorem 4.15 and Proposition 4.17 is the following result on the continuity of the semigroup associated to the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion Y_N^Ω .

Proposition 4.18. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Y_N^Ω as in Definition 4.16. For each $t > 0$ the semigroup associated with Y_N^Ω*

$$(4.27) \quad \begin{aligned} Q_t : L^2(\Omega) &\rightarrow L^2(\Omega) \\ f &\mapsto Q_t f(x) := \int_{\Omega} f(y) r_N^s(t, x, y) dy, \end{aligned}$$

satisfies

$$\|Q_t f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}.$$

In Proposition 3.24 of Chapter 3 we established that the generator associated with the subordinate killed Brownian motion is the Dirichlet spectral fractional

Laplacian. The next result provides the corresponding property for the subordinate standard reflecting Brownian motion, namely that the Neumann spectral fractional Laplacian $(-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s$ in (4.2) is the generator of Y_N^Ω . Since the proof of this fact is similar to the one of Proposition 3.24 of Chapter 3, we omit it.

Proposition 4.19. *The generator of the process Y_N^Ω is given by the spectral fractional Laplacian with Neumann boundary conditions. Namely for each $f \in H_N^{2s}(\Omega)$ the following limit holds*

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{Q_t f - f}{t} = -(-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s f$$

where the convergence is meant in $L^2(\Omega)$.

Existence, Uniqueness and Maximum Principle for the Neumann spectral fractional heat equation

Now we state the main auxiliary results that lead to Theorems 4.9 and 4.10, on the existence, uniqueness and regularity of the solution to the Neumann spectral fractional heat equation (4.8) and on the Maximum Principle for its solution. The procedure to prove these results is the same that we used in Section 3.3 of Chapter 3 for the Dirichlet case. For this reason most of the proof will be omitted.

Thus, taking the same steps of Section 3.3 of Chapter 3 we begin this discussion by establishing the following regularity result for the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel r_N^s given in equation (4.9).

Lemma 4.20. *Let $s \in (0, 1]$ and Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected. Then, $r_N^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \overline{\Omega} \times \overline{\Omega})$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$.*

In the following result we state that the Neumann kernel r_N^s is a solution to the first and second equation in (4.8).

Lemma 4.21. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected. Then, for each $y \in \Omega$ the function $r_{N,y}^s(t, x) := r_N^s(t, x, y)$ is a solution to the first and second equation in (4.8).*

We now prove that the Neumann Kernel r_N^s has unit mass.

Lemma 4.22. *Let $s \in (0, 1]$ and Ω be open, bounded, smooth and connected. Then for each $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ it holds*

$$(4.28) \quad \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, x, y) dy = 1.$$

Proof. Using Lemma 4.20, Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28, together with the integration by parts formula, we deduce that for each $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, x, y) dy &= \frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) dy \\ &= - \int_{\Omega} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \mu_k^s \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \int_{\Omega} -\mu_k^s \psi_k(y) dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \int_{\Omega} \Delta \psi_k(y) dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \int_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial \nu}(y) dH_y^{n-1}(y) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, one easily observes that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, x, y) dy = \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{|\Omega|} + \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) dy = 1,$$

as desired. □

For completeness, we mention that an alternative approach to establish (4.28) relies on the probabilistic framework previously developed, using equation (4.21) and equation (4.24), which allow one to write r_N^s as a time weighted superposition of the classical Neumann heat kernel p_N^{Ω} . The computation provided above instead does not make use of the probabilistic setting, but relies on the fact that the first eigenvalue of $(-\Delta)_{N,\Omega}^s$ is vanishing.

Now we remark that a result in the spirit of Lemma 3.27 of Chapter 3 holds true in the Neumann case as well, thus providing the existence, uniqueness and regularity

of the solution to the Neumann spectral fractional heat equation with initial datum $f \in L^2(\Omega)$. This result, which is showcased here below, will be employed in this chapter to prove a Maximum Principle in the Neumann framework. Moreover, the uniform continuity with respect to the initial datum will be used to prove that r_N^s satisfies also third equation in (4.8), in analogy with what we already did for the Dirichlet case.

Lemma 4.23. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be open, bounded smooth and connected. For each $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ the function $Q_t f$ defined in (4.27) is the unique solution in $C([0, +\infty), L^2(\Omega)) \cap C^1((0, +\infty), H_N^{2s}(\Omega))$ to the system of equations*

$$(4.29) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, y) = -(-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s u(t, y) & \text{for all } (t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu}(t, y) = 0 & \text{for all } (t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \partial\Omega, \\ u(0, y) = f(y) & \text{for all } y \in \Omega. \end{cases}$$

The last equation in (4.29) is meant as

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \|u(t, y) - f(y)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = 0.$$

Furthermore, for each $\varepsilon > 0$, it holds that $Q_t f(y) \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega})$. Moreover, if $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$, then

$$(4.30) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \|Q_t f(y) - f(y)\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} = 0.$$

Below we give a proof of the Maximum Principle in the Neumann setting that was stated in Theorem 4.10. The argument that we present here can be seen as a natural modification of the analytic proof that we provided in the case of Dirichlet boundary conditions.

Alternatively, one can also obtain this Maximum Principle by using the probabilistic framework previously developed, relying on the Maximum Principle for the classical Neumann heat equation (this approach is developed in Appendix 4.4 for the Dirichlet case, but the Neumann case can be treated similarly).

Proof of Theorem 4.10. We prove the right-hand side inequality in (4.10). First we assume that $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$, since the general case of $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ will be addressed below using an approximation argument. Thanks to Lemma 4.23 we know that

$Q_t f(y) =: f(t, y) \in C([0, +\infty) \times \bar{\Omega}) \cap C^\infty((0, +\infty) \times \Omega)$. Let $K := \max\{0, \sup_\Omega f\}$ and assume, by contradiction, that there exists $(t^*, y^*) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ such that

$$f(t^*, y^*) > K.$$

We define the function $W(t, y) := f(t^*, y^*) - \varepsilon - f(t, y)$, where ε is such that

$$\varepsilon < \inf_\Omega (f(t^*, y^*) - f(x)).$$

Applying the same reasoning as in proof of Theorem 3.9 in Chapter 3, we obtain the existence of $(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} W(t, y) &> 0 \quad \text{for all } (t, y) \in [0, \tilde{t}) \times \Omega, \\ W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) &= 0 \quad \text{and} \quad W(\tilde{t}, y) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in \Omega. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, this means that

$$\partial_t W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \leq 0.$$

We note that $W(\tilde{t}, \cdot)$ cannot identically vanish in Ω . Indeed, $W(t, y) = f(t^*, y^*) - \varepsilon - f(t, y)$, and $f(t, y)$ cannot be constant unless its initial data f is, as one can easily infer from the $L^2(\Omega)$ decomposition of $f(t, y)$ in eigenfunctions. Therefore, since \tilde{y} is a minimum for $W(\tilde{t}, \cdot)$, Lemma 4.8 gives us that

$$(-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) < 0.$$

Therefore

$$\partial_t W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) + (-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) < 0.$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) + (-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s W(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) & \\ &= -\partial_t f(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) + (-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s (f(t^*, y^*) - \varepsilon) - (-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s f(\tilde{t}, \tilde{y}) \\ &= (-\Delta)_{N, \Omega}^s (f(t^*, y^*) - \varepsilon) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

providing a contradiction. Therefore we have proved the right-hand side inequality in (4.10) for each solution with initial condition smooth with compact support. The left-hand side inequality is proved similarly.

With the same procedure followed in the proof of Theorem 3.9 in Chapter 3, one can show that also $r_N^s(t, x, y) \geq 0$ for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$.

If $f \in L^2(\Omega)$, according to equation (4.28) we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, y) &= \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx \\ &\leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\} \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx = \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

which proves the right-hand side of (4.10) when $f \in L^2(\Omega)$. Similarly we also obtain the left-hand side inequality in (4.10). \square

The following result is the analogue of Corollary 3.28 in Chapter 3 for the Neumann kernel r_N^s .

Corollary 4.24. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be bounded, smooth and connected. Then, for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$ it holds that*

$$r_N^s(t, x, y) > 0.$$

While a modification of the proof of Corollary 3.28 in Chapter 3 would produce a purely analytical argument to establish Corollary 4.24, for completeness we also note that the proof of this result can be alternatively achieved by using equation (4.24) and the strict positivity of the classical Neumann kernel p_N^Ω (see [Hsu84]).

As a consequence of Corollary 4.24 we have the following result:

Corollary 4.25. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected. Then,*

$$\begin{aligned} Q_t : C_0(\Omega) &\rightarrow C(\overline{\Omega}) \\ f &\mapsto Q_t f \end{aligned}$$

satisfies

$$\|Q_t f\|_{C(\overline{\Omega})} \leq \|f\|_{C_0(\Omega)}.$$

Now we prove Theorem 4.9.

Proof of Theorem 4.9. In Lemma 4.20 we have already stated that $r_N^s \in C^\infty([\varepsilon, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega)$ for each $\varepsilon > 0$, while in Lemma 4.21 we showed that $r_{N,y}^s(t, x) := r_N^s(t, x, y)$ satisfies the first and second equation in (4.8) for each $y \in \Omega$.

It remains to prove that $r_{N,y}^s$ satisfies the third equation and that such a solution is unique in the space $C^1((0, +\infty); H_N^{2s}(\Omega))$. One can obtain that $r_N^s \in C^1((0, +\infty); H_N^{2s}(\Omega))$ proceeding analogously to the Dirichlet case.

Using Proposition 4.18 and Corollary 4.25, one can show that, if $f \in C_0(\Omega)$, then

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} Q_t f(y) = f(y)$$

for each $y \in \Omega$. Therefore, we have showed that $r_{N,y}^s$ is a solution to (4.8) for each $y \in \Omega$. The proof of the uniqueness statement is analogous to the one in the Dirichlet case. \square

Proof of Theorems 4.11 and 4.12

Here we give the proof of Theorems 4.11 and 4.12 related to the monotonicity properties, with respect to the fractional parameter of subordination s , of the Neumann heat kernel r_N^s and of the conditional probability in equation (4.26). To prove these results, we account for the effects of subordination on the standard reflecting Brownian motion from a probabilistic point of view, in dependence of the geometric properties of the domain Ω encoded by the first non-trivial eigenvalue of the Neumann Laplacian.

To prove Theorems 4.11 and 4.12 we also rely on the following ancillary result:

Proposition 4.26. *Let $\Omega' \subset \Omega$ with positive measure, and $x \in \Omega$. Then, the eigenvalues $\mu_{k(\Omega')}$ and $\mu_{k(x)}$ defined respectively in (4.13) and (4.14) exist.*

Proof. We argue by contradiction. Suppose that for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k \geq 1$ we have that

$$\int_{\Omega'} \psi_k(x) dx = 0,$$

and let $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ such that $f \geq 0$ and $f = 0$ in Ω' . In view of Proposition 4.30 the Fourier series in eigenfunctions of a smooth and compactly supported function converges uniformly. Then we see that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \int_{\Omega'} f(y) dy = \int_{\Omega'} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f_k \psi_k(y) dy = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f_k \int_{\Omega'} \psi_k(y) dy \\ &= f_0 \frac{|\Omega'|}{|\Omega|^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \left(\frac{1}{|\Omega|^{\frac{1}{2}}} \int_{\Omega} f(y) dy \right) \frac{|\Omega'|}{|\Omega|^{\frac{1}{2}}} \neq 0, \end{aligned}$$

which provides a contradiction.

Similarly, suppose that for each $k \geq 1$ one has that

$$\psi_k(x) = 0,$$

and take $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ such that $f(x) = 0$ and $f \geq 0$. Then,

$$0 = f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f_k \psi_k(x) = f_0 \psi_0 = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \int_{\Omega} f(y) dy \neq 0,$$

which provides a contradiction. □

Proof of Theorems 4.11 and 4.12. Let us first prove point (i) of Theorem 4.11. We take the derivative of $r_N^s(t, x, y)$ with respect to s and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} r_N^s(t, x, y) &= \frac{d}{ds} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \\ (4.31) \qquad \qquad \qquad &= -t \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x) \psi_k(y) \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k). \end{aligned}$$

Note that we can differentiate with respect to s inside the sum thanks to Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28. Let us assume $x = y \in \Omega$, and let $\mu_{k(x)}$ be defined as in equation (4.14). Then, from (4.31) we deduce that if $\mu_{k(x)} \geq 1$, then all the terms in the sum are positive. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} r_N^s(t, x, y) &= \frac{d}{ds} \sum_{k=k(x)}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x)^2 \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \\ &= -t \sum_{k=k(x)}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x)^2 \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k) < 0, \end{aligned}$$

which proves point (i) in Theorem 4.11. Similarly, if we take the integral over $\Omega' \times \Omega'$ of both sides of (4.31), with Ω' as in the statement of Theorem 4.12, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy &= \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} \frac{d}{ds} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy \\ (4.32) \qquad \qquad \qquad &= -t \sum_{k=k(\Omega')}^{+\infty} c_{k, \Omega'}^2 \exp(-t\mu_k^s) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k), \end{aligned}$$

where we have defined $c_{k,\Omega'} := \int_{\Omega'} \psi_k(x) dx$, and $k(\Omega')$ is the index of the eigenvalue $\mu_{k(\Omega')}$ defined in (4.13). Therefore, if $\mu_{k(\Omega')} \geq 1$, the right-hand side of (4.32) is strictly negative, which proves point (i) of Theorem 4.12.

We prove now point (ii) of Theorems 4.11 and 4.12. If $\mu_{k(\Omega')} < 1$, from (4.32) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 (4.33) \quad & \frac{\exp\left(t\mu_{k(\Omega')}^s\right)}{t} \left(\frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy \right) \\
 & = c_{k(\Omega'),\Omega'}^2 \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s |\ln(\mu_{k(\Omega')})| \\
 & \quad - \sum_{k=k(\Omega')+1}^{+\infty} c_{k,\Omega'}^2 \exp(-t(\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s)) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k).
 \end{aligned}$$

We claim that for each $t \in (0, +\infty)$ large enough (depending on s and Ω') one has

$$(4.34) \quad \frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy > 0.$$

Indeed, using Hölder's inequality and the fact that ψ_k 's are normalized in $L^2(\Omega)$ we observe that

$$(4.35) \quad c_{k,\Omega'}^2 = \left(\int_{\Omega'} \psi_k(x) dx \right)^2 \leq \left(\left(\int_{\Omega'} \psi_k(x)^2 dx \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} |\Omega'|^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)^2 \leq |\Omega'|.$$

Thus from this latter inequality and (4.33) we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (4.36) \quad & \frac{\exp\left(t\mu_{k(\Omega')}^s\right)}{t} \left(\frac{d}{ds} \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy \right) \\
 & \geq c_{k(\Omega'),\Omega'}^2 \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s |\ln(\mu_{k(\Omega')})| \\
 & \quad - |\Omega'| \sum_{k=k(\Omega')+1}^{+\infty} \exp(-t(\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s)) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k) \\
 & \geq c_{k(\Omega'),\Omega'}^2 \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s |\ln(\mu_{k(\Omega')})| \\
 & \quad - |\Omega'| \sum_{k=k''}^{\infty} \exp(-t(\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s)) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $k'' = \min \{k \in \mathbb{N} \text{ s.t. } \mu_k \geq 1\}$.

Also, thanks to the classical estimates on the Neumann eigenvalues (see e.g. the second line in (4.48)), we can apply Lemma 4.29 to the last series in (4.36) with $a_k = \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k)$ and $b_k = (\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s)$. In this way, we obtain that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} |\Omega'| \sum_{k=k''}^{+\infty} \exp(-t(\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(\Omega')}^s)) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k) = 0.$$

By combining this limit with the inequality in (4.36) we conclude the proof of the claim in (4.34).

Now, given $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$, we deduce from inequality (4.34) that there exists some $T > 0$ depending on s_0, s_1 and Ω' such that for each $t > T$

$$\int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_N^{s_0}(t, x, y) dx dy < \int_{\Omega' \times \Omega'} r_N^{s_1}(t, x, y) dx dy.$$

This concludes the proof of point (ii) of Theorem 4.12.

Analogously, from (4.31) one obtains that, if $x = y \in \Omega$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\exp(t\mu_{k(x)}^s)}{t} \left(\frac{d}{ds} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy \right) \\ &= \psi_{k(x)}(x)^2 \mu_{k(x)}^s |\ln(\mu_{k(x)})| \\ & \quad - \sum_{k=k(x)+1}^{+\infty} \psi_k(x)^2 \exp(-t(\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(x)}^s)) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k). \end{aligned}$$

We claim that for each $t > 0$ large enough (depending on x and s) it holds that

$$(4.37) \quad \frac{d}{ds} r_N^s(t, x, x) > 0.$$

Indeed, thanks to Proposition 4.27 and this latter inequality we obtain that

$$(4.38) \quad \begin{aligned} & \frac{\exp(t\mu_{k(x)}^s)}{t} \left(\frac{d}{ds} r_N^s(t, x, y) dx dy \right) \\ & \geq \psi_{k(x)}(x)^2 \mu_{k(x)}^s |\ln(\mu_{k(x)})| - \sum_{k=k''}^{+\infty} \mu_k^{2\alpha(m_0)} \exp(-t(\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(x)}^s)) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k), \end{aligned}$$

where $k'' = \min \{k \in \mathbb{N} \text{ s.t. } \mu_k \geq 1\}$. Using the the second line in (4.48), we are in the position of applying Lemma 4.29 to the last series in (4.38) with $a_k = \mu_k^{2\alpha(m_0)+s} \ln(\mu_k)$ and $b_k = (\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(x)}^s)$, proving thus that

$$(4.39) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{k=k''}^{+\infty} \mu_k^{2\alpha(m_0)} \exp(-t(\mu_k^s - \mu_{k(x)}^s)) \mu_k^s \ln(\mu_k) = 0.$$

This limit and the lower bound in (4.38) yield to the claim in (4.37). Hence if $0 < s_0 < s_1 \leq 1$, there exists some $T' > 0$ depending on s_0, s_1 and x such that

$$r_N^{s_0}(t, x, x) < r_N^{s_1}(t, x, x)$$

for each $t > T'$. This concludes the proof of point (ii) of Theorem 4.11. \square

4.4 Appendices

Auxiliary and technical results

Proposition 4.27. *Let $k \geq 1$ and $\{\phi_k\}_k$ be such that*

$$(4.40) \quad \begin{cases} -\Delta \phi_k = \lambda_k \phi_k & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \phi_k \in H_0^1(\Omega). \end{cases}$$

Let also $\{\psi_k\}_k$ be such that

$$(4.41) \quad \begin{cases} -\Delta \psi_k = \mu_k \psi_k & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial \psi_k}{\partial \nu} = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases}$$

Then, for each $r \in \mathbb{N}$, we have that

$$(4.42) \quad \begin{aligned} & \|\phi_k\|_{C^r(\bar{\Omega})} \leq c_{m_r, \Omega, r} \lambda_k^{\alpha(m_r)} \\ \text{and} \quad & \|\psi_k\|_{C^r(\bar{\Omega})} \leq \tilde{c}_{m_r, \Omega, r} \mu_k^{\alpha(m_r)}, \end{aligned}$$

where $c_{m_r, \Omega, r}, \tilde{c}_{m_r, \Omega, r}$ are positive constants depending on m_r, r and Ω .

Also, here above we have used the notation

$$\alpha(m) := \begin{cases} \frac{m}{2} + 1 & \text{if } m \text{ is even,} \\ \left[\frac{m}{2} \right] + \frac{3}{2} & \text{if } m \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

and

$$m_r := \begin{cases} \left[\frac{n+2r-4}{2} \right] + 1 & \text{if } n+2r-4 \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. We apply the elliptic estimate (77) at page 323 of [Eva10] to the eigenfunctions ϕ_k 's and get

$$(4.43) \quad \|\phi_k\|_{H^{2+m}(\Omega)} \leq c_{m,\Omega} \lambda_k \|\phi_k\|_{H^m(\Omega)} \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N},$$

where $c_{m,\Omega} > 0$ is a constant depending on m and on the domain Ω . We also observe that

$$(4.44) \quad \|\phi_k\|_{H_0^1(\Omega)}^2 := \int_{\Omega} |\nabla \phi_k|^2 dx = - \int_{\Omega} \Delta \phi_k \phi_k dx = \lambda_k \int_{\Omega} |\phi_k|^2 dx = \lambda_k,$$

where we have used the fact that the ϕ_k 's are eigenfunctions of the Laplacian, and that they are normalized in $L^2(\Omega)$. Applying iteratively inequality (4.43), we see that if $m = 2n_0$ for some $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$, then

$$(4.45) \quad \|\phi_k\|_{H^{2+m}(\Omega)} \leq C_{m,\Omega} \lambda_k^{1+n_0} \|\phi_k\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = C_{m,\Omega} \lambda_k^{1+n_0},$$

while if $m = 2n_0 + 1$ for some $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$, using now also identity (4.44), we get

$$(4.46) \quad \|\phi_k\|_{H^{2+m}(\Omega)} \leq C_{m-1,\Omega} \lambda_k^{n_0 + \frac{3}{2}},$$

where $C_{m,\Omega}$ is a constant depending on $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and Ω . Let us take $r \in \mathbb{N}$ and call m_r the smallest integer with respect to which the following Sobolev embedding is satisfied

$$(4.47) \quad H^{2+m_r}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow C^r(\overline{\Omega}),$$

namely $m_r := \lceil \frac{n+2r-4}{2} \rceil + 1$, if $n + 2r - 4 \geq 0$, otherwise $m_r = 0$. Therefore, if m_r is even, using (4.45) and (4.47) we obtain

$$\|\phi_k\|_{C^r(\overline{\Omega})} \leq c_{r,\Omega} \|\phi_k\|_{H^{2+m_r}(\Omega)} \leq c_{m_r,\Omega,r} \lambda_k^{1 + \frac{m_r}{2}},$$

where $c_{r,\Omega}$ is the constant of the Sobolev embedding, and if instead m_r is odd, then using the Sobolev embedding (4.47) and the estimate (4.46) we get

$$\|\phi_k\|_{C^r(\overline{\Omega})} \leq c_{r,\Omega} \|\phi_k\|_{H^{2+m_r}(\Omega)} \leq c_{m_r,\Omega,r} \lambda_k^{\frac{3}{2} + \lceil \frac{m_r}{2} \rceil}.$$

The constants $c_{m_r,\Omega,r}$ depends on Ω , r and m_r . Since the elliptic estimate in (4.43) and the identities in (4.44), with obvious adjustments, hold true also for the eigenfunctions ψ_k 's, we can repeat the above reasoning to obtain the bound (4.42) for the family $\{\psi_k\}_k$. \square

Lemma 4.28. *Let λ_k 's and μ_k 's be defined respectively as in equations (4.40) and (4.41). Then, for each $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $s \in (0, 1]$ and $t \in (0, +\infty)$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^m \exp(-t \lambda_k^s) &< +\infty \\ \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \mu_k^m \exp(-t \mu_k^s) &< +\infty \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We prove the first inequality only, since the proof of the second one is the same. Indeed, thanks to Weyl's law (see [Pro87]), we know that there exists some $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that if $k \geq k_0$ then the following double sided inequality holds for both λ_k 's and μ_k 's

$$(4.48) \quad \begin{aligned} c k^{\frac{2}{n}} &\leq \lambda_k \leq C k^{\frac{2}{n}}, \\ c k^{\frac{2}{n}} &\leq \mu_k \leq C k^{\frac{2}{n}} \end{aligned}$$

for some constants $C, c > 0$. Therefore, if $k \geq k_0$ we have that that

$$\lambda_k^m \exp(-t \lambda_k^s) \leq C^m k^{\frac{2m}{n}} \exp(-c^s t k^{\frac{2s}{n}}).$$

Since it holds that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} k^{\frac{2m}{n}} \exp\left(-\frac{c^s t k^{\frac{2s}{n}}}{2}\right) = 0,$$

then there exists $k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $k \geq k_1$

$$k^{\frac{2m}{n}} \exp(-c^s t k^{\frac{2s}{n}}) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{c^s t k^{\frac{2s}{n}}}{2}\right).$$

Therefore, if we call $k_2 := \max\{k_0, k_1\}$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^m \exp(-t \lambda_k^s) &\leq \sum_{k=1}^{k_2-1} \lambda_k^m \exp(-t \lambda_k^s) + C^m \sum_{k=k_2}^{+\infty} k^{\frac{2m}{n}} \exp(-c^s t k^{\frac{2s}{n}}) \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^{k_2-1} \lambda_k^m \exp(-t \lambda_k^s) + \sum_{k=k_2}^{+\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{c^s t k^{\frac{2s}{n}}}{2}\right) \\ &< +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of Lemma 4.28. □

Lemma 4.29. *Let $\{a_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}, \{b_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be sequences of real numbers such that*

$$(4.49) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{a_k}{k^M} = C$$

$$(4.50) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{b_k}{k^m} = c,$$

for some $M, m \in (0, +\infty)$ and $C, c > 0$. Then,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} a_k \exp(-tb_k) = 0.$$

Proof. We assume $d > 0$ and $t \in [d, +\infty)$. In view of (4.49) and (4.50), we obtain that there exists some $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for each $k \geq k_0$ one has

$$a_k \exp(-tb_k) \leq C_1 k^M \exp(-tc_1 k^m),$$

for some $c_1, C_1 > 0$ and for all $t \in [d, +\infty)$. Moreover, since

$$(4.51) \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} C_1 k^M \exp\left(-\frac{tc_1 k^m}{2}\right) = 0,$$

we deduce the existence of some $k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $k \geq k_1$ it holds

$$C_1 k^M \exp(-tc_1 k^m) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{c_1 t k^m}{2}\right).$$

Therefore, taking $k_2 = \max\{k_0, k_1\}$ we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|a_k \exp(-tb_k)\|_{L^\infty([d, +\infty))} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{k_2-1} \|a_k \exp(-tb_k)\|_{L^\infty([d, +\infty))} + \sum_{k=k_2}^{+\infty} \|a_k \exp(-tb_k)\|_{L^\infty([d, +\infty))} \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^{k_2-1} \|a_k \exp(-tb_k)\|_{L^\infty([d, +\infty))} + \sum_{k=k_2}^{+\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{c_1 d k^m}{2}\right) < +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we can take the limit inside the sum as follows

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} a_k \exp(-tb_k) = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} a_k \exp(-tb_k) = 0.$$

The proof of the desired result is thus complete. □

Proposition 4.30. *Let $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$, and consider the $L^2(\Omega)$ expansion $f = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k$, where $f_k := (f, \phi_k)_{L^2(\Omega)}$ and the ϕ_k 's are given in equation (4.40). Then the following estimate for the L^2 projection f_k holds*

$$(4.52) \quad |f_k| \leq \lambda_k^{-m} \|f\|_{H_0^{2m}(\Omega)} \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In particular, for each $r \in \mathbb{N}$, the sequence $f_M(x) := \sum_{k=1}^M f_k \phi_k(x)$ converges in $C^r(\overline{\Omega})$ to f as $M \rightarrow +\infty$.

Similarly, if we consider as $L^2(\Omega)$ Hilbert basis $\{\psi_k\}_k$, then by calling now $f_k := (f, \psi_k)_{L^2(\Omega)}$, for each $k \geq 1$ it holds

$$(4.53) \quad |f_k| \leq \mu_k^{-m} \|f\|_{H_0^{2m}(\Omega)} \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

and, as $M \rightarrow +\infty$, the sequence $f_M(x) := \sum_{k=0}^M f_k \psi_k(x)$ converges to f in $C^r(\overline{\Omega})$ for each $r \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. As usual, we use the notation $\Delta^m f := \underbrace{\Delta \circ \Delta \cdots \circ \Delta}_{m\text{-times}} f$ and $\Delta^0 f := f$.

We prove by induction on $m \in \mathbb{N}$ the following identity

$$(4.54) \quad f_k = \frac{(-1)^m}{\lambda_k^m} \int_{\Omega} \Delta^m f(x) \phi_k(x) dx$$

Let $m = 1$, using the first equation (4.40) and then the integration by parts formula we obtain

$$f_k := \int_{\Omega} f(x) \phi_k(x) dx = -\frac{1}{\lambda_k} \int_{\Omega} f(x) \Delta \phi_k(x) dx = -\frac{1}{\lambda_k} \int_{\Omega} \Delta f(x) \phi_k(x) dx.$$

Next we show that if the identity (4.54) holds true for $m - 1$, then it is valid also for m . Indeed, using the induction hypothesis and repeating the latter computations we get

$$\begin{aligned} f_k &= \frac{(-1)^{m-1}}{\lambda_k^{m-1}} \int_{\Omega} \Delta^{m-1} f(x) \phi_k(x) dx \\ &= \frac{(-1)^m}{\lambda_k^m} \int_{\Omega} \Delta^{m-1} f(x) \Delta \phi_k(x) dx \\ &= \frac{(-1)^m}{\lambda_k^m} \int_{\Omega} \Delta^m f(x) \phi_k(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

From equation (4.54), applying Hölder's inequality we obtain

$$(4.55) \quad |f_k| \leq \lambda_k^{-m} \|\phi_k\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \|f\|_{H_0^{2m}(\Omega)} = \lambda_k^{-m} \|f\|_{H_0^{2m}(\Omega)}$$

which is the desired estimate. The series $f_N(x)$ is converging a.e. in Ω to f , as consequence of the $L^2(\Omega)$ convergence. The estimates proved in Proposition 4.27 lead us to the $C^k(\bar{\Omega})$ convergence of the series. Indeed,

$$\sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \|f_k \phi_k\|_{C^r(\bar{\Omega})} \leq \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} |f_k| \lambda_k^{\alpha(m_r)} \leq \|f\|_{H_0^{2m}(\Omega)} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{-m+\alpha(m_r)} =: \mathcal{I}_m$$

and choosing m such that it satisfies $m - \alpha(m_r) > 1$, we see that \mathcal{I}_m is a finite quantity, proving our latter claim.

The identity (4.54), with obvious adjustments, holds true also for the ψ_k 's when $k \geq 1$. By repeating the above reasoning we obtain the desired result. \square

Alternative proofs of Theorems 3.9 and 4.10

Here we give an alternative proof of the Maximum Principle for the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat equation (see Theorem 3.9), using the probabilistic framework that was developed in Section 3.3 of Chapter 3 for the Dirichlet case.

To be more precise, in Proposition 3.21 we showed that the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel r_D^s can be rewritten as

$$r_D^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(dl),$$

where $p_D^\Omega(t, x, y)$ is the classical Dirichlet heat kernel, and μ_t^s is the probability density in $(0, +\infty)$ given in Definition 3.17 of Chapter 3.

From the above equation it is clear that starting from the Maximum Principle for the classical Dirichlet heat equation one can obtain the corresponding result for the fractional case.

The proof for the Neumann case is analogous, and therefore here we will stick to the one for the Dirichlet equation.

Alternative proof of Theorem 3.9 in Chapter 3. We need to prove that

$$(4.56) \quad \min \left\{ 0, \inf_{\Omega} f \right\} \leq \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx \leq \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}.$$

Let us start by checking the right-hand side inequality in (4.56). Let $f \in L^2(\Omega)$ and consider the map

$$f(t, y) = \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(x) dx.$$

Then, using equation (3.45) in Chapter 3, one gets that

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, y) &= \int_{\Omega} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^{\Omega}(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(dl) f(x) dx \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\Omega} p_D^{\Omega}(l, x, y) f(x) dx \mu_t^s(dl). \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, by the Maximum Principle for the classical Dirichlet heat equation (see equation (3.7) in Chapter 3), one gets that

$$f(t, y) \leq \int_0^{+\infty} \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\} \mu_t^s(dl) = \max \left\{ 0, \sup_{\Omega} f \right\}.$$

This proves the right-hand side inequality in (4.56). The left-hand side inequality of (4.56) is obtained analogously using the results in Chapter 3 (explicitly, equation (3.45) and the left-hand side inequality of (3.7). therein). \square

THE LÉVY FLIGHT FORAGING
HYPOTHESIS IN BOUNDED REGIONS:
SUBORDINATE BROWNIAN MOTIONS
AND HIGH-RISK/HIGH-GAIN
STRATEGIES

We investigate the problem of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis in an ecological niche described by a bounded region of space, with either absorbing or reflecting boundary conditions.

To this end, we consider a forager diffusing according to a fractional heat equation in a bounded domain and we define several efficiency functionals whose optimality is discussed in relation to the fractional exponent $s \in (0, 1)$ of the diffusive equation.

Such equation is taken to be the spectral fractional heat equation (with Dirichlet or Neumann boundary conditions).

We analyze the biological scenarios in which a target is close to the forager. In particular, for all the efficiency functionals considered here, we show that if the target is close enough to the forager, then the most rewarding search strategy will be in a small neighborhood of $s = 0$.

Interestingly, we show that $s = 0$ is a global pessimizer for some of the efficiency functionals. From this, together with the aforementioned optimality results, we

deduce that the most rewarding strategy can be unsafe or unreliable in practice, given its proximity with the pessimizing exponent, thus the forager may opt for a less performant, but safer, hunting method.

However, the biological literature has already collected several pieces of evidence of foragers diffusing with very low Lévy exponents, often in relation with a high energetic content of the prey. It is thereby suggestive to relate these patterns, which are induced by distributions with a very fat tail, with a high-risk/high-gain strategy, in which the forager adopts a potentially very profitable, but also potentially completely unrewarding, strategy due to the high value of the possible outcome.

Preamble

On the one hand, many popular adages share the idea that *to achieve a prominent goal one has to take risks* (e.g., “no gain without pain”, “nothing ventured, nothing gained”, “no guts, no glory”, just to name a few proverbs). On many occasions, the ambition to a high reward may lead individuals to face potential dangers, and in some situations there is a full master plan centered around a high-risk/high-gain plan: for instance, the blueprint of the European Research Council is to fund high-risk/high-reward research, in which severe conceptual challenges (which, by definition, are prone to scientific failure) are accepted downsides for a research project to be truly successful and impactful.

On the other hand, there is nowadays a great interest in the investigation of *optimal searching strategies*, e.g. in the study of animal behavior, and the research on this topic has necessarily to be somewhat controversial, given the complexity of the phenomenon into consideration.

Our view on this point is that the difficulty of addressing the topic of optimal searching is not only due to the *enormous amount of parameters* which should be accounted for (such as predators and prey distributions, previous knowledge of the territory, interactions with the environment, social factors, different reactions to adverse circumstances, competition phenomena, cooperative behaviors, etc.), and not only due to the difficulty of measuring many of these parameters via *objective empirical observations*.

In fact, in our opinion, a core difficulty in this topic stems from the difficulty of assessing unambiguously and indisputably a suitable notion of “gain” which should be maximized by a searching algorithm. This gain cannot be limited to the actual effectiveness of the procedure (i.e., whether or not the predator captures the prey), but it has to take into account the cost of the procedure itself (e.g., the time needed for the task, or the energy spent for it), and, at least on some occasions, the possible value of the outcome of the search.

One of the findings of our research is indeed that the high-risk/high-reward situation may appear naturally even in very simple situations, therefore the notion of “best strategy” requires a *very careful mathematical setting*, in which an *efficiency functional* is chosen and *maximized*, and *the location of the maxima is confronted with that of the minima*.

In doing so, one discovers immediately some interesting features. First of all, different efficiency functionals can produce different results. This already highlights a structural complication towards a full understanding of the notion of optimal searching strategy: for instance, in a biological study, different species, or different individuals of the same species, may, implicitly or explicitly, address a different type of efficiency functional.

In addition, in several concrete situations, the maximizers of some efficiency functional may end up to be dangerously close to the minimizers: this is a clear case of high-risk/high-reward pattern and, in this “unstable” situation, one should expect that the practical outcome of the optimal searching pattern be influenced by intermediate strategies aiming at a balance between top performances and conservative options (e.g., a risk assessment which compromises between the most rewarding and the safest result). Quite likely, in these conditions, different biological species, or different members of the same group, may end up adopting different search strategies.

Interestingly, in our setting, the situation in which the most rewarding strategy is arbitrarily close to a complete failure of the searching pattern is related to Lévy distributions with a very low exponent and a very fat tail. This pattern is known to be related to foraging modes of “ambush” type (see [Dyb+17] and Chapter 6). The literature has also collected experimental evidence of some species, such as anglers

and blonde skates, which do follow diffusive paths with very low Lévy exponent: remarkably, a correlation has been found between this type of diffusion and the high content of energy of the targets (see [Dyb+17]).

In our setting, this correlation is possibly motivated precisely by the fact that the most rewarding Lévy exponent happens to be very close to the pessimizer. In a sense, it can be significant to imagine that such a high-risk/high-gain strategy becomes particularly suitable when the possible outcome is of exceptional value (in the case of a biological predator, a prey of exceptionally high energetic content).

That is, in an implicit risk assessment, the value of the target may mitigate the prospect of an unsuccessful search, thus favoring the emergence, in these specific situations, of high-risk/high-reward diffusive patterns.

In this work, this general vision will be embodied into a precise mathematical study of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis, considering the possibility that processes with long jumps (instead of standard Gaussian random movements) can optimize search efficiency by diminishing the repetitions of visits to previously inspected sites. Different efficiency functionals will be taken into account, with a thorough analysis of their optimizers and pessimizers. This phenomenon in which optimizers and pessimizers cluster together will be also explicitly detected and discussed.

The Lévy flights will be modeled via a heat equation of fractional type in bounded domains. We consider the case of a hostile environment (such as a “fence”, modeled by homogeneous Dirichlet conditions which “annihilate” a biological species outside a confinement domain) as well as the case of reflecting boundaries (modeled by homogeneous Neumann conditions which maintain a biological species within a niche without altering the number of individuals present in the region).

To implement these boundary conditions in the setting of the fractional heat equation, we will make use of the spectral version of the fractional Laplacian.

In some of the efficiency functionals that we consider, predators and targets are modeled as points in the space. In other cases instead we will model predators and targets as regions of space (assuming e.g. that the biological individuals are uniformly distributed within these regions): this situation can also be considered as a technical and conceptual simplification of the notion of “direct vision” which

was previously adopted in the literature, see e.g. [Vis+99]. That is, here we do not introduce an additional parameter to truncate the Lévy distribution in the proximity of its singularity (which entails in itself some delicate issues, see [PV21]) and we do not alter the diffusive equation to account for foragers directly aiming at the prey when they lie at short mutual distance. Instead, the diffusive equation is supposed to hold at every spatial scale and the role of a different region of influence (e.g., induced by uncertainties in the data or by a different hunting pattern at a small scale) is encoded only in the efficiency functional.

Here, we do not restrict our analysis to the one-dimensional case; in fact, we deal with an arbitrary large number n of dimensions. We note that the case of higher dimension is, in many instances, not only a situation of utmost biological interest, but also a source of technical difficulties and scientific controversies, see e.g. [Lev+20; Bul+21; Lev+21].

5.1 Introduction to the mathematical setting and main results

In the last decades, anomalous diffusion has been investigated as an appropriate substitute for normal diffusion in several branches of science, such as biology and in particular the foraging theory (see for instance [SK86c; Vis+96; Edw+07; Vis+99; Rey18]). In this context a special case of anomalous diffusion occurs when a forager in search of food, rather than diffusing according to the classical Brownian motion, performs long-jump patterns characterized by a space and time steps scale invariance, see e.g. [KS05] and the references therein.

This type of searches fits the model of the Lévy flight, according to the probabilistic description given in Section 4.3 of [AV19]. In contrast to what happens with the classical random walk, the forager performing these flights has less chances to revisit intensively the immediate surrounding areas and then being confined in a narrow region. Therefore, in the biological framework, Lévy flights seem to be a better search strategy when the source of food is scarce and sparsely distributed and there is a large area to be covered in order to succeed in the hunt.

These kinds of foraging search strategies have been empirically observed in many ecological systems, see e.g. [Vis+96; Atk+02; RF+04; Edw+07; Sim+08; Hum+10; Hum+12; HWS13]. Moreover, several studies have been made in order to validate the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis from a mathematical and statistical point of view [Vis+99; Bar+02; Rap+09; Vis+02].

In these models a number of assumptions are usually made on the environment, on targets and foragers. For instance, a low prey density is often assumed and the targets are randomly distributed in a wide area; the forager does not keep memory of previous encounters; the forager has scarce information on the area to search and on the prey location. On the one hand, on some occasions, these structural assumptions are introduced in order to simplify the problem, which otherwise would be extremely challenging to be analyzed from a theoretical perspective; on the other hand, some of these conditions can actually be structurally necessary for the convenience of the Lévy flight strategy over more standard type of diffusive processes. In any case, the complexity of the raw problem is a consequence of its dependence on a great number of environmental, evolutionary and biological variables. Even though an oversimplification may lead to a less accurate model in some circumstances, we can evince from a simplified model some remarkable properties, advancing the knowledge on such a complex topic.

In this chapter we will investigate the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis relying on a fractional elliptic operator. This is motivated by the fact that in the limit of the time step going to zero, the distribution of a seeker performing Lévy flights converges to the solution of a fractional heat equation, see e.g. [Val09; BV16; AV19].

In order to test the Lévy flights foraging hypothesis, we consider some efficiency functionals, accounting for the random encounter rate between the forager and the target. We maximize these efficiency functionals with respect to the fractional exponent, with the aim of understanding which flight was more advantageous for the forager. From a biological perspective, this optimization with respect to the fractional exponent corresponds to the possibility of a forager to modify its searching strategy by tuning e.g. the average length of a hunting path and the waiting times between different paths.

We will assume that the forager is confined in some bounded region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, which plays the role of an ecological niche. Both Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions will be taken into account to describe absorbing and reflecting boundaries.

For us, the choice of a spectral fractional heat equation as a diffusion equation for the forager was motivated by its stochastic interpretation as a subordinate Brownian motion in Ω , see Chapters 3 and 4. See also [MPV13; CDV17; SV17; DV21; DPLV23] and the references therein for several applications of fractional elliptic equations to biological problems.

In this chapter, we will test the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis by taking into account different biological configurations, such as:

- the case in which the forager starting position and the target location coincide,
- the case in which the forager starting position is located in proximity of the target,
- the case in which the forager and the target, instead of being modeled as material points, are uniformly distributed in some regions of space.

The situation in which the biological population is not confined into a bounded region of space and can travel through the whole of \mathbb{R}^n is technically different and is treated in Chapters 2 and 6.

The chapter is structured as follows. In Section 5.1, we define the *efficiency functionals* for the spectral search in the bounded region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$. They will be taken to be proportional to the encounter rate between the forager and the target. Moreover, different “penalization quantities” will be considered, such as the average distance and the mean square displacement, in order to build physically reliable efficiency functionals.

Sections 5.1 and 5.1 are devoted to the study of the *maximizer* for the aforementioned functionals. These maximizers thus correspond to the most rewarding searching mode. In particular, in Section 5.1 we will assume that the forager starting position and the prey location coincide. This scenario, though physically less relevant, will let us detect some *monotonicity properties* of one of the functionals, when the domain satisfies suitable geometric properties, see Theorem 5.4 below. This

result shows how *the search for a maximizer is related to the geometric structure of the play field*.

In Section 5.1, as well as in Section 5.1 for the case of distributed foragers and targets, we analyze the case in which the target is in some small neighborhood of the forager starting position. Here we establish that *if the target position converges to the initial location of the seeker, then the maximizer of the efficiency functionals is located in a neighborhood of $s = 0$* . This is the content of Theorems 5.7, 5.8, 5.15 and 5.16.

Furthermore, in Theorems 5.6 and 5.14 it will be proved that for some of these efficiency functionals the strategy $s = 0$ is the *unique global minimizer*, thus corresponding to the unique pessimizer of the searching mode. This minimality result, together with the convergence of the best strategy, will entail that, roughly speaking, the most rewarding strategy may end up being not reliable, presenting arbitrarily close pessimizers, thus opening the dilemma of whether in practice one should follow the most performant option, or the safest one, or, say, a balanced combination of the two (see Remark 5.9 below).

In Section 5.2 we collect the main analytical tools that will be employed in order to prove our main results.

Finally in Section 5.3 we prove the results stated in Sections 5.1 and 5.1.

Efficiency Functionals

To measure the effectiveness of a foraging strategy, one can consider different functionals which account for the rate of hunting “success” for the predator versus the “effort” needed.

The possibility of accounting for different efficiency functionals plays, in our opinion, a crucial role in biology and ethology, since, while the notion of “foraging success” may be somewhat objective (as measured for instance by the amount of food eaten, or by the calories carried by such a food), the notion of “cost spent to achieve the success” is intrinsically more ambiguous and different biological theories may end up measuring this concept in different ways. As an example, we recall the debate about the way honey bees assess how far they have flown (whether based on the energy expended in flying or on the fatigue required by the action,

as conjectured in former experiments, or on the image motion of the surrounding landscape through visual perception, as pointed out in the “optic flow hypothesis” and addressed in recent tests, see [Sri+00]). Related to this, we also recall that in some situations the measure of the distance traveled can be performed according to a number of possible strategies (e.g., in the case of ants, which can use optic flow, pheromone and chemical trails, as well as the “counting” of the number of steps, see [WWW06]). See also [Gad21] and the references therein for further reading on how animals measure distances.

The mathematical setting that we consider here goes as follows. We model a forager moving in some bounded region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ through a spectral fractional diffusion with either Dirichlet or Neumann homogeneous boundary conditions. The domain Ω where the diffusion occurs can be seen as an ecological niche where the forager is confined (the Dirichlet condition corresponding to the case in which the forager is killed at the boundary of the niche, and the Neumann datum corresponding e.g. to fences that prevent the forager to exit the niche).

Specifically, the probability density $u = u(t, x)$ of the forager satisfies the diffusive equation

$$(5.1) \quad \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) \quad \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega,$$

with either Dirichlet or Neumann homogeneous boundary conditions.

Here above s is a fractional parameter in $(0, 1)$ and the operator $(-\Delta)^s$ represents the spectral fractional Laplacian, see e.g. Sections 2.3 and 4.3 in [AV19] for the basics of this operator. See also [Dyb+17] for different approaches to the problem of Lévy flights in (one-dimensional) bounded domains.

We also assume that the targets are scattered in Ω according to a distribution $p(t, x)$, where $(t, x) \in [0, +\infty) \times \Omega$.

We consider, as an initial measure of the success of the hunting strategy of the predator, a *foraging success functional* which accounts for the random encounters between the forager following the anomalous diffusion equation in (5.1) and the targets.

Specifically, in the situation considered here, given $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $y \in \Omega$, the

foraging success functional takes the form

$$(5.2) \quad \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} r^s(t, x, y) p(t, x) dx dt,$$

where $r^s(t, x, y)$ represents either the Dirichlet or the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel, for some fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1)$, see Chapters 3 and 4 and the beginning of the forthcoming Section 5.2 for definitions and basic properties of these kernels.

We notice indeed that the quantity in (5.2) is associated with the probability that a forager starting at the position $y \in \Omega$ and following the diffusion process modeled by the fractional heat equation with either Dirichlet or Neumann boundary condition hits a target distributed according to $p(t, x)$ in the time interval $(0, T)$.

To obtain an efficiency functional, we compare this quantity with some other quantities of physical and biological significance that instead provide a penalization for the seeker. Here, we will consider as penalization quantities the *time* T , the *average distance traveled by the forager* $l^y(s, T)$ after a time T and the *mean square displacement* $\mathcal{A}^y(s, T)$ after a time T .

More explicitly, the average distance traveled by the forager at time $T \in (0, +\infty)$ is given by

$$(5.3) \quad l^y(s, T) := \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\zeta - y| r^s(t, \zeta, y) d\zeta dt.$$

The probabilistic interpretation underpinning this definition consists in taking into account the random process Y_t starting at y corresponding to a subordinate Brownian motion which is either killed or reflected at the boundary (the generator of such a process corresponding to the spectral fractional Laplacian with either Dirichlet or Neumann datum).

In this framework, the quantity $|Y_t|$ represents the distance at time t for a single representation of the process, whence it is natural to consider its expected value

$$\mathbb{E}_y^s[|Y_t|] = \int_{\Omega} |x - y| r^s(t, x, y) dx$$

as the mean distance traveled at time t . The setting in (5.3) is thus the average over time $t \in (0, T)$ of this quantity.

Similarly, the mean square displacement is given by

$$(5.4) \quad \mathcal{A}^y(s, T) := \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\zeta - y|^2 r^s(t, \zeta, y) d\zeta dt$$

and represents the average over time $t \in (0, T)$ of the expected value of the squared distance

$$\mathbb{E}_y^s[|Y_t|^2] = \int_{\Omega} |x - y|^2 r^s(t, x, y) dx.$$

Interestingly, subordinators related to waiting times may have an intimate connection to biology, since spontaneous patterns of waiting times are known to occur in nature, and they can be species-specific, depend on body size, foraging modes, prey preference, etc., see [Wea+14].

While the notations in (5.3) and (5.4) are the same for the Dirichlet and the Neumann cases (the difference being only in the fractional heat kernel, which is sensitive to the boundary conditions), it is convenient to distinguish explicitly between the two types of boundary data and for this we add the subscript D or N to the notation, namely we write $l_D^y(s, T)$, $l_N^y(s, T)$, $\mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T)$ and $\mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T)$ to emphasize the dependence of the average distance traveled and of the mean square displacement with respect to the Dirichlet or the Neumann boundary condition.

As a special case of target distribution $p(t, \xi)$, we consider the situation in which there is only one target located at $x \in \Omega$. In this case, the distribution $p(t, \xi)$ reduces to the Dirac's delta $\delta_x(\xi)$ and the foraging success functional in (5.2) will be denoted (depending on the boundary condition) by

$$(5.5) \quad \begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, \zeta, y) \delta_x(\zeta) d\zeta dt = \int_0^T r_D^s(t, x, y) dt \\ \text{or } \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, \zeta, y) \delta_x(\zeta) d\zeta dt = \int_0^T r_N^s(t, x, y) dt. \end{aligned}$$

In this chapter we focus on the optimal foraging strategy according to the following efficiency functionals:

$$(5.6) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{T}, & \mathcal{E}_{1,N}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T)}{T}, \\ \mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{l_D^y(s, T)}, & \mathcal{E}_{2,N}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T)}{l_N^y(s, T)}, \\ \mathcal{E}_{3,D}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{\mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T)} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{E}_{3,N}^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \frac{\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T)}{\mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T)}. \end{aligned}$$

In addition to the functionals in (5.6), we consider the following set-dependent functionals. Here, the exact initial positions of target and forager are replaced by uniform densities in two subregions of Ω . Namely, we assume that the targets are distributed in Ω according to

$$p(t, x) := \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}(x)}{|\Omega_1|},$$

for some measurable set $\Omega_1 \subset \Omega$, where χ_{Ω_1} is the characteristic function of Ω_1 and $|\Omega_1|$ denotes the Lebesgue measure of Ω_1 .

The forager diffusing via the spectral fractional heat equation is initially uniformly distributed in some measurable set $\Omega_2 \subset \Omega$ and therefore, dropping for the moment the subscript D and N , its density in $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ is given by

$$f^s(t, x) := \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_2} r^s(t, x, y) dy,$$

see e.g. Lemmas 3.27 and 4.23 respectively in Chapters 3 and 4.

With this notation, the *set-dependent forager success functional* takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Phi}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} f^s(t, x) p(t, x) dx dt \\ (5.7) \quad &= \frac{1}{|\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} r^s(t, x, y) dx dy dt. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, in this framework, the average distance traveled by the forager and the mean square displacement are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{l}^{\Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| f^s(t, \xi) d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega \times \Omega_2} |\xi - y| r^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dy dt \\ (5.8) \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\mathcal{A}}^{\Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y|^2 f^s(t, \xi) d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega \times \Omega_2} |\xi - y|^2 r^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dy dt. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, with these set-dependent foraging success functional and penalization quantities, we define the *set-dependent efficiency functionals* as

$$(5.9) \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T)}{T}, & \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,N}^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_N^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T)}{T}, \\ \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T)}{\tilde{l}_D^{\Omega_2}(s,T)}, & \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_N^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T)}{\tilde{l}_N^{\Omega_2}(s,T)}, \\ \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,D}^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T)}{\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_D^{\Omega_2}(s,T)} \quad \text{and} \quad & \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,N}^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T) &:= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_N^{\Omega_1,\Omega_2}(s,T)}{\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_N^{\Omega_2}(s,T)}. \end{aligned}$$

Prey at forager starting position and change of monotonicity

In this section we will assume that the forager starts its search from the prey location. In this case, all the efficiency functionals in (5.6) diverge if $n \geq 2$ or $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$, as better specified in the following proposition. For this reason, in this scenario where the forager starting position coincides with the target location, we will only work in one dimension.

Proposition 5.1. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected, $x \in \Omega$ and \mathcal{E} be any of the efficiency functionals in (5.6) with $x = y$.*

Then, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$, if either $n \geq 2$ or $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$ it holds that $\mathcal{E}(s, T) = +\infty$.

In the one-dimensional framework, the connectedness hypothesis on Ω forces the domain to be an interval. Thus, up to a translation, we can suppose that $\Omega = (0, a)$ for some $a \in (0, +\infty)$. In this case, several results can be obtained at the same time for all the efficiency functionals in (5.6).

In the following proposition we establish that the range of the fractional exponent in which these functionals achieve a finite value coincides with $(\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, and that in this interval they are continuous in s .

Proposition 5.2. *Let $a \in (0, +\infty)$, $\Omega = (0, a)$, $x \in \Omega$, $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and \mathcal{E} be any of the efficiency functionals in (5.6) with $x = y$.*

Then, $\mathcal{E}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ and $\mathcal{E}(\cdot, T) \in C((\frac{1}{2}, 1])$.

In terms of detecting the most rewarding foraging strategy with respect to the Lévy exponent s , we show that *if the initial position of the forager coincides with the*

location of the target then $s = 1/2$ is the optimizer for all the efficiency functionals in (5.6):

Theorem 5.3. *Let $a \in (0, +\infty)$, $\Omega = (0, a)$, $x \in \Omega$ and \mathcal{E} be any of the efficiency functionals in (5.6) with $x = y$.*

Then, for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$, the supremum over $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ of \mathcal{E} is attained at $s = \frac{1}{2}$, with

$$(5.10) \quad \lim_{s \searrow \frac{1}{2}} \mathcal{E}(s, T) = +\infty.$$

Even though the environmental scenario of a forager starting its search precisely from the target location is physically less relevant than the other cases, it can serve as an example of the complexity of the optimization problem and its dependence on external factors, such as the geometrical properties of the domain.

In what follows, we provide an example of *change of monotonicity* for the functionals in equation (5.5). Specifically, we show that *if the interval in which we consider the motion is small enough, then the functionals are strictly decreasing in s* . On the other hand, we prove that *if the interval is large enough, then there is a region of this interval such that if the search starts there, then the monotonicity property is violated* in a neighborhood of the Brownian strategy $s = 1$, see Figure 13.1.

Theorem 5.4. *Let $a \in (0, +\infty)$, $\Omega = (0, a)$, $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $x \in \Omega$. Let Φ be any of the foraging success functional in (5.5) with $x = y$.*

Then, if $a \in (0, \pi]$, for every $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ and $s_1 \in (s_0, 1]$, we have that

$$(5.11) \quad \Phi(s_0, T) > \Phi(s_1, T).$$

Also, for every $\nu \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ there exists $a_\nu \in (\pi, +\infty)$ such that if $a \in (a_\nu, +\infty)$ then, for every $T \in [\nu a^{2s}, +\infty)$, $x \in (\nu a, (1 - \nu)a)$, $s_0 \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1)$ and $s_1 \in (s_0, 1]$, it holds that

$$(5.12) \quad \Phi_D^{x,x}(s_1, T) > \Phi_D^{x,x}(s_0, T).$$

Furthermore, for every $\nu \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ there exists $a_\nu \in (\pi, +\infty)$ such that if $a \in (a_\nu, +\infty)$ then, for every $T \in [\nu a^{2s}, +\infty)$, $x \in (0, \frac{(1-\nu)a}{2}) \cup (\frac{(1+\nu)a}{2}, a)$, $s_0 \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1)$ and $s_1 \in (s_0, 1]$, it holds that

$$(5.13) \quad \Phi_N^{x,x}(s_1, T) > \Phi_N^{x,x}(s_0, T).$$

Figure 5.1: Plot of $(\frac{1}{2}, 1) \ni s \mapsto \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T)$ for $\Omega = (0, a)$ with $x = 2.5$, $T = 100$ and $a \in \{3, 10\}$. We have approximated Φ_D , as explicitly given in (5.148), by summing to the 5×10^5 th term.

In Chapters 3 and 4 we studied the monotonicity properties of the fractional heat kernel $r^s(t, x, x)$ with respect to the fractional parameter s and we showed that these properties depend on the geometry of the domain. This dependence is expressed via the eigenvalues of either the Dirichlet or the Neumann Laplacian, which are well-known to depend on geometric features of the domain, like its measure or the Hausdorff measure of its boundary. For further details on this relation see the comments after Theorems 3.10 and 4.11 and the references therein.

More precisely, in Theorem 3.10 we established that if the first eigenvalue of the Dirichlet Laplacian is greater than 1, then the fractional heat kernel $r_D^s(t, x, x)$ is strictly decreasing in s . Analogously, in Theorem 4.11 we proved that if the first nonvanishing eigenvalue $\mu_{k(x)}$ of the Neumann Laplacian associated to a nonvanishing eigenfunction in x is greater than 1, then $r_N^s(t, x, x)$ is strictly decreasing in s . The monotonicity property given in (5.11) is thus a consequence of Theorems 3.10 and 4.11 and the definitions in (5.5).

On the other hand, in Theorems 3.10 and 4.11 we proved that under some circumstances there is a change of monotonicity for $r^s(t, x, x)$. Indeed, we showed that if the first eigenvalue of the Dirichlet Laplacian, or $\mu_{k(x)}$ as described above for the Neumann case, is smaller than 1, then for every $s_0, s_1 \in (0, 1)$ such that $s_0 < s_1$ there exists some $T \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $r^{s_0}(t, x, x) < r^{s_1}(t, x, x)$ for all $t \in (T, +\infty)$. This latter change of monotonicity in relation to the size of the eigenvalues inspired the

search for a change of monotonicity also for the efficiency functionals $\Phi_D^{x,x}$ and $\Phi_N^{x,x}$, which is proved to be true, as expressed by equations (5.12) and (5.13) above.

Prey in proximity of the forager

We now turn our attention to the efficiency functionals in (5.6) when the initial position of the forager $y \in \Omega$ is different from the target location $x \in \Omega$. We begin by stating the following *continuity result* with respect to the fractional exponent s .

Proposition 5.5. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected. For every $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$ such that $x \neq y$, let us denote by $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}$ any of the efficiency functionals in (5.6).*

Then, $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$ and $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$.

In the following result we establish that for each $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$, satisfying $x \neq y$, the first Dirichlet functional $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T)$ attains its infimum at $s = 0$. Moreover, we show that the Dirichlet functionals in (5.6) admit a finite limit for $s \searrow 0$, as far as $x \neq y$.

Theorem 5.6. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, for every $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$ with $x \neq y$, it holds that

$$(5.14) \quad \inf_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = 0.$$

Moreover, we have that

$$(5.15) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{3,D}^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty).$$

From Theorem 5.6 we evince that we can extend by continuity the Dirichlet functionals in (5.6) to the whole compact interval $[0, 1]$. Hence, from now on, we will adopt the notation

$$(5.16) \quad \mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}(0, T) := \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}(s, T),$$

for all $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$, with $x \neq y$ and $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

The following two theorems are the most important results of this section. We state that *if the forager starting position $y \in \Omega$ is close enough to the prey location*

$x \in \Omega$, then the best search strategy for the efficiency functionals in (5.6) will be in some small neighborhood of $s = 0$.

Theorem 5.7. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $\delta = \delta_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x \in B_\delta(y) \setminus \{y\}$ it holds that

$$(5.17) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{1, D}^{x, y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1, D}^{x, y} \left(s_{x, y, T}^{(1)}, T \right) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x, y, T}^{(1)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Moreover, for each $j \in \{2, 3\}$ it holds that

$$(5.18) \quad \mathcal{E}_{j, D}^{x, y}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{j, D}^{x, y}(s, T).$$

We stress that the situation $x \neq y$ treated in Theorem 5.7 is conceptually quite different from the case $x = y$ presented in Theorem 5.3: indeed, when the initial location of the predator is different from the position of the target, the efficiency functionals are finite for all $s \in (0, 1]$ independently from the dimension, as stated in Proposition 5.5.

The result in Theorem 5.7 is general enough to include different Dirichlet efficiency functionals and detects a somewhat “universal” qualitative behavior.

Moreover, an analogous situation holds true also for the Neumann functionals in (5.6):

Theorem 5.8. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $\delta = \delta_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x \in B_\delta(y) \setminus \{y\}$ and for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ it holds that

$$(5.19) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{j, N}^{x, y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{j, N}^{x, y} \left(s_{x, y, T}^{(j)}, T \right) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x, y, T}^{(j)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Therefore, from Theorems 5.7 and 5.8 we deduce that *if the initial position of the forager approaches the position of the target, the fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1)$ maximizing the functionals in (5.6) converges to 0. Thus, in the regime of close proximity of seeker starting position and prey location, the above functionals are maximized by a search strategy with a very fat tail.*

It is interesting to notice that the maximizer $s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}$ of $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$ given by Theorem 5.7 may turn out to be unreliable in practice, differently from the other two maximizers of the Dirichlet functionals, according to the following remark.

Remark 5.9. On the one hand, Theorem 5.6 establishes that $s = 0$ is a global minimizer for $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$. On the other hand, if $s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}$ is a maximizer of $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(\cdot, T)$, then from Theorem 5.7 we evince that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow y} s_{x,y,T}^{(1)} = 0.$$

This means that as x approaches y , the maximizer of the functional $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}$ converges to $s = 0$, which is a global minimizer. Therefore, a small perturbation of $s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}$ can lead to very small values for $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$, making such choice of the most rewarding fractional exponent quite unreliable. Therefore, in an environmental scenario where the forager starts its search in proximity of the target and the efficiency functional modelling the energy to maximize is given by $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$, the “most rewarding” search strategy is to be considered “unreliable”.

Things turn out to be different for $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{3,D}^{x,y}$. Indeed, if $s_{x,y,T}^{(j)}$ is a maximizer of the functional $\mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}(\cdot, T)$ with $j \in \{2, 3\}$, then, according to Theorem 5.7, one still has the limit

$$(5.20) \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow y} s_{x,y,T}^{(j)} = 0.$$

Nevertheless, in contrast with the case $j = 1$, now $s = 0$ is not necessarily a global minimum. Actually, see equation (5.18), for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, if x and y are close enough, then

$$\mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{j,D}^{x,y}(s, T),$$

so that $s = 0$ in these two cases is “almost” a maximizer. Roughly speaking, we can say that the functionals $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{3,D}$ present more reliable optimal configurations than $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$, since the maximizing fractional exponent is “separated” from the minimizers, whence the most rewarding strategy appears to be safer.

Remark 5.10. It has been observed in [Wea+14] that the case $s = 0$ occurs when some marine predators, such as anglers and blonde skates, specifically aim at a type of prey with a high energy content. It is therefore natural to relate the high-energy content of the prey and the high-risk/high-reward strategy related to $s = 0$:

namely a high gain prospected by the energy content of the prey may serve as a mitigation of the chance of failure entailed by searching mode selected and as an indirect encouragement towards a potentially very beneficial, but intrinsically very risky, strategy.

Remark 5.11. One may wonder whether the unreliability of the most rewarding strategies and the corresponding high-risk/high-reward searching mode are specific of the situation considered in this chapter, i.e. of a forager confined in a bounded region and a nearby prey. This is not the case, in fact in Chapter 6 we will show that the same pattern persists, for instance, for a predator diffusing in the whole space and also for a prey located arbitrarily far from the predator.

The case that will be addressed in Chapter 6 is technically different from the one here, since the spectral analysis cannot be performed in unbounded domains and we will have to rely on singular integral calculations instead.

In what follows we observe a phenomenon which arises in the one-dimensional framework as a consequence of Theorem 5.4. In particular, under the same geometric assumptions of Theorem 5.4 on the domain Ω , we show that if the target location $x \in \Omega$ is sufficiently close to the forager initial position $y \in \Omega$, then *there exists a local maximizer $s_{x,y,T}^*$ for $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{1,N}^{x,y}$ in a neighborhood of the Brownian strategy $s = 1$.*

Corollary 5.12. *Let $a \in (0, +\infty)$, $\Omega = (0, a)$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for every $\nu \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $a_\nu \in (\pi, +\infty)$ such that if $a \in (a_\nu, +\infty)$ then, for every $T \in [\nu a^{2s}, +\infty)$ and $y \in (\nu a, (1 - \nu)a)$, there exists some $\delta = \delta_{\nu,\varepsilon,y,T,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $x \in B_\delta(y) \setminus \{y\}$ then

$$(5.21) \quad \sup_{s \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}^*, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T}^* \in (1 - \varepsilon, 1].$$

Also, for every $\nu \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $a_\nu \in (\pi, +\infty)$ such that if $a \in (a_\nu, +\infty)$ then, for every $T \in [\nu a^{2s}, +\infty)$ and $y \in \left(0, \frac{(1-\nu)a}{2}\right) \cup \left(\frac{(1+\nu)a}{2}, a\right)$, there exists some $\delta = \delta_{\nu,\varepsilon,y,T,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $x \in B_\delta(y) \setminus \{y\}$ then

$$(5.22) \quad \sup_{s \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,N}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,N}^{x,y}(\widehat{s}_{x,y,T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad \widehat{s}_{x,y,T} \in (1 - \varepsilon, 1].$$

It is interesting to compare this result with Remark 5.9 on the unreliability of the most rewarding search strategy for $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}$. Indeed, as a consequence of Theorem 5.7 and Corollary 5.12, we have that for each $\nu \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $a_\nu \in (\pi, +\infty)$ such that for every a, T and y given as in the statement of Corollary 5.12, there exists some $\delta^* = \delta_{\nu, \varepsilon, y, T, \Omega}^* \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $x \in B_{\delta^*}(y) \setminus \{y\}$,

$$\sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}\left(s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}, T\right) \quad \text{with } s_{x,y,T}^{(1)} \in (0, \varepsilon)$$

and

$$\sup_{s \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}\left(s_{x,y,T}^*, T\right) \quad \text{with } s_{x,y,T}^* \in (1 - \varepsilon, 1].$$

From this, we deduce that in this framework *there exist a global and a local maximizer*. The global maximizer $s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}$ seems to be the most rewarding option for the forager performing the search. Nevertheless, thanks to Remark 5.9, we also know that it is extremely *unreliable* for practical purposes. Indeed, a small deviation from $s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}$ can lead to the unique global minimizer $s = 0$, that makes the functional vanish.

On the other hand, even though the local maximizer $s_{x,y,T}^*$ is not optimal, it could be a better choice due to its stability. As a matter of fact, as stated in Proposition 5.5, the functional $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}$ vanishes nowhere near the Brownian strategy $s = 1$. Therefore, by choosing $s_{x,y,T}^*$, even under the presence of a positive error in the choice of the strategy, the outcome would not be heavily affected, as it could be for the most rewarding, but unreliable, strategy $s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}$.

This observation highlights how the definition of “best search strategy” is arguable, and how in some contexts it could not coincide with the classical notion of maximizer of a given energy: after all, what does “best” mean, is it “most rewarding” or “safest”? Thus, it may be appropriate to define new efficiency functionals that, rather than depending on an “exact choice” of the fractional exponent $s \in (0, 1)$, take into account a probability measure in $(0, 1)$ that allows the existence of an error range for the forager. This new approach will be investigated by the authors in a forthcoming work.

Foragers and targets uniformly distributed in some regions

Now we focus our attention on the study of the functionals in equation (5.9). In this case, the forager starting position and the prey location are replaced by uniform densities in disjoint subsets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$. We begin by analyzing the continuity of these functionals with respect to the fractional exponent $s \in (0, 1]$.

Proposition 5.13. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected. For every $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and measurable sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$, let us denote by $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ any of the efficiency functionals in (5.9).*

Then, $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$.

The following result can be considered as the set-dependent counterpart of Theorem 5.6.

Theorem 5.14. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and smooth and disjoint sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$, it holds that

$$(5.23) \quad \inf_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = 0.$$

Moreover, we have that

$$(5.24) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty).$$

From Theorem 5.14 we deduce that we can extend by continuity also the Dirichlet functionals in (5.9) to the whole compact interval $[0, 1]$. From now on, for $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, we will adopt the notation

$$(5.25) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(0, T) := \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T),$$

for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$ satisfying the hypothesis of Theorem 5.14.

In Theorems 5.7 and 5.8 we have established that the Neumann and Dirichlet functionals in (5.6) have a common feature. Indeed, if the prey location $x \in \Omega$ is in a sufficiently small neighborhood of the forager starting position $y \in \Omega$, then $\mathcal{E}_{j, D}^{x, y}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{j, N}^{x, y}$ attain their maximum for some value close to $s = 0$.

This characteristic is somewhat preserved if we consider the set-dependent functionals in (5.9). Indeed, we can show that if Ω_1, Ω_2 are close enough (in a sense that

will be made precise later), then also for the functionals in (5.9) a strongly nonlocal search strategy will be preferred.

Before stating the precise results we fix some notation. For each $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $r \in (0, +\infty)$ we denote

$$(5.26) \quad r_y B := \{r(x - y) + y \quad \text{s.t. } x \in B\}.$$

Theorem 5.15. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $r = r_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for any smooth and disjoint sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_r(y)$ it holds that

$$(5.27) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)}, T \right) \quad \text{with } s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Moreover, let $K \Subset \Omega$ be star-shaped with respect to some $y \in K$. Then, for all $j \in \{2, 3\}$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, there exists some $r = r_{\varepsilon, K, T, \Omega}$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset r_y K$ are smooth and disjoint it holds that

$$(5.28) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T).$$

As a consequence of Theorems 5.14 and 5.15 we can deduce that the most rewarding strategy may not be the safest, similarly to what happens for the functional $\mathcal{E}_{1, D}$ (recall Remark 5.9). Also, a result analogous to Theorem 5.15 holds true when considering the Neumann functionals in (5.9).

Theorem 5.16. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $r = r_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for any smooth and disjoint sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_r(y)$ and for each $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ it holds that

$$(5.29) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(j)}, T \right) \quad \text{with } s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(j)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

5.2 Mathematical framework for the efficiency functionals

Preliminary results and asymptotics

In this section we establish some technical results regarding the efficiency functionals in (5.5), (5.6) and (5.9). These are the main analytical tools that we will use to prove the results stated in the introduction.

In Section 5.2 we provide some estimates for the functionals in (5.5) and (5.7). This is the content of Lemma 5.23, Theorem 5.25 and Corollary 5.27. These results will be employed in Section 5.3 in order to discuss the environmental scenario where the prey is in proximity of the forager starting location, and thus to prove Theorems 5.7, 5.8, 5.15 and 5.16. Moreover, we establish the limits of the Dirichlet functionals in (5.6) and (5.9) as $s \searrow 0$ as stated in Lemma 5.29. These asymptotics will be used to prove Theorems 5.6, 5.14, 5.7 and 5.15.

To conclude, in Theorem 5.31 and Corollary 5.32 we show that the Neumann functionals in (5.3), (5.4), (5.5), (5.7) and (5.8) do not vanish for $s \searrow 0$, and we provide upper and lower bounds for their \liminf and \limsup . These results will be used in the proofs of Theorem 5.8 and 5.16.

To prove these results, it is useful to recall some properties regarding the fractional heat kernels r_D^s and r_N^s . It is well-known that for each $s \in (0, 1)$ these two kernels can be written for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$ as

$$(5.30) \quad r_D^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl \quad \text{and} \quad r_N^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl,$$

where p_D^Ω and p_N^Ω are the classical Dirichlet and Neumann heat kernels in Ω , while μ_t^s is the density of a s -stable subordinator in $(0, +\infty)$ (see e.g. Definition 3.17). For a proof of this latter fact see for instance Propositions 3.21 and 4.17.

If $s = 1$, the kernels r_N^1 and r_D^1 coincide respectively with the classical kernels p_N^Ω and p_D^Ω . Furthermore, we also know that the density μ_t^s admits the explicit

representation formula

$$(5.31) \quad \mu_t^s(l) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) du \text{ for all } (l, s) \in (0, +\infty) \times (0, 1),$$

see Proposition 3.1 in [KV18].

Moreover, we also recall the following fact on the spectral representation of r_D^s and r_N^s . In what follows we denote by $\{\zeta_{D,k}\}_k$ and $\{\zeta_{N,k}\}_k$ two orthonormal basis of $L^2(\Omega)$ satisfying

$$(5.32) \quad \begin{cases} -\Delta \zeta_{D,k} = \beta_{D,k} \zeta_{D,k} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \zeta_{D,k} \in H_0^1(\Omega), \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} -\Delta \zeta_{N,k} = \beta_{N,k} \zeta_{N,k} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial \zeta_{N,k}}{\partial \nu} = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < \beta_{D,1} < \beta_{D,2} \dots$ and $0 = \beta_{N,0} < \beta_{N,1} < \dots$ are respectively the eigenvalues of the Laplace operator with homogeneous Dirichlet and homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions.

Thus, thanks to Theorems 3.8 and 4.9, we can rewrite the Dirichlet and Neumann kernels r_D^s and r_N^s as

$$(5.33) \quad \begin{aligned} r_D^s(t, x, y) &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \zeta_{D,k}(x) \zeta_{D,k}(y) \exp(-t\beta_{D,k}^s) \\ \text{and} \quad r_N^s(t, x, y) &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \zeta_{N,k}(x) \zeta_{N,k}(y) \exp(-t\beta_{N,k}^s), \end{aligned}$$

for all $s \in (0, 1]$ and $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$.

Now, we establish some results on μ_t^s . In what follows we recall a scaling property for the density μ_t^s of the s -stable subordinator. For the convenience of the reader the statement is proved.

Lemma 5.17. *Let $l \in (0, +\infty)$, $t \in (0, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$.*

Then, we have that

$$(5.34) \quad \mu_t^s(l) = \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \mu_1^s\left(\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}}\right).$$

Proof. Let $\alpha := u^s \cos(\pi s)$, $\beta := u^s \sin(\pi s)$ and

$$g(\alpha, \beta) := e^{-t\alpha} \sin(t\beta).$$

With this notation, we integrate by parts the expression on the right-hand side of (5.31) and obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_t^s(l) &= -\frac{1}{l\pi} e^{-lu} g(\alpha, \beta) \Big|_0^{+\infty} + \frac{1}{\pi l} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} \frac{d}{du} g(\alpha, \beta) du \\
 (5.35) \quad &= 0 + \frac{1}{\pi l} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} e^{-t\alpha} s t u^{s-1} (-\cos(\pi s) \sin(t\beta) + \sin(\pi s) \cos(t\beta)) du \\
 &= \frac{s t}{\pi l} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} e^{-tu^s \cos(\pi s)} u^{s-1} \sin(\pi s - tu^s \sin(\pi s)) du.
 \end{aligned}$$

We employ the change of variable $v = ut^{\frac{1}{s}}$ and infer from the last identity that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_t^s(l) &= \frac{s}{\pi l} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} v} e^{-v^s \cos(\pi s)} v^{s-1} \sin(\pi s - v^s \sin(\pi s)) dv \\
 &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \frac{st^{\frac{1}{s}}}{\pi l} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} v} e^{-v^s \cos(\pi s)} v^{s-1} \sin(\pi s - v^s \sin(\pi s)) dv \\
 &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \mu_1^s \left(\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \right). \quad \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we discuss some asymptotic estimates for the the density $\mu_t^s(l)$ in l . As it is recalled in [Bog+09] by R. Song and proved by Skorohod in [Sko61], one has that

$$(5.36) \quad \mu_1^s(l) \sim 2\pi\Gamma(1+s) \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \frac{1}{l^{1+s}}, \quad \text{for } l \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Using this estimate and Lemma 5.17 on the time-scaling property of μ_t^s one obtains an interesting asymptotic expansion in the forthcoming Lemma 5.18. As a side comment, we point out that the asymptotic properties of this type of distributions are relevant to understand how the tail of μ_t^s changes by varying the fractional parameter s , which in turn provides some important information about the optimization problem that we analyze in this chapter.

Lemma 5.18. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $t \in (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, we have that

$$(5.37) \quad \mu_t^s(t) \sim 2\pi\Gamma(1+s) \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \frac{t}{l^{1+s}}, \quad \text{for } l \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Proof. Thanks to Lemma 5.17, we know that for each $s \in (0, 1)$, $l \in (0, +\infty)$ and $t \in (0, +\infty)$ one has that

$$\mu_t^s(l) = \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \mu_1^s \left(\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \right).$$

Thus, using this identity and the estimate in (5.36) one readily obtains that

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_t^s(l) &\sim \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} 2\pi\Gamma(1+s) \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \frac{t^{\frac{1+s}{s}}}{l^{1+s}} \\ &= 2\pi\Gamma(1+s) \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \frac{t}{l^{1+s}},\end{aligned}$$

for $l \rightarrow +\infty$. □

The following theorem provides similar estimates to the one given in (5.37) in the range $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$. Here, the constants involved are less accurate than the one appearing in (5.37), but on the other hand we gain some important information. In particular, while the estimate in (5.37) holds true for $l \rightarrow +\infty$, the ones that we prove below are true for each $l \in (t^{\frac{1}{s}}, +\infty)$. This additional information will be used several times.

Theorem 5.19. *Let $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $t \in (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, there exists some constant $C_1 \in (0, +\infty)$, independent of s and l , such that

$$(5.38) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{stC_1}{\pi l^{1+s}} &\leq \mu_t^s(l) && \text{for all } l \in \left(t^{\frac{1}{s}}, +\infty\right) \\ \text{and} \quad \mu_t^s(l) &\leq \frac{st\Gamma(1+s)}{l^{1+s}} && \text{for all } l \in (0, +\infty). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Thanks to the scaling property proved in Lemma 5.17, it is enough to show the result for $t = 1$. Indeed, if for $t = 1$ the inequalities in (5.38) hold true, then if $t > 1$ and $l \geq t^{\frac{1}{s}}$, we have in view of (11.66) that

$$\mu_t^s(l) = \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \mu_1^s\left(\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}}\right) \geq \frac{sC_1 t}{\pi l^{1+s}}.$$

The second inequality in (5.38) is proved similarly. For this reason, we focus our attention on the case $t = 1$.

We will first prove the second inequality in (5.38). If $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, from (5.31) we notice that

$$\mu_1^s(l) \leq \frac{\sin(\pi s)}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} t u^s du \leq \frac{s}{\pi l^{1+s}} \Gamma(1+s),$$

which concludes the proof of the second inequality in (5.38).

Now we focus on the proof of the first inequality. To do so, we observe that thanks to equation (5.35) one has that

$$\mu_1^s(l) = \frac{s}{\pi l} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} e^{-u^s \cos(\pi s)} u^{s-1} \sin(\pi s - u^s \sin(\pi s)) du.$$

We perform the change of variable $lu = \theta$ and obtain that

$$(5.39) \quad \begin{aligned} \mu_s^1(l) &= \frac{s}{\pi l^{1+s}} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\theta} e^{-\frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \cos(\pi s)} \theta^{s-1} \sin\left(\pi s - \frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \sin(\pi s)\right) d\theta \\ &=: \frac{s}{\pi l^{1+s}} f(s, l), \end{aligned}$$

where by construction $f(s, l) > 0$ for each $l \in (0, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$.

Now we observe that, for each $\theta \geq 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$,

$$(5.40) \quad \left| e^{-\theta} e^{-\frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \cos(\pi s)} \theta^{s-1} \sin\left(\pi s - \frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \sin(\pi s)\right) \right| \leq e^{-\theta}.$$

Thus, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} \int_1^{+\infty} e^{-\theta} e^{-\frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \cos(\pi s)} \theta^{s-1} \sin\left(\pi s - \frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \sin(\pi s)\right) d\theta = 0.$$

Also, by using the change of variable $\theta^s = l^s z$ we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^1 e^{-\theta} e^{-\frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \cos(\pi s)} \theta^{s-1} \sin\left(\pi s - \frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \sin(\pi s)\right) d\theta \\ &= \frac{l^s}{s} \int_0^{\frac{1}{l^s}} e^{-lz^{\frac{1}{s}}} e^{-z \cos(\pi s)} \sin(\pi s - z \sin(\pi s)) dz \\ &= l^s \int_0^{+\infty} \chi_{[0, l^{-s}]} e^{-lz^{\frac{1}{s}}} e^{-z \cos(\pi s)} \frac{\sin(\pi s - z \sin(\pi s))}{s} dz. \end{aligned}$$

If $s \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$ we also notice that

$$\left| \chi_{[0, l^{-s}]} e^{-lz^{\frac{1}{s}}} e^{-z \cos(\pi s)} \frac{\sin(\pi s - z \sin(\pi s))}{s} \right| \leq \pi e^{-\frac{z}{2}} (1+z),$$

and therefore, since $l \geq 1$, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} \int_0^1 e^{-\theta} e^{-\frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \cos(\pi s)} \theta^{s-1} \sin\left(\pi s - \frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \sin(\pi s)\right) d\theta = \pi \int_0^1 e^{-z} (1-z) dz.$$

Consequently, for each $l \geq 1$

$$(5.41) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} f(s, l) = \pi \int_0^1 e^{-z}(1-z) dz = \frac{\pi}{e}.$$

We also observe that, if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$,

$$\left| e^{-\theta} e^{-\frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \cos(\pi s)} \theta^{s-1} \sin\left(\pi s - \frac{\theta^s}{l^s} \sin(\pi s)\right) \right| \leq e^{-\theta} \theta^{s-1},$$

for all $\theta \in (0, +\infty)$.

As a consequence, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we evince that

$$(5.42) \quad \lim_{l \rightarrow +\infty} f(s, l) = \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(s) > 0,$$

for all $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$.

Besides, by the definition of $f(s, l)$, we have that $f \in C((0, \frac{1}{2}) \times (1, +\infty))$ and

$$(5.43) \quad f(s, l) > 0 \quad \text{for all } (s, l) \in \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right] \times [1, +\infty).$$

Therefore, using (5.41), (5.42) and (5.43) we deduce that there exists some $C_1 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$C_1 \leq f(s, l) \quad \text{for all } (s, l) \in \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right) \times [1, +\infty).$$

In light of this observation and equation (5.39) we deduce that

$$\frac{C_1 s}{\pi l^{1+s}} \leq \mu_1^s(l). \quad \square$$

Structural results for the efficiency functionals

Now we develop the main technical tools that will be employed in the proofs of the results contained in Sections 5.1 and 5.1.

In what follows we adopt the subscript $*$ to refer to the fact that the functional considered can be the one associated with both the Dirichlet and the Neumann case.

We begin by recalling here the following estimates for the classical Dirichlet heat kernel in relation to the classical heat kernel. Using the Weak Maximum Principle for the heat equation one can show that

$$(5.44) \quad p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) \leq \frac{1}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

On compact subsets of Ω and for finite time spans, one can prove the following lower bound for $p_D^\Omega(t, x, y)$.

Lemma 5.20 (See Lemma 2.1 in [Zha02]). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, there exists a constant $T_\Omega \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $K \Subset \Omega$, if we define

$$(5.45) \quad T_{K,\Omega} := \min \left\{ T_\Omega, \min_{x \in K} \frac{d^2(x, \partial\Omega)}{2} \right\},$$

then there exist two constants $c_1, c_2 \in (0, +\infty)$, depending on K and Ω , such that

$$(5.46) \quad p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) \geq \frac{c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2|x-y|^2}{t}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, T_{K,\Omega}] \times K \times K.$$

Using the Weak Maximum Principle, it is also possible to compare the Neumann heat kernel with the Dirichlet one, as better specified in the following result.

Theorem 5.21. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $K' \Subset \Omega$.*

Then, for each $s \in (0, 1]$ we have that

$$(5.47) \quad r_D^s(t, x, y) \leq r_N^s(t, x, y) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

Furthermore, if $K \subseteq K' \Subset \Omega$ is star-shaped with respect to some $x_0 \in K$, there exist some constants $C_{K',\Omega}, c_{K',\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\varepsilon_0 \in (0, 1)$, depending on K' and Ω , such that

$$(5.48) \quad r_N^s(t, x, y) \leq C_{K',\Omega} r_D^s(t, x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) + c_{K',\Omega} \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times K \times K,$$

for each $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$, where $(x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) := (\varepsilon x + (1 - \varepsilon)x_0, \varepsilon y + (1 - \varepsilon)x_0)$.

Proof. We begin by proving the lower bound in (5.47). To do so, we observe that thanks to the Maximum Principle for the heat equation, one has that

$$p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) \leq p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

Therefore, using (5.30) and the latter inequality, we obtain that

$$r_D^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl \leq \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl = r_N^s(t, x, y),$$

for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$. This concludes the proof of (5.47).

Now we show (5.48). Thanks to Theorem 3.2.9 in [Dav90], we have that there exists some constant c_Ω such that

$$(5.49) \quad p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) \leq c_\Omega \max \left\{ 1, \frac{1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \right\} \exp \left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6t} \right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

Furthermore, if $K \subseteq K' \Subset \Omega$, thanks to Lemma 5.20 we obtain that

$$(5.50) \quad p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) \geq \frac{c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{c_2|x-y|^2}{t} \right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, T_{K',\Omega}] \times K' \times K',$$

where $T_{K',\Omega}$ is introduced in (5.45) and c_1, c_2 depends on K' and Ω .

Up to a translation we can assume that K is star-shaped with respect to $x_0 = 0$. Now we observe that there exists two constants $C_{K',\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\varepsilon_0 \in (0, 1)$, such that

$$C_{K',\Omega} c_1 \geq c_\Omega \quad \text{and} \quad c_2 \varepsilon^2 \leq \frac{1}{6} \quad \text{for all } \varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0).$$

As a consequence, if for each $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$ we call $(x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) = \varepsilon(x, y)$, then from (5.49) and (5.50) we obtain that

$$(5.51) \quad \begin{aligned} C_{K',\Omega} p_D^\Omega(t, x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) - p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) &\geq C_{K',\Omega} \frac{c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{c_2|x_\varepsilon - y_\varepsilon|^2}{t} \right) - \frac{c_\Omega}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6t} \right) \\ &= \frac{c_\Omega}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \left(C_{K',\Omega} \frac{c_1}{c_\Omega} \exp \left(-\varepsilon^2 c_2 \frac{|x-y|^2}{t} \right) - \exp \left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6t} \right) \right) \\ &\geq \frac{c_\Omega}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp \left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6t} \right) \left(\exp \left(-\left(\varepsilon^2 c_2 - \frac{1}{6} \right) \frac{|x-y|^2}{t} \right) - 1 \right) \\ &\geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, T_{K',\Omega}] \times K \times K$.

Thus, using equation (5.30) and the relation in (5.51) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_N^s(t, x, y) &= \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl \\
 &= \int_0^{T_{K', \Omega}} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl + \int_{T_{K', \Omega}}^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl \\
 &\leq C_{K', \Omega} \int_0^{T_{K', \Omega}} p_D^\Omega(l, x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) \mu_t^s(l) dl \\
 &\quad + c_\Omega \int_{T_{K', \Omega}}^{+\infty} \max \left\{ 1, \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \right\} \exp \left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6l} \right) \mu_t^s(l) dl \\
 &\leq C_{K', \Omega} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) \mu_t^s(l) dl + c_{K', \Omega} \\
 &= C_{K', \Omega} r_D^s(t, x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) + c_{K', \Omega},
 \end{aligned}$$

for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times K \times K$, where we defined

$$(5.52) \quad c_{K', \Omega} := \max_{x, y \in K'} \max_{l \in [T_{K', \Omega}, +\infty)} c_\Omega \max \left\{ 1, \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \right\} \exp \left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6l} \right). \quad \square$$

As a useful consequence of Theorem 5.21, we obtain that it is possible to compare the Neumann functional Φ_N with the Dirichlet one Φ_D . The result goes as follows:

Corollary 5.22. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $K' \Subset \Omega$.*

Then, for each $s \in (0, 1]$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that

$$(5.53) \quad \Phi_D^{x, y}(s, T) \leq \Phi_N^{x, y}(s, T) \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C},$$

where

$$(5.54) \quad \mathcal{C} := (\Omega \times \Omega) \setminus \{(p, p) \text{ s.t. } p \in \Omega\} = \{(p, q) \in \Omega \times \Omega \text{ s.t. } p \neq q\}.$$

Furthermore, for each $K \subseteq K' \Subset \Omega$ star-shaped with respect to some $x_0 \in K$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$, there exists some $\varepsilon_0 \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$(5.55) \quad \Phi_N^{x, y}(s, T) \leq C_{K', \Omega} \Phi_D^{x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon}(s, T) + c_{K', \Omega} T \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K),$$

for each $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$, where $(x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon) := (\varepsilon x + (1-\varepsilon)x_0, \varepsilon y + (1-\varepsilon)x_0)$ and $C_{K', \Omega}, c_{K', \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ are given in Theorem 5.21.

Proof. Inequalities (5.53) and (5.55) are respectively obtained by integrating over the time t in $(0, T)$ both sides of (5.47) and (5.48). \square

In Lemma 5.23 below we establish a lower bound for $\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T)$, for $x \in \Omega$ in a sufficiently small neighborhood of $y \in \Omega$.

This estimate is pivotal to determine the asymptotic behavior of the functionals in (5.6) when x approaches y , providing some information on the best search strategy in the environmental scenario addressed in Section 5.1, namely where the forager starts its search in proximity of the target.

Lemma 5.23. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected. If $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$, then there exists some $\hat{\delta} = \hat{\delta}_{s,y,T,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for each $x, z \in B_{\hat{\delta}}(y)$ satisfying $x \neq z$,*

$$(5.56) \quad \Phi_*^{x,z}(s, T) \geq \frac{C_{s,y,\Omega}}{|x - z|^{n-2s}},$$

for some constant $C_{s,y,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$.

Proof. In virtue of inequality (5.53) it is enough to show the result for Φ_D .

Let $y \in \Omega$ and let us denote $d_y := \frac{d(y, \partial\Omega)}{2}$, where

$$d(y, \partial\Omega) := \inf_{x \in \partial\Omega} |x - y|.$$

With this notation we set $B_y := B_{d_y}(y)$.

Now, by (5.45) and (5.46) (used here with $K := B_y$),

$$(5.57) \quad p_D^\Omega(t, x, z) \geq \frac{c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2|x - z|^2}{t}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, z) \in (0, T_{B_y,\Omega}] \times B_y \times B_y.$$

We also observe that for each $x, z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $x \neq z$, the function

$$g(t) := \frac{c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2|x - z|^2}{t}\right)$$

has a maximum in $\varepsilon_{x,z} := \frac{2c_2}{n}|x - z|^2$ and it is increasing in $(0, \varepsilon_{x,z})$ and decreasing in $(\varepsilon_{x,z}, +\infty)$.

We set

$$l_{s,y,T} := \min \left\{ T_{B_y,\Omega}, T^{\frac{1}{s}} \right\}$$

and we choose $\widehat{\delta} = \widehat{\delta}_{s,y,T,\Omega}$ such that

$$(5.58) \quad \widehat{\delta}_{s,y,T,\Omega} := \min \left\{ \left(\frac{nl_{s,y,T}}{2c_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, d_y \right\}.$$

It follows that if $x, z \in B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y)$ with $x \neq z$, then $\varepsilon_{x,z} \leq l_{s,y,T}$ and $x, z \in B_y$.

To simplify the notation, we simply write $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{x,z}$. In this way, by (5.30) and (5.57), if $x, z \in B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y)$ and $x \neq z$ we have that

$$(5.59) \quad \begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,z}(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, z) \mu_t^s(l) dl dt \\ &\geq \int_0^{\varepsilon^s} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^\varepsilon p_D^\Omega(l, x, z) \mu_t^s(l) dl dt \\ &\geq \int_0^{\varepsilon^s} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^\varepsilon \frac{c_1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2|x-z|^2}{l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) dl dt \\ &\geq \frac{C}{\varepsilon^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^{\varepsilon^s} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^\varepsilon \mu_t^s(l) dl dt \end{aligned}$$

where we set $C := c_1 2^{\frac{n}{2}} e^{-n}$.

Now we substitute μ_t^s in (5.59) with the expression in (5.31) and obtain that

$$(5.60) \quad \begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,z}(s, T) &\geq \frac{C}{\pi \varepsilon^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^{\varepsilon^s} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^\varepsilon \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu-tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) du dl dt \\ &= \frac{C}{\pi \varepsilon^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^\varepsilon \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{\varepsilon^s} e^{-lu-tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) dt du dl \\ &=: \mathcal{L}. \end{aligned}$$

Setting $F(t) := e^{-t\alpha} \sin(t\beta)$, with $\alpha := u^s \cos(\pi s)$ and $\beta := u^s \sin(\pi s)$, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ we integrate by parts and see that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T F(t) dt &= -\frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-t\alpha} \sin(t\beta) \Big|_0^T + \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \int_0^T e^{-t\alpha} \cos(t\beta) dt \\ &= -\frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-T\alpha} \sin(T\beta) - \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} e^{-t\alpha} \cos(t\beta) \Big|_0^T - \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha^2} \int_0^T e^{-t\alpha} \sin(t\beta) dt \\ &= -\frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-T\alpha} \sin(T\beta) - \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} e^{-T\alpha} \cos(T\beta) + \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} - \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha^2} \int_0^T F(t) dt. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by replacing α and β with their corresponding values, one obtains that

$$(5.61) \quad \begin{aligned} \int_0^T F(t) dt &= -\frac{\cos(\pi s)}{u^s} e^{-Tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(Tu^s \sin(\pi s)) \\ &\quad - \frac{\sin(\pi s)}{u^s} e^{-Tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \cos(Tu^s \sin(\pi s)) + \frac{\sin(\pi s)}{u^s} \\ &= \frac{1}{u^s} (\sin(\pi s) - e^{-Tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(Tu^s \sin(\pi s) + \pi s)). \end{aligned}$$

By (5.60), (6.58) and the change of variables $(U, L) = (u\varepsilon, \frac{l}{\varepsilon})$ one obtains that

$$(5.62) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &= \frac{C}{\pi \varepsilon^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^{\varepsilon} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-lu}}{u^s} (\sin(\pi s) - e^{-\varepsilon^s u^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(\pi s + \varepsilon^s u^s \sin(\pi s))) du dl \\ &= \frac{C}{\pi \varepsilon^{\frac{n}{2}-s}} \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-LU}}{U^s} (\sin(\pi s) - e^{-U^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(\pi s + U^s \sin(\pi s))) dU dL \\ &=: \frac{C}{\pi \varepsilon^{\frac{n}{2}-s}} \mathcal{J}_s, \end{aligned}$$

where \mathcal{J}_s does not depend on ε and is defined by

$$(5.63) \quad \mathcal{J}_s := \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-LU}}{U^s} (\sin(\pi s) - e^{-U^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(\pi s + U^s \sin(\pi s))) dU dL.$$

Note also that by construction

$$\mathcal{J}_s = \frac{1}{\varepsilon^s} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{2}}^{\varepsilon} \int_0^{\varepsilon^s} \mu_t^s(l) dt dl,$$

which means that $\mathcal{J}_s \in (0, +\infty)$, since $\mu_t^s(l) \in (0, +\infty)$ for each s, t and l .

Accordingly, from (5.60) and (5.62),

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,z}(s, T) &\geq \frac{C\pi^{-1}}{\varepsilon^{n-2s}} \mathcal{J}_s \\ &= \frac{2^s e^{-n} c_1 n^{\frac{n}{2}-s}}{\pi c_2^{\frac{n}{2}-s} |x-z|^{n-2s}} \mathcal{J}_s \\ &\geq \frac{C_{y,\Omega}}{|x-z|^{n-2s}} \mathcal{J}_s \\ &= \frac{C_{s,y,\Omega}}{|x-z|^{n-2s}}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have defined

$$(5.64) \quad C_{y,\Omega} := \min_{s \in (0,1)} \frac{2^s e^{-n} c_1 n^{\frac{n}{2}-s}}{\pi c_2^{\frac{n}{2}-s}} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{s,y,\Omega} := C_{y,\Omega} \mathcal{J}_s. \quad \square$$

As a consequence of Lemma 5.23, we have that if x approaches y , then the functional $\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T)$ diverges to infinity as far as $n > 2s$.

In the following result we make this statement precise. In particular, we show that divergence holds true as far as $n \geq 2s$.

Theorem 5.24. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected and $T \in (0, +\infty)$. If $n \geq 2$ or $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$ we have that*

$$(5.65) \quad \lim_{(x,y) \rightarrow (z,z)} \Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) = +\infty$$

$$(5.66) \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_*^{z,z}(s, T) = +\infty,$$

for each $z \in \Omega$.

Proof. We will prove only the Dirichlet case, since the Neumann one follows easily from the Dirichlet one and (5.47).

We first focus on the proof of (5.66). Using the identity (5.30), equations (5.45) and (5.46) together with the formula in (5.31) we deduce that if

$$\delta_{s,x,T} := \min \left\{ T_{x,\Omega}, T_s^{\frac{1}{s}} \right\},$$

where $T_{x,\Omega}$ is given in (5.45), then for each $\delta \in (0, \delta_{s,x,T})$ it holds that

$$(5.67) \quad \begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, x) \mu_t^s(l) dl dt \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, x) \int_0^T \mu_t^s(l) dt dl \\ &\geq \int_0^\delta \frac{c_1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^{\delta^s} \mu_t^s(l) dt dl \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\delta \frac{c_1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^{\delta^s} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) du dt dl \\ &\geq \frac{c_1}{\pi \delta^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^\delta \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{\delta^s} e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) dt du dl, \end{aligned}$$

where c_1 is introduced in (5.46).

Now, in light of (6.58) and (5.67), and using the change of variables $(L, U) = (\frac{l}{\delta}, u\delta)$, we find that

(5.68)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \\
& \geq \frac{c_1}{\pi \delta^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^\delta \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{\delta^s} e^{-lu-tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) dt du dl \\
& = \frac{c_1}{\pi \delta^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^\delta \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} \frac{1}{u^s} (\sin(\pi s) - e^{-\delta^s u^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(\delta^s u^s \sin(\pi s) + \pi s)) du dl \\
& = \frac{c_1}{\pi \delta^{\frac{n}{2}-s}} \int_0^1 \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-LU} \frac{1}{U^s} (\sin(\pi s) - e^{-U^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(U^s \sin(\pi s) + \pi s)) dU dL \\
& = : \frac{c_1}{\pi \delta^{\frac{n}{2}-s}} \mathcal{G}_s.
\end{aligned}$$

We also observe that \mathcal{G}_s does not depend on δ and by construction

$$\mathcal{G}_s = \frac{1}{\delta^s} \int_0^\delta \int_0^{\delta^s} \mu_t^s(l) dt dl,$$

which means that $\mathcal{G}_s \in (0, +\infty)$, since $\mu_t^s(l) \in (0, +\infty)$ for each $s \in (0, 1)$, $t \in (0, +\infty)$ and $l \in (0, +\infty)$.

Therefore, recalling (5.68) we deduce that

$$\Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \geq \lim_{\delta \searrow 0} \frac{c_1}{\pi \delta^{\frac{n}{2}-s}} \mathcal{G}_s = +\infty,$$

if either $n \geq 2$ or $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$.

Hence, to complete the proof of (5.66), it is left to consider the case $n = 1$ and $s = \frac{1}{2}$. When $s = \frac{1}{2}$ equation (5.31) boils down to

$$(5.69) \quad \mu_t^{\frac{1}{2}}(l) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} \sin\left(tu^{\frac{1}{2}}\right) du.$$

Therefore, using the latter identity, (5.45) and (5.46) we obtain that there ex-

ists $T_{x,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $\delta \in (0, T_{x,\Omega})$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_D^{x,x} \left(\frac{1}{2}, T \right) &= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x, x) \mu_t^{\frac{1}{2}}(l) dl dt \\
 &\geq \int_0^\delta \int_0^T p_D^\Omega(l, x, x) \mu_t^{\frac{1}{2}}(l) dt dl \\
 &\geq c_1 \int_0^\delta \int_0^T \frac{1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} \mu_t^{\frac{1}{2}}(l) dt dl \\
 &= \frac{c_1}{\pi} \int_0^\delta \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-lu} \sin \left(tu^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) du dt dl \\
 &= \frac{c_1}{\pi} \int_0^\delta \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^T \frac{1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-lu} \sin \left(tu^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) dt du dl \\
 &= \frac{c_1}{\pi} \int_0^\delta \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} e^{-lu} \left(1 - \cos \left(Tu^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right) \frac{1}{u^{\frac{1}{2}}} du dl,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$ has been introduced in (5.46).

Furthermore, by making the change of variable $lu = a$ in the l variable we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_D^{x,x} \left(\frac{1}{2}, T \right) &\geq \frac{c_1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{\delta u} \frac{e^{-a}}{a^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left(1 - \cos \left(Tu^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right) \frac{1}{u} da du \\
 (5.70) \quad &\geq \frac{c_1}{\pi} \int_{\frac{1}{8}}^{+\infty} \int_0^{\delta u} \frac{e^{-a}}{a^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left(1 - \cos \left(Tu^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right) \frac{1}{u} da du \\
 &=: \mathcal{I}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We also observe that for each $u \geq \frac{1}{8}$ one has that

$$0 < c := \int_0^1 \frac{e^{-a}}{a^{\frac{1}{2}}} da \leq \int_0^{\delta u} \frac{e^{-a}}{a^{\frac{1}{2}}} da \leq \Gamma \left(\frac{1}{2} \right).$$

Moreover, defining

$$\tilde{k} := \min \left\{ k \in \mathbb{N} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad k \geq -\frac{1}{4} + \frac{T}{2\pi\delta^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\},$$

we find that $\left(\frac{\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi\tilde{k}}{T}\right)^2 > \frac{1}{\delta}$, and thus we deduce from (5.70) that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I} &\geq \frac{cc_1}{\pi} \int_{\frac{1}{\delta}}^{+\infty} \frac{1 - \cos\left(Tu^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)}{u} du \\ &\geq \frac{cc_1}{\pi} \sum_{k=\tilde{k}}^{+\infty} \int_{\left(\frac{\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi k}{T}\right)^2}^{\left(\frac{3\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi k}{T}\right)^2} \frac{du}{u} \\ &= \frac{2cc_1}{\pi} \sum_{k=\tilde{k}}^{+\infty} \ln\left(\frac{\frac{3\pi}{2k} + 2\pi}{\frac{\pi}{2k} + 2\pi}\right) \\ &=: \mathcal{II}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, using Taylor's expansion we infer that there exists some $\tilde{K} \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\tilde{K} \geq \tilde{k}$ such that

$$(5.71) \quad \mathcal{II} \geq \frac{2cc_1}{\pi} \sum_{k=\tilde{K}}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{2k} + o\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right) = +\infty.$$

This concludes the proof of (5.66).

Now we prove (5.65). If $n > 2s$, equation (5.65) is a direct consequence of inequality (5.56). Therefore, to conclude the proof of (5.65) it is left to show the case $n = 1$ and $s = \frac{1}{2}$. In order to achieve this, we observe that if $V_x \Subset \Omega$ is some neighborhood of x in Ω , then there exists some $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for each $k \geq k_0$ it holds that $(x_k, y_k) \in V_x \times V_x$.

Thus, if we define $\varepsilon_k := |x_k - y_k|^2$, in view of (5.45) and (5.46), and recall-

ing (5.69), we obtain that, if $k \geq k_0$,

(5.72)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_D^{x_k, y_k} \left(\frac{1}{2}, T \right) &= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(l, x_k, y_k) \mu_t^{\frac{1}{2}}(l) dl dt \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^T p_D^\Omega(l, x_k, y_k) \mu_t^{\frac{1}{2}}(l) dt dl \\
 &\geq \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{T_{V_x, \Omega}} \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{c_1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2 \varepsilon_k}{l}\right) e^{-lu} \sin\left(tu^{\frac{1}{2}}\right) du dt dl, \\
 &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{T_{V_x, \Omega}} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{c_1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2 \varepsilon_k}{l}\right) e^{-lu} \frac{\left(1 - \cos\left(Tu^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)\right)}{u^{\frac{1}{2}}} du dl \\
 &\geq \frac{c_1}{\pi} \int_{\frac{2}{T_{V_x, \Omega}}}^{+\infty} \int_{\frac{1}{u}}^{\frac{2}{u}} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2 \varepsilon_k}{l}\right) e^{-lu} \frac{\left(1 - \cos\left(Tu^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)\right)}{u^{\frac{1}{2}}} dl du,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{V_x, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ and $c_1, c_2 \in (0, +\infty)$ are given respectively in (5.45) and (5.46).

Now we choose $\tilde{j}, j(\varepsilon_k) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{j} &:= \min \left\{ j \in \mathbb{N} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad j \geq \frac{T}{2\pi} \left(\frac{2}{T_{V_x, \Omega}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{1}{4} \right\} \\
 \text{and} \quad j(\varepsilon_k) &:= \max \left\{ j \in \mathbb{N} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad j \leq \frac{T}{2\pi \varepsilon_k^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{3}{4} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that if ε_k is chosen small enough, then $\tilde{j} < j(\varepsilon_k)$.

With this choices one has that

$$(5.73) \quad \left(\frac{\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi\tilde{j}}{T} \right)^2 \geq \frac{2}{T_{V_x, \Omega}} \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{3\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j(\varepsilon_k)}{T} \right)^2 \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon_k}.$$

Therefore, with this latter notation we obtain from (5.72) that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_D^{x_k, y_k} \left(\frac{1}{2}, T \right) &\geq \frac{c_1}{\pi} \sum_{j=\tilde{j}}^{j(\varepsilon_k)} \int_{\left(\frac{\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2}^{\left(\frac{3\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2} \int_{\frac{1}{u}}^{\frac{2}{u}} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2 \varepsilon_k}{l}\right) e^{-lu} \frac{1}{u^{\frac{1}{2}}} dl du \\
 &\geq \frac{c_1}{\pi} \sum_{j=\tilde{j}}^{j(\varepsilon_k)} \int_{\left(\frac{\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2}^{\left(\frac{3\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2} \int_{\frac{1}{u}}^{\frac{2}{u}} \exp(-c_2 u \varepsilon_k) e^{-2} dl du \\
 &= \frac{c_1 e^{-2}}{\pi} \sum_{j=\tilde{j}}^{j(\varepsilon_k)} \int_{\left(\frac{\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2}^{\left(\frac{3\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2} \frac{1}{u} \exp(-c_2 u \varepsilon_k) du.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we deduce from (5.73) that since $u \leq \left(\frac{3\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j(\varepsilon_k)}{T}\right)^2$, then $u\varepsilon_k \leq 1$, and thus from the latter computations we obtain that

$$(5.74) \quad \begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x_k, y_k} \left(\frac{1}{2}, T \right) &\geq \frac{c_1 e^{-c_2}}{\pi e^2} \sum_{j=\tilde{j}}^{j(\varepsilon_k)} \int_{\left(\frac{\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2}^{\left(\frac{3\pi}{2T} + \frac{2\pi j}{T}\right)^2} \frac{1}{u} du \\ &= \frac{2c_1 e^{-c_2}}{\pi e^2} \sum_{j=\tilde{j}}^{j(\varepsilon_k)} \ln \left(\frac{\frac{3\pi}{2k} + 2\pi}{\frac{\pi}{2k} + 2\pi} \right). \end{aligned}$$

As we observed in (5.71), one has that

$$\sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \ln \left(\frac{\frac{3\pi}{2k} + 2\pi}{\frac{\pi}{2k} + 2\pi} \right) = +\infty.$$

With reference to that, from (5.74) and the latter observation we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \Phi_D^{x_k, y_k} \left(\frac{1}{2}, T \right) &\geq \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{2c_1 e^{-c_2}}{\pi e^2} \sum_{j=\tilde{j}}^{j(\varepsilon_k)} \ln \left(\frac{\frac{3\pi}{2k} + 2\pi}{\frac{\pi}{2k} + 2\pi} \right) \\ &= \frac{2c_1 e^{-c_2}}{\pi e^2} \sum_{j=\tilde{j}}^{+\infty} \ln \left(\frac{\frac{3\pi}{2k} + 2\pi}{\frac{\pi}{2k} + 2\pi} \right) \\ &= +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of (5.65). \square

In the following result we give some upper bounds for the functional $\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T)$. These estimates, together with the lower bound in (5.56), will turn out to be pivotal in order to determine the most rewarding search strategy in a regime where the initial position of the forager is close to the one of the prey, and thus prove Theorems 5.7 and 5.8.

In the Dirichlet framework, the behavior of the functional $\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)$ for x approaching y could be deduced from the already known estimates on the Green function $G_D^\Omega(x, y)$ of the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian, see Theorem 5.4 in [SVc03].

Indeed, the Green function is given by

$$G_D^\Omega(x, y) := \int_0^{+\infty} r_D^s(t, x, y) dt,$$

for $x \neq y$, and therefore

$$\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) \leq G_D^\Omega(x, y),$$

for each $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$ with $x \neq y$ and $s \in (0, 1)$.

Nevertheless, for our optimization purposes we need upper bounds where the dependence of the constants on the fractional exponent $s \in (0, 1)$ is known. In this sense, the inequalities provided in the following result are more suitable in this context than the ones available in the literature for G_D^Ω .

Before stating and proving the theorem, we fix the following notation. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$ we define the set

$$(5.75) \quad A_{n,s} := \left(0, 1 + \frac{n}{2} - s\right) \cap \left[\frac{n}{2} - s, 1 + \frac{n}{2} - s\right).$$

Theorem 5.25. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected. Moreover, let $K \Subset \Omega$ be star-shaped with respect to some $x_0 \in K$.*

Then, for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$, there exists some $C_{,K,T,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $n \geq 3$ then*

$$(5.76) \quad \Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{*,K,T,\Omega}}{|x - y|^{n-2s}} \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K),$$

where \mathcal{C} is given in (5.54).

Furthermore, if $n \leq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s}$ there exists some $C_{*,\mu,K,T,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(5.77) \quad \Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{*,\mu,K,T,\Omega}}{|x - y|^{2\mu}} \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K),$$

where $A_{n,s}$ is defined (6.34).

Proof. We will first show the result for the Dirichlet case. To this aim, we recall the following identity

$$(5.78) \quad \int_0^{+\infty} r_D^s(t, x, y) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C},$$

see for instance equation (2.4) in [SVc03]. For the convenience of the reader we give a proof of it in the appendix, see Proposition 5.34.

We first prove (5.76). If $((x, y), T) \in \mathcal{C} \times (0, +\infty)$, thanks to the identity in (5.78) we have that

$$\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) = \int_0^T r_D^s(t, x, y) dt \leq \int_0^{+\infty} r_D^s(t, x, y) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt.$$

Using inequality (6.42) and the change of variable $a = \frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}$ we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{t^{s-1}}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}\right) dt \\ (5.79) \quad &= \frac{4^{-s}}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} \Gamma(s)} \frac{1}{|x-y|^{n-2s}} \int_0^{+\infty} a^{\frac{n}{2}-1-s} e^{-a} da \\ &= \frac{4^{-s}}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} \Gamma(s)} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} - s\right)}{|x-y|^{n-2s}}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, by defining the constant

$$(5.80) \quad C_D := \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \frac{4^{-s}}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} \Gamma(s)} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} - s\right),$$

we conclude the proof of (5.76) for the Dirichlet case.

Now, we prove (5.77). To this end, we observe that there exists some constant $c_3 \in (0, +\infty)$, depending on Ω , such that for all $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ it holds that

$$(5.81) \quad p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) \leq \frac{c_3}{t^{\frac{n}{2}+\gamma}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6t}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega,$$

see for instance Theorem 4.6.9 in [Dav90].

Accordingly, using the identity given in equation (5.78) and the inequality in (5.81), we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) &= \int_0^T r_D^s(t, x, y) dt \\ &\leq \int_0^{+\infty} r_D^s(t, x, y) dt \\ (5.82) \quad &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt \\ &\leq \frac{c_3}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}+\gamma-s+1}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6t}\right) dt \\ &= \frac{c_3}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{(6\theta)^{\frac{n}{2}+\gamma-s-1}}{|x-y|^{n-2(s-\gamma)}} e^{-\theta} d\theta \\ &= \frac{C_{s,\gamma,n,\Omega}}{\Gamma(s)} \frac{1}{|x-y|^{n-2(s-\gamma)}}, \end{aligned}$$

where we applied the change of variable $\theta = \frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}$ and we defined

$$C_{s,\gamma,n,\Omega} := c_3 6^{\frac{n}{2}+\gamma-s-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} + \gamma - s\right),$$

for all $\gamma \in (s - \frac{n}{2}, 1) \cap [0, 1)$.

Now, we observe that if we define $\mu := \frac{n}{2} + \gamma - s$, then $\mu \in (0, 1 + \frac{n}{2} - s) \cap [\frac{n}{2} - s, 1 + \frac{n}{2} - s)$, and inequality (5.82) becomes

$$(5.83) \quad \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{c_3}{\Gamma(s)} 6^{\mu-1} \frac{\Gamma(\mu)}{|x-y|^{2\mu}} \leq \frac{C_{D,\mu}}{|x-y|^{2\mu}},$$

where we defined

$$(5.84) \quad C_{D,\mu} := \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \frac{c_3}{\Gamma(s)} 6^{\mu-1} \Gamma(\mu).$$

This concludes the proof of (5.77) for the Dirichlet case.

Employing the result in Corollary 5.22 we prove now (5.76) and (5.77) for the Neumann case. Let $K \Subset \Omega$ and, up to a translation, let us assume that it is star-shaped with respect to $x_0 = 0$.

Then, if $T \in (0, +\infty)$, $n \geq 3$ and $s \in (0, 1)$, using equations (5.79) and (5.55) with $K' = K$ we obtain the existence of some $c_{K,\Omega}, C_{K,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\varepsilon_0 \in (0, 1)$, depending on K and Ω , such that

$$\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq C_{K,\Omega} \Phi_D^{x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon}(s, T) + c_{K,\Omega} T \leq C_{K,\Omega} \frac{C_D \varepsilon^{2s-n}}{|x-y|^{n-2s}} + c_{K,\Omega} T,$$

for all $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$ and $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K)$.

Consequently, if in the last equation we choose $\varepsilon_1 \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$ such that

$$(5.85) \quad \varepsilon_1 \leq \inf_{s \in (0,1)} \left(C_{K,\Omega} C_D \frac{d_K^{2s-n}}{c_{K,\Omega} T} \right)^{\frac{1}{n-2s}},$$

which depends on K, Ω and T , we obtain that for all $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$ it holds that

$$\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{K,T,\Omega}}{|x-y|^{n-2s}},$$

with

$$(5.86) \quad C_{K,T,\Omega} := 2 \sup_{s \in (0,1)} C_n \varepsilon_1^{2s-n} C_{K,\Omega}.$$

Analogously, if $n \leq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s}$, then one deduces from (5.83) and (5.55) that

$$\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq C_{K,\Omega} \Phi_D^{x_\varepsilon, y_\varepsilon}(s, T) + c_{K,\Omega} T \leq C_{K,\Omega} \frac{C_{D,\mu} \varepsilon^{-2\mu}}{|x-y|^{2\mu}} + c_{K,\Omega} T,$$

for all $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$ and $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K)$.

As a result, if we choose some $\varepsilon_2 \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$ satisfying

$$(5.87) \quad \varepsilon_2^{2\mu} \leq C_{K,\Omega} C_{D,\mu} \frac{d_K^{-2\mu}}{c_{K,\Omega} T},$$

which depends on μ, K, Ω and T , we obtain that for all $(x, y) \in \mathcal{K}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$ it holds that

$$\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{\mu,K,T,\Omega}}{|x-y|^{2\mu}},$$

where we set

$$(5.88) \quad C_{\mu,K,T,\Omega} := 2C_{K,\Omega} C_{\mu,\Omega} \varepsilon_2^{-2\mu}. \quad \square$$

Remark 5.26. We note that for the Dirichlet case we obtained that the constants in equation (5.76) and (5.77) can be chosen independently from K and T . In particular, we have proved that if $n \geq 3$, then

$$(5.89) \quad \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{4^{-s} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} - s\right)}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |x-y|^{n-2s}}$$

for all $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C}$. If $n \leq 2$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s}$, where $A_{n,s}$ is given in (6.34), then

$$(5.90) \quad \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{6^{\mu-1} c_3 \Gamma(\mu)}{\Gamma(s) |x-y|^{2\mu}},$$

for all $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C}$.

We now turn our attention to the functional $\tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ defined in (5.7). For this, it is convenient, for every bounded and measurable sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and each $s \in (0, 1)$, to define

$$(5.91) \quad F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s) := \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \frac{dx dy}{|x-y|^{n-2s}}.$$

As a direct consequence of Lemma 5.23 and Theorem 5.25 we obtain the following upper and lower bounds for $\tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$. These bounds will play a crucial role in proving Theorems 5.15 and 5.16.

Corollary 5.27. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected, $K \Subset \Omega$ be star-shaped with respect to some $x_0 \in K$ and $\varepsilon_0 \in (0, 1)$ be given as in Theorem 5.22.*

Then, for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$, if $n \geq 3$, we have that

$$(5.92) \quad \tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{*,K,T,\Omega}}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s) \quad \text{for all } \Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset K,$$

where F^{Ω_1, Ω_2} is given in (5.91).

Furthermore, if $n \leq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s}$, where $A_{n,s}$ is given in (6.34), one has that

$$(5.93) \quad \tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{*,\mu,K,T,\Omega}}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(\frac{n - 2\mu}{2} \right) \quad \text{for all } \Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset K.$$

Moreover, for all $s \in (0, 1]$ we have that

$$(5.94) \quad \tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \geq \frac{C_{s,y,\Omega}}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s),$$

with $C_{s,y,\Omega}$ defined in (5.64).

The following result is devoted to the proof of the continuity of the functionals Φ_* , l_* and \mathcal{A}_* with respect to the space, time and fractional variables. Also, we show that if $n < 2s$ then the limit in (5.65) is finite, and similarly $\Phi_*^{z,z}(s, T) < +\infty$ for each $z \in \Omega$.

Proposition 5.28. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be open, bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, $\Phi_^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $(s, (x, y), T) \in (0, 1] \times \mathcal{C} \times (0, +\infty)$ and $\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) \in C((0, 1] \times \mathcal{C} \times (0, +\infty))$, where \mathcal{C} is given in (5.54).*

Also, if $n = 1$, then $\Phi_^{x,y}(s, T) \in C\left(\left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \times \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)\right)$.*

Moreover, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ there exists some $M \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $l_N^y(s, T), \mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T) \in (0, M)$ for all $(s, y) \in (0, 1] \times \Omega$ and $l_D^y(s, T), \mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T) \in C((0, 1] \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty))$.

Furthermore, there exists some $M \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $l_D^y(s, T), \mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T) \in (0, M)$ for all $(s, y, T) \in (0, 1] \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$

Proof. The positivity of the functionals follows from (5.3), (5.4) and the fact that $r_*^s(t, x, y)$ is strictly positive for all $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$, see for instance Corollaries 3.28 and 4.24.

Now we establish the continuity statement. Thanks to equation (5.33) we have that

$$r_*^s(t, x, y) = \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \zeta_{*,k}(x) \zeta_{*,k}(y) \exp(-t\beta_{*,k}^s),$$

and each term of the series is continuous in $(s, t, x, y) \in (0, 1] \times (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$.

Furthermore, thanks to Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28, we have the existence of some $M \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1]$ and $\delta \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \|\zeta_{*,k}(x) \zeta_{*,k}(y) \exp(-t\beta_{*,k}^s)\|_{C^0(\Omega \times \Omega \times (\varepsilon, 1) \times (\delta, +\infty))} \\ & \leq \sum_{k=0}^M \|\zeta_{*,k}(x) \zeta_{*,k}(y) \exp(-t\beta_{*,k}^s)\|_{C^0(\Omega \times \Omega \times (\varepsilon, 1) \times (\delta, +\infty))} \\ & \quad + C_{*,m_0,\Omega,0}^2 \sum_{k=M}^{+\infty} \beta_{*,k}^{2\alpha(m_0)} \exp(-\delta\beta_{*,k}^\varepsilon) \\ & < +\infty, \end{aligned}$$

where $C_{*,m_0,\Omega,0}$ and $\alpha(m_0)$ are positive constants given in Proposition A.1.

Consequently, $r_*^s(t, x, y)$ is continuous for all $(s, t, x, y) \in (0, 1] \times (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$.

Suppose now that $(\xi, y) \in \mathcal{C}$, and that $\{(s_k, T_k, y_k)\}_k \subset (0, 1] \times (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$ satisfies $(s_k, T_k, y_k) \rightarrow (s, T, y) \in (0, 1] \times (0, +\infty) \times \Omega$. Then, since $r_*^s(t, \xi, y)$ is continuous for all $(s, y) \in (0, 1] \times \Omega$, we have that

$$r_*^{s_k}(t, \xi, y_k) \chi_{(0, T_k)}(t) \rightarrow r_*^s(t, \xi, y) \chi_{(0, T)}(t),$$

for almost every $t \in (0, +\infty)$.

Moreover, if $\tilde{T} := \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} T_k$, then using equations (5.30), (6.42) and (5.49) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} (5.95) \quad \chi_{T_k}(t) r_*^{s_k}(t, \xi, y_k) & \leq \chi_{\tilde{T}}(t) \int_0^{+\infty} p_*^\Omega(l, \xi, y_k) \mu_t^{s_k}(l) dl \\ & \leq \chi_{\tilde{T}}(t) \int_0^{+\infty} C_{*,l} \exp\left(-\frac{|\xi - y_k|^2}{4l}\right) \mu_t^{s_k}(l) dl \\ & \leq \chi_{\tilde{T}}(t) M_* \int_0^{+\infty} \mu_t^{s_k}(l) dl \\ & = \chi_{\tilde{T}}(t) M_*, \end{aligned}$$

where we defined

$$M_* := \sup_{l \in (0, +\infty)} \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} C_{*,l} \exp\left(-\frac{|\xi - y_k|^2}{4l}\right).$$

The last function in (5.95) is in $L^1((0, +\infty))$, and thus by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain that $\Phi_*^{\xi,y}(s, T)$ is continuous for all $(s, y, T) \in (0, 1] \times (\Omega \setminus \{\xi\}) \times (0, +\infty)$, and since it is symmetric with respect to the space variables, we deduce the continuity for all $(s, (\xi, y), T) \in (0, 1] \times \mathcal{C} \times (0, +\infty)$.

If $n = 1$ the eigenfunctions $\zeta_{*,k}$'s are uniformly bounded in $L^\infty(\Omega)$ and the eigenvalues $\beta_{*,k}$'s are proportional to k^2 , for each $k \geq 1$. More precisely, there exist two positive constants $C_*, c_* > 0$ such that

$$c_* k^2 \leq \beta_{*,k} \leq C_* k^2,$$

for each $k \geq 1$, see for instance [Pro87].

Therefore, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} (5.96) \quad r_*^s(t, x, y) &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \zeta_{*,k}(x) \zeta_{*,k}(y) \exp(-t\beta_{*,k}^s) \\ &\leq \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \|\zeta_{*,k}\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)}^2 \exp(-t\beta_{*,k}^s) \\ &\leq M_*^2 \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \exp(-tc_*^s k^{2s}) \\ &=: f_{*,s}(t), \end{aligned}$$

where $\|\zeta_{*,k}\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \leq M_*$ for some $M_* \in (0, +\infty)$ and we adopted the convention $\zeta_{D,0} = 0 = \beta_{D,0}$.

Thus, if $s, s_k \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, then we can choose also $(\xi, y) \in \Omega \times \Omega$, and thanks to (5.96) we have that

$$\chi_{T_k}(t) r_*^{s_k}(t, \xi, y_k) \leq \chi_{\bar{T}}(t) \inf_{k \in \mathbb{N}} f_{*,s_k}(t),$$

and the right-hand side is $L^1(0, +\infty)$.

Repeating the above reasoning, if $n = 1$, we obtain that $\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) \in C\left(\left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right] \times \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)\right)$.

Now, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 l_*^y(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| r_*^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dt \\
 (5.97) \qquad &= \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| \int_0^T r_*^s(t, \xi, y) dt d\xi \\
 &= \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| \Phi_*^{\xi, y}(s, T).
 \end{aligned}$$

Using this identity, the continuity of Φ_* and the estimates in Theorem 5.25, we conclude using the Dominated Convergence Theorem. The proof of the continuity of $\mathcal{A}_*^y(s, T)$ is analogous

Also, if $n \geq 3$, from (5.97) and (6.41) we have that

$$l_D^y(s, T) \leq \frac{C_n}{\Gamma(s)} \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y|^{n-1} d\xi,$$

for some suitable C_n , which proves that l_D^y is uniformly bounded in $(0, 1] \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$ if $n \geq 3$.

The proof of the uniform boundedness in the case $n \leq 2$ is done similarly replacing (6.41) in the above equation with (5.90).

Finally, using 4.28 we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 l_N^y(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| r_N^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dt \\
 &\leq d_{\Omega} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} r_N^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dt \\
 &= d_{\Omega} T.
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof of the boundedness of \mathcal{A}_* is analogous. □

In the following two lemmas we establish the limits as $s \searrow 0$ of the Dirichlet efficiency functionals given in (5.6) and (5.9).

We will show that $\Phi_D, l_D, \mathcal{A}_D, \tilde{\Phi}_D, \tilde{l}_D$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_D$ all go to 0 linearly in s . Moreover, we will also determine the value of the limit for $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}, \mathcal{E}_{3,D}, \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,D}$ so that we will be able to extend them by continuity in $[0, 1]$.

This asymptotic analysis is a fundamental tool in order to establish Theorems 5.6 and 5.14 and the claims in (5.18) and (5.28).

Lemma 5.29. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected, and let \mathcal{C} be as in (5.54).*

Then, for all $((x, y), T) \in \mathcal{C} \times (0, +\infty)$, it holds that

$$(5.98) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = 0,$$

$$(5.99) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \frac{F_D(x, y)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi},$$

$$(5.100) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{3,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \frac{F_D(x, y)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y|^2 F_D(\xi, y) d\xi},$$

where we have defined

$$(5.101) \quad F_D(x, y) := \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{p_D^\Omega(l, x, y)}{l} dl \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C}.$$

Proof. Equation (5.98) is a direct consequence of (6.41) and (5.90), since $\Gamma(s) \rightarrow +\infty$ for $s \searrow 0$.

Now we focus on the proof of (5.99). For this, we claim that

$$(5.102) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{s} = (1 - e^{-T}(T + 1)) F_D(x, y) \quad \text{for all } ((x, y), T) \in \mathcal{C} \times (0, +\infty).$$

Thanks to (5.38) and (6.42), if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ we have that

$$(5.103) \quad \frac{1}{s} \left| p_D^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \right| \leq \frac{t}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}\right) \frac{\Gamma(1 + s)}{l^{1+s}}.$$

This bound together with (5.30), (5.218) and the Dominated Convergence Theorem yields to

$$(5.104) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{r_D^s(t, x, y)}{s} = t e^{-t} F_D(x, y),$$

for all $(t, (x, y)) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathcal{C}$. Therefore, if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, from (5.30) and (5.103) we obtain that

$$(5.105) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{r_D^s(t, x, y)}{s} &\leq \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{t \Gamma(1 + s)}{(4\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}} l^{\frac{n}{2} + s + 1}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}\right) dl \\ &\leq \frac{C_0 t}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} \\ &=: f_{x,y}(t), \end{aligned}$$

where we defined

$$C_0 := \sup_{s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})} \frac{4^s \Gamma(1+s)}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} + s\right).$$

Now, clearly we have that

$$(5.106) \quad f_{x,y} \in L^1((0, T)),$$

and thus from (5.104), (5.105) and (5.106) we can apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem to obtain that

$$(5.107) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{s} = \int_0^T t e^{-t} F_D(x, y) dt = (1 - e^{-T}(T+1)) F_D(x, y).$$

This concludes the proof of (5.102).

Note that using (6.41), (5.90) and (5.102), we obtain that

$$(5.108) \quad \begin{aligned} \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{l_D^y(s, T)}{s} &= \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{1}{s} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| r_D^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dt \\ &= \lim_{s \searrow 0} \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| \frac{\Phi_D^{\xi,y}(s, T)}{s} d\xi \\ &= (1 - e^{-T}(T+1)) \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi, \end{aligned}$$

by means of the Dominated Convergence Theorem. Finally, from (5.102) and (5.108) we deduce that

$$(5.109) \quad \begin{aligned} \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{l_D^y(s, T)} &= \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\int_0^T r_D^s(t, x, y) dt}{\int_0^T \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| r_D^s(t, \xi, y) d\xi dt} \frac{s}{s} \\ &= \frac{F_D(x, y)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi}, \end{aligned}$$

which concludes the proof of (5.99).

It is left to show (5.100). To do so, we observe that applying the same reasoning we used to show (5.108), one can easily prove that

$$(5.110) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T)}{s} = (1 - e^{-T}(T+1)) \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y|^2 F_D(\xi, y) d\xi,$$

for all $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$. From this identity and (5.102) it is immediate to deduce (5.100). \square

The following result can be considered as the set functional version of Lemma 5.29.

Lemma 5.30. *Let Ω be bounded, smooth and connected and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$ be smooth and disjoint.*

Then, for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$, it holds that

$$(5.111) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = 0,$$

$$(5.112) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \frac{|\Omega_2| \tilde{F}_D(\Omega_1, \Omega_2)}{\int_{\Omega_2 \times \Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi dy}$$

$$(5.113) \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \frac{|\Omega_2| \tilde{F}_D(\Omega_1, \Omega_2)}{\int_{\Omega_2 \times \Omega} |\xi - y|^2 F_D(\xi, y) d\xi dy},$$

where

$$(5.114) \quad \tilde{F}_D(\Omega_1, \Omega_2) := \frac{1}{|\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} F_D(x, y) dx dy,$$

and F_D is given in equation (5.101).

Proof. We begin by proving (5.111). We have that

$$\frac{\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T)}{s} = \frac{1}{|\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{s} dx dy.$$

Thanks to equations (6.41) and (5.90), if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, there exists some constant \hat{C}_n depending on n such that

$$(5.115) \quad \frac{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)}{s} \leq \frac{\hat{C}_n}{s\Gamma(s)} \frac{1}{|x - y|^{n-2s}} \leq \frac{C_3}{|x - y|^n} =: g(x, y),$$

where C_3 depends only on Ω . If Ω_1, Ω_2 are smooth and disjoint, then $g \in L^1(\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2)$. Therefore, under these assumptions we can apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem, which together with (5.102) yields to

$$(5.116) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T)}{s} = (1 - e^{-T}(T + 1)) \tilde{F}_D(\Omega_1, \Omega_2).$$

Also, thanks to Lemma 5.40 and the hypotheses on Ω_1, Ω_2 we have that $\tilde{F}_D(\Omega_1, \Omega_2)$ is finite. From this observation and (5.116) one readily deduces (5.111).

Now, we show (5.112). To do so, we claim that

$$(5.117) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\tilde{l}_D^{\Omega_2}(s, T)}{s} = \frac{(1 - e^{-T}(T+1))}{|\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_2 \times \Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi dy,$$

for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$. As a matter of fact

$$\frac{\tilde{l}_D^{\Omega_2}(s, T)}{s} := \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_2} \frac{l_D^y(s, T)}{s} dy.$$

Hence, from (5.115) and the definition of $l_D^y(s, T)$ we infer the existence of some $C_4 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$\frac{l_D^y(s, T)}{s} \leq C_4,$$

for all $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$. Therefore, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we can conclude the proof of (5.117). The limit in equation (5.112) follows easily from (5.116) and (5.117).

Following the same procedure adopted to prove (5.117), one obtains that

$$(5.118) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\tilde{A}_D^{\Omega_2}(s, T)}{s} = \frac{(1 - e^{-T}(T+1))}{|\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_2 \times \Omega} |\xi - y|^2 F_D(\xi, y) d\xi dy,$$

for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Thereby, the limit in equation (5.113) follows easily from (5.116) and (5.118). \square

In the following lemma we study the asymptotic behavior of the Neumann functional $\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T)$ for $s \searrow 0$. In particular, we observe that the limit substantially differs from the one of $\Phi_D^{x,y}$, which was indeed vanishing, see Lemma 5.29. With this result we establish also that the \liminf and \limsup of $\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T)$ for $s \searrow 0$ are controlled by some quantities that do not depend on $x, y \in \Omega$. This feature will let us prove that if the forager starting position and target location are close enough, then the most rewarding search strategy for the Neumann functionals in equation (5.6) is not $s = 0$.

Lemma 5.31. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, there exist $h_1, h_2 \in C([0, +\infty))$ such that for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that

$$(5.119) \quad \frac{h_1(T)}{T} \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{1,N}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{1,N}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{h_2(T)}{T},$$

$$(5.120) \quad \frac{h_1(T)}{h_2(T)M(y)} \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{2,N}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{2,N}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{h_2(T)}{M(y)h_1(T)}$$

(5.121)

$$\text{and} \quad \frac{h_1(T)}{h_2(T)\widetilde{M}(y)} \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{3,N}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{3,N}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{h_2(T)}{\widetilde{M}(y)h_1(T)},$$

for all $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C}$, where we set

$$(5.122) \quad M(y) := \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| d\xi \quad \text{and} \quad \widetilde{M}(y) := \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y|^2 d\xi.$$

Proof. Let $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C}$. Notice that if $t \in (0, +\infty)$ we can write

$$p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} + \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \zeta_{N,k}(x)\zeta_{N,k}(y) \exp(-t \beta_{N,k}),$$

where $\zeta_{N,k}$'s and $\beta_{N,k}$'s are given in (5.32). Now, thanks to Proposition ?? and Lemma 4.29, together with Weyl's law on the asymptotic behavior of the eigenvalues $\beta_{N,k}$'s (see for instance [Pro87]), we have that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \zeta_{N,k}(x)\zeta_{N,k}(y) \exp(-t \beta_{N,k}) = 0,$$

from which we deduce that

$$\lim_{l \rightarrow +\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) = \frac{1}{|\Omega|}.$$

Therefore, there exists some $t_0 \in (1, +\infty)$ such that

$$\frac{1}{2|\Omega|} \leq p_N^\Omega(t, x, y) \quad \text{for all } t \in [t_0, +\infty).$$

Thus, using (5.30), we have that if $t_{1,s} = \max \left\{ t_0, T^{\frac{1}{s}} \right\}$, we can apply Theorem 5.19

and obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2|\Omega|} \int_0^T \int_{t_{1,s}}^{+\infty} \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\
&\geq \frac{C_1}{2\pi|\Omega|} \int_0^T \int_{t_{1,s}}^{+\infty} \frac{st}{l^{1+s}} \, dl \, dt \\
&\geq \frac{C_1}{2\pi|\Omega|} \int_0^T \frac{t}{t_{1,s}^s} \, dt \\
&= \frac{C_1}{4\pi|\Omega|} \frac{T^2}{t_{1,s}^s}.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if $T \in (1, +\infty)$ from the above inequality we obtain

$$(5.123) \quad \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \geq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \geq \frac{C_1}{4\pi|\Omega|} T,$$

while if $T \in (0, 1]$ we have that

$$(5.124) \quad \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \geq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \geq \frac{C_1}{4\pi|\Omega|} T^2.$$

Hence, we have just proved the left-hand side inequality in (5.119) with

$$(5.125) \quad h_1(T) := \begin{cases} \frac{C_1}{4\pi|\Omega|} T^2 & \text{if } T \in (0, 1], \\ \frac{C_1}{4\pi|\Omega|} T & \text{if } T \in (1, +\infty). \end{cases}$$

Now we show the right-hand side inequality of (5.119). Using (5.49), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
(5.126) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \\
&\leq \int_0^T \int_0^1 \frac{c_\Omega}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt + \int_0^T \int_1^{+\infty} c_\Omega \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\
&\leq \int_0^T \int_0^1 \frac{c_\Omega}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt + c_\Omega T.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, in view of (5.38) we have that

$$\left| \frac{c_\Omega}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) \right| \leq \frac{tc_\Omega \Gamma(1+s)}{l^{\frac{n}{2}+1+s}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6l}\right),$$

and the function on the right-hand side in the above equation is in $L^1((0, T) \times (0, 1))$.

Therefore, using also (5.38) we can apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem and obtain the limit

$$(5.127) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \int_0^T \int_0^1 \frac{c_\Omega}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{6l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt = 0.$$

From this equation and (5.126), we can infer that if $T \in (1, +\infty)$

$$(5.128) \quad \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq c_\Omega T.$$

Also, assuming that $T \in (0, 1]$, from (5.38) we obtain that

$$\int_0^T \int_1^{+\infty} c_\Omega \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \leq c_\Omega \int_0^T \int_1^{+\infty} \frac{st\Gamma(1+s)}{l^{1+s}} \, dl \, dt = \frac{c_\Omega \Gamma(1+s)}{2} T^2.$$

Thus, from this latter observation, the limit in (5.127) and equation (5.126) we deduce that

$$(5.129) \quad \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{c_\Omega}{2} T^2.$$

In light of (5.128) and (5.129), and defining

$$(5.130) \quad h_2(T) := \begin{cases} c_\Omega T^2 & \text{if } T \in (0, 1], \\ c_\Omega T & \text{if } T \in (1, +\infty), \end{cases}$$

we conclude the proof of the right-hand side inequality of (5.119).

Now, we prove (5.120). To do so, we claim that

$$(5.131) \quad h_1(T)M(y) \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} l_N^y(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} l_N^y(s, T) \leq h_2(T)M(y).$$

We recall that

$$l_N^y(s, T) = \int_\Omega |\xi - y| \Phi_N^{\xi,y}(s, T) \, d\xi,$$

with $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$. Then, using (5.123), (5.124) and Fatou's Lemma we prove the left-hand side inequality of (5.120).

Now, we focus on the proof of the right-hand side inequality. Let $K \Subset \Omega$ be any compact such that it is star-shaped with respect to y and $y \in K^\circ$, and $d_K \leq 1$. Then, in view of (5.76), (5.77) and Proposition 5.38 with $E = \Omega \setminus K$ and $F = y$, we evince the existence of some $u \in L^1(\Omega)$ such that

$$|\xi - y| \Phi_N^{\xi, y}(s, T) \leq u(\xi),$$

for all $\xi \in \Omega$. Thus, thanks to Fatou's Lemma and (5.128) we obtain the right-hand side inequality of (5.120). Note that from (5.119) and (5.131) one evinces (5.120).

It is left to show (5.121). Reasoning analogously to the proof of claim (5.131), one obtains that

$$h_1(T) \widetilde{M}(y) \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T) \leq h_2(T) \widetilde{M}(y)$$

Making use of this two sided inequality and (5.119) we conclude the proof of (5.121). \square

The following result is the Neumann counterpart of Lemma 5.30.

Lemma 5.32. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \Subset \Omega$ smooth and disjoint, it holds that

$$(5.132) \quad \frac{h_1(T)}{T} \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \frac{h_2(T)}{T},$$

$$(5.133) \quad \frac{h_1(T)}{h_2(T)P(\Omega_2)} \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \frac{h_2(T)}{h_1(T)P(\Omega_2)}$$

$$(5.134) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{h_1(T)}{h_2(T)\widetilde{P}(\Omega_2)} \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \frac{h_2(T)}{h_1(T)\widetilde{P}(\Omega_2)},$$

where h_1 and h_2 are given respectively in (5.125) and (5.130), and we set

$$(5.135) \quad P(\Omega_2) := \frac{\|M\|_{L^1(\Omega_2)}}{|\Omega_2|} \quad \text{and} \quad \widetilde{P}(\Omega_2) := \frac{\|\widetilde{M}\|_{L^1(\Omega_2)}}{|\Omega_2|},$$

where M and \widetilde{M} are defined in (5.122).

Proof. We begin by proving (5.132). To do so, we notice that by definition we have

$$(5.136) \quad \tilde{\Phi}_N^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \frac{1}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) dx dy.$$

From Proposition 5.28 we know that $\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \geq 0$. Thus, by Fatou's Lemma, (5.123) and (5.124) we conclude the proof of the left-hand side inequality of (5.132).

Now, if $\bar{\Omega}_1 \cap \bar{\Omega}_2 = \emptyset$, thanks to Proposition 5.38 with $\Omega_1 = E$ and $\Omega_2 = F$, we easily obtain the right-hand side inequality of (5.132) using Fatou's Lemma.

We assume now that $\bar{\Omega}_1 \cap \bar{\Omega}_2 \neq \emptyset$. We claim that there exists some $z \in L^1(\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2)$ such that for all $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ it holds that

$$(5.137) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq z(x, y) \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \Omega_1 \times \Omega_2.$$

We prove claim (5.137). Thanks to the assumption $\bar{\Omega}_1 \cap \bar{\Omega}_2 \neq \emptyset$, the set $A := \partial\Omega_1 \cap \partial\Omega_2$ is nonempty.

Since $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \Subset \Omega$ and A is compact, then we can choose $r > 0$ and $P_i \in A$ with $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ such that

$$A \subset B := \bigcup_{i=1}^N \overline{B_r(P_i)} \Subset \Omega.$$

If for some $i, j \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ it holds that $\overline{B_r(P_i)} \cap \overline{B_r(P_j)} \neq \emptyset$, then we can choose $K_{i,j} = \overline{B_r(P_i)} \cup \overline{B_r(P_j)}$ in (5.76) and (5.77) and deduce that

$$(5.138) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C}{|x - y|^n},$$

for all $(x, y) \in K_{i,j} \times K_{i,j}$ with i, j such that $\overline{B_r(P_i)} \cap \overline{B_r(P_j)} \neq \emptyset$, where C depends on B, T, Ω . Moreover, we define the constant

$$(5.139) \quad \tilde{C}_N := \max \left\{ C_{B_r(P_i), B_r(P_j)} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \overline{B_r(P_i)} \cap \overline{B_r(P_j)} = \emptyset \right\},$$

where $C_{B_r(P_i), B_r(P_j)}$ is given in (5.221) with $E = B_r(P_i)$ and $F = B_r(P_j)$. Therefore, if $x \in \Omega_1 \cap \overline{B_r(P_i)}$ and $y \in \Omega_2 \cap \overline{B_r(P_j)}$, such that $\overline{B_r(P_i)} \cap \overline{B_r(P_j)} = \emptyset$, then by (5.220) and (5.139) we see that

$$(5.140) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \tilde{C}_N T.$$

Finally, if we set

$$\widehat{C}_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} := \max \{ C_{\Omega_1 \cap K', \Omega_2 \setminus K'}, C_{\Omega_1 \setminus K', \Omega_2 \cap K'}, C_{\Omega_1 \setminus K', \Omega_2 \setminus K'} \},$$

thanks to Proposition 5.38, we obtain that

$$(5.141) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \widehat{C}_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} T,$$

for all $(x, y) \in ((\Omega_1 \cap K') \times (\Omega_2 \setminus K')) \cup ((\Omega_1 \setminus K') \times (\Omega_2 \cap K')) \cup ((\Omega_1 \setminus K') \times (\Omega_2 \setminus K'))$.

Thanks to (5.138), (5.140) and (5.141) we conclude the proof of claim (5.137).

By that means, we can apply Fatou's Lemma and using (5.119) we prove the right-hand side inequality in (5.132).

Now, we focus our attention on the proof of (5.133). In order to do so, we claim that

$$(5.142) \quad h_1(T)P(\Omega_2) \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{l}_N^{\Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{l}_N^{\Omega_2}(s, T) \leq h_2(T)P(\Omega_2).$$

We observe that

$$\widetilde{l}_N^{\Omega_2} := \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_2} l_N^y(s, T) dy$$

and, since $l_N^y(s, T) \geq 0$, see Proposition 5.28, using Fatou's Lemma and (5.131) we prove the left-hand side inequality of (5.142).

Furthermore, we discussed in Proposition 5.28 that $l_N^y(s, T)$ is uniformly bounded in $(s, y) \in (0, 1) \times \Omega$. Thus, we can apply again Fatou's Lemma together with (5.131) and conclude the proof of the right-hand side inequality of (5.142). The inequalities in (5.132) and (5.142) yields to (5.133).

It is left to show (5.134). To do so, it is enough to show that

$$(5.143) \quad h_1(T)\widetilde{P}(\Omega_2) \leq \liminf_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}_N^{\Omega_2}(s, T) \leq \limsup_{s \searrow 0} \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}_N^{\Omega_2}(s, T) \leq h_2(T)\widetilde{P}(\Omega_2).$$

From this and (5.132) it is easy to deduce (5.134). The proof of (5.143) is analogous to the one of (5.142), and thus it is omitted. \square

5.3 Proof of the main results

This section is devoted to the proofs of the main results discussed in the introduction. It is divided into two main parts.

In Section 5.3 we prove the results stated in Section 5.1. Namely, we analyze the environmental scenario where the target location coincides with the forager starting point.

In Section 5.3 we instead discuss the best search strategy when the prey is in a small neighborhood of the seeker initial position. In particular, we prove all the results contained in Sections 5.1 and 5.1.

Proof of the results in Section 5.1

To prove the results presented in Section 5.1, we consider $\Omega = (0, a)$ for some $a \in (0, +\infty)$. The normalized eigenfunctions of the Laplacian in $(0, a)$ with Dirichlet datum as defined in (5.32) are

$$(5.144) \quad \zeta_{D,k}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{a}} \sin\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right)$$

and the corresponding eigenvalues are

$$(5.145) \quad \beta_{D,k} = \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^2.$$

As a consequence, recalling (5.33), the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel reads as

$$(5.146) \quad r_D^s(t, x, y) = \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \sin\left(\frac{\pi ky}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right) \exp\left(-t \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right).$$

This and (5.5) lead to

$$(5.147) \quad \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) = \frac{2}{a} \int_0^T \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \sin\left(\frac{\pi ky}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right) \exp\left(-t \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right) dt$$

and accordingly, if $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$,

$$(5.148) \quad \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) = \frac{2a^{2s-1}}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} \sin\left(\frac{\pi ky}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right) \left[1 - \exp\left(-T \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right)\right].$$

We can also compute explicitly the average distance $l_D^y(s, T)$ and the mean square displacement $\mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T)$ as a series, as showed in detail in Appendix 5.4.

The normalized eigenfunctions of the Laplacian in $(0, a)$ under Neumann conditions as defined in (5.32) take the form

$$(5.149) \quad \begin{cases} \zeta_{N,k}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{a}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right) & \text{if } k \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}, \\ \zeta_{N,0}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} & \text{if } k = 0, \end{cases}$$

and the corresponding eigenvalues are

$$(5.150) \quad \beta_{N,k} = \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^2 \quad \text{if } k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}.$$

Therefore, in view of (5.33), the Neumann spectral fractional heat kernel reads as

$$r_N^s(t, x, y) = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \cos\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi ky}{a}\right) \exp\left(-t \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right).$$

Hence, by (5.5),

$$(5.151) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) = \frac{T}{a} + \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \int_0^T \cos\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi ky}{a}\right) \exp\left(-t \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right) dt$$

and, as a result, when $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$,

$$(5.152) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) = \frac{T}{a} + \frac{2a^{2s-1}}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi kx}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi ky}{a}\right) \left[1 - \exp\left(-T \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right)\right].$$

Thanks to these preliminary observations, we are now in the position of proving the results presented in Section 5.1. We begin by showing Proposition 5.1.

We recall that we adopt the subscript $*$ every time that a functional refers to both the Dirichlet and the Neumann case.

Proof of Proposition 5.1. Let $x \in \Omega$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, thanks to Theorem 5.24 we know that if either $n \geq 2$ or $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$ it holds that

$$(5.153) \quad \Phi_*^{x,x}(s, T) = +\infty.$$

Furthermore, from Proposition 5.28 we have that

$$(5.154) \quad l_*^x(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{A}_*^x(s, T) \in (0, +\infty),$$

for all $s \in (0, 1]$. Therefore, as a direct consequence of (5.153) and (5.154) we obtain the desired claim. □

The proof of Proposition 5.2 that we present here below is a consequence of Theorem 5.24. For the sake of completeness, in Appendix 5.4 we also provide an alternative proof of Proposition 5.2 which employs directly the spectral structure of the efficiency functionals.

Proof of Proposition 5.2. Let $x \in \Omega = (0, a)$, for some $a \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, thanks to Theorem 5.24 we have that for each $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$ the statement in (5.153) holds true. Also, if $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, in view of Proposition 5.28 one has that

$$(5.155) \quad \Phi_*^{x,x}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty).$$

Furthermore, from Proposition 5.28 we know that for each $s \in (0, 1]$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$ the statement in (5.154) holds true as well. Therefore, using equation (5.155), in the notation of Proposition 5.2, we conclude that

$$\mathcal{E}_{*,j}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{for all } s \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right],$$

for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Hence, to complete the proof of Proposition 5.2, it is only left to show the continuity statement. Thanks to Proposition 5.28 we have that, for each $x \in \Omega$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$, the functional $\Phi_*^{x,x}(\cdot, T)$ is continuous with respect to $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$. Also, the continuity with respect to $s \in (0, 1]$ of the functionals $\mathcal{A}_*^x(s, T)$ and $l_*^x(s, T)$ was already established in Proposition 5.28.

As a consequence, recalling (5.154) we conclude that the functionals in (5.6) are continuous in $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ for $x = y$. \square

Now we prove Theorem 5.3. Here we establish that $s = \frac{1}{2}$ is the best search strategy in $(\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ when the forager initial point coincide with the target location.

Proof of Theorem 5.3. We point out that, in order to prove Theorem 5.3, it suffices to establish (5.10). Indeed, once (5.10) is proved, we already know from Proposition 5.2 that $\mathcal{E}_{*,j}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ and $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and accordingly the supremum over $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ of $\mathcal{E}_{j,*}$ is attained at $s = 1/2$.

Furthermore, thanks to (5.208) it is enough to show (5.10) for $a := 1$. To prove it, we observe that all the denominators in (5.6) satisfy (5.154). Consequently, the

claim in (5.10) is equivalent to

$$(5.156) \quad \lim_{s \searrow \frac{1}{2}} \Phi_*^{x,x}(s, T) = +\infty$$

Thus, from now on we focus on the proof of the claims in (5.156). We establish the claim for the Dirichlet case, since the Neumann one follows from the Dirichlet one and (5.53).

For this, we recall (5.214) and we see that there exist $K_0, N \geq 1$ such that, for every $\bar{N} \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \geq \frac{1}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\bar{N}-1} \frac{\varepsilon_0}{(N + 3\ell K_0)^{2s}}.$$

We now pick $L > 0$, to be taken as large as we wish in what follows, such that $e^L \in \mathbb{N}$, and we choose $\bar{N} := e^{2L} + 1$. In this way, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) &\geq \frac{1}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{\ell=\exp(L)+1}^{\exp(2L)} \frac{\varepsilon_0}{(N + 3\ell K_0)^{2s}} \geq \frac{1}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{\ell=\exp(L)+1}^{\exp(2L)} \frac{\varepsilon_0}{(4\ell K_0)^{2s}} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_0}{(4\pi K_0)^{2s}} \sum_{j=1}^L \sum_{\ell=\exp(L+j-1)+1}^{\exp(L+j)} \frac{1}{\ell^{2s}} \\ &\geq \frac{\varepsilon_0}{(4\pi K_0)^{2s}} \sum_{j=1}^L \sum_{\ell=\exp(L+j-1)+1}^{\exp(L+j)} \frac{1}{\exp(2s(L+j))} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_0 (e-1)}{(4\pi K_0)^{2s}} \sum_{j=1}^L \frac{\exp(L+j-1)}{\exp(2s(L+j))} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_0 (e-1)}{(4\pi K_0)^{2s} \exp((2s-1)L+1)} \sum_{j=1}^L \frac{1}{\exp((2s-1)j)} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_0 (e-1)}{(4\pi K_0)^{2s} \exp((2s-1)L+1)} \times \frac{\exp(1-2s)(1-\exp((1-2s)L))}{1-\exp(1-2s)} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_0 (e-1)}{(4\pi e K_0)^{2s} \exp(2(2s-1)L)} \times \frac{(\exp((2s-1)L)-1)}{1-\exp(1-2s)}. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, we can choose $L \in [\frac{1}{2s-1}, \frac{2}{2s-1}]$ such that $e^L \in \mathbb{N}$ and deduce from the above estimate that

$$\Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \geq \frac{\varepsilon_0 (e-1)^2}{(4\pi e K_0)^{2s} e^4} \times \frac{1}{1-\exp(1-2s)}.$$

Sending now $s \searrow \frac{1}{2}$ we see that

$$\lim_{s \searrow \frac{1}{2}} \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) = +\infty,$$

proving the claim in (5.156) for the Dirichlet case, as desired. \square

Finally, we prove Theorem 5.4. In this result, we discuss the impact of some geometrical properties of the domain, such as the size of it, on the monotonicity of the efficiency functionals in (5.5) with respect to the fractional exponent.

Proof of Theorem 5.4. We prove the monotonicity properties of Φ_* . To this end, in the Dirichlet case, when $a \in (0, \pi]$ the first eigenvalue of the Laplacian is less than or equal to 1, thanks to (5.145): hence, we capitalize on Theorem 3.10 and we conclude that, for all $s_0 \in (0, 1)$ and $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$, we have that, for every $x \in (0, a)$,

$$(5.157) \quad r_D^{s_0}(t, x, x) > r_D^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

Similarly, in the Neumann case, when $a \in (0, \pi]$ the first nontrivial eigenvalue of the Laplacian is less than or equal to 1, due to (5.150). This allows us to use Theorem 4.11 and obtain that, for all $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $x \in (0, a)$,

$$(5.158) \quad r_N^{s_0}(t, x, x) > r_N^{s_1}(t, x, x).$$

Now, from (5.5), (5.157) and (5.158) it follows that, for all $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $x \in (0, a)$,

$$(5.159) \quad \Phi_*^{x,x}(s_0, T) > \Phi_*^{x,x}(s_1, T).$$

From (5.159) we obtain the desired monotonicity property when $a \in (0, \pi]$, as stated in formula (5.11) of Theorem 5.4.

Now we deal with the case in which a is sufficiently large and we prove (5.12) and (5.13). To this end, we start with the Dirichlet case, utilize (5.148) with the

notation $\alpha := \frac{a}{\pi}$ and deduce that, for every $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $x \in (0, a)$,

(5.160)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{a}{2} \partial_s \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left[\alpha^{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right] \right] \\
&= 2\alpha^{2s} \ln \alpha \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right] \\
&\quad - 2\alpha^{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln k}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right] \\
&\quad + 2T\alpha^{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \ln \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right) \\
&= 2\alpha^{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln \alpha - \ln k}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right] \\
&\quad - 2T\alpha^{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln \alpha - \ln k}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \\
&= 2\alpha^{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln \alpha - \ln k}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \left(1 + T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

These observations lead to

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{a}{4\alpha^{2s}} \partial_s \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \\
&= \ln \alpha \sin^2 \left(\frac{x}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-\frac{T}{\alpha^{2s}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{T}{\alpha^{2s}} \right) \right] \\
&\quad + \sum_{k=2}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln \alpha - \ln k}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \left(1 + T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

We also observe that, if $f(\tau) := 1 - e^{-\tau}(1 + \tau)$, we have that $f'(\tau) = \tau e^{-\tau} > 0$ for all $\tau > 0$. Accordingly, we see that $1 - e^{-\tau}(1 + \tau) > f(0) = 0$ for all $\tau > 0$. In addition, we have that $f(\tau) \leq 1$ for all $\tau > 0$. As a result,

$$\sum_{k=2}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln \alpha - \ln k}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \left(1 + T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \sum_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cap (\alpha, +\infty)} \frac{\ln \alpha - \ln k}{k^{2s}} \sin^2 \left(\frac{kx}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \left(1 + T \left(\frac{k}{\alpha} \right)^{2s} \right) \right] \\ &\geq - \sum_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cap (\alpha, +\infty)} \frac{\ln k}{k^{2s}}. \end{aligned}$$

From these remarks, we arrive at

$$\frac{a}{4\alpha^{2s}} \partial_s \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \geq \ln \alpha \sin^2 \left(\frac{x}{\alpha} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(-\frac{T}{\alpha^{2s}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{T}{\alpha^{2s}} \right) \right] - \sum_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cap (\alpha, +\infty)} \frac{\ln k}{k^{2s}}.$$

Now, if $T \in [\nu a^{2s}, +\infty) = [\nu \pi^{2s} \alpha^{2s}, +\infty)$ then

$$1 - \exp \left(-\frac{T}{\alpha^{2s}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{T}{\alpha^{2s}} \right) = f \left(\frac{T}{\alpha^{2s}} \right) \geq f(\nu \pi^{2s}) \geq f(\nu).$$

Hence, in this situation,

$$\frac{a}{4\alpha^{2s}} \partial_s \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \geq \ln \alpha \sin^2 \left(\frac{x}{\alpha} \right) f(\nu) - \sum_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cap (\alpha, +\infty)} \frac{\ln k}{k^{2s}}.$$

We also recall that

$$\int_{\alpha-2}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln \tau}{\tau^{2s}} d\tau = \frac{1 + (2s - 1) \ln(\alpha - 2)}{(2s - 1)^2 (\alpha - 2)^{2s-1}}$$

and therefore, if α is large enough,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k \in \mathbb{N} \cap (\alpha, +\infty)} \frac{\ln k}{k^{2s}} &\leq \frac{1 + (2s - 1) \ln(\alpha - 2)}{(2s - 1)^2 (\alpha - 2)^{2s-1}} \\ &\leq \frac{2s \ln(\alpha - 2)}{(2s - 1)^2 (\alpha - 2)^{2s-1}} \\ &\leq \frac{2s \ln \alpha}{(2s - 1)^2 (\alpha - 2)^{2s-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Besides, if $x \in (\nu a, (1 - \nu)a) = (\nu \alpha \pi, (1 - \nu)\alpha \pi)$ we have that

$$(5.161) \quad \left| \sin \left(\frac{x}{\alpha} \right) \right| > \sin(\varepsilon \pi).$$

These observations lead to

$$\frac{a}{4\alpha^{2s} \ln \alpha} \partial_s \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \geq \sin^2(\nu \pi) f(\nu) - \frac{2s}{(2s - 1)^2 (\alpha - 2)^{2s-1}}$$

$$\geq \sin^2(\nu\pi)f(\nu) - \frac{2}{\nu^2(\alpha - 2)^\nu} > 0,$$

as long as α (whence a) is sufficiently large, possibly in dependence of ν .

This establishes (5.12) in the Dirichlet case and we now focus on the proof of (5.13) in the Neumann case. In this situation, recalling (5.152),

$$\frac{a}{2}\Phi_N^{x,x}(s, T) = \frac{T}{2} + \alpha^{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} \cos^2\left(\frac{kx}{\alpha}\right) \left[1 - \exp\left(-T\left(\frac{k}{\alpha}\right)^{2s}\right)\right]$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a}{4\alpha^{2s}}\partial_s\Phi_N^{x,x}(s, T) &= \ln\alpha \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} \cos^2\left(\frac{kx}{\alpha}\right) \left[1 - \exp\left(-T\left(\frac{k}{\alpha}\right)^{2s}\right)\right] \\ &\quad - \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln k}{k^{2s}} \cos^2\left(\frac{kx}{\alpha}\right) \left[1 - \exp\left(-T\left(\frac{k}{\alpha}\right)^{2s}\right)\right] \\ &\quad - T \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln\alpha - \ln k}{k^{2s}} \cos^2\left(\frac{kx}{\alpha}\right) \exp\left(-T\left(\frac{k}{\alpha}\right)^{2s}\right) \left(\frac{k}{\alpha}\right)^{2s}. \end{aligned}$$

This puts us in the same position as in (5.160), but with the sine replaced by the cosine. Hence, in this case, we only need to detect the analog of (5.161). For this, we observe that if $x \in \left(0, \frac{(1-\nu)a}{2}\right) \cup \left(\frac{(1+\nu)a}{2}, a\right) = \left(0, \frac{(1-\nu)\alpha\pi}{2}\right) \cup \left(\frac{(1+\nu)\alpha\pi}{2}, \alpha\pi\right)$ we have that

$$\left|\cos\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)\right| > \cos\left(\frac{(1-\nu)\pi}{2}\right).$$

Thus, the same argument as in the Dirichlet case leads to (5.13). □

Proof of the results in Sections 5.1 and 5.1

In this section we prove the results stated in Section 5.1. Here we discuss the optimal search strategy when the forager starting position $y \in \Omega$ is sufficiently close to the prey location $x \in \Omega$, but does not coincide with it.

We recall that we adopt the subscript $*$ every time that we refer to both the Dirichlet and the Neumann case.

We start this section by showing that all the functionals defined in (5.6) are continuous with respect to $s \in (0, 1]$.

Proof of Proposition 5.5. Let $(x, y, T) \in \Omega \times \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$ be such that $x \neq y$. Then, thanks to Proposition 5.28 we have that

$$\Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty),$$

and also

$$(5.162) \quad l_*^y(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{A}_*^y(s, T) \in (0, +\infty),$$

for each $s \in (0, 1]$. These considerations give that $\mathcal{E}_{j,*}^{x,y}(s, T)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$.

Now, from Proposition 5.28 and (5.162), we deduce that the functionals $\mathcal{E}_{j,*}^{x,y}(\cdot, T)$ are continuous with respect to $s \in (0, 1]$. \square

Now we prove Theorem 5.6. We show that $s = 0$ is a global minimizer for $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(\cdot, T)$ in $(0, 1)$ for each $x, y \in \Omega$ such that $x \neq y$ and for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Moreover, we discuss the existence of the limit for $s \searrow 0$ of $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{3,D}$.

Proof of Theorem 5.6. Let $x, y \in \Omega$ such that $x \neq y$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, thanks to Lemma 5.29 we have that

$$(5.163) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = 0.$$

Since $\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for each $s \in (0, 1]$, see Proposition 5.28, we establish (5.14). We point out that the existence of the limits in (5.15) was already obtained in Lemma 5.29.

Besides, making use of the Maximum Principle for the heat equation, we see that

$$(5.164) \quad F_D(z, w) > 0 \quad \text{for all } z, w \in \Omega,$$

and so the right-hand sides of the expressions in (5.99) and (5.100) are non negative. Also, using (5.223) and (5.164) we deduce that the limits in (5.99) and (5.100) are also positive and finite. \square

We prove now Theorems 5.7 and 5.8. We recall that this result states that if the forager starting position is close enough to the target location, then the optimal search strategy for the functionals in equation (5.6) is in a small neighborhood of $s = 0$.

Proof of Theorems 5.7 and 5.8. Let $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$. We recall the limit in (5.98) and we observe that

$$(5.165) \quad \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}^{(1)}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T}^{(1)} \in (0, 1],$$

for each $x \in \Omega \setminus \{y\}$.

Also, From Lemma 5.31 and equation (5.56), we evince that if $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ there exists some $\beta = \beta_{s_0, y, T, \Omega} \in (0, \widehat{\delta})$ such that, if $x \in B_\beta(y) \setminus \{y\}$, then

$$\limsup_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}_{j,N}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \mathcal{E}_{j,N}^{x,y}(s_0, T),$$

for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, where $\widehat{\delta}$ is provided in (5.58).

Thus, we deduce that there exists some $\widehat{\beta} = \widehat{\beta}_{y, T, \Omega}$ such that if $x \in B_{\widehat{\beta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$, then

$$(5.166) \quad \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}_{j,N}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}^{(j)}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T}^{(j)} \in (0, 1],$$

for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Let us first study the case $n \leq 2$. We recall that thanks to Lemma 5.23, for each $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ we have the existence of some $\widehat{\delta} = \widehat{\delta}_{s_0, y, T, \Omega}$, given in (5.58), such that, for each $x \in B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$, one has that

$$(5.167) \quad \Phi_*^{x,y}(s_0, T) \geq \frac{C_{s_0, y, \Omega}}{|x - y|^{n-2s_0}},$$

where $C_{s_0, y, \Omega}$ is provided in (5.64). Also, for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s}$, where $A_{n,s}$ is given in (6.34), thanks to (5.77) we have the existence of some constant $C_{*, \mu, B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y), T, \Omega}$ such that

$$(5.168) \quad \Phi_*^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{*, \mu, B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y), T, \Omega}}{|x - y|^{2\mu}},$$

for each $x \in B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$.

Consequently, from the last two inequalities we obtain that if $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n, s_1}$, then

$$(5.169) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}_{1,*}^{x,y}(s_0, T)}{\mathcal{E}_{1,*}^{x,y}(s_1, T)} = \frac{\Phi_*^{x,y}(s_0, T)}{\Phi_*^{x,y}(s_1, T)} \geq \frac{C_{*, s_0, y, \mu, B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y), T, \Omega}}{|x - y|^{n-2s_0-2\mu}},$$

for all $x \in B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$, where we set

$$(5.170) \quad C_{*,s_0,y,\mu,B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega} := \frac{C_{s_0,y,\Omega}}{C_{*,\mu,B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}}.$$

As a result, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, by choosing $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$, $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ and $\mu := (n - \varepsilon)/2$ in (5.169), and recalling also (5.165) and (5.166), we infer the existence of some $\delta^{(1)} = \delta_{\varepsilon,y,T,\Omega}^{(1)} \in (0, \widehat{\delta})$ such that for each $x \in B_{\delta^{(1)}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$ it holds that

$$\sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,*}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,*}^{x,y}(s^{(1)}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{*,x,y,T}^{(1)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

This concludes the proof of (5.17) and (5.19) with $j = 1$.

Let us now prove (5.18) for the functional $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}$. To this end, let $d_y := \frac{d(y,\partial\Omega)}{2}$ and $B_y := B_{d_y}(y)$. Then, thanks to equation (5.222) in Lemma 5.40 we have that there exists a constant $\widetilde{c}_{B_y,\Omega}$ such that for each $x \in B_y \setminus \{y\}$ it holds that

$$(5.171) \quad \mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(0, T) = \frac{F_D(x, y)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi} \geq \frac{\widetilde{c}_{B_y,\Omega}}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi} \frac{1}{|x - y|^n}.$$

Therefore, using (5.168) and the estimates in (5.171), if $s \in (0, 1)$, $x \in B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$ and μ is given as in (6.34), we obtain that

$$(5.172) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(0, T)}{\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s, T)} &= \frac{F_D(x, y)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi} \frac{l_D^y(s, T)}{\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)} \\ &\geq \frac{\Gamma(s) l_D^y(s, T)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi} \frac{\widetilde{c}_{B_y,\Omega}}{C_{D,\mu,B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}} \frac{1}{|x - y|^{n-2\mu}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, using (5.108) and the limit

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} s \Gamma(s) = 1,$$

we obtain that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\Gamma(s) l_D^y(s, T)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi} = 1 - e^{-T}(T + 1).$$

Thanks to this observation and Proposition 5.28, we can define the positive constant

$$(5.173) \quad C_{\mu,y,B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega} := \inf_{s \in (0,1)} \frac{\Gamma(s) l_D^y(s, T)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi} \frac{\widetilde{c}_{B_y,\Omega}}{C_{D,\mu,B_{\widehat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}} > 0.$$

Then, we obtain from (5.172) that for each $x \in B_y \setminus \{y\}$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and μ as in (6.34) it holds that

$$(5.174) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(0, T)}{\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s, T)} \geq \frac{C_{\mu,y,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}}{|x - y|^{n-2\mu}}.$$

Therefore, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ by taking $s \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ and choosing $\mu := (n - \varepsilon)/2$ in (5.174), we deduce that there exists some $\delta^{(2)} = \delta_{\varepsilon,y,T,\Omega}^{(2)}$ such that for each $x \in B_{\delta^{(2)}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$ it holds that

$$\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s, T).$$

The proof of (5.18) for $\mathcal{E}_{3,D}$ is analogous to the one for $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}$ and therefore it will be omitted. This last step concludes the proof of Theorem 5.7 for $n \leq 2$.

Now we show (5.19) when $n \leq 2$ for $\mathcal{E}_{2,N}$. To do so, thanks to Proposition 5.28 and (5.131) we can define the positive constant

$$(5.175) \quad \tilde{C}_{y,T,\Omega} := \inf_{\substack{s_0 \in (0,1) \\ s_1 \in (0,1)}} \frac{l_N^y(s_1, T)}{l_N^y(s_0, T)} > 0.$$

Then, if $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s_1}$, thanks to equations (5.167) and (5.168) we have that

$$(5.176) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}_{2,N}^{x,y}(s_0, T)}{\mathcal{E}_{2,N}^{x,y}(s_1, T)} = \frac{\Phi_N^{x,y}(s_0, T) l_N^y(s_1, T)}{\Phi_N^{x,y}(s_1, T) l_N^y(s_0, T)} \geq \frac{\tilde{C}_{\mu,s_0,y,K,T,\Omega}}{|x - y|^{n-2s_0-2\mu}},$$

for all $x \in B_{\hat{\delta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$, where we defined

$$(5.177) \quad \tilde{C}_{\mu,s_0,y,K,T,\Omega} := C_{N,s_0,y,\mu,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega} \tilde{C}_{y,T,\Omega}.$$

Therefore, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, by choosing $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$, $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ and $\mu := (n - \varepsilon)/2$ in (5.176), and recalling (5.166), we deduce the existence of some $\delta^{(2)} = \delta_{\varepsilon,y,T,\Omega}^{(2)} \in (0, \hat{\beta})$ such that for each $x \in B_{\delta^{(2)}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$ it holds that

$$\sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}_{2,N}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{2,N}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}^{(2)}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T}^{(2)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

This concludes the proof of (5.19) for $\mathcal{E}_{2,N}$. The proof of (5.19) for $\mathcal{E}_{3,N}$ is analogous to the one for $\mathcal{E}_{2,N}$.

It is left to prove Theorems 5.7 and 5.8 when $n \geq 3$.

If $n \geq 3$, we just have to replace the inequality (5.168) with the one in (5.76). Thus, repeating the above procedure with this change, the inequalities in (5.169) and (5.176) become

$$(5.178) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}_*^{x,y}(s_0, T)}{\mathcal{E}_*^{x,y}(s_1, T)} \geq \frac{C_{*,s_0,y,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}}{|x - y|^{2(s_1-s_0)}},$$

for all $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $x \in B_{\hat{\delta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$, where we denoted by \mathcal{E}_* any of the functionals $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$, $\mathcal{E}_{1,N}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{2,N}$.

The constant $C_{*,s_0,y,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}$ is obtained substituting the constant $C_{*,\mu,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}$ with $C_{*,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}$ in (5.170) for $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{1,N}$, and in (5.177) for $\mathcal{E}_{2,N}$.

Analogously, equation (5.174) becomes

$$(5.179) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(0, T)}{\mathcal{E}_{2,D}^{x,y}(s_1, T)} \geq \frac{C_{y,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}^{(1)}}{|x - y|^{2s_1}}$$

for all $s \in (0, 1)$ and $x \in B_{\hat{\delta}}(y) \setminus \{y\}$, where we defined

$$C_{y,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}^{(1)} := \inf_{s \in (0,1)} \frac{\Gamma(s)l_D^y(s, T)}{\int_{\Omega} |\xi - y|F_D(\xi, y) d\xi} \frac{\tilde{c}_{B_y,\Omega}}{C_{D,B_{\hat{\delta}}(y),T,\Omega}}.$$

Therefore, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, by choosing $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ in (5.178) and $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ in (5.178) and (5.179), we obtain (5.17), (5.18) for $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}$ and (5.19) for both $\mathcal{E}_{1,N}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{2,N}$ when $n \geq 3$.

The proof of (5.18) and (5.19) respectively for $\mathcal{E}_{3,D}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{3,N}$ are analogous to the one of $\mathcal{E}_{2,D}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{2,N}$ when $n \geq 3$ and are therefore omitted. \square

Now, we prove Corollary 5.12. Namely, we establish in the one-dimensional framework, and under suitable geometric assumptions on the domain, that if the target location $x \in \Omega$ is close enough to the forager starting position $y \in \Omega$, then there exists a local maximizer for the functionals $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{1,N}^{x,y}$ in a neighborhood of the local Brownian strategy $s = 1$.

Proof of Corollary 5.12. We will only prove (5.21), since the proof of (5.22) is analogous. For this, let $\nu \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$. Then, thanks to Theorem 5.4, we have that there

exists some $a_\nu \in (\pi, +\infty)$ such that, for all $a \in (a_\nu, +\infty)$, $T \in [\nu a^{2s}, +\infty)$ and $y \in (\nu a, \nu(1 - a))$, it holds that

$$(5.180) \quad \Phi_D^{y,y}(s_0, T) < \Phi_D^{y,y}(s_1, T),$$

for all $s_0 \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1]$ and $s_1 \in (s_0, 1]$.

Now, for any $\varepsilon \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1)$ we define the positive quantity

$$\tilde{\delta} = \tilde{\delta}_{\varepsilon,\nu,y,T} := \Phi_D^{y,y}(1, T) - \Phi_D^{y,y}(1 - \varepsilon, T).$$

Also, thanks to the continuity of $\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T)$ with respect to $(s, x, y) \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1] \times \Omega \times \Omega$ stated in Proposition 5.28, we can define $\delta_{\varepsilon,\nu,y,T,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$, such that

$$|\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) - \Phi_D^{y,y}(s, T)| \leq \frac{\tilde{\delta}}{4} \quad \text{for all } s \in \left(\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1\right].$$

Thus, using the monotonicity of $\Phi_D^{y,y}$ in (5.180), we obtain that, for each $x \in \Omega$ and $s_0 \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1 - \varepsilon)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi_D^{x,y}(1, T) - \Phi_D^{x,y}(s_0, T) \\ &= \Phi_D^{x,y}(1, T) - \Phi_D^{y,y}(1, T) + \Phi_D^{y,y}(1, T) - \Phi_D^{y,y}(s_0, T) + \Phi_D^{y,y}(s_0, T) - \Phi_D^{x,y}(s_0, T) \\ &> \Phi_D^{x,y}(1, T) - \Phi_D^{y,y}(1, T) + \tilde{\delta} + \Phi_D^{y,y}(s_0, T) - \Phi_D^{x,y}(s_0, T) \\ &\geq -\frac{\tilde{\delta}}{4} + \tilde{\delta} - \frac{\tilde{\delta}}{4} \\ &= \frac{\tilde{\delta}}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

From this, we infer that

$$\sup_{s \in (\frac{1+\nu}{2}, 1)} \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}^*, T) \quad \text{with } s_{x,y,T}^* \in (1 - \varepsilon, 1],$$

which proves (5.21). □

We now prove Proposition 5.13 and establish the continuity with respect to the fractional exponent of the set functionals in (5.9).

Proof of Proposition 5.13. Since the proof for the Dirichlet and Neumann case are analogous, we focus on the Dirichlet framework.

We already established in Proposition 5.28 that for all $y \in \Omega$ and $s \in (0, 1)$ one has that (5.162) holds, and also the functionals in (5.3) and (5.4) are uniformly bounded in $(0, 1] \times \Omega$.

Therefore, by definition we obtain that, for all $\Omega_2 \subset \Omega$,

$$(5.181) \quad \tilde{l}_D^{\Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_D^{\Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty),$$

for all $s \in (0, 1]$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$.

Besides, thanks to Proposition 5.28 we know that $l_D^y(\cdot, T)$ and $\mathcal{A}_D^y(\cdot, T)$ are continuous in $(0, 1]$. Thus, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain that $\tilde{l}_D^{\Omega_2}(\cdot, T)$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}_D^{\Omega_2}(\cdot, T)$ are continuous in $(0, 1]$.

Now, we observe that

$$\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \frac{1}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} r_D^s(t, x, y) \, dx \, dy \, dt.$$

Therefore, thanks to Theorem 3.9 we obtain that

$$(5.182) \quad \tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty).$$

Also, $r_D^s(t, x, y)$ is continuous for $s \in (0, 1]$ for all $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$, see e.g. Theorem 3.8. Thanks to Proposition 4.27 and Lemma 4.28, we have that, for each $t \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, the kernel $r_D^s(t, x, y)$ is uniformly bounded in $(s, x, y) \in (\varepsilon, 1] \times \Omega \times \Omega$. Thus, as a consequence of the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain that

$$f(s, t) := \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} r_D^s(t, x, y) \, dx \, dy$$

is continuous in $s \in (0, 1]$.

Additionally, in view of Theorem 3.9, we see that

$$|f(s, t)| \leq |\Omega_2| \quad \text{for all } (s, t) \in (0, 1) \times (0, +\infty),$$

and therefore by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain the continuity of $\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ for $s \in (0, 1]$.

Finally, the continuity of the functionals in (5.9) with respect to $s \in (0, 1]$ follows from (5.181) and the fact that $\tilde{\Phi}_D^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$ and $\tilde{l}_D^{\Omega_2}(\cdot, T), \tilde{\mathcal{A}}_D^{\Omega_2}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$. \square

Now we prove Theorem 5.14. In this result we show that $s = 0$ is a minimizer for the functional $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$, where Ω_1 and Ω_2 are disjoint and smooth. Also, we show that $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ admit a positive and finite limit for $s \searrow 0$.

Proof of Theorem 5.14. Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \Subset \Omega$ be disjoint and smooth. Then, thanks to Lemma 5.30, we obtain that

$$\lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = 0.$$

Furthermore, thanks to (5.182), we see that $\mathcal{E}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$. This latter observation together with the above limit lead to (5.23).

Now we prove (5.24). The existence of the limits in (5.24) was already established in Lemma 5.30. Using the fact that Ω_1 and Ω_2 are disjoint and smooth, together with the inequality in (5.223) and also (5.164), we evince that

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{F}_D(\Omega_1, \Omega_2) \in (0, +\infty), \quad \int_{\Omega \times \Omega_2} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) \, d\xi \, dy \in (0, +\infty) \\ \text{and} \quad & \int_{\Omega \times \Omega_2} |\xi - y|^2 F_D(\xi, y) \, d\xi \, dy \in (0, +\infty), \end{aligned}$$

where F_D and \tilde{F}_D are given respectively in (5.101) and (5.114). Therefore, from (5.112), (5.113) and these considerations we conclude the proof of (5.24). □

Now we focus our attention on Theorems 5.15 and 5.16. To prove these results, it is useful to state and prove the following proposition regarding a monotonicity property with respect to s and a scaling property for the functional F^{Ω_1, Ω_2} introduced in (5.91). In what follows we denote by d_B the diameter of B for each bounded set $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$.

Proposition 5.33. *Let $K \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a compact set and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset K$ be measurable sets such that $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 = \emptyset$.*

Then, if $d_K \leq 1$, we have that

$$(5.183) \quad \frac{d}{ds} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s) \leq 0 \quad \text{for all } s \in (0, 1).$$

Moreover, for each $r \in (0, +\infty)$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, it holds that

$$(5.184) \quad F^{r y \Omega_1, r y \Omega_2}(s) = r^{n+2s} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s).$$

Proof. We observe that, thanks to the Dominated Convergence Theorem,

$$\frac{d}{ds} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s) = 2 \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \frac{\ln|x-y|}{|x-y|^{n-2s}} dx dy.$$

Hence, if $d_K \leq 1$, then

$$\frac{d}{ds} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s) \leq 0,$$

which proves (5.183).

Now we show the scaling property in (5.184). Let $r \in (0, +\infty)$ and, up to a translation, assume that $y = 0$. Then, applying the change of variable $(x, y) = (rX, rY)$ we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} F^{r\Omega_1, r\Omega_2}(s) &= \int_{r\Omega_1 \times r\Omega_2} \frac{1}{|x-y|^{n-2s}} dx dy \\ &= \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \frac{r^{2n}}{r^{n-2s}|X-Y|^{n-2s}} dX dY \\ &= r^{n+2s} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s), \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof. □

With this preliminary work, we can now prove Theorems 5.15 and 5.16. We recall that the aim of this result is to show that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$ are disjoint, smooth and close enough, then the best search strategy for the set efficiency functionals provided in (5.9) is in a small neighborhood of $s = 0$.

Proof of Theorems 5.15 and 5.16. Let $(y, T) \in \Omega \times (0, +\infty)$. If $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \Omega$ are smooth and disjoint, then thanks to Theorem 5.14 we have that

$$(5.185) \quad \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)}, T \right) \quad \text{with } s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)} \in (0, 1].$$

Moreover, If P and \tilde{P} are given as in (5.135), we observe that

$$\inf_{\Omega_2 \subset \Omega} P(\Omega_2) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \inf_{\Omega_2 \subset \Omega} \tilde{P}(\Omega_2) \in (0, +\infty).$$

Now, using (5.94) we have that, for $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $r \in (0, \hat{\delta})$, where $\hat{\delta} = \hat{\delta}_{s_0, y, T, \Omega}$ has been given in (5.58), then

$$\tilde{\Phi}_N^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_0, T) \geq \frac{C_{s_0, y, \Omega}}{(2r)^{n-2s_0}},$$

for all $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_r(y)$, where $C_{s_0, y, \Omega}$ is given (5.64).

Consequently, using also (5.132), (5.133) and (5.134), we deduce that there exists some $\beta = \beta_{y, T, \Omega} \in (0, 1)$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_\beta(y)$ are smooth and disjoint then

$$(5.186) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{j, N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(j)}, T \right) \quad \text{with } s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(j)} \in (0, 1],$$

for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

We will first prove the results for $n \leq 2$.

We recall that, by Corollary 5.27, if $s_1 \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n, s_1}$, where A_{n, s_1} is given in (6.34), then

$$(5.187) \quad \tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_1, T) \leq \frac{C_{*, \mu, B_{\hat{\delta}}(y), T, \Omega}}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(\frac{n - 2\mu}{2} \right),$$

for all $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \Subset B_{\hat{\delta}}(y)$, where $C_{*, \mu, B_{\hat{\delta}}(y), T, \Omega}$ is introduced in Theorem 5.25.

Also, in light of (5.94) we deduce that if $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \Subset B_{\hat{\delta}}(y)$, then

$$(5.188) \quad \tilde{\Phi}_*^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_0, T) \geq \frac{C_{s_0, y, \Omega}}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_0).$$

Now, we define

$$\delta_0 := \min \left\{ \hat{\delta}, \frac{1}{2} \right\},$$

and we consider $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_{\delta_0}(y)$ smooth and such that $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 = \emptyset$. Thus, from (5.9), (5.183), (5.184), (5.187) and (5.188) we deduce that if $r \in (0, 1)$, $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $\mu \in (0, \frac{n}{2} - s_0) \cap A_{n, s_1}$, where A_{n, s_1} is given as in (6.34), it holds that

$$(5.189) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1, *}^{r, y, \Omega_1, r, y, \Omega_2}(s_0, T)}{\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1, *}^{r, y, \Omega_1, r, y, \Omega_2}(s_1, T)} &= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_*^{r, y, \Omega_1, r, y, \Omega_2}(s_0, T)}{\tilde{\Phi}_*^{r, y, \Omega_1, r, y, \Omega_2}(s_1, T)} \\ &\geq C_{s_0, *, \mu, B_{\hat{\delta}}(y), y, T, \Omega}^{(1)} \frac{F^{r, y, \Omega_1, r, y, \Omega_2}(s_0)}{F^{r, y, \Omega_1, r, y, \Omega_2} \left(\frac{n - 2\mu}{2} \right)} \\ &\geq C_{s_0, *, \mu, B_{\hat{\delta}}(y), y, T, \Omega}^{(1)} \frac{r^{n + 2s_0} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_0)}{r^{2n - 2\mu} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(\frac{n - 2\mu}{2} \right)} \\ &\geq \frac{C_{s_0, *, \mu, B_{\hat{\delta}}(y), y, T, \Omega}^{(1)}}{r^{n - 2s_0 - 2\mu}}, \end{aligned}$$

where we defined

$$C_{s_0, *, \mu, B_{\hat{\delta}}(y), y, T, \Omega}^{(1)} := \frac{C_{s_0, y, \Omega}}{C_{*, \mu, B_{\hat{\delta}}(y), T, \Omega}}.$$

We recall that in writing $r_y\Omega_1$ and $r_y\Omega_2$ we adopted the notation in (5.26).

As a result, for all $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, by choosing for instance $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$ and $\mu := (n - \varepsilon)/2$ in (5.189), and using also (5.185) and (5.186), we infer that there exists some $r^{(1)} = r_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega}^{(1)}$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \Subset B_{r^{(1)}\delta_0}(y)$ are smooth and satisfy $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 = \emptyset$, then

$$\sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,*}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{1,*}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(s_{*, \Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)}, T \right) \quad \text{with } s_{*, \Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(1)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

We now focus on the proof of (5.28) for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}$. Let $K \Subset \Omega$ and assume that $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset K$. Then, thanks to equations (5.112) and (5.222) we have that

$$(5.190) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(0, T) \geq \frac{\tilde{c}_{K, \Omega}}{\int_{\Omega \times \Omega_2} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) \, d\xi \, dy} \frac{F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(0)}{|\Omega_1|},$$

where F_D and $\tilde{c}_{K, \Omega}$ are given respectively in (5.101) and (5.225). Then, in light of (5.93) and (5.187), if $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s} \cap (0, 1)$, where $A_{n,s}$ is given in (6.34), we have that, for each $r \in (0, 1)$,

$$(5.191) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(0, T)}{\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,D}^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(s, T)} &= \frac{|r_y\Omega_2| \tilde{F}_D(r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2)}{\int_{\Omega \times r_y\Omega_2} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) \, d\xi \, dy} \frac{\tilde{l}_D^{r_y\Omega_2}(s, T)}{\tilde{\Phi}_D^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(s, T)} \\ &\geq \frac{|r_y\Omega_2| \tilde{c}_{K, \Omega} \Gamma(s)}{\int_{\Omega \times r_y\Omega_2} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) \, d\xi \, dy} \frac{\tilde{l}_D^{r_y\Omega_2}(s, T)}{C_{D, \mu, K, T, \Omega}} \frac{F^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(0)}{F^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2} \left(\frac{n-2\mu}{2} \right)}, \end{aligned}$$

where $C_{D, \mu, K, T, \Omega}$ was introduced in Theorem 5.25.

Now, we observe that thanks to the limit in equation (5.117) one has that

$$(5.192) \quad \begin{aligned} \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{l}_D^{r_y\Omega_2}(s, T) \Gamma(s) &= \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\tilde{l}_D^{r_y\Omega_2}(s, T)}{s} \Gamma(s) s \\ &= \frac{(1 - e^{-T(T+1)})}{|r_y\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega \times r_y\Omega_2} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) \, d\xi \, dy. \end{aligned}$$

Let us set the notation

$$(5.193) \quad C_{\mu, K, T, r_y\Omega_2, \Omega} := \inf_{s \in (0, 1)} \frac{|r_y\Omega_2| \tilde{c}_{K, \Omega} \Gamma(s)}{\int_{\Omega \times r_y\Omega_2} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) \, d\xi \, dy} \frac{\tilde{l}_D^{r_y\Omega_2}(s, T)}{C_{D, \mu, K, T, \Omega}}.$$

In view of (5.192), we see that if such infimum is attained at $s = 0$, then it does not depend on $r_y\Omega_2$.

If the infimum is attained for some $\widehat{s} \in (0, 1]$, then using Proposition 5.28 and Lemma 5.39 with

$$(5.194) \quad f(y) := l_D^y(\widehat{s}, T) \quad \text{and} \quad g(y) = \int_{\Omega} |\xi - y| F_D(\xi, y) d\xi,$$

we obtain that

$$C_{\mu, K, T, \Omega} := \inf_{\substack{r \in (0, 1) \\ \Omega_2 \subset K}} C_{\mu, K, T, r_y \Omega_2, \Omega} > 0.$$

As a result, using equation (5.191) and Proposition 5.33, we deduce that if $d_K \leq 1$, then

$$(5.195) \quad \frac{\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, D}^{r_y \Omega_1, r_y \Omega_2}(0, T)}{\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, D}^{r_y \Omega_1, r_y \Omega_2}(s, T)} \geq C_{\mu, K, T, \Omega} \frac{F^{r_y \Omega_1, r_y \Omega_2}(0)}{F^{r_y \Omega_1, r_y \Omega_2}\left(\frac{n-2\mu}{2}\right)} \geq \frac{C_{\mu, K, T, \Omega}}{r^{n-2\mu}}.$$

Therefore, for all $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ and $K \Subset \Omega$ that are start-shaped with respect to $y \in K$, by choosing $s \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ and $\mu := (n - \varepsilon)/2$ in (5.195), we deduce the existence of some $r^{(2)} = r_{\varepsilon, K, T, \Omega}^{(2)}$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset r_y^{(1)} K$ satisfy $\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2 = \emptyset$ and are smooth, then

$$\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(0, T) \geq \sup_{s \in (\varepsilon, 1)} \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, D}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T).$$

This concludes the proof of (5.28) for $\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, D}$. The proof of (5.28) for $\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3, D}$ will be omitted, being analogous to the one for $\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, D}$.

We now prove (5.29) for $\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2, N}$. To do so, we fix some $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, and, in light of Proposition 5.28, we define the positive constant

$$C_{s_0, T, \Omega_2, \Omega} := \inf_{s_1 \in (s_0, 1)} \frac{\widetilde{l}_N^{\Omega_2}(s_1, T)}{\widetilde{l}_N^{\Omega_2}(s_0, T)}.$$

Also, if the above infimum is attained for some $\widehat{s} \in [s_0, 1]$, using Lemma 5.39 with

$$f(y) = l_N^y(\widehat{s}, T) \quad \text{and} \quad g(y) = l_N^y(s_0, T),$$

we set

$$(5.196) \quad C_{s_0, T, \Omega} := \inf_{\Omega_2 \Subset \Omega} C_{s_0, T, \Omega_2, \Omega} > 0.$$

Thus, making use of equations (5.183), (5.184), (5.187) and (5.188), we deduce that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \Subset B_{\delta_0}(y)$, and $K \supset B_{\delta_0}(y)$, $r \in (0, 1)$, $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and

$\mu \in A_{n,s_1} \cap (0, \frac{n}{2} - s_0)$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(s_0, T)}{\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(s_1, T)} &= \frac{\tilde{\Phi}_N^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(s_0, T)}{\tilde{l}_N^{r_y\Omega_2}(s_0, T)} \frac{\tilde{l}_N^{r_y\Omega_2}(s_1, T)}{\tilde{\Phi}_N^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(s_1, T)} \\
 &\geq C_{\mu, s_0, y, K, T, \Omega}^{(1)} \frac{F^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}(s_0)}{F^{r_y\Omega_1, r_y\Omega_2}\left(\frac{n-2\mu}{2}\right)} \\
 &= C_{\mu, s_0, y, K, T, \Omega}^{(1)} \frac{r^{n+2s_0} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_0)}{r^{2n-2\mu} F^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}\left(\frac{n-2\mu}{2}\right)} \\
 &\geq \frac{C_{\mu, s_0, y, K, T, \Omega}^{(1)}}{r^{n-2s_0-2\mu}},
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5.197}$$

where we defined

$$C_{\mu, s_0, y, K, T, \Omega}^{(1)} := \frac{C_{s_0, y, \Omega}}{C_{N, \mu, B_{\delta}(y), T, \Omega}} C_{s_0, T, \Omega}.$$

Therefore, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, by choosing for instance $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$, $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ and $\mu := (n-\varepsilon)/2$ in (5.197), and also thanks to (5.186), we deduce that there exists some $r^{(2)} = r_{\varepsilon, y, T, \Omega}^{(2)} \in (0, \beta)$ such that, for each $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_{r^{(2)}\delta_0}(y)$ smooth and disjoint,

$$\sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}\left(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(2)}, T\right) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}^{(2)} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

This concludes the proof of (5.29) for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}$. The proof of (5.29) for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{3,N}$ is analogous to the one for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_{2,N}$ just concluded and therefore it will be omitted.

This concludes the proof of Theorems 5.15 and 5.16 for $n \leq 2$.

Few changes are in order to show Theorems 5.15 and 5.16 also for $n \geq 3$. In particular, we have to repeat the above arguments by replacing (5.187) with the inequality in (5.93). The procedure will determine changes only on the constants involved, in the same fashion of the proof of Theorems 5.7 and 5.8 for $n \geq 3$.

□

5.4 Appendices

Green Function for the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian

Here we give a proof of a well-known identity for the Green function $G_D^s(x, y)$ of the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian. The Green function is given by

$$G_D^s(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt,$$

see also [AD17]. Before we state the following result, let us recall the notation

$$\mathcal{C} = \{(x, y) \in \Omega \times \Omega \text{ s.t. } x \neq y\}.$$

Proposition 5.34. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, for each $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C}$ it holds that

$$(5.198) \quad \int_0^{+\infty} r_D^s(t, x, y) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt.$$

Proof. Given $x, y \in \mathcal{C}$, we let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}(x, y) &:= \int_0^{+\infty} r_D^s(t, x, y) dt \\ \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}(x, y) &:= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt, \end{aligned}$$

Now, let $\{\phi_k\}_k$ be an orthonormal basis of $L^2(\Omega)$ made of eigenfunctions of the Laplacian with Dirichlet boundary conditions, ordered such that if λ_k 's are the corresponding eigenvalues, then $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots$ (see for instance [Eva10]). In view of Theorem 3.8 we know that

$$r_D^s(t, x, y) = \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x) \phi_k(y) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s),$$

for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$. In order to prove (5.198), we first show that $\mathcal{I}(x, y)$ and $\mathcal{J}(x, y)$ are both continuous in \mathcal{C} . Thanks to Theorem 5.24 we know that

$$\int_0^T r_D^s(t, x, y) dy < +\infty$$

for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, 1]$ and $x \neq y$. Moreover, thanks to Proposition 4.27 we observe that for each $t > T$ and $s \in (0, 1]$ it holds that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (5.199) \quad r_D^s(t, x, y) &= \exp(-t\lambda_1^s) \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \phi_k(x)\phi_k(y) \exp(-t(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \\
 &\leq c_{m_0, \Omega, 0} \exp(-t\lambda_1^s) \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \lambda_k^{2\alpha(m_0)} \exp(-T(\lambda_k^s - \lambda_1^s)) \\
 &\leq C_{T, s, \Omega} \exp(-t\lambda_1^s),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality is a consequence of Lemma 4.29, and $C_{T, s, \Omega} > 0$ is a constant depending on $T > 0$, $s \in (0, 1]$ and Ω . The constants $\alpha(m_0)$ and $c_{m_0, \Omega, 0}$ have been explicitly defined in Proposition 4.27. Therefore, if we call

$$g_D^s(t, x, y) := \begin{cases} r_D^s(t, x, y) & \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, T] \times \mathcal{C}, \\ C_{T, s, \Omega} \exp(-t\lambda_1^s) & \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (T, +\infty) \times \mathcal{C}, \end{cases}$$

we obtain that $g_D^s(t, x, y) \in L^1(0, +\infty)$ for each $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C}$, and also

$$r_D^s(t, x, y) \leq g_D^s(t, x, y),$$

for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega$ and $s \in (0, 1]$. Therefore, thanks to the continuity of the kernel r_D^s discussed in Lemma 3.25, we conclude by the Dominated Convergence Theorem that $\mathcal{I}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is continuous in \mathcal{C} .

Furthermore, thanks to the inequalities in (6.42) and (5.199) we have that if we define

$$f_D(t, x, y) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}\right) & \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, T] \times \mathcal{C}, \\ C_{T, 1, \Omega} \exp(-t\lambda_1) & \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (T, +\infty) \times \mathcal{C}, \end{cases}$$

then we get that $f_D(t, x, y)t^{s-1} \in L^1(0, +\infty)$ for each $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C}$, and also

$$p_D^\Omega(t, x, y)t^{s-1} \leq f_D(t, x, y)t^{s-1}$$

for each $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathcal{C}$. Thanks to the continuity of p_D^Ω (see for instance Theorem 3.4) and the last observations we can apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem and conclude that $\mathcal{J}(\cdot, \cdot) \in C(\mathcal{C})$.

Now let $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ such that $f \geq 0$. Then, for each $x \in \Omega$ we compute

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{I}(x, y) f(y) dy &= \int_{\Omega} \int_0^{+\infty} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(y) dt dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\Omega} r_D^s(t, x, y) f(y) dy dt \\
 (5.200) \qquad &= \int_0^{+\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k(x) \exp(-t\lambda_k^s) dt \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{f_k \phi_k(x)}{\lambda_k^s}.
 \end{aligned}$$

In the above computation we denoted

$$f_k := \int_{\Omega} f(y) \phi_k(y) dy,$$

and the identity between the first and the second line, as well as between the second and the third, are due to Lemma 4.28; in addition, the estimates on the coefficients f_k given in Proposition 4.30.

Similarly, we also observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{J}(x, y) f(y) dy &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_{\Omega} \int_0^{+\infty} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) t^{s-1} f(y) dt dy \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} t^{s-1} \int_{\Omega} p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) f(y) dy dt \\
 (5.201) \qquad &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k(x) \exp(-t\lambda_k) t^{s-1} dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k(x) \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-t\lambda_k) t^{s-1} dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} f_k \phi_k(x) \frac{\Gamma(s)}{\lambda_k^s} \\
 &= \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{f_k \phi_k(x)}{\lambda_k^s}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from equations (5.200) and (5.201) we deduce that for each $x \in \Omega$ and $f \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ such that $f \geq 0$ it holds

$$\int_{\Omega} (\mathcal{I}(x, y) - \mathcal{J}(x, y)) f(y) dy = 0.$$

Thanks to this latter identity and the fact that $\mathcal{J}, \mathcal{I} \in C(\mathcal{C})$ we conclude the proof of (5.198). \square

Some explicit formulas for the 1-dimensional functionals

Lemma 5.35. *We have that*

$$(5.202) \quad l_D^y(s, T) = 2a^{1+2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{y}{\pi k a} + \frac{y(-1)^k}{\pi k a} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi k y}{a}\right) \right) \\ \times \sin\left(\frac{\pi k y}{a}\right) \left(\frac{1 - \exp\left(-T \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right)}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \right)$$

and

$$(5.203) \quad \mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T) = 2a^{2+2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{2(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{y^2(-1)^k}{\pi k a^2} + \frac{y^2}{\pi k a^2} - \frac{2y(-1)^k}{\pi k a} \right) \\ \times \sin\left(\frac{\pi k y}{a}\right) \left(\frac{1 - \exp\left(-T \left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right)}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \right).$$

Proof. The gist to obtain explicit formulas for the average distance $l_D^y(s, T)$ and the mean square displacement $\mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T)$ is to compute the $L^2((0, a))$ components of the decomposition in eigenfunctions of the functions $|x - y|$ and $(x - y)^2$. For this, it is first useful to consider the case $a := 1$ and then to reduce to it via a scaling argument. Thus, we first suppose that $a = 1$ and note that

$$\int_0^1 |x - y| \sin(\pi k x) dx = \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{y}{\pi k} + \frac{y(-1)^k}{\pi k} - 2 \frac{\sin(\pi k y)}{(\pi k)^2}$$

and

$$\int_0^1 (x - y)^2 \sin(\pi k x) dx = \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{2(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{y^2(-1)^k}{\pi k} \\ + \frac{y^2}{\pi k} - \frac{2y(-1)^k}{\pi k}.$$

Therefore $l_D^y(s, T)$ and $\mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T)$ take the form

(5.204)

$$\begin{aligned} & l_D^y(s, T) \\ &= 2 \int_0^T \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{y}{\pi k} + \frac{y(-1)^k}{\pi k} - 2 \frac{\sin(\pi k y)}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \sin(\pi k y) \exp(-(\pi k)^{2s} t) dt \\ &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{y}{\pi k} + \frac{y(-1)^k}{\pi k} - 2 \frac{\sin(\pi k y)}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \sin(\pi k y) \left(\frac{1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s})}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and

(5.205)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_D^y(s, T) &= 2 \int_0^1 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{2(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{y^2(-1)^k}{\pi k} + \frac{y^2}{\pi k} - \frac{2y(-1)^k}{\pi k} \right) \\ &\quad \times \sin(\pi k y) \exp(-(\pi k)^{2s} t) dt \\ &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{2(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{y^2(-1)^k}{\pi k} + \frac{y^2}{\pi k} - \frac{2y(-1)^k}{\pi k} \right) \\ &\quad \times \sin(\pi k y) \left(\frac{1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s})}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

which is the desired result for $a = 1$.

Now we address the case of a general $a > 0$. To this end, we denote with an additional subscript a the quantities related to the interval $(0, a)$ (and, consistently, with an additional subscript 1 the quantities related to the interval $(0, 1)$). With this notation, we infer from (5.144), (5.145) and (5.146) that

$$\phi_{k,a}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \phi_{k,1}\left(\frac{x}{a}\right), \quad \lambda_{k,a} = \frac{\lambda_{k,1}}{a^2} \quad \text{and} \quad r_{D,a}^s(t, x, y) = \frac{1}{a} r_{D,1}^s\left(\frac{t}{a^{2s}}, \frac{x}{a}, \frac{y}{a}\right).$$

As a consequence, by (5.3),

$$\begin{aligned} (5.206) \quad l_{D,a}^y(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_0^a |\zeta - y| r_{D,a}^s(t, \zeta, y) d\zeta dt \\ &= \int_0^T \int_0^a \left| \frac{\zeta}{a} - \frac{y}{a} \right| r_{D,1}^s\left(\frac{t}{a^{2s}}, \frac{\zeta}{a}, \frac{y}{a}\right) d\zeta dt \\ &= a^{1+2s} \int_0^{T/a^{2s}} \int_0^1 \left| \tilde{\zeta} - \frac{y}{a} \right| r_{D,1}^s\left(\tilde{t}, \tilde{\zeta}, \frac{y}{a}\right) d\tilde{\zeta} d\tilde{t} \\ &= a^{1+2s} l_{D,1}^{y/a}\left(s, \frac{T}{a^{2s}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This and (5.204) yield that

$$l_{D,a}^y(s, T) = 2a^{1+2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{y}{\pi k a} + \frac{y(-1)^k}{\pi k a} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi k y}{a}\right) \right) \times \sin\left(\frac{\pi k y}{a}\right) \left(\frac{1 - \exp\left(-T\left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right)}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \right)$$

and this gives (5.202), as desired.

Furthermore, by (5.4),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{D,a}^y(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_0^a |\zeta - y|^2 r_{D,a}^s(t, \zeta, y) d\zeta dt \\ &= \frac{1}{a} \int_0^T \int_0^a |\zeta - y|^2 r_{D,1}^s\left(\frac{t}{a^{2s}}, \frac{\zeta}{a}, \frac{y}{a}\right) d\zeta dt \\ (5.207) \quad &= a^{2+2s} \int_0^{T/a^{2s}} \int_0^1 \left|\tilde{x} - \frac{y}{a}\right|^2 r_{D,1}^s\left(\tilde{t}, \tilde{x}, \frac{y}{a}\right) d\tilde{x} d\tilde{t} \\ &= a^{2+2s} \mathcal{A}_{D,1}^{y/a}\left(s, \frac{T}{a^{2s}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, recalling (5.205),

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{A}_{D,a}^y(s, T) \\ &= 2a^{2+2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{\pi k} + \frac{2(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^3} - \frac{y^2(-1)^k}{\pi k a^2} + \frac{y^2}{\pi k a^2} - \frac{2y(-1)^k}{\pi k a} \right) \\ &\quad \times \sin\left(\frac{\pi k y}{a}\right) \left(\frac{1 - \exp\left(-T\left(\frac{\pi k}{a}\right)^{2s}\right)}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

which proves (5.203), as desired. □

Additionally, the Neumann counterpart of Lemma 5.35 reads

Lemma 5.36. *We have that*

$$l_N^y(s, T) = aT \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{y^2}{a^2} - \frac{y}{a} \right) + 2a^{1+2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} - \frac{2}{(\pi k)^2} \cos \left(\frac{\pi k y}{a} \right) + \frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \cos \left(\frac{\pi k y}{a} \right) \times \frac{1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{\pi(2k+1)}{a} \right)^{2s} \right)}{(\pi(2k+1))^{2s}},$$

and $\mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T) = a^2 T \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{y^2}{a^2} - \frac{y}{a} \right) + 2a^{2+2s} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{2}{(\pi k)^2} - \frac{2y}{a} \left(\frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} - \frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \right) \cos \left(\frac{\pi k y}{a} \right) \times \frac{1 - \exp \left(-T \left(\frac{\pi k}{a} \right)^{2s} \right)}{(\pi k)^{2s}}.$

Proof. As in the proof of Lemma 5.35, we can focus on the case $a := 1$, since the general case then would follow from scaling. Thus, we consider the coefficients of the $L^2((0, 1))$ expansion of the functions $|x - y|$ and $(x - y)^2$ in terms of the Neumann eigenfunctions, thus finding that

$$\int_0^1 |x - y| \cos(\pi k x) dx = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} + y^2 - y & \text{if } k = 0, \\ \frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} - 2 \frac{\cos(\pi k y)}{(\pi k)^2} + \frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} & \text{if } k \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

and

$$\int_0^1 (x - y)^2 \cos(\pi k x) dx = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} - y + y^2 & \text{if } k = 0, \\ \frac{2}{(\pi k)^2} - 2y \left(\frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} - \frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} \right) & \text{if } k \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

Therefore $l_N^y(s, T)$ and $\mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T)$ take the form

$$\begin{aligned} & l_N^y(s, T) \\ &= \int_0^T \left(\frac{1}{2} + y^2 - y \right) dt \\ &+ \int_0^T 2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} - 2 \frac{\cos(\pi k y)}{(\pi k)^2} + \frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \cos(\pi k y) \exp(-t(\pi(2k+1))^{2s}) dt \\ &= T \left(\frac{1}{2} + y^2 - y \right) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} - 2 \frac{\cos(\pi k y)}{(\pi k)^2} + \frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \cos(\pi k y) \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{1 - \exp(-T(\pi(2k+1))^{2s})}{(\pi(2k+1))^{2s}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_N^y(s, T) &= 2 \int_0^T \left(\frac{1}{3} + y^2 - y \right) dt \\ &+ 2 \int_0^T \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{2}{(\pi k)^2} - 2y \left(\frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} - \frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \right) \cos(\pi k y) \exp(-t(\pi k)^{2s}) dt \\ &= T \left(\frac{1}{3} + y^2 - y \right) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{2}{(\pi k)^2} - 2y \left(\frac{(-1)^k}{(\pi k)^2} - \frac{1}{(\pi k)^2} \right) \right) \cos(\pi k y) \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s})}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

as claimed. □

Alternative proof of Proposition 5.2

Here we showcase an alternative proof of Proposition 5.2. The advantage of this argument is that it does not make use of the explicit formula (5.31) for the density μ_t^s of a s -stable subordinator. The details go as follows:

Proof of Proposition 5.2. As in the proof of Lemma 5.35, we denote by an additional subscript a the quantities related to the interval $(0, a)$. In particular, by (5.147) and (5.151),

$$(5.208) \quad \Phi_{D,a}^{x,y}(s, T) = a^{2s-1} \Phi_{D,1}^{x/a,y/a} \left(s, \frac{T}{a^{2s}} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_{N,a}^{x,y}(s, T) = a^{2s-1} \Phi_{N,1}^{x/a,y/a} \left(s, \frac{T}{a^{2s}} \right).$$

From this, (5.206) and (5.207) (and the corresponding scaling properties for the Neumann case), we deduce that it suffices to establish Proposition 5.2 for $a := 1$.

Hence, let $x = y \in \Omega = (0, 1)$. We have that

$$\frac{1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s})}{(\pi k)^{2s}} + \frac{1 - \exp(-T(\pi(2k + 1))^{2s})}{(\pi(2k + 1))^{2s}} \leq \frac{1}{(\pi k)^{2s}} + \frac{1}{(\pi(2k + 1))^{2s}} \leq \frac{2}{(\pi k)^{2s}}$$

and, as a result, we obtain that

(5.209)

the series in Lemmata 5.35 and 5.36 converge absolutely for all $s \in (0, 1)$ and $T > 0$ and uniformly in s in every set of the form $(s_0, 1)$ with $s_0 \in (0, 1)$.

Consequently, the convergence or divergence of $\mathcal{E}(s, T)$ in this case is equivalent to that of $\Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T)$ or $\Phi_N^{x,x}(s, T)$, depending on the boundary conditions considered. Hence, when $s \in (0, 1/2]$, for all $M \in \mathbb{N}$, we infer from (5.147) that

(5.210)

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) &\geq 2 \sum_{k=1}^M \int_0^T \sin^2(\pi kx) \exp(-t(\pi k)^{2s}) dt \\ &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{\sin^2(\pi kx)(1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s}))}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \end{aligned}$$

and from (5.151) that

(5.211)

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_N^{x,x}(s, T) &\geq 2 \sum_{k=1}^M \int_0^T \cos^2(\pi kx) \exp(-t(\pi k)^{2s}) dt \\ &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{\cos^2(\pi kx)(1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s}))}{(\pi k)^{2s}}. \end{aligned}$$

We now want to check the fact that, when $s \in (0, 1/2]$, the quantities in (5.210) and (5.211) are divergent as $M \rightarrow +\infty$. To this end, we need to estimate “how often” in k the functions $\sin^2(\pi kx)$ and $\cos^2(\pi kx)$ can get close to zero. This concept is formalized via the following claim: given $x \in (0, 1)$,

(5.212)

there exist $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ and $K_0 \in \mathbb{N} \cap [1, +\infty)$ such that for every $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists $k \in \{k_0, k_0 + 1, \dots, k_0 + K_0\}$ such that $\sin^2(\pi kx) \geq \varepsilon_0$.

To prove this, up to exchanging x with $1 - x$, we can suppose that $x \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$. Thus, we argue by contradiction and we suppose that, for some $x \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$, for every $\varepsilon > 0$, as small as we wish, and every $K \in \mathbb{N}$, as large as we wish, there exists $k_{\varepsilon, K} \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $k \in \{k_{\varepsilon, K}, k_{\varepsilon, K} + 1, \dots, k_{\varepsilon, K} + K\}$ we have that $\sin^2(\pi kx) < \varepsilon$.

This means that for all $k \in \{k_{\varepsilon, K}, k_{\varepsilon, K} + 1, \dots, k_{\varepsilon, K} + K\}$ the angle πkx is sufficiently close to either 0 or π , modulo multiples of 2π . Hence, for concreteness, let us suppose that the angle $\pi k_{\varepsilon, K} x$ is sufficiently close to 0 modulo multiples of 2π , namely that

$$|\pi k_{\varepsilon, K} x + 2\pi J| < \delta := \arcsin \sqrt{\varepsilon},$$

for some $J \in \mathbb{N}$.

Therefore, for every $j \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\pi(k_{\varepsilon, K} + j)x + 2\pi J \in (-\delta + \pi jx, \delta + \pi jx).$$

We also note that, if $j \leq \frac{\pi - 2\delta}{\pi x}$ and δ is sufficiently small, it follows that $(-\delta + \pi jx, \delta + \pi jx) \subseteq (-\delta, \pi - \delta)$. Choosing $K \geq 1 + \frac{\pi - 2\delta}{\pi x}$, we thus conclude that, for every $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap [0, \frac{\pi - 2\delta}{\pi x}]$,

$$\pi(k_{\varepsilon, K} + j)x + 2\pi J \in (-\delta, \delta).$$

Now we remark that, for sufficiently small δ , we have

$$\frac{\pi - 2\delta}{\pi x} \geq \frac{2(\pi - 2\delta)}{\pi} \geq \frac{3}{2}.$$

In particular, we can find $j_* \in \mathbb{N} \cap [\frac{\pi - 2\delta}{\pi x} - 1, \frac{\pi - 2\delta}{\pi x}]$. It thereby follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \delta &> \pi(k_{\varepsilon, K} + j_*)x + 2\pi J = \pi k_{\varepsilon, K} x + 2\pi J + \pi j_* x > -\delta + \pi j_* x \\ &\geq -\delta + \pi x \left(\frac{\pi - 2\delta}{\pi x} - 1 \right) = \pi - 3\delta - \pi x \geq \frac{\pi}{2} - 3\delta > \delta, \end{aligned}$$

provided that δ is sufficiently small. This is a contradiction and the claim in (5.212) is established.

Similarly, one can prove that given $x \in (0, 1)$

$$(5.213) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{there exist } \varepsilon_0 > 0 \text{ and } K_0 \in \mathbb{N} \cap [1, +\infty) \text{ such that for every } k_0 \in \mathbb{N} \\ &\text{there exists } k \in \{k_0, k_0 + 1, \dots, k_0 + K_0\} \text{ such that } \cos^2(\pi kx) \geq \varepsilon_0. \end{aligned}$$

We now pick arbitrary integers $N, \bar{N} \in \mathbb{N}$ with $N < \bar{N}$ and take $M := \bar{N}(K_0 + 2)$ in (5.210). Thus, assuming N large enough such that $\exp(-T(\pi N)^{2s}) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and using (5.212), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) &\geq 2 \sum_{k=N}^{\bar{N}(K_0+2)} \frac{\sin^2(\pi kx)(1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s}))}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \\
 &\geq \sum_{k=N}^{\bar{N}(K_0+2)} \frac{\sin^2(\pi kx)}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \\
 (5.214) \quad &\geq \sum_{\ell=0}^{\bar{N}-1} \sum_{k=N+\ell K_0+\ell}^{N+(\ell+1)K_0+\ell} \frac{\sin^2(\pi kx)}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \\
 &\geq \frac{1}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\bar{N}-1} \sum_{k=N+\ell K_0+\ell}^{N+(\ell+1)K_0+\ell} \frac{\sin^2(\pi kx)}{(N + (\ell + 1)K_0 + \ell)^{2s}} \\
 &\geq \frac{1}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\bar{N}-1} \frac{\varepsilon_0}{(N + (\ell + 1)K_0 + \ell)^{2s}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Sending now $\bar{N} \rightarrow +\infty$ we conclude that, when $s \in (0, 1/2]$,

$$(5.215) \quad \Phi_D^{x,x}(s, T) \geq \frac{\varepsilon_0}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{\ell=0}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(N + (\ell + 1)K_0 + \ell)^{2s}} = +\infty.$$

Similarly, combining (5.211) and (5.213), we find that, when $s \in (0, 1/2]$,

$$\Phi_N^{x,x}(s, T) = +\infty.$$

This and (5.215) yield that $\mathcal{E}(s, T) = +\infty$ for all $s \in (0, 1/2]$, as claimed in the statement of Proposition 5.2.

We now consider the case $s \in (1/2, 1]$. In this situation, it follows from (5.148) that, for every $x, y \in (0, 1)$,

$$(5.216) \quad \Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) \leq 2 \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1 - \exp(-T(\pi k)^{2s})}{(\pi k)^{2s}} \leq \frac{2}{\pi^{2s}} \sum_{k=1}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{k^{2s}} < +\infty.$$

Similarly, using (5.152), for all $s \in (1/2, 1]$ and $x, y \in (0, 1)$,

$$(5.217) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) < +\infty.$$

From this estimate and (5.216) we infer that $\mathcal{E}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (1/2, 1)$, as desired. \square

Some technical results

In this section we collect some technical results which have been used throughout the chapter.

Proposition 5.37. *Let $(l, t) \in (0, +\infty) \times (0, +\infty)$. Then,*

$$(5.218) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\mu_t^s(l)}{s} = \frac{te^{-t}}{l}.$$

Proof. Thanks to (5.31), we have that

$$(5.219) \quad \begin{aligned} \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{\mu_t^s(l)}{s} &= \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} e^{-tu^s \cos(\pi s)} tu^s \frac{\sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s))}{tu^s s} du \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \lim_{s \searrow 0} e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} tu^s \frac{\sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s))}{tu^s s} du \\ &= te^{-t} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} du \\ &= \frac{te^{-t}}{l}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the fact that for each $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ it holds that

$$\left| e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} tu^s \frac{\sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s))}{tu^s s} \right| \leq te^{-lu} \left(\chi_{(0,1)}(u) + \chi_{(1,+\infty)}(u) u^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \in L^1((0, +\infty))$$

in order to apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem in (5.219). \square

Proposition 5.38. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, if $E, F \subset \Omega$ and $\overline{E} \cap \overline{F} = \emptyset$, there exists some constant $C_{E,F} \in (0, +\infty)$, depending only on E and F , such that for all $(s, T) \in (0, 1) \times (0, +\infty)$ it holds that

$$(5.220) \quad \Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) \leq C_{E,F} T \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in E \times F.$$

Proof. Thanks to the hypothesis $\overline{E} \cap \overline{F} = \emptyset$, we can define the positive constant

$$\bar{d} := \inf_{\substack{x \in E \\ y \in F}} |x - y|.$$

Then, by the definition of Φ_N and the upper bound in (5.49), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_N^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} p_N^\Omega(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\ &\leq \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} c_\Omega \max \left\{ \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}}, 1 \right\} \exp \left(-\frac{\bar{d}^2}{6l} \right) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\ &\leq \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} C_{E,F} \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\ &= C_{E,F} T,\end{aligned}$$

where we set

$$(5.221) \quad C_{E,F} := \sup_{l \in (0, +\infty)} c_\Omega \max \left\{ \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}}}, 1 \right\} \exp \left(-\frac{\bar{d}^2}{6l} \right). \quad \square$$

Lemma 5.39. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded and $f, g \in C(\bar{\Omega})$ be strictly positive in a compact set $K \Subset \Omega$.*

Then,

$$\inf_{\Omega_2 \subset K} \frac{\int_{\Omega_2} f(x) \, dx}{\int_{\Omega_2} g(x) \, dx} \in (0, +\infty).$$

Proof. We set

$$m := \min_{x \in K} f(x) \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad M = \max_{x \in K} g(x) \in (0, +\infty).$$

Then,

$$\inf_{\Omega_2 \subset K} \frac{\int_{\Omega_2} f(x) \, dx}{\int_{\Omega_2} g(x) \, dx} \geq \frac{m}{M} \in (0, +\infty). \quad \square$$

We give some lower and upper bounds for the function $F_D(x, y)$ defined in equation (5.101). This result is applied several times, when proving Theorem 5.7.

Lemma 5.40. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and connected.*

Then, for each $K \Subset \Omega$ there exists some constant $\tilde{c}_{K,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(5.222) \quad F_D(x, y) \geq \frac{\tilde{c}_{K,\Omega}}{|x - y|^n} \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K),$$

where \mathcal{C} has been defined in (5.54).

Furthermore, it holds that

$$(5.223) \quad F_D(x, y) \leq \frac{C_n}{|x - y|^n} \quad \text{for all } (x, y) \in \mathcal{C},$$

for some $C_n \in (0, +\infty)$.

Proof. We first prove (5.222). Thanks to equations (5.45) and (5.46) we observe that there exists two constants c_1, c_2 and some $T_{K,\Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$ depending on Ω and K , such that

$$p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) \geq \frac{c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2|x - y|^2}{t}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times K \times K.$$

Therefore, thanks to equation (5.101) we deduce that for each $(x, y) \in \mathcal{C} \cap (K \times K)$ it holds that

$$(5.224) \quad \begin{aligned} F_D(x, y) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{p_D^\Omega(l, x, y)}{l} dl \\ &\geq \int_0^{T_{K,\Omega}} \frac{c_1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}+1}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2|x - y|^2}{l}\right) dl \\ &= \frac{c_1 c_2^{-\frac{n}{2}}}{|x - y|^n} \int_{\frac{c_2|x - y|^2}{T_{K,\Omega}}}^{+\infty} a^{\frac{n}{2}-1} e^{-a} da \\ &\geq \frac{\tilde{c}_{K,\Omega}}{|x - y|^n}, \end{aligned}$$

where, by calling as usual d_K the diameter of K , we defined

$$(5.225) \quad \tilde{c}_{k,\Omega} := c_1 c_2^{-\frac{n}{2}} \int_{\frac{c_2 d_K^2}{T_{K,\Omega}}}^{+\infty} a^{\frac{n}{2}-1} e^{-a} da.$$

This concludes the proof of (5.222).

We now show (5.223). By equation (6.42) and the change of variable $\theta = \frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}$ we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} F_D(x, y) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{p_D^\Omega(l, x, y)}{l} dl \\ &\leq \frac{1}{(4\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}+1}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}\right) dl \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} |x - y|^n} \int_0^{+\infty} \theta^{\frac{n}{2}-1} e^{-\theta} d\theta \\ &= \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}}} \frac{1}{|x - y|^n}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, (5.223) is proved with $C_n := \frac{\Gamma(\frac{n}{2})}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}}}$. □

6

ANALYSIS OF THE LÉVY FLIGHT FORAGING HYPOTHESIS IN \mathbb{R}^n AND UNRELIABILITY OF THE MOST REWARDING STRATEGIES

We analyze the searching strategies of a forager diffusing in the whole space via an equation of fractional type. Specifically, the diffusion of the forager is regulated by a Lévy flight whose exponent can be chosen in order to optimize a suitable foraging efficiency functional. Here, the dimension of the space is arbitrary.

On the one hand, we show that the exponent $s = 0$ corresponding to the limit case of heavy-tailed Lévy flights is a pessimizer for the efficiency functional. On the other hand, we prove that, in situations of biological interest, one finds the most rewarding strategies arbitrarily close to $s = 0$. The combination of these results gives that the most rewarding searching option may turn out to be unfeasible, or at least unreliable, in practice, since small perturbations of the optimal searching exponent lead to pessimal patterns.

The cases analyzed specifically are those of a target located in the proximity of the forager and that of sparse prey modeled by a target infinitely far from the initial position of the seeker. The efficiency functionals taken into account are either of pointwise type (in which the predator and the prey are modeled by moving points) and of set-dependent type (in which the predator and the prey correspond to re-

gions of space with uniform density, thus modeling also the case of a sight range of the biological individuals involved). To implement our analysis, we also provide a number of structural results about finiteness, continuity and asymptotic behaviors of the efficiency functionals.

It is suggestive to relate the adoption of the most rewarding searching pattern close to pessimizers to a “high-risk/high-gain” strategy, in which the forager aims at high-energy content prey to mitigate the risk of failure. This setting is also connected to foraging modes of “ambush” type.

6.1 Introduction

The Lévy flight foraging hypothesis conjectures that search efficiency can be optimized by a random relocation induced by a distribution with a fat tail. In this, the theory of Lévy flights challenged the previous paradigm which used Brownian motion as a default template for describing ecological movements. Experimental evidence and empirical results supporting animal diffusion related to Lévy flights have been repeatedly put forth, see e.g. [Vis+96; Atk+02; RF+04; Sim+06; Sim+08; Hum+10; Hum+12; Rev+15]. In several occasions, the Lévy flights observed in concrete situations appeared to be independent of the specific distribution of resource [DJ+14] and it has been conjectured that they are a consequence of an adaptive process [Vis+96].

The adoption of anomalous diffusion models to describe animal motion is often unavoidable: for example, by monitoring pink snappers on the coast of New South Wales, [Har+15] detected a remarkable outlier with respect to Brownian motion, namely a fish moving the considerable distance of about 290 kilometers over the short time frame of 46 days (while all the other individuals exhibited 50% occupancy of a region of median area 0.33 km^2). If one models this behavior by a Brownian motion, the probability of detecting an excursion of more than 240 km in only 46 days would be zero up to more than two million decimal places. Instead Lévy flight models are compatible with these situations, see [Bro+22]. A large collection of Lévy flights has been observed also at a microscopical level, in collective movements, in trace fossils, etc., see for instance Table 1 in [Rey18] for an interesting list of ubiquitous evidence of Lévy flights, as well as an account on the known generative mechanisms and selection criteria.

Some authors consider the infinite mean squared displacements produced by the Lévy flight description of anomalous diffusion somewhat as a shortcoming for physical applications. For instance, in the opening sentence of [MS94], one reads that “in physical systems, the variance of any stationary processes is *finite*”. Though other authors may find such a statement perhaps too peremptory, given the capacity of Lévy flights to model several situations of concrete interest, a rather common approach to study anomalous diffusion with finite mean squared displacements is to consider instead “Lévy walks”. In this setting, a random particle moves on a straight line with a finite (e.g., unit) speed for a random time selected through a given probability distribution and, at the end of the excursion, a new direction and a new travel time are picked, and the process is repeated over and over, see Section II in [ZDK15]. In future projects, we wish to extend the notion of efficiency functionals and the related optimization analysis to the case of Lévy walks. We stress however that in this case one cannot select homogeneous distributions for the random process (since such a distribution would not be integrable and therefore would not be compatible with the notion of probability). Namely, in this case, it is essentially unavoidable to either introduce a cutoff or a regularization, see e.g. equation (8) in [ZDK15], and this additional procedure presents somehow inescapably at least another structural parameter which one has to further investigate in the optimization process.

As every topic of real scientific interest, the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis is also subject to debate and controversy. Typically, issues can arise about the statistical methods used in some of these studies (see e.g. [Edw+07]) and on the mathematical framework developed and utilized (see e.g. [Lev+20; Bul+21; Lev+21]). Therefore, when dealing with the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis, a very careful, and even pedantic, mathematical setting is absolutely necessary in order to specify exactly the assumptions taken and the models used, and give precise meaning, and possibly limitations, to the results obtained.

In this chapter, we consider a forager diffusing in \mathbb{R}^n according to the fractional heat equation. The fractional parameter characterizing this diffusion is denoted by $s \in (0, 1]$. In our notation, the exponent $s = 1$ corresponds to normal diffusion and the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis, in its strictest sense, concerns the expo-

ment $s = \frac{1}{2}$. An example of fractional diffusion in the whole space was already considered in Chapter 2 when $n = 1$ and here we address the higher dimensional situation (the case in which the anomalous diffusion is confined in a bounded region is considered in Chapters 3, 4 and 5). For completeness, we do not even limit ourselves to the cases $n = 2$ and $n = 3$, and instead we comprise all dimensions $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We recall that the analysis of animal foraging in dimension higher than 1 is not only important for biological purposes, but it also entails a delicate, and possibly controversial, mathematical scrutiny, see e.g. [Lev+20; Bul+21; Lev+21].

The choice of a fractional heat equation to model the diffusion of a Lévy flyer is not new in the literature, see [BV16; Law23] where it is showed tha the probability density of a Lévy flyer converges to the solution of a fractional heat equation as the space and time steps go to zero. We will consider an efficiency functional accounting for the success of the search strategy. This efficiency functional is directly proportional to the expected density of targets hit by the forager and inversely proportional to the time of the search process (differently from most of the existing literature, we will look at time averages of successes, rather than at situations at a frozen instant of time).

The results that we provide are both in terms of most rewarding strategies and of pessimal searching patterns. The main results related to most rewarding strategies (see Theorems 6.3, 6.6, 6.13 and 6.14) are of asymptotic type and establish that *if either the target position converges to the forager initial position, or the target position diverges towards infinity, then the most rewarding search strategy approaches $s = 0$* . Note that these two cases correspond, respectively, to the biological scenarios of *targets adjacent to the seeker* and of *sparse targets*.

The results concerning pessimal seeking options (see Theorems 6.2 and 6.12) are of universal type and prove that, in our framework, *the search strategy given by $s = 0$ is always a pessimizer*, namely a global minimizer for the efficiency functionals considered. The combination of these types of main results reveals that *these most rewarding strategies are somewhat unsafe, in the sense that small perturbations of the optimal fractional parameter may produce pessimal searching patterns*.

As it will be further detailed in Remarks 6.9 and 6.10, the case of optimizers close to $s = 0$ corresponds to hunting strategies of “ambush type”: indeed, from

the mathematical point of view, parabolic equations of low diffusive order present poor regularity properties, entailing, on the one hand, that a considerable portion of the initial density remains in the close vicinity of the starting point, while, on the other hand, a considerable portion of the initial density is quickly sent out towards infinity (and “almost breaking” an initial density into two “disconnected” portions is clearly related to an “almost lack of regularity” for the solution, as well as to a rather unpredictable motion of the forager who can either remain close to the origin or suddenly jump off).

On occasions, these ambush patterns are known to be connected to high-risk strategies that predators undertake in presence of high-energy preys. In this sense, the possibility of having maximizers of the efficiency functionals close to a pessimizer corresponding to $s = 0$ suggests the possibility of linking ambush strategies of the predators to high-risk/high-gain approaches to foraging (again, see the forthcoming Remarks 6.9 and 6.10 for a more thorough mathematical analysis of these aspects and for a comparison with experimental evidence from the literature; see also Remark 6.11 for some heuristic comments on the lack of regularity for small s from the point of view of the underlying stochastic Lévy flight).

The main results are complemented by several foundational results, establishing the finiteness and continuity of the efficiency functionals that we take into account (see Propositions 6.1, 6.24 and 6.25).

As a technical remark, we observe that the model presented here deals with a linear diffusive equation governed by the fractional Laplacian, in which individuals have no preexisting knowledge of the environment and no memory of previous events (from the biological point of view, this situation occurs e.g. when targets are mobile, thus providing no useful reference for subsequent foraging patterns). The scenario considered is that of a non-destructive foraging in which exploited targets are replaced at once. No biological competition is taken into account, nor changes in the numerosness and behaviors of individuals (roughly speaking, this corresponds to the very common biological setting in which the logistic terms play a role only on a significantly longer time scale than the foraging process).

We stress that, during the Lévy flight which we consider here, the forager does not “see” anything while moving to the new location (i.e., the predator cannot stop and

eat a target while “passing by”). While for some animals this assumption may appear to be not completely plausible, for other cases of interest it could be sufficiently realistic: for instance, in situations in which the motion occurs by flying in the air and the foraging by diving into the sea (as for albatrosses), or in all circumstances in which the relocation and predatory activities are somewhat separated.

The environment and the time are modeled as continua (see below for a precise mathematical set-up).

The rest of this chapter is organized as follows. Section 6.2 presents the mathematical set-up in which we work and showcases our main results. The proofs of the main results are given in Section 6.3. The appendices collect some ancillary results needed for the proofs of the main results. The conclusions of this article are summarized in the last section.

6.2 Mathematical setting and main results

In this section, we describe the mathematical framework used in this chapter and we state our main results.

Set-up for fractional diffusion and efficiency functionals

To start with, one needs to model the distribution of predators and targets at a given instant of time t . For this, we let $p(t, x)$ be the target probability density in $(0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n$. In particular $p(t, x) \geq 0$ and

$$(6.1) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p(t, \xi) d\xi = 1,$$

for each $t > 0$. Note that $p(t, \xi)$ has dimension¹ “one over volume”, see Table 1. As for the forager, the anomalous diffusion considered here is that modeled by the fractional heat equation

$$(6.2) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = \delta(y - x). \end{cases}$$

¹Alternatively, one can say that p has dimension “number of targets over volume”, but, to ease notation, we have normalized the total quantity of targets to be 1 in (6.1).

When $s = 1$, the operator $-(-\Delta)^s$ reduces to the standard Laplacian (i.e., the sum of pure second derivatives). Instead, when $s \in (0, 1)$ the fractional Laplacian is defined as

$$-(-\Delta)^s u(x) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{u(x+y) + u(x-y) - 2u(x)}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy,$$

up to a normalizing constant that we disregard for simplicity (see e.g. [AV19] and the references therein for the basics of the fractional Laplace operator² and [Law23] for further connection between this operator, the notion of random walks and its link to Lévy flights in biology).

We assume that the forager may tune the fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1]$ in order to maximize the convenience of the corresponding hunting strategy. In this context, we recall that $s = 1$ in (6.2) corresponds to the classical diffusion pattern induced by the Brownian motion, while $s \in (0, 1)$ is related to an anomalous diffusion produced by the corresponding Lévy flight, see e.g. Section 4 in [AV19] and the references therein.

We denote by $G^s(t, x, y)$ the solution³ to (6.2). In our model, $G^s(t, x, y)$ describes the forager's distribution at time $t \in (0, +\infty)$ with respect to the spatial position $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The point $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ identifies the initial position of the forager (indeed, as customary, the notation δ in (6.2) represents the Dirac delta distribution centred at 0).

Since

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, x, y) dx = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(0, x, y) dx = 1,$$

we have that G^s has dimension “one over volume”, see Table 1.

²In the literature, in the one-dimensional case, the fractional Laplacian is sometimes called the fractional Riesz derivative, or the fractional Riesz-Weil derivative, see e.g. [Dyb+17]. The name of derivative can however be confusing, since the fractional Laplacian is invariant under reflections, while usually derivatives are not. See also [MPV13; SV17; DV21] and the references therein for several applications of the fractional Laplacian to problems of biology and ethology.

³Notice that we use G^s instead of u in this notation to reserve u as an “unknown” while G^s denotes explicitly the solution. Also, in this way we can track explicitly the dependence of the solution on the parameter s , which will play a role, e.g. in Remark 6.17.

Table 1 – <i>Physical quantities for the foraging model</i>		
Target probability density at $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n$	$p(t, x)$	$[p(t, x)] = 1/\text{Volume}$
Searcher probability density at $(t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n$ starting from $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and diffusing according to (6.2)	$G^s(t, x, y)$	$[G^s(t, x, y)] = 1/\text{Volume}$
Foraging success functional for a time span T for a forager starting from $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and a target located at x , according to (6.5)	$\Psi^{x,y}(s, T)$	$[\Psi^{x,y}(s, T)] = \text{Time}/\text{Volume}$
Efficiency functional for a time span T for a forager starting from $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and a target located at x , according to (6.6)	$\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T)$	$[\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T)] = 1/\text{Volume}$
Set-dependent efficiency functional for a time span T for a forager starting in the region Ω_2 and a target uniformly distributed in Ω_1 , according to (6.7)	$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T)$	$[\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T)] = 1/\text{Volume}$

Let us briefly discuss the notion of “random encounters” between a predator and a target in terms of the associated stochastic process. As customary in the theory of continuous probability densities, this requires some care to avoid mathematically incoherent descriptions such as the one of foragers and targets as described merely by material points (in which case one expects random encounters to occur with null probability) or the one in which either foragers or targets contain open sets (in which case the number of encounters may be infinite with strictly positive probability, see Section 2 in [ADV20]). To avoid these inconsistencies, it is key to rephrase the stochastic process describing the forager in terms⁴ of a heat kernel, which represents

⁴Notice in particular that the heat kernel reduces to a single “particle” only at time $t = 0$. The advantage of dealing with heat kernels is thus that one is not moving “particles” around, but rather probability densities.

the probability density, at a certain time, to locate the forager at a given point in the space, and similarly to model the targets as probability densities. In this way, the notion of random encounters is expressed in terms of a product of these probability densities.

More explicitly, if X is the subordinate Brownian motion associated with the transition density G^s (see for instance [KSVc12; SSVc06]), then the quantity

$$(6.3) \quad \mathbb{E}[p(t, X_t) | X_0 = y] := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, \xi, y) p(t, \xi) d\xi$$

coincides with the expected density of encounters between the target and the forager at the time $t > 0$, assuming that the search started at $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (i.e., that the initial value for the fractional heat kernel G^s is the Dirac delta at y). In particular, if we integrate over some region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ with respect to y , we obtain, roughly⁵ speaking, the “number” of encounters at $t > 0$ if the forager occupies uniformly the whole region Ω at $t = 0$. Since we are not interested in the outcome on a specific $t > 0$, but rather in the overall result over some time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$, we will consider also integrals with respect to $t \in (0, T)$. This will provide us with the expected

The link between stochastic processes and probability distributions (seen as solutions of a suitable heat equation) is a classic in mathematical biology and dates back at least to a famous question posed by Karl Pearson in 1905, see [Pea05]: “A man starts from a point O and walks I yards in a straight line; he then turns through any angle whatever and walks another I yards in a second straight line. He repeats this process n times. I require the probability that after these n stretches he is at a distance between r and $r + \delta r$ from his starting point O ”. The question was probably inspired by a mosquito infestation in a forest.

A striking application of this probability distribution approach was provided in the same year by Albert Einstein (see [Ein05]) to describe the movement of a particle in a fluid, which in turn entailed a statistical physics analysis of random motions, a rigorous proof of the reality of atoms and molecules, and a precise strategy to calculate Avogadro’s Number that was implemented by the experimental physicist Jean Perrin (the experimental verification of Einstein’s predictions paved the way for Perrin to receive the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1926).

⁵Though, strictly speaking, in this case one should instead say that one is looking at the solution of the fractional heat equation with initial datum 1 in Ω and 0 outside. The linearity of the fractional heat equation entails that this solution is precisely

$$\int_{\Omega} G^s(t, x, y) dy,$$

making the jargon adopted in this case usually acceptable and justifying the use of the integral over Ω .

Once again, the advantage of using the heat kernel approach is that even when we start with a “set” (say, Ω), its evolution is not a set, but a probability density.

density of encounters on a time interval $(0, T)$, namely

$$(6.4) \quad \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, \xi, y) p(t, \xi) d\xi dt.$$

This can be considered as a first approximation of a *foraging success functional* (based on the ansatz that the higher the number of encounters between predators and targets, the more rewarding the hunting for the predator).

In particular, if the target is stationary, i.e. it remains at a given point $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for all times, we have that $p(t, \xi) = \delta(x - \xi)$ and the foraging success functional in (6.4) reduces to

$$(6.5) \quad \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) := \int_0^T G^s(t, x, y) dt.$$

From this, we introduce an *efficiency functional* to be defined as the ratio between the foraging success functional and the time employed for the search (based on the ansatz that for a searching strategy to be efficient, it is important not only to ensure a foraging success for the predator, but also to do so as quickly as possible). These considerations lead us to the definition

$$(6.6) \quad \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) := \frac{\Psi^{x,y}(s, T)}{T} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T G^s(t, x, y) dt.$$

This type of efficiency functional was introduced in the one-dimensional framework in Chapter 2. It is worth pointing out that our model would apply, with suitable changes, also to the case where the normalized distribution $p(t, x)$ is replaced by a mass density. In this case, the foraging success functional in (6.3) could be interpreted as the expected mass density eaten by a forager starting the search in y .

Furthermore, we will also consider the scenario in which the precise locations of the seeker and the prey are replaced by uniform distributions in subregions of \mathbb{R}^n (this setting is also biologically relevant, since it replaces the exact location of individuals with regions of interests of individuals, e.g. accounting for visual interactions with the environment). More precisely, given some measurable and

bounded sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, we will consider the *set-dependent efficiency functional*

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) &:= \frac{1}{|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) \, dx \, dy \\
 (6.7) \qquad \qquad \qquad &= \frac{1}{T|\Omega_1||\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} G^s(t, x, y) \, dx \, dy \, dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

As customary, here above we have denoted by $|\Omega_1|$ and $|\Omega_2|$ the Lebesgue measures of the sets Ω_1 and Ω_2 . From a biological standpoint we observe that $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ is proportional to the integral over the time $t \in (0, T)$ of the expected number of encounters at t for a forager starting the search in the region Ω_2 and a prey spread in Ω_1 , with uniform distributions (see Table 1 for its physical dimensions, due to the averaging processes in (6.7)).

The choice of this functional is coherent with the energy defined in (6.6). Indeed, as Ω_1 and Ω_2 converge respectively to the points x and y , one obtains that

$$(6.8) \qquad \lim_{(\Omega_1, \Omega_2) \rightarrow (x, y)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T),$$

thanks to the Lebesgue Differentiation Theorem. Of course, dividing by T , $|\Omega_1|$ and $|\Omega_2|$ in (6.7) is only for normalizing purposes and one could alternatively define energy functionals without these normalizations (the analysis carried out in this chapter remaining basically unchanged): our preference for this type of normalization lies in the possibility of recovering the limit property in (6.8).

We also stress that when $\Omega_1 \subset \Omega_2$ one may suspect that the best forager is a “stationary forager”, but we observe that purely stationary foragers are not allowed⁶

⁶The assumption that foragers are always subject to dispersal is perhaps more realistic than how it appears at first sight: indeed, nothing like a “stationary wandering albatross” exists in nature. Actually, the situation in which the forager is never stationary occurs in several biological scenarios. For instance, some species of sharks (white sharks, bull sharks, sandbar sharks, porbeagles, salmon sharks, thresher sharks, pelagic threshers, bigeye threshers, alopias vulpinus, mako sharks, hammerheads, winghead sharks, bonnetheads, scoopheads, etc.) are considered obligate ram ventilators and must keep moving in order to receive oxygen from the water passing through their gills. Similarly, some species of whales, dolphins, tunas, billfishes, swordfishes, bonitos, scombrids and bluefishes need to keep moving. See e.g. [BB92; Oli+11; Weg+13; Cre+19]. Some species of lizards, gerbils and turtles are also known to be very actively moving animals, see e.g. [Sch77; OSF00; Jon04]. Drifters in constantly moving waters, such as some jellyfishes, could also be considered as purely diffusive foragers, see e.g. [Muk16]. Other animals, such as cyamids permanently attached to constantly moving cetaceans, can be thought as purely diffusive seekers (the target being e.g. algae), see [SBH19].

in our model, since all foragers are subject to some random dispersal parameterized by the parameter s . Therefore, optimality questions for predators and preys with the same initial distributions are interesting and, in general, nontrivial: we provide a brief investigation on this type of problems in the forthcoming Chapter 7.

This set-dependent approach to foraging, which is new in the literature, can serve as a useful technical *simplification of the notion of “direct vision”* which was often utilized to account for the predator directly reaching the target when it lies within a given distance. Indeed, with this set-dependent approach one still identifies foragers and targets with regions of space, rather than points, but maintaining the advantage of working always with the same diffusion equation, holding at every spatial scale, without the necessity of truncating the Lévy distribution near its singularity, and without introducing an additional parameter in many steps of the intermediate calculations.

Main results

To study the efficiency functionals introduced in Section 6.2, one needs firstly to understand their basic mathematical properties in terms of *finiteness* and *continuity* with respect to the fractional parameter s (we stress that our goal is to pick s in order to optimize the foraging strategy, hence these properties are indispensable for any further analysis).

In this spirit, we observe that the efficiency functional in (6.6) is finite for $x = y$ only if $n = 1$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, as stated in the following proposition.

Proposition 6.1. *Let $(x, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$. Then, if $n = 1$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ we have that $\mathcal{E}^{x,x}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$, while if either $n \geq 2$ or $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$ we have that $\mathcal{E}^{x,x}(s, T) = +\infty$.*

This result is proved in Appendix 6.4.

Since our goal here is to focus on higher dimensional phenomena (i.e., on the case $n \geq 2$, being the case $n = 1$ contained in Chapter 2), from now on we will

In future projects, we aim at investigating also the case of diffusive targets (the case of stationary targets is biologically interesting anyway, since they can also represent plants, eggs, dormant individuals, or animals in a burrow).

consider the case $x \neq y$ in (6.6). In this setting, in Proposition 6.24 we show that $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$ and also that $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(\cdot, T) \in (0, +\infty)$.

Now we turn our attention to the detection of the *most and least rewarding searching strategies*. We establish that *independently from the starting position of the forager $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, of the prey location $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (as far as $x \neq y$) and of the time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$, the strategy $s = 0$ is a global minimizer for \mathcal{E}* . That is, $s = 0$ is a pessimizer for the foraging strategy, as stated in the following result:

Theorem 6.2. *Let $(x, y, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$ such that $x \neq y$. Then,*

$$(6.9) \quad \inf_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = 0.$$

In view of Theorem 6.2 and Proposition 6.24, we evince that we can extend by continuity the functional $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(\cdot, T)$ to the compact interval $[0, 1]$. From now on we will adopt the notation

$$(6.10) \quad \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(0, T) := \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = 0,$$

for all $(x, y, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$ with $x \neq y$.

Since Theorem 6.2 addressed the case of the least rewarding strategy, we now focus on finding the optimal pattern. While one can imagine that the best strategy may depend on the specific configuration of targets, some general results can be obtained in terms of asymptotic analysis.

One case of interest is the one in which *the prey is located close to the initial position of the forager*. In this situation we show that *the most rewarding strategy corresponds to values of the fractional parameter close to $s = 0$* . More specifically, we show that as the prey location gets closer and closer to the initial position of the forager the fractional parameter maximizing the efficiency functional approaches the value $s = 0$. The precise statement goes as follows:

Theorem 6.3. *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $r = r_{\varepsilon,n,T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| \in (0, r)$ it holds that*

$$(6.11) \quad \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Remark 6.4. In Figure 13.1 we provide some plots of $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}$ for smaller and smaller values of $|x - y|$: we see that the maximizer approaches the value $s = 0$, as stated in Theorem 6.3. Notice also that the case $s = 0$ is however a minimizer, as pointed out in Theorem 6.2. This situation clearly shows that in cases of biological interest *the most rewarding strategy (i.e. the one maximizing an efficiency functional) can result to be unsafe (because dangerously close to strategies that instead pessimize the efficiency functional)*. From the mathematical viewpoint, this phenomenon is described by an efficiency functional which *develops a global maximizer in a small neighborhood of a global minimizer*.

Remark 6.5. Concerning the biological scenarios in which the most rewarding strategy may turn up to be unsafe, an interesting similarity arises between the situation described in Remark 6.4 and the results obtained in [HK21], which showed that the maximization of a biological population subject to a logistic equation with small diffusion rate occurs for highly fragmented resources (but this strategy is somewhat potentially dangerous for the species, since instead resource concentration is beneficial for the survival of the species).

From the technical viewpoint, the setting considered in [HK21] is different from the one studied here, since the main interest there was focusing on the variation of the diffusivity coefficient of the classical dispersal, rather than the exponent of the fractional diffusion. However, we think it is an interesting problem to further understand possible links and connections among these two frameworks, also trying to understand the role of nonlinear sources in diffusive equations which account for competition for environmental resources.

See also [MRB21; NLY21] for related results on situations with fragmented environments.

A natural question in this setting is thereby whether or not this phenomenon of finding *optimizers and pessimizers of efficiency functionals arbitrary close to each other* is induced by the targets being located “too close” to the initial location of the predator. We will see below that this phenomenon is indeed persistent and remains true also for the case of sparse targets.

Figure 6.1: Plots of $(0, \frac{1}{2}) \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, 1)$ for $(x, y) \in \{(1, 1.01), (1, 1.001), (1, 1.0001), (1, 1.00001)\}$ and $n = 1$. The horizontal axis corresponds to the fractional parameter s and the vertical axis to $z = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, 1)$.

Indeed, while Theorem 6.3 dealt with targets located close to the forager, we now focus our attention on the case of sparse targets. From the point of view of asymptotic analysis, it is customary (see e.g. [Vis+99]) to model sparse prey with a target located arbitrarily far away from the forager initial position. We show that *when the target diverges towards infinity, the most rewarding strategy converges to the value $s = 0$* . More precisely:

Theorem 6.6. *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $R = R_{\varepsilon, n, T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for each $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| > R$ it holds that*

$$(6.12) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{x,y,T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Remark 6.7. Once again, we can compare Theorem 6.6 with Theorem 6.2: while the latter states that $s = 0$ is a pessimizer for the efficiency functional, from Theorem 6.6 we have that the most rewarding strategy is also arbitrarily close to $s = 0$ as the target diverges from the predator.

In this sense, the phenomenon described in Remark 6.4 for which optimizers and pessimizers of an efficiency functional can get arbitrarily close to each other, making

the most rewarding searching strategy somewhat unsafe, persists also in the case of sparse targets.

Remark 6.8. From the mathematical point of view, the diffusion models related to $s = 0$ are related to the new, but rapidly growing, field of integral equations with zero order kernels, see [CW19; KM17; CLSn24]. In terms of applications, these equations arise in several fields of science, including probability [SSVc06; Beg14], relativistic Schrödinger operators [Feu23], and reconstruction of blurred images from the Hubble space telescope [Car10].

Remark 6.9. From the biological point of view, the diffusion models related to $s = 0$ have often appeared in both theoretical analyses⁷ and experimental data. In terms of theoretical deductions, it was already observed in [Vis+99; VRDL08] that the strategy $s = 0$ is optimal in one-dimensional environments when the location of targets, once visited, become depleted and are no longer targets for future searches (this case being named “destructive search”; see also [San+04] for an interpolation of targets that regenerate arbitrarily quickly and those vanishing after a single visit). We point out that the setting considered here is structurally different from that in [Vis+99; San+04; VRDL08]. Indeed, the framework here is that of a “non-destructive search” in which the previously-visited sites can be revisited infinitely often and the consumed targets get replaced instantaneously.

Moreover, in [Vis+99; San+04; VRDL08] the analysis relied on the notion of a “direct vision”, i.e. an additional distance parameter below which the forager moves on a straight line to the nearest target site (instead, we do not distinguish between small and large scale motions, considering the diffusive pattern as produced by the full fractional Laplacian, not a modified operator⁸ that avoids singularities).

⁷As a notational remark, the literature often denotes by $\mu \in [1, 3]$ the exponent of the fat tail of a Lévy distribution. In our notation, $\mu = 1 + 2s$, hence the setting $s = 0$ corresponds to $\mu = 1$. The notation is anyway not uniform over the literature, for instance such μ corresponds to a in [RF+04], to $2\alpha + 1$ in [Dyb+17], to β in [Boy+06], to $\beta + 1$ in [Pro+12], to γ in [BR13], to u in [CSS22], etc. Also, the specific details of each article may be structurally different, therefore comparisons between different works have to be taken with a pinch of salt.

The situation $s = 0$ is also referred with the name of “ballistic”. See also [ZDK15] for a thorough discussion of this case and several applications to physics.

⁸The specific assumptions on the singularity of the diffusive operator taken into account are important, though sometimes overlooked or not explicitly stressed in the literature, see e.g. [PV21].

In addition, the optimality condition in [Vis+99; San+04; VRDL08] had a “monotonic” behavior and no issue of reliability of the most rewarding strategy appeared in that context (compare instead with Remarks 6.4 and 6.7 here). Furthermore, our efficiency functional considers averages in time over the time span of the search process, rather than single situations at a frozen instant of time. Besides, our mathematical analysis here is not confined to the one-dimensional case and holds true in every dimension. The calculation in [Vis+99] has also been retaken in [JPE11], where it was shown that the exponent $s = 0$ attains optimality when foragers and targets are located far apart (this is in agreement with our result in Theorem 6.6, though, once again, our setting differs from that in [JPE11] for the reasons explained above).

In terms of experimental evidence, several cases have been recorded of Lévy flights with exponent close to $s = 0$. For instance, just to name a few, black-browed albatrosses and wandering albatrosses (see [Hum+12]) have exhibited a Lévy distribution with $s = 0.135$ and $s = 0.095$, respectively, male spider monkeys exhibit $s = 0.235$ (see [RF+04]), seals ranged between $s = 0.06$ and $s = 0.15$ (see [ABM04]), etc. In some cases, the empirical exponents measured corresponded to values of s which are so small that a reanalysis with different plotting methods led to a value of s below zero (not corresponding to a properly defined probability distribution), see e.g. Figure 4c in [SRP07], relating to the value $s = -0.1$. Similarly, when dealing with fruit flies, exponents such as $s = 0.15$ and $s = -0.11$ have been obtained in Figures 3B.1 and 3B.2 of [May+07].

In a slightly different setting related to waiting times, it has been suggested in [Wea+14] that the case $s = 0$ is closely related to “ambush” strategies by predators and to a high energy content of the targets, as indicated also by the patterns shown by anglers and blonde skates, which present a Lévy exponent very close to the value $s = 0$ and largely specializing on high-energy content prey. It is quite suggestive to relate this high-energy content of the targets and the high-risk strategy related to $s = 0$: in a sense, one can imagine that a forager may not be discouraged by the fact that the most rewarding strategy can be dangerously close to the pessimizer (as pointed out in Remarks 6.4 and 6.7) precisely when the target is also highly rewarding. The adoption of an optimal strategy close to $s = 0$ would then correspond to a *high-risk/high-gain* situation, in which the expectation of the

forager is that the hunt's gain will be so high to compensate for the risk of failure. In human cognition, power law behaviors with exponents as low as $s = 0.185$ have been detected in [BR13]. See also [CSS22] for numerical experiments related to the Lévy exponent $s = 0$.

Remark 6.10. Regarding [Dyb+17], it is also interesting to relate the case $s = 0$ to an “ambush” strategy of the forager. Namely, for small values of s , on the one hand, the fat tail of the Lévy distribution “tends to dislocate mass towards infinity”; on the other hand, the diminished regularity effect of the diffusive equation also “leaves more mass near the origin” (see Figure 6.2 for a sketch of this phenomenon). That is, roughly speaking, a strategy close to $s = 0$ allows the predator to switch rather abruptly from the initial location to a remote region (which, in a sense, provides a good mathematical description of an ambush).

Remark 6.11. From a stochastic standpoint, while the case $s \nearrow 1$ recovers the classical Brownian motion, the trajectories produced by random Lévy flights with a low Lévy exponent display a stronger nonlocal component. More precisely, for $s \in (0, 1)$ let us denote by $\mathbb{P}_s(l)$ the probability of performing a jump of length $l > 0$. Then, for each $0 < s_0 < s_1 < 1$ there exists some $\tilde{l} > 0$, depending on s_0 and s_1 , such that $\mathbb{P}_{s_0}(l) > \mathbb{P}_{s_1}(l)$ for each $l > \tilde{l}$. As a consequence, random Lévy flights with a small exponent are characterized by groups of small consecutive steps followed by longer reorientation jumps. This behavior becomes increasingly pronounced as s decreases.

The fact that small values of s correspond to a proportion of the initial density being “pushed towards infinity” may be also heuristically understood in terms of the underlying discrete stochastic process (see e.g. [Val09]): specifically, if we suppose, for a small $h > 0$, that particles move in the lattice $h\mathbb{Z}^n$ at discrete time steps $\tau = h^{2s}$ with a probability density of jumps given by $\frac{c_{n,s}}{|k|^{n+2s}}$, we see that the normalization condition of probability densities imposes that

$$c_{n,s} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}^n \setminus \{0\}} \frac{1}{|k|^{n+2s}}} \simeq s,$$

for small s , up to a multiplicative constant that depends only on the dimension n , and thus that a fraction $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ of the initial mass is sent, in a time step, at distance

proportional at least to $\alpha^{-\frac{1}{2s}}$ (because, for small $s > 0$, the probability of jumping further than a large quantity R is proportional to R^{-2s} , hence a fraction $\alpha := R^{-2s}$ of the total mass jumps at least proportionally to $R = \alpha^{-\frac{1}{2s}}$), which diverges as $s \searrow 0$.

The strong tendency of this stochastic process of delivering mass far away for small s is also, perhaps surprisingly, complemented with a reluctance to move mass at all: indeed, the small time step of the process $\tau = h^{2s}$ ends up approaching the fixed value 1 as $s \searrow 0$, showing, very roughly speaking, an inclination of leaving particles in their starting position before pushing them quickly towards infinity. The superposition of these mutually contrasting effects can be seen as an indication of the lack of regularity properties for the fractional heat equation as $s \searrow 0$.

The link between lack of regularity and masses pushed towards infinity can be also heuristically guessed by taking the formal limit as $s \searrow 0$ of (6.2), which is

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = \delta(y - x). \end{cases}$$

Indeed, the corresponding formal solutions $e^{-t}\delta(y - x)$ shows both lack of regularity (the solution is not a smooth function when $t > 0$) and loss of mass (the total mass being equal to e^{-t} and so it is not preserved, suggesting that part of the mass is “instantaneously” pushed towards infinity).

Figure 6.2: Plots of the fractional heat kernel when $s = 0.99$ (in blue) and when $s = 0.2$ (in yellow). Note the displacement of mass both near the origin and at infinity for small values of s (“ambush” foraging mode).

Now we consider the set-dependent efficiency functional introduced in (6.7). As done in Propositions 6.1 and 6.24, the first step towards the understanding of this

situation deals with detecting finiteness and continuity results. To this end, in Proposition 6.25 in Appendix 6.4 we prove that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are bounded and measurable, then $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$.

We stress that in Proposition 6.25 the sets Ω_1 and Ω_2 are not necessarily disjoint: this detail was perhaps not obvious to start with since, in view of Proposition 6.1, the corresponding pointwise efficiency functional $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}$ fails to be finite when $x = y$ (except in the special case in which $n = 1$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$). More explicitly, we have that, on the one hand $G^s(t, x, x) \in (0, +\infty)$ for every $t > 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, but

$$\int_0^T G^s(t, x, x) dt = +\infty \quad \text{for every } T > 0 \text{ and } x \in \mathbb{R}^n,$$

except in the special case in which $n = 1$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, due to the singularity of $G^s(t, x, x)$ at $t = 0$.

On the other hand, the set-dependent efficiency functional, as defined in (6.7), is finite since the singularity of the Dirac delta distribution is integrable, thus leading to

$$(6.13) \quad \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} G^s(t, x, y) dx dy dt < +\infty$$

for every $T > 0$ and every measurable and bounded sets Ω_1 and Ω_2 (and note that it is not necessary to assume that these sets are disjoint for (6.13) to hold true).

In the case where Ω_1 and Ω_2 are disjoint and regular enough, we observe that a result analogous to the one given in Theorem 6.2 holds true. Namely, we can show that the infimum for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ is attained at $s = 0$.

Theorem 6.12. *Let $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and disjoint. Then, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that*

$$(6.14) \quad \inf_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = 0.$$

From Theorem 6.12 and Proposition 6.25 we deduce that we can extend by continuity $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(\cdot, T)$ in $[0, 1]$. Hence, we will adopt the notation

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(0, T) := \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T),$$

for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ bounded, smooth and disjoint.

Now we address the results related to the optimization of the set-dependent efficiency functional. Specifically, we establish results in line with Theorems 6.3 and 6.6 by replacing the pointwise functional in (6.6) with the set-dependent functional defined in (6.7). More precisely, we show that *if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are close enough, or sufficiently far away from each other, then the maximizer of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ is in some small neighborhood of $s = 0$* . The formal statements are the following ones:

Theorem 6.13. *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $r = r_{\varepsilon, n, T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are smooth, disjoint and such that $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_r(x_0)$ for some $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$, it holds that*

$$(6.15) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Theorem 6.14. *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ there exists $R = R_{\varepsilon, n, T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfy*

$$\inf_{\substack{x \in \Omega_1 \\ y \in \Omega_2}} |x - y| \geq R,$$

then it holds that

$$(6.16) \quad \sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T}, T) \quad \text{with} \quad s_{\Omega_1, \Omega_2, T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

Remark 6.15. The situation described in Remarks 6.4 and 6.7 carries over for the case of set-dependent efficiency functionals: namely, from Theorems 6.12, 6.13 and 6.14 we can evince that the most rewarding strategy for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}$ is unreliable, developing pessimizers and optimizers arbitrarily close to each other, both when the average locations of predators and targets are close and when they are far away.

Remark 6.16. To keep our analysis as simple as possible, we have investigated here the case of linear equations. In the future, we aim at studying in further detail the nonlinear case of equations, and systems of equations, of logistic type. Though some of the analysis developed in this chapter could be of use (especially for the notion of efficiency functionals and when dealing with spectral properties and linearized equations, accounting for an additional source term), the nonlinear case presents additional difficulties, since Fourier methods are typically not exploitable and explicit solutions may be inaccessible.

6.3 Proofs of the main results

This section develops the necessary tools to prove the main results and completes the proofs of the theorems.

Some of the intermediate results obtained may have independent interest. For instance, we provide two-sided estimates for the efficiency functional $\Psi^{x,y}(s, T)$ in (6.5) under different environmental scenarios. In particular, we establish a polynomial growth for $\Psi^{x,y}$ when the forager starting position and the target location are close enough. This is the content of Theorem 6.21 below.

Moreover, in Theorems 6.19 and 6.20 we prove some estimates for $\Psi^{x,y}$ when the target is far away from the forager starting point. These results on the behavior of $\Psi^{x,y}$ under these two different configurations will be pivotal in order to show the main results presented in Section 6.2.

Analysis of the efficiency functionals

In this section we study the efficiency functionals given in (6.6) and (6.7). We will start the section by proving an identity regarding the fractional heat kernel $G^s(t, x, y)$, that is the unique solution to (6.2). We show that, for each $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $G^s(t, x, y)$ can be written as the linear superposition over the time variable of the classical kernel of the m -order heat equation and the density $\mu_t^{s/m}$ of the s/m -stable subordinator (see Definition 3.17 and the references in Chapter 5 for the basic properties of such a subordinator). This result will be useful later in order to prove an upper bound for the foraging success functional $\Psi^{x,y}$. Before stating it we provide a remark on some key aspects of μ_t^s .

Remark 6.17. For the convenience of the reader we recall here that the Laplace transform of μ_t^s corresponds to an exponential function of a power. More precisely, for each $\lambda \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that

$$(6.17) \quad \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda l} \mu_t^s(l) dl = e^{-t\lambda^s}.$$

Also, it is worth pointing out that μ_t^s admits the following representation formula

$$(6.18) \quad \mu_t^s(l) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) du,$$

see Proposition 3.1 in [KV18].

To appreciate the importance of (6.17) one may notice that if $G^s(t, x, 0)$ is the heat kernel corresponding to the heat equation with power $s \in (0, 1]$, it would be desirable to be able to reconstruct the fractional heat kernel $G^s(t, x, 0)$ with $s \in (0, 1)$ from the knowledge of the classical heat kernel $G^1(t, x, 0)$ (that is, the standard Gaussian). However, fractional heat kernels typically do not have a simple expression in closed form, therefore to obtain a formula of this type it is more convenient to consider the Fourier transforms of the heat kernels given by $\widehat{G}^s(t, \xi, 0) = e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t}$. Then, in Fourier space, it is possible to reconstruct $\widehat{G}^s(t, \xi, 0)$ for all $s \in (0, 1)$ from its classical counterpart $\widehat{G}^1(t, \xi, 0)$: specifically, this reconstruction occurs via integration against a density μ_t^s , in the sense that, for every $s \in (0, 1)$,

$$(6.19) \quad \widehat{G}^s(t, \xi, 0) = \int_0^{+\infty} \widehat{G}^1(l, \xi, 0) \mu_t^s(l) dl,$$

or equivalently

$$e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^2l} \mu_t^s(l) dl,$$

which is precisely (6.17) with the choice $\lambda := (2\pi|\xi|)^2$ (and, interestingly, an approach based merely on *Fourier* transforms produces a formula, namely (6.17), which naturally looks like a *Laplace* transform). In this framework, the relevance of (6.18) is that this reconstructing density μ_t^s possesses an explicit, and sometimes sufficiently manageable, expression.

In the following Proposition 6.18 we extend the validity of (6.17) and (6.19) to higher order parabolic kernels of integer exponent. Namely, for all $s \in (0, 1)$, it would be desirable to reconstruct $\widehat{G}^s(t, \xi, 0)$ from the knowledge of $\widehat{G}^m(t, \xi, 0)$, for a given $m \in \mathbb{N}$. We show not only that this is indeed possible, but also that this new reconstructing kernel (which in principle could depend on m and s separately) is nothing but the previous reconstructing kernel μ_t^σ , with the choice of exponent $\sigma := s/m$.

Proposition 6.18. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $G^m(t, x, y)$ be the solution to the higher order parabolic equation*

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^m u(t, x) & \text{in } (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = \delta(y - x). \end{cases}$$

Then, it holds that

(6.20)

$$G^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} G^m(l, x, y) \mu_t^{\frac{s}{m}}(l) dl \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Proof. Up to a translation we can assume that $y = 0$. Moreover, we denote by $P^s(t, x)$ the function defined by

$$(6.21) \quad P^s(t, x) := \int_0^{+\infty} G^m(l, x) \mu_t^{\frac{s}{m}}(l) dl \quad \text{with } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n.$$

For $m > 1$, $G^m(t, x)$ is not positive everywhere, see for instance [GP02] and references therein. Nevertheless, if $m > 1$, we have the existence of two positive constants d, D , depending only on n and m , such that

$$(6.22) \quad |G^m(t, x)| \leq \frac{D}{t^{\frac{n}{2m}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d|x|^\alpha}{t^{\frac{\alpha}{2m}}}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n,$$

where we defined $\alpha := \frac{2m}{2m-1}$, see Proposition 2.1 and equation (2.8) in [GP02]. In particular, from the inequality in (6.22), we obtain that

$$(6.23) \quad \left|G^m(\cdot, \cdot) \mu_t^{\frac{s}{m}}(\cdot)\right| \in L^1((0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n).$$

Indeed, using (6.22), we can compute

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |G^m(l, x) \mu_t^s(l)| dx dl &\leq \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D \mu_t^s(l)}{l^{\frac{n}{2m}}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \exp\left(-\frac{d|x|^\alpha}{l^{\frac{\alpha}{2m}}}\right) dx dl \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D \mu_t^s(l)}{l^{\frac{n}{2m}}} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\partial B_\rho} \exp\left(-\frac{d\rho^\alpha}{l^{\frac{\alpha}{2m}}}\right) dH^{n-1} d\rho dl \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D \mu_t^s(l)}{l^{\frac{n}{2m}}} \int_0^{+\infty} \omega_{n-1} \rho^{n-1} \exp\left(-\frac{d\rho^\alpha}{l^{\frac{\alpha}{2m}}}\right) d\rho dl \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\omega_{n-1} D \mu_t^s(l)}{\alpha d^{\frac{n}{\alpha}}} \int_0^{+\infty} \theta^{\frac{n}{\alpha}-1} e^{-\theta} d\theta dl \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\omega_{n-1} D \mu_t^s(l)}{\alpha d^{\frac{n}{\alpha}}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{\alpha}\right) dl \\ &= \frac{\omega_{n-1} D}{\alpha d^{\frac{n}{\alpha}}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{\alpha}\right) \end{aligned}$$

where $\omega_{n-1} := H^{n-1}(\partial B_1)$, and between the third and fourth line we applied the change of variable $\rho = \frac{\theta^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} l^{\frac{1}{2m}}}{d^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}$. This proves (6.23).

Therefore, taking the Fourier transform in the space variable of both sides of (6.21), we obtain for each $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^n$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(P^s(\cdot, t))(\xi) &= \mathcal{F}\left(\int_0^{+\infty} G^m(l, x)\mu_t^{\frac{s}{m}}(l) dl\right)(\xi) = \int_0^{+\infty} \mathcal{F}(G^m(l, \cdot))(\xi)\mu_t^{\frac{s}{m}}(l) dl \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-l(2\pi|\xi|)^{2m}}\mu_t^{\frac{s}{m}}(l) dl = e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second identity is due to equation (6.23) and Fubini's Theorem, while the fourth is a direct consequence of the property highlighted in (6.17).

As a consequence, $\mathcal{F}(P^s(\cdot, t))(\xi)$ is the unique solution to the problem

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, \xi) = -|2\pi\xi|^{2s}u(t, \xi) & \text{in } (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(\xi, 0) = 1. \end{cases}$$

Thus, taking the inverse of the Fourier's transform of the last relation we obtain that $P^s(t, x)$ is the unique solution to (6.2) with $y = 0$, see e.g. [AV19], and then it must coincide with $G^s(t, x, 0)$, as desired. \square

It is well-known that the fractional heat kernel has the polynomial growth

$$(6.24) \quad G^s(1, x, y) \leq \frac{C_{n,s}}{1 + |x - y|^{n+2s}} \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n,$$

where $C_{n,s}$ is a constant depending on n and s , see for instance [AV19] and the references therein. By using the scaling property of G^s , see for instance [AV19], and integrating over t in the time interval $(0, T)$, one then obtains from (6.24) the inequality

$$\Psi^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{n,s,T}}{|x - y|^{n+2s}},$$

where $C_{n,s,T}$ depends on n , s and T .

In the following theorem, using the identity proved in Proposition 6.18, we show that we can choose $C_{n,s,T}$ and some constant $\tilde{C}_{n,T}$, such that $C_{n,s,T} \leq s\tilde{C}_{n,T}$, for each $s \in (0, 1)$. This result will be employed in Section 6.3 in the proof of Theorem 6.6.

Theorem 6.19. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $(x, y, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$ satisfying $x \neq y$.*

Then, there exists some constant $\tilde{C}_{n,T} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(6.25) \quad \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{s\tilde{C}_{n,T}}{|x - y|^{n+2s}}.$$

Proof. Using Proposition 6.18 with $m = 2$, we can write for each $s \in (0, 1)$ that

$$G^s(t, x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} G^2(l, x, y) \mu_t^{\frac{s}{2}}(l) dl \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n,$$

where G^2 is the kernel of the biharmonic heat equation. Thus, using the inequality in (6.22) with $m = 2$, we obtain that

(6.26)

$$G^2(t, x, y) \leq \frac{D_2}{t^{\frac{n}{4}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2|x-y|^{\frac{4}{3}}}{t^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n,$$

where d_2 and D_2 depend only on n .

We now set $s_0 := s/2$ and we recall that

$$\mu_t^{s_0}(l) \leq \frac{s_0 t \Gamma(1 + s_0)}{l^{1+s_0}} \quad \text{for all } l \in (0, +\infty),$$

thanks to Theorem 5.19.

Accordingly, using this and (6.26) we deduce that

(6.27)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{G^s(t, x, y)}{s} &= \frac{1}{2s_0} \int_0^{+\infty} G^2(l, x, y) \mu_t^{s_0}(l) dl \leq \frac{1}{2s_0} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D_2}{l^{\frac{n}{4}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2|x-y|^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) \mu_t^{s_0}(l) dl \\ &\leq \frac{t\Gamma(1 + s_0)}{2} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D_2}{l^{\frac{n}{4}+1+s_0}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2|x-y|^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) dl \\ &= \frac{3D_2 t \Gamma(1 + s_0)}{2d_2^{\frac{3n}{4}+3s_0}} |x-y|^{-n-4s_0} \int_0^{+\infty} a^{\frac{3n}{4}+3s_0-1} e^{-a} da \\ &= \frac{3D_2 t \Gamma(1 + s_0)}{2d_2^{\frac{3n}{4}+3s_0}} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{3n}{4} + 3s_0\right)}{|x-y|^{n+4s_0}} \leq \frac{2\tilde{C}_n t}{|x-y|^{n+2s}}, \end{aligned}$$

where we applied the change of variable $a = \frac{d_2|x-y|^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}$ and denoted

$$(6.28) \quad \tilde{C}_n := \frac{1}{4} \sup_{s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})} \frac{3D_2 \Gamma(1 + s_0)}{2d_2^{\frac{3n}{4}+3s_0}} \Gamma\left(\frac{3n}{4} + 3s_0\right).$$

Integrating both sides in (6.27) with respect to t in the interval $(0, T)$ and defining

$$(6.29) \quad \tilde{C}_{n,T} := \tilde{C}_n T^2,$$

we obtain the desired result. □

With the following theorem we establish a lower bound for $\Psi^{x,y}(s, T)$ when $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$. This result shows that the functional can be bounded by below by a function with the same polynomial growth at infinity as the one in the right-hand side of (6.25).

Moreover, this result, together with Theorem 6.19, will be necessary in order to prove Theorem 6.6 on the optimality of a highly nonlocal search strategy when the forager is far enough from the prey.

Theorem 6.20. *Let $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$.*

Then, for each $\delta \in (0, +\infty)$ there exists a constant $C_{\delta, T} \in (0, +\infty)$, depending only on δ and T , such that for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| > \delta$ it holds that

$$(6.30) \quad \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) \geq \frac{sC_{\delta, T}}{|x - y|^{n+2s}}.$$

Proof. We recall that, if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $t \in (0, 1)$,

$$\mu_t^s(l) \geq \frac{stC_1}{\pi l^{1+s}} \quad \text{for all } l \in (t^{\frac{1}{s}}, +\infty),$$

for some $C_1 \in (0, +\infty)$, independent of s and l , see Theorem 5.19.

Using this and (6.20), for each $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $t \in (0, 1)$ we have that

$$(6.31) \quad \begin{aligned} G^s(t, x, y) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) dl \\ &\geq \int_{t^{\frac{1}{s}}}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) dl \\ &\geq \int_{t^{\frac{1}{s}}}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}\right) \frac{stC_1}{\pi l^{1+s}} dl \\ &= \frac{stC_1}{4^{\frac{n}{2}} \pi^{\frac{n}{2}+1}} \int_{t^{\frac{1}{s}}}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}+s+1}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4l}\right) dl \\ &= \frac{stC_1}{4^{1-s} \pi^{\frac{n}{2}+1}} \int_0^{\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t^{\frac{1}{s}}}} \frac{a^{\frac{n}{2}+s-1}}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} e^{-a} da \\ &\geq \frac{stC_1}{4^{1-s} \pi^{\frac{n}{2}+1}} \int_0^{\frac{\delta^2}{4}} \frac{a^{\frac{n}{2}+s-1}}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} e^{-a} da \geq \frac{2C_{\delta}st}{|x - y|^{n+2s}}, \end{aligned}$$

where we defined

$$(6.32) \quad C_{\delta} := \frac{1}{2} \inf_{s \in (0, 1)} \frac{C_1}{4^{1-s} \pi^{\frac{n}{2}+1}} \int_0^{\frac{\delta^2}{4}} a^{\frac{n}{2}+s-1} e^{-a} da.$$

If $T \in (0, 1]$, integrating both sides of (6.31) with respect to t in the interval $(0, T)$, we obtain (6.30) with

$$(6.33) \quad C_{\delta,T} := C_\delta T^2$$

If instead $T \in (1, +\infty)$, it is enough to observe that

$$\Psi^{x,y}(s, T) \geq \Psi^{x,y}(s, 1) \geq \frac{s C_\delta}{|x - y|^{n+2s}}. \quad \square$$

Now, we focus our attention to the main tools that we will use in order to prove Theorem 6.3. For this, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$, we define

$$(6.34) \quad A_{n,s} := \left(0, 1 + \frac{n}{2} - s\right) \cap \left[\frac{n}{2} - s, 1 + \frac{n}{2} - s\right)$$

and we establish the following asymptotic behavior:

Theorem 6.21. *Let $(z, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$. Then, for all $n \leq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s}$, where $A_{n,s}$ is given in (6.34), there exists a constant $C_{\mu,T,B_1(z)} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that*

$$(6.35) \quad \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{\mu,T,B_1(z)}}{|x - y|^{2\mu}},$$

for all $x, y \in B_1(z)$ with $x \neq y$.

Also, if $n \geq 3$ it holds that

$$(6.36) \quad \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_n}{\Gamma(s)} \frac{1}{|x - y|^{n-2s}},$$

for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $x \neq y$, where C_n is defined as

$$(6.37) \quad C_n := \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \frac{4^{-s}}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}} \Gamma(s)} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} - s\right).$$

Proof. Up to a translation we can assume that $z = 0$ and we consider the classical Dirichlet heat kernel $p_D^{B_2}(t, x, y)$ in the ball B_2 . Thanks to Lemma 2.1 in [Zha02], we have the existence of two constants c_1, c_2 and a time span $T_{B_1, B_2} \in (0, +\infty)$, depending on B_1 and B_2 , such that

$$p_D^{B_2}(t, x, y) \geq \frac{c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2|x - y|^2}{t}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, T_{B_1, B_2}] \times B_1 \times B_1.$$

Now, we fix two constants $c_0, \eta_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$c_0 c_1 \geq \frac{1}{(4\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \quad \text{and} \quad \eta_0^2 c_2 \leq \frac{1}{4}$$

and we obtain that, for each $\eta \in (0, \eta_0)$ and $(t, x, y) \in (0, T_{B_1, B_2}] \times B_1 \times B_1$,

(6.38)

$$\begin{aligned} c_0 p_D^{B_2}(t, \eta x, \eta y) - G(t, x, y) &\geq \frac{c_0 c_1}{t^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{c_2 |\eta x - \eta y|^2}{t}\right) - \frac{1}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4t}\right) \\ &= \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{|x - y|^2}{4t}\right)}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \left(c_0 c_1 (4\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}} \exp\left(\frac{(\frac{1}{4} - c_2 \eta^2) |x - y|^2}{t}\right) - 1 \right) \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Let us now prove (6.35). To do so, assume that $n \leq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n,s}$, where the set $A_{n,s}$ is given in (6.34).

Then, if $x, y \in B_1$, thanks to (6.38) here, (5.83) and Proposition 6.18 with $m = 1$, for all $\eta \in (0, \eta_0)$ we have that

(6.39)

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) &= \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} G(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\ &= \int_0^T \int_0^{T_{B_1, B_2}} G(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt + \int_0^T \int_{T_{B_1, B_2}}^{+\infty} G(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\ &\leq \int_0^T \int_0^{T_{B_1, B_2}} c_0 p_D^{B_2}(l, \eta x, \eta y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt + \int_0^T \int_{T_{B_1, B_2}}^{+\infty} G(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) \, dl \, dt \\ &\leq C_{\mu, B_1, B_2} \frac{\eta^{-2\mu}}{|x - y|^{2\mu}} + C_{B_1, B_2} T, \end{aligned}$$

where we defined

(6.40)
$$C_{B_1, B_2} := \max_{l \in (T_{B_1, B_2}, +\infty)} G(l, x, x) \quad \text{and} \quad C_{\mu, B_1, B_2} := C_{D, \mu} c_0,$$

being $C_{D, \mu}$ given in formula (5.84).

Accordingly, if we take $\eta_1 \in (0, \eta_0)$ such that

$$\eta_1 \leq \left(\frac{C_{\mu, B_1, B_2}}{C_{B_1, B_2} T} \right)^{-2\mu},$$

depending on B_1, B_2, μ and T , then we obtain from (6.39) that, for all $s \in (0, 1)$ and $x, y \in B_1$,

$$\Psi^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \frac{C_{\mu,T,B_1}}{|x - y|^{2\mu}}.$$

The constant C_{μ,T,B_1} is defined as $C_{\mu,T,B_1} := 2C_{\mu,B_1,B_2}\eta_1^{-2\mu}$. This concludes the proof of (6.35).

Let us now show (6.36). To do so, if $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfy $x \neq y$, we consider the following identity for the Green function of the fractional Laplacian

$$\int_0^{+\infty} G^s(t, x, y) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} G(t, x, y)t^{s-1} dt,$$

which for the convenience of the reader is proved in Proposition 6.23.

We also point out that, using the change of variable $a = \frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} G(t, x, y)t^{s-1} dt &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{t^{s-1}}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}\right) dt \\ (6.41) \quad &= \frac{4^{-s}}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}}} \frac{1}{|x-y|^{n-2s}} \int_0^{+\infty} a^{\frac{n}{2}-1-s} e^{-a} da = \frac{4^{-s}}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}}} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} - s\right)}{|x-y|^{n-2s}}. \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) &:= \int_0^T G^s(t, x, y) dt \leq \int_0^{+\infty} G^s(t, x, y) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} G(t, x, y)t^{s-1} dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{t^{s-1}}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}\right) dt \\ &\leq \frac{C_n}{\Gamma(s)} \frac{1}{|x-y|^{n-2s}}, \end{aligned}$$

where C_n is given in (6.37). □

If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is some smooth, bounded and connected domain, then thanks to the Weak Maximum Principle, one has that

$$(6.42) \quad p_D^\Omega(t, x, y) \leq \frac{1}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}\right) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

In what follows we will denote by r_D^s the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel in Ω , see for instance Chapter 3. Also, adopting the same notation of Chapter 5, the success functional associated with r_D^s is denoted by Φ_D , which is defined as

$$\Phi_D^{x,y}(s, T) = \int_0^T r_D^s(t, x, y) dt,$$

see equation (5.5).

As a direct consequence of the identity in (6.20) and the estimate in (6.42) we have the following corollary. From this result we can infer a lower bound for $\Psi^{x,y}$ analogous to the one in equation (5.56) of Lemma 5.23 for $\Phi_D^{x,y}$.

Such a lower bound will be employed in order to prove Theorem 6.3.

Corollary 6.22. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded, smooth and connected domain.*

Then, it holds that

$$(6.43) \quad r_D^s(t, x, y) \leq G^s(t, x, y) \quad \text{for all } (t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \Omega \times \Omega.$$

Completion of the proof of the main results

This section is devoted to the proofs of all the main results contained in Section 6.2.

Proof of Theorem 6.2. Let $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $x \neq y$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, thanks to equation (6.25) in Theorem 6.19, we have that

$$(6.44) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) \leq \lim_{s \searrow 0} \frac{s \tilde{C}_{n,T}}{T|x-y|^{n+2s}} = 0,$$

where $\tilde{C}_{n,T}$ is given in (6.29). This limit and equation (6.66) lead to (6.9). □

Proof of Theorem 6.3. Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. From Theorem 6.2 we have that, that for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $x \neq y$,

$$(6.45) \quad \sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}, T) \quad \text{with } s_{x,y,T} \in (0, 1].$$

We will first prove Theorem 6.3 for $n \leq 2$. Let $z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and let r_D^s be the Dirichlet spectral fractional heat kernel in $B_1(z)$. Then, thanks to Lemma 5.23, applied to the functional Φ_D in $B_1(z)$, and thanks to Corollary 6.22 here, we have that for each $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ there exists some $\hat{\delta} = \hat{\delta}_{s_0,z,T,B_1(z)}$, given by Lemma 5.23 (defined explicitly in formula (5.58)), such that

$$(6.46) \quad \Psi^{x,y}(s_0, T) \geq \frac{C_{s_0,z,B_1(z)}}{|x-y|^{n-2s_0}},$$

for all $x, y \in B_{\hat{\delta}}(z)$ with $x \neq y$, where $C_{s_0, z, B_1(z)}$ is some positive constant, given by formula (5.64).

We also recall that in Theorem 6.21 we showed that for all $s_1 \in (0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n, s_1}$, where A_{n, s_1} is the set provided in equation (6.34), there exists some constant C_{μ, T, B_1} such that

$$(6.47) \quad \Psi^{x, y}(s_1, T) \leq \frac{C_{\mu, T, B_1(z)}}{|x - y|^{2\mu}},$$

for all $x, y \in B_1(z)$ such that $x \neq y$. Therefore, using (6.46) and (6.47), for all $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $\mu \in A_{n, s_1}$, one obtains that

$$(6.48) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s_0, T)}{\mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s_1, T)} = \frac{\Psi^{x, y}(s_0, T)}{\Psi^{x, y}(s_1, T)} \geq \frac{C_{\mu, s_0, z, T, B_1(z)}}{|x - y|^{n - 2s_0 - 2\mu}}$$

for all $x, y \in B_{\hat{\delta}}(z)$ such that $x \neq y$, where we denoted

$$C_{\mu, s_0, z, T, B_1(z)} := \frac{C_{s_0, z, B_1(z)}}{C_{\mu, T, B_1(z)}}.$$

Therefore, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, by choosing $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$, $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ and $\mu := (n - \varepsilon)/2$ in (6.48), and using also (6.45), we obtain that there exists some $r = r_{\varepsilon, n, T}$ such that, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| \in (0, r)$,

$$\sup_{s \in (0, 1)} \mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s_{x, y, T}, T) \quad \text{with } s_{x, y, T} \in (0, \varepsilon).$$

This concludes the proof of (6.11) when $n \leq 2$.

In order to complete the proof of Theorem 6.3, it is only left to show (6.11) when $n \geq 3$. In this case, we just have to replace the inequality in (6.47) with the one in (6.36). By doing so, equation (6.48) becomes

$$(6.49) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s_0, T)}{\mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s_1, T)} \geq \frac{\tilde{C}_{s_0, z, T, B_1(z)}}{|x - y|^{2(s_1 - s_0)}},$$

for all $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$ and $x, y \in B_{\hat{\delta}}(z)$ with $x \neq y$, where we defined the constant

$$\tilde{C}_{s_0, z, T, B_1(z)} := \inf_{s_1 \in (s_0, 1)} \Gamma(s_1) \frac{C_{s_0, z, B_1(z)}}{C_n}.$$

The constant C_n is given in (6.37). Therefore, if for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ we choose $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ and $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ in (6.49), we can easily show (6.11). □

Proof of Theorem 6.6. Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$. Thanks to equations (6.25) and (6.30) we have that for all $\delta > 0$ and $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $|x - y| > \delta$, and for all $s_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $s_1 \in (s_0, 1)$,

$$(6.50) \quad \frac{\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_0, T)}{\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_1, T)} = \frac{\Psi^{x,y}(s_0, T)}{\Psi^{x,y}(s_1, T)} \geq s_0 C_{\delta,n,T} |x - y|^{2(s_1 - s_0)},$$

where we set

$$C_{\delta,n,T} := \frac{C_{\delta,T}}{\tilde{C}_{n,T}}.$$

The constant $C_{\delta,T}$ is given in (6.32) and (6.33) (for $T \in (1, +\infty)$ and $T \in (0, 1]$ respectively), while $\tilde{C}_{n,T}$ is provided in (6.29).

As a consequence, by choosing $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ and $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ in (6.50), and making use of (6.45), we obtain the existence of some $R = R_{n,\varepsilon,T}$ such that, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| > R$,

$$\sup_{s \in (0,1)} \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) = \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s_{x,y,T}, T) \quad \text{with } s_{x,y,T} \in (0, \varepsilon). \quad \square$$

Proof of Theorem 6.12. Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, smooth and disjoint.

We recall that

$$(6.51) \quad \mu_t^s(l) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu - tu^s \cos(\pi s)} \sin(tu^s \sin(\pi s)) du \quad \text{for all } (l, s) \in (0, +\infty) \times (0, 1),$$

see Proposition 3.1 in [KV18].

Therefore, if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, using also (6.20) with $m = 1$, we obtain that

$$(6.52) \quad \begin{aligned} \Psi^{x,y}(s, T) &= \int_0^T G^s(t, x, y) dt = \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} G(l, x, y) \mu_t^s(l) dl dt \\ &\leq 2 \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} G(l, x, y) \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} du dl dt \\ &= (4\pi)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{2}+1}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4l}\right) dl dt \\ &= \pi^{-\frac{n}{2}} |x-y|^{-n} \int_0^T \int_0^{+\infty} a^{\frac{n}{2}-1} e^{-a} da dt \\ &= T \pi^{-\frac{n}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) |x-y|^{-n} \\ &=: h(x, y), \end{aligned}$$

for all $(x, y) \in \Omega_1 \times \Omega_2$. Note that since Ω_1, Ω_2 are bounded, smooth and disjoint, one has that $h \in L^1(\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2)$. Therefore, recalling (6.44), we obtain that

$$(6.53) \quad \lim_{s \searrow 0} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) = 0.$$

Proposition 6.25, together with the limit in (6.53), gives the identities in (6.14), thus completing the proof of Theorem 6.12. \square

Proof of Theorem 6.13. Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$. We will begin by proving the result when $n \leq 2$. To do so, we consider equation (6.48) with $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$, $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$ and $\mu := (n - \varepsilon)/2$. Then, we obtain the existence of some $r = r_{\varepsilon, n, T}$ such that, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| \in (0, r)$,

$$(6.54) \quad \mathcal{E}^{x, y} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{4}, T \right) \geq \mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s, T),$$

if $s \in (\varepsilon, 1)$.

Therefore, if for some $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we have that $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x_0)$, then integrating both sides of (6.54) in $\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2$ we obtain that

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{4}, T \right) \geq \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T),$$

for all $s \in (\varepsilon, 1)$. The latter inequality, together with Theorem 6.12, gives (6.15), which concludes the proof of Theorem 6.13 when $n \leq 2$.

In order to deal with the case $n \geq 3$, it is enough to repeat the above reasoning, using equation (6.49) instead of (6.48), with $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ and $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$. \square

Proof of Theorem 6.14. Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$. We begin by taking into account equation (6.50) with $s_0 := \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ and $s_1 \in (\varepsilon, 1)$. Then, we obtain that there exists some $R = R_{n, \varepsilon, T}$ such that, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $|x - y| \in (R, +\infty)$,

$$(6.55) \quad \mathcal{E}^{x, y} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2}, T \right) \geq \mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s, T),$$

for all $s \in (\varepsilon, 1)$. Therefore, if $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are disjoint and satisfy

$$\inf_{\substack{x \in \Omega_1 \\ y \in \Omega_2}} |x - y| \geq R,$$

by integrating in $\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2$ both sides of (6.55), we obtain that

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2}, T \right) \geq \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T),$$

for all $s \in (\varepsilon, 1)$. This latter inequality, together with Theorem 6.2, entails (6.16), which concludes the proof of Theorem 6.14. \square

6.4 Appendices

Green function for the fractional Laplacian

This section is devoted to the proof of an identity for the Green function of the fractional Laplacian. We recall that for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $x \neq y$, the Green function $G^s(x, y)$ for the fractional Laplacian is given by

$$G^s(x, y) := \int_0^{+\infty} G^s(t, x, y) dt,$$

where $G^s(t, x, y)$ is the kernel of the spectral fractional heat equation.

Proposition 6.23. *Let $n \geq 2$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. Then, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ satisfying $x \neq y$ it holds that⁹*

$$(6.56) \quad \int_0^{+\infty} G^s(t, x, y) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} G(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt.$$

Proof. Let us set the notation

$$\mathcal{I}(x, y) := \int_0^{+\infty} G^s(t, x, y) dt \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}(x, y) := \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} G(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt,$$

for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $x \neq y$.

It is well-known that $G^s(t, x, y), G(t, x, y) \in C((0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n)$. Furthermore, let

$$\mathcal{R}^n := (\mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n) \setminus \{(x, x) \text{ s.t. } x \in \mathbb{R}^n\}.$$

In this way, if $\{(x_k, y_k)\}_k \subset \mathcal{R}^n$ is some sequence such that $(x_k, y_k) \rightarrow (x, y) \in \mathcal{R}^n$ for $k \rightarrow +\infty$, then using (6.20) with $m = 2$, one observes that

$$G(t, x_k, y_k) t^{s-1} \leq \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{t^{s-1}}{(4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x_k - y_k|^2}{4t}\right) \in L^1(0, +\infty)$$

and

$$G^s(t, x_k, y_k) \leq \int_0^{+\infty} \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} |G^2(l, x_k, y_k)| \mu_t^{\frac{s}{2}}(l) dl \in L^1(0, +\infty),$$

⁹As a side remark, we point out that, differently from the Green function for the Dirichlet spectral fractional Laplacian (see e.g. Proposition 5.34), the identity in (6.56) holds true only for $n \geq 2$. This is due to the fact that the heat kernel in this case decays polynomially with respect to the time, while the Dirichlet heat kernel decays exponentially.

for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $n \geq 2$. Indeed, if $d = \inf_{k \in \mathbb{N}} |x_k - y_k| > 0$, then using inequality (6.26) and recalling (6.51), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
(6.57) \quad & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} |G^2(l, x_k, y_k)| \mu_t^{s_0}(l) \, dl \, dt \\
& \leq \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D_2}{l^{\frac{n}{4}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2 d^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) \mu_t^{s_0}(l) \, dl \, dt \\
& = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D_2}{l^{\frac{n}{4}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2 d^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) \mu_t^{s_0}(l) \, dt \, dl \\
& = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D_2}{l^{\frac{n}{4}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2 d^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) \left(\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu - tu^{s_0} \cos(\pi s_0)} \sin(tu^{s_0} \sin(\pi s_0)) \, du\right) \, dt \, dl,
\end{aligned}$$

where we denoted $s_0 := s/2$,

Setting $F(t) := e^{-t\alpha} \sin(t\beta)$, with $\alpha := u^{s_0} \cos(\pi s_0)$ and $\beta := u^{s_0} \sin(\pi s_0)$, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ we integrate by parts and see that

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^T F(t) \, dt &= -\frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-t\alpha} \sin(t\beta) \Big|_0^T + \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \int_0^T e^{-t\alpha} \cos(t\beta) \, dt \\
&= -\frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-T\alpha} \sin(T\beta) - \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} e^{-t\alpha} \cos(t\beta) \Big|_0^T - \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha^2} \int_0^T e^{-t\alpha} \sin(t\beta) \, dt \\
&= -\frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-T\alpha} \sin(T\beta) - \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} e^{-T\alpha} \cos(T\beta) + \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} - \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha^2} \int_0^T F(t) \, dt.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by replacing α and β with their corresponding values, one obtains that

$$\begin{aligned}
(6.58) \quad \int_0^T F(t) \, dt &= -\frac{\cos(\pi s_0)}{u^{s_0}} e^{-Tu^{s_0} \cos(\pi s_0)} \sin(Tu^{s_0} \sin(\pi s_0)) \\
&\quad - \frac{\sin(\pi s_0)}{u^{s_0}} e^{-Tu^{s_0} \cos(\pi s_0)} \cos(Tu^{s_0} \sin(\pi s_0)) + \frac{\sin(\pi s_0)}{u^{s_0}} \\
&= \frac{1}{u^{s_0}} \left(\sin(\pi s_0) - e^{-Tu^{s_0} \cos(\pi s_0)} \sin(Tu^{s_0} \sin(\pi s_0) + \pi s_0) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Taking the limit as $T \rightarrow +\infty$ in (6.58) we thus obtain that

$$\int_0^{+\infty} F(t) \, dt = \frac{\sin(\pi s_0)}{u^{s_0}}.$$

Plugging this information into (6.57), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} |G^2(l, x_k, y_k)| \mu_t^{s_0}(l) dl dt \\
 & \leq \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{D_2}{\pi l^{\frac{n}{4}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2 d^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-lu} u^{-s_0} \sin(\pi s_0) du dl \\
 & = \frac{D_2 \Gamma(1-s_0) \sin(\pi s_0)}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{l^{\frac{n}{4}+1-s_0}} \exp\left(-\frac{d_2 d^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) dl \\
 & = \frac{3D_2 \Gamma(1-s_0) \sin(\pi s_0)}{\pi} d_2^{-\frac{3n}{4}+3s_0} d^{-n+4s_0} \int_0^{+\infty} a^{\frac{3n}{4}-3s_0-1} e^{-a} da \\
 & = \frac{3D_2 \Gamma(1-s_0) \sin(\pi s_0)}{\pi} d_2^{-\frac{3n}{4}+3s_0} d^{-n+4s_0} \Gamma\left(\frac{3n}{4}-3s_0\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

where we have applied the change of variable $a := \frac{d_2 d^{\frac{4}{3}}}{l^{\frac{1}{3}}}$.

Therefore, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain that $\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{J} \in C(\mathcal{R}^n)$.

Now let $f \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$ such that $f \geq 0$. Using the Fourier transform, for each $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we compute

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \mathcal{I}(x, y) f(y) dy &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_0^{+\infty} G^s(t, x, y) f(y) dt dy \\
 &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, x, y) f(y) dy dt = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \widehat{G}^s(t, x, \xi) \overline{\widehat{f}}(\xi) d\xi dt \\
 (6.59) \quad &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s} t} \overline{\widehat{f}}(\xi) d\xi dt \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s} t} \overline{\widehat{f}}(\xi) dt d\xi \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} \frac{\overline{\widehat{f}}(\xi)}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi,
 \end{aligned}$$

where we denoted by $\overline{\widehat{f}}(\xi)$ the complex conjugate of $\widehat{f}(\xi)$.

Notice that between the fourth and fifth line we change the order of integration since

$$e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s} t} \overline{\widehat{f}}(\xi) \in L^1((0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n).$$

Indeed, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left| e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} \widehat{f}(\xi) \right| d\xi dt &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} \left| \widehat{f}(\xi) \right| d\xi dt \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|\widehat{f}(\xi)|}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi, \end{aligned}$$

and the last integral is finite since $n \geq 2$ and \widehat{f} is a Schwarz function.

Using the Fourier transform, we obtain also that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \mathcal{J}(x, y) f(y) dy &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_0^{+\infty} G(t, x, y) t^{s-1} f(y) dt dy \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \widehat{G}(t, x, \xi) \widehat{f}(\xi) t^{s-1} d\xi dt \\ (6.60) \quad &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} \widehat{f}(\xi) t^{s-1} d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} \widehat{f}(\xi) t^{s-1} d\xi dt \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} \frac{\widehat{f}(\xi)}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, thanks to (6.59) and (6.60) we conclude that, for each $f \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (\mathcal{I}(x, y) - \mathcal{J}(x, y)) f(y) dy = 0.$$

In light of this latter identity and the fact that $\mathcal{J}, \mathcal{I} \in C(\mathcal{R}^n)$ we conclude the proof of (6.56). □

As a consequence of (6.56), we also obtain the following integral identity:

$$(6.61) \quad t \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{s}{l^s} \mu_t^s(l) dl = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \quad \text{for all } (s, t) \in (0, 1) \times (0, +\infty).$$

To establish (6.61) we argue as follows. Using the change of variable $\theta = -\frac{|x-y|^2}{4t}$, it is not hard to show that the left-hand side of (6.56) satisfies

$$(6.62) \quad \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{+\infty} G(t, x, y) t^{s-1} dt = 4^{-s} \pi^{-\frac{n}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} - s\right) \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} |x - y|^{2s-n},$$

see e.g. equation (6.41).

On the other hand, thanks to scaling property of μ_t^s , we have that

$$(6.63) \quad \mu_t^s(l) = \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \mu_1^s\left(\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}}\right),$$

see e.g. Lemma 5.17. Therefore, using this and the identity (6.20) with $m = 1$, we obtain that

$$(6.64) \quad \begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} G^s(t, x, y) dt &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) dl dt \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4l}\right) \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}} \mu_1^s\left(\frac{l}{t^{\frac{1}{s}}}\right) dl dt \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(4\pi \ell t^{\frac{1}{s}})^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4\ell t^{\frac{1}{s}}}\right) \mu_1^s(\ell) dt d\ell \\ &= 4^{-s} \pi^{-\frac{n}{2}} |x-y|^{2s-n} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2} - s\right) \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{s}{l^s} \mu_1^s(l) dl \end{aligned}$$

where we have also used the change of variables $\ell = l/t^{1/s}$ and $\theta = -\frac{|x-y|^2}{4\ell t^{\frac{1}{s}}}$ in t .

Accordingly, recalling (6.56), using (6.62) and (6.64) and exploiting again the scaling property in (6.63), we get (6.61), as desired.

Some continuity results

Proof of Proposition 6.1. Let $(x, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$. Then, if $n = 1$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, recalling the first equation in (2.15) we have that

$$\mathcal{E}^{x,x}(s, T) = \frac{1}{\pi T^{\frac{1}{2s}}(2s-1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2s}\right).$$

Thus, we deduce that $\mathcal{E}^{x,x}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$.

If either $n \geq 2$ or $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$, as a consequence of Theorem 5.24 and Corollary 6.22, we obtain that $\mathcal{E}^{x,x}(s, T) = +\infty$. □

Proposition 6.24. *Let $(x, y, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$ such that $x \neq y$. Then, it holds that $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$ and $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$.*

Proof. Let $(x, y, T) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n \times (0, +\infty)$ with $x \neq y$. Using equation (6.20) with $m = 1$, we see that

$$(6.65) \quad \begin{aligned} G^s(t, x, y) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4l}\right) \mu_t^s(l) dl \\ &\leq \sup_{l \in (0, +\infty)} \frac{1}{(4\pi l)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{|x-y|^2}{4l}\right) =: C_{x,y}, \end{aligned}$$

where $C_{x,y}$ does not depend on t . Thus, by equation (6.6) and the Maximum Principle for the fractional heat equation, we obtain that

$$(6.66) \quad \mathcal{E}^{x,y}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty),$$

for all $s \in (0, 1]$.

Taking the Fourier transform of the system of equations (6.2) we obtain that

$$(6.67) \quad G^s(t, x, y) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-|2\pi\xi|^2 s t} e^{2\pi i \xi \cdot (x-y)} d\xi,$$

and we observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left| e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^2 s t} e^{2\pi i \xi \cdot (x-y)} \right| d\xi &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^2 s t} d\xi = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\partial B_\rho} e^{-(2\pi\rho)^2 s} dH^{n-1} d\rho \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} \omega_{n-1} \rho^{n-1} e^{-(2\pi\rho)^2 s} d\rho \\ &= \frac{\omega_{n-1} t^{-\frac{n}{2s}}}{2s(2\pi)^n} \int_0^{+\infty} \theta^{\frac{n}{2s}-1} e^{-\theta} d\theta = \frac{\omega_{n-1} t^{-\frac{n}{2s}}}{2s(2\pi)^n} \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2s}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ and $t \in (0, +\infty)$, the last term is uniformly bounded in $s \in (\varepsilon, 1]$. Applying the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we obtain the continuity of $G^s(t, x, y)$ in $s \in (0, 1]$. Finally, from this and equation (6.65), we can apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem to prove that $\mathcal{E}^{x,y}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$. \square

Proposition 6.25. *Let $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be measurable and bounded. Then, $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$.*

Proof. For each $(s, t) \in (0, 1) \times (0, +\infty)$ we define the function

$$(6.68) \quad f(s, t) := \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} G^s(t, x, y) dx dy.$$

Then, using (6.20) with $m = 1$ and the well-known identity for the solution of the classical heat equation

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G(t, x, y) dx = 1 \quad \text{for all } (t, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n,$$

we obtain that

$$(6.69) \quad |f(s, t)| \leq |\Omega_2| \quad \text{for all } (s, t) \in (0, 1] \times (0, +\infty).$$

Thus, as a consequence we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) &= \frac{1}{|\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s, T) dx dy \\ (6.70) \quad &= \frac{1}{T |\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} \int_0^T G^s(t, x, y) dt dx dy \\ &= \frac{1}{T |\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_0^T f(s, t) dt \leq \frac{1}{|\Omega_1|}. \end{aligned}$$

Also, using the positivity of $\mathcal{E}^{x, y}(s, T)$, see Proposition 6.24, we obtain that, for all measurable and bounded sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$, it holds that $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(s, T) \in (0, +\infty)$.

We already proved in Proposition 6.24 that $G^s(t, x, y)$ is continuous in $s \in (0, 1]$ for all $(t, x, y) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$. Moreover, in view of equation (6.67) we have that $G^s(t, x, y)$ is uniformly bounded in $(s, x, y) \in (s_0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$ for all $s_0 \in (0, 1)$ and $t \in (0, +\infty)$. Thus, thanks to the Dominated Convergence Theorem we obtain that $f(\cdot, t) \in C((s_0, 1])$ for all $(s_0, t) \in (0, 1) \times (0, +\infty)$.

Finally, using the bound in (6.69) and the continuity of $f(s, t)$ we can conclude by means of the Dominated Convergence Theorem that $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}^{\Omega_1, \Omega_2}(\cdot, T) \in C((0, 1])$ for all $T \in (0, +\infty)$ and all measurable and bounded sets $\Omega_1, \Omega_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$. \square

Conclusions

In this chapter we investigated the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis in view of a fractional diffusive equation in \mathbb{R}^n , without any restriction on the number n of dimensions of the ambient space. The anomalous diffusion is regulated by a parameter $s \in (0, 1)$, which the forager can tune in order to maximize the success of its search.

The parameter $s = 0$ corresponds to ballistic motions (i.e., to the limit case of heavy-tailed Lévy flights), while the parameter $s = 1$ corresponds to the classical Brownian motion.

The biological scenarios of a target located in proximity of the forager and of a target arbitrarily far away have been considered in detail. We have also taken into account the case in which predators and targets are distributed uniformly in some regions.

We showed that the exponent $s = 0$ is a pessimizer for the efficiency functional. However, the most rewarding strategy for the forager may also lie arbitrarily close to $s = 0$.

As a result, the most rewarding searching option may turn out to be unreliable, since small perturbations of the optimal searching exponent lead to pessimal patterns.

It is thereby suggestive to link the adoption of the most rewarding strategy, even when close to pessimizers, to a *high-risk/high-gain* program, in which the forager aims at high-energy content prey to mitigate the risk of failure of the search (known experimental evidence on anglers and blonde skates having already related ballistic motions of the forager with the predation of targets with high-energy content).

This foraging mode can also be considered of “ambush” type, due to the tendency of Lévy distributions with fat tails to displace mass both close to the origin and at infinity.

THE LÉVY FLIGHT FORAGING
HYPOTHESIS: COMPARISON BETWEEN
STATIONARY DISTRIBUTIONS AND
ANOMALOUS DIFFUSION

We consider a stationary prey in a given region of space and we aim at detecting optimal foraging strategies.

On the one hand, when the prey is uniformly distributed, the best possible strategy for the forager is to be stationary and uniformly distributed in the same region.

On the other hand, in several biological settings, foragers cannot be completely stationary, therefore we investigate the best seeking strategy for Lévy foragers in terms of the corresponding Lévy exponent. In this case, we show that the best strategy depends on the region size in which the prey is located: large regions exhibit optimal seeking strategies close to Gaussian random walks, while small regions favor Lévy foragers with small fractional exponent.

We also consider optimal strategies in view of the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey. When this distribution is supported in a suitable volume, then the foraging efficiency functional is monotone increasing with respect to the Lévy exponent and accordingly the optimal strategy is given by the Gaussian dispersal. If instead the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is

supported in the complement of a suitable volume, then the foraging efficiency functional is monotone decreasing with respect to the Lévy exponent and therefore the optimal strategy is given by a null fractional exponent (which in turn corresponds, from a biological standpoint, to a strategy of “ambush” type).

We will devote a rigorous quantitative analysis also to emphasize some specific differences between the one-dimensional and the higher-dimensional cases.

Preamble: the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis for a general audience

Understanding how animals search for food in their environment is not only important for our knowledge of nature and animal behavior but it is also useful for suggesting optimal seeking strategies, for instance, for robots and internet engines.

The classical description of animal foraging relied on “random walks”: an animal looking for something to eat in a big area, such as a forest, unaware of the details of the environment, was supposed to take a small step in a random direction and eat the food found in this way.

However, “longer” steps may provide a better strategy. After all, on many occasions, the preys do not sit there waiting for being eaten, therefore a predator may have better hunting chances through a “hit-and-go” procedure. Also, preys may occur in sparse patches, therefore hunting strategies that are too “localized” may end up revisiting too often the same region, not allowing for a sufficiently fast exploration of the territory.

In this scenario, the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis suggested that sometimes it may be better for the forager to take a few really long steps, almost like jumping, instead of taking lots of short steps.

In jargon, these long jumps are called “Lévy flights” and they may be useful to cover “more ground” quickly: animals which thereby explore a larger area in less time may be more “efficient” in finding food. Moreover, strategies of this sort could help animals adapt to different environments, adjusting to different conditions and prey distributions, and finally enhancing their chance of survival.

The Lévy flight foraging hypothesis is however rather controversial and it is

very difficult to have ultimate answers for such a complex topic, involving so many parameters and so various conditions.

When things get difficult, some mathematics can be helpful, also to isolate different kinds of complications, to provide simple, but unambiguous models, to provide some exact answer under precisely stated and possibly verifiable hypotheses.

In this chapter, we investigate the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis looking at several main scenarios.

When prey is evenly spread out in a given area, the best strategy for the predator is to remain in that area and search around.

But in some cases, animals cannot just stay in one place. They need to move around to search for food or for a number of other activities (such as finding a partner). In these situations, in large areas, it may be better for foragers to move in a way that is similar to random walking, but in smaller areas the Lévy pattern may be preferable.

Analytical methods, such as the Fourier transform, can be useful to describe the distribution of prey and detect where it is concentrated. If prey is mostly concentrated in a certain area, it appears that random walks are preferable, but if prey is mostly found outside of that area very long jumps may become optimal, also in view of “ambush” strategies.

The dimension of the environment also plays an important role.

7.1 Introduction

A classical topic in mathematical biology consists in the detection of optimal strategies for a forager in search of food. This problem has been broadly investigated in the recent literature also in relation with the so-called Lévy flight foraging hypothesis, according to which Lévy flights, and in particular the ones with inverse square distribution of flight times or distances, can optimize search efficiencies for sparsely and randomly distributed revisitable preys in the absence of memory, reducing the oversampling associated with the classical Brownian motion. On the one hand, over the years experimental evidence has supported the occurrence of Lévy flights in animal environment (see for example [Rey+07b], in which the patterns of foraging honeybees were traced using harmonic radar and detecting resemblance

with Lévy-flights, [Sim+08], in which diverse marine predators, such as sharks, bony fishes, sea turtles, and penguins, have been demonstrated to exhibit a suitable Lévy type behavior, [Har+12], which proposed that the motility of some lymphocytes in the brain is accurately described by a Lévy distribution, also enhancing their capability of finding rare targets, [CWG15], which showed how intracellular trafficking self-organize into Lévy patterns, [Ari+15], in which dense swarms of bacteria have been shown to perform a Lévy type superdiffusion, etc.). Additionally, Lévy patterns seem to occur also in human activities (see e.g. [Bro10] which showed that geographical movements of US banknotes display dispersal relations similar to Lévy flights).

On the other hand, the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis is still a highly debated and somewhat controversial topic and a precise and rigorous approach appears to be essential in stating exactly the hypothesis and in describing carefully the several biological phenomena related to it (see e.g. [Lev+20; Bul+21; Lev+21; GK21b; Cle+21]; further suggestions and disagreements related to Lévy flights will be discussed in Section 7.2). See [Rey18] for a detailed review.

In this context, in Chapters 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 we have introduced and discussed several “efficiency functionals” related to animal foraging and motivated by the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis.

In a nutshell, the gist of these functionals is to consider the distribution of foragers and preys as probability densities and evaluate the outcome of the search from the random encounters of foragers and preys, as encoded by the product of the corresponding distributions. In addition, one can account for the energy spent by the forager during the search, by considering it as a penalization gauging the time needed for the hunt or the distance traveled by the forager. From the biological point of view, one may also consider negative values of the distribution of preys, e.g. to account for a lack of resources or for regions containing poisonous food.

A simplified, but biologically interesting, scenario is that of stationary preys: in this case the distribution of prey does not depend on time. In this setting, one could also consider the case of stationary foragers, or foragers with the ability of choosing the foraging strategy of remaining stationary. We stress however that several biological scenarios exhibit foragers which can never remain stationary. For instance,

some species of sharks (white sharks, bull sharks, sandbar sharks, porbeagles, salmon sharks, thresher sharks, pelagic threshers, bigeye threshers, alopias vulpinus, mako sharks, hammerheads, winghead sharks, bonnetheads, scoopheads, etc.) are considered obligate ram ventilators and must keep moving in order to receive oxygen from the water passing through their gills. Similarly, some species of whales, dolphins, tunas, billfishes, swordfishes, bonitos, scombrids and bluefishes need to keep moving. See e.g. [BB92; Oli+11; Weg+13; Cre+19]. Some species of lizards, gerbils and turtles are also known to be very actively moving animals, see e.g. [Sch77; OSF00; Jon04]. Drifters in constantly moving waters, such as some jellyfishes, or parasites, such as cyamids attached to constantly moving cetaceans, can be thought as seekers in continuous motions (see e.g. [Muk16; SBH19]). Also, in principle, the capacity of detecting adjacent preys could be influenced by the length and tempo of the forager's attention span (see e.g. [Swi07; Nie22] for some measurements of these quantities), hence the ansatz that stationary foragers are always capable to intercept nearby preys would also require some specific validation. Therefore it is biologically very interesting to compare the efficiency of foraging strategies of stationary and diffusive foragers in different environmental scenarios and to provide a rigorous mathematical framework to address these types of problems.

The results that we obtain in this chapter deal with a suitable efficiency functional (which will be made precise below) and with its optimization in terms of a Lévy flight fractional exponent $s \in (0, 1)$ (the case $s = 1$ corresponding to Gaussian diffusion). Surfing over technicalities, our results¹ in plain language can be expressed as follows:

Theorem 7.1 *Consider two bounded regions $\Omega_1 \subset \Omega_2$ of \mathbb{R}^n and a stationary prey uniformly distributed in Ω_1 . Then, a stationary forager uniformly distributed in Ω_2 attains a higher efficiency than any diffusive forager which is initially uniformly distributed in Ω_2 .*

¹The numbering of these theorems matches the corresponding ones presented in Section 7.3 in a formal mathematical setting. The biological interpretation of these results has not to be taken literally, and several limitations will be discussed in Section 7.2.

Theorem 7.2 *Consider a bounded region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and the case of a stationary prey uniformly distributed in a dilation Ω_r by a factor r of Ω , combined with a diffusive forager starting with a uniform distribution in Ω_r . Then, large dilations and very long searching times are optimized by dispersals close to $s = 1$ (the case of small dilations requiring a finer discussion in terms of dimension).*

Theorem 7.5 *If the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is supported in a suitable ball, then this efficiency functional is monotone increasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by the Gaussian dispersal $s = 1$. If instead the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is supported in the complement of a suitable ball, then the efficiency functional is monotone decreasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by $s = 0$.*

In Chapter 8 we will also show that the framework proposed here is general enough to consider the case of foragers with *finite lifetime* (i.e., of foragers who cannot survive after a certain time if they do not eat sufficient food).

The results presented in this section are just temporary, and somewhat imprecise, statements, aimed at introducing problems, methodologies and solutions without relying on technical lingo (also, Theorem 7.2 will be further specified according to quantitative parameters which shed light on the difference between the one-dimensional and the higher-dimensional cases). Indeed, we will give a more precise statement of these results in Section 7.3 and compare them with the corresponding biological scenarios. Before that, we will analyze some limitation and criticalities of the setting into consideration in Section 7.2.

7.2 Criticalities and limitations of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis

Scientific theories are always constrained by the extent of existing knowledge and of the available experimental observability. Biological theories often face the additional difficulty of dealing with very complex and multifaceted phenomena, in which

many different components diversely contribute and influence each other. The vast interactions of the biological world are, on numerous occasions, a severe obstruction to the mathematical analysis of a given phenomenon, since, due to the technical difficulties involved, it would be more desirable to “separate” different scenarios, “isolate” different contributions and “weigh” them differently. However, in doing so, it is virtually impossible to avoid replacing the “real world” with a somewhat simplified model. This model, however, is not merely an abstract artifact and, every so often, is helpful towards a deeper understanding of the original phenomenon.

The Lévy flight foraging hypothesis is not an exception in terms, on the one hand, of the creative stimulus towards the advance of knowledge and, on the other hand, of the criticalities and limitations intrinsic in its modelization and analysis. Actually, as it always happens to important scientific theories, the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis is (and must be) constantly challenged, improved and revised. In all this, in our humble opinion, it would be scientifically erroneous to simplistically deem theories as “right” or “wrong” (for the same reason for which Einstein’s general relativity does not make Newtonian mechanics wrong), instead the main resource of science consists precisely in having different visions to compare, different theories to confront, different scenarios to which different approaches fit better, in an harmonious framework in which these diversities complement and complete each other.

In particular, it is often difficult to discern different causes which may contribute to the formation of Lévy patterns: for example, in alternative to optimal searching strategies to detect scarce, randomly distributed resources, an alternative hypothesis has been also explored in [Boy+06], for which this pattern may result from the interaction of the foragers with a particular distribution of resources.

The literature is also full of concrete examples of theories and explanations which involved the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis which have been intensively debated and modified over time. For instance, [Vis+96] monitored five wandering albatrosses on Bird Island by attaching a salt-water immersion logger to one of their legs, with the aim of recording flight durations (i.e., time intervals between landing on the ocean) from the evidence of the logger being dry. In doing so, it was assumed that birds landed on the water solely to forage and the data collected seemed to

strongly imply that the albatrosses were performing Lévy flights. This conclusion was challenged in [Edw+07], due to a new set of high-resolution data, which instead suggested the absence of Lévy flights and that the extremely long flights, essential for demonstrating the Lévy flight behavior, were actually spurious, due to the fact that birds sitting on a nest would maintain their logger dry, without flying. See also [Edw11], in which seventeen data sets from seven previous studies have been revisited and reconsidered, also stressing the importance of considering possible alternative hypotheses to Lévy flights instead of taking them for granted (the final conclusion of [Edw11] being that “Lévy flights do not appear to have potential application as marine ecosystem indicators”).

Yet, that was not the end of the story. In [Hum+12] an accurate GPS monitor of albatrosses detected both Lévy and Brownian movement patterns for individuals. This is very telling, since it already highlights some of the specific criticalities of this research topic, such as the dependence of the results on the technology, on the instruments of measurements available at the time of the experiment, on the quantity and quality of data, and it emphasizes the difficulty in distinguishing between “individual” and “collective” behaviors.

In relation to this, also the path analysis of black bean aphids (small insects that feed on plants) carried out in [PMJ11] evidenced a structural difference between individual and collective behaviors, in this case pointing out that individuals may follow classical Brownian patterns, but, due to the variation at population level (some individuals move much farther than others) the collective motion displays superdiffusion structures similar to a Lévy flight (from the mathematical point of view, because individual movement lengths can be exponentially distributed, but with different parameters of this exponential distribution, so that the collective superposition of these exponential distributions produce a power law of Lévy type).

Furthermore, it was proposed in [Jag+11] that Lévy movements accelerate mussels’ pattern formations, but, confronting with a larger model set, it was later argued in [Bul+21] that mussels’ movements could be more accurately described by a composite Brownian walk. This topic was reconsidered also in [Rey14] bringing mussels’ movements back into the family of Lévy patterns (though, as mentioned in [Rey14], “for some of these other taxa, as with the mussels, it is possible that the tails of the step-length distributions are strictly not power-laws but are instead better rep-

resented by functions with multiple parameters”).

The comparison between Lévy type diffusion and composite Brownian walks also emerged in [Ben07] in which the alternation of extensive and intensive searching modes was related to a mixture of classical random walks, also stressing that an emergent movement patterns, such as a Lévy distribution, should not be confused with the original process giving rise to the patterns, which can well be of classical type. On this note, the role of the environmental feedback has been further analyzed in [BC15], addressing specifically the case in which the probability for the forager to detect the prey encountered during movement is low, further reinforcing the hypothesis in favor of a two-scale composite Brownian walk.

Also in relation to human mobility patterns, it is sometimes inferred from [Bro10] that human trajectories are best modeled by Lévy distribution (roughly speaking, given that money is carried by individuals, one could argue that the Lévy type dispersal of banknotes pointed out in [Bro10] is a sufficiently accurate proxy for human movement). However, this conclusion was challenged in [GHB08], on the basis that dollar bills follow the trajectory of their current owner (thus exhibiting a diffusion phenomena) while individuals tend to return to a few highly frequented locations, such as home or work. See also [Kla23] for several examples and counterexamples of experimental data either confirming or refuting the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis.

Another sector related to human activities in which Lévy flights have been adopted is related to crime modeling. In this case, a proxy of the criminal motion is taken as the distance between criminals’ homes and their targets as evidenced by solved crimes. Several sets of data indicate that burglars may undertake long trips toward attractive² burglary sites and that experienced professional burglars are willing to travel farther than amateurs (see [Hes92; VKJ98; O’L11]); both agent-based models driven by the fractional Laplacian operator (see [Cha+13]) and mean-field continuum models with truncated Lévy flights (see [Pan+18]) have been utilized to model these phenomena (and the two models are structurally different, since the continuum model ends up being more related to classical diffusion, rather than fractional diffusion).

²It is in fact suggestive to compare the willingness of burglars to perform long excursions in view of more appealing targets with the “ambush strategy” for animal foragers looking for a high energy content prey, as it will be discussed on page 312.

In addition, Lévy flights are perhaps less “universal” than what one may expect and their efficiency highly dependent on small modifications of the search conditions: for instance, it has been shown in [PCM14] that the drift caused by currents or winds may let the Lévy forager overshoot the target, favoring instead a classical Brownian forager, or Lévy foragers with exponents in the entire interval $[\frac{1}{2}, 1]$.

Other criticalities of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis include:

- Given the complicated genetic interactions, there is no guarantee that natural selection alone can always optimize a specific parameter (such as the Lévy distribution exponent),
- The classical Lévy models do not take into account the memory of the forager and the correlation between directions of successive movements,
- The comparison between Lévy and Brownian movements often does not consider other possible movement models,
- The foraging strategy may depend on a large number of parameters (density and mobility of preys, environmental conditions, etc.),
- It is often difficult to distinguish when animals are searching for food or moving for some other reason (e.g. between known locations).

Given this and other difficulties, the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis has received severe criticisms, see in particular [Pyk15].

Nonetheless, we also recall that alternative (and somewhat reinforcing) versions of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis were proposed, see e.g. [Rey15], where the author considered the situation in which Lévy patterns do not arise specifically to optimize the search of food but emerge spontaneously as byproducts of otherwise “innocuous” behaviors: if advantageous, these Lévy patterns are maintained by the natural selection.

Several researchers also intensively discussed a technical criticality of Lévy flights related to the divergence of the corresponding mean square displacements. Specifically, while the mean square displacement of the classical Brownian diffusion is linear in time (hence the mean displacement grows as the square root of time), the one

associated with the Lévy flights anomalous diffusion is infinite. At first glance, this feature of the Lévy flights seems problematic: one may think that a model arising from random walks with an infinite average square step size is a biological nonsense and that no organisms can have movement patterns resembling Lévy flights, since in nature each step must be of some finite length and no organism can escape to infinity in finite time. It is sometimes believed that the only way to circumvent this logical incongruence is to replace the notion of Lévy flights with that of Lévy “walks” (a continuous random walk typically executed at constant speed with a coupled space-time probability distributions penalizing excessively long steps). This has created a rather intense debate concerning infinite versus finite propagation velocity, often considering Lévy flights rather pathological.

However, in the words of George Box, “all models are wrong, some are useful” and the models based on Lévy flights have the convenient advantage of producing diffusive operators that can be coherently and rigorously treated from a mathematical point of view. This is a strong indication that, maybe, after all, the model is not only useful, but also not completely wrong. Specifically, an infinite mean square displacement does not mean that all organisms escape to infinity straight away, it only means that while long steps are rare, they are not sufficiently rare to make their squared average dislocation finite. In other words, the divergence of the second moment of the jump size distribution indicates that at least few long steps are present, but the coherence of the model relies on the fact that most steps are much smaller, and, all in all, most, but not all, steps are “quite short”. See [SK86a; Dyb+17] for further discussions about Lévy flights and Lévy walks.

To confirm that Lévy flights and objects with infinite mean square displacement do exist in nature, see e.g. [Bou+91], in which anomalous diffusion was observed, in a certain range of concentration and temperature, for a systems of breakable micelles. In this framework, the fact that the second moment of the jump size distribution diverges was interpreted as a byproduct of the fact that short micelles diffuse more rapidly than long ones, in such a way that the effective diffusion constantly increases with time.

See also [Wee+95], where the observations of a flow in a rapidly rotating tank in a suitably non-turbulent regime indicated the presence of Lévy flight patterns.

In this situation, the divergent second moment for flight time resulted from the alternate behavior of the flow, from sticking in vortices to long distance flies in the jets.

From the historical point of view, it is interesting to recall that power law alternatives to more consolidated Gaussian models have always raised concerns and skepticism among more traditional scientists, the first occurrence of this dispute dating back at least to the first half of the nineteenth century, see Mandelbrot's discussion in [Man01], and the specific comment according to which science is “a search for insights and simple invariances. Power laws are consequences of scale invariance. They do not claim to provide a microscopically precise multiparameter representation of everything. What they aim at is a “macroscopic” description of reality”.

In fact, well before the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis, issues related to fat tail distribution and infinite variance were highly debated among experts. Specifically, in the case just mentioned, Mandelbrot had addressed the well accepted feature of financial prices to show an extremely “anomalous” variability by casting this phenomenon into the realm of Lévy's stable distributions. This raised eyebrows, since, according to [Man73], “numerous earlier critics are sensible in their belief that infinite variance per se is a feature so undesirable that, in order to paper it over, the economist should welcome a finite-variance reformulation, even when [...] it is marred by otherwise undesirable features. [...] However, though the use of infinite variance distributions was called a radical departure, I don't believe it should continue to arouse emotion”. See also [Fam63] for related discussions about the infinity of second moments in the approach by Lévy and Mandelbrot.

Let us also mention that the criticalities of the Lévy flight foraging assumptions may also be part of the broader discussion concerning the Marginal Value Theorem (often abbreviated as MVT), see [Cha76; SK86b]. In this model, foragers perform a search within a “patch” and preys are located in patches separated by areas with no resources, therefore the search of food to meet the foragers' energetic needs is weighted by the energetically costly travel between patches (this philosophy is somewhat also in common with our notion of efficiency functional). In spite of the interest and the support for the Marginal Value Theorem, some criticalities

and limitations arose in this topic as well, since it is often difficult to objectively measure payoff rates and foraging times (especially in unfamiliar environments for the forager), or to distinguish between the foraging activity and other activities (such as avoiding predation risks or searching for mating opportunities). These criticalities have motivated some researchers to state that “the simplifying assumptions of the MVT introduce a systematic bias rather than just imprecision”, see [Non01]. See moreover Chapter 9 in [SK86b] for further discussions about limitations and pitfalls in foraging models, also beyond the specific criticalities of the MVT or the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis. So, once again, any research related to animal behavior has not to be taken literally, not as the conclusive answer, and always challenged and improved, to add yet a new bit to our modest knowledge³ of the universe.

Let us stress that the interest of Lévy distributions to optimize search strategies goes well beyond the realm of biology and, in fact, biologically inspired strategies have been adopted for several technological purposes. For example, Lévy flights have found fruitful applications in the study of robot behavior and in the development of computationally effective methods to optimize the movements of robot swarms to cover a given area, find rare targets, or track objects (see [Dar+04; ERG20; Dun+22]). On a similar note, Lévy flights have been utilized for optimization algorithms (see [CD18]) as well as wired networks and mine detection (see [GA14]). As for the biological case, Lévy flights should not be considered as a “panacea” and a fine tuning is often required (especially when the targets are clustered, see [ZGS22]).

Concerning the above mentioned criticalities, of course this chapter does not purport to be the ultimate answer in such a difficult and controversial topic. Instead, we aim at showing how these complications actually arise even in very simple situations, thus underlining the importance of tolerant, but rigorous, approaches, which sometimes cannot avoid precise, and maybe “pedantic”, mathematical definitions and an explicit set of quantitative and unambiguous hypotheses.

³See e.g. [HV21], recalling “the need for intellectual humility or being transparent about and owning the limitations of our work. Although intellectual humility is presented as a widely accepted scientific norm, [...] current research practice does not incentivize intellectual humility. [...] We hope that by pushing each other to own the limitations of our work, we can reshape the incentives so that intellectual humility is rewarded and the credibility of science increases.”

We also remark that, with an abuse of notation, we speak about “a prey” or “a forager”, while of course solutions of the fractional heat equation under consideration must be considered, strictly speaking, as “distribution of preys” or “distribution of foragers”. With this respect, one of the advantages of the approach using a fractional heat equation is that the distinction between individual and collective behaviors is somewhat implicitly overcome in the model, since the equation is itself an averaged expression and can only produce “aggregate” results (with this respect, strictly speaking, even initial conditions corresponding to Dirac’s Delta Function should not really be thought as an “individual” located at a specific point, but rather as a concentrate distribution of individuals – but it is common to surf over this subtle distinction and we will often adopt a simple language to describe the results, relegating the technical part to the mathematical theorems).

Another advantage of the fractional heat equation is that it somehow reduces the number of parameters involved in the analysis. This can also be seen as a limitation, since on many occurrences it can be desirable to include specific biological parameters (such as the sight of the animal, the previous knowledge about the environment, the interaction with other species, the fact that a search pattern could be terminated whenever a prey is found, possible spatial or temporal cutoffs, etc.). We do not aim at neglecting the importance of these parameters, which are oftentimes useful to obtain good fit with experiments, but we wanted to analyze the “simplest possible” model which can already provide some useful information on a difficult and controversial topic.

It is maybe worth completing this section by stressing that the theory of Lévy flights clearly shows the remarkable unity of different disciplines and goes beyond the rigid barriers which too often artificially separate “theory” and “application”. As a confirmation of this fact we recall the fact mentioned in [SK86a], according to which the original motivation for Paul Lévy in the 1920’s to introduce this kind of distributions was, in a sense, rather theoretical (though obviously motivated by very concrete applications): at that time the vogue seemed to be that of proving the Central Limit Theorem under the most general possible assumptions, and the work by Lévy intended to provide a limitation for such generalizations by looking at random variables with infinite second moments. This approach would have

eventually led to a broad and intense research activity involving mathematicians, physicists, biologists, engineers, computer scientists, etc., addressing the topics of anomalous diffusion, fractals, and fractional equations, from different viewpoints and with complementary techniques. And this, after all, is the beauty of science.

7.3 Formal statement of the main results

The mathematical framework that we consider takes into account a distribution of foragers, denoted by $u(t, x)$, and of preys, denoted by $p(t, x)$. Here, $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the space variable and $t \in [0, +\infty)$ denotes the time variable.

The efficiency functional accounting for the random encounters of foragers and preys takes the form

$$(7.1) \quad \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u(t, x) p(t, x) dx dt.$$

The initial densities of foragers and preys are normalized to be probability distributions, i.e.

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u(0, x) dx = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} p(0, x) dx = 1.$$

However, we will not necessarily assume here that these densities are nonnegative (hence, the notion of probability measure has to be intended as a “signed” measure⁴ with unit total mass).

We will focus on the case of *stationary prey* $p(t, x) = p(x)$, i.e. p independent of time. As for the forager, we will consider two main scenarios. The first scenario is that of a *stationary forager* described by $u(t, x) = u(x)$. The second consists of a *diffusive forager* evolving according to the fractional heat equation

$$(7.2) \quad \partial_t u = -(-\Delta)^s u.$$

⁴While in the foraging problem densities of individuals are naturally nonnegative, our framework is general enough to comprise the situation in which the sign of the quantities involved is not specified, and this may find applications in other circumstances in which “negative densities” may indicate “debts” or “gaps”. From the technical point of view, this is useful for us when we consider Fourier transforms, see Figure 7.1.

In this setting, for all $s \in (0, 1)$, the operator $-(-\Delta)^s$ is the *fractional Laplacian* defined as

$$(7.3) \quad -(-\Delta)^s \phi(x) := c_{n,s} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\phi(x+y) + \phi(x-y) - 2\phi(x)}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy,$$

where $c_{n,s}$ is a suitable⁵ normalization constant (specifically, $c_{n,s} = \frac{2^{2s-1}\Gamma(\frac{n}{2}+s)}{\pi^{n/2}|\Gamma(-s)|}$, where Γ is Euler's Gamma function). An interesting role of this constant is to allow one to account for the cases $s = 0$ and $s = 1$ as limit situations in (7.3) and thus consider (7.2) for all $s \in [0, 1]$ in a unified notation. In particular, the case $s = 1$ corresponds to a classical Laplace operator on the right-hand side of (7.2), hence, (7.2) for $s = 1$ reduces to the classical heat equation, generated by the standard random walk (instead, for $s \in (0, 1)$, the infinitesimal generator of (7.2) is a Lévy flight). See also [Sil05; AV19] for a basic introduction to the fractional Laplacian.

When $s = 0$, equation (7.2) reduces to $\partial_t u = -u$. In particular, for a forager initially concentrated at a given point $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the case $s = 0$ produces

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = \delta(y - x), \end{cases}$$

where δ stands for Dirac's Delta Function. In this setting, the formal solution takes the form

$$(7.4) \quad e^{-t} \delta(y - x).$$

This solution shows an interesting feature of the $s = 0$ case, which is perhaps not completely intuitive: indeed (7.4) exhibits both a lack of regularity (the solution is not a smooth function when $t > 0$, since it still presents a Dirac's Delta Function) and loss of mass (the total mass at time t being equal to e^{-t} , showing that the mass is not preserved in time and suggesting that part of the mass is “instantaneously” pushed far away). These mathematical characteristics can be interpreted as an “ambush

⁵The role of this normalization constant is simply to allow a “nice” representation of the fractional Laplacian operator in terms of the Laplace transform. Specifically, with this normalization, the Fourier transform of $(-\Delta)^s u(x)$ is simply $(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s} \hat{u}(\xi)$, where \hat{u} is the Fourier transform of u , namely

$$\hat{u}(\xi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u(x) e^{2\pi i x \cdot \xi} dx.$$

strategy”, in which a forager can remain still and suddenly perform a long jump, see Remark 6.10. These ambush patterns have also been observed in nature, especially when the prey possesses high energy content, see [Dyb+17], therefore they can also be related to “high risk/high gain” strategies. Namely, this approach of “risking it all for a big reward”, related to sudden “surprise attacks” by the forager striving for a highly advantageous target, is the counterpart of a small Lévy exponent anomalous diffusion in which the low regularizing effect of the parabolic operator allows both a significant forager density to remain at the initial point and a notable part of this density to drift away.

A natural question in foraging strategies is whether stationary foragers would better fit stationary preys with uniform distributions sharing the same region. We give a rigorous positive answer to this problem, according to the following result:

Theorem 7.1. *Consider a stationary prey uniformly distributed in $\Omega_1 \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, i.e.*

$$p(x) = \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}(x)}{|\Omega_1|},$$

and suppose that $\Omega_1 \subset \Omega_2$.

Then, the efficiency functional associated with a stationary forager uniformly distributed in Ω_2 , i.e.

$$(7.5) \quad u(x) = \frac{\chi_{\Omega_2}(x)}{|\Omega_2|},$$

is larger than that associated with a diffusive forager satisfying

$$(7.6) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = \frac{\chi_{\Omega_2}(x)}{|\Omega_2|}, \end{cases}$$

for any value of $s \in [0, 1]$.

Here above and in the rest of this chapter, we are adopting the standard notation for the indicator function of a set, namely

$$\chi_A(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We stress that Theorem 7.1 must not be taken literally in a biological context, since one does not expect⁶ passive foragers waiting for a stationary prey to arrive. The fact is that Theorem 7.1 describes an optimality “at the group level”, dealing with distributions of foragers and preys, not at individual level. The disparity of these approaches sits in the fact that selection pressures seem not to operate at the group (i.e., population) level but rather at the individual (i.e., genetic) level, making “dynamic” strategies more advantageous for single individuals. Besides, as mentioned in Section 7.2, the search for food is not the unique pressure for an animal and other needs, such as avoiding predation risks or searching for mating opportunities, can favor movement and penalize stationary strategies. Also, Theorem 7.1 assumes the locations to be revisitable and the prey to be instantaneously replaceable by a new prey, which is certainly an idealized situation (the scarcity of the remaining food after depleting the resource being otherwise an incentive for the forager to leave the patch). In any case, results such as Theorem 7.1 only focus on the time of the forager dedicated to the search of food, not on the entire lifespan of the forager.

In spite of these limitations, Theorem 7.1 provides a useful “sanity check” to attest the coherence of the model. Also, Theorem 7.1 raises the natural question of what the best diffusive forager is (this is also a relevant biological question, since, as we have already pointed out, some biological foragers cannot be stationary and therefore cannot reach the optimal strategy of Theorem 7.1). In the next result we prove that the best diffusive search strategy (in terms of the most appropriate choice of s) heavily depends on the size of the domain.

Notice indeed that the analysis of optimal foraging strategies in the class of fractional dispersal remains interesting and possibly nontrivial even when the forager and the prey share the same initial distribution, since, even in the case of a stationary prey, the forager cannot be stationary and one has still to detect the optimal exponent s for this type of search.

⁶There are however many examples of sit-and-wait predators in nature. Some, such as the striated frogfish and the orchid mantis, use camouflage to attract prey, others, such as web-spinning spiders, build traps, others, such as the chameleons, use their abilities and special biological features (e.g., an exceptional tongue) to accomplish their goals. See e.g. Chapter 5 in [Cur12] for further details.

In this framework, one could expect, on the one hand, the exponent $s = 0$ to provide some kind of optimality, since, essentially, the distribution of the forager would remain qualitatively unchanged, in view of (7.4), yet some mass of the foragers is instantaneously delivered towards infinity. On the other hand, one could also expect $s = 1$ to give some chance of optimality, since this would somewhat correspond to short Gaussian excursions. These considerations suggest that the optimality problem of stationary preys and fractional dispersive foragers with the same initial distributions is interesting and can reserve some surprises.

To clarify our result, given a bounded region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, we consider a stationary prey uniformly distributed in Ω , with corresponding distribution

$$p_\Omega(x) := \frac{\chi_\Omega(x)}{|\Omega|},$$

and a diffusive forager whose initial configuration is also uniformly distributed in Ω . More explicitly, given $s \in [0, 1]$, the distribution of such a forager corresponds to the solution of

$$(7.7) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = \frac{\chi_\Omega(x)}{|\Omega|}, \end{cases}$$

and we denote by $u_{s,\Omega}$ this solution. Thus, recalling (7.1), given a time duration $T > 0$, we consider the associated efficiency functional

$$(7.8) \quad \mathcal{J}^\Omega(s, T) := \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u_{s,\Omega}(t, x) p_\Omega(x) dx dt.$$

Given $r > 0$, we also consider the dilation by a factor r of the region Ω , namely

$$\Omega_r := \{rx \text{ s.t. } x \in \Omega\}.$$

Our result states that for each region Ω we can find some time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$ of the search and a dilation Ω_r for some large $r \in (1, +\infty)$, such that $\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ is strictly increasing. The biological intuition for this result is that short range dispersal strategies maintain the foragers close to the prey, with a possible error localized near the boundary of the region, and a large dilation makes this boundary region more negligible with respect to the bulk of the domain: consequently, for

large regions, in which the boundary effect becomes negligible with respect to the core of the domain, the classical Brownian motion becomes optimal.

Moreover, we show that by considering instead a small dilation Ω_r , for some $r \in (0, 1)$, then $\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ is strictly decreasing. The biological intuition for this being that, if the distribution of prey occurs in a very small region, then any dispersal strategy would move the forager away from the prey, making it more convenient for the seeker to adopt an extreme strategy which maintains it, as much as possible, at the initial position, possibly at the risk of being quickly pushed towards infinity, since in any case small displacement would be sufficient to miss the prey.

The precise result needs to take into account the time span of the search and goes as follows:

Theorem 7.2. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, measurable and strictly convex. Then, there exists some $r_\Omega \in (1, +\infty)$ such that*

$$(7.9) \quad \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \quad \text{is strictly increasing in } s \in (0, 1),$$

for each $r \in (r_\Omega, +\infty)$ and $T \in [r^2, +\infty)$.

Furthermore, for each $T \in (0, +\infty)$ there exists some $r_{\Omega, T} \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$(7.10) \quad \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \quad \text{is strictly decreasing in } s \in \left(0, \frac{n}{2}\right] \cap (0, 1),$$

for each $r \in (0, r_{\Omega, T})$.

Also, if $n = 1$, for each $\sigma \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ there exist some $T_\sigma \in (1, +\infty)$ and $\tilde{r}_\Omega \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$(7.11) \quad \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \quad \text{is strictly increasing in } s \in (\sigma, 1),$$

for each $T \in (T_\sigma, +\infty)$ and $r \in (0, \tilde{r}_\Omega)$.

Some comments about Theorem 7.2 are in order. First of all, the claim in (7.9) holds true in every dimension and states, roughly speaking, that, in case of large domains and very long searching times, the forager strategy is optimized by the Gaussian dispersal: this is consistent with the idea that very long times combined with Lévy flights at some point would make the forager jump out of the domain.

The claim in (7.10) also holds true in every dimension, but its interpretation varies according to the cases $n = 1$ and $n \geq 2$. When $n \geq 2$, the claim in (7.10) boils down to

$$\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \text{ is strictly decreasing in } s \in (0, 1),$$

for each $r \in (0, r_{\Omega, T})$, saying that given any prescribed searching time, if the domain is sufficiently small, then the optimal strategy is $s = 0$. This is in agreement with the idea that the exponent $s = 0$ tends to keep a significant portion of the mass close to the original position.

However, the exponent $s = 0$ also tends to send a significant portion of the mass towards infinity, therefore these types of statements do require a careful analysis, and indeed the situation in dimension 1 is different. Indeed, when $n = 1$ the claim in (7.10) becomes

$$\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \text{ is strictly decreasing in } s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}],$$

for each $r \in (0, r_{\Omega, T})$, giving that $s = 0$ outperforms every other strategy $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$, leaving however the possibilities that other strategies $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ may be optimizers (or at least local optimizers). The role played by $s = \frac{1}{2}$ in this case is possibly related to the transient/recurrent phenomena of the Lévy flights (see Section 2 in [ADV20]). Specifically, when $n \geq 2$, and when $n = 1$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, the Lévy flight drifts away from the initial location, without coming back: in this setting, the foragers' mass sent out of the domain is not expected to return and therefore keeping a portion of the mass at the original location becomes particularly efficient (thus favoring the strategy $s = 0$).

Instead, when $n = 1$ and $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$, part of the mass sent out will eventually come back arbitrarily close to the original location. This effect is of course important when the searching time is sufficiently long, and this is the content of (7.11), which implies that long searching times and small domains may produce $s = 1$ as a local optimizer (possibly because some preys is found by the forager after exiting and reentering the domain).

We also remark that (7.11) gives that the claim in (7.10) is sharp, since the intersection with the interval $(0, \frac{n}{2}]$ cannot be dropped (hence, the one-dimensional case is significantly different from the others).

It is certainly worth investigating deeper the special case $n = 1$ to further understand the differences with respect to the higher-dimensional cases. For example, in the one-dimensional case, due to the lack of monotonicity in the efficiency functional, one can also look at pessimizers for the foraging strategies. In this context, it follows from a careful analysis of (7.10) and (7.11) that in the one-dimensional case the functional $\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ develops a global minimizer in a neighbourhood of $s = \frac{1}{2}$, for r small enough and T large enough. More precisely, we can state the following result.

Corollary 7.3. *Let $n = 1$ and Ω be some bounded interval. Then, there exist some $T_\Omega \in (1, +\infty)$ and $r_\Omega \in (0, 1)$ such that for each $r \in (0, r_\Omega)$, $T \in (T_\Omega, +\infty)$ and some $\sigma_T \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$*

$$(7.12) \quad \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T) \text{ has a global minimizer in the interval } s \in \left[\frac{1}{2}, \sigma_T \right].$$

Furthermore, it holds that

$$(7.13) \quad \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \sigma_T = \frac{1}{2}.$$

In the one-dimensional case, for each $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, we will consider the functional⁷

$$(7.14) \quad \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s) := r^{2s-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi.$$

As stated in (7.15) here below, this functional corresponds to the limit for the time span T diverging to infinity of the functional $T\mathcal{J}$, therefore it is interesting to consider this functional as a proxy for the *renormalized efficiency of a very long search*.

We establish that $\mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot)$ is strictly increasing for each dilation of parameter r large enough. Furthermore, we also prove that for every subset $(0, \sigma) \subset (0, \frac{1}{2})$ there exists some $r_{\sigma, \Omega} \in (0, 1)$ such that the functional $\mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot)$ is strictly decreasing in $(0, \sigma)$ for each $r \in (0, r_{\sigma, \Omega})$. To conclude, we also show that if $\sigma \nearrow \frac{1}{2}$, then the parameter $r_{\sigma, \Omega}$ converges to zero.

⁷The right-hand side of (7.14) diverges when $s \geq \frac{1}{2}$ and this is the reason for us to restrict our attention to the range $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ in this case.

Corollary 7.4. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}$ be some bounded interval and $\mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot)$ be given as in equation (7.14). Then, for each $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $r \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that*

$$(7.15) \quad \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} T \mathcal{J}^{\Omega r}(s, T) = \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s).$$

Also, there exists some $r_\Omega \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for each $r \in (r_\Omega, +\infty)$,

$$(7.16) \quad \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot) \text{ is strictly increasing in the interval } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right).$$

Furthermore, for each $\sigma \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, there exists $r_{\sigma, \Omega} \in (0, +\infty)$, with

$$(7.17) \quad \lim_{\sigma \nearrow \frac{1}{2}} r_{\sigma, \Omega} = 0$$

and such that,

$$(7.18) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{for each } r \in (0, r_{\sigma, \Omega}), \text{ the function } \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot) \\ &\text{is strictly decreasing in the interval } s \in (0, \sigma) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$(7.19) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{for each } r \in (r_{\sigma, \Omega}, +\infty), \text{ the function } \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot) \\ &\text{cannot be decreasing in the interval } s \in (0, \sigma). \end{aligned}$$

In a nutshell, the result in (7.16) suggests that, for very long time asymptotics of a one-dimensional searching pattern, when the prey is uniformly distributed in a large interval, the pessimizer occurs at $s = 0$ and the optimizer at $s = \frac{1}{2}$.

The situation for small intervals is instead different, since (7.18) shows that for any $\sigma \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ the pessimizer cannot occur in the interval $[0, \sigma]$, provided that the domain is sufficiently small.

All in all, these results warn us about the complexity of the foraging problem, which needs to quantitatively and rigorously examine different cases (depending on dimensionality, distribution of preys, etc.), since each scenario presents its own specificity.

Some further comments about (7.17) and (7.19) are in order. These claims state the sharpness of the choice of $r_{\sigma, \Omega}$ in Corollary 7.4. Namely, by (7.19) one knows that $r_{\sigma, \Omega}$ is taken “as large as possible” (of course, choosing a smaller value would still produce (7.18), but this would violate (7.19)).

Interestingly, even this choice of $r_{\sigma,\Omega}$ in its largest possible sense does not allow it to be bounded from zero as $\sigma \nearrow \frac{1}{2}$, as expressed in (7.17), thus showing the quantitative optimality of the claims in Corollary 7.4.

From a biological standpoint, it is also interesting to consider the case of a stationary prey which is not uniformly distributed and a diffusive forager that aims at optimizing its searching strategy. In this case, we consider a stationary distribution of prey $p \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and a diffusive forager with initial distribution equal to the prey. Thus, the distribution of forager is a probability density satisfying

$$(7.20) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = p(x). \end{cases}$$

We will denote by u_p the solution of (8.7). We recall that we are not assuming here that $p \geq 0$ (as already observed, from the biological point of view, we may consider negative values of p as denoting a lack of resources, or by regions containing poisonous food). In light of (7.1), we consider in this setting the efficiency functional of the form

$$(7.21) \quad \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u_p(t, x) p(x) dx dt.$$

For simplicity, we are dropping here the normalization obtained by dividing by T (compare (7.8) and (7.21)), since this normalization does not play a role when optimizing in the diffusion exponent s .

Thus, we have:

Theorem 7.5. *The efficiency functional (7.21) associated with a forager diffusing as in (8.7) has the form*

$$(7.22) \quad \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2st}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi dt.$$

In particular, if the Fourier transform of p is supported in the ball of radius $\frac{1}{2\pi}$, then this efficiency functional is monotone strictly increasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by the Gaussian dispersal $s = 1$.

If instead the Fourier transform of p is supported in the complement of the ball of radius $\frac{1}{2\pi}$, then this efficiency functional is monotone strictly decreasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by $s = 0$.

Figure 7.1: Plots of the inverse Fourier transform of $\chi_{(-1/2,1/2)}(\xi - a)$, with $a \in \{0, 2, 8\}$. Analytically, this corresponds to the plots of $y = \frac{\cos(2\pi ax) \sin(\pi x)}{\pi x}$.

Let us comment on the consistency of Theorem 7.5 with the biological scenario. Roughly speaking, distributions whose Fourier transform are supported close to the origin present “mild oscillations”, while the ones whose Fourier transform has support reaching towards infinity present “wilder oscillations” (see e.g. Figure 7.1, for an explicit example of oscillations increased by shifting the support of the Fourier transform). Thus, in a sense, the monotonicity statement in Theorem 7.5 suggests that:

- on the one hand, when the distribution of preys has mild oscillations, the classical random walk is better than any fractional diffusion (coherently with the intuition that it is not convenient for the forager to leave its original location),
- on the other hand, when the distribution of preys has wild oscillations, the fractional parameter $s = 0$ is the optimizer (because, roughly speaking, it is more convenient for the forager to try not to move at all, possibly at the risk of being sent to infinity straight away, since in any case small fluctuations in a highly oscillatory framework may end up in inconvenient regions for the prey distribution, recall the discussion below (7.4)).

The change of monotonicity detected in Theorem 7.5 can be visualized in Figures 8.1 and 7.3 (see also Figure 7.6 for a graphical sketch in higher dimension).

Figure 7.2: Plots of the efficiency functional in (8.1) when $T = 1$ and $\widehat{p} = \chi_{(-a,a)}$, with $a \in \{0.08, 0.3, 2\}$. Notice the change in monotonicity in the fractional exponent s .

We can also interpret the results stated in Theorem 7.2 in light of Theorem 7.5, according, very roughly speaking, to a prescription of the type

as well as

That is, if one considers, as a model case, a uniform distribution of prey in the interval $(-a, a)$, the corresponding Fourier transform takes the form $\widehat{p}(\xi) = \frac{\sin(2\pi a\xi)}{\pi\xi}$. Hence, one can renormalize the efficiency functional in (8.1) by dividing by a^2 (since this does not change the optimization procedure in s): in this way, a noticeable quantity for the efficiency functional becomes

(7.25)

$$\frac{|\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2}{a^2} = \frac{\sin^2(2\pi a\xi)}{(\pi a\xi)^2}.$$

The advantage of this normalization is that the value at $\xi = 0$ of this function is always equal to 4, for every choice of $a > 0$. A sketch of such a function for different values of a is given in Figure 7.4.

From these diagrams it is apparent that for small values of a the function in (7.25) presents a significant portion of mass far from the origin (indeed, its limit as $a \rightarrow 0$ is identically equal to 4), and therefore, by Theorem 7.5, we would expect the efficiency functional to be maximized for values of the Lévy exponent close to $s = 0$, which is indeed proved to be true in Theorem 7.2. Note that these considerations are consistent with the heuristic presented in (7.23).

Instead, for large values of a the function in (7.25) concentrates at the origin (indeed, its limit as $a \rightarrow +\infty$ is the indicator function of the origin), and therefore, by Theorem 7.5, we would expect the efficiency functional to be maximized for values of the Lévy exponent close to $s = 1$, which is indeed proved to be true in Theorem 7.2. Note that these considerations are consistent with the heuristic presented in (7.24).

Figure 7.3: Plots of the efficiency functional in (8.1) when $T = 1$ and $\hat{p} = \chi_{(r-\frac{1}{3\pi}, r+\frac{1}{3\pi})}$, with $r \in \{0, 0.16, 3\}$. Notice the change in monotonicity in the fractional exponent s .

We stress however that the argument for large domains presents an important caveat: namely, as stressed in Theorem 7.2, the optimizer for large domain is indeed close to $s = 1$, but only provided that the search lasts long enough. In Figure 7.5 we exhibit an example of how, for the same initial domain Ω , we can have a change of monotonicity for \mathcal{J}^Ω , as we consider different lifetimes $T \in (0, +\infty)$.

Figure 7.4: Plots of $\frac{\sin^2(2\pi a\xi)}{(\pi a\xi)^2}$ with $a \in \{0.035, 0.1, 0.5\}$.

This is due to the fact that, for small times $T \in (0, +\infty)$, most of the mass of a forager diffusing according to (7.7) for some s close to zero is fixed at the initial location, with only a small part of it sent to infinity. In this case, even for a large domain, a strongly nonlocal approach seems more convenient, since most of the mass will be confined in Ω .

Instead, when the time span $T \in (0, +\infty)$ is large enough, the monotonicity properties of \mathcal{J} change. Indeed, as s is close to zero, as a consequence of the large time span T , we have that a greater part of the forager mass is going to infinity, thus exiting the perimeter of the domain Ω where the prey is distributed. In this case, it is more convenient to move according to a strategy close to the Brownian motion. Indeed, this leads to short-medium jumps which allow to search the domain while letting as little mass as possible out of Ω .

Figure 7.5: Plots of $(0, 1) \ni s \rightarrow \mathcal{J}^\Omega(s, T)$, with $\Omega = (-10^4, 10^4)$ and $T \in \{1, 10^8\}$.

It would be also interesting to consider more general cases of the above results, in which an active interaction between the forager and the prey takes place. For

instance, one could consider the case of foragers with the ability of “smelling” preys, which could produce a drift, or chemotactic, term in the diffusive equation. An interesting model for foragers with long range smell has been proposed in [SMS20], see also [BR14]. This model also accounts for the situation in which the forager has a finite lifetime (that is, it can forage only for a finite time, since if it does not eat any food for a given time interval, then it dies). This is a very interesting possibility and we will deal with it in Chapter 8.

We now provide the proofs of the above results.

7.4 Proof of the main results

Given $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $s \in [0, 1]$, we denote by $G^s(t, x, y)$ the solution of the fractional heat equation with initial condition given by the Dirac’s Delta Function at y , namely $G^s(t, x, y)$ solves

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = \delta(y - x). \end{cases}$$

Also, if u_p is the solution to (8.7), then we can write

$$(7.26) \quad u_p(t, x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} G^s(t, x, y) p(y) dy.$$

We now start the proofs of the main results by checking (8.1), so that we will be able to use it in the proofs of the main theorems.

Proof of (8.1). Taking the Fourier transforms in the spatial variables of (7.26) we see that

$$\widehat{u}_p(t, \xi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \widehat{G}^s(t, x, y) p(y) dy = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t - 2\pi iy \cdot \xi} p(y) dy.$$

Hence, by (7.21) and Plancherel’s Theorem, denoting with the bar the complex conjugation, the efficiency functional can be written as

$$\int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u_p(t, x) \overline{p(x)} dx dt = \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \widehat{u}_p(t, x\xi) \overline{\widehat{p}(\xi)} d\xi dt$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t - 2\pi iy \cdot \xi} p(y) \overline{\widehat{p}(\xi)} dy d\xi dt \\
 &= \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} \widehat{p}(\xi) \overline{\widehat{p}(\xi)} d\xi dt,
 \end{aligned}$$

giving (8.1). □

Now we address the proofs of the main theorems.

Proof of Theorem 7.1. In light of (7.1), the efficiency functional associated with a stationary forager as in (7.5) is

$$(7.27) \quad \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u(t, x)p(t, x) dx dt = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{\Omega_2}(x)}{|\Omega_2|} \frac{\chi_{\Omega_1}(x)}{|\Omega_1|} dx dt = \frac{|\Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2|}{|\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|}.$$

In particular, if $\Omega_1 \subset \Omega_2$ we have that this value coincides with $\frac{1}{|\Omega_2|}$.

Recalling (7.26) and owing to the Maximum Principle for the fractional heat equation (7.6), we have that the efficiency functional in the fractional diffusion case is bounded from above by

$$\frac{1}{T |\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1 \times \Omega_2} G^s(t, x, y) dx dy dt \leq \frac{1}{T |\Omega_1| |\Omega_2|} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_1} dx dt = \frac{1}{|\Omega_2|}.$$

This completes the proof. □

The material developed so far is sufficient to prove Theorem 7.2. For the reader’s facility, this technical proof is deferred to Appendix 7.6.

Proof of Corollary 7.3. We begin by recalling (7.52). In this way, if $r \in (0, \tilde{r}_\Omega)$ and $T \in (4, +\infty)$, we have that, for each $\sigma \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ and $s \in (\sigma, 1)$,

$$\partial_s \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) \geq \frac{1}{T} \left(C \ln \left(\frac{T}{4} \right) T^{1-\frac{1}{2s}} - \frac{|\Omega|^2}{\pi(2\sigma - 1)^2} \right).$$

Thus, since in this setting $1 - \frac{1}{2s} \geq 0$, and accordingly $T^{1-\frac{1}{2s}} \geq 1$, we find that

$$(7.28) \quad \inf_{s \in (\sigma, 1)} \partial_s \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) \geq \frac{1}{T} \left(C \ln \left(\frac{T}{4} \right) - \frac{|\Omega|^2}{\pi(2\sigma - 1)^2} \right).$$

Now we define

$$(7.29) \quad \sigma_T := \frac{1}{2} + \frac{|\Omega|}{2\sqrt{C\pi \ln(T/4)}}.$$

We observe that $\sigma_T \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ for T large enough, and in fact

$$(7.30) \quad \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \sigma_T = \frac{1}{2}.$$

In view of (7.28) and (7.29), we find that

$$\inf_{s \in (\sigma_T, 1)} \partial_s \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) \geq 0,$$

whence the minimum of $\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ must occur for $s \in [0, \sigma_T]$.

However, when $r > 0$ is small enough, by (7.10) (applied here with $n = 1$) we know that $\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ is decreasing in $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$.

Therefore, when T is sufficiently large and r is sufficiently small, the minimum of $\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ must occur for $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, \sigma_T]$. This proves (7.12).

Also, the claim in (7.13) follows from (7.30). □

One is now in the position of completing the proof of Corollary 7.4. For the reader's convenience, this technical proof is deferred to Appendix 7.6.

Proof of Theorem 7.5. We begin by observing that since the integrand in (8.1) is nonnegative, then we can change the order of integration and obtain

$$(7.31) \quad \begin{aligned} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-t(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi dt &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_0^T e^{-t(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 dt d\xi \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{1 - e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we define the function

$$f(\xi, s, T) := \frac{1 - e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}},$$

and we compute its partial derivative with respect to the fractional parameter s

$$(7.32) \quad \begin{aligned} &\partial_s f(\xi, s, T) \\ &= \frac{2T e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} \ln(2\pi|\xi|) (2\pi|\xi|)^{4s} - \left(1 - e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}\right) 2 \ln(2\pi|\xi|) (2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{4s}} \\ &= 2 \ln(2\pi|\xi|) (2\pi|\xi|)^{2s} \left(\frac{T (2\pi|\xi|)^{2s} e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} - 1 + e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{4s}} \right) \\ &= T^2 k(\xi, s) \sigma'(T (2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}), \end{aligned}$$

where σ is the function given by

$$(7.33) \quad \sigma(x) := \frac{1 - e^{-x}}{x}$$

and we set

$$(7.34) \quad k(\xi, s) := 2 \ln(2\pi |\xi|) (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}.$$

We notice that $k(\xi, s) \in L^\infty(B_1 \times (\beta, 1))$ for each $\beta \in (0, 1)$.

Also,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \sigma'(x) = -\frac{1}{2}, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} \sigma'(x) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad e^x \geq x + 1.$$

From these observations, it follows that

$$(7.35) \quad \sigma'(x) \leq 0 \quad \text{for each } x \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma' \in L^\infty((0, +\infty)).$$

Therefore, if $\beta \in (0, 1)$, we obtain the estimate

$$(7.36) \quad \sup_{\substack{\xi \in B_1 \\ s \in (\beta, 1)}} |\partial_s f(\xi, s, T)| \leq T^2 \|k\|_{L^\infty(B_1 \times (\beta, 1))} \|\sigma'\|_{L^\infty((0, +\infty))} =: C_{T, \beta}.$$

Furthermore, we notice that we can rewrite the second line in (7.32) as

$$\partial_s f(\xi, s, T) = -2u(\xi, s)v(T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}),$$

where

$$v(x) := 1 - e^{-x}(x + 1) \quad \text{and} \quad u(\xi, s) := \frac{\ln(2\pi|\xi|)}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}.$$

We note that $v \in L^\infty((0, +\infty))$. Also, for each $\beta \in (0, 1)$, we see that $u \in L^\infty((\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \times (\beta, 1))$. As a consequence, for each $s \in (\beta, 1)$,

$$\sup_{\substack{\xi \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \\ \beta \in (0, 1)}} |\partial_s f(\xi, s, T)| \leq \|u\|_{L^\infty((\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \times (\beta, 1))} \|v\|_{L^\infty((0, +\infty))} =: \tilde{C}_\beta.$$

In view of this estimate and (7.36), we conclude that for each $\beta \in (0, 1)$ there exists some constant $\widehat{C}_{T, \beta}$, depending on β and T , such that, for every $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $s \in (\beta, 1)$,

$$|\partial_s f(\xi, s, T)| |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 \leq \widehat{C}_{T, \beta} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2.$$

Accordingly, we can apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem, and obtain that, for every $s \in (0, 1)$,

$$(7.37) \quad \partial_s \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{1 - e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} T^2 k(\xi, s) \sigma'(T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi.$$

Now, we notice that $k(\xi, s)$ is negative if and only if $\xi \in B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}$. From this observation, (7.31) and (8.33), we can conclude the proof of Theorem 7.5. \square

Remark 7.6. We observe that the result stated in Theorem 7.5 is optimal, in the sense that translations of \widehat{p} supported in $B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}$ produce internal critical points in $[0, 1]$, breaking the monotonicity of (8.1) with respect to the Lévy exponent (in particular, one cannot expect that the efficiency functional is always monotone in s). Indeed, if for some $v \in \partial B_1$ and some $\widehat{p} \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$ supported in $B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}$ we define the function

$$g(s, r) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} T k(\xi, s) \sigma'(T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) |\widehat{p}(\xi - rv)|^2 d\xi dt,$$

where σ and k are given respectively in (7.33) and (8.31), then by (7.31), (8.30), and Theorem 7.5 we have that $g(s, 0) > 0$, while $g(s, \frac{3}{2\pi}) < 0$ for each $s \in (0, 1)$. Since $g(s, \cdot) \in C((0, +\infty))$ and g is the derivative of the efficiency functional in (8.1), we have that for each $s_0 \in (0, 1)$ there exists some $r_0 \in (0, \frac{3}{2\pi})$ such that s_0 is a critical point of (8.1) for $\widehat{p}(\xi - rv)$.

As an example of this phenomenon we consider the translations of $\widehat{p}(\xi) = \chi_{B_{\frac{1}{3\pi}}}(\xi)$. In particular, in Figure 7.6 we have plotted the two variables function

$$L(s, r) := \int_0^1 \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2st}} |\chi_{B_{\frac{1}{3\pi}}}(\xi - r)|^2 d\xi dt.$$

We can clearly see that as we translate the support of $\widehat{p}_r(\xi) := \chi_{B_{\frac{1}{3\pi}}}(\xi - r)$, the monotonicity in s of $L(s, r)$ changes, according to Theorem 7.5.

7.5 Conclusions

Like all significant scientific theories, the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis has undergone continuous questioning, discussion, debate, and revision. This is particularly

Figure 7.6: Plot of $(0, 1) \times (0, 5) \ni (s, r) \rightarrow L(s, r)$. As r increases we see that the monotonicity of $L(\cdot, r)$ changes.

due to the inherent challenge of distinguishing various factors that might contribute to anomalous diffusion, the influence of technological limitations on data collection and interpretation, and the sometimes nuanced differentiation between individual and collective behaviors.

In Section 7.2 we have recalled the different views emerged on the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis and also discussed the controversies about the use of distributions with infinite moment and processes with infinite propagation velocity.

The main results of this chapter have been presented in plain English in Section 7.1 and in full mathematical detail in Section 7.3. Their interest lies in the attempt of providing a rigorous quantitative framework for a simple model related to optimal strategies of foraging patterns. The model considered resembles that of search within patches and takes into account foragers diffusing through a fractional heat equation. The forager can pick the Lévy exponent of this diffusion in order to maximize the encounters with a given distribution of preys.

Models of this type, relying on a continuous version of Lévy flights, may be conceptually advantageous, since they can reduce the number of external parameters involved in the analysis, allow explicit mathematical treatments, help understanding the core features of the model, and favor the introduction of further realistic characteristics as a generalization of the system considered to start with. Moreover, in spite of its structural simplicity, the model is rich enough to exhibit complicated behaviors which can be confronted with biological data and experiments. Additionally, these models can be utilized in the field of artificial intelligence, e.g. in the study of robot behavior and optimization algorithms.

Models of this type have been introduced and studied in Chapter 2, where suitable efficiency functionals have been put in place and analyzed in one spatial dimension, in Chapters 3, 4 and 5, where similar models have been investigated in bounded domains in the light of spectral analysis, and in Chapter 6, where the notion of optimal strategy has been confronted with its factual feasibility.

In this chapter, we provide three new main results, namely:

- Theorem 7.1, confirming, as a sanity check, that, in this model, the foragers attaining the highest efficiency in situations in which the prey is available at the initial location are the stationary ones,
- Theorem 7.2, stating that Gaussian strategies are optimal for large domains and very large searching times (with a finer and quantitative discussion also in terms of the spatial dimension),
- Theorem 7.5, affirming that if the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is supported in a suitable volume, then this efficiency functional is monotone increasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by the Gaussian dispersal $s = 1$, while if the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is supported in the complement of a suitable volume, then the efficiency functional is monotone decreasing in s and therefore the optimal strategy is given by $s = 0$.

We stress that, roughly speaking, compactly supported Fourier transforms correspond to distributions of preys with controlled oscillation, while Fourier transforms supported close to infinity give rise to very oscillatory distributions of preys.

The precise statements of these results were given in Section 7.3 and confronted with their biological interpretation.

We also mention that our model can be suitably modified to include the case of foragers possessing a limited lifespan (meaning that they must consume at least a specific quantity of food within a certain time frame, or die): we will specifically address this point in Chapter 8.

7.6 Appendices

Proof of Theorem 7.2

For the sake of simplicity in what follows we will denote by C , up to renaming it, constants depending only on Ω and n . We claim that for each $r \in (0, +\infty)$ it holds that

$$(7.38) \quad \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) = \frac{1}{r^n} \mathcal{J}^\Omega \left(s, \frac{T}{r^{2s}} \right).$$

To prove this, we observe that, using the scaling properties of $G^s(t, x, y)$ (see e.g. [AV19, Difference 2.10]),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) &= \frac{1}{T |\Omega|^2 r^{2n}} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega_r \times \Omega_r} G^s(t, x, y) dx dy dt \\ &= \frac{1}{T |\Omega|^2} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega \times \Omega} G^s(t, rx, ry) dx dy dt \\ &= \frac{r^{-n}}{T |\Omega|^2} \int_0^T \int_{\Omega \times \Omega} G^s \left(\frac{t}{r^{2s}}, x, y \right) dx dy dt \\ &= \frac{r^{2s-n}}{T |\Omega|^2} \int_0^{\frac{T}{r^{2s}}} \int_{\Omega \times \Omega} G^s(t, x, y) dx dy dt \\ &= \frac{1}{r^n} \mathcal{J}^\Omega \left(s, \frac{T}{r^{2s}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

which leads to (7.38).

We define the function

$$g(s, r, T) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \sigma(T r^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi,$$

where we have set

$$\sigma(x) := \frac{1 - e^{-x}}{x}.$$

We notice that

$$(7.39) \quad \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) = \frac{1}{r^n} g(s, r, T).$$

To check this, we use (8.1) and (7.38) to see that

$$(7.40) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) &= \frac{1}{r^n} \mathcal{J}^\Omega \left(s, \frac{T}{r^{2s}} \right) = \frac{r^{2s-n}}{T} \int_0^{T/r^{2s}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi dt \\ &= \frac{r^{2s-n}}{T} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{1 - e^{-Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi = \frac{1}{r^n} g(s, r, T), \end{aligned}$$

which establishes (7.39).

As a consequence of (7.39), the monotonicity properties of $\mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(\cdot, T)$ coincide with the ones of $g(\cdot, r, T)$. Hence, from now on we will focus on the monotonicity of the function $g(s, r, T)$ with respect to s .

For this, we compute the derivative

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_s \left(\sigma \left(T r^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} \right) \right) &= \sigma' \left(T r^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} \right) \partial_s \left(T r^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} \right) \\ &= \sigma' \left(T r^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} \right) \cdot 2 T r^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} \ln \left(\frac{2\pi |\xi|}{r} \right) \\ &= 2 \theta \left(T r^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} \right) \ln \left(\frac{r}{2\pi |\xi|} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where we have denoted

$$(7.41) \quad \theta(x) := -\sigma'(x)x = \frac{1 - e^{-x}(x+1)}{x}.$$

We also observe that

$$(7.42) \quad \|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 = |\Omega| \quad \text{and} \quad \|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq |\Omega|.$$

Using these facts and Theorem 2 in [Her62], we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
(7.43) \quad & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left| \ln \left(\frac{2\pi |\xi|}{r} \right) \right| |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left(|\ln(2\pi |\xi|)| + \ln(r) \right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
&= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{B_{2^{k+1}} \setminus B_{2^k}} |\ln(2\pi |\xi|)| |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi + \int_{B_1} |\ln(2\pi |\xi|)| |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
&\quad + |\ln r| \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
&\leq \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{B_{2^{k+1}} \setminus B_{2^k}} \frac{|\ln(2\pi |\xi|)|}{|\xi|^2} |\xi|^2 |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi + \int_{B_1} |\ln(2\pi |\xi|)| |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi + \ln r |\Omega| \\
&\leq \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln(\pi 2^{k+2})}{2^{2k}} \int_{B_{2^{k+1}} \setminus B_{2^k}} |\xi|^2 |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi + |\Omega|^2 \int_{B_1} |\ln(2\pi |\xi|)| d\xi + \ln r |\Omega| \\
&\leq \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{C \ln(\pi 2^{k+2})}{2^{2k}} 2^{k+1} + C |\Omega|^2 + \ln r |\Omega| \\
&= C \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\ln \pi + (k+2) \ln 2}{2^{k-1}} + C |\Omega|^2 + \ln r |\Omega| \\
&= C + \ln r |\Omega|.
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we notice that $\theta \in L^\infty((0, +\infty))$. Thanks to this and (7.43), we can apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem and conclude that

$$\partial_s g(s, r, T) = 2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \theta (Tr^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) \ln \left(\frac{r}{2\pi |\xi|} \right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi.$$

We write $\partial_s g(s, r, T) = 2(I + II)$, where I and II are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
(7.44) \quad & I := \int_{B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \theta (Tr^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) \ln \left(\frac{r}{2\pi |\xi|} \right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
& \text{and} \quad II := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \theta (Tr^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) \ln \left(\frac{r}{2\pi |\xi|} \right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, we prove (7.9). Since $\ln \left(\frac{r}{2\pi |\xi|} \right) \geq 0$ for each $\xi \in B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}$ and $\theta \geq 0$, then

$$(7.45) \quad \theta (Tr^{-2s} (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) \ln \left(\frac{r}{2\pi |\xi|} \right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 \geq 0$$

for $\xi \in B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}$. In particular, if $r \geq 2\pi$ this means that

$$I \geq \int_{B_1 \setminus B_{\frac{1}{2}}} \theta(Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) \ln\left(\frac{r}{2\pi|\xi|}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi.$$

Moreover, we notice that

$$(7.46) \quad \theta(x) \leq \frac{1}{x},$$

for each $x \in (0, +\infty)$, and also $\theta(x) > \frac{1}{2x}$ if $x \in (0, +\infty)$ is large enough. Thanks to this lower bound we have

$$(7.47) \quad \begin{aligned} I &\geq \int_{B_1 \setminus B_{\frac{1}{2}}} \frac{r^{2s}}{2T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} \ln\left(\frac{r}{2\pi|\xi|}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\ &\geq \frac{r^{2s} \ln r}{4T} \int_{B_1 \setminus B_{\frac{1}{2}}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi \\ &\geq C \frac{r^{2s} \ln r}{T}. \end{aligned}$$

for $r \in (1, +\infty)$ large enough and $T \geq r^2$.

Now, we estimate II . To do so, we observe that in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}$ it holds that $\ln\left(\frac{r}{2\pi|\xi|}\right) \leq 0$, and thus, to ease notation and identify positive quantities, we write

$$II = - \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \theta(Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) \ln\left(\frac{2\pi|\xi|}{r}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi,$$

with

$$(7.48) \quad \theta(Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) \ln\left(\frac{2\pi|\xi|}{r}\right) \geq 0.$$

Therefore, using (7.46) we can estimate

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \theta(Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) \ln\left(\frac{2\pi|\xi|}{r}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\ &\leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \frac{r^{2s}}{T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} \ln\left(\frac{2\pi|\xi|}{r}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\ &\leq \frac{1}{T} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \ln\left(\frac{2\pi|\xi|}{r}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Now, applying Theorem 2 in [Her62] we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \ln \left(\frac{2\pi |\xi|}{r} \right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \int_{B_{\frac{2^k r}{\pi}} \setminus B_{\frac{2^{k-1} r}{\pi}}} \ln \left(\frac{2\pi |\xi|}{r} \right) \frac{|\xi|^2}{|\xi|^2} |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
 &\leq \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\pi^2 (k+1) \ln 2}{r^2 2^{2k-2}} \int_{B_{\frac{2^k r}{\pi}} \setminus B_{\frac{2^{k-1} r}{\pi}}} |\xi|^2 |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\
 &\leq C \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\pi^2 (k+1) \ln 2}{r^2 2^{2k-2}} \cdot \frac{2^k r}{\pi} \\
 &= \frac{C}{r}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Gathering these observations, we deduce that

$$II \geq -\frac{C}{rT}.$$

From this and (7.47), we infer that, if $r \in (1, +\infty)$ is large enough and $T \in [r^2, +\infty)$,

$$\partial_s g(s, r, T) = 2(I + II) \geq \frac{C}{T} \left(r^{2s} \ln r - \frac{\tilde{C}}{r} \right) > 0.$$

Recalling (7.39), we complete the proof of (7.9)

Now, we show (7.10). To do so, we recall the definition of the function θ in (7.41) and we observe that, for each $x \in (0, +\infty)$,

$$(7.49) \quad \theta(x) \leq \widehat{C} x,$$

for some positive constant \widehat{C} .

We recall the definition of I in (7.44) and we change variable to see that

$$(7.50) \quad I = \frac{r^n}{(2\pi)^n} \int_{B_1} \theta(T |\eta|^{2s}) \ln \left(\frac{1}{|\eta|} \right) \left| \widehat{\chi}_\Omega \left(\frac{r\eta}{2\pi} \right) \right|^2 d\eta.$$

In view of (7.42) and (7.49), we can estimate

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &\leq \frac{\widehat{C} r^n}{(2\pi)^n} \int_{B_1} T |\eta|^{2s} \ln \left(\frac{1}{|\eta|} \right) |\Omega|^2 d\eta \\
 &\leq \frac{\widehat{C} r^n T |\Omega|^2}{(2\pi)^n} \int_{B_1} \ln \left(\frac{1}{|\eta|} \right) d\eta \\
 &\leq Cr^n T.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, recalling the definition of II in (7.44), if $r \in (0, \pi)$ is sufficiently small, possibly in dependance of T , we have that

$$\begin{aligned} -II &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2\pi}}} \theta(Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) \ln\left(\frac{2\pi|\xi|}{r}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\ &\geq \int_{B_1 \setminus B_{1/2}} \theta(Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) \ln\left(\frac{2\pi|\xi|}{r}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\ &\geq \int_{B_1 \setminus B_{1/2}} \frac{r^{2s}}{T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} \ln\left(\frac{\pi}{r}\right) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi \\ &= \frac{r^{2s}}{T} \ln\left(\frac{\pi}{r}\right) \int_{B_1 \setminus B_{1/2}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi \\ &= \frac{Cr^{2s}}{T} \ln\left(\frac{\pi}{r}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we conclude that

$$\partial_s g(s, T, r) = 2(I + II) \leq Cr^{2s} \left(\tilde{C}r^{n-2s}T - \frac{1}{T} \ln\left(\frac{\pi}{r}\right) \right),$$

which gives that for $r > 0$ small enough, depending on Ω and T , we have that $\partial_s g(s, r, T) < 0$ as far as $n \geq 2s$. This completes the proof of (7.10).

Now, we study the case $n < 2s$, that is, $n = 1$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$. For this, we notice that for each $x \in (0, +\infty)$ there exists some constant C_x such that

$$\theta(y) \geq C_x y,$$

for each $y \in (0, x)$. Therefore, if $|\eta| \in \left(\frac{1}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}}}, \frac{2}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}}}\right)$ then $T|\eta|^{2s} \in (1, 2^{2s}) \subseteq (1, 4)$, and thus

$$\theta(T|\eta|^{2s}) \geq CT|\eta|^{2s},$$

and moreover $2T^{-\frac{1}{2s}} \leq 1$ for each $s \in (0, 1)$ if $T \geq 4$.

Also, we notice also that there exists some $\tilde{r}_\Omega \in (0, 1)$ such that, for each $r \in (0, \tilde{r}_\Omega)$ and $\eta \in B_1$, it holds that

$$\left| \widehat{\chi}_\Omega\left(\frac{r\eta}{2\pi}\right) \right| \geq \frac{|\Omega|}{2}.$$

As a consequence of this, recalling also (7.50) and using the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we deduce that, if $T \geq 4$ and $r \in (0, \tilde{r}_\Omega)$, then it holds that

$$I \geq Cr \int_{\frac{1}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}}}}^{\frac{2}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}}}} T|\eta|^{2s} \ln\left(\frac{1}{|\eta|}\right) \left| \widehat{\chi}_\Omega\left(\frac{r\eta}{2\pi}\right) \right|^2 d\eta \geq Cr \ln\left(\frac{T}{4}\right) \frac{1}{T^{\frac{1}{2s}}}.$$

Furthermore, changing variables $\eta := \frac{2\pi\xi}{r}$ and then $\omega := \frac{\eta}{|\eta|^2}$ in II , we see that

$$\begin{aligned} II &= -\frac{r^n}{(2\pi)^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \theta(T|\eta|^{2s}) \ln(|\eta|) \left| \widehat{\chi}_\Omega\left(\frac{r\eta}{2\pi}\right) \right|^2 d\eta \\ &= -\frac{r^n}{(2\pi)^n} \int_{B_1} \theta(T|\omega|^{-2s}) \ln\left(\frac{1}{|\omega|}\right) \left| \widehat{\chi}_\Omega\left(\frac{r\omega}{2\pi|\omega|^2}\right) \right|^2 \frac{d\omega}{|\omega|^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, if $n = 1$, $\sigma \in (1/2, 1)$ and $s \in (\sigma, 1)$, we use (7.42) and (7.46) to estimate

$$\begin{aligned} -II &\leq \frac{|\Omega|^2 r}{2\pi} \int_{B_1} \frac{|\omega|^{2s}}{T} \ln\left(\frac{1}{|\omega|}\right) \frac{d\omega}{|\omega|^2} \\ &= \frac{|\Omega|^2 r}{\pi T} \int_0^1 \omega^{2s-2} \ln\left(\frac{1}{\omega}\right) d\omega \\ (7.51) \quad &= \frac{|\Omega|^2 r}{\pi T(2s-1)^2} \\ &\leq \frac{|\Omega|^2 r}{\pi T(2\sigma-1)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if $T \geq 4$ and $r \in (0, \tilde{r}_\Omega)$, making use also of (7.40) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_s \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) &= \frac{1}{r} \partial_s g(s, r, T) \\ (7.52) \quad &= \frac{2}{r} (I + II) \\ &\geq \frac{1}{T} \left(C \ln\left(\frac{T}{4}\right) T^{1-\frac{1}{2s}} - \frac{|\Omega|^2}{\pi(2\sigma-1)^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

As a result, there exists some $T_\sigma \in (4, +\infty)$ such that for each $T \in (T_\sigma, +\infty)$, $r \in (0, \tilde{r}_\Omega)$ and $s \in (\sigma, 1)$ it holds that

$$\partial_s \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) > 0$$

This completes the proof of (7.11). □

Proof of Corollary 7.4

We begin by observing that, if $R > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\chi}_{(-R,R)}(\xi) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-2i\pi\xi x} \chi_{(-R,R)}(x) dx = \int_{-R}^R \cos(2\pi\xi x) - i \sin(2\pi\xi x) dx \\ (7.53) \quad &= \frac{\sin(2\pi x\xi)}{2\pi\xi} \Big|_{-R}^R = \frac{\sin(2\pi R\xi)}{\pi\xi}. \end{aligned}$$

Besides, we notice that the value of $\mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s)$ is invariant under translations of the domain Ω . Indeed, if $v \in \mathbb{R}$, then

$$\widehat{\chi}_{\Omega+v}(\xi) = \int_{\Omega+v} e^{-2\pi i \xi x} dx = \int_{\Omega} e^{-2\pi i (x+v)\xi} dx = e^{-2\pi i v \xi} \widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)$$

and therefore, by (7.14),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_\infty^{\Omega+v}(r, s) &= r^{2s-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{\Omega+v}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi = r^{2s-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|e^{-2\pi i v \xi} \widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi \\ &= r^{2s-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi = \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s). \end{aligned}$$

For this reason, without loss of generality, we can assume that $\Omega = (-R, R)$ for some $R \in (0, +\infty)$.

Now we prove the limit in (7.15). For this, we recall (7.40) and see that

$$T \mathcal{J}^{\Omega_r}(s, T) = r^{2s-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{1 - e^{-Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 d\xi.$$

Now, we notice that if $\beta \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s \in [0, \beta)$ and $T \in (0, +\infty)$, then

$$\frac{1 - e^{-Tr^{-2s}(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2 \leq \chi_{B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}}(\xi) \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2\beta}} + \chi_{B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}^c}(\xi) |\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2.$$

In particular, since $\widehat{\chi}_\Omega \in L^2(\mathbb{R}) \cap L^\infty(\mathbb{R})$, due to (7.53), we obtain that the function on the right-hand side is in $L^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$. Therefore, thanks to the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we can conclude that (7.15) holds.

Now, we prove (7.16) and (7.18). We observe that

$$\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi) = \int_{-R}^R e^{-2i\pi\xi x} dx = R \int_{-1}^1 e^{-2i\pi R\xi x} dx = R \widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(R\xi),$$

and therefore the following scaling property holds true:

$$\mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s) = r^{2s-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_\Omega(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi = R^{1+2s} r^{2s-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi = R^{1+2s} \mathcal{J}_\infty^{(-1,1)}(r, s).$$

From this latter equation we evince that

$$(7.54) \quad \partial_s \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s) = 2R^{1+2s} r^{2s-1} \left(\ln(Rr)g(s) + \frac{1}{2}g'(s) \right),$$

where we have set

$$g(s) := \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi.$$

Now, given $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\ell > 0$, we use the notation $\ln^m \ell := (\ln \ell)^m$ and we observe that, for all $\beta \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $s \in [0, \beta)$,

$$\ln^m (2\pi|\xi|) \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} \leq \ln^m (2\pi|\xi|) \left(\chi_{B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}}(\xi) \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2\beta}} + \chi_{B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}^c}(\xi) |\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2 \right).$$

Thus, recalling (7.53), we have that

$$\ln^m (2\pi|\xi|) \left(\chi_{B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}}(\xi) \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2\beta}} + \chi_{B_{\frac{1}{2\pi}}^c}(\xi) |\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2 \right) \in L^1(\mathbb{R}).$$

Thanks to these observations, we can apply the Dominate Convergence Theorem and obtain that $g \in C^2([0, \frac{1}{2}))$, and for each $s \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$,

$$(7.55) \quad \begin{aligned} g'(s) &= -2 \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} \ln(2\pi|\xi|) d\xi \\ \text{and} \quad g''(s) &= 4 \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\widehat{\chi}_{(-1,1)}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} \ln^2(2\pi|\xi|) d\xi > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, according to (7.53) and (7.55), we can compute that

$$(7.56) \quad \begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{4}g'(0) &= \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sin^2(2\pi\xi)}{(\pi\xi)^2} \ln(2\pi\xi) d\xi = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\sin^2(\eta)}{\eta^2} \ln(\eta) d\eta \\ &= -\frac{1}{\pi^2} (-1 + \gamma + \ln(2)) < 0, \end{aligned}$$

where γ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant.

Also, thanks to (7.55) and (7.56) we obtain that

$$g'(s) = g'(0) + \int_0^s g''(s) ds > 0.$$

Now we introduce the function

$$f(s) := -\frac{g'(s)}{2g(s)}.$$

We observe that f is negative and, according to (7.54),

(7.57)

$$\partial_s \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s) = 2R^{1+2s} r^{2s-1} g(s) \left(\ln(Rr) + \frac{g'(s)}{2g(s)} \right) = 2R^{1+2s} r^{2s-1} g(s) (\ln(Rr) - f(s)).$$

We also define

$$M := \sup_{s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})} f(s) \in (-\infty, 0].$$

Therefore, by (7.57), if

$$r > r_\Omega := \frac{e^M}{R} \in (0, +\infty),$$

then, for every $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$,

$$\partial_s \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s) \geq 2R^{1+2s} r^{2s-1} g(s) (\ln(Rr) - M) > 0$$

and consequently the functional $\mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot)$ is strictly increasing in $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$. This concludes the proof of (7.16).

Now we prove (7.18). First, using also the fact that $g(s) > 0$ in $s \in [0, \frac{1}{2})$, we notice that $f \in C([0, \frac{1}{2}))$. Thus, for each $\sigma \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, we can define the finite value

$$m_\sigma := \inf_{s \in (0, \sigma)} f(s) \in (-\infty, 0],$$

and, by (7.57), we obtain that if

$$(7.58) \quad r < r_{\sigma, \Omega} := \frac{e^{m_\sigma}}{R} \in (0, +\infty)$$

then, for all $s \in (0, \sigma)$,

$$\partial_s \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s) \leq 2R^{1+2s} r^{2s-1} g(s) (\ln(Rr) - m_\sigma) < 0,$$

showing that $\mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, \cdot)$ is strictly decreasing in $s \in (0, \sigma)$. This last step concludes the proof of (7.18).

It is only left to show (7.17) and (7.19). To this end, we notice that, for each $\sigma \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$,

(7.59)

$$\int_0^\sigma f(s) ds = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^\sigma \frac{g'(s)}{g(s)} ds = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^\sigma \frac{d}{ds} (\ln(g(s))) ds = -\frac{1}{2} (\ln(g(\sigma)) - \ln(g(0))).$$

Since

$$\lim_{\sigma \nearrow \frac{1}{2}} g(\sigma) = +\infty,$$

we deduce from (7.59) that

$$\lim_{\sigma \nearrow \frac{1}{2}} \int_0^\sigma f(s) ds = -\infty.$$

In particular, this implies that

$$\lim_{\sigma \nearrow \frac{1}{2}} f(\sigma) = -\infty$$

and thus

$$(7.60) \quad \lim_{\sigma \nearrow \frac{1}{2}} m_\sigma = -\infty.$$

This and (7.58) lead to the desired claim in (7.17).

It remains to prove (7.19). For this, we take $r \in (r_{\sigma, \Omega}, +\infty)$ and observe that

$$\ln(Rr) > \ln(Rr_{\sigma, \Omega}) = \ln(e^{m_\sigma}) = m_\sigma = \inf_{s \in (0, \sigma)} f(s).$$

Therefore, there exists $s_\sigma \in (0, \sigma)$ such that $\ln(Rr) > f(s_\sigma)$. As a result, by (7.57),

$$\partial_s \mathcal{J}_\infty^\Omega(r, s_\sigma) = 2R^{1+2s_\sigma} r^{2s_\sigma-1} g(s_\sigma) (\ln(Rr) - f(s_\sigma)) > 0,$$

from which we obtain (7.19), as desired. \square

8

LÉVY FLIGHTS, OPTIMAL FORAGING STRATEGIES, AND FORAGERS WITH FINITE LIFESPAN

In some recent work, we have introduced some efficiency functionals to account for optimal dispersal strategies of predators in search of food. The optimization parameter in this framework is given by the Lévy exponent of the dispersal of the predators.

In this chapter, we apply our model to the case of foragers with finite lifetime (i.e., foragers which need to eat a certain amount of food in a given time, otherwise they die).

Specifically, we consider the case in which the initial distribution of the forager coincides with a stationary distribution of the targets and we determine the optimal Lévy exponent for the associated efficiency functional.

Namely, we show that if the Fourier transform of the prey distribution is supported in a sufficiently small ball, then the optimizer is given by a Gaussian dispersal, and if instead the Fourier transform of the prey distribution is supported in the complement of a suitable ball, then the ballistic diffusion provides an optimizer (precise conditions for the uniqueness of these optimizers are also given).

8.1 Introduction

Understanding animal foraging strategies is of great importance in biology and ethology, with applications in conservation biology and population dynamics (see [Vis+11; KBG15]). As a simplified model for this goal, one can consider a given distribution of targets and some predators which move according to some law in the space. The optimization problem is thus provided by some parameters that the predators can “tune” in order to maximize the success of their search.

Framed in this way, the problem goes even beyond the interest range of biology, since similar features can be shared by automatic searches of robots, internet engines, mine detection, human mobility, human cognition, and so on (see [Dar+04; Bro10; BR13; GA14; BM18; ERG20; Dun+22]).

In the last three decades, the investigation of animal search pattern has been deeply influenced by the so-called Lévy flight foraging hypothesis, as put forth in [Vis+99]. The working assumption of this setting is, roughly speaking, that the classical Brownian motion may be inadequate to capture the complexity of animal movements, even in the absence of chemotactical attractions or memory effects. Indeed, heavy-tailed distributions might provide advantageous searching patterns, especially for sparsely, randomly distributed, revisitable targets, since they potentially explore the environment faster and avoid long term confinement in regions with no available prey.

The validity of the Lévy flight foraging hypothesis is subject to a very intense debate and a precise and rigorous approach appears to be essential for further progress (see in particular [Pyk15] and Section 7.2 in Chapter 7 for a list of major objections and scientific disagreements). One of the difficulties in the analysis of such a topic is that optimizers and pessimizers are often closely intertwined (see Chapter 6): this is not a mere mathematical curiosity and indeed, especially in the presence of preys with high energy content, patterns of this type may lead to high-risk/high-reward hunting strategies of ambush type which have been observed in nature (see [Bur21]).

Several quantifications of the hunting success are possible. In particular, in Chapter 2 we have introduced several efficiency functionals based on the random encounters between a predator, diffusing according to a fractional heat equation

which accounts for heavy-tailed spatial relocations, and a given distribution of prey. The exponent of this Lévy-type tail is used as a free parameter that the predator can tune in order to maximize the amount of food found during the search (this efficiency functional can be also normalized to account for the length of the search, the energy spent, etc.).

In addition, recently (see [BR14]) the problem of animal foraging has also specifically considered the case of predators with a finite lifespan, subject to the success of the search for food: roughly speaking, in these models the forager is allowed to search for food during a finite time interval: then, on the one hand, if the search is successful, the forager is allowed for additional time, but, on the other hand, the forager dies if it does not find any prey within the given time frame.

In view of these recent trends, the goal of this chapter is to determine the optimal Lévy exponent for the forager with finite lifetime in some specific conditions.

In particular, we establish that:

- if the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is supported in a suitable volume, then the only optimal strategy for this forager is Gaussian, while
- if the Fourier transform of the distribution of a stationary prey is supported in the complement of a suitable volume, then the optimal strategy corresponds to the ballistic one.

Precise mathematical statements will be given in Theorem 8.4 and Corollary 8.5 below, which are the main results of this chapter.

The above conditions about the support of the Fourier transform of the prey distribution may require a clarification. On the one hand, the assumption that the Fourier transform is supported in a suitable volume means that the stationary prey distribution is composed only of frequencies within a certain range and does not exhibit “too high” frequencies. This, roughly speaking, excludes “highly oscillatory” behaviors of this distribution and accordingly an assumption of this type can be considered as a “regularity” hypothesis.

On the other hand, the assumption that the Fourier transform of the distribution is supported¹ in the complement of a suitable volume (in particular, zero is not in the support of the Fourier transform) indicates that the total mass of prey is equal to zero. It would be however too simplistic to dismiss this situation as biologically inessential, for at least two reasons.

The first reason is conceptual: whenever one has a result under an assumption on the support of the Fourier transform, it is of fundamental importance to understand whether this assumption is required. Our dichotomy above makes it clear that this is the case: in particular, it highlights that the detection of the optimal strategy cannot overlook the support of the Fourier transform, i.e. the oscillatory patterns, of the prey distribution.

The second reason is in terms of modelization: in this chapter, the calculations do not actually require that the prey distribution is nonnegative. As stated by Paul Dirac [Dir42], these negative values (in the setting of negative probabilities, or quasiprobabilities) “should not be considered as nonsense. They are well-defined concepts mathematically, like a negative of money” (similar observations were also pointed out by Richard Feynman [Fey87]). Not only these notions are commonly used in quantum physics (e.g., for antiparticles) and finance (e.g., for risk neutral probabilities), but they have a natural counterpart in animal foraging: for example, negative values of the prey can model traps or potential hazard sites for the predator (such as a predator of the predator). In this sense, the case of Fourier transforms supported away from zero appears to be ideal to describe complex, and biologically relevant situations in which the predator is also at some risk of being attacked or framed (though in different settings, ballistic optimizers were also detected in [Bur21] and Chapter 5 as a result of a high-risk/high-gain foraging pattern; differently than in the existing literature, the risk here is embodied by the negative values of the

¹As an explicit example of distribution with Fourier transform supported away from an interval, one can consider a smooth and even function $\tau \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R})$ with $\tau = 1$ in $[-\rho, \rho]$ and take

$$\widehat{p}(\xi) := (1 - \tau(\xi)) e^{-|\xi|^2}.$$

The corresponding distribution reads

$$p(x) := \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \widehat{p}(\xi) e^{2\pi i x \xi} d\xi = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (1 - \tau(\xi)) e^{-|\xi|^2} \cos(2\pi x \xi) d\xi.$$

prey distribution).

The rest of this chapter is devoted to the rigorous statements and proofs of these results. While on the subject, we will also provide additional results in Theorems 8.1 and 8.3 to relate the efficiency functional with the success or failure of the search.

More specifically, the main results will be stated in Section 8.2 and their proofs will be presented in Section 8.3. The conclusions of this chapter will be summarized in Section 8.4.

8.2 Mathematical framework and main results

In this section, we state precisely our main results, in view of a quantitative mathematical formulation. We specifically address here the case of foragers that can only search for food during a finite time interval and die if they do not find any prey within such a time frame. In our setting, the “discrete” notion of finding a prey is replaced by a given threshold on the efficiency functional. Specifically, in our model, the forager dies if the corresponding efficiency functional after a certain time is below this threshold.

To focus on an elementary case, we consider a closed interval $I \subseteq [0, 1]$, time spans $T_1 > 0$ and $T_2 > T_1$, and a threshold $c_1 > 0$. We take into account a forager diffusing as in

$$\partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) \quad \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n,$$

with $s \in I$, and looking for prey in the time interval $[0, T_2]$ (unless it dies before). Here above, the initial condition for u is that at time $t = 0$ it coincides with the prey distribution.

As customary, the fractional Laplace operator $(-\Delta)^s$ can be defined in the Fourier space as the operator for which, given any smooth and rapidly decaying function ϕ , the Fourier transform of $(-\Delta)^s \phi$ equals $(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s} \widehat{\phi}(\xi)$, where $\widehat{\phi}$ is the Fourier transform of ϕ , namely

$$\widehat{\phi}(\xi) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \phi(x) e^{-2\pi i x \cdot \xi} d\xi.$$

We consider a distribution of prey $p = p(x)$ and, for all $s \in I$, we let

$$E(s, T) := \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} u(t, x) p(x) dx dt.$$

This efficiency functional can be conveniently expressed in the Fourier space as

$$(8.1) \quad E(s, T) = \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}t} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi dt = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{1 - e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi,$$

see Theorem 7.5 and equation (7.31).

We suppose that the forager dies at time T_1 if $E(s, T_1) < c_1$, while if $E(s, T_1) \geq c_1$ then the forager can keep looking for food till time T_2 . In this way, the efficiency functional for this finite lifespan forager can be written in the form

$$(8.2) \quad I \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}(s) := \begin{cases} E(s, T_1) & \text{if } E(s, T_1) < c_1, \\ E(s, T_2) & \text{if } E(s, T_1) \geq c_1. \end{cases}$$

For this simple case, unless the forager always dies at time T_1 , the optimal Lévy exponent is given by the optimizer of $E(s, T_2)$ among all s guaranteeing the survival after time T_1 :

Theorem 8.1. *We have the following dichotomy:*

- either $E(s, T_1) < c_1$ for all $s \in I$, and in this case

$$\sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I} E(s, T_1),$$

- or there exists $s \in I$ such that $E(s, T_1) \geq c_1$, and in this case

$$\sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_\star} E(s, T_2),$$

where

$$I_\star := \{s \in I \text{ s.t. } E(s, T_1) \geq c_1\}.$$

The construction above can be iterated in order to comprise more than two and possibly infinitely many lifespans. To do so, it is convenient to introduce the extended natural numbers $\bar{\mathbb{N}} := \mathbb{N} \cup \{\infty\}$, where ∞ denotes a maximum element for the naturals. In particular, we have that $j + \infty = \infty + j = \infty$ for every $j \in \bar{\mathbb{N}}$

and $\infty - j = \infty$ for every $j \in \mathbb{N}$. In this way, we can present the case of finite and infinite (but countable) lifespans in a unified framework.

For this, we consider $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty\}$, an ordered set of lifespans $\{T_i\}_{i \in \{1, \dots, k\}}$ such that $0 < T_i < T_{i+1}$ and $\{c_i\}_{i \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}}$ with $c_i > 0$ for every $i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$. Also, if $k = \infty$, we make the assumption that

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} T_i = T_\infty = +\infty.$$

We suppose that the forager dies at time T_j for some $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ if $E(s, T_j) < c_j$, while if $E(s, T_j) \geq c_j$ the forager survives and can look for food till time T_{k+1} .

In this situation, the efficiency functional for this forager can be written for every $s \in I$ as

$$(8.3) \quad \mathcal{E}(s) := \begin{cases} E(s, T_j) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\} \text{ and } E(s, T_j) < c_j, \\ E(s, T_k) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}. \end{cases}$$

Note that in this setting the forager cannot modify the Lévy exponent s for all the duration of its life (in the future, we plan to consider also the case in which this exponent can be adjusted at each time step, but for the moment we stick to the simpler scenario).

Without loss of generality, we can suppose from now on that the surviving thresholds are monotone, consistently with the biological idea that the total food threshold at a subsequent foraging time is higher than the ones at previous times. Namely, without loss of generality, we will assume that

$$(8.4) \quad c_{j+1} \geq c_j,$$

thanks to the following observation:

Lemma 8.2. *Let $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty\}$, $\tilde{c}_j := \max\{c_1, \dots, c_j\}$ with $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ and for every $s \in I$*

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}(s) := \begin{cases} E(s, T_j) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq \tilde{c}_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\} \text{ and } E(s, T_j) < \tilde{c}_j, \\ E(s, T_k) & \text{if } E(s, T_i) \geq \tilde{c}_i \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}. \end{cases}$$

Then, $\tilde{\mathcal{E}} = \mathcal{E}$.

The generalization of Theorem 8.1 in the setting of (8.3) goes as follows:

Theorem 8.3. *Let $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty\}$. We have the following dichotomy:*

- either there exists $s_\star \in I$ such that $E(s_\star, T_i) \geq c_i$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$, in which case

$$(8.5) \quad \sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_{k-1}} E(s, T_k),$$

where

$$I_{k-1} := \{s \in I \text{ s.t. } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}\},$$

- or there exists $j_\star \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ such that² if $s \in I$ and $E(s, T_i) \geq c_i$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, k-1\} \cap [1, j_\star - 1]$, then necessarily $E(s, T_{j_\star}) < c_{j_\star}$, and the set

$$I_{j_\star} := \{s \in I \text{ s.t. } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k-1\} \cap [1, j_\star - 1]\}$$

is nonempty.

In this case,

$$(8.6) \quad \sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_{j_\star}} E(s, T_{j_\star}).$$

Figure 8.1: Plots of the efficiency functional in (8.3) when $\hat{p} = \chi_{(-0.3, 0.3)}$, $(T_1, T_2, T_3) = (2, 4, 6)$ and $((c_1^1, c_2^1), (c_1^2, c_2^2), (c_1^3, c_2^3)) = ((1, 2), (0.6, 1), (0.6, 0.8))$.

²As customary, we use the notation $[1, j_\star - 1] = \emptyset$ when $j_\star = 1$, and in this case the requirement on i becomes void. For instance, if $j_\star = 1$, then $I_{j_\star} = I$.

In Figure 8.1, we present a simulation of the energy in (8.3) for $k = 3$ and for three different choices of energy thresholds. These have been selected to showcase the content of Theorem 8.3.

Specifically, the first set of thresholds is taken such that $E(s, T_1) < c_1$ for all $s \in (0, 1)$, and in this way the supremum of $\mathcal{E}(s)$ coincides with the supremum of $E(s, T_1)$ over $I_1 = (0, 1)$.

In the second plot, (c_1^2, c_2^2) are taken so that there are some values of $s \in (0, 1)$ such that $E(s, T_1) \geq c_1^2$ and $E(s, T_2) < c_2^2$ for all $s \in (0, 1)$. Thus, in this case, we obtain that the supremum of \mathcal{E} coincides with the supremum of $E(s, T_2)$.

In the last simulation in Figure 8.1, the thresholds have been chosen in such a way that there exist some values of $s \in (0, 1)$ such that $E(s, T_1) > c_1^3$ and $E(s, T_2) > c_2^3$. In this case, we have that the supremum of \mathcal{E} coincides with the supremum of $E(s, T_3)$.

Figure 8.2: Plot of the function $(0, 1) \times (0, 6) \ni (s, T) \rightarrow E(s, T)$ with $\hat{p} = \chi_{(-0.3, 0.3)}$ (in red) compared to the graph of the step functions $(0, 1) \times (0, 6) \ni (s, T) \rightarrow L^i(s, T) = \sum_{j=1}^2 c_j^i \chi_{(T_j, T_{j+1})}(T)$ (in blue) for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, $(T_1, T_2, T_3) = (2, 4, 6)$ and $((c_1^1, c_2^1), (c_1^2, c_2^2), (c_1^3, c_2^3)) = ((1, 2), (0.6, 1), (0.6, 0.8))$.

In Figure 8.2, we compare the energy $E(s, T)$ with the step function $L(s, T) = \sum_{j=1}^2 c_j^i \chi_{(T_j, T_{j+1})}(T)$ with c_j^i as in the plots of Figure 8.1. More precisely, the three-dimensional plots in Figure 8.2 are built with the same data of Figure 8.1 with the purpose of detecting the change between $E(s, T_j)$ and $E(s, T_{j+1})$, which in turn is visible as a discontinuity of the graphs in Figure 8.1, with respect to the thresholds c_j^i .

Figure 8.3: Plot of the function $(0, 6) \ni T \rightarrow E(0.5, T)$ (in red) with $\widehat{p} = \chi_{(-0.3, 0.3)}$ compared to the graph of the step functions $(0, 6) \ni T \rightarrow L^i(T) = \sum_{j=1}^2 c_j^i \chi_{(T_j, T_{j+1})}(T)$ (in blue) for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, $(T_1, T_2, T_3) = (2, 4, 6)$ and $((c_1^1, c_2^1), (c_1^2, c_2^2), (c_1^3, c_2^3)) = ((1, 2), (0.6, 1), (0.6, 0.8))$.

The three graphs in Figure 8.3 are given by the intersection of the graphs in Figure 8.2 with the plane passing through $s = \frac{1}{2}$ and parallel to the one spanned by the time and vertical axes. In this case we can visualize, at a given s (in this case $s = 1/2$), how different choices of energy thresholds lead to different energy levels.

More specifically, we can compare Figure 8.3 with Figure 8.1 as follows: in the first simulation starting from the left in Figure 8.3 we see that $E(1/2, T_1) < c_1^1$ and therefore in Figure 8.1 we have that $\mathcal{E}(1/2) = E(1/2, T_1)$. On the other hand, in the second picture in Figure 8.3 we have that $E(1/2, T_1) > c_1^2$ and $E(1/2, T_2) < c_2^2$. As a consequence of this, in Figure 8.1 we have that $\mathcal{E}(1/2) = E(1/2, T_2)$.

Then, in the third plot from the left in Figure 8.3, we observe that $E(1/2, T_j) > c_j^3$ for every $j \in \{1, 2\}$. As a consequence of (8.3) and as plotted in the third picture in Figure 8.1, we obtain that $\mathcal{E}(1/2) = E(1/2, T_3)$.

In general, for many thresholds and time spans, the explicit analysis of the maximizers of Theorem 8.3 could be quite involved. There are however special cases in which explicit maximizers can be obtained. For instance, one can rely on Theorem 7.5 and obtain the following result:

Theorem 8.4. *Let $n \geq 1$ and $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots, \infty\}$. Consider a forager diffusing as*

$$(8.7) \quad \begin{cases} \partial_t u(t, x) = -(-\Delta)^s u(t, x) & \text{for all } (t, x) \in (0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R}^n, \\ u(0, x) = p(x). \end{cases}$$

for a prey distribution p not identically zero.

Suppose that this forager has a finite lifespan, as in (8.3), with $I := [0, 1]$.

Then,

- (i) if the Fourier transform of the prey p is supported in the ball of radius $\frac{1}{2\pi}$, then the Gaussian dispersal $s = 1$ is a maximizer for \mathcal{E} . Also, if either $n \geq 2$ or $k \in \mathbb{N}$ the maximizer is unique.
- (ii) if instead the Fourier transform of p is supported in the complement of the ball of radius $\frac{1}{2\pi}$, then $s = 0$ is the unique maximizer for \mathcal{E} .

The condition that $n \geq 2$ in Theorem 8.4(i) can be relaxed. In fact, this condition was used only to guarantee the finite energy condition in (8.29) in the proof. In particular, it was used to establish uniqueness of the maximizer in the case $k = \infty$.

In dimension $n = 1$ and for $k = \infty$ a result similar to Theorem 8.4(i) holds true as well, with the only caveat that the counterpart of Theorem 8.4(i) cannot exclude that there are more maximizers for which the efficiency functional attains infinite value. Thus, for completeness, we state and prove the version of Theorem 8.4(i) for dimension $n = 1$:

Corollary 8.5. *Let $n = 1$ and $k = \infty$. Consider a forager diffusing as in (8.7), for a prey distribution p not identically zero.*

Suppose that this forager has a finite lifespan, as in (8.3), with $I := [0, 1]$.

Then, if the Fourier transform of the prey p is supported in $(-\frac{1}{2\pi}, \frac{1}{2\pi})$, then the Gaussian dispersal $s = 1$ is a maximizer for \mathcal{E} ; moreover, if either for every $s_0 \in [0, 1)$ there exists $j \in \{2, 3, 4, \dots\}$ such that

$$(8.8) \quad E(s_0, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j - 1\}, E(s_0, T_j) < c_j \text{ and } \mathcal{E}(s_0) = E(s_0, T_j)$$

or

$$(8.9) \quad \int_{(-\frac{1}{2\pi}, \frac{1}{2\pi})} \frac{|\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2}{|\xi|^2} d\xi < +\infty,$$

then $s = 1$ is the unique maximizer.

As a final remark, we point out that, for the sake of concreteness, we focused here on “discrete lifespans”. It is possible, however, to treat as well the case of continuous lifespans, in which the efficiency functional is compared, for every time $T \geq 0$, to a given threshold, and the forager dies as soon as this threshold is not met. For this, it suffices to consider a continuous threshold $c = c(T)$, define

$$T_\star := \sup \{ \tau \geq 0 \text{ s.t. } E(s, T) \geq c(T) \text{ for all } T \in [0, \tau] \}$$

and introduce, as a continuous analogue of (8.3), the functional

$$I \ni s \mapsto \mathcal{E}_\star(s) := E(s, T_\star).$$

Actually, the discrete setting can be considered as a particular case of the continuous one, in the special situation of piecewise constant thresholds, as pointed out in the next result. To this end, we use the notation $c_0 := 0$ and $T_0 := 0$.

Theorem 8.6. *Let $k \in \bar{\mathbb{N}} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, \infty\}$ and suppose that $C(T) = c_{j-1}$ for all $T \in [T_{j-1}, T_j)$ and all $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k\}$.*

Then, either $T_\star = T_k$ or there exists $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k-1\}$ such that $T_\star = T_j$.

In the first case, we have that $\mathcal{E}_\star(s) = E(s, T_k)$. In the second case, we have that $\mathcal{E}_\star(s) = E(s, T_j)$.

In any case, $\mathcal{E}_\star(s) = E(s, T_\star) = \mathcal{E}(s)$.

8.3 Proofs of the main results

Below are the detailed proofs of the main results presented in Section 8.2.

Proof of Theorem 8.1. If $E(s, T_1) < c_1$ for all $s \in I$, then, for all possible choices of $s \in I$, the forager always dies at time T_1 . In this situation, for all $s \in I$ we have that $\mathcal{E}(s) = E(s, T_1)$. This says that we are in the first case showcased in the statement of Theorem 8.1.

We can therefore now suppose that $I_\star \neq \emptyset$. We observe that

$$(8.10) \quad \sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_\star} \mathcal{E}(s).$$

Indeed, if not, then necessarily

$$\sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) > \sup_{s \in I_\star} \mathcal{E}(s)$$

and accordingly

$$\sup_{s \in I \setminus I_\star} \mathcal{E}(s) > \sup_{s \in I_\star} \mathcal{E}(s).$$

But when $s \in I \setminus I_\star$ it holds that $\mathcal{E}(s) = E(s, T_1) \leq c_1$ while when $s \in I_\star$ we have that $\mathcal{E}(s) = E(s, T_2) \geq E(s, T_1) \geq c_1$. From this, a contradiction plainly follows and the proof of (8.10) is complete.

The claim stated in the second case of Theorem 8.1 now follows from (8.10), since if $s \in I_\star$ then $\mathcal{E}(s) = E(s, T_2)$. □

Proof of Lemma 8.2. The desired result is a consequence of these two claims:

$$(8.11) \quad \begin{aligned} E(s, T_i) \geq \tilde{c}_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\} \\ \text{if and only if } E(s, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\} \end{aligned}$$

and, if either of the above holds,

$$(8.12) \quad E(s, T_j) < \tilde{c}_j \text{ if and only if } E(s, T_j) < c_j.$$

To prove (8.11), we first point out that $\tilde{c}_i \geq c_i$, whence the first condition in (8.11) implies the second one.

Conversely, if the second condition in (8.11) is fulfilled, then, for all $i \leq l \leq j-1$, we have that $E(s, T_l) \geq E(s, T_i) \geq c_i$, yielding that $E(s, T_l) \geq \max\{c_1, \dots, c_l\} = \tilde{c}_l$ for all $l \in \{1, \dots, j-1\}$, which is the first condition in (8.11). This establishes (8.11).

Concerning (8.12), the fact that $\tilde{c}_j \geq c_j$ gives that the second condition in (8.12) implies the first one.

Besides, if the first condition in (8.12) holds true, together with either of the equivalent conditions in (8.11), suppose by contradiction that $E(s, T_j) \geq c_j$. Hence, we see that, for each $i \leq j$, $E(s, T_j) \geq E(s, T_i) \geq c_i$, giving that $E(s, T_j) \geq \max\{c_1, \dots, c_j\} = \tilde{c}_j$, which is absurd, and the proof of (8.12) is thereby complete. □

Proof of Theorem 8.3. Let us first suppose that there exists s_\star as mentioned in the first claim of Theorem 8.3. Then, we have that $s_\star \in I_{k-1} \neq \emptyset$.

Moreover,

$$(8.13) \quad \text{if } s \in I_{k-1} \text{ then } \mathcal{E}(s) = E(s, T_k).$$

We claim that

$$(8.14) \quad \sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_{k-1}} \mathcal{E}(s).$$

Indeed, if not, then necessarily

$$\sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) > \sup_{s \in I_{k-1}} \mathcal{E}(s)$$

and accordingly

$$(8.15) \quad \sup_{s \in I \setminus I_{k-1}} \mathcal{E}(s) > \sup_{s \in I_{k-1}} \mathcal{E}(s).$$

However, if $s \in I \setminus I_{k-1}$, then there exists $k_s \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k-1\}$ for which $E(s, T_{k_s}) < c_{k_s}$, and thus

$$\mathcal{E}(s) \leq E(s, T_{k_s}) < c_{k_s} \leq E(s_\star, T_{k_s}) \leq E(s_\star, T_k) = \mathcal{E}(s_\star) \leq \sup_{s \in I_{k-1}} \mathcal{E}(s),$$

leading to

$$\sup_{s \in I \setminus I_{k-1}} \mathcal{E}(s) \leq \sup_{s \in I_{k-1}} \mathcal{E}(s).$$

This is in contradiction with (8.15) and it thereby proves (8.14).

The claim in (8.5) now follows from (8.13) and (8.14).

Having established the first claim in Theorem 8.3, we can now suppose that

$$(8.16) \quad \text{there exists no } s_\star \in I \text{ such that } E(s_\star, T_j) \geq c_j \text{ for all } j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k-1\}.$$

The first step of this argument focuses on proving that (8.16) implies that the setting in the second part of Theorem 8.3 is in place, namely that

$$(8.17) \quad \text{there exists } j_\star \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k-1\}, \text{ such that if } s \in I \text{ and } E(s, T_j) \geq c_j \text{ for all } j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots\} \cap [1, j_\star - 1], \text{ then necessarily } E(s, T_{j_\star}) < c_{j_\star}$$

and that

$$(8.18) \quad I_{j_\star} \neq \emptyset.$$

To this end, let us first remark that, for all $S \in I$ and all $T > 0$,

$$(8.19) \quad \lim_{s \rightarrow S} E(s, T) = E(S, T),$$

thanks to (8.1) and the Dominated Convergence Theorem.

Then, to prove (8.17) and (8.18), we define $J_0 := I$ and recursively, for all $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k - 1\}$,

$$J_j := \{s \in J_{j-1} \text{ s.t. } E(s, T_j) \geq c_j\}$$

and we claim that there exists $j_\star \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k - 1\}$ for which

$$(8.20) \quad J_{j_\star} = \emptyset.$$

Indeed, if not, for every $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k - 1\}$ there would exist $s_j \in J_j \subseteq J_i$ for all $i \leq j$. This would give that $E(s_j, T_i) \geq c_i$ for all $i \leq j$. If $k \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots\}$, then this implies that

$$E(s_{k-1}, T_i) \geq c_i$$

for all $i \in \{1, \dots, k - 1\}$, which is in contradiction with (8.16) and the proof of (8.20) for the case $k \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{2, 3, 4, \dots\}$ is complete. On the other hand, if $k = \infty$, since I is compact, up to a subsequence we may suppose that s_j converges to some $s_\infty \in I$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$. Accordingly, by (8.19), given any $i \in \mathbb{N}$ we see that

$$E(s_\infty, T_i) = \lim_{j \rightarrow +\infty} E(s_j, T_i) \geq c_i.$$

But this is in contradiction with (8.16) and the proof of (8.20) is complete also for the case $k = \infty$.

Moreover, in (8.20), by taking j_\star as small as possible, we can also suppose that $J_j \neq \emptyset$ for all $j \leq j_\star - 1$. In this way, we see that $I_{j_\star} = J_{j_\star-1} \neq \emptyset$ and we obtain (8.17) and (8.18), as desired.

From this, in order to complete the proof of Theorem 8.3, we only need to check (8.6). To this end, we claim that, in this case,

$$(8.21) \quad \sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) = \sup_{s \in I_{j_\star}} \mathcal{E}(s).$$

Indeed, if not, then necessarily

$$\sup_{s \in I} \mathcal{E}(s) > \sup_{s \in I_{j^*}} \mathcal{E}(s)$$

and accordingly

$$(8.22) \quad \sup_{s \in I \setminus I_{j^*}} \mathcal{E}(s) > \sup_{s \in I_{j^*}} \mathcal{E}(s).$$

Now, if $s \in I \setminus I_{j^*}$, then there exists $j_s \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k - 1\} \cap [1, j^* - 1]$ for which $E(s, T_{j_s}) < c_{j_s}$ and consequently $\mathcal{E}(s) \leq E(s, T_{j_s}) < c_{j_s}$. In view of our monotonicity assumption in (8.4), as motivated by Lemma 8.2, this gives that $\mathcal{E}(s) \leq c_{j_s-1}$. As a result,

$$(8.23) \quad \sup_{s \in I \setminus I_{j^*}} \mathcal{E}(s) \leq c_{j^*-1}.$$

Instead, if $s \in I_{j^*}$, we have that $E(s, T_{j^*-1}) \geq c_{j^*-1}$, yielding that

$$\sup_{s \in I_{j^*}} \mathcal{E}(s) \geq c_{j^*-1}.$$

From this, (8.22) and (8.23) a contradiction follows and the proof of (8.21) is thereby complete.

Now we observe that, by construction, if $s \in I_{j^*}$ then $\mathcal{E}(s) = E(s, T_{j^*})$. From this and (8.21) we obtain (8.6), as desired. \square

Proof of Theorem 8.4. Notice that we do not aim here at determining the lifespan of the forager, but only its optimal strategy. This will be possible thanks to a monotonicity trick. Indeed, by Theorem 7.5 we know that, in this setting, for every $T > 0$, each efficiency functional $[0, 1] \ni s \mapsto E(s, T)$ is monotone in s , and specifically strictly increasing in case (i) and strictly decreasing in case (ii).

Therefore, in case (i) we have that $E(s, T) < E(1, T)$ for all $s \in [0, 1)$, and in case (ii) that $E(s, T) < E(0, T)$ for all $s \in (0, 1]$.

Now, suppose that we are in case (i) (the argument for case (ii) being analogous) and pick any $s_0 \in [0, 1)$.

Then, by (8.3), two situations arise: either for some $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k - 1\}$

$$(8.24) \quad E(s_0, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, j - 1\}, E(s_0, T_j) < c_j \text{ and } \mathcal{E}(s_0) = E(s_0, T_j)$$

or

$$(8.25) \quad E(s_0, T_i) \geq c_i \text{ for all } i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\} \text{ and } \mathcal{E}(s_0) = E(s_0, T_k).$$

If (8.24) arises, then $E(1, T_i) > E(s_0, T_i) \geq c_i$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, j-1\}$ and accordingly

$$(8.26) \quad \mathcal{E}(1) \geq E(1, T_j) > E(s_0, T_j) = \mathcal{E}(s_0).$$

If instead (8.25) occurs, then $E(1, T_i) > E(s_0, T_i) \geq c_i$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, \dots, k-1\}$. Therefore, if $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we have that

$$(8.27) \quad \mathcal{E}(1) = E(1, T_k) > E(s_0, T_k) = \mathcal{E}(s_0).$$

From this and (8.26) we deduce that $s = 1$ is the unique maximizer for \mathcal{E} in $(0, 1)$ if $k \in \mathbb{N}$, concluding the proof of (i) for $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

On the other hand, if $k = \infty$, we have that

$$(8.28) \quad \mathcal{E}(1) = E(1, +\infty) = \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} E(1, T) \geq \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} E(s_0, T) = E(s_0, +\infty) = \mathcal{E}(s_0).$$

Combining this and (8.26), we infer that the Gaussian exponent is a maximizer also if $k = \infty$. Some more work is needed to check that the Gaussian exponent is the unique maximizer, the technical issue is that the strict inequality is lost in the above limit procedure. To this end, we pick $s_0 \in [0, 1)$. If (8.24) holds true, then $\mathcal{E}(1) > \mathcal{E}(s_0)$, in light of (8.26), therefore we can focus on the case in which (8.25) is satisfied. Thus, we deduce from (8.1) that, for all $s \in [0, 1)$,

$$E(s, +\infty) = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-(2\pi|\xi|)^{2st}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi dt = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-\tau} \frac{|\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} d\xi d\tau.$$

Since $n \geq 2 > 2s$, we conclude that

$$(8.29) \quad E(s, +\infty) < +\infty \text{ for all } s \in [0, 1).$$

We recall the expression in (8.1) and differentiate under the integral sign (see equation (8.30) for a justification of this) and we see that

$$(8.30) \quad \partial_s \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{1 - e^{-T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}}}{(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} T^2 k(\xi, s) \sigma'(T(2\pi|\xi|)^{2s}) |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi.$$

Here above and in what follows, we use the notation

$$\sigma(x) := \frac{1 - e^{-x}}{x}$$

and

$$(8.31) \quad k(\xi, s) := 2 \ln(2\pi |\xi|) (2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}.$$

Accordingly, we use (8.1), (8.29) and (8.30), we use the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus and we see that

$$(8.32) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}(1) - \mathcal{E}(s_0) &= \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \left(E(1, T) - E(s_0, T) \right) \\ &= \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{s_0}^1 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} T^2 k(\xi, s) \sigma'(T(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi \right] ds. \end{aligned}$$

We recall (see equation (8.33)) that

$$(8.33) \quad \sigma'(x) \leq 0 \quad \text{for each } x \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma' \in L^\infty((0, +\infty)).$$

We also notice that $k \leq 0$ in the support of \widehat{p} . This and the sign of σ' detected in (8.33) give that the integrand in (8.32) is nonnegative.

As a consequence, by Fatou's Lemma,

$$(8.34) \quad \mathcal{E}(1) - \mathcal{E}(s_0) \geq \int_{s_0}^1 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} T^2 k(\xi, s) \sigma'(T(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi \right] ds.$$

We observe that

$$\sigma'(x) = \frac{e^{-x}(x+1) - 1}{x^2}$$

and therefore

$$T^2 \sigma'(T(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}) = \frac{e^{-T(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}} (T(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} + 1) - 1}{(2\pi |\xi|)^{4s}}.$$

We plug this information and (8.31) into (8.34) and we find that

$$(8.35) \quad \begin{aligned} &\frac{\mathcal{E}(1) - \mathcal{E}(s_0)}{2} \\ &\geq \int_{s_0}^1 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \lim_{T \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\ln(2\pi |\xi|)}{(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}} \left[e^{-T(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}} (T(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s} + 1) - 1 \right] |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi \right] ds \\ &= - \int_{s_0}^1 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\ln(2\pi |\xi|)}{(2\pi |\xi|)^{2s}} |\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2 d\xi \right] ds, \end{aligned}$$

which is strictly positive, thus confirming that $s = 1$ is the unique maximizer. \square

Proof of Corollary 8.5. We begin by observing that $s = 1$ is a maximizer, since this part of the proof of Theorem 8.4(i) is not affected by dimensionality.

Now, if (8.8) holds true, then we deduce from (8.26) that $\mathcal{E}(1) > \mathcal{E}(s_0)$ for all $s_0 \in [0, 1)$ and we are done.

Therefore, we can reduce ourselves to (8.9), under the condition that (8.8) is violated.

In this situation, since (8.8) does not hold true, we infer from the monotonicity result in Theorem 7.5 that there exists $s_0 \in [0, 1)$ such that, for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$,

$$E(1, T_j) \geq E(s_0, T_j) \geq c_j$$

and accordingly $\mathcal{E}(1) = E(1, +\infty)$ and $\mathcal{E}(s_0) = E(s_0, +\infty)$.

Besides, in view of (8.9), for every $s_0 \in [0, 1)$,

$$\int_{(-\frac{1}{2\pi}, \frac{1}{2\pi})} \frac{|\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2}{|\xi|^{2s_0}} d\xi \leq \int_{(-\frac{1}{2\pi}, \frac{1}{2\pi})} \frac{|\widehat{p}(\xi)|^2}{|\xi|^2} d\xi < +\infty$$

and therefore both $E(1, +\infty)$ and $E(s_0, +\infty)$ are finite (recall (8.1)).

Consequently, we can apply Fatou's Lemma as in (8.34) and (8.35) to conclude that

$$\mathcal{E}(1) - \mathcal{E}(s_0) = E(1, +\infty) - E(s_0, +\infty) > 0,$$

as desired. □

Proof of Theorem 8.6. Assume first that $T_\star = T_k$. In this case, we have that $E(s, T) \geq c(T)$ for all $T \in [0, T_k)$, and accordingly $E(s, T_j) \geq c(T_j) = c_j$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, k - 1\}$, giving that both $\mathcal{E}_\star(s)$ and $\mathcal{E}(s)$ are equal to $E(s, T_k)$, as claimed.

We now suppose that $T_\star < T_k$. Since, for every $T \in [0, T_1)$ it holds that $E(s, T) \geq 0 = c_0$, it follows that $T_\star \geq T_1$. Thus, we take $j \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{1, 2, 3, \dots, k - 1\}$ such that $T_\star \in [T_j, T_{j+1})$.

Given $T \in [0, T_\star)$, we know that $E(s, T) \geq c(T)$ and in particular, for each $i \leq j$, we have that $E(s, T_i) \geq c(T_i) = c_i$.

Also, by construction, $E(s, T_{j+1}) < c_{j+1}$. Accordingly, $\mathcal{E}(s) = E(s, T_j) = \mathcal{E}_\star(s)$, as desired. □

8.4 Conclusions

In this chapter, the foraging model of a predator with finite lifetime was considered and the optimal search strategy was determined as an optimal Lévy exponent for an efficiency functional.

We determined that the optimal exponent varies depending on the Fourier transform of the prey distribution. When this distribution is supported in a sufficiently small ball, then the optimizer is given by a Gaussian dispersal. If instead the support lies in the complement of a suitable ball, then the ballistic diffusion provides an optimizer.

Both these situations have biological relevance: that of Fourier transforms with small support corresponding to distributions of preys with low oscillations and those supported away from the origin being related to hunts in the presence of risks or traps for the predator.

The process of decomposing a function into its elementary oscillatory components is the core of Fourier analysis, which is abundantly employed in mathematical biology and ecology, see e.g. [Les97; Kot01; Mur02]. In the framework of this chapter, this methodology is useful to decompose “low frequency” patterns (roughly speaking, the ones in which the oscillations take place only at a large scale) and “high frequency” ones (the ones in which wilder oscillations take place at a small scale), relating the latter to an “unpredictable” behavior similar to that of a hunt by ambush.

For a visual representation of how high-frequency components in the Fourier transform are used to represent the “irregular” or “rapidly changing” parts of a function, see e.g. Figure 9.4 in [Sue+18].

Uniqueness conditions for the optimizing strategies were also given. We remark that uniqueness conditions for the optimizing strategies are important from an ecological perspective, since they suggest that evolution may select this unique optimizer through the process of natural selection (instead, in the process of more optimizers, different foraging patterns could in principle be selected). For more details about how unique optimal foraging strategies may emerge as a result of the evolutionary pressures of natural selection, see e.g. [Cha76].

PART II

NONLOCAL WILLMORE ENERGY

INTRODUCTION TO PART II

In this part we present the nonlocal counterpart of the classical problem of the Willmore surfaces. More precisely, we consider the L^p -norm of the *fractional mean curvature* and we discuss the existence of minimizers in the critical and subcritical case.

9.1 Nonlocal Willmore energy

In this section we define the nonlocal counterpart of the classical Willmore energy. Moreover, we present the main results regarding the associated minimization problem obtained in Chapters 10 and 11.

The classical Willmore energy of an immersed surface $f : \Sigma \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ with mean curvature vector \bar{H} and induced measure area μ is given by

$$\mathcal{W}(f(\Sigma)) := \frac{1}{4} \int_{\Sigma} |\bar{H}|^2 d\mu.$$

This functional interests mathematicians from different areas, such as conformal geometry and mathematical analysis [Wil93; Sim86; BK03; KS04; Riv08].

The minimization problem associated to this functional has been first solved for surfaces of genus 0 by T. Willmore in [Wil65]. In [Sch02], Schmidt presented the proof of the long-standing Willmore conjecture, according to which the minimizer among surfaces of genus 1 is provided by the stereographic projection of the Clifford torus (up to conformal transformations). Finally, the existence of minimizers among surfaces of a prescribed genus $g \geq 2$ has instead been proved in [BK03].

Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that the Willmore energy finds applications in biology and physics, such as in the modelling of thin elastic structures, see e.g. [Ger21; Hel73; Can70].

Now, we introduce the nonlocal Willmore energy. To do so, given some set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $x \in \partial E$ we consider the quantity given by

$$H_{\partial E}^s(x) := P.V. \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{n+s}} dy.$$

$H_{\partial E}^s$ is known as *fractional or nonlocal mean curvature of E in x* , and it is obtained as the first variation of the fractional perimeter $\text{Per}_s(E)$ of E , see [CCC23].

We also notice that the definition of nonlocal mean curvature is consistent with the classical concept of mean curvature. Indeed, as it is showed in [AV14], if $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is smooth enough then

$$(9.1) \quad \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (1 - s) H_{\partial E}^s(x) = c_n H_{\partial E}(x).$$

where $H_{\partial E}$ is the classical mean curvature of ∂E and $c_n \in (0, +\infty)$ some constant depending on n .

Furthermore, for $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ smooth enough, making use of the Divergence Theorem, we can rewrite the fractional mean curvature as

$$(9.2) \quad H_{\partial E}^s(x) = c_s \int_{\partial E} \frac{\langle n(y), y - x \rangle}{|y - x|^{n+s}} dH_y^{n-1}$$

where $n(y) \in \mathbb{S}^{n-1}$ is the outward unit normal of ∂E at y and $c_s \in (0, +\infty)$ some constant depending on s .

Then, for $p \in (1, +\infty)$ we can define the following functional

$$(9.3) \quad \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\partial E) := \int_{\partial E} |H_{\partial E}^s(x)|^p dH_x^{n-1}.$$

This quantity can be regarded as the nonlocal counterpart of the Willmore energy functional. As a matter of fact, in light of (9.1), for $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ smooth enough, when $p = 2$ and $s \rightarrow 1$ we see that $\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \mathcal{W}_{s,2}(\partial E) = \mathcal{W}(\partial E)$, up to a normalizing constant.

In Chapters 10 and 11 we analyse the energy in (9.3) and we discuss the existence of its minimizer.

Nonlocal minimal surfaces, i.e. surfaces with vanishing fractional mean curvature $H^s \equiv 0$, are absolute minimizers of the nonlocal Willmore energy. Indeed, since $H^s \equiv 0$, their nonlocal Willmore energy is equal to zero. Nevertheless, in general a curve or surface which is critical for the Willmore-energy is not necessarily a minimal surface (in the sense of vanishing mean curvature). For example there are no compact nonlocal minimal surfaces [Cir+18; Cab+18]. While nonlocal minimal and constant mean curvature surfaces have been studied very thoroughly, for an overview see e.g. [DV16; DV22], the theory of nonlocal Willmore surfaces is only at the very beginning.

When studying such a minimization problem, we need to consider separately the following three cases:

- supercritical: $ps < n - 1$,
- critical: $ps = n - 1$,
- subcritical: $ps > n - 1$.

Indeed, for $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, we notice the scaling property

$$(9.4) \quad \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\lambda \partial E) = \lambda^{(n-1)-sp} \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\partial E) \quad \text{for all } \lambda > 0.$$

In Chapter 10 we deal with the subcritical case. In particular, the scaling property in (9.4) is the core of the main result of the chapter, namely a uniform bilipschitz control on the local parametrization of ∂E , from which (under some further hypothesis), one deduces the existence of minimizers.

The scaling invariant case, or critical case, $sp = n - 1$ will be discussed in Chapter 11. This requires more profound tools from Geometry and/or Harmonic Analysis.

Another way to give a meaning of the terminology *critical* and *subcritical* is the Sobolev embedding. As we shall see, very roughly $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$ corresponds to a control of a parametrization of Σ in $W^{1+s,p}$, and if $s > \frac{n-1}{p}$ we have that $W^{1+s,p} \hookrightarrow C^{1,s-\frac{n-1}{p}}$, but for $s = \frac{n-1}{p}$ we have $W^{1+s,p} \not\hookrightarrow C^{0,1}$.

In both Chapters 10 and 11 we restrict our analysis to convex surfaces. To fix the ideas, we say that a surfaces $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is convex if for every $x \in \Sigma$ there exists

some $v_x \in \mathbb{S}^{n-1}$ such that for all $y \in \Sigma$ it holds that

$$\langle v_x, x - y \rangle \geq 0.$$

As we will see more in detail in the next two subsections, the reason why we need the convexity assumption is the positivity of the scalar product $\langle n(y), y - x \rangle$ appearing in the equation for the nonlocal mean curvature in (9.2). Indeed, as we will discuss, in such a case the energy $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$ displays the topological property of *self-repulsiveness*. This is typical of tangent-point energies, see [SM18; SM13b], and it is fundamental for the arguments used to ensure the existence of minimizers for such energies.

In particular, making use of this similarity between tangent-point energies and nonlocal Willmore energy for convex surfaces, we manage to use some techniques based on the ideas from the corresponding existence argument for minimizers of the tangent-point energies.

The subcritical case - Chapter 10

In Chapter 10 we discuss the existence of minimizers for (9.3), restricting our analysis to convex surfaces and focusing only on the subcritical case where $p > \frac{n-1}{s}$.

The main step to achieve the existence of minimizers (among convex surfaces) is the following uniform Lipschitz graph control:

Theorem 9.1 (Theorem 10.1 in Chapter 10). *Let $p > \frac{n-1}{s}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. Then, for any $\Lambda > 0$ there exists $R > 0$ such that the following holds:*

Let $\Sigma = \Sigma^{n-1} = \partial\Omega$ be the smooth boundary of a compact convex body in \mathbb{R}^n , such that

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda.$$

Then, for any $x_0 \in \Sigma$ there exists a rotation $P \in SO(N)$ and a smooth map

$$f : B(0, R) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

with

$$[\nabla f]_{C^{s-(n-1)/p}(B(0,R))} \leq C(\Lambda, s, p, d),$$

so that $x_0 + P(x, f(x))$ is a local parametrization of Σ , that is

$$\Phi(x) := x_0 + P(x, f(x))$$

is a diffeomorphism as a map $B(0, R) \rightarrow \Phi(B(0, R)) \subset \Sigma$.

Theorem 9.1 guarantees a uniform control on the $C^{1, s - \frac{n-1}{p}}$ -norm of the local graph parametrization of a convex surface $\Sigma = \partial\Omega$ with respect to the upper bound on the fractional Willmore-energy. From this result we can draw some observations.

First, as a corollary of Theorem 9.1 we can obtain a uniform lower Ahlfor’s regularity for (convex) sets with bounded fractional Willmore-energy, see Corollary 10.2.

Also, making use of Theorem 9.1 together with a covering argument, we can prove a weak Michael-Simon type inequality for surfaces with a uniform bound of the fractional Willmore-energy, see Corollary 10.3. We observe that a stronger, real Michael-Simon inequality was recently obtained by Cabré-Cozzi-Csató [CCC23] – without the subcritical assumption $p > \frac{n-1}{s}$, however also using the convexity assumption.

Moreover, we notice that it is possible to rewrite all the results discussed above for nonconvex surfaces by replacing the nonlocal Willmore energy with a sort-of nonlocal bending energy. To be more precise, the convexity assumption in Theorem 9.1 comes from the fact that we need to consider

$$|A|_{\Sigma, s}(x) := c_s \int_{\Sigma} \frac{|\langle y - x, n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{n+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^{n-1}.$$

It clearly follows from (9.2), that if Σ is the boundary of a convex set, then

$$|A|_{\Sigma, s}(x) = H_{\Sigma}^s(x).$$

Thus, if we define the nonlocal bending energy

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) := \| |A|_{\Sigma, s} \|_{L^p(\Sigma)}^p,$$

for every Σ that is the boundary of a convex set it holds that

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) = \mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma).$$

The positivity (or negativity) of the scalar product $n(y) \cdot (y - x)$ is actually the only reason why we need required convexity in the previous results (see Proposition 10.5).

Furthermore, $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$ is self-repulsive, meaning that distant strands cannot come close to each other. In other words, $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$ preserves embeddings. This is a feature known for subcritical (and to some extent also critical) tangent-point energies, [SM18; SM13b].

Theorem 9.2 (Theorem 10.6 in Chapter 10, Self-Replusivness). *Assume $p > \frac{d}{s}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. For every $\Lambda > 0$ there exists a constant $\Gamma = \Gamma(p, d, s, \Lambda) > 1$ such that if $\Sigma = \partial\Omega$ is a compact surface as above (without any convexity assumptions) and*

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{H}^d(\Sigma) \leq 1,$$

then

$$|x - y| \leq d_\Sigma(x, y) \leq \Gamma |x - y|,$$

where d_Σ denotes the intrinsic distance within Σ .

The main consequence of Theorem 9.1 is the following existence of minimizers for $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}$ for every genus g . More precisely, the result is the following

Theorem 9.3 (Theorem 10.7 in Chapter 10). *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. Then, for every genus g there exists an embedded C^1 -surface Σ minimizing the $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}$ -energy among all embedded C^1 -surfaces $\tilde{\Sigma}$ of the same genus with $\mathcal{H}^d(\tilde{\Sigma}) \leq 1$.*

Analogously to the previous results, we observe that if we assume a priori convexity, whence $\mathcal{B}_{s,p} = \mathcal{W}_{s,p}$, then the same result is true – and thus we also find minimizers for the fractional Willmore energy $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$, if $p > \frac{n-1}{s}$, among all *convex* sets:

Theorem 9.4. *Let $p > (n - 1)/s$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. Then, there exists some smooth and convex $\tilde{E} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $\partial\tilde{E}$ minimizes $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$ among all ∂E such that $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is smooth and convex.*

However, there is no convex surfaces of nontrivial genus, so the above minimization problem is likely converging simply to the sphere (as of now, we do not know for a fact that the minimizer is the sphere).

The proof of Theorem 9.3 almost immediately follows from the uniform bound on the Hölder constant of the derivative of the parametrization, Theorem 9.1, and the non-collapsing guaranteed by Theorem 9.2, combined with the arguments in [Bre12].

The critical case - Chapter 11

In Chapter 11 we study the existence of minimizers for $\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s,p}$ among curves $\Sigma = \partial E$ where $E \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ is convex and Lipschitz. In particular, we focus our analysis on the critical regime $p = \frac{1}{s}$.

To do so, we rewrite the energy $\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s,p}(\partial E)$ by suitably parametrizing ∂E by a curve. More precisely, if $\partial E \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ is smooth enough and $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is a parametrization of ∂E , we can express the nonlocal mean curvature of ∂E as

$$H_{\partial E}^s(x) = \pm \frac{2}{s} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} |\gamma'(y)| \, dy.$$

This leads to a nonlocal Willmore energy for curves $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$,

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) = \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} |\gamma'(y)| \, dy \right|^p |\gamma'(x)| \, dx.$$

Then, if ∂E is smooth and $\partial E = \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$ for some $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, we have that

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) = c_{s,p} \hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s,p}(E).$$

We observe that we can rephrase the scale invariance for the energy $\mathcal{W}_{s,\frac{1}{s}}$ as follows: If for some $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\rho > 0$ we consider the rescaled curve $\gamma_\rho(\cdot) := \rho\gamma(\frac{\cdot}{\rho}) : \rho\mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, then we have

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,\frac{1}{s}}(\gamma) = \mathcal{W}_{s,\frac{1}{s}}(\gamma_\rho).$$

For simplicity of notation, for every $s \in (0, 1)$ we denote $\mathcal{W}_s(\gamma) := \mathcal{W}_{s,\frac{1}{s}}(\gamma)$.

Regarding the existence of minimizers, scaling invariant variational functionals are prone to bubbling effects, and the existence of minimizers becomes a nontrivial question, see for instance [SU81; Sim86; KS12; Riv16].

In Chapter 11 we are interested in minimizing *convex* curves, which will be taken to be in arc-length parametrization. More precisely, we consider the class

$$(9.5) \quad X := \left\{ \gamma \in C^1(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2) \left| \begin{array}{l} \gamma \text{ is a homeomorphism} \\ |\gamma'| \equiv 1 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{S}^1 \\ \gamma \text{ is convex in } \mathbb{S}^1 \end{array} \right. \right\}.$$

The main result is the following:

Theorem 9.5 (Theorem 11.1 Chapter 11). *For any $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists a minimizer of \mathcal{W}_s in X .*

The nonlocal Willmore energy is only defined on co-dimension one objects, since the nonlocal perimeter is only defined on those sets (albeit, see [MS23]). In particular, we can reformulate our result for sets E whose boundary are represented by curves γ . Let

$$C := \left\{ E \subset \mathbb{R}^2 \left| \begin{array}{l} E \text{ is convex and bounded} \\ \partial E \text{ is } C^1 \\ E \text{ has nonempty interior} \end{array} \right. \right\}.$$

Then, as a direct consequence of Theorem 9.5 we have the following:

Theorem 9.6 (Theorem 11.2 in Chapter 11). *For any $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists a minimizer of $\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s, \frac{1}{s}}$ in C .*

The arguments presented in Chapter 11 to discuss the minimization problem for $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$ are inspired by the relation between nonlocal Willmore energy and the tangent-point energies, see for instance [BO95; GM99; BR15] for details on these latest variational problems.

Indeed, some of the techniques used to prove Theorem 9.5 are based on ideas from the corresponding existence argument for minimizers of the tangent-point energy, [Bla+24].

Nevertheless, there are substantial technical differences that we need to overcome. One is the sign of the mean curvature H_s , which for general curves could be changing – we remedy this by working only with convex curves, an unsatisfying but for now seemingly unavoidable assumption (cf. also [CCC23]).

Another one is the change of underlying Sobolev space, which creates surprising technical difficulties. In particular, instead of the fractional Sobolev space $W^{s,p}$ which is typical of tangent-point energies, see [Bla+24], we need to consider for $I \subset \mathbb{R}$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$ the space $W_2^{s,p}(I)$ defined in the usual way via its semi-norm,

$$[f]_{W_2^{s,p}(I)} := \left(\int_I \left(\int_I \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2s}} dy \right)^{\frac{p}{2}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

The main strategy to prove Theorem 9.5 can be summarized in the following points.

- i) First, we show that the Willmore energy controls the BMO-norm of γ' in a locally quantifiable way, Proposition 11.12.

- ii) Then, we establish that local BMO-control suffices to obtain (quantifiably) local control of the BiLipschitz constant of the curve, Lemma 11.15. This in turn gives quantitative control of the graphical behavior of γ , Lemma 11.16.
- iii) On sets where γ is a graph, we can use convexity to obtain a control in the sharp Sobolev space $W_2^{1+s, \frac{1}{s}}$ Theorem 11.17.
- iv) The convexity of the curves considered allows us to use the self-repulsiveness, typical of tangent-point energies, for the nonlocal Willmore energy, see Theorem 11.21. From the self-repulsiveness one obtains that convex curves with finite \mathcal{W}_s -energy are topological one-manifolds, see Proposition 11.23.

Finally, in Theorem 11.30, making use of the points i)-iv), we obtain reflexivity and lower semicontinuity in the class of convex homeomorphisms. Then, the existence of minimizers stated in Theorem 9.5 follows from Theorem 11.30 by direct method.

It is important to observe that most of the results in i)-iv) are achieved with the technical simplification that γ is C^1 . Such an hypothesis on the regularity of γ does not represent a loss of generality in the study of the minimization problem for \mathcal{W}_s . Indeed, as it is precisely stated below, all convex curves that are not C^1 have infinite (critical and subcritical) nonlocal Willmore energy. To be more precise, if we define the set

$$\gamma \in \tilde{X} := \left\{ \gamma \in \text{Lip}(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2) \left| \begin{array}{l} \gamma \text{ is a homeomorphism} \\ |\gamma'| \equiv 1 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{S}^1 \\ \gamma \text{ is convex in } \mathbb{S}^1 \end{array} \right. \right\},$$

we have the following result:

Theorem 9.7 (Theorem 11.24 in Chapter 11). *Assume $\gamma \in \tilde{X}$ and that some $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \geq \frac{1}{s}$ it holds that*

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) < +\infty.$$

Then, $\gamma \in C^1$.

Theorem 9.7 relies on two main results.

The first one is that if $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is a Lipschitz homeomorphism which is convex and in arc-length parametrization, then if it is not C^1 , there exists some point $x_0 \in \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$ with two distinct supporting hyperplanes, see Lemma 11.26.

The second ingredient used to prove Theorem 9.7 is the construction of a convex and Lipschitz barrier $G \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, with two distinct supporting hyperplanes in some point $x_0 \in \partial G$, see Proposition 11.28. In particular, for such a barrier, we estimate $H_{\partial G}^s$ in points $x \in \partial G$ close to x_0 , and we show that

$$H_{\partial G}^s(x) \geq \frac{c}{|x - x_0|^s}.$$

for some structural constant $c \in (0, +\infty)$.

Making use of the Maximum Principle for the nonlocal mean curvature (see e.g. Proposition 11.10) and the barrier in Proposition 11.28, we obtain that if $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is a Lipschitz homeomorphism which is convex and in arc-length parametrization and in some point has two distinct supporting hyperplanes, then it has infinite critical (and subcritical) nonlocal Willmore energy, see Proposition 11.27. Finally, making use of Proposition 11.27 and Lemma 11.26 we obtain Theorem 9.7.

A FRACTIONAL WILLMORE-TYPE ENERGY FUNCTIONAL - SUBCRITICAL OBSERVATIONS

We investigate surfaces with bounded L^p -norm of the fractional mean curvature, a quantity we shall refer to as fractional Willmore-type functional. In the subcritical case and under convexity assumptions we show how this Willmore-functional controls local parametrization, and conclude as consequences lower Ahlfors-regularity, a weak Michael-Simon type inequality, and an application to stability.

10.1 Introduction

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ be a bounded open set and consider (under appropriate smoothness assumptions) $\Sigma := \partial\Omega$ as a d -dimensional hypersurface, $N = d + 1$. For $s \in (0, 1)$, Caffarelli-Roquejoffre-Savin initiated in [CRS10] the study of the so-called fractional perimeter, and obtained as the first variation thereof the notion of fractional mean curvature H_Σ^s given by the formula

$$H_\Sigma^s(x) := c_s \int_\Sigma \frac{\langle y - x, n(y) \rangle}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d,$$

cf. [CCC23]. Here $n : \Sigma \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^d \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ is the outwards pointing unit normal on $\Sigma = \partial\Omega$ and c_s is a constant.

This integral does not need to be considered in the principal value sense, observing that $\frac{x-y}{|x-y|}$ is approximately tangent to Σ we see that $\lim_{y \rightarrow x} \langle \frac{y-x}{|y-x|}, n(y) \rangle = 0$, and

(under sufficient smoothness assumptions on $\partial\Omega$) we see that $H_\Sigma^s(x)$ is well-defined for any $x \in \Sigma$.

Also let us remark that by suitably choosing c_s one can see that $\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} H_\Sigma^s(x) = H_\Sigma(x)$ where H is the usual (scalar) mean curvature of Σ .

The definition of fractional perimeter and fractional mean curvature has spawned a new area of nonlocal geometric questions and problems, for e.g. fractional minimal surfaces (i.e. assuming $H^s \equiv 0$), fractional constant-mean-curvature surfaces (assuming $H^s \equiv \text{const}$). See, among many other works, e.g. [CV11; Cab+18; DPW18].

This article is an invitation to consider a fractional version of the Willmore energy, i.e.

$$\mathscr{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) := \int_\Sigma |H_\Sigma^s(x)|^p d\mathcal{H}_x^d.$$

For $p = 2$ and $s \rightarrow 1$ (again, under a suitable choice of the normalizing constant c_s) we see that $\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \mathscr{W}_{s,p} = \mathscr{W}(\Sigma)$, the classical Willmore energy that is of great interest in Geometric Analysis, involving the resolution of the Willmore conjecture not too long ago, [MN14], see also [AMN16]. Critical points of the Willmore energy are commonly referred to as Willmore surfaces, and Willmore surfaces clearly form a larger class than minimal surfaces.

We point out that a very related curvature energy to $\mathscr{W}_{s,p}$ has been studied for more than two decades in applied mathematics and topology: the class of integral tangent-point energies, that were first considered for modelling purposes, [BO95; GM99]. See [SM12; SM13b] for discussions under very weak assumptions of the underlying sets Σ , Sobolev-space characterizations [Bla13], regularity for minimizers in the subcritical regime, [BR15], and in the scaling-invariant case, [Bla+24].

The relation between fractional Willmore-energy and tangent-point energy becomes obvious once we write both formulas next to each other: the fractional Willmore energy is given by

$$\mathscr{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) := |c_s|^p \int_\Sigma \left| \int_\Sigma \frac{\langle y-x, n(y) \rangle}{|x-y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d \right|^p d\mathcal{H}_x^d,$$

while the tangent-point energy is denoted as

$$\mathcal{T}_{p,q}(\Sigma) := |c_s|^p \int_\Sigma \int_\Sigma \frac{|\langle y-x, n(y) \rangle|^p}{|x-y|^{q-p}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d d\mathcal{H}_x^d,$$

for some parameters $q > p > 0$. The name *tangent-point energy* derives from the fact that

$$R(x, y) := \frac{|x - y|^2}{|\langle n(y), y - x \rangle|}$$

is the radius of the (smallest) sphere tangent to $y + T_y \Sigma$ passing through x , so the tangent-point energy is closely related to an integrated norm of $1/R(x, y)$.

Tangent-point and related curvature energies¹ have been around for a long time in the topological-analytical community, and by the (formal) similarity of the corresponding nonlocal curvature quantities we hope that the two fields can positively influence each other.

Our analysis below will be restricted to two major simplifications: firstly we will *de facto* mostly consider convex surfaces. Also, we focus on the so-called subcritical case where $p > \frac{d}{s}$ – with the hope that the arguments we present here are still useful for e.g. minimal and constant mean curvature. Observe that we have the scaling property

$$(10.1) \quad \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\lambda \Sigma) = \lambda^{d-sp} \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \quad \forall \lambda > 0.$$

Thus, $p = \frac{d}{s}$ is the scaling invariant case, a case which requires more profound tools from Geometry and/or Harmonic Analysis. This case is sometimes referred to as the *critical* scaling. Another way to give a meaning of the terminology *critical* and *subcritical* is the Sobolev embedding. As we shall see, very roughly $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$ corresponds to a control of a parametrization of Σ in $W^{1+s,p}$, and if $s > \frac{d}{p}$ we have that $W^{1+s,p} \hookrightarrow C^{1,s-\frac{d}{p}}$, but for $s = \frac{d}{p}$ we have $W^{1+s,p} \not\hookrightarrow C^{0,1}$.

Our first result is the following uniform Lipschitz graph control. Since we are in the subcritical scaling the following results should be compared to e.g. [Mon14; KLL15] for $d = 2$ in the local case $s = 1$.

Theorem 10.1. *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. Then for any $\Lambda > 0$ there exists $R > 0$ such that the following holds:*

¹Those have been defined first for curves, often called knot energies, to capture topology of knots. We refer the interested reader e.g. to O'hara energies [O'H91; O'H92; O'H94], a special case of which is the Möbius energy [FHW94]. See also [BRS16; BRS22] and [OS18; O'H19]. Another popular class are the Menger curvature energies, [SM13a].

Let $\Sigma = \Sigma^d = \partial\Omega$ be the smooth boundary of a compact convex body in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} , such that

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda.$$

Then for any $x_0 \in \Sigma$ there exists a rotation $P \in SO(N)$ and a smooth map

$$f : B(0, R) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

with

$$[\nabla f]_{C^{s-d/p}(B(0,R))} \leq C(\Lambda, s, p, d),$$

so that $x_0 + P(x, f(x))$ is a local parametrization of Σ , that is

$$\Phi(x) := x_0 + P(x, f(x))$$

is a diffeomorphism as a map $B(0, R) \rightarrow \Phi(B(0, R)) \subset \Sigma$.

Observe that it is by no means clear that the fractional Willmore-energy rules out distant strands to come close to Σ —unless we work with convex sets, where this self-repulsiveness holds similarly to tangent-point energies, Theorem 10.6.

A corollary of Theorem 10.1 is uniform lower Ahlfor's regularity for (convex) sets with bounded fractional Willmore-energy in the subcritical regime.

Corollary 10.2 (Uniform lower Ahlfor's regularity). *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\Lambda > 0$. Then there exists a constant $c = c(p, d, s, \Lambda)$ and radius $R_0 = R_0(p, d, s, \Lambda)$ such that the following holds:*

Let $\Sigma = \Sigma^d = \partial\Omega$ be the smooth boundary of a compact convex body in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} , such that

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda.$$

Then for any $x \in \Sigma$

$$\inf_{R \in (0, R_0)} R^{-d} \mathcal{H}^d(\Sigma \cap B(x, R)) > c$$

Another immediate consequence is a sort of weak Michael-Simon type inequality:

Corollary 10.3 (Weak Michael-Simon type inequality). *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $\Lambda > 0$, $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ and $q \in (1, \infty)$. Then there exists a constant $C = C(p, d, s, \alpha, q, \Lambda)$ such that the following holds.*

Let $\Sigma = \Sigma^d = \partial\Omega$ be the smooth boundary of a compact convex body in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} , such that

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda.$$

Then for any $f \in W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)$ with $q \in (1, \frac{d}{\alpha})$ we have

$$(10.2) \quad \|f\|_{L^{\frac{dq}{d-\alpha q}}(\Sigma)} \leq C ([f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}).$$

If $\alpha - \frac{d}{q} = \beta$ for some $\beta \in (0, \alpha)$ then

$$\|f\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma)} + [f]_{C^\beta(\Sigma)} \leq C ([f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}).$$

A very similar inequality was obtained in Cabré-Cozzi's [CC19] who only need to assume a lower Ahlfors regularity, but for all $R > 0$ (and for bounded sets that is clearly not possible). In our case, it follows from a simple covering argument, covering \mathbb{R}^{d+1} with copies of cutoff-functions $\eta \in C_c^\infty(B(0, R))$, $\eta \equiv 1$ in $B(0, R/2)$, and using the local representation by graphs (and the classical Sobolev inequality).

Let us stress that a way stronger, real Michael-Simon inequality was recently obtained by Cabré-Cozzi-Csató [CCC23] – without the subcritical assumption $p > \frac{d}{s}$, however also using the convexity assumption.

Applying $f \equiv 1$ to Corollary 10.3, equation (10.2), we obtain the following lower bound on the area – compare this with the scaling (10.1).

Corollary 10.4. *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\Lambda > 0$. Then there exists a constant $c = c(p, d, s, \Lambda)$ such that the following holds.*

Let $\Sigma = \Sigma^d = \partial\Omega$ be the smooth boundary of a compact convex body in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} , and assume

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda$$

Then

$$\mathcal{H}^d(\Sigma) \geq c.$$

The uniform parametrization is also useful when discussing flows and minimization problems – observe however that the convexity assumption rules out surfaces Σ of nontrivial genus, so that the only locally minimizing objects are most likely the sphere, cf. [Abr+03].

We believe it would be very interesting to start an analysis of fractional Willmore-surfaces – the scaling-invariant case – e.g. for curves Σ and $\mathcal{W}_{1/2,2}(\Sigma)$, eventually with the goal of developing as sophisticated arguments as for the classical Willmore-surfaces e.g. [Wil93; Sim86; BK03; KS04; Riv08].

As a last point let us remark that without the convexity assumption everything discussed above still applies to a sort-of nonlocal bending energy: Namely, the convexity assumption in Theorem 10.1 comes from the fact that we need to consider

$$|A|_{\Sigma,s}(x) := c_s \int_{\Sigma} \frac{|\langle y - x, n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d.$$

Observe that $\lim_{s \rightarrow 1^-} |A|_{\Sigma,s}(x) = |H(x)|$. We can define then the nonlocal bending energy

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) := \| |A|_{\Sigma,s} \|_{L^p(\Sigma)}^p.$$

This sort of energy is even more similar to the tangent-point energy due to the absolute value inside the integral. If Σ is the boundary of a *convex* set, then

$$|A|_{\Sigma,s}(x) = H_{\Sigma}^s(x),$$

and thus

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma) = \mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma).$$

Indeed this property is the only reason why we need required convexity in the previous results. Namely we have:

Proposition 10.5. *All the previous results are true for possibly non-convex surfaces $\Sigma = \partial\Omega$, if we replace the fractional Willmore energy $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$ by the bending energy $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}$.*

As an additional feature, we expect that $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$ is self-repulsive, meaning that distant strands cannot come close to each other. In other words, $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$ preserves embeddings. This is a feature known for subcritical (and to some extent also critical) tangent-point energies, [SM18; SM13b].

Theorem 10.6 (Self-repulsiveness and chord-arc constant). *Assume $p > \frac{d}{s}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. For every $\Lambda > 0$ there exists a constant $\Gamma = \Gamma(p, d, s, \Lambda) > 1$ such that if $\Sigma = \partial\Omega$ is a compact surface as above (without any convexity assumptions) and*

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{H}^d(\Sigma) \leq 1,$$

then

$$|x - y| \leq d_\Sigma(x, y) \leq \Gamma|x - y|,$$

where d_Σ denotes the intrinsic distance within Σ .

The assumptions on $\mathcal{H}^d(\Sigma)$ is crucial. Recall that we are subcritical, so not scaling invariant, but rather

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\lambda\Sigma) = \lambda^{d-sp} \mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma), \quad \lambda > 0.$$

This implies that if $p > \frac{d}{s}$ for any family of finite energy surfaces \mathcal{S} with the property $\lambda\mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{S}$, we have

$$\inf_{\Sigma \in \mathcal{S}} \mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) = 0.$$

Note this does not contradict the uniform parametrization, Theorem 10.1. So when we talk about minimizer, we have to bound the area from above.

Theorem 10.7 (Existence of minimizers). *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. For every genus g there exists an embedded C^1 -surface Σ minimizing the $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}$ -energy among all embedded C^1 -surfaces $\tilde{\Sigma}$ of the same genus with $\mathcal{H}^d(\tilde{\Sigma}) \leq 1$.*

Observe again: if we assume a priori convexity, whence $\mathcal{B}_{s,p} = \mathcal{W}_{s,p}$, then the same result is true – and thus we also find minimizers for the fractional Willmore energy $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$, if $p > \frac{d}{s}$, among all *convex* sets. However, there is no convex surfaces of nontrivial genus, so the above minimization problem is likely converging simply to the sphere (as of now, we do not know for a fact that the minimizer is the sphere).

The proof of Theorem 10.7 almost immediately follows from the uniform bound on the Hölder constant of the derivative of the parametrization, Theorem 10.1, and the non-collapsing guaranteed by Theorem 10.6, combined with the arguments in [Bre12].

We also remark that we are not aware of a commonly accepted way of extending the fractional mean curvature to higher co-dimension – since there is no commonly accepted way of extending the perimeter to higher co-dimension, however see [PPS22; MS23]. In contrast to this, it is easy to extend the functional $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}$ to higher-codimension manifolds $\Sigma^d \subset \mathbb{R}^N$,

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) := \int_\Sigma \left(\int_\Sigma \frac{|\Pi^\perp(y)(y-x)|}{|x-y|^{d+s+1}} dy \right)^p.$$

Here $\Pi^\perp(y)$ denotes the orthogonal projection from \mathbb{R}^N onto $T_y^\perp \Sigma$. In this note we focus only on co-dimension 1 surfaces, but our arguments easily extend to higher codimension $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}$ – indeed with little extra work one obtains then minimizing manifolds in any ambient isotopy class (again in the subcritical case only). Again, the scaling invariant case $p = \frac{d}{s}$ is extremely challenging.

We conclude this introduction with several directions that we find interesting, are partially working on, but invite anyone interested to study

- Classification of minimizers in subcritical and scaling-invariant case.
- The scaling-invariant case: existence of minimizers, regularity of minimizers.
- The fractional Willmore-flow, existence, uniqueness, and bubbling.

10.2 Proof of Theorem 10.1

We believe that the following can be relatively easily generalized to higher co-dimension, and to surfaces Σ with boundary or which do not bound a set. In particular it would apply to a convex or concave subset of Σ . For the (subcritical) tangent-point energies and probably many other energies the following argument is likely well-known, albeit possibly not written down.

Theorem 10.1 is a consequence of the following Theorem 10.8. Yet again we stress that if Σ is the boundary of *convex* sets then $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) = \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$, so the following theorem applies to the fractional Willmore energy for *convex* sets Σ .

Theorem 10.8. *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$ and $s \in (0,1)$. Then for any $\Lambda > 0$ there exists $R = R(s, d, p, \Lambda) > 0$ such that the following holds:*

Let Σ be a closed smooth d -dimensional hypersurface, such that

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \equiv c_{s,p} \int_{\Sigma} \left(\int_{\Sigma} \frac{|\langle y-x, n(y) \rangle|}{|x-y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d \right)^p d\mathcal{H}_x^d \leq \Lambda.$$

Then for any $x_0 \in \Sigma$ there exists a rotation $P \in SO(N)$ and a smooth map

$$f : B(0, R) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

with

$$[\nabla f]_{C^{s-d/p}(B(0,R))} \leq C(\Lambda, s, p, d),$$

so that $x_0 + P(x, f(x))$ is a local parametrization of Σ , that is

$$\Phi(x) := x_0 + P(x, f(x))$$

is a diffeomorphism as a map $B(0, R) \rightarrow \Phi(B(0, R)) \subset \Sigma$.

Remark 10.9. By scaling, one can easily make the constant $C(d, s, p, \Lambda)$ explicit in terms of Λ .

Fix any point $x_0 \in \Sigma$. By translation we may assume that $x_0 = 0$. By a rotation P we may assume that Σ is horizontal at 0, meaning that

$$T_0\Sigma = \mathbb{R}^d \times \{0\}.$$

There is a small neighborhood $U \subset \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ of 0 such that

$$U \cap \Sigma$$

can be represented as a graph, i.e. for some $\rho > 0$ there is $f : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \Sigma$ such that

$$\Phi(\cdot) := (\cdot, f(\cdot)) : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \Sigma$$

is a diffeomorphism onto its image. The idea is that if we have uniform control on ∇f then we can extend f to a larger ball. Indeed, this is a consequence of the implicit function theorem:

Lemma 10.10. *Let Σ be a smooth d -manifold without boundary in \mathbb{R}^N , $N = d + 1$. Fix some $\alpha > 0$. Assume $\rho > 0$ and that there exists a smooth $f : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that*

$$\Phi = (\cdot, f(\cdot)) : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \Sigma$$

is a local parametrization. If $f \in C^1(B(0, \rho))$ with

$$\|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B(0, \rho))} \leq 1$$

and uniformly continuous first derivatives, then there exists $\rho_2 > \rho$ and a smooth extension f of \tilde{f}

$$\tilde{f} : B(0, \rho_2) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

such that

$$\Phi = (\cdot, \tilde{f}(\cdot)) : B(0, \rho_2) \rightarrow \Sigma$$

is a local parametrization.

Proof. Since $f, \nabla f$ are uniformly continuous on the open set $B(0, \rho)$ there exists a C^1 -extension of f to $\overline{B(0, \rho)}$. By continuity we still have

$$\Phi(\cdot) := (\cdot, f(\cdot)) : \overline{B(0, \rho)} \rightarrow \Sigma.$$

Now fix any $x_0 \in \partial B(0, \rho)$. There exists a small tubular neighborhood $U \subset \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ around $(x_0, f(x_0))$ for which the nearest point projection $\pi : U \rightarrow \Sigma$ exists. Set

$$d(x, t) := \langle (x, t) - \pi(x, t), n(\pi(x, t)) \rangle, \quad (x, t) \in U.$$

Here $n(\pi(x, t))$ denotes a choice of unit normal. Then d is smooth, and we can ensure that

$$\forall (x, t) \in U : \quad (x, t) \in \Sigma \iff d(x, t) = 0.$$

Indeed $(x, t) - \pi(x, t) = 0$ if $(x, t) \in \Sigma$, and if $(x, t) \notin \Sigma$ then $(x, t) - \pi(x, t) \in (T_{\pi(x, t)}\Sigma)^\perp$.

If we can show that $\partial_t d(x_0, f(x_0)) \neq 0$, then by the implicit function theorem there exists a possibly smaller neighborhood U (not relabeled) of $(x_0, f(x_0))$ and for some $\varepsilon = \varepsilon(x_0) > 0$ a map $\tilde{f} : B(x_0, \varepsilon) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\forall (x, t) \in U : \quad (x, t) \in \Sigma \iff d(x, t) = 0 \iff t = \tilde{f}(x).$$

Since $B(x_0, \varepsilon) \cap B(0, \rho) \neq \emptyset$ we conclude that \tilde{f} is an extension of f to $B(x_0, \varepsilon) \cup B(0, \rho)$. We can do this for any $x_0 \in \partial B(0, \rho)$ (which is compact). Take a finite sequence $(x_i, \varepsilon(\rho_i))$ so that $V := \bigcup B(x_i, \varepsilon_i)$ covers $\partial B(0, \rho)$. Setting $U := V \cup B(0, \rho)$ and $2\varepsilon := \inf\{|x - y| : x \in B(0, \rho) \text{ and } y \in \mathbb{R}^d \setminus U\}$, we conclude that we have found an extension $\tilde{f} : B(0, \rho + \varepsilon) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with the desired properties.

So all we need to show is $\partial_t d(x_0, f(x_0)) \neq 0$. We observe that

$$\left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \right|_{\varepsilon=0} d((x_0, f(x_0)) + \varepsilon v) = 0 \quad \forall v \in T_{(x_0, f(x_0))}\Sigma.$$

On the other hand if $v \in (T_{(x_0, f(x_0))}\Sigma)^\perp$ then $\pi((x_0, f(x_0)) + v) = (x_0, f(x_0))$ and thus

$$d((x_0, f(x_0)) + \varepsilon v) = \varepsilon \underbrace{\langle v, n((x_0, f(x_0))) \rangle}_{\neq 0},$$

and we conclude that

$$\frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} d((x_0, f(x_0)) + \varepsilon v) \neq 0 \quad \forall v \notin T_{(x_0, f(x_0))}\Sigma.$$

So, all we actually have to establish is that $(0, \dots, 0, 1) \notin T_{(x_0, f(x_0))}\Sigma$, then $\partial_t d(x, t) \neq 0$ and we are done.

But again, we observe that for each $x \in B(0, \rho)$ we have with the standard vectors $e_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$,

$$T_{(x, f(x))}\Sigma = \text{span} \{(e_i, \partial_i f(x))\}_{1 \leq i \leq d}.$$

By continuity this again holds for any $x \in \overline{B(0, \rho)}$. In particular $(0, \dots, 0, 1) \notin T_{(x_0, f(x_0))}\Sigma$ and we can conclude. \square

The control that we need to apply Lemma 10.10, and which thus by a standard method of continuity concludes the proof of Theorem 10.1 and Theorem 10.8 is the following:

Lemma 10.11. *Let $\Lambda > 0$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p > \frac{d}{s}$. Then the following holds.*

Assume that Σ is a smooth d -manifold and that $f : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a smooth map with $f(0) = 0$, $Df(0) = 0$, and set

$$\Phi(x) := (x, f(x)).$$

Then whenever $\Phi : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ is a parametrization of Σ , we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\int_{B(0, \rho)} \left(\int_{B(0, \rho)} \frac{|f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right)^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \lesssim (1 + \|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B(0, \rho))})^\tau (\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma))^{1/p}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\tau = d + 2 + s$.

Proof. Set $B = B(0, \rho)$. Since $\Phi : B \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ is a parametrization of Σ , identifying by an abuse of notation $n(y) = n(\Phi(y))$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) &= c_{s,p} \int_{\Sigma} \left| \int_{\Sigma} \frac{|\langle x - y, n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d \right|^p d\mathcal{H}_x^d \\ &\geq \int_{\Phi(B)} \left| \int_{\Phi(B)} \frac{|\langle x - y, n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d \right|^p d\mathcal{H}_x^d \\ &= \int_B \left| \int_B \frac{|\langle \Phi(x) - \Phi(y), n(y) \rangle|}{|\Phi(x) - \Phi(y)|^{d+1+s}} \text{Jac}(\Phi(y)) d\mathcal{H}_y^d \right|^p \text{Jac}(\Phi(x)) d\mathcal{H}_x^d. \end{aligned}$$

Observe that

$$\text{Jac}(\Phi) \gtrsim 1,$$

and

$$|\Phi(x) - \Phi(y)| \leq \|D\Phi\|_{L^\infty(B)}|x - y| \lesssim (1 + \|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B)})|x - y|.$$

Thus we have

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \gtrsim (1 + \|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B)})^{-p(d+s+1)} \int_B \left| \int_B \frac{|\langle \Phi(x) - \Phi(y), n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d \right|^p d\mathcal{H}_x^d,$$

and hence

$$(10.3) \quad \int_B \left| \int_B \frac{|\langle \Phi(x) - \Phi(y), n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right|^p dx \lesssim (1 + \|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B)})^{p(d+s+1)} \mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma).$$

Since $\partial_\alpha \Phi(y) \perp n(y)$ we have

$$(10.4) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_B \left| \int_B \frac{|\langle \Phi(x) - \Phi(y), n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right|^p dx \\ &= \int_B \left| \int_B \frac{|\langle \Phi(x) - \Phi(y) - \partial_\alpha \Phi(y)(x - y)^\alpha, n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right|^p dx. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, since $\Phi(x) = (x, f(x))$, we have

$$(\Phi(x) - \Phi(y) - \partial_\alpha \Phi(y)(x - y)^\alpha)^i = (x - y)^i - (x - y)^i = 0, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, d\}.$$

Moreover

$$(10.5) \quad n(y) = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f(y)|^2}} \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f(y) \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and thus

$$(10.6) \quad \begin{aligned} & \langle \Phi(x) - \Phi(y) - \partial_\alpha \Phi(y)(x - y)^\alpha, n(y) \rangle \\ &= \mp \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f(y)|^2}} (\Phi(x) - \Phi(y) - \partial_\alpha \Phi(y)(x - y)^\alpha)^{d+1} \\ &= \mp \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f(y)|^2}} (f(x) - f(y) - \partial_\alpha f(y)(x - y)^\alpha). \end{aligned}$$

Combining (10.3), (10.4), and (10.6) we arrive at

$$\int_B \left| \int_B \frac{|(f(x) - f(y) - \partial_\alpha f(y)(x - y)^\alpha)|}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f(y)|^2} |x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right|^p dx \lesssim (1 + \|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B)})^{p(d+s+1)} \mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma)$$

and consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\int_B \left| \int_B \frac{|(f(x) - f(y) - \partial_\alpha f(y)(x - y)^\alpha)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \lesssim (1 + \|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B)})^{d+2+s} (\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma))^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 10.12. *Let $\Lambda > 0$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p > \frac{d}{s}$. Then there is a radius $R > 0$ depending only on Λ, d, s and p such that for all $0 < \rho < R$ the following holds: Let Σ be a closed smooth d -manifold, such that*

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \equiv c_{s,p} \int_\Sigma \left(\int_\Sigma \frac{|\langle x - y, n(y) \rangle|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} d\mathcal{H}_y^d \right)^p d\mathcal{H}_x^d \leq \Lambda^p.$$

Let us furthermore assume that for any $x_0 \in \Sigma$ there exists a rotation $P \in SO(N)$ and a smooth map

$$f : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

with $f(0) = 0, \nabla f(0) = 0$, and

$$\|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B(0,\rho))} \leq 1,$$

so that $x_0 + P(x, f(x))$ is a local parametrization of Σ , that is

$$\Phi(x) := x_0 + P(x, f(x))$$

is a diffeomorphism as a map $B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \Sigma$. Then,

$$\|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B(0,\rho))} \lesssim \Lambda \rho^{s-d/p} \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Proof. Let us assume without loss of generality that $x_0 = 0$. Lemma 10.11 tells us that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\int_{B(0,\rho)} \left(\int_{B(0,\rho)} \frac{|f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right)^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \lesssim (1 + \|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B(0,\rho))})^\sigma (\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma))^{1/p} \\ & \lesssim \Lambda. \end{aligned}$$

Let for simplicity $B = B(0, \rho)$. From Morrey-Sobolev embedding, Lemma 10.16, since $sp > d$ for $\sigma = s - \frac{d}{p}$

$$[Df]_{C^\sigma(B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho))} \lesssim_{s,p} \left(\int_B \left(\int_B \frac{|f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right)^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Since by assumption $Df(0) = 0$, this implies

$$\|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho))} \lesssim \rho^\sigma \left(\int_B \left(\int_B \frac{|f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right)^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

and hence

$$\|\nabla f\|_{L^\infty(B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho))} \lesssim \rho^\sigma \Lambda.$$

Using this, we can already achieve that the gradient of f is as small as we wish on the smaller ball $B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho)$.

To get control over the gradient of f on the complete ball $B(0, \rho)$, for a point $y \in B(0, \rho) \setminus B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho)$ we consider $x_1 = \frac{3\rho}{4} \cdot \frac{y}{\|y\|}$ on $\partial B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho)$. Then

$$|\nabla f(x_1)| \lesssim \rho^\sigma \Lambda.$$

Furthermore, we get using that the Lipschitz constant of f on B is bounded by one that

$$d_\Sigma((x_1, f(x_1)), (y, f(y))) \leq \frac{1}{4}\sqrt{2}\rho < \frac{3}{4}\rho,$$

where d_Σ denotes the distance along the surface Σ .

Our assumption applied to the point $\tilde{x}_0 = (x_1, f(x_1)) \in \Sigma$ now tells us that there exists a rotation $\tilde{P} \in SO(N)$ and a smooth map

$$\tilde{f} : B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

with $\tilde{f}(0) = 0, \nabla \tilde{f}(0) = 0$, and

$$\|\nabla \tilde{f}\|_{L^\infty(B(0, \rho))} \leq 1,$$

so that $\tilde{x}_0 + \tilde{P}(x, \tilde{f}(x))$ is a local parametrization of Σ , that is

$$\tilde{\Phi}(x) := \tilde{x}_0 + \tilde{P}(x, \tilde{f}(x))$$

is a diffeomorphism onto its image as a map $B(0, \rho) \rightarrow \Sigma$. As above we get that

$$\|\nabla \tilde{f}\|_{L^\infty(B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho))} \lesssim \rho^\sigma \Lambda$$

and since $d_\Sigma(\tilde{x}_0, (y, f(y))) < \frac{3}{4}\rho$ we get that

$$(y, f(y)) \in \tilde{\Phi}(B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho))$$

i.e. there is a point $\tilde{y} \in B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho)$ such that

$$(y, f(y)) = \tilde{x}_0 + \tilde{P}(\tilde{y}, \tilde{f}(\tilde{y})).$$

We will now deduce from this, that indeed

$$|\nabla f(y)| \lesssim \rho^\sigma \Lambda \leq R^\sigma \Lambda \leq \frac{1}{2}$$

whenever $R > 0$ is sufficiently small.

To this end let us denote by

$$P_x^T : \mathbb{R}^{d+1} \rightarrow T_x \Sigma, \quad P_x^\perp : \mathbb{R}^{d+1} \rightarrow N_x \Sigma$$

the orthogonal projection onto the tangent space $T_x \Sigma$ and the normal space $N_x \Sigma$ along Σ in the point $x \in \Sigma$ respectively.

We have

$$P_x^\perp(v) = \langle v, n \rangle n$$

where $n = n(x)$ denotes a unit normal and hence can be considered as a Lipschitz function from the unit vectors onto the set of orthogonal projection equipped with the operator norm . If Σ is the graph of a function g around the point we consider, we obtain a local Gauß-map setting

$$n = \frac{(\nabla g(x), -1)}{\sqrt{|\nabla g(x)|^2 + 1}},$$

i.e. the unit normal can be considered as a Lipschitz map of the gradient under the condition that the gradient is bounded by 1 as in our case.

Applying this first to f and the points 0 and x_1 and then to \tilde{f} and the points 0 and \tilde{y} we get

$$|P_0^\perp - P_{(y, f(y))}^\perp| \leq |P_0^\perp - P_{(x_1, f(x_1))}^\perp| + |P_{(x_1, f(x_1))}^\perp - P_{(y, f(y))}^\perp|$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\lesssim |\nabla f(0) - \nabla f(x_1)| + |\nabla \tilde{f}(0) - \nabla \tilde{f}(\tilde{y})| \\ &\lesssim \rho^\sigma \Lambda. \end{aligned}$$

But from this we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |f(x) - f(y)| &= |P_0^\perp(x - y, f(x) - f(y))| \\ &\leq |P_{(y, f(y))}^\perp(x - y, f(x) - f(y))| \\ &\quad + |P_{(y, f(y))}^\perp - P_0^\perp|(x - y, f(x) - f(y)). \end{aligned}$$

If we divide by $|x - y|$ let $x \rightarrow y$ and observe that then

$$P_{(y, f(y))}^\perp\left(\frac{1}{|x-y|}(x - y, f(x) - f(y))\right) \rightarrow 0,$$

we get

$$|\nabla f(y)| \lesssim \Lambda \rho^\sigma \sqrt{1 + |\nabla f(y)|^2} \leq \Lambda \rho^\sigma (1 + |\nabla f(y)|).$$

If R is small enough, this gives

$$|\nabla f(y)| \leq C \Lambda \rho^\sigma \leq C \Lambda R^\sigma \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

□

Proof of Theorem 10.8. We chose $\tilde{\rho}_0 > 0$ maximal with the property that for all $\rho < \tilde{\rho}_0$ the assumption of Lemma 10.12 are satisfied. Let us assume that $\tilde{\rho}_0 < R$ where again $R > 0$ is the radius obtained from Lemma 10.12. Keeping in mind that Σ is a compact C^1 -submanifold, the assumptions of Lemma 10.12 are then also satisfied for $\rho = \tilde{\rho}_0$.

Then the previous lemma implies that around all points $x_0 \in \Sigma$ we can write Σ up to translations and rotations as graphs of $C^{1,\sigma}$ -functions on $B(0, \tilde{\rho}_0)$ whose gradient is bounded by $\frac{1}{2}$. Since the submanifold Σ is C^1 and compact, and hence the unit normals are uniformly continuous, we can combine Lemma 10.10 with a continuity argument, to prove that $\tilde{\rho}_0 > 0$ was not maximal. □

10.3 Proof of Michael-Simon type inequality, Corollary 10.3

In view of the equivalence of $\mathcal{B}_{s,q}(\Sigma)$ and $\mathcal{W}_{s,q}(\Sigma)$ for convex Σ , Corollary 10.3 is a consequence of the following

Corollary 10.13 (Weak Michael-Simon type inequality). *Let $p > \frac{d}{s}$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $\Lambda > 0$, $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ and $q \in (1, \infty)$. Then there exists a constant $C = C(p, d, s, \alpha, q, \Lambda)$ such that the following holds.*

Let $\Sigma = \Sigma^d = \partial\Omega$ be the smooth boundary of a compact body in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} , such that

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda.$$

Then for any $f \in W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)$ with $q \in (1, \frac{d}{\alpha})$ we have

$$(10.7) \quad \|f\|_{L^{\frac{dq}{d-\alpha q}}(\Sigma)} \leq C ([f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}).$$

If $\alpha - \frac{d}{q} = \beta$ for some $\beta \in (0, \alpha)$ then

$$\|f\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma)} + [f]_{C^\beta(\Sigma)} \leq C ([f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}).$$

Proof of Corollary 10.13: Hölder case. Let $R \in (0, +\infty)$ be the Λ -dependent radius provided in Theorem 10.8. We can cover \mathbb{R}^{d+1} with dyadic cubes Q_i (with pairwise disjoint interior) and of sidelength $2^{-100}R$

$$\mathbb{R}^{d+1} = \bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} Q_i.$$

Denote B_j the ball with same center as Q_j and radius $2^{-50}R$. Observe that there is a fixed dimensional constant K such that any point in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} is contained in at most K balls B_j .

Subordinated to B_j we choose a partition of unity, $\eta_j \in C_c^\infty(B_j)$, $\sum_{j=1} \eta_j(\cdot) = 1$ everywhere in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} . Let $J := \{j \in \mathbb{Z} | Q_j \cap \Sigma \neq \emptyset\}$.

We have

$$\|f\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma)} \leq \max_{j \in J} \|f\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma \cap B_j)}$$

and

$$[f]_{C^\beta(\Sigma)} \lesssim_R \|f\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma)} + \max_j [f]_{C^\beta(\Sigma \cap B_j)}.$$

In view of Theorem 10.8 we obtain for each $j \in J$ a parametrization

$$\Phi_j : B(0, R) \subset \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \Sigma$$

as provided in the statement of Theorem 10.8, where $\Phi_j(B(0, R)) \supset B_j \cap \Sigma$, is a graph, and thus

$$|x - y| \lesssim |\Phi_j(x) - \Phi_j(y)|.$$

Thus, set $\beta := \alpha - \frac{d}{q}$ and

$$[\eta_j f]_{C^\beta(\Sigma \cap B_j)} \leq [(\eta_j f) \circ \Phi_j]_{C^\beta(B(0,R))},$$

and

$$\|(\eta_j f)\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma \cap B_j)} \leq \|(\eta_j f) \circ \Phi_j\|_{L^\infty(B(0,R))}.$$

By Sobolev embedding,

$$\|(\eta_j f)\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma \cap B_j)} + [\eta_j f]_{C^\beta(\Sigma \cap B_j)} \lesssim_R [f \circ \Phi_j]_{W^{\alpha,q}(B(0,R))} + \|f \circ \Phi_j\|_{L^q(B(0,R))}.$$

Since Φ_j are uniformly Lipschitz, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{L^\infty(\Sigma)} + [f]_{C^\beta(\Sigma)} &\lesssim \max_j [f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma \cap B_j)} + \max_j \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma \cap B_j)} \\ &\lesssim \max_j [f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} + \max_j \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)} \quad \square \\ &= [f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Corollary 10.13: Sobolev case. Fix Σ with $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda$.

Our aim is to show

$$\left(\int_\Sigma |f|^{q^*} \right)^{\frac{q}{q^*}} \lesssim_\Lambda [f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)}^q + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}^q.$$

with a constant independent of Σ .

With the same notation as in the previous proof, in view of Theorem 10.8 we obtain that for each for each $j \in J$ there exists a parametrization

$$\Phi_j : B(0, R) \rightarrow \Sigma$$

as provided in the statement of Theorem 10.8, where $\Phi_j(B(0, R)) \supset B_j \cap \Sigma$.

Since $\frac{q}{q^*} < 1$, we have $\ell^1(\mathbb{N}) \subset \ell^{\frac{q}{q^*}}(\mathbb{N})$ and we obtain

$$\left(\int_\Sigma |f|^{q^*} \right)^{\frac{q}{q^*}} \leq \left(\sum_j \int_{\Sigma \cap B_j} |f|^{q^*} \right)^{\frac{q}{q^*}} \leq \sum_{j \in J} \|f\|_{L^{q^*}(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q.$$

With the uniform parametrization $\Phi_j : B(0, R) \subset \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \Sigma$ we have

$$\|f\|_{L^{q^*}(\Sigma \cap B_j)} \lesssim_\Lambda \|f \circ \Phi_j\|_{L^{q^*}(\Phi_j^{-1}(B_j))}.$$

By Sobolev embedding, with a constant depending on $\text{diam } \Phi_j^{-1}(B_j)$ (which is controlled by Λ due to the bi-Lipschitz control of Φ_j)

$$\|f\|_{L^{q^*}(\Sigma \cap B_j)} \lesssim_{\Lambda} [f \circ \Phi_j]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Phi_j^{-1}(\Sigma \cap B_j))} + \|f \circ \Phi_j\|_{L^q(\Phi_j^{-1}(\Sigma \cap B_j))}.$$

Reverting the parametrization Φ_j we then have

$$\|f\|_{L^{q^*}(\Sigma \cap B_j)} \lesssim_{\Lambda} [f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma \cap B_j)} + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma \cap B_j)}$$

and thus

$$\|f\|_{L^{q^*}(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q \lesssim_{\Lambda} [f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q.$$

This implies

$$\left(\int_{\Sigma} |f|^{q^*} \right)^{\frac{q}{q^*}} \lesssim_{\Lambda} \sum_{j \in J} \left([f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q \right).$$

Since each point in \mathbb{R}^{d+1} is covered by a maximal number of balls B_j , say K (and K depends only on the dimension) we conclude

$$\sum_j \left([f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma \cap B_j)}^q \right) \leq K \left([f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)}^q + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}^q \right),$$

and hence

$$\left(\int_{\Sigma} |f|^{q^*} \right)^{\frac{q}{q^*}} \lesssim_{\Lambda} [f]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)}^q + \|f\|_{L^q(\Sigma)}^q.$$

This concludes the proof of Corollary 10.13. □

10.4 Stability for fractional curvature energies

The energy $\mathcal{B}_{s,p}$ vanishes precisely on planes. However, in analogy with the classical traceless second fundamental form of a surface Σ , it would also be desirable to have an energy which characterizes the sphere. Inspired by the observation that the linear map

$$T = A - \frac{1}{R} \text{id} = D \left(n(x) - \frac{1}{R} x \right), \quad R > 0$$

is zero precisely when Σ is umbilic and must be a sphere of radius R , we define the quantity

$$\|A - \frac{1}{R} \text{id}\|_{p,s,\Sigma}^p := c_{s,p} \int_{\Sigma} \int_{\Sigma} \frac{|(n(x) - \frac{1}{R}x) - (n(y) - \frac{1}{R}y)|^p}{|x - y|^{d+sp}} d\mathcal{H}_x^d d\mathcal{H}_y^d.$$

This vanishes precisely on spheres of radius R . The aim of this section is to obtain a stability version of this rigidity statement, based on our weak Michael-Simon type inequality. Therefore it suffices to consider the normal component of the quantity $n(x) - \frac{1}{R}x$, which is

$$1 - \frac{1}{R}u(x) := \langle n(x) - \frac{1}{R}x, n(x) \rangle.$$

We define R_0 to be the mean-value of u , which is positive due to the divergence theorem. Then we obtain the following stability result:

Theorem 10.14. *Let $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ be a closed hypersurface and suppose that for some $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p > \frac{d}{s}$ we have*

$$\mathcal{B}_{s,p}(\Sigma) + \text{diam}(\Sigma) \leq \Lambda.$$

Let $\alpha q > d$. Then for any $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta = \delta(\alpha, q, d, \varepsilon, \Lambda) > 0$ (otherwise independent of Σ) such that the following holds: If

$$[u]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} < R_0 \delta$$

then

$$\text{dist}(\Sigma, \mathbb{S}^d(R_0)) < \varepsilon,$$

where $\mathbb{S}^d(R_0)$ is a sphere of radius R_0 and where dist is the Hausdorff distance.

Proof. Apply our weak Michael-Simon type inequality, Corollary 10.13 to $R_0 - u$, then we have

$$[R_0 - u]_{C^{\alpha-\frac{d}{q}}(\Sigma)} \lesssim [R_0 - u]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)} + \|R_0 - u\|_{L^q(\Sigma)} \lesssim_{\Lambda} R_0 \delta,$$

and due to the Poincaré-Sobolev inequality,

$$\|R_0 - u\|_{L^q(\Sigma)} \lesssim (\mathcal{H}^d(\Sigma))^{-1} \text{diam}(\Sigma)^{\frac{d}{q}+\alpha} [u]_{W^{\alpha,q}(\Sigma)}.$$

Observe that we have control over $\mathcal{H}^d(\Sigma)$ in terms of Λ by Corollary 10.4.

We conclude that for sufficiently small δ , the support function satisfies

$$u(x) = \langle x, n(x) \rangle > 0$$

and hence Σ is starshaped around the origin and it may be parametrized over a sphere by the function $r: \mathbb{S}^d \rightarrow \Sigma$. Define

$$v^2 = 1 + r^{-2} |\nabla r|^2,$$

then

$$\langle x, n(x) \rangle = \frac{r}{v} \leq r$$

with equality precisely when $\nabla r = 0$. Hence

$$\min_{\mathbb{S}^d} \langle x, n(x) \rangle \leq \min_{\mathbb{S}^d} r, \quad \max_{\mathbb{S}^d} \langle x, n(x) \rangle = \max_{\mathbb{S}^d} r.$$

However, $\langle x, n(x) \rangle$ is $R_0\delta$ -close to R_0 and hence Σ lies within an annulus of size $R_0\delta$ around $\mathbb{S}^d(R_0)$. □

It is worth to compare this to a local result (i.e. a stability in terms of local curvature integrals) in the subcritical regime. In [DRG21, Theorem 1.3] it is proven that for $p > d$ a closed hypersurface $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ with normalized volume, a bound c_0 on $\|A\|_{L^p(\Sigma)}$ and small traceless second fundamental form $\|\mathring{A}\|_{L^p(\Sigma)}$ admits a parametrization

$$\psi(x) = e^{f(x)} x$$

over the unit sphere with the property

$$\|f\|_{W^{2,p}(\mathbb{S}^d)} \leq C \|\mathring{A}\|_{L^p(\Sigma)},$$

where C depends on d, p and c_0 . Our 10.14 gives a related result in the nonlocal setting.

10.5 Appendices

Some basic inequalities

Lemma 10.15. *Fix $\Lambda > 1$, $\Upsilon > 0$, $\alpha > 0$, $\sigma > 0$. Assume $\rho < \left(\frac{1}{2^\sigma \Lambda \Upsilon}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}$, then the following holds.*

Let $f : [0, \rho] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be any nonnegative continuous function with $f(0) = 0$ and such that

$$f(r) \leq \Lambda(1 + r^\alpha f(r))^\sigma \Upsilon \quad \forall r \in (0, \rho),$$

then $\sup_{r \in [0, \rho]} f(r) \leq 2^\sigma \Lambda \Upsilon$.

Proof. We use the method of continuity. Set

$$I := \{0 \leq r \leq \rho : f(r) \leq 2^\sigma \Lambda \Upsilon\}.$$

Clearly $0 \in I$ since $f(0) = 0$. If $r_k \in I$, $r = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} r_k$ then by continuity $f(r) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} f(r_k) \leq 2^\sigma \Lambda \Upsilon$. Lastly, if $r \in I$, then we have

$$f(r) \leq \Lambda(1 + r^\alpha f(r))^\sigma \Upsilon \leq \Lambda(1 + r^\alpha 2^\sigma \Lambda \Upsilon)^\sigma \Upsilon,$$

and since $r \leq \rho$ we find

$$f(r) \leq \Lambda(1 + 1)^\sigma \Upsilon < 2^\sigma \Lambda \Upsilon.$$

Thus, by continuity we have $f(\tilde{r}) < 2\Lambda\Upsilon$ for all $\tilde{r} \approx r$.

□

Lemma 10.16 (Morrey-Sobolev embedding). *Assume $s > \frac{d}{p}$. Then there exists $C = C(s, p, d)$ such that,*

$$[Df]_{C^{s-\frac{d}{p}}(B(0, \frac{3}{4}\rho))} \leq C \left(\int_{B(0, \rho)} \left(\int_{B(0, \rho)} \frac{|f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right)^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Proof. By scaling we may assume that $\rho = 1$. Set

$$\Lambda := \left(\int_{B(0,1)} \left(\int_{B(0,1)} \frac{|f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy \right)^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Now, for every ball $B(x_0, r)$ we denote by

$$A_{x_0, r} := B(x_0, r) \cap B(0, 1).$$

Then, by Hölder's inequality we observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{A_{x_0, r}} \int_{A_{x_0, r}} \frac{|f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+1+s}} dy dx \\ \leq |A_{x_0, r}|^{1-\frac{1}{p}} \Lambda \lesssim_d r^{d(1-\frac{1}{p})} \Lambda. \end{aligned}$$

Also, using the triangular inequality we obtain that

$$|(Df(x) - Df(y))(x - y)| \leq |f(x) - f(y) - Df(y)(x - y)| + |f(y) - f(x) - Df(x)(y - x)|$$

and hence by Fubini's Theorem,

$$\int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \frac{|(Df(x) - Df(y))(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{d+s+1}} dy dx \lesssim_d r^{d(1-\frac{1}{p})} \Lambda.$$

Thus

$$\int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |(Df(x) - Df(y)) \frac{x - y}{|x - y|}| dy dx \lesssim_d r^{d+s} r^{d(1-\frac{1}{p})} \Lambda.$$

Now consider

$$\begin{aligned} & |f(x) + f(y) - 2f(\frac{x+y}{2})| \\ (10.8) \quad & \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 |\langle \nabla f(\frac{x+y}{2} + t\frac{x-y}{2}) - \nabla f(\frac{x+y}{2} - t\frac{x-y}{2}), x - y \rangle| dt \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 |\langle \nabla f(\frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y) - \nabla f(\frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y), x - y \rangle| dt. \end{aligned}$$

Now we observe that for $t \geq \frac{1}{2}$, substituting $\tilde{x} := \frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y$, $\tilde{y} := \frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y$ and observing that then $dx \approx d\tilde{x}$, $dy \approx d\tilde{y}$ and $|x - y| \approx |\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}|$ (all since $t \geq \frac{1}{2}$) and using the convexity of $A_{x_0,r}$

$$\begin{aligned} (10.9) \quad & \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(\frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y) - \nabla f(\frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y), x - y \rangle| dx dy \\ & \lesssim r \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(\tilde{x}) - \nabla f(\tilde{y}), \frac{\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}}{|\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}|} \rangle| d\tilde{x} d\tilde{y} \\ & \lesssim \Lambda r^{2d+1+s-\frac{d}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

If on the other hand $t \leq \frac{1}{2}$ we decompose

$$\begin{aligned} (10.10) \quad & \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(\frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y) - \nabla f(\frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y), x - y \rangle| dx dy \\ & \leq \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(\frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y) - \nabla f(x), x - y \rangle| dx dy \\ & \quad + \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(y) - \nabla f(\frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y), x - y \rangle| dx dy \\ & \quad + \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(x) - \nabla f(y), x - y \rangle| dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

In the first term on the right-hand side of (10.10) we substitute $\tilde{y} := \frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y$, observe that $\tilde{y} - x$ is parallel to $x - y$ and $|\tilde{y} - x| \approx |x - y|$ and that $d\tilde{y} \approx dy$ to obtain

$$\int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(\frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y) - \nabla f(x), x - y \rangle| dx dy \lesssim \Lambda r^{2d+1+s-\frac{d}{p}}.$$

For the second term on the right-hand side of (10.10) we substitute $\tilde{x} := \frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y$, observe that $\tilde{x} - y$ is parallel to $x - y$ with comparable norm, and thus

$$\int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(y) - \nabla f(\frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y), x - y \rangle| dx dy \lesssim \Lambda r^{2d+1+s-\frac{d}{p}}.$$

Thus, (10.10) becomes

$$(10.11) \quad \int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\langle \nabla f(\frac{1+t}{2}x + \frac{1-t}{2}y) - \nabla f(\frac{1-t}{2}x + \frac{1+t}{2}y), x - y \rangle| dx dy \lesssim \Lambda r^{2d+1+s-\frac{d}{p}}.$$

Using (10.8), (10.9) and (10.10) we arrive at

$$\int_{A_{x_0,r}} \int_{A_{x_0,r}} |\frac{1}{2}f(x) + \frac{1}{2}f(y) - f(\frac{x+y}{2})| dy dx \leq C \Lambda r^{2d+1+s-\frac{d}{p}}.$$

For a.e. $x_0, y_0 \in B(0, 1)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |f(x_0) + f(y_0) - f(\frac{x_0 + y_0}{2})| \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B(0,2^{-k})} \int_{B(0,2^{-k})} |f(x_0 + z_1) + f(y_0 + z_2) - 2f(\frac{x_0 + z_1 + y_0 + z_2}{2})| dz_1 dz_2 \end{aligned}$$

So if we set

$$a_k := \int_{B(0,2^{-k})} \int_{B(0,2^{-k})} |f(x_0 + z_1) + f(y_0 + z_2) - 2f(\frac{x_0 + z_1 + y_0 + z_2}{2})| dz_1 dz_2$$

we have

$$|f(x_0) + f(y_0) - 2f(\frac{x_0 + y_0}{2})| = a_K + \sum_{k=K+1}^{\infty} (a_k - a_{k-1}) \lesssim \sum_{k=K}^{\infty} a_k.$$

But (observe the mean value!) when $x_0 \in B(0, 1)$ and K is large enough, we have

$$a_k \lesssim \Lambda(2^{-k})^{1+s-\frac{d}{p}}$$

so

$$\sum_{k=K}^{\infty} a_k \lesssim \Lambda(2^{-K})^{1+s-\frac{d}{p}}.$$

So if we choose $2^{-K} \approx \min\{|x_0 - y_0|, \text{dist}(x_0, \partial B(0, 1)), \text{dist}(y_0, \partial B(0, 1))\}$ then we have shown

$$|f(x_0) + f(y_0) - 2f\left(\frac{x_0 + y_0}{2}\right)| \lesssim \Lambda|x_0 - y_0|^{1+s-\frac{d}{p}},$$

whenever $|x_0 - y_0| < \text{dist}(y_0, \partial B(0, 1)), \text{dist}(x_0, \partial B(0, 1))$.

In other words we have

$$|f(x_0 + h) + f(x_0 - h) - 2f(x_0)| \lesssim \Lambda|h|^{1+s-\frac{d}{p}} \quad \forall |h| < \text{dist}(x_0, \partial B).$$

From here one can show by elementary means that Df is Hoelder continuous with exponent $s - d/p$.

□

CONVEX MINIMIZING CURVES OF THE SCALING-INVARIANT WILLMORE ENERGY

We consider the scaling-invariant nonlocal Willmore energy, defined via the nonlocal mean curvature by Caffarelli, Roquejoffre and Savin. Our main result is the existence of minimizers in the class of convex C^1 -curves.

11.1 Introduction and main results

Given a subset $E \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ the nonlocal mean curvature at $x \in \partial E$ introduced by Caffarelli, Roquejoffre and Savin in [CRS10] is defined as

$$H_{\partial E}^s(x) := \text{P.V.} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \equiv \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_\varepsilon(x)} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy,$$

whenever that limit exists, e.g. in the case of smooth ∂E . The fractional mean curvature is obtained as the first variation of the fractional perimeter, just like the classical mean curvature is the first variation of the usual perimeter (or area) functional.

Having a nonlocal mean curvature, we can naturally define a nonlocal Willmore energy: For $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \geq 1$ we set

$$\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s,p}(\partial E) := \int_{\partial E} |H_{\partial E}^s(x)|^p d\sigma^1(x).$$

This energy is well-defined on measurable sets E for which $H_{\partial E}^s(x)$ exists for a.e. $x \in \partial E$ – for all other measurable sets we set $\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s,p}(\partial E) := +\infty$. Also, observe that it does not matter if we consider E or E^c , the nonlocal Willmore energy stays the same.

If we parametrize a suitably nice set ∂E by a curve $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} H_{\partial E}^s(x) &= \pm c_s \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} |\gamma'(y)| dy \\ &\equiv \pm c_s \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(y - x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} |\gamma'(y)| dy. \end{aligned}$$

Here, for $z \in \partial E$ the vector $n(z) \in \mathbb{S}^1$ denotes the unit normal, and the sign of $H_{\partial E}^s$ depends on whether it is the outwards facing or inwards facing normal (or, in other words, if we consider E or E^c). Observe that if γ is smooth, then the last integral in the equality above is absolutely convergent.

This leads to a nonlocal Willmore energy for curves $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$,

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) = \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} |\gamma'(y)| dy \right|^p |\gamma'(x)| dx,$$

and in the smooth setting we have

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) = c_{s,p} \hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s,p}(E).$$

In Chapter 10, we discussed some aspects of the *subcritical* nonlocal Willmore energy, i.e. when $s > \frac{1}{p}$. In this work we are interested in the critical case, which corresponds to $p = \frac{1}{s}$, when the nonlocal Willmore energy becomes scaling invariant. Scaling invariance means: If for some $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\rho > 0$ we consider the rescaled curve $\gamma_\rho(\cdot) := \rho\gamma(\frac{\cdot}{\rho}) : \rho\mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, then we have

$$\mathcal{W}_{s,\frac{1}{s}}(\gamma) = \mathcal{W}_{s,\frac{1}{s}}(\gamma_\rho).$$

For simplicity of notation we shall denote from now on

$$\mathcal{W}_s(\gamma) = \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} |\gamma'(y)| dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} |\gamma'(x)| dx,$$

It is obvious that nonlocal minimal surfaces, i.e. surfaces with vanishing fractional mean curvature $H_s \equiv 0$, are absolute minimizers of the nonlocal Willmore

energy – but in general a curve or surface which is critical for the Willmore-energy is not necessarily a minimal surface (in the sense of vanishing mean curvature). For example there are no compact nonlocal minimal surfaces [Cir+18; Cab+18]. While nonlocal minimal and constant mean curvature surfaces have been studied very thoroughly, for an overview see e.g. [DV16; DV22], the theory of nonlocal Willmore surfaces is only at the very beginning. Similar to recent results on nonlocal minimal surfaces [Cha+23; CFS23] one could hope that eventually one can transfer properties for s -Willmore surfaces to classical Willmore surfaces by letting $s \rightarrow 1$.

Regarding the existence of minimizers, scaling invariant variational functionals are prone to bubbling effects, and the existence of minimizers becomes a nontrivial question. The classical example is the Sacks-Uhlenbeck theory for harmonic maps in homotopy groups, [SU81]. But also in the theory of classical Willmore surfaces [Sim86; KS12; Riv16] existence of minimizers is a highly nontrivial question.

In this work we are interested in minimizing *convex* curves, w.l.o.g. they are in arc length parametrization, more precisely we consider the class

$$(11.1) \quad X := \left\{ \gamma \in C^1(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2) \left| \begin{array}{l} \gamma \text{ is a homeomorphism} \\ |\gamma'| \equiv 1 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{S}^1 \\ \gamma \text{ is convex in } \mathbb{S}^1 \end{array} \right. \right\}.$$

The main result of this chapter is the following:

Theorem 11.1. *For any $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists a minimizer of \mathcal{W}_s in X .*

In Chapter 10 we obtained an analogous result for C^1 -convex curves for the *subcritical* case $p > \frac{1}{s}$. There, the arguments crucially rely on the non-scaling invariance of the subcritical regime. In our critical regime we need completely different techniques, more similar to the minimizing methods used for Willmore's energy for surfaces (which is also scaling invariant).

The nonlocal Willmore energy is only defined on co-dimension one objects, since the nonlocal perimeter is only defined on those sets (albeit, see [MS23]). In particular, we can reformulate our result for sets E whose boundary are represented by

curves γ . Let

$$C := \left\{ E \subset \mathbb{R}^2 \left| \begin{array}{l} E \text{ is convex and bounded} \\ \partial E \text{ is } C^1 \\ E \text{ has nonempty interior} \end{array} \right. \right\}.$$

Then we have

Theorem 11.2. *For any $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists a minimizer of $\widehat{\mathcal{W}}_{s, \frac{1}{s}}$ in C .*

Strategy and Outline

Our arguments are substantially inspired by the relation between nonlocal Willmore energy and the tangent-point energies, studied first by Buck and Orloff [BO95], Gonzalez and Maddocks [GM99], and Blatt and Reiter [BR15]. Tangent-point energies are just one class of topological knot or surface energies, and thus related to the Möbius energy [O'H91; FHW94], the O'Hara energies [O'H92; O'H94; BRS22], and Menger curvature energies [SSM09; Meu18; Goe21; GG20]. Indeed, our arguments draw substantial inspiration from the corresponding existence argument for minimizers of the tangent-point energy, [Bla+24]. There are, however, substantial technical differences that we need to overcome. One is the sign of the mean curvature H_s , which for general curves could be changing – we remedy this by working only with convex curves, an unsatisfying but for now seemingly unavoidable assumption (cf. also [CCC23]). Another one is the change of underlying Sobolev space, which creates surprising technical difficulties. The basic idea is as follows:

- We first show that the Willmore energy controls the BMO-norm of γ' in a locally quantifiable way, Proposition 11.12.
- Then we establish that local BMO-control suffices to obtain (quantifiably) local control of the BiLipschitz constant of the curve, Lemma 11.15. This in turn gives quantitative control of the graphical behavior of γ , Lemma 11.16.
- On sets where we are graphs, we can use convexity to obtain a control in the sharp Sobolev space $W_2^{1+s, \frac{1}{s}}$ Theorem 11.17.

- Having Sobolev control allows us to pass to the limit for sequences. We then show that *qualitatively* any convex curve with finite Willmore energy is actually C^1 (a fact, probably interesting on its own), Theorem 11.24.
- Those are the main ingredients that are needed to obtain reflexivity, lower semicontinuity in the class of convex homeomorphisms, which we carry out in Theorem 11.30

11.2 Preliminaries and Notation

For a vector $v = (v_1, v_2)^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$ we denote its rotation by $-\frac{\pi}{2}$

$$v^\perp = (v_2, -v_1)^T.$$

We also use the notation

$$R_\theta v$$

for counterclockwise rotation by θ . For two nonnegative quantities A, B we write $A \lesssim B$ if there exists a multiplicative constant C such that $A \leq C B$, and write $A \approx B$ if $A \lesssim B$ and $B \lesssim A$. Special dependencies in such inequalities are denoted by subscript, but essentially all constants depend on s .

Sobolev spaces

Our argument relies on a suitable Sobolev control. It turns out, that the “usual” Gagliardo-Slobokdeckij space seems not to be the right space to work with – instead we work with the Bessel potential space. However, for localization purposes it is beneficial to keep a seminorm similar to the Gagliardo seminorm.

Definition 11.3. For $I \subset \mathbb{R}$, the Sobolev space $W_2^{s,p}(I)$ is defined in the usual way via its semi-norm,

$$[f]_{W_2^{s,p}(I)} := \left(\int_I \left(\int_I \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2s}} dy \right)^{\frac{p}{2}} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

The main reason we are interested in using this space is the following identification, which is due to Stein [Ste61, Theorem 1], for the general versions we refer to [PS17; Wan23]. To state the result, we adopt the notation

$$|D|^s f := (-\Delta)^{\frac{s}{2}} f.$$

Here, $(-\Delta)^{\frac{s}{2}}$ denotes the usual fractional Laplacian, cf. [DNPV12].

Theorem 11.4. *Assume that $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (\frac{2}{1+2s}, \infty)$, then*

$$[f]_{W_2^{s,p}(\mathbb{R})} \approx \| |D|^s f \|_{L^p(\mathbb{R})}.$$

In particular, for any $s \in (0, 1)$

$$[f]_{W_2^{s,\frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R})} \approx \| |D|^s f \|_{L^{\frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R}^n)}.$$

We are interested in local estimates, and for this will need a Sobolev-type inequality on a ball. Towards this, we first observe the following Poincaré type inequality.

Lemma 11.5. *For $0 < t < 1$ we have for the interval $B = (-1, 1)$ and any $f \in L^2(B)$*

$$\left(\int_B \int_B |f(x) - f(y)|^{\frac{1}{t}} dx dy \right)^t + \left(\int_B \int_B |f(x) - f(y)|^2 dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \lesssim [f]_{W_2^{t,\frac{1}{t}}(B)}$$

In particular, if $\int_B f = 0$ we have

$$\|f\|_{L^{\frac{1}{t}}(B)} + \|f\|_{L^2(B)} \lesssim [f]_{W_2^{t,\frac{1}{t}}(B)}.$$

Proof. The inequality

$$(11.2) \quad \left(\int_B \int_B |f(x) - f(y)|^{\frac{1}{t}} dx dy \right)^t \lesssim [f]_{W_2^{t,\frac{1}{t}}(B)}$$

is a consequence of Hölder's inequality. Indeed, denote by $(f)_B := |B|^{-1} \int f$, then, since $t \in (0, 1)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\int_B \int_B |f(x) - f(y)|^{\frac{1}{t}} dx dy \right)^t &\leq 2 \left(\int_B \int_B |f(x) - (f)_B|^{\frac{1}{t}} dx dy \right)^t \\ &= C \left(\int_B |f(x) - (f)_B|^{\frac{1}{t}} dx \right)^t \\ &\lesssim \left(\int_B \left(\int_B |f(x) - f(z)| dz \right)^{\frac{1}{t}} dx \right)^t \\ &\lesssim \left(\int_B \left(\int_B |f(x) - f(z)|^2 dz \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \right)^t \\ &\lesssim [f]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(B)}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves (11.2).

The inequality

$$(11.3) \quad \left(\int_B \int_B |f(x) - f(y)|^2 dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \lesssim [f]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(B)}$$

follows from (11.2) and Hölder's inequality if $\frac{1}{t} \geq 2$. So from now on we will focus on proving (11.3) under the condition

$$(11.4) \quad \frac{1}{t} \leq 2.$$

We argue by contradiction. Assume (11.3) is not true for any constant in \lesssim . Then there exists a sequence of counterexamples $f_k \in L^2(B)$ such that

$$\left(\int_B \int_B |f_k(x) - f_k(y)|^2 dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} > k [f_k]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(B)}.$$

Both sides do not change if we replace f_k by $f_k - (f_k)_B$, where $(f_k)_B := \frac{1}{2} \int_B f_k$, so w.l.o.g. we may assume

$$(11.5) \quad (f_k)_B = 0 \quad \text{for all } k.$$

Dividing both sides by $\left(\int_B \int_B |f_k(x) - f_k(y)|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ we may also assume that for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\left(\int_B \int_B |f_k(x) - f_k(y)|^2 dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 1$$

and

$$(11.6) \quad [f_k]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(B)} \leq \frac{1}{k}.$$

The first equality, combined with the assumption $(f)_B = 0$ implies in particular

$$(11.7) \quad \frac{1}{2} \leq \|f_k\|_{L^2(B)} \leq 1.$$

Fix $\eta \in C_c^\infty((-5/4, 5/4))$, $\eta \equiv 1$ in $(-1, 1)$, and set

$$g_k := \eta \tilde{f}_k,$$

where

$$\tilde{f}_k(x) := \begin{cases} f_k(-2-x) & x \in (-2, -1) \\ f_k(x) & x \in (-1, 1) \\ f_k(2-x) & x \in (1, 2). \end{cases}$$

We see that

$$(11.8) \quad \sup_k \|g_k\|_{L^2(\mathbb{R})} \lesssim \sup_k \|\tilde{f}_k\|_{L^2((-2,2))} \lesssim \sup_k \|f_k\|_{L^2((-1,1))} \leq 1.$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|g_k(x) - g_k(y)|^2}{|x-y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{(-3/2, 3/2)} \left(\int_{(-3/2, 3/2)} \frac{|g_k(x) - g_k(y)|^2}{|x-y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \quad + \int_{\mathbb{R} \setminus (-3/2, 3/2)} \left(\int_{(-5/4, 5/4)} \frac{|g_k(y)|^2}{(1+|x|)^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \quad + \int_{(-5/4, 5/4)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R} \setminus (-3/2, 3/2)} \frac{|g_k(x)|^2}{(1+|y|)^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \approx \int_{(-3/2, 3/2)} \left(\int_{(-3/2, 3/2)} \frac{|g_k(x) - g_k(y)|^2}{|x-y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{(-5/4, 5/4)} |g_k(y)|^2 dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} \\ & \quad + \int_{(-5/4, 5/4)} |g_k(x)|^{\frac{1}{t}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{(-3/2, 3/2)} \left(\int_{(-3/2, 3/2)} \frac{|g_k(x) - g_k(y)|^2}{|x-y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx + \|g_k\|_{L^2(\mathbb{R})}^{\frac{1}{t}}. \end{aligned}$$

In the last inequality we used (11.4).

Next we use the discrete product rule

$$\eta(x)\tilde{f}_k(x) - \eta(y)\tilde{f}_k(y) = \eta(y) \left(\tilde{f}_k(x) - \tilde{f}_k(y) \right) + (\eta(x) - \eta(y))\tilde{f}_k(x)$$

to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \left(\int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \frac{|g_k(x) - g_k(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \left(\int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \frac{|\tilde{f}_k(x) - \tilde{f}_k(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \quad + \int_{(-3/2,3/2)} |\tilde{f}_k(x)|^{\frac{1}{t}} \left(\int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \frac{|x - y|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \left(\int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \frac{|\tilde{f}_k(x) - \tilde{f}_k(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx + \|\tilde{f}_k\|_{L^2((-3/2,3/2))} \end{aligned}$$

where in the last inequality we used $t < 1$ and (11.4). Next, by substitution and our choice of reflection we find

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \left(\int_{(-3/2,3/2)} \frac{|\tilde{f}_k(x) - \tilde{f}_k(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{(-1,1)} \left(\int_{(-1,1)} \frac{|f_k(x) - f_k(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{1+2t}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{2t}} dx. \end{aligned}$$

In summary, we have shown

$$\sup_k \|g_k\|_{L^2(\mathbb{R})} + [g_k]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(\mathbb{R})} < +\infty.$$

By Theorem 11.4 and Rellich-Kondrachov theorem we find a subsequence (not re-labelled) such that $g_k \xrightarrow{k \rightarrow \infty} g$ strongly in $L^2_{loc}(\mathbb{R})$. Since $f_k = g_k$ in $(-1, 1)$ we conclude that for $f := g|_{(-1,1)}$ we have in view of (11.7)

$$\|f\|_{L^2((-1,1))} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|g_k\|_{L^2((-1,1))} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|f_k\|_{L^2((-1,1))} \geq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Moreover, by strong L^2 -convergence and (11.5)

$$(f)_B = 0.$$

On the other hand, by Fatou's lemma and (11.6) we have

$$[f]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}((-1,1))} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} [f_k]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}((-1,1))} = 0,$$

thus $f \equiv \text{const}$ – since $(f)_B = 0$ we conclude $f \equiv 0$ contradicting $\|f\|_{L^2(-1,1)} \geq \frac{1}{2}$. This proves (11.3) under the assumption (11.4). We can conclude. \square

Lemma 11.6 (Sobolev inequality). *For $0 < s < t < 1$ we have for any interval $B \subset \mathbb{R}$*

$$[f]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(B)} \lesssim_{s,t} [f]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(B)}.$$

Proof. From Theorem 11.4 (observe that $\frac{1}{s} > \frac{2}{1+2s}$ is always satisfied) and the Sobolev embedding theorem

$$(11.9) \quad [f]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R})} \approx \| |D|^s f \|_{L^{\frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R})} \lesssim \| |D|^t f \|_{L^{\frac{1}{t}}(\mathbb{R})} \approx [f]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(\mathbb{R})}.$$

Now, if $f : B \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we can assume by scaling w.l.o.g. $B = (-1, 1)$. By invariance under additive constants we also assume

$$(11.10) \quad (f)_B = 0.$$

Set

$$\tilde{f}(x) := \begin{cases} f(-2-x) & x \in (-2, -1) \\ f(x) & x \in (-1, 1) \\ f(2-x) & x \in (1, 2). \end{cases}$$

Then, for every $\eta \in C_c^\infty((-3/2, 3/2))$, $\eta \equiv 1$ in $(-1, 1)$, using (11.9) we have

$$[f]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}((-1,1))} \leq [\eta \tilde{f}]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R})} \lesssim [\eta \tilde{f}]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(\mathbb{R})}.$$

In the proof of Lemma 11.5 we already estimated that

$$[\eta \tilde{f}]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(\mathbb{R})} \lesssim [f]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(B)} + \|f\|_{L^{\frac{1}{t}}(B)} + \|f\|_{L^2(B)}.$$

Since we have (11.10), the statement of Lemma 11.5 implies

$$[f]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}((-1,1))} \lesssim [\eta \tilde{f}]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(\mathbb{R})} \lesssim [f]_{W_2^{t, \frac{1}{t}}(B)}.$$

We can conclude. \square

We also record the following important potential formula for the fractional Laplacian. It is most likely well-known to experts, but we give the argument for completeness.

Lemma 11.7. *Let $f \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R})$. Then for each $s \in (0, 1)$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}$ it holds that*

$$(11.11) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f(x) - f(y) - f'(y)(x - y)}{|x - y|^{1+s+1}} dy = C_s(-\Delta)^{\frac{s+1}{2}} f(x),$$

for some C_s depending only on s .

Proof. We notice that

$$\begin{aligned} Tf(x) &:= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f(x) - f(y) - f'(y)(x - y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f(x) - f(x+h) + f'(x+h)(h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f(x) - f(x+h) + f'(x+h)(h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f(x) - f(x-h) + f'(x-h)(-h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h) + f'(x+h)(h) - f'(x-h)(h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h) + \partial_h f(x+h)(h) + \partial_h f(x-h)(h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h) + \partial_h (f(x+h) + f(x-h))(h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\partial_h (2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h))(h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh. \end{aligned}$$

Integrating by parts and observing that

$$\partial_h \frac{h}{|h|^{2+s}} = \frac{|h|^{2+s} - h(2+s)|h|^{1+s} \frac{h}{|h|}}{|h|^{4+2s}} = -(1+s) \frac{1}{|h|^{2+s}},$$

we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
& Tf(x) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h) - \partial_h(2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h))(h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h) - (1+s)(2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h))}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\
&= \frac{1-(1+s)}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{2f(x) - f(x+h) - f(x-h)}{|h|^{2+s}} dh \\
&= \frac{1-(1+s)}{2} c_{d,s}(-\Delta)^{\frac{s+1}{2}} f(x).
\end{aligned}$$

□

The fractional mean curvature

While it is irrelevant for most calculation-based analysis, for convenience and geometric arguments we shall assume that whenever possible, curves are parametrized counter-clockwise,

(11.12) γ is a counter clockwise parametrization of its image,

For some interval $I \subset \mathbb{R}$ and $\gamma \in Lip(I, \mathbb{R}^2)$, for $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \geq 1$, we define the s, p -nonlocal Willmore energy of γ as

$$\mathscr{W}_{s,p}(\gamma|_I) = \left(\int_I \left(\int_I \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} |\gamma'(y)| dy \right)^p |\gamma'(x)| dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}},$$

where $n(\gamma(y))$ is a.e. a unit normal to the curve γ at $\gamma(y)$. We remind the reader of our abuse of notation by writing $\mathscr{W}_s := \mathscr{W}_{s, \frac{1}{s}}$. Under the assumption (11.12) for a.e. $y \in I$ we define fix the direction of the vectorfield $n(\gamma(y))$ as

$$n(\gamma(y)) := \gamma'(y)^\perp.$$

We define

$$\tilde{X} := \left\{ \gamma \in Lip(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2) \left| \begin{array}{l} \gamma \text{ is a homeomorphism} \\ |\gamma'| \equiv 1 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{S}^1 \\ \gamma \text{ is convex in } \mathbb{S}^1 \\ \gamma \text{ satisfies (11.12) in } \mathbb{S}^1 \end{array} \right. \right\}.$$

Clearly X in (11.1) is a subset of \tilde{X} – up to inverting the orientation so that (11.12) holds.

For every $\gamma \in \tilde{X}$ the s, p -nonlocal Willmore energy takes the form

$$(11.13) \quad \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) := \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} \right)^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

In the definitions of X and \tilde{X} we assumed convexity, the following is the precise definition we are going to use.

Definition 11.8 (convexity). Let $\gamma : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ be continuous. Given some subset $A \subset I$, we say that γ is convex in A if

$$(11.14) \quad \begin{aligned} &\text{for all } x \in A \text{ there exists } \nu_x \in \mathbb{S}^1 \text{ such that} \\ &\nu_x \cdot (\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)) \geq 0 \text{ for all } y \in A. \end{aligned}$$

It is worth pointing out that for every $\gamma \in \tilde{X}$ and for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{S}^1$ one has that ν_x satisfying the inequality in (11.14) is unique, and actually $\nu_x = n(\gamma(x))$, see for instance Corollary 11.39. In particular for convex curves we have

$$\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{a.e. } x, y \in I$$

Our analysis in this chapter relies on a relation between curves with finite Willmore energy and curves that belong to the Sobolev space $W_2^{1+s, \frac{1}{s}}$. One direction is the following Lemma.

Lemma 11.9. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ be a BiLipschitz homeomorphism with $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{S}^1 and such that*

$$[\gamma']_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1)} < +\infty.$$

Then, it holds that

$$\mathcal{W}_s(\gamma) = \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s < +\infty.$$

Let us stress two things: We will not really use the previous lemma in our analysis, obtaining a quantitative converse of Lemma 11.9 is the main challenge of the present chapter – see Section 11.4. Secondly, the assumption that γ is a homeomorphism is not needed, certain crossings and figure-eight shapes are permissible, this will be investigated more in future work.

Proof. Since $\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(y) \rangle = 0$ a.e. we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle \\ &= \langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(y - x) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since γ is a BiLipschitz homeomorphism we also have $|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)| \approx |x - y|$.

Then, we first observe that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)) - n(\gamma(x)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(y - x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} \right| dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{|\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(x)| |\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Using the fundamental theorem of calculus, we obtain

$$|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)| \leq |x - y| \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(z) - \gamma'(y)| dz.$$

By Hölder's inequality we then find

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)) - n(\gamma(x)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(y - x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} \right| dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ & \lesssim [\gamma]_{W_2^{\frac{s}{2}, \frac{2}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1)}^2 \\ & \lesssim [\gamma']_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1)}^2. \end{aligned}$$

In the last line we use Sobolev embedding Lemma 11.6.

Thus, in order to show $\mathscr{W}_s(\gamma) < \infty$ we exchange $n(\gamma(y))$ with $n(\gamma(x))$ and simply need to show

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(x)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Next, we observe (see e.g. [BRS16; Bla+24] and references within)

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 - \frac{|x - y|^2}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^2} \\ &= \frac{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^2 - |x - y|^2}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^2} \\ &= \frac{\int_{[x,y]} \int_{[x,y]} \gamma'(z_1) \cdot \gamma'(z_2) - 1 \, dz_1 \, dz_2}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^2} \\ &= \frac{\int_{[x,y]} \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(z_1) - \gamma'(z_2)|^2 \, dz_1 \, dz_2}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^2}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$\left| 1 - \frac{|x - y|^2}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^2} \right| \approx \int_{[x,y]} \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(z_1) - \gamma'(z_2)|^2 \, dz_1 \, dz_2.$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} \, dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} \, dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} \, dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} \, dx + [\gamma']^3_{W_2^{\frac{3}{s}, \frac{3}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1)} \\ & \lesssim \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} \, dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} \, dx + [\gamma']^3_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1)}, \end{aligned}$$

where in the last line we used again the Sobolev embedding Lemma 11.6. We now conclude by using Lemma 11.7, which – after a stereographic projection to the sphere implies

$$\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} \, dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} \, dx \lesssim \| |D|^{s+1} \gamma \|_{L^{\frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1)} \approx [\gamma']_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1)},$$

where in the last inequality we used Stein’s theorem, Theorem 11.4. □

The maximum principle for the nonlocal mean curvature

The maximum principle for nonlocal mean curvature is well known and will play a crucial role in our argument.

Proposition 11.10 (Maximum Principle for the nonlocal mean curvature). *Let $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be measurable and $s \in (0, 1)$. Moreover, we assume that $A \subset B$ and there exists some point $z \in \partial A \cap \partial B$.*

If $H_A^s(z)$ and $H_B^s(z)$ exist, then we have

$$(11.15) \quad H_A^s(z) \geq H_B^s(z).$$

Furthermore, if B is convex it holds that

$$(11.16) \quad H_B^s(z) \geq 0.$$

for any z where $H_B^s(z)$ exists.

Proof. According to the hypothesis we have that

$$B^c \subset A^c.$$

Therefore, for each $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we have that

$$\chi_{A^c}(y) - \chi_A(y) \geq \chi_{B^c}(y) - \chi_B(y).$$

From this equation we evince that for each $\varepsilon > 0$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\varepsilon(z)} \frac{\chi_{A^c}(y) - \chi_A(y)}{|z - y|^{n+s}} dy \geq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\varepsilon(z)} \frac{\chi_{B^c}(y) - \chi_B(y)}{|z - y|^{n+s}} dy.$$

Taking the limit with respect to $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ in both sides we conclude the proof of (11.15), since we assume that this limit exists.

Since B is convex, for each $z \in \partial B$ there exists an half plane π_z such that

$$B \subset \pi_z.$$

Therefore, applying (11.15) we obtain that

$$H_B^s(z) \geq H_{\pi_z}^s(z) = 0. \quad \square$$

In the following proposition we establish sufficient conditions for the boundary parametrization of a set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ in order to rewrite the nonlocal mean curvature as a surface integral. We stress that this result is not sharp and that it is possible to determine more general conditions on the regularity of a set for such identity to hold. The proof of Proposition 11.11 is in Appendix 11.8.

Proposition 11.11. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, $\gamma \in Lip(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ be a homeomorphism such that $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{S}^1 and γ satisfies the convexity assumption (11.14) in \mathbb{S}^1 . Then, if we denote $E := co(\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1))$, for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{S}^1$ it holds that*

$$(11.17) \quad H_{\partial E}^s(\gamma(x)) = \frac{2}{s} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy,$$

where $n(\gamma(y)) := \gamma'(y)^\perp$.

11.3 Small energy controls BMO-parametrization

The main result of this section is the fact that when the Willmore energy is suitably small, then the *BMO*-norm of the derivative of the parametrization γ is dominated by the Willmore energy. More precisely, we have the following:

Proposition 11.12. *For any $p \in [1, \infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists a uniform $\varepsilon > 0$ such that the following holds:*

Assume that $\gamma \in C^1(B_{R_0}, \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ satisfies (where $n(\gamma(x)) = \gamma'(x)^\perp$)

$$(11.18) \quad \int_{B_{R_0}} \left(\int_{B_{R_0}} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < \varepsilon.$$

Then, for all $B_r(x_0) \subset B_{R_0}$

$$(11.19) \quad \left(\int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^p dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \lesssim_p \left(\int_{B_{R_0}} \left(\int_{B_{R_0}} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s.$$

Let us point out a subtlety in Proposition 11.12. There is no convexity assumption. However, only if γ is a convex curve $\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle$ has a sign, and the absolute value inside the integral can be ignored – that is for convex curves (11.18) is indeed the Willmore energy restricted to a ball.

In order to prove Proposition 11.12, we need the following local John-Nirenberg type result, see [GM12, Corollary 6.22].

Lemma 11.13. *For any $u \in L^\infty(B_1)$ and any $p \in [1, \infty)$ we have*

$$(11.20) \quad \sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_1} \left(\int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |u(x) - u(y)|^p dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ \lesssim_p \sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_1} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |u(x) - u(y)| dx dy,$$

whenever the right-hand side is finite.

Lastly we need a certain mean valued estimate for double integrals.

Lemma 11.14. *For any $p > 1$*

$$\int_{B(x_0, r)} \int_{B(x_0, r)} \int_{[x, y]} |U(y, z)| dz dx dy \lesssim_p \left(\int_{B(x_0, r)} \int_{B(x_0, r)} |U(x, y)|^p dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Proof. By translation and scaling, w.l.o.g. $x_0 = 0$ and $r = 1$, i.e. we need to show

$$\int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{[x, y]} |U(y, z)| dz dx dy \lesssim_p \left(\int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 |U(x, y)|^p dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{[x, y]} |U(y, z)| dz dx dy \\ &= \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y \int_{-1}^z \frac{1}{y-x} |U(y, z)| dx dz dy + \int_{-1}^1 \int_y^1 \int_z^1 \frac{1}{x-y} |U(y, z)| dx dz dy \\ &= \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y |U(y, z)| \log \left(\frac{|1+y|}{|z-y|} \right) dz dy + \int_{-1}^1 \int_y^1 \log \left(\frac{|1-y|}{|z-y|} \right) |U(y, z)| dz dy \\ &\leq \left(\int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 |U(y, z)|^p dz dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y \left(\log \left(\frac{|1+y|}{|z-y|} \right) \right)^{p'} dz dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p'}} \\ &\quad + \left(\int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 |U(y, z)|^p dz dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{-1}^1 \int_y^1 \left(\log \left(\frac{|1-y|}{|z-y|} \right) \right)^{p'} dz dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p'}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we use that for any $\gamma > 0$ there exists $C(\gamma)$ such that

$$|\log a| \leq C(\gamma) (a^\gamma + a^{-\gamma}) \quad \forall a \in (0, \infty).$$

Thus, we have for some small $\delta < 1$ (and a suitable choice of γ)

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y \left(\log \left(\frac{y+1}{|z-y|} \right) \right)^{p'} dz dy \\ & \lesssim \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y \frac{(y+1)^\delta}{|y-z|^\delta} dz dy + \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y \frac{|y-z|^\delta}{(y+1)^\delta} dz dy \\ & \leq 2^\delta \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y |y-z|^{-\delta} dz dy + 2^\delta \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^y (y+1)^{-\delta} dz dy \\ & = 2^\delta \int_{-1}^1 \frac{1}{1-\delta} (y+1)^{1-\delta} dy + 2^\delta \int_{-1}^1 (y+1)^{1-\delta} dy \\ & = C(\delta). \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, it holds that

$$\int_{-1}^1 \int_y^1 \left(\log \left(\frac{|1-y|}{|z-y|} \right) \right)^{p'} dz dy \lesssim C^*(\delta).$$

We can conclude. □

Proof of Proposition 11.12. Since $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ we have

$$\langle \gamma'(x), \gamma'(x) - \gamma'(z) \rangle = \frac{1}{2} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(z)|^2.$$

With the fundamental theorem of calculus we then have

$$\langle \gamma'(y), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x-y) \rangle = \int_y^x \langle \gamma'(y), \gamma'(z) - \gamma'(y) \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \int_y^x |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^2.$$

Using this and the fact that $n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(y)$ forms an orthonormal basis of \mathbb{R}^2 ,

$$\begin{aligned}
& |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| \\
&= \frac{|\gamma'(x)(x-y) - \gamma'(y)(x-y)|}{|x-y|} \\
&\leq \frac{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(y-x)|}{|x-y|} + \frac{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(x)(x-y)|}{|x-y|} \\
&\lesssim \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x-y) \rangle|}{|x-y|} + \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(x)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(x)(y-x) \rangle|}{|x-y|} \\
&\quad + \frac{|\langle \gamma'(y), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x-y) \rangle|}{|x-y|} + \frac{|\langle \gamma'(x), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(x)(y-x) \rangle|}{|x-y|} \\
&\lesssim \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x-y) \rangle|}{|x-y|} + \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(x)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(x)(y-x) \rangle|}{|x-y|} \\
&\quad + \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 dz + \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(z) - \gamma'(x)|^2 dz \\
&= \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|x-y|} + \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(x)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle|}{|x-y|} \\
&\quad + \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 dz + \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(z) - \gamma'(x)|^2 dz.
\end{aligned}$$

We now observe that whenever $B_r(x_0) \subset B_R$ (we use that $r \gtrsim |x-y| \geq |\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|$ since $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|x-y|} dx dy \\
&\lesssim r^{1+s} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy dx \\
&= r^{s-1} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy dx \\
&\lesssim \left(\int_{B_r(x_0)} \left(\int_{B_r(x_0)} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s \\
&\lesssim \left(\int_{B_R} \left(\int_{B_R} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s
\end{aligned}$$

and similarly, using Fubini's Theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(x)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle|}{|x - y|} dx dy \\ & \lesssim \left(\int_{B_R} \left(\int_{B_R} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, by Lemma 11.14, for any $p > 1$

$$\int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 dz dx dy \lesssim \left(\int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^{2p} dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Combining the above estimates we find

$$\begin{aligned} & \sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_1} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy \\ (11.21) \quad & \lesssim \sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_1} \left(\int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^{2p} dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & + \left(\int_{B_R} \left(\int_{B_R} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Lemma 11.13 we find

$$\begin{aligned} & \sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_1} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy \\ (11.22) \quad & \lesssim \sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_1} \left(\int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy \right)^2 \\ & + \left(\int_{B_R} \left(\int_{B_R} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s. \end{aligned}$$

Now set

$$F(R) := \sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_R} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy.$$

Then (11.22) becomes

$$(11.23) \quad F(R) \leq CF(R)^2 + \left(\int_{B_R} \left(\int_{B_R} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s.$$

As for properties of $F(R)$, it is clearly increasing function. Moreover, since $\gamma \in C^1$ we have

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow 0} F(R) = 0.$$

Lastly, $R \mapsto F(R)$ is continuous: Fix any $\varepsilon > 0$ and $R > 0$. Since γ' is continuous, there exists an r_1 such that we have $\int_{B_r(x)} \int_{B_r(x)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy < \frac{\varepsilon}{4}$ whenever $r \in (0, r_1)$ and $x \in B_{2R}$. So if $|R - R'| \leq \frac{r_1}{100}$ and $B_r(x_0) \subset B_R$ with $r \geq r_1$ then we can find $\tilde{x}_0 \in B_{R'}$ and \tilde{r} with $B_{\tilde{r}}(\tilde{x}_0) \subset B_{R'}$ such that

$$|\tilde{x}_0 - x_0| \lesssim_{r_1} |R - R'|, \quad \text{and} \quad |r - \tilde{r}| \lesssim_{r_1} |R - R'|.$$

The same holds if $B_r(x_0) \subset B_{R'}$ and $r \geq r'$ then we find a ball $B_{\tilde{r}}(\tilde{x}_0) \subset B_R$ with the above estimates. So if we choose $|R - R'| \ll 1$, we have in these cases by continuity of γ'

$$\left| \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy - \int_{B_{\tilde{r}}(\tilde{x}_0)} \int_{B_{\tilde{r}}(\tilde{x}_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy \right| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{4}.$$

Thus,

$$|F(R) - F(R')| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{4} + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} + \frac{\varepsilon}{4} < \varepsilon.$$

These properties combined with (11.23) and a continuity argument imply that there is some $\delta > 0$ (depending on C) such that if

$$\left(\int_{B_R} \left(\int_{B_R} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s < \delta$$

then

$$F(R) \leq C_2 \left(\int_{B_R} \left(\int_{B_R} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s.$$

This, combined with Lemma 11.13, implies (11.19). □

Consequence of VMO-control: BiLipschitz-control and graph

Lemma 11.15 (BiLipschitz control). *For any $\delta > 0$ there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that the following holds:*

Assume that $\gamma \in Lip(B_{R_0}, \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. and it satisfies

$$\sup_{B_r(x_0) \subset B_{R_0}} \int_{B_r(x_0)} \int_{B_r(x_0)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)| dx dy < \varepsilon_0.$$

Then, it holds that

$$1 - \delta \leq \frac{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|}{|x - y|} \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } x, y \in B_{R_0}.$$

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} |\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^2 - |x - y|^2 &= \int_x^y \int_x^y (\langle \gamma'(z_1), \gamma'(z_2) \rangle - 1) \, dz_1 \, dz_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_x^y \int_x^y |\gamma'(z_1) - \gamma'(z_2)|^2 \, dz_1 \, dz_2. \end{aligned}$$

In view of Lemma 11.13 and the assumption we then have

$$\left| \frac{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^2}{|x - y|^2} - 1 \right| \leq \frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}.$$

This readily implies the claim. □

Lemma 11.16. *Assume that $\gamma \in C^1(B_{R_0}, \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ and γ is a convex curve in the sense of (11.14). Then, for each $\tau \in B_{\frac{R_0}{4}}$ there exists some $\delta \in (0, 1)$ such that if*

$$(11.24) \quad 1 - \delta \leq \frac{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|}{|x - y|} \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } x, y \in B_{R_0},$$

then

$$(11.25) \quad \gamma \left(B_{\frac{R_0}{4}}(\tau) \right) \quad \text{is a graph over } \{t\gamma'(\tau) + \gamma(\tau) \mid t \in \mathbb{R}\},$$

which is either convex or concave.

Proof. The proof below is based on ideas by S. Blatt, [Bla23].

First, we prove that for every τ as in the statement $\gamma \left(B_{\frac{R_0}{4}}(\tau) \right)$ is a graph. To do so, we proceed by contradiction and assume that there exists some $\tau \in B_{\frac{R_0}{4}}$ such that $\gamma \left(B_{\frac{R_0}{4}}(\tau) \right)$ is not a graph over $\{t\gamma'(\tau) + \gamma(\tau) \mid t \in \mathbb{R}\}$.

Now, up to translations and rotations of γ we can assume that

$$\gamma'(\tau) = (1, 0)^T \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma(\tau) = 0.$$

Also, as consequence of this and Lemma 11.31, we obtain that either $\gamma_2(t) \geq 0$ or $\gamma_2(t) \leq 0$ for all $t \in B_{R_0}$. Without loss of generality we assume that

$$(11.26) \quad \gamma_2(t) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in B_{R_0}.$$

Since, by assumption, γ is not a graph on $B(x_0, R)$ there must be some $x_0 \in B_{\frac{R_0}{4}}(\tau)$ such that $\gamma'(x_0) = (0, 1)^T$ and $\gamma_1(x_0) > 0$ (if $x_0 > \tau$) or $\gamma'(x_0) = (0, -1)^T$ and $\gamma_1(x_0) < 0$ (if $x_0 < \tau$).

We only consider the case $x_0 > \tau$ and $\gamma'(x_0) = (0, 1)^T$, the proof of the other case is analogous. Moreover, without loss of generality we assume that $\tau < 0$.

Then, since $\gamma(\tau) = 0$ and $|\gamma'| = 1$ we obtain that

$$|\gamma(t)| \leq |t - \tau|,$$

from which we evince that

$$\gamma(B_{R_0}) \subset [\tau - R_0, R_0 - \tau]^2.$$

Also, it follows from (11.26) that

$$\gamma(B_{R_0}) \subset [\tau - R_0, R_0 - \tau] \times [0, R_0 - \tau].$$

Now, if ν_{x_0} is given as in (11.14), then as a consequence of Lemma 11.31 we have that ν_{x_0} is uniquely defined and either $\nu_{x_0} = (1, 0)^T$ or $\nu_{x_0} = (-1, 0)^T$. Then, applying (11.14) in x_0 we obtain

$$0 \leq \langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(\tau) \rangle = \langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma(x_0) \rangle,$$

from which it follows that $\nu_{x_0} = n(\gamma(x_0)) = (1, 0)^T$. Making use of this and (11.14) a second time we obtain for all $t \in B_{R_0}$

$$\left\langle \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(t) \right\rangle \geq 0$$

which gives that

$$(11.27) \quad \gamma_1(t) \leq \gamma_1(x_0) \quad \text{for all } t \in B_{R_0}.$$

Furthermore, using $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ and $\gamma(\tau) = 0$, we evince

$$\gamma_1(x_0) < \frac{R_0}{4}.$$

From this and (11.27) we obtain

$$\gamma(B_{R_0}) \subset \left[\tau - R_0, \frac{R_0}{4} \right] \times [0, R_0 - \tau].$$

In particular, we can compute that

$$\begin{aligned} |\gamma(-R_0) - \gamma(R_0)| &\leq \text{diam} \left(\left[\tau - R_0, \frac{R_0}{4} \right] \times [0, R_0 - \tau] \right) \\ &= \left| (\tau - R_0, 0) - \left(\frac{R_0}{4}, R_0 - \tau \right) \right| \\ &= \left| \left(\tau - R_0 - \frac{R_0}{4}, \tau - R_0 \right) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{7}{4} R_0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if we pick $\delta < 1 - \frac{7}{8}$, we obtain that

$$\frac{|\gamma(-R_0) - \gamma(R_0)|}{2R_0} \leq \frac{7}{8} < 1 - \delta.$$

This contradicts (11.24) and we conclude that $\gamma \left(B_{\frac{R_0}{4}}(\tau) \right)$ is a graph over $\{t\gamma'(\tau) + \gamma(\tau) \mid t \in \mathbb{R}\}$. The convexity or concavity of such graph follows immediately from Proposition 11.37. \square

11.4 Sobolev control

The goal of this section is to obtain local Sobolev control for curves with small Willmore energy. More precisely, in Theorem 11.17 we state that if a convex curve γ has small energy in some ball B , then the energy controls a suitable Sobolev seminorm of γ' in some ball $B' \subset B$. The precise statement goes as follows:

Theorem 11.17. *For any $s \in (0, 1)$ there exists $\varepsilon = \varepsilon(s) > 0$ such that the following holds:*

Assume that for $R > 0$ we have a curve $\gamma \in C^1(B_{20R}, \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ satisfies (where $n(\gamma(x)) = \gamma'(x)^\perp$)

$$(11.28) \quad \int_{-20R}^{20R} \left(\int_{-20R}^{20R} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < \varepsilon.$$

Assume also that γ is convex in the sense of Definition 11.8 in B_{20R} .

Then, it holds that

$$(11.29) \quad [\gamma']_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(B_R)} \lesssim_s \int_{-10R}^{10R} \left(\int_{-10R}^{10R} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx.$$

The first observation to prove Theorem 11.17 is that under the assumption that γ is locally a graph (or the weaker assumptions, that the derivatives γ' do not make a full turn) we have a pointwise control of corresponding second order difference quotient.

Lemma 11.18. *Assume that $\gamma \in \text{Lip}(B_R, \mathbb{R}^2)$ with $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in B_R . If*

$$\sup_{z_1, z_2 \in B_R} |\gamma'(z_1) - \gamma'(z_2)| = c < 2,$$

then for almost every $x, y \in B_R$ we have

$$\int_{[x,y]} |\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(z) \rangle| dz \gtrsim_c |\gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)|.$$

Proof. We have by Pythagoras' Theorem

$$|\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 = |\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z) \rangle|^2 + |\langle \gamma'(y), \gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z) \rangle|^2.$$

Now $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ implies

$$|\langle \gamma'(y), \gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z) \rangle|^2 = \frac{1}{4} |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^4.$$

Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z) \rangle|^2 &= |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 - \frac{1}{4} |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^4 \\ &= |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{4} |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 \right) \\ &\geq |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)|^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{4} c^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by the fundamental theorem we obtain that

$$\int_{[x,y]} |\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(z) \rangle| dz \gtrsim_c \int_{[x,y]} |\gamma'(y) - \gamma'(z)| \gtrsim |\gamma(y) - \gamma(x) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)|. \quad \square$$

On the other hand, we have also the following result.

Lemma 11.19. *Assume that $\gamma \in C^1(B_R)$ with $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$. Also, assume that γ is the graph of a convex function. Then, for every $x, y \in B_R$ we have*

$$\int_{[x,y]} |\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(z) \rangle| dz = \langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle.$$

Proof. Indeed, being γ the graph of a convex function f , we have that

$$\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(z) \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(x))^2} \sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(y))^2}} (f'(\gamma_1(y)) - f'(\gamma_1(z))) \geq 0,$$

since f' is non decreasing and $\gamma_1(y) > \gamma_1(z)$ for every $z \in (x, y)$.

That is, if $x \leq z \leq y$ then

$$\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(z) \rangle \geq 0$$

and if $y \leq z \leq x$ then

$$\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma'(z) \rangle \leq 0.$$

In both cases the claim follows from the fundamental theorem of calculus. □

Proof of Theorem 11.17. W.l.o.g. $R = 1$. Taking ε small enough in (11.28) we obtain from Proposition 11.12 combined with Lemma 11.16 and Lemma 11.15 that γ is a convex graph, and BiLipschitz on B_5 .

Thus, we can apply Lemma 11.18 and Lemma 11.19 to obtain

$$|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)| \lesssim \langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle.$$

Integrating this, and using that $|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)| \leq |x - y|$ we conclude

$$(11.30) \quad \int_{[-5,5]} \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \frac{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \lesssim \int_{[-5,5]} \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx.$$

Now, pick the usual bump function $\eta \in C_c^\infty(B(0, 3))$, $\eta \equiv 1$ in $B(0, 2)$. We set

$$\tilde{\gamma}(x) := \eta(x)(\gamma(x) - q(x)) + q(x) \equiv \eta(x)\bar{\gamma}(x) + q(x),$$

where $\bar{\gamma} := \gamma - q$ and $q(x) = q_1 + x q_2$ is an affine map which essentially corresponds to zero-th and first moment of γ . More precisely,

$$q_1 := \int_{(-2,2)} \gamma(z) dz, \quad q_2 := \int_{(-2,2)} \gamma'(z) dz.$$

We notice that

$$\int_{(-2,2)} q(x) dx = \int_{(-2,2)} \gamma(x) dx \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{(-2,2)} q'(x) dx = \int_{(-2,2)} \gamma'(x) dx.$$

By the discrete product rule

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x - y) \\ &= \eta(x)\bar{\gamma}(x) - \eta(y)\bar{\gamma}(y) - (\eta\bar{\gamma})'(y)(x - y) \\ &= \eta(x)(\bar{\gamma}(x) - \bar{\gamma}(y) - \bar{\gamma}'(y)(x - y)) \\ & \quad + (\eta(x) - \eta(y) - \eta'(y)(x - y))\bar{\gamma}(y) \\ & \quad + (\eta(x) - \eta(y))\bar{\gamma}'(y)(x - y). \end{aligned}$$

Since q is affine, we have

$$\gamma(x) - \gamma(y) - \gamma'(y)(x - y) = \bar{\gamma}(x) - \bar{\gamma}(y) - \bar{\gamma}'(y)(x - y).$$

With these observations, (11.30) readily implies

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{[-5,5]} \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \frac{\eta(x)|\bar{\gamma}(x) - \bar{\gamma}(y) - \bar{\gamma}'(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{[-5,5]} \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Also, we have for $x \in [-5, 5]$, for any $p \in (1, \infty)$ with $p' < \frac{1}{s}$, using Hölder's inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{[-5,5]} \frac{|\eta(x) - \eta(y)| |\bar{\gamma}'(y)|}{|x - y|^{1+s}} dy & \lesssim \int_{[-5,5]} |\gamma'(y) - q'(y)| |x - y|^{-s} dy \\ & \lesssim \left(\int_{[-5,5]} |\gamma'(y) - q'(y)|^p dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \frac{|(\eta(x) - \eta(y)) \bar{\gamma}'(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s \\ & \lesssim \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^p dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we have for $x \in [-5, 5]$, for any $p \in (1, \infty)$ with $p' < \frac{1}{s}$ (observe that $(\bar{\gamma}(y))_{[-5,5]} = 0$)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \int_{[-5,5]} \frac{(\eta(x) - \eta(y) - \eta'(y)(x - y))\bar{\gamma}(y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \right| \\
& \lesssim \int_{[-5,5]} |x - y|^{-s} |\bar{\gamma}(y)| dy \\
& = \int_{[-5,5]} |x - y|^{-s} |\bar{\gamma}(y) - (\bar{\gamma}(y))_{[-5,5]}| dy \\
& \leq \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} |x - y|^{-s} |\bar{\gamma}(y) - \bar{\gamma}(z)| dz dy \\
& \leq \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[y,z]} |x - y|^{-s} |\bar{\gamma}'(z_2)| dz_2 dz dy \\
& = \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[y,z]} |x - y|^{-s} |\bar{\gamma}'(z_2) - (\bar{\gamma}')_{[-5,5]}| dz_2 dz dy \\
& \leq \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} |x - y|^{-s} |\gamma'(z_2) - \gamma'(z_3)| dz_3 dz_2 dz dy \\
& \lesssim \int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} |\gamma'(z_2) - \gamma'(z_3)| dz_3 dz_2.
\end{aligned}$$

So that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \left| \int_{[-5,5]} \frac{(\eta(x) - \eta(y) - \eta'(y)(x - y))\bar{\gamma}(y)}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \right|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s \\
& \lesssim \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \int_{[-5,5]} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^p dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.
\end{aligned}$$

In conclusion, using also (11.19),

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{[-5,5]} \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \frac{|\tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x - y)|}{|x - y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\
& \lesssim \int_{[-5,5]} \left(\int_{[-5,5]} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx.
\end{aligned}$$

The claim now follows from the following proposition, Proposition 11.20, and again (11.19). \square

Proposition 11.20. *Let $\gamma : [-4, 4] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ and set for $\eta \in C_c^\infty([-3, 3])$, $\eta \equiv 1$ in $[-2, 2]$,*

$$\tilde{\gamma}(x) := \eta(x)(\gamma(x) - q(x)) + q(x) \equiv \eta(x)\bar{\gamma}(x) + q(x),$$

where $\bar{\gamma} := \gamma - q$, $q(x) := q_1 + x q_2$ and

$$q_1 := \int_{(-2,2)} \gamma(z) dz, \quad q_2 := \int_{(-2,2)} \gamma'(z) dz.$$

Assume that

$$\Gamma := \int_{(-4,4)} \left(\int_{(-4,4)} \frac{|\tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x-y)|}{|x-y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < +\infty.$$

Then, for some $q \geq 1$

$$[\gamma']_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}((-1,1))} \lesssim \Gamma^s + \left(\int_{(-4,4)} \int_{(-4,4)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^q dx dy \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

Proof. Thanks to Poincaré inequality, for $1 \leq p < +\infty$ we evince that

$$(11.31) \quad \|\bar{\gamma}\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} = \|\gamma - q\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} \lesssim \|\gamma' - q'\|_{L^p(B(0,2))}.$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$(11.32) \quad \begin{aligned} \|\tilde{\gamma}' - q'\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} &\leq \|\eta'(\gamma - q)\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} + \|\eta(\gamma' - q')\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} \\ &\lesssim \|\gamma - q\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} + \|\gamma' - q'\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} \\ &\lesssim \|\gamma' - q'\|_{L^p(B(0,2))} \\ &\lesssim \left(\int_{(-2,2)} \int_{(-2,2)} |\gamma'(z) - \gamma'(y)|^p dz dy \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to the support of η (and the fact that q is affine) we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{(-4,4)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x-y)|}{|x-y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ &\lesssim \int_{(-4,4)} \left(\int_{(-4,4)} \frac{|\tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x-y)|}{|x-y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ &\quad + \int_{(-3,3)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R} \setminus (-4,4)} \frac{|\tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x-y)|}{|x-y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx. \end{aligned}$$

We see that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{(-3,3)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R} \setminus (-4,4)} \frac{|\tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x-y)|}{|x-y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ &= \int_{(-3,3)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R} \setminus (-4,4)} \frac{|\eta(x)\tilde{\gamma}(x)|}{|x-y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ &= \int_{(-3,3)} |\tilde{\gamma}(x)|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \\ &\stackrel{(11.31)}{\lesssim} \int_{(-4,4)} \int_{(-4,4)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

Now we have by the representation formula of the fractional Laplacian, Lemma 11.7

$$\| |D|^{s+1}(\eta\tilde{\gamma}) \|_{L^{\frac{1}{s}}(-4,4)} \lesssim \left(\int_{(-4,4)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{|\tilde{\gamma}(x) - \tilde{\gamma}(y) - \tilde{\gamma}'(y)(x-y)|}{|x-y|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx \right)^s.$$

By Stein’s theorem, Theorem 11.4,

$$[\eta\tilde{\gamma}]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R})} \lesssim \| |D|^{s+1}(\eta\tilde{\gamma}) \|_{L^{\frac{1}{s}}(-4,4)} + \| |D|^{s+1}(\eta\tilde{\gamma}) \|_{L^{\frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R} \setminus (-4,4))}.$$

Using the distance between $\text{supp } \eta$ and $\mathbb{R} \setminus (-4, 4)$, see, e.g., [BRS16, Lemma A.1], we find

$$\| |D|^{s+1}(\eta\tilde{\gamma}) \|_{L^{\frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R} \setminus (-4,4))} \lesssim \|\eta\tilde{\gamma}\|_{L^1(\mathbb{R})} \stackrel{(11.31)}{\lesssim} \int_{(-4,4)} \int_{(-4,4)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx dy.$$

Thus, we have shown

$$[\tilde{\gamma}]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}((-1,1))} \leq [\eta\tilde{\gamma}]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{R})} \lesssim \Gamma^s + \left(\int_{(-4,4)} |\gamma'(x) - \gamma'(y)|^{\frac{1}{s}} dx dy \right)^s. \quad \square$$

11.5 Self-repulsiveness of Willmore energy for convex curves

Strongly inspired by results of Strzelecki-von der Mosel [SM12], as adapted to the tangent point energy [Bla+24, Theorem 4.9.] we obtain the following statement, which states that points with locally small energy do not collide with any other points.

Theorem 11.21. *There exists $\delta > 0$ such that the following holds.*

Let $\gamma \in C^1(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ be a homeomorphism, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$. Also, assume

$$(11.33) \quad \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{B_\rho(x_0)} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle|}{|\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < \delta.$$

If for any $z_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ we have

$$|\gamma(x_0) - \gamma(z_0)| < \frac{1}{10}\rho,$$

then there exists $\bar{x} \in B_\rho(x_0)$ such that $\gamma(\bar{x}) = \gamma(z_0)$. In particular, we have $z_0 \in B_\rho(x_0)$.

This result is a consequence of the following Lemma (see [Bla+24, Lemma 4.8] which is an adaptation of [SM12, Lemma 2.1, Lemma 2.3]).

We omit the proofs which are almost verbatim to [Bla+24, Lemma 4.8] and [Bla+24, Theorem 4.9].

Lemma 11.22 (Strzelecki-von der Mosel). *Let $s \in (0, 1)$. For any $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists δ such that the following holds.*

Let $\gamma \in Lip(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$, and assume that for some $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ and $\rho > 0$ we have

$$(11.34) \quad \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{B_\rho(x_0)} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle|}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < \delta.$$

Moreover, assume that there is $y_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ with $d := |\gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y_0)| \leq \rho$.

Then

$$(11.35) \quad \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1) \cap B_{2d}(\gamma(x_0)) \subset L_{\varepsilon d}(\gamma(x_0), \gamma(y_0)),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} L(\gamma(x_0), \gamma(y_0)) &:= \{(1-t)\gamma(x_0) + t\gamma(y_0) \mid t \in [0, 1]\} \quad \text{and} \\ L_{\varepsilon d}(\gamma(x_0), \gamma(y_0)) &:= \{p \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \text{dist}(p, L(\gamma(x_0), \gamma(y_0))) < \varepsilon d\}. \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence, see [SM12, Remark after Lemma 2.3 and Theorem 1.4] we have the following result.

Proposition 11.23 (Strzelecki-von der Mosel). *Let $s \in (0, 1)$. Assume $\gamma \in \text{Lip}(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{S}^1 .*

If

$$\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{|\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle|}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < +\infty$$

and if γ is convex in the sense of Definition 11.8 and has finite Willmore energy, then $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$ is a topological one-manifold.

11.6 Convex curves with finite energy are continuously differentiable

In this section we prove that all *convex* Lipschitz curves with finite $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$ -energy are actually C^1 if $s \geq \frac{1}{p}$ – a fact that is interesting on its own. We also believe it holds in higher dimensions, but we will not pursue this here any further.

The precise statement goes as follows:

Theorem 11.24. *Assume γ belongs to the set*

$$\gamma \in \tilde{X} := \left\{ \gamma \in \text{Lip}(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2) \left| \begin{array}{l} \gamma \text{ is a homeomorphism} \\ |\gamma'| \equiv 1 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{S}^1 \\ \gamma \text{ is convex in } \mathbb{S}^1 \end{array} \right. \right\}.$$

If for some $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \geq \frac{1}{s}$ we have finite energy,

$$(11.36) \quad \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) < +\infty,$$

then $\gamma \in C^1$.

Let us stress that convexity is absolutely crucial in the assumption of Theorem 11.24 – as evinced by Lemma 11.9.

Of course, Theorem 11.24 can be formulated for sets:

Theorem 11.25. *Let E be a bounded and convex set with nonempty interior. If for some $s \in (0, 1)$ and some $p \geq \frac{1}{s}$ it holds*

$$\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{s,p}(E) < +\infty,$$

then ∂E is C^1 .

In the proof below observe that the C^1 -control is purely qualitative, and we get no estimate whatsoever. This means in particular that when we consider minimizing sequences, we do not seem to get any uniform C^1 -control.

It is also worth pointing out that this result is false in the supercritical regime (namely $p < 1/s$): then it is possible to construct an example of a homeomorphism $\gamma \in Lip(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ that is a parametrization of the boundary of a convex set, which has finite $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}$ energy, but it is not C^1 . Cf. Remark 11.29.

To prove Theorem 11.24 we will first need the following preliminary results.

Lemma 11.26. *Let $\gamma \in Lip(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ be a homeomorphism satisfying the convexity assumption (11.14) in \mathbb{S}^1 and such that $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{S}^1 . Then, if $\gamma \notin C^1(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ there exists some $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ and $v \neq w \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that*

$$\langle v, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(x) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle w, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(x) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

Proof. Assume to the contrary that for all $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$

$$(11.37) \quad \text{there exists a unique } \nu_{x_0} \in \mathbb{S}^1 \text{ such that } \langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(x) \rangle \geq 0$$

for all $x \in \mathbb{S}^1$.

Set $v(x_0) := \nu_{x_0}$. We claim that

$$(11.38) \quad v \in C(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{S}^1).$$

If this was not the case, by compactness of the target \mathbb{S}^1 , there must exist some $v_1 \neq v_2 \in \mathbb{S}^1$, a point $t_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$, and two sequences $t_n, \tilde{t}_n \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that $t_n, \tilde{t}_n \rightarrow t_0$, but

$$\lim_n v(t_n) = v_1 \neq v_2 = \lim_n v(\tilde{t}_n).$$

According to (11.37)

$$\langle v_{t_n}, \gamma(t_n) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle v_{\tilde{t}_n}, \gamma(\tilde{t}_n) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

Taking the limit for $n \rightarrow +\infty$ and using continuity of γ , we find

$$\langle v_1, \gamma(t_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle v_2, \gamma(t_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in \mathbb{S}^1,$$

with $v_1 \neq v_2$. This is in contradiction to the uniqueness of ν_{t_0} in (11.37).

That is, if (11.37) was true, then (11.38) is true. However, up to replacing $\gamma(\cdot)$ with $\gamma(-\cdot)$, for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{S}^1$ we have that

$$\gamma'(x)^\perp = \nu(x),$$

see Corollary 11.39. This means that γ' coincides with a continuous function a.e. and therefore, it is continuous – if (11.37) was true.

Thus, if $\gamma \notin C^1$, (11.37) cannot be true, and since by (11.37) there exists at least one v , the logical negation of (11.37) implies that there must be at least two point $v, w \in \mathbb{S}^1$, and we can conclude. \square

Proposition 11.27. *Let $\gamma \in Lip(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ be a homeomorphism satisfying the convexity assumption (11.14) in \mathbb{S}^1 , and such that $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{S}^1 . Also, assume that there exists $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ and two unit vectors $v, w \in \mathbb{S}^1$ satisfying*

$$(11.39) \quad v \neq w, \quad \langle v, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \langle w, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0, \quad \forall y \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

Then, if we define the convex hull of $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$, $E := co(\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1))$, for every $p \geq \frac{1}{s}$ it holds

$$(11.40) \quad \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1 \setminus B_\varepsilon(x_0)} |H_{\partial E}^s(\gamma(x))|^p dx = +\infty.$$

Proof of Proposition 11.27. Thanks to Theorem 11.38 we have that there exists some neighbourhood $U_{x_0} \subset \mathbb{S}^1$ of x_0 and a convex function f such that up to rotations

$$(11.41) \quad \gamma(t) = (\gamma_1(t), f(\gamma_1(t)))^T \quad \text{for all } t \in U_{x_0}.$$

We now find now two vectors v' and w' in \mathbb{S}^1 that still satisfy (11.39) with better properties. For two sequences $x_n, \tilde{x}_n \in \gamma_1(U_{x_0})$ such that $x_n \searrow \gamma_1(x_0)$, $\tilde{x}_n \nearrow \gamma_1(x_0)$ and f is differentiable in x_n and \tilde{x}_n we define

$$v' := \lim_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + (f'(x_n))^2}} \begin{pmatrix} f'(x_n) \\ -1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$w' := \lim_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + (f'(\tilde{x}_n))^2}} \begin{pmatrix} f'(\tilde{x}_n) \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The convergence of the two limits above is guaranteed by the monotonicity of f' wherever it exists, and independent of the particular sequences chosen.

As a consequence of Theorem 11.38, v' and w' almost satisfy (11.39) – however it could be that $v' = w'$. But indeed, if we had $v' = w'$, then it follows that $\lim_n f'(x_n) = \lim_n f'(\tilde{x}_n)$. In this case by convexity of f we deduce for every n that

$$f'(\tilde{x}_n) \leq \frac{f(\tilde{x}_n) - f(\gamma_1(x_0))}{\tilde{x}_n - \gamma_1(x_0)} \leq \frac{f(x_n) - f(\gamma_1(x_0))}{x_n - \gamma_1(x_0)} \leq f'(x_n).$$

Taking the limits, we obtain that f is differentiable in $\gamma_1(x_0)$. As a consequence of this and Theorem 11.38 we deduce that γ is differentiable in x_0 . This and Lemma 11.31 imply that there is a unique unit vector v satisfying (11.14) in x_0 – but this is contradiction to (11.39). So indeed $v' \neq w'$. So, w.l.o.g. $v = v'$ and $w = w'$.

Without loss of generality we can assume that for some $\theta_0 \in (\pi, 2\pi)$ it holds $w = R_{\theta_0}v$, where R_{θ_0} denotes the counterclockwise rotation by θ_0 . The case $\theta_0 \in (0, \pi)$ follows from the first one by renaming v and w . Also, note that $\theta_0 = \pi$ is not allowed since equation (11.39) would give that $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$ is a line, contradicting the hypothesis that γ is a homeomorphism.

Assume first $\theta_0 \in (\frac{3}{2}\pi, 2\pi)$, then up to a translation, rotation and by possibly choosing U_{x_0} smaller, we obtain for some $m > 0$

$$(11.42) \quad \gamma(x_0) = 0, \quad v = (0, -1)^T \quad \text{and} \quad w = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+m^2}}(-m, -1)^T.$$

Note that as a consequence of (11.42) and (11.39) we have that

$$(11.43) \quad \gamma_2(y) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all} \quad y \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

Now, we claim that for a.e. $x \in V_{x_0} := U_{x_0} \cap \{x > x_0\}$ there exists some convex set $E_x \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, such that

$$(11.44) \quad E \subset E_x \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma(x) \in \partial E \cap \partial E_x,$$

and furthermore, $H_{\partial E_x}^s$ satisfies

$$(11.45) \quad H_{\partial E_x}^s(\gamma(x)) \gtrsim_{m,s} \frac{1}{|x - x_0|^s}.$$

If claim (11.44) and (11.45) are true, then we can apply the Maximum Principle for the nonlocal mean curvature, Proposition 11.10, to obtain for a.e. $x \in V_{x_0}$ that

$$H_{\partial E}^s(\gamma(x)) \geq H_{\partial E_x}^s(\gamma(x)) \gtrsim_{m,s} \frac{1}{|x - x_0|^s}.$$

In particular, from this last equation we evince that

$$\int_{U_{x_0} \setminus B_\varepsilon(x_0)} |H_{\partial E}^s(\gamma(x))|^p dx \gtrsim_{m,s} \int_{V_{x_0} \setminus B_\varepsilon(x_0)} \frac{dx}{|x - x_0|^{ps}}.$$

Recalling that $p \geq \frac{1}{s}$, and taking the limit for $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ we obtain (11.40).

Construction of the set E_x :

To find a set E_x with (11.44) and (11.45) we recall that for every $x \in V_{x_0}$ there exists some $\nu_x \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that

$$(11.46) \quad \langle \nu_x, \gamma(x) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

Moreover, since γ is Lipschitz, the set

$$S := \{x \in V_{x_0} \mid \gamma \text{ is differentiable in } x\}$$

is such that $\sigma^1(V_{x_0} \setminus S) = 0$. From Lemma 11.31, we deduce that for $x \in S$, the normal $\nu_x \in \mathbb{S}^1$ is uniquely determined. We adhere to the notation $\nu_x = (\nu_{x_1}, \nu_{x_2})^T$. Also, thanks to Theorem 11.38 we have for every $x \in S$

$$\nu_x = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(x))^2}} \begin{pmatrix} f'(\gamma_1(x)) \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence, under the assumptions provided in (11.42), it follows from this last equation that

$$(11.47) \quad -1 \leq \nu_{x_2} < 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \nu_{x_1} \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in S.$$

Let $x \in S$. Now, we begin by setting the non negative gradient

$$m_1 := \frac{-\nu_{x_1}}{\nu_{x_2}}$$

and

$$(11.48) \quad \tilde{t} := \begin{cases} \frac{-\gamma_2(x) + m_1 \gamma_1(x)}{m_1} & \text{if } m_1 > 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } m_1 = 0. \end{cases}$$

Then, we define the function

$$(11.49) \quad g_x(t) := \begin{cases} -mt & \text{for } t \in (-\infty, 0) \\ 0 & \text{for } t \in [0, \tilde{t}] \\ m_1(t - \tilde{t}) & \text{for } t \in [\tilde{t}, +\infty). \end{cases}$$

and its epigraph

$$E_x := \{(y_1, y_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid y_2 \geq g_x(y_1)\}.$$

Since g_x is convex, we obtain that

$$(11.50) \quad E_x \text{ is convex.}$$

Proof of (11.44):

From the fact that

$$(11.51) \quad g_x(\gamma_1(x)) = \gamma_2(x),$$

and Proposition 11.36 it follows that

$$(11.52) \quad \gamma(x) \in \partial E_x \cap \partial E.$$

According to equation (11.39), (11.42), (11.46) and the fact that $E = \text{co}(\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1))$ we have that

$$\begin{cases} \langle (m, 1)^T, P \rangle \geq 0 & \text{for all } P = (P_1, P_2)^T \in E \\ \langle (0, 1)^T, P \rangle \geq 0 & \text{for all } P = (P_1, P_2)^T \in E \\ \langle (\nu_{x_1}, \nu_{x_2})^T, \gamma(x) - P \rangle \geq 0 & \text{for all } P = (P_1, P_2)^T \in E. \end{cases}$$

Writing explicitly the above set of equations we obtain

$$(11.53) \quad \begin{cases} P_2 \geq -mP_1 & \text{for all } P = (P_1, P_2)^T \in E \\ P_2 \geq 0 & \text{for all } P = (P_1, P_2)^T \in E \\ P_2 \geq m_1(P_1 - \gamma_1(x)) + \gamma_2(x) & \text{for all } P = (P_1, P_2)^T \in E. \end{cases}$$

The set of inequalities in (11.53) guarantees that $g_x(P_1) \leq P_2$ for each $P \in E$, and therefore

$$(11.54) \quad E \subset E_x.$$

Equations (11.50), (11.52) and (11.54) yield to (11.44).

Proof of (11.45):

To prove (11.45) it is enough to apply Proposition 11.28 in x with $g_x = g$ and

$G = E_x$. By doing so we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} H_{\partial E_x}^s(\gamma(x)) &\gtrsim_{m,s} \frac{1}{(|g_x(\gamma_1(x))| + |\gamma_1(x)|)^s} \\ &= \frac{1}{(|\gamma_2(x)| + |\gamma_1(x)|)^s} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2^s |x|^s}. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (11.45). And in turn the case of $\theta_0 \in (\frac{3\pi}{2}, 2\pi)$ is concluded.

Now, we discuss the case $\theta_0 \in (\pi, \frac{3\pi}{2})$. In this case, up to translations and rotations of $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$, we can assume that for some $m > 0$ it holds that

$$(11.55) \quad \gamma(x_0) = 0, \quad v = (0, -1)^T \text{ and } w = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+m^2}}(-m, 1)^T.$$

We observe that if we define $\tilde{w} := \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+m^2}}(-m, -1)^T$, then $\tilde{w} = R_{\tilde{\theta}}v$ for some $\tilde{\theta} \in (\frac{3}{2}\pi, 2\pi)$.

If we plug in the expression for w as in (11.55) in equation (11.39), we obtain for every $y \in \mathbb{S}^1$ that

$$0 \leq \left\langle \begin{pmatrix} m \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1(y) \\ \gamma_2(y) \end{pmatrix} \right\rangle = m\gamma_1(y) - \gamma_2(y).$$

From this inequality, and the fact that $\gamma_2 \geq 0$, we obtain for every $y \in \mathbb{S}^1$

$$\langle \tilde{w}, (\gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y)) \rangle \geq 0.$$

In particular, we have that v and \tilde{w} satisfies (11.39), $v \neq \tilde{w}$ and $\tilde{w} = R_{\tilde{\theta}}v$ for some $\tilde{\theta} \in (\frac{3}{2}\pi, 2\pi)$. This means that we recovered the first case, and we conclude. \square

Proposition 11.28. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, $m, \tilde{t} > 0$ and $m_1 \geq 0$ and consider the function given by*

$$g(t) := \begin{cases} -mt & \text{for } t \in (-\infty, 0) \\ 0 & \text{for } t \in [0, \tilde{t}) \\ m_1(t - \tilde{t}) & \text{for } t \in [\tilde{t}, +\infty). \end{cases}$$

Set $G := \{(t, y) \mid y \geq g(t)\}$, see Figure 11.1.

Then for some constant $c_{m,s} > 0$ depending on m and s ,

Figure 11.1: The barrier G from Proposition 11.28

- if $m_1 > 0$ for all $x \in (0, \tilde{t}) \cup (\tilde{t}, +\infty)$
- if $m_1 = 0$ for every $x > 0$

we have

$$H_{\partial G}^s((x, g(x))) \geq \frac{C_{m,s}}{(|g(x)| + |x|)^s}.$$

Proof of Proposition 11.28. Let x be as in the statement. Set $z := (x, g(x))^T$. Define the unit vectors

$$u := \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+m^2}}(1, -m)^T \quad \text{and} \quad v := \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+m_1^2}}(1, m_1)^T.$$

Then we can parameterize the graph of g using the curve

$$\mu(t) := \begin{cases} ut & \text{for } t \in (-\infty, 0] \\ (t, 0) & \text{for } t \in [0, \tilde{t}] \\ v(t - \tilde{t}) + (\tilde{t}, 0) & \text{for } t \in [\tilde{t}, +\infty). \end{cases}$$

We observe that if we denote $\hat{t} := \frac{g(x)}{u_2}$ then

$$\mu_2(t) \geq g(x) \quad \text{for all } t \in (-\infty, \hat{t}].$$

From this it follows that for every $t \in (-\infty, \hat{t}]$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\mu(t) - z| &\leq |\mu_1(t) - x| + |\mu_2(t) - g(x)| \\
 &= |\mu_1(t) - x| + (\mu_2(t) - g(x)) \\
 (11.56) \quad &\leq |\mu_1(t) - x| + |u_2 t| \\
 &= |\mu_1(t) - x| + |-m u_1 t| \\
 &\leq |\mu_1(t) - x| + m |u_1 t - x| \\
 &\lesssim_m |\mu_1(t) - x|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we notice that g admits second order Taylor expansion in x . In particular, recalling that $u^\perp := (u_2, -u_1)^T$, we can use Remark 11.40 and (11.56) to estimate

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_{\partial E}^s(z) &= \frac{2}{s} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\langle n(\mu(t)), \mu(t) - z \rangle}{|\mu(t) - z|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &= \frac{2}{s} \int_{-\infty}^{\hat{t}} \frac{\langle n(\mu(t)), \mu(t) - z \rangle}{|\mu(t) - z|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &\geq \frac{2}{s} \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\langle n(\mu(t)), \mu(t) - z \rangle}{|\mu(t) - z|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &= -\frac{2}{s} \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\langle n(\mu(t)), z \rangle}{|\mu(t) - z|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &= -\frac{2}{s} \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\langle n(\mu(t)), z \rangle}{|\mu(t) - z|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &= -\frac{2}{s} \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\langle u^\perp, (x, g(x)) \rangle}{|\mu(t) - z|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &= \frac{2}{s} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+m^2}} \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{mx + g(x)}{|\mu(t) - z|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &\gtrsim_{m,s} \int_{-\infty}^{\hat{t}} \frac{mx + g(x)}{|\mu_1(t) - x|^{2+s}} dt \\
 &\stackrel{=}{=}_{m,s} \frac{mx + g(x)}{|u_1 \hat{t} - x|^{1+s}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we notice that

$$\begin{aligned}
 |u_1 \hat{t} - x| &\leq |u_1 \hat{t}| + |x| \\
 &= \frac{|g(x)|}{m} + |x| \\
 &\lesssim_m |g(x)| + |x|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, recalling that $x, g(x) \geq 0$, we have

$$H_{\partial E}^s(z) \gtrsim_{m,s} \frac{g(x) + mx}{|g(x) + x|^{1+s}} \geq \frac{c_{m,s}}{|g(x) + x|^s}. \quad \square$$

Proof of Theorem 11.24. Let $E := \text{co}(\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1))$. Then, thanks to Proposition 11.36 we have that $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1) = \partial E$. Also, using Proposition 11.11 we obtain for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{S}^1$

$$H_{\partial E}^s(\gamma(x)) = \frac{2}{s} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy,$$

where $n(\gamma(y)) = \gamma'(y)^\perp$ for a.e. $y \in \mathbb{S}^1$.

Making use of Proposition 11.27 and the last identity, we obtain the existence of some $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\gamma) &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1 \setminus B_\varepsilon(x_0)} \left| \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right|^p dx \\ &= c_{s,p} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1 \setminus B_\varepsilon(x_0)} |H_{\partial E}^s(\gamma(x))|^p dx \\ &= +\infty, \end{aligned}$$

and this concludes the proof of the theorem. □

Remark 11.29. It is important to observe that the above result holds only in critical and subcritical regime, $\mathcal{W}_{s,p}(\partial E)$ where $p \geq \frac{1}{s}$. In the supercritical regime, $p < \frac{1}{s}$ any polygon has finite energy.

11.7 Proof of Theorem 11.1

In Theorem 11.30 we prove that sequences in X with bounded \mathcal{W}_s -energy weakly converge locally in $W_2^{s+1, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma)$ (where Σ is finite) to a limit curve which belongs to X . Having this, Theorem 11.1 is a consequence of the direct method of calculus of variations.

Theorem 11.30. *Assume we have a sequence of $\gamma_k \in C^1(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ such that*

- each γ_k is a homeomorphism onto its image,
- $|\gamma'_k| \equiv 1$ for all k ,

- γ_k are convex on \mathbb{S}^1 , in the sense of Definition 11.8.

Assume moreover

$$(11.57) \quad \Lambda := \sup_k \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma_k(y)), \gamma_k(y) - \gamma_k(x) \rangle}{|\gamma_k(x) - \gamma_k(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} dx < +\infty.$$

Then, up to translations of γ_k , and up to taking a subsequence the following holds for some finite set $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{S}^1$:

- 1) γ_k converges uniformly to γ in \mathbb{S}^1 ,
- 2) for each $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma$ there exists some ρ_{x_0} such that γ_k converges weakly to γ in $W_2^{s+1, \frac{1}{s}}(\mathbb{S}^1 \cap B_{\rho_{x_0}}(x_0))$,
- 3) $\gamma \in C^1(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ and γ satisfies all the bullet points above from γ_k .

Furthermore, it holds that

$$(11.58) \quad \mathcal{W}_s(\gamma) \leq \liminf_k \mathcal{W}_s(\gamma_{k_j}).$$

Proof of Theorem 11.30. As for 1), by a translation argument we may assume that $\gamma_k(0) = 0$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Since $|\gamma'_k| \equiv 1$, up to subsequence we obtain from the Arzela-Ascoli theorem the uniform convergence to some $\gamma \in \text{Lip}(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^3)$, $|\gamma'| \leq 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{S}^1 .

Convexity is preserved: Fix $y \in \mathbb{S}^1$. Since γ_k are by assumption differentiable at y , as a consequence of convexity, (11.14), and Lemma 11.31 we have that

$$\langle n(\gamma_k(y)), \gamma_k(y) - \gamma_k(x) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{S}^1,$$

where $n(\gamma_k(y)) = (\gamma'_k)^\perp(y)$. Since $n(\gamma_k(y)) \in \mathbb{S}^1$, it admits a converging subsequence to some $v_y \in \mathbb{S}^1$, and using the uniform convergence of the full sequence γ_k , one deduces from the above equation that

$$(11.59) \quad \langle v_y, \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

In particular, we have proved γ is still convex in the sense of Definition 11.8.

As for 2), by a covering argument, Proposition 11.41, for each $\delta > 0$ there exists a subset $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{S}^1$ such that $\#\Sigma \leq L$ with $L(\Lambda, \delta) \in \mathbb{N}$ and for each $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma$ there exists some $\rho_{x_0} \in (0, 1)$ with respect to which

$$(11.60) \quad \sup_k \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{B_{40\rho_{x_0}}(x_0)} \frac{\langle n(\gamma_k(y)), \gamma_k(y) - \gamma_k(x) \rangle}{|\gamma_k(x) - \gamma_k(y)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} < \delta.$$

Thus, by choosing δ small enough, we can apply Theorem 11.17 and obtain that

$$[\gamma'_k]_{W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(B_{5\rho_{x_0}}(x_0))} \leq C\delta.$$

By reflexivity of $W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(B_{5\rho_{x_0}}(x_0))$ and Banach-Alaoglu combined with Rellich's Theorem, we find that γ'_k weakly converges to γ' , up to a subsequence, in $W_2^{s, \frac{1}{s}}(B_{5\rho_{x_0}}(x_0))$ and the convergence is pointwise a.e. in $B_{5\rho_{x_0}}(x_0)$ and strong in L^1 . This proves 2).

γ is in arclength-parametrization: Since γ'_k converges a.e. in $\mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma$ and Σ is a finite set, we obtain that

$$(11.61) \quad |\gamma'(x)| = \lim_k |\gamma'_k(x)| \equiv 1 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

γ is locally BiLipschitz: Also, by choosing δ small enough, as a consequence of (11.60), Proposition 11.12 and Lemma 11.15 we obtain that for each $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\frac{1}{2}|x - y| \leq |\gamma_k(x) - \gamma_k(y)| \leq |x - y| \quad \text{for all } x, y \in B_{\rho_{x_0}}(x_0).$$

From this and the uniform convergence of γ_k to γ we obtain that

$$(11.62) \quad \frac{1}{2}|x - y| \leq |\gamma(x) - \gamma(y)| \leq |x - y| \quad \text{for all } x, y \in B_{\rho_{x_0}}(x_0).$$

Now, thanks to the uniform convergence of γ_k to γ we obtain that if for some $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma$ and any $y_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ it holds that

$$(11.63) \quad |\gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y_0)| < \frac{\rho_{x_0}}{100},$$

then for all k sufficiently large it holds that

$$|\gamma_k(x_0) - \gamma_k(y_0)| < \frac{\rho_{x_0}}{100}.$$

Using this last equation together with (11.60) and Theorem 11.21, we evince that

$$(11.64) \quad |x_0 - y_0| \leq \rho_{x_0}.$$

Moreover, assume that $\gamma(x) = \gamma(y)$ for some $x, y \in \mathbb{S}^1$. Then, if $x \notin \Sigma$, as a consequence of (11.63) and (11.64) we deduce that $y \in B_{\rho_x}(x)$. In particular, using this last information and (11.62) we obtain that $x = y$. Analogously, one shows that if $y \notin \Sigma$ then $x = y$. In conclusion,

$$(11.65) \quad \text{if } \gamma(x) = \gamma(y) \text{ then either } x = y \text{ or } x, y \in \Sigma.$$

Lower semicontinuity: Now that we obtained point wise convergence of γ'_k , we notice that for a.e. $x, y \in \mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma$ such that $x \neq y$, one has that

$$\frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} = \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\langle n(\gamma_k(y)), (\gamma_k(y) - \gamma_k(x)) \rangle}{|\gamma_k(y) - \gamma_k(x)|^{2+s}}.$$

In particular, from Fatou's lemma we obtain that

$$\left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) - \gamma(x) \rangle}{|\gamma(y) - \gamma(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma_k(y)), \gamma_k(y) - \gamma_k(x) \rangle}{|\gamma_k(y) - \gamma_k(x)|^{2+s}} dy \right)^{\frac{1}{s}}.$$

By integrating with respect to x in \mathbb{S}^1 the above expression and applying Fatou's Lemma a second time, we obtain

$$\mathcal{W}_s(\gamma) \leq \liminf_k \mathcal{W}_s(\gamma_k).$$

This concludes the proof of lower semicontinuity, i.e. (11.58).

γ is a homeomorphism: In view of Proposition 11.23, $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$ is a topological one-manifold. Since γ has only finitely many self intersection, namely only on Σ , this implies that actually γ must be injective – for the details of this argument see [Bla+24].

γ is C^1 : Since γ has finite Willmore-energy it belongs to X as in (11.1).

Therefore, applying Theorem 11.24 we deduce that $\gamma \in C^1(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$. This last result together with (11.59) and (11.61) proves 3).

□

11.8 Appendices

Facts about convex curves in \mathbb{R}^2

In this section we recall geometric properties of convex curves and graphs, where we recall the notion of convexity in (11.14).

Lemma 11.31. *Assume $\gamma \in \text{Lip}((a, b), \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{S}^1 and γ is convex in the sense of (11.14). Then, if γ is differentiable at $x_0 \in (a, b)$, it holds that $\langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma'(x_0) \rangle = 0$. Also, if $\gamma((a, b))$ is not a straight line ν_{x_0} is unique.*

Proof. We observe that according to (11.14) one has that

$$0 \geq \left\langle \nu_{x_0}, \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0^+} \frac{\gamma(x) - \gamma(x_0)}{x - x_0} \right\rangle = \langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma'(x_0) \rangle$$

and similarly

$$0 \leq \left\langle \nu_{x_0}, \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0^-} \frac{\gamma(x) - \gamma(x_0)}{x - x_0} \right\rangle = \langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma'(x_0) \rangle.$$

From the above equations we deduce that $\langle \gamma'(x_0), \nu_{x_0} \rangle = 0$. Also, we claim that if $\gamma((a, b))$ is not a line then

$$(11.66) \quad \nu_{x_0} \text{ is unique.}$$

Indeed, if (11.66) was false we would necessarily have that there are two vectors $\nu_{x_0}, \tilde{\nu}_{x_0} \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that $\langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma'(x_0) \rangle = 0$ and $\langle \tilde{\nu}_{x_0}, \gamma'(x_0) \rangle = 0$, which implies that (up to renaming the two vectors) $\nu_{x_0} = -\gamma'(x_0)^\perp$ and $\tilde{\nu}_{x_0} = \gamma'(x_0)^\perp$. Thus, we would have that $\nu_{x_0} = -\tilde{\nu}_{x_0}$ and

$$\langle \nu_{x_0}, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle -\nu_{x_0}, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0.$$

This implies that $\gamma((a, b))$ is necessarily a straight line, providing a contradiction. \square

Lemma 11.32. *Assume there are two distinct points $p_0, p_1 \in \mathbb{R}^2$, and set*

$$T = p_1 - p_0 \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \{0\}.$$

Also, let m on the segment $[p_1, p_0]$, i.e. for some $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ it holds that

$$(11.67) \quad m = p_0 + \lambda T.$$

Then, if at m we have the convexity condition Definition 11.8, that is if we find $v_m \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $|v_m| = 1$ and

$$(11.68) \quad \langle v_m, m - y \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall y \in \{p_1, p_2\},$$

then necessarily

$$v_m \in \left\{ -\frac{T^\perp}{|T^\perp|}, \frac{T^\perp}{|T^\perp|} \right\}$$

Proof. By scaling we may assume that $|T| = |p_1 - p_0| = 1$.

The assumption (11.67) readily implies

$$\langle T^\perp, m - p_0 \rangle = 0$$

Since $T = p_1 - p_0$ we thus have

$$(11.69) \quad 0 = \langle m - p_0, T^\perp \rangle = \langle m - p_1, T^\perp \rangle.$$

Assume that for some $v_m \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $|v_m| = 1$, we have (11.68), i.e. assume

$$\begin{cases} \langle v_m, m - p_0 \rangle \geq 0 & \text{and} \\ \langle v_m, m - p_1 \rangle \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

Since $|T| = |T^\perp| = 1$ we can write $v_m = \langle v_m, T \rangle T + \langle v_m, T^\perp \rangle T^\perp$. Thus, taking into account (11.69) the previous equations become

$$\begin{cases} \langle v_m, T \rangle \langle T, m - p_0 \rangle \geq 0 & \text{and} \\ \langle v_m, T \rangle \langle T, m - p_1 \rangle \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

But now

$$\langle T, m - p_1 \rangle = \langle T, m - p_0 - T \rangle = \langle T, m - p_0 \rangle - 1.$$

So we find

$$\begin{cases} \langle v_m, T \rangle \langle T, m - p_0 \rangle \geq 0 & \text{and} \\ \langle v_m, T \rangle (\langle T, m - p_0 \rangle - 1) \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

In view of (11.67) this implies

$$\begin{cases} \langle v_m, T \rangle \lambda \geq 0 & \text{and} \\ \langle v_m, T \rangle (\lambda - 1) \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

Since $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ this implies $\langle v_m, T \rangle = 0$, that is $v_m = \pm T^\perp$. We can conclude. \square

Lemma 11.33. *Assume $\gamma : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is continuous, convex in the sense of Definition 11.8 and that*

$$T = \gamma(1) - \gamma(0) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \{0\}.$$

Furthermore, $\gamma(t) \notin \{\gamma(0), \gamma(1)\}$ for all $t \in (0, 1)$. Then, either

$$\langle T^\perp, \gamma(t) - \gamma(0) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall t \in [0, 1]$$

or

$$\langle T^\perp, \gamma(t) - \gamma(0) \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall t \in [0, 1].$$

Proof. By continuity, injectivity, and the intermediate value theorem, if the claim is false, the only way the claim is not true is if there exists $\bar{t} \in [0, 1]$ with $\gamma(\bar{t}) \neq \gamma(0), \gamma(1)$ but

$$\langle T^\perp, \gamma(\bar{t}) - \gamma(0) \rangle = 0.$$

This implies that one of the following must be true

$$\begin{cases} \gamma(\bar{t}) \in [\gamma(0), \gamma(1)] & \text{or} \\ \gamma(0) \in [\gamma(\bar{t}), \gamma(1)] & \text{or} \\ \gamma(1) \in [\gamma(\bar{t}), \gamma(0)]. \end{cases}$$

In either case we find from the convexity condition in Definition 11.8 combined with Lemma 11.32 that

$$\begin{cases} \langle T^\perp, \gamma(\tilde{t}) - \gamma(t) \rangle \geq 0 & \forall t \in [0, 1] & \text{or} \\ \langle T^\perp, \gamma(\tilde{t}) - \gamma(t) \rangle \leq 0 & \forall t \in [0, 1] \end{cases}$$

when $\tilde{t} \in \{0, 1, \bar{t}\}$ is chosen correctly. Whichever of the three options \tilde{t} is, we have $\gamma(\tilde{t}) - \gamma(0) \in \text{span}\{T\}$, so we find either

$$\begin{cases} \langle T^\perp, \gamma(0) - \gamma(t) \rangle \geq 0 & \forall t \in [0, 1] & \text{or} \\ \langle T^\perp, \gamma(0) - \gamma(t) \rangle \leq 0 & \forall t \in [0, 1]. \end{cases}$$

We can conclude. □

Figure 11.2: The geometry in the proof of Lemma 11.34

Lemma 11.34. *Assume that $(x, f(x)) : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is a continuous graph that is convex in the sense of Definition 11.8.*

Then, f is either convex or concave on $[0, 1]$.

Proof. Assume the claim is wrong. Then, there must be some some f , and we may assume w.l.o.g. $f(0) = 0$, $f(1) = 1$, such that for some $0 < \mu < \lambda < 1$ $(\lambda, f(\lambda))$ lies below the line connecting $(0, f(0))$ and $(1, f(1))$, and $f(\mu)$ lies above the line connecting $(0, f(0))$ and $(\lambda, f(\lambda))$. In formulas we have

$$(11.70) \quad f(\lambda) < \lambda f(1)$$

and

$$(11.71) \quad f(\mu) > \frac{\mu}{\lambda} f(\lambda).$$

We now consider the line starting from $(0, f(0))$ with slope

$$m_\varepsilon := \frac{f(\lambda) - f(0)}{\lambda - 0} + \varepsilon,$$

where ε is small, Cf. Figure 11.2. This line is the graph of

$$g_\varepsilon(x) := m_\varepsilon x.$$

We clearly have $g(0) = f(0) = 0$. For all small enough $\varepsilon > 0$

$$g_\varepsilon(\mu) = \frac{\mu}{\lambda}f(\lambda) + \mu\varepsilon \stackrel{(11.71)}{<} f(\mu).$$

Also, for all $\varepsilon > 0$

$$g_\varepsilon(\lambda) = f(\lambda) + \varepsilon > f(\lambda).$$

Lastly, for possibly even smaller $\varepsilon > 0$ we have

$$g_\varepsilon(1) = \frac{f(\lambda)}{\lambda} + \varepsilon \stackrel{(11.70)}{<} f(1).$$

By the intermediate value theorem we find $p \in (\lambda, 1)$ such that $g_\varepsilon(p) = f(p)$.

That is the curve $\gamma(x) := (x, f(x))$ and the line $L = (x, g_\varepsilon(x))$ coincide at 0 and p but $\gamma(\mu)$ lies above the line L and $\gamma(\lambda)$ lies below the line L – which is a contradiction to Lemma 11.33. \square

Lemma 11.35. *Assume $\gamma : \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is continuous and injective and fix $\theta_1 \neq \theta_2 \in \mathbb{S}^1$.*

Set

$$T := \gamma(\theta_2) - \gamma(\theta_1) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \{0\}.$$

We consider the two different arcs connecting θ_1 and θ_2 in \mathbb{S}^1 , we call them $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$ and $[\theta_2, \theta_1]$.

Then the curve is separated by $\gamma(\theta_1) + \lambda T$, more precisely we have either

$$\begin{cases} \langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \geq 0 & \forall t \in [\theta_1, \theta_2] & \text{and} \\ \langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \leq 0 & \forall t \in [\theta_2, \theta_1] \end{cases}$$

or

$$\begin{cases} \langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \leq 0 & \forall t \in [\theta_1, \theta_2] & \text{and} \\ \langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \geq 0 & \forall t \in [\theta_2, \theta_1]. \end{cases}$$

Proof. In view of Lemma 11.33, the only way the claim is false would be that there exists $t^+ \in (\theta_1, \theta_2)$ and $t^- \in (\theta_2, \theta_1)$ such that (the sign is w.l.o.g. negative)

$$\langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t^+), T^\perp \rangle < 0, \text{ and } \langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t^-), T^\perp \rangle < 0$$

and otherwise we have

$$\langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \leq 0 \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

By continuity and injectivity, we may assume w.l.o.g. that for some $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, $0 < \mu_- < \mu_+$ we have

$$\gamma(t^+) = \gamma(\theta_1) + \lambda T + \mu_+ T^\perp$$

and

$$\gamma(t^-) = \gamma(\theta_1) + \lambda T + \mu_- T^\perp$$

$$0 > \langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t^-), T^\perp \rangle > \langle \gamma(\theta_1) - \gamma(t^+), T^\perp \rangle.$$

Set

$$w_1 := \gamma(t^-) - \gamma(t^+)$$

$$w_2 := \gamma(t^-) - \gamma(\theta_1)$$

$$w_3 := \gamma(t^-) - \gamma(\theta_2).$$

We then observe from $w_1 = T^\perp(\mu_- - \mu_+)$ we have

$$\langle w_1, T^\perp \rangle < 0.$$

Also, we notice that

$$\langle w_2, T^\perp \rangle > 0$$

and since $w_3 = w_2 - T$ we find

$$\langle w_3, T^\perp \rangle = \langle w_2, T^\perp \rangle > 0.$$

Moreover, we have

$$\langle w_1, T \rangle = 0,$$

$$\langle w_2, T \rangle = \lambda,$$

$$\langle w_3, T \rangle = \lambda - 1.$$

Now let $v_{t^-} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $|v_{t^-}| = 1$ such that

$$\langle v_{t^-}, \gamma(t^-) - \gamma(t) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

That is, we have

$$\langle v_{t^-}, w_i \rangle \geq 0 \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

Take $\sigma, \delta \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $v_{t^-} = \sigma T + \delta T^\perp$. Then, we have

$$\sigma \underbrace{\langle T, w_1 \rangle}_{=0} + \delta \underbrace{\langle T^\perp, w_1 \rangle}_{<0} \geq 0.$$

This implies $\delta = 0$. Then, we compute that

$$\sigma \underbrace{\langle T, w_2 \rangle}_{=\lambda} + \underbrace{\delta \langle T^\perp, w_2 \rangle}_{=0} \geq 0$$

$$\sigma \underbrace{\langle T, w_3 \rangle}_{=\lambda-1} + \underbrace{\delta \langle T^\perp, w_3 \rangle}_{=0} \geq 0.$$

Since $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ these equalities imply that $\sigma = 0$, a contradiction to $|v_{t^-}| = 1$. \square

Proposition 11.36. *Let $\gamma \in \text{Lip}(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ be injective and satisfying the convexity assumption (11.14) in \mathbb{S}^1 . Then, if we define the convex set $E := \text{co}(\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1))$ it holds that*

$$\partial E = \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1).$$

Proof of Proposition 11.36. We begin by proving that

$$(11.72) \quad \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1) \subset \partial E.$$

To do so, we first observe that $E \neq \emptyset$, and since $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$ is compact, then we can apply Theorem 1.4.3 in [HUL04] and obtain that E is compact.

Also, being $\gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$ a connected set, we can apply Theorem 1.3.7 in [HUL04] and obtain that

$$(11.73) \quad E = \{ \lambda \gamma(t_1) + (1 - \lambda) \gamma(t_2) \mid t_1, t_2 \in \mathbb{S}^1 \text{ and } \lambda \in [0, 1] \}.$$

In particular, from (11.73) and equation (11.14) we deduce that for every $t \in \mathbb{S}^1$ and $P \in \mathbb{S}^1$ there are $t_1, t_2 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \nu_t, \gamma(t) - P \rangle &= \langle \nu_t, \gamma(t) - \lambda \gamma(t_1) - (1 - \lambda) \gamma(t_2) \rangle \\ &= \lambda \langle \nu_t, \gamma(t) - \gamma(t_1) \rangle + (1 - \lambda) \langle \nu_t, \gamma(t) - \gamma(t_2) \rangle \\ &\geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, we have just proved that for every $t \in \mathbb{S}^1$ there exists some $\nu_t \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that for every $Q \in E$

$$\langle \nu_t, \gamma(t) - Q \rangle \geq 0.$$

From this and the fact that $\gamma(t) \in E$, we readily evince (11.72).

To conclude the proof of the proposition we claim that

$$(11.74) \quad \partial E \subset \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1).$$

To prove this, let $P \in \partial E$. Then, applying Lemma 4.2.1 in [HUL04] we obtain that there exists some $\nu_P \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that

$$(11.75) \quad \langle \nu_P, P - \gamma(t) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

According to (11.73), there are $t_1, t_2 \in \mathbb{S}^1$ and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ such that

$$P = \lambda\gamma(t_1) + (1 - \lambda)\gamma(t_2).$$

If either $\gamma(t_1) = \gamma(t_2)$ or $\lambda \in \{0, 1\}$ then $P \in \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$, and there is nothing to prove. We assume therefore that

$$\gamma(t_1) \neq \gamma(t_2) \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda \in (0, 1).$$

Thus, we observe that

$$0 \leq \langle \nu_P, P - \gamma(t_1) \rangle = \langle \nu_P, \gamma(t_2) - \gamma(t_1) \rangle (1 - \lambda)$$

and also

$$0 \leq \langle \nu_P, P - \gamma(t_2) \rangle = \langle \nu_P, \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t_2) \rangle \lambda.$$

From these two equations we evince that if we denote $T := \frac{\gamma(t_2) - \gamma(t_1)}{|\gamma(t_2) - \gamma(t_1)|}$ then

$$\nu_P \in \{T^\perp, -T^\perp\},$$

and without any loss of generality we can assume that $\nu_P = T^\perp$.

Now, using Lemma 11.35 with $\theta_1 = t_1$ and $\theta_2 = t_2$ we have that either

$$(11.76) \quad \begin{cases} \langle \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \geq 0 & \forall t \in [t_1, t_2] \quad \text{and} \\ \langle \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \leq 0 & \forall t \in [t_2, t_1] \end{cases}$$

or

$$\begin{cases} \langle \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \leq 0 & \forall t \in [t_1, t_2] \quad \text{and} \\ \langle \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t), T^\perp \rangle \geq 0 & \forall t \in [t_2, t_1]. \end{cases}$$

Without loss of generality, we assume that (11.76) holds, the second case being analogous.

On the other hand, as a consequence of (11.75), we also have for every $t \in \mathbb{S}^1$ that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq \langle \nu_P, P - \gamma(t) \rangle &= \langle T^\perp, |P - \gamma(t_1)|T + \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t) \rangle \\ &= \langle T^\perp, \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in view of this and equation (11.76), we obtain that

$$\langle T^\perp, \gamma(t_1) - \gamma(t) \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in [t_2, t_1].$$

In particular, from this we infer the existence of some $\mu \in C([t_2, t_1])$ such that $\gamma(t) = \mu(t)T + \gamma(t_1)$. Since by assumptions we have that $\mu(t_1) = 0$ and $\mu(t_2) = |\gamma(t_2) - \gamma(t_1)|$, then by continuity there exists some $t^* \in [t_2, t_1]$ such that

$$\mu(t^*) = (1 - \lambda) |\gamma(t_2) - \gamma(t_1)|.$$

In particular, for such t^* it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma(t^*) &= \mu(t^*)T + \gamma(t_1) \\ &= (1 - \lambda) (\gamma(t_2) - \gamma(t_1)) + \gamma(t_1) \\ &= \lambda\gamma(t_1) + (1 - \lambda)\gamma(t_2) \\ &= P. \end{aligned}$$

We have just proved that $P \in \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1)$, and (11.74) follows. \square

Proposition 11.37. *Let $\gamma \in Lip((a, b), \mathbb{R}^2)$, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in (a, b) , injective and satisfying the convexity assumption (11.14) in (a, b) . Furthermore, we assume that there exists some Lipschitz $f : \gamma_1((a, b)) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that*

$$(11.77) \quad \gamma(t) = (\gamma_1(t), f(\gamma_1(t)))^T \quad \text{for all } t \in (a, b).$$

Then, up to replacing $\gamma(\cdot)$ with $\gamma((a + b) - \cdot)$, for a.e. $t \in (a, b)$ it holds that

$$(11.78) \quad \gamma'_1(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(t))^2}}.$$

Also, up to rotating γ by π , f is convex.

Proof. If $\gamma((a, b))$ is a straight line then the statement easily follows. For this reason, from now on we assume that $\gamma((a, b))$ is not a straight line.

We notice that the convexity of f follows immediately from Lemma 11.34 up to rotating γ by π .

Now, we evince from the injectivity of γ and (11.77) that $\gamma_1 : (a, b) \rightarrow \gamma_1((a, b))$ is a Lipschitz bijection. Therefore, up to replacing $\gamma(\cdot)$ with $\gamma((a + b) - \cdot)$, we have that

$$(11.79) \quad \gamma'_1 > 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } (a, b).$$

From this we obtain that if $S \subset \gamma_1((a, b))$ such that $\sigma^1(S) = 0$, then using the coarea formula (see for instance [Eva18]) we obtain

$$(11.80) \quad \begin{aligned} \int_{\gamma_1^{-1}(S)} |\gamma'_1(x)| \, dx &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \sigma^0(\gamma_1^{-1}(S) \cap \gamma_1^{-1}(y)) \, dy \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} \chi_S(y) \, dy = 0 \\ &= \int_S dy \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Henceforth, from (11.79) and (11.80) we infer that $\sigma^1(\gamma_1^{-1}(S)) = 0$. Analogously, one can prove that if $S \subset (a, b)$ and $\sigma^1(S) = 0$ then $\sigma^1(\gamma_1(S)) = 0$. We conclude that for every $S \subset (a, b)$

$$(11.81) \quad \sigma^1(S) = 0 \iff \sigma^1(\gamma_1(S)) = 0.$$

Therefore, making use of (11.81) and the fact that γ_1 and f are respectively differentiable a.e. in (a, b) and $\gamma_1(a, b)$, we deduce for a.e. $t \in (a, b)$

$$(11.82) \quad \gamma'(t) = (\gamma'_1(t), f'(\gamma_1(t))\gamma'_1(t))^T,$$

and using the hypothesis that $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. in (a, b) together with (11.79) we obtain for a.e. $t \in (a, b)$ that

$$\gamma'_1(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(t))^2}}.$$

This concludes the proof of (11.78). □

Theorem 11.38 (Implicit Function Theorem, see [Cla90]). *Let $\gamma \in \text{Lip}([a, b], \mathbb{R}^2)$, injective, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ a.e. and γ satisfies the convexity assumption (11.14) in $[a, b]$. Then, for every $x_0 \in (a, b)$ there exists some open neighbourhood $U_{x_0} \subset (a, b)$ of x_0 and a convex function f , such that up to rotations we have that*

$$(11.83) \quad \gamma(t) = (\gamma_1(t), f(\gamma_1(t)))^T \quad \text{for all } t \in U_{x_0},$$

and

$$(11.84) \quad \gamma \text{ is differentiable in } t \in U_{x_0} \iff f \text{ is differentiable in } \gamma_1(t).$$

Moreover, up to replacing $\gamma(\cdot)$ with $\gamma((a+b) - \cdot)$, for all $t \in U_{x_0}$ where γ is differentiable

$$(11.85) \quad \nu_t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(t))^2}} (f'(\gamma_1(t)), -1)^T,$$

where ν_t is as in Definition 11.8.

Proof. If $\gamma([a, b])$ coincides with a straight line then the statement easily follows. Therefore, from now on we assume that $\gamma([a, b])$ is not a line.

We begin by setting the distance function

$$d(y) := \inf \{|x - y| \mid x \in \gamma([a, b])\}.$$

We fix some $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and up to a translation we assume that $\gamma(x_0) = 0$. Then, for $\varepsilon > 0$ small enough we consider the ball B_ε , and define the sets

$$B_\varepsilon^+ := \{x \in B_\varepsilon \mid \nu_y \cdot (\gamma(y) - x) \geq 0 \text{ for all } y \in [a, b] \text{ and } \nu_y \text{ as in (11.14)}\},$$

and

$$B_\varepsilon^- := B_\varepsilon \setminus B_\varepsilon^+.$$

Then, in B_ε we define the function

$$\tilde{d}(x) := \begin{cases} -d(x) & \text{for all } x \in B_\varepsilon^+ \\ d(x) & \text{for all } x \in B_\varepsilon^-. \end{cases}$$

Being $\gamma([a, b])$ closed, we have that

$$(11.86) \quad p \in \gamma([a, b]) \iff d(p) = 0 \iff \tilde{d}(p) = 0.$$

Also, thanks to [Cla90, Proposition 2.4.1] we have that d is Lipschitz. From this, it follows that \tilde{d} is Lipschitz as well and therefore ∇d and $\nabla \tilde{d}$ exist a.e. in \mathbb{R}^2 . Moreover, thanks to [Cla90, Theorem 2.5.1] we can define the generalized gradient of \tilde{d} in 0 as

$$(11.87) \quad \partial \tilde{d}(0) = \text{co} \left\{ \lim_n \nabla \tilde{d}(x_n) \mid x_n \rightarrow 0, x_n \notin \Omega_{\tilde{d}} \right\},$$

where $\Omega_{\tilde{d}} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ is any subset of measure zero containing the set of points where \tilde{d} is not differentiable. Similarly, we denote by Ω_d any subset of measure zero containing all the points where d is not differentiable.

Being γ Lipschitz, we can assume that $\gamma([a, b]) \subset \Omega_{\tilde{d}} \subset \Omega_d$.

Now, we claim that

$$(11.88) \quad \nabla d(x) \neq 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \Omega_d.$$

As a matter of fact, being $\gamma([a, b])$ closed, we observe that for every point $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$ there exists some point $c_x \in \gamma([a, b])$, not necessarily unique, such that

$$d(x) = |c_x - x|.$$

Then, if $x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \Omega_d$ and we set $v := c_x - x$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla d(x) \cdot v &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{d(x + t(c_x - x)) - d(x)}{t} \\ &= \lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{(1-t)|c_x - x| - |c_x - x|}{t} \\ &= -|c_x - x|. \end{aligned}$$

This proves (11.88). Finally, we apply in [Cla90, Proposition 2.5.4], and obtain that for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \Omega_d$ we have that there exists a unique closest point c_x (i.e. the projection is well-defined) and

$$\nabla d(x) = \frac{x - c_x}{|x - c_x|}.$$

In particular, we deduce that

$$\nabla \tilde{d}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{-x + c_x}{|c - c_x|} & \text{for all } x \in B_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega_d \\ \frac{x - c_x}{|c - c_x|} & \text{for all } x \in B_\varepsilon^- \setminus \Omega_d. \end{cases}$$

Also, from this and the convexity condition (11.14) we observe that for all $x \in B_\varepsilon \setminus \Omega_d$ it holds

$$(11.89) \quad \nabla \tilde{d}(x) \cdot (c_x - \gamma(y)) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in [a, b].$$

Also, we observe that if x_n is as in (11.87) then we have that

$$\lim_n x_n = \lim_n c_{x_n} = 0 = \gamma(x_0).$$

In particular, from this last equation and (11.89) we obtain

$$\lim_n \nabla \tilde{d}(x_n) \cdot (\gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y)) \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } y \in [a, b].$$

Exploiting this and (11.87) we evince that

$$(11.90) \quad \partial \tilde{d}(0) \subset \text{co} \{ \nu_{x_0} \in \mathbb{S}^1 \mid \nu_{x_0} \text{ satisfies (11.14) in } x_0 \} =: N_x.$$

Also, we notice that $0 \notin \partial N_x$. Indeed, if this was the case we would obtain the existence of two vectors $v, w \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that $v = -w$ and

$$\langle v, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle w, \gamma(x_0) - \gamma(y) \rangle \geq 0,$$

giving that γ is a line, and providing a contradiction.

Since N_x is convex, closed, contained in B_1 and $0 \notin N_x$, then up to a rotation we can assume that

$$\text{for every } v = (v_1, v_2)^T \in N_x \text{ we have that } v_2 < 0.$$

In particular, making use of (11.90) we obtain

$$\text{for every } v = (v_1, v_2)^T \in \partial \tilde{d}(0) \text{ we have that } v_2 < 0.$$

As a consequence of this, we are entitled now to apply the Implicit Function Theorem for Lipschitz maps in [Cla90, Section 7.1], and obtain the existence of some neighbourhood $V_0 \subset B_\varepsilon$ of 0 and a Lipschitz function $f : V_0 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\tilde{d}(y_1, f(y_1)) = 0 \quad \text{for all } y_1 \in V_0.$$

Now, from (11.86) and this last identity we deduce that for all $t \in (a, b)$ such that $\gamma_1(t) \in V_0$ it holds that

$$\gamma(t) = (\gamma_1(t), f(\gamma_1(t)))^T.$$

Being γ_1 continuous we can define $U_{x_0} = \gamma_1^{-1}(V_0)$ and obtain (11.83). In particular, thanks to Lemma 11.34 we obtain that, up to rotating γ by π , f is convex. This concludes the proof of (11.83).

Now, we need to prove (11.84). To do so, first we assume that γ is differentiable in $t \in U_{x_0}$. Being f convex we have that

$$(11.91) \quad \lim_{h \searrow 0} \frac{f(\gamma_1(t) + h) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{h} \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{h \nearrow 0} \frac{f(\gamma_1(t) + h) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{h}$$

exist. To prove the differentiability of f in $\gamma(t)$ we only need to prove that the two limits coincide. To this end, thanks to Proposition 11.37, up to replacing $\gamma(\cdot)$ with $\gamma((a+b) - \cdot)$, we can assume that (11.78) holds. Thus, if we set $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $B_\varepsilon(t) \subset U_{x_0}$, then for every $h \in (0, \varepsilon)$ it holds

$$\gamma_1(t+h) - \gamma_1(t) = \int_t^{t+h} \frac{dz}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(z))^2}} \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + M^2}} h =: Ch,$$

where $M := \|f'\|_{L^\infty(B_\varepsilon(t))}$ and so $C \in (0, 1)$. Analogously, we can prove that for every $h \in (0, \varepsilon)$

$$\gamma_1(t-h) \leq -Ch + \gamma_1(t).$$

Making use of this and the convexity of f we evince

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{f(\gamma_1(t) + Ch) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{Ch} &\leq \frac{f(\gamma_1(t+h)) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{\gamma_1(t+h) - \gamma_1(t)} \\ &= \frac{f(\gamma_1(t+h)) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{h} \frac{h}{\gamma_1(t+h) - \gamma_1(t)} \\ &= \frac{\gamma_2(t+h) - \gamma_2(t)}{h} \frac{h}{\gamma_1(t+h) - \gamma_1(t)}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{f(\gamma_1(t) - Ch) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{-Ch} &\geq \frac{f(\gamma_1(t-h)) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{\gamma_1(t-h) - \gamma_1(t)} \\ &= \frac{f(\gamma_1(t-h)) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{-h} \frac{-h}{\gamma_1(t-h) - \gamma_1(t)} \\ &= \frac{\gamma_2(t-h) - \gamma_2(t)}{-h} \frac{-h}{\gamma_1(t-h) - \gamma_1(t)}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, since γ is differentiable in t and by convexity

$$\frac{f(\gamma_1(t) - Ch) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{-Ch} \leq \frac{f(\gamma_1(t) + Ch) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{Ch},$$

we obtain that the limits in (11.91) coincide, proving that f is differentiable in $\gamma_1(t)$.

On the other hand, assume that f is differentiable in $\gamma_1(t)$. Then, using convexity we can define for every $z \in V_0$

$$f'_+(z) := \lim_{h \searrow 0} \frac{f(z+h) - f(z)}{h} \quad \text{and} \quad f'_-(z) := \lim_{h \nearrow 0} \frac{f(z) - f(z-h)}{h}.$$

In particular, by convexity we know that $f'(z) = f'_+(z)$ and $f'(z) = f'_-(z)$ for a.e. $z \in V_0$.

In particular, it holds that

$$(11.92) \quad f'(\gamma_1(t)) = f'_+(\gamma_1(t)) = f'_-(\gamma_1(t))$$

and f'_+ and f'_- are both non decreasing. Then, for $l > t$ and every $h > 0$ small enough

$$0 \leq f'_+(\gamma_1(l)) - f'(\gamma_1(t)) \leq \frac{f(\gamma_1(l)+h) - f(\gamma_1(l))}{h} - f'(\gamma_1(t)).$$

Taking the limit for $l \searrow z$, we obtain for every $h > 0$ small enough

$$0 \leq \lim_{l \rightarrow t^+} f'_+(\gamma_1(l)) - f'(\gamma_1(t)) \leq \frac{f(\gamma_1(t)+h) - f(\gamma_1(t))}{h} - f'(\gamma_1(t)),$$

and taking the limit for $h \searrow 0$ we obtain that

$$(11.93) \quad \lim_{l \searrow t} |f'_+(\gamma_1(l)) - f'(\gamma_1(t))| = 0.$$

Analogously, we can prove that

$$(11.94) \quad \lim_{l \nearrow t} |f'(\gamma_1(t)) - f'_-(\gamma_1(l))| = 0.$$

Thus, if we define the function

$$\hat{f}'(\gamma_1(z)) := \begin{cases} f'_+(\gamma_1(z)) & \text{for } z > t \\ f'_-(\gamma_1(z)) & \text{for } z \leq t, \end{cases}$$

as a consequence of (11.93) and (11.94) we have that $\hat{f}'(\gamma_1)$ is continuous in t . Also, recall that by definition $\hat{f}'(\gamma_1(l)) = f'(\gamma_1(l))$ for a.e. $l \in U_{x_0}$.

Therefore, using this and (11.78) we have if $h \in (-\delta, \delta)$ for $\delta > 0$ small enough

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\gamma_1(t+h) - \gamma_1(t)}{h} &= \frac{1}{h} \int_t^{t+h} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(z))^2}} dz \\ &= \frac{1}{h} \int_t^{t+h} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \hat{f}'(\gamma_1(z))^2}} dz. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\hat{f}'(\gamma_1(t))$ is continuous in t , we have that t is a Lebesgue point and thanks to the Lebesgue differentiation Theorem and equation (11.92)

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{\gamma_1(t+h) - \gamma_1(t)}{h} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \hat{f}'(\gamma_1(t))^2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(t))^2}}$$

and we conclude.

Now, we prove (11.85). To do so, we notice that since f is convex then for all $x \in \gamma_1((a, b))$ where f is differentiable and every $y \in \gamma_1((a, b))$ one has that

$$\left\langle \begin{pmatrix} f'(x) \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} x \\ f(x) \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} y \\ f(y) \end{pmatrix} \right\rangle \geq 0.$$

In view of (11.84) this readily implies that for all $t \in (a, b)$ where γ is differentiable and every $t_1 \in (a, b)$ it holds that

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(t))^2}} \left\langle \begin{pmatrix} f'(\gamma_1(t)) \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1(t) \\ f(\gamma_1(t)) \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1(t_1) \\ f(\gamma_1(t_1)) \end{pmatrix} \right\rangle.$$

We also notice that thanks to Lemma 11.31 for all $t \in (a, b)$ where γ is differentiable there exists a unique vector $\nu_t \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that for every $t_1 \in (a, b)$ it holds that

$$\langle \nu_t, \gamma(t) - \gamma(t_1) \rangle \geq 0.$$

Therefore, we have proved that for all $t \in (a, b)$ where γ is differentiable

$$\nu_t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + f'(\gamma_1(t))^2}} \begin{pmatrix} f'(\gamma_1(t)) \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

concluding the proof of (11.78). □

In view of Proposition 11.37 and Theorem 11.38 we obtain

Corollary 11.39. *Let $\gamma \in Lip(\mathbb{S}^1, \mathbb{R}^2)$ be a homeomorphism, $|\gamma'| \equiv 1$ and γ satisfies (11.14) in some $(a, b) \subset \mathbb{S}^1$. Then, if γ satisfies (11.12), for every $x \in (a, b)$ where γ is differentiable it holds*

$$(11.95) \quad \nu_x = \gamma'(x)^\perp.$$

Integration formula for the mean curvature – Proof of Proposition 11.11

Proof of Proposition 11.11. Thanks to the Implicit Function Theorem 11.38 for every $z \in \mathbb{S}^1$ there exists some neighbourhood $U_z \subset \mathbb{S}^1$ and a convex function $f \in Lip(\mathbb{R})$ such that (up to rotations) it holds that

$$\gamma(t) = (\gamma_1(t), f(\gamma_1(t))) \quad \text{for all } t \in U_z.$$

Also, we notice that for every $x \in \gamma(U_z)$ there exists some $\varepsilon_x > 0$ such that

$$(11.96) \quad B_{\varepsilon_x}(x) \cap E = \{(y_1, y_2) \in B_{\varepsilon_x}(x) \mid f(y_1) \leq y_2\}.$$

Being f convex, thanks to Alexandrov Theorem, we obtain that f is twice differentiable a.e. in $\gamma_1(U_z)$. Let us stress what this actually means: for a.e. $p \in \gamma_1(U_z)$ there exists $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(11.97) \quad \lim_{q \rightarrow p} \frac{f(q) - f(p) - a(q-p) - \frac{b}{2}(q-p)^2}{|q-p|^2} = 0.$$

Thus, we denote by

$$\mathcal{A}_f := \{p \in \gamma_1(U_z) \mid f \text{ is twice differentiable in } p\}.$$

Let $\gamma_1(x) \in \mathcal{A}_f$ be fixed. Also, up to translations and rotations we can assume w.l.o.g. that $\gamma(x) = 0$ and $\gamma'(x) = (1, 0)$.

Now, we compute the nonlocal mean curvature in $\gamma(x) = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} H_{\partial E}^s(0) &= P.V. \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|y|^{2+s}} dy \\ &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{\chi_{E^c}(y) - \chi_E(y)}{|y|^{2+s}} dy \\ &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \left(\int_{E^c \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{dy}{|y|^{2+s}} - \int_{E \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{dy}{|y|^{2+s}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Then, we observe that for every $y \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \{0\}$

$$\operatorname{div}_y \frac{y}{|y|^{2+s}} = -\frac{s}{|y|^{2+s}}.$$

Since by construction E is a Lipschitz set, we have that for σ^1 a.e. $y \in \partial E$ the outward unit normal $\nu_E(y)$ at E in y is well defined. Note that $\nu_E(y) = -\nu_{E^c}(y)$. Thus, applying the Divergence Theorem for Lipschitz sets we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} H_{\partial E}^s(0) &= \frac{1}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \left(- \int_{E^c \setminus B_\varepsilon} \operatorname{div}_y \frac{y}{|y|^{2+s}} dy + \int_{E \setminus B_\varepsilon} \operatorname{div}_y \frac{y}{|y|^{2+s}} dy \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \left(- \int_{\partial(E^c \setminus B_\varepsilon)} \frac{\langle \nu_{E^c \setminus B_\varepsilon}(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 + \int_{\partial(E \setminus B_\varepsilon)} \frac{\langle \nu_{E \setminus B_\varepsilon}(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \left(- \int_{\partial E^c \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{\langle \nu_{E^c}(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 - \int_{E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon} \frac{\langle \nu_{B_\varepsilon}(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{\partial E \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{\langle \nu_E(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 + \int_{E \cap \partial B_\varepsilon} \frac{\langle \nu_{B_\varepsilon}(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \left(2 \int_{\partial E \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{\langle \nu_E(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon^{1+s}} (-\sigma^1(E \cap \partial B_\varepsilon) + \sigma^1(E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon)) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \left(2 \int_{\partial E \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{\langle \nu_E(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 + \frac{1}{\varepsilon^{1+s}} (-2\pi\varepsilon + 2\sigma^1(E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon)) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now, assuming that ε is small enough, by convexity of E we have that

$$(11.98) \quad \sigma^1(E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon) \geq \sigma^1(\{P_2 < 0\} \cap \partial B_\varepsilon) = \pi\varepsilon.$$

Also, thanks to (11.96), for some $c > 0$ uniform with respect to ε , we evince that

$$\begin{aligned} (11.99) \quad \sigma^1(E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon) &= \sigma^1(\{P_2 < f(P_1)\} \cap \partial B_\varepsilon) \\ &= \pi\varepsilon + \sigma^1(\{0 < P_2 < f(P_1)\} \cap \partial B_\varepsilon) \\ &\leq \pi\varepsilon + c(f(\varepsilon) + f(-\varepsilon)). \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to the twice differentiability of f in the origin, (11.97), and the assumption that $f(0) = f'(0) = 0$, we obtain that

$$f(\varepsilon) = f''(0)\varepsilon^2 + o(\varepsilon^2).$$

Similarly, one also computes

$$f'(-\varepsilon) = f''(0)\varepsilon^2 + o(\varepsilon^2).$$

Therefore, using these last two equations, (11.98) and (11.99) we infer that

$$\pi\varepsilon \leq \sigma^1(E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon) \leq \pi\varepsilon + O(\varepsilon^2).$$

These estimates allow us to conclude that

$$0 \leq (-2\pi\varepsilon + 2\sigma^1(E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon)) \leq O(\varepsilon^2),$$

from which we evince that

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{1}{\varepsilon^{1+s}} (-2\pi\varepsilon + 2\sigma^1(E^c \cap \partial B_\varepsilon)) = 0.$$

In particular, this means that

$$\begin{aligned} H_{\partial E}^s(0) &= \frac{2}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\partial E \setminus B_\varepsilon} \frac{\langle \nu_E(y), y \rangle}{|y|^{2+s}} d\sigma^1 \\ &= \frac{2}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \gamma^{-1}(B_\varepsilon \cap \gamma(\mathbb{S}^1))} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) \rangle}{|\gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \\ &= \frac{2}{s} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1 \setminus B_\varepsilon(x)} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) \rangle}{|\gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \\ &=: \frac{2}{s} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(y)), \gamma(y) \rangle}{|\gamma(y)|^{2+s}} dy \end{aligned}$$

where the penultimate identity is due to the fact that $f' \in L^\infty(B_\varepsilon)$. □

Remark 11.40. It is important to observe that (11.17) holds true also under different hypothesis on E and γ .

For instance, let $E \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be convex and with nonempty interior. Also, let $\gamma : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ be BiLipschitz and $|\gamma'| = 1$ a.e. in \mathbb{R} , satisfying the convexity assumption in (11.14) in \mathbb{R} . Then, thanks to Theorem 11.38, up to a rotation of γ , for every $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ there exists some neighbourhood U_{x_0} and a convex function $f : \gamma_1(U_{x_0}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\gamma(t) = (\gamma_1(t), f(\gamma_1(t))) \quad \text{for all } t \in U_{x_0}.$$

Then, following almost verbatim the proof of Proposition 11.11, we obtain that for all $x \in U_{x_0}$ where f admits a second order Taylor expansion it holds that

$$H_{\partial E}^s((x, f(x))) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{\langle n(\gamma(t)), \gamma(t) - (x, f(x)) \rangle}{|\gamma(t) - (x, f(x))|^{2+s}} dt,$$

where (up to replacing $\gamma(\cdot)$ with $\gamma(-\cdot)$) $n(\gamma(t)) := \gamma'(t)^\perp$ for a.e. $t \in \mathbb{R}$.

The covering argument: Locally uniform smallness

In what follows we show locally uniform smallness for sequences of functions with uniformly bounded global integral energy. This is a standard covering argument, see for instance [SU81] Proposition 4.3 and Theorem 4.4. For the sake of completeness we provide here a proof of the result.

Proposition 11.41. *For any $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\Lambda > 0$ there exists $L = L(\varepsilon, \Lambda)$ such that the following holds.*

For any sequence $F_k : \mathbb{S}^1 \times \mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$\sup_k \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \leq \Lambda,$$

there exists a subsequence (still denoted by F_k) and set $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{S}^1$ consisting of at most L points such that for any $x_0 \in \mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \Sigma$ there exists a radius $\rho = \rho_{x_0} > 0$ and an index $K \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\sup_{k \geq K} \int_{\mathbb{S}^1} \left(\int_{B(x_0, \rho)} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx < \varepsilon$$

and

$$\sup_{k \geq K} \int_{B(x_0, \rho)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{S}^1} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx < \varepsilon.$$

Proof. We give the details for the convenience of the reader, but only consider the first inequality, since an easy adaptation implies that the first and second inequality hold simultaneously.

Pick $\delta \ll \frac{\varepsilon}{2^p \Lambda}$ and let $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, cover \mathbb{S}^1 by finitely many intervals $B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})$ such that every point $x \in \mathbb{S}^1$ is covered at most two times. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\sum_i \int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \\ & \leq 2^p \Lambda = \frac{2^p \Lambda}{\varepsilon} \varepsilon. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} (a_i)^p \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} a_i \right)^p$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_i \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \\ & \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\sum_i \int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \\ & \leq 2^p \Lambda. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, for every k and any m there exist at most $L := L(\varepsilon, \Lambda) := \lfloor \frac{2^p \Lambda}{\varepsilon} \rfloor$ intervals $B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})$ such that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \geq \varepsilon.$$

Next, we observe that for any fixed m we can pass to a subsequence of $(F_k)_k$ (not relabelled) so that

$$\#\{i : \sup_k \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \geq \varepsilon\} \leq L.$$

This is true since for any k there are only L many intervals for which

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \geq \varepsilon.$$

We can then pass to a further subsequence such that for any m there exists a $K = K(m)$ for which

$$\#\{i : \sup_{k \geq K(m)} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \geq \varepsilon\} \leq L.$$

Set

$$\Sigma_m := \mathbb{S}^1 \setminus \{x \in B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m}) : \text{for some } i \text{ with } \int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \leq \varepsilon\}.$$

Then, we obtain

$$\Sigma_m \subset \bigcup_{\ell=1}^L B(x_{i_\ell}, \delta 2^{-m}).$$

Nesting the balls $B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})$ as $m \rightarrow \infty$ we can ensure that $\Sigma_{m+1} \subset \Sigma_m$.

Set

$$\Sigma := \bigcap_m \Sigma_m.$$

Then, by the definition of the \mathcal{H}^0 -measure, since Σ is covered by Σ_m which consists of at most L intervals of sidelength $2^{-m}\delta$ (and this for each m) we have

$$\mathcal{H}^0(\Sigma) \leq L.$$

Also, if $x \notin \Sigma$ there must be some $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $x \notin \Sigma_m$, but $x \in B(x_{i,m}, \delta 2^{-m})$ for some $x_{i,m}$ such that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x_i, \delta 2^{-m})} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \leq \varepsilon.$$

But then for $\rho := \text{dist}(x, \partial B(x_{i,m}, \delta 2^{-m}))$ we have

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}} \left(\int_{B(x, \rho)} |F_k(x, y)| dy \right)^p dx \leq \varepsilon.$$

□

PART III

DENSITY ESTIMATES FOR (NON)LOCAL PHASE SEPARATION

INTRODUCTION TO PART III

Phase coexistence models were introduced in physics to study the interfaces between regions associated with different values of a suitable state parameter, see for instance [Row79; CH58; GP58].

All these models are described by some region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and a state parameter $u : \Omega \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, where the “pure phases” correspond in our setting to the values 1 and -1 , and the phase separation is induced by the minimization of a suitable energy functional.

The prototype of such an energy consists of a potential term and an interaction term. The role of the potential is to push the state parameter towards the pure phases, while the interaction term discourages the production of unneeded interfaces. More precisely, the potential term is often taken of the form

$$\int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) \, dx$$

with $W \geq 0$ and $W(t) > 0 = W(1) = W(-1)$ for any $t \in (-1, 1)$ and a natural candidate for the interaction is the Dirichlet integral

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^2 \, dx.$$

With these choices, the energy for phase separation becomes

$$\mathcal{E}(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^2 \, dx + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) \, dx,$$

From one point of view, as expected from the shape of the potential W , a minimizer for \mathcal{E} will be more likely to attain values close to the pure phases, to reduce the overall contribution of W in Ω .

Yet, from another point of view, the interaction term penalizes “big jumps” of the state parameter. As a consequence of the simultaneous action of potential and kinetic term, the minimizer will be pushed to attain values close to the pure phases but in such a way that at large scales the portion of the domain where the state parameter jumps from one pure phase to the other is negligible.

A common question in physics and mathematics is related to the geometrical features of these interfaces as we “zoom out”. An interesting approach to this problem is provided by density estimates.

12.1 Density estimates

The purpose of density estimates is to provide lower bounds for the measure of the portion of the domain characterized by values of the minimizers (of the energy inducing the phase separation) close to the pure phases.

The first result in this direction is due to L. Caffarelli and A. Córdoba. In the work [CC95], they proved density estimates for the energy functional

$$\mathcal{E}(u, \Omega) := \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^2 dx + \int_{\Omega} W(x, u(x)) dx,$$

where, for some $\theta \in (0, 1)$, W belongs to a class \mathcal{S}_{θ} characterized by potentials with quadratic (or less than quadratic) growth from their minima. For further details on \mathcal{S}_{θ} , see conditions (i)-(iv) at page 2 in [CC95].

Theorem 12.1 (Theorem 1 in [CC95]). *Let $\theta \in (0, 1)$ and u with $|u| \leq 1$ be a local minimizer of $\mathcal{E}(\cdot, B_R)$, with $W \in \mathcal{S}_{\theta}$ and we assume that for some $\mu_0 > 0$*

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_1 \cap \{u > \theta\}) \geq \mu_0.$$

Then, for any $\rho > 1$ and for some $\tilde{C} > 0$ it holds that

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{\rho} \cap \{u > \theta\}) \geq \tilde{C}\rho^n.$$

In other words, state parameters close to the pure phases occupy a considerable portion of the domain.

Since the pioneering work of L. Caffarelli and A. Córdoba, density estimates have been used to study the interface convergence of minimizers and quasiminimizers of

a larger spectrum of local energy functionals related to phase separation, see for e.g. [PV05a; PV05b; Val01; FV08].

Nonlocal counterparts of the energies studied in [CC95; PV05b; PV05a; FV08; Val01] have already been considered in the literature. A common approach to generalize phase separation in a nonlocal framework is to replace the gradient term of L^p -type with the Gagliardo seminorm. With such a choice the interaction term in $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ reads as

$$\mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy$$

and the energy used to describe nonlocal phase separation becomes

$$(12.1) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

where $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$. Density estimates for the energy functional in (12.1) with $p = 2$ were proved in [AKS10] and [SV14]. We stress that also in those two papers W is taken to grow quadratically from its minimizers. For the precise conditions on W see equation (1.9) in [SV14] and (1) in [AKS10].

The cases $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ can be treated separately. As a matter of fact, in [AKS10] density estimates are proved for \mathcal{E}_s^2 for every $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ using the Sobolev inequality. This approach fails when $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ and in [SV14] a fine measure theoretic result is established, namely Theorem 1.6 in [SV14], to obtain density estimates for every $s \in (0, 1)$. The statement of such a result is the following:

Theorem 12.2 (Theorem 1.4 in [SV14]). *Let u be a minimizer of \mathcal{E}_s^2 in B_R . Then, for any $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, 1)$ such*

$$u(0) > \theta_1$$

we have that

$$\mathcal{L}^n(\{u > \theta_2\} \cap B_R) \geq \bar{c}R^n$$

if $R \geq \bar{R}(\theta_1, \theta_2)$. The constant $\bar{c} > 0$ depends only on n, s and W and $\bar{R}(\theta_1, \theta_2)$ is a large constant that depends also on θ_1 and θ_2 .

12.2 Density estimates with degenerate double-well potential

In all the aforementioned results on density estimates, the potential W is taken such that its growth from the minima is comparable to a polynomial of degree m , where $m \in (1, p]$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$ is the homogeneity of the gradient term.

Potentials that detach from their minima with $m > p$ are known as *degenerate potentials*.

These potentials provide an interesting topic of research, since a very slow growth from the minima might affect phase separation and induce, in some cases, the formation of “intermediate phases”. To picture this, we may consider the extreme situation where for some $a \in (0, 1)$ and every $x \in (-1, 1)$ the potential is given by $W(x) := \chi_{[-a, a]}(x)$. Then, in this case, the minimizer will occupy values close to $-a$ and a to reduce the interaction, while the state parameters with value in $(-1, -a)$ and $(a, 1)$ become empty violating density estimates. This shows that to obtain density estimates some assumptions on W are necessary.

Such a problem has been first addressed in [DFV18]. There the authors considered an energy functional of the form

$$(12.2) \quad \mathcal{E}_\Omega(u) := \int_\Omega E(x, u(x), \nabla u(x)) \, dx$$

where for any $x, \xi \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$ it holds that

$$(12.3) \quad \lambda (|\xi|^p + |\tau + 1|^m) \leq E(x, \tau, \xi) \leq \Lambda (|\xi|^p + |\tau + 1|^m),$$

for some $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, $\Lambda \in [1, +\infty)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $m \in (p, +\infty)$.

In [DFV18], the authors established density estimates for quasiminimizers of \mathcal{E}_Ω , provided the parameters m , p and n satisfy some additional assumption.

Theorem 12.3 (Corollary 1.9 in [DFV18]). *Let $u \in W^{1, \infty}(\Omega, [-1, 1])$ be a Q -minimum in Ω for \mathcal{E}_Ω , with*

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta\}) \geq c_0$$

for some $\theta \in (-1, 1)$ and $c_0, r_0 > 0$ with $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$. Assume that

$$(12.4) \quad \frac{pm}{m-p} > n.$$

Then, for any $\Theta \in (-1, 1)$ there exists $\hat{r}, \hat{c} > 0$, possibly depending on $\lambda, \Lambda, \theta, \Theta, n, m, p, Q, r_0, c_0$ and $\|u\|_{W^{1,\infty}(\Omega)}$ such that for any $r \geq \hat{r}$ for which $B_r \subset \Omega$ it holds that

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \Theta\}) \geq \hat{c}r^n.$$

Such a result has been proved with an additional condition on the exponents m and p . Indeed, we observe that $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in (p, +\infty)$ and n must satisfy the inequality in (12.4). It is an open problem to understand whether this condition is optimal or not, see Remark 1.7 in [DFV18]. The optimality of (12.4) will be addressed in Chapter 14 for minimizers of a functional of the form (12.2)-(12.3). To achieve this, we will first establish density estimates for minimizers of a nonlocal counterpart of \mathcal{E}_Ω and then deduce local density estimates through a Γ -convergence method for $s \rightarrow 1$. This will be outlined at the end of this section, see Theorem 12.8.

In Chapter 13 we obtain density estimates for minimizers of the functional in (12.1), when the potential W is degenerate. To achieve this result, the Sobolev inequality will be employed. Analogously to the case $p = 2$ dealt with in [AKS10] and [SV14], this approach only works if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$. The case $s \in [\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ is treated in Chapter 14.

To fix the ideas, we consider $W \in C^1([-1, 1], \mathbb{R}^+)$ such that for some $\lambda \in (0, 1]$, $\Lambda \in [1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$ and for every $x \in [-1, 1]$,

$$(12.5) \quad \lambda |1 + x|^m \leq W(x) \leq \Lambda |1 + x|^m.$$

Moreover, we assume that, for some $q \in (0, 1)$, $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$ and for every $x \in (-1, -1 + q)$

$$(12.6) \quad c_1 |1 + x|^{m-1} \leq W'(x).$$

Then, the main result of Chapter 13 are the following density estimates:

Theorem 12.4 (Corollary 13.5 in Chapter 13). *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$ and $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, 1)$.*

Assume that u is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p in Ω and that, for some $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$,

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) > c_0.$$

Then, there exist $\tilde{R} := \tilde{R}_{s,n,p,m,\theta_1,\theta_2,r_0,\lambda} \in [r_0, +\infty)$ and $\hat{c} := \hat{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_1,\theta_2,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ such that, for any $r \in [\tilde{R}, +\infty)$ with $B_{\frac{3r}{2}} \subset \Omega$,

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) \geq \hat{c} r^n.$$

In Chapter 14, we extend Theorem 12.4 to the case $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $s \in [\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ and for a class of state parameters containing all minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p , see Theorem 12.6 below.

Moreover, we will use such an extension together with a Γ -convergence argument to obtain local density estimates from the nonlocal ones, see Theorem 12.8 below. As aforementioned, this will allow us to address the optimality of the condition between m, p and n in (12.4).

To do so, we consider the energy functional

$$(12.7) \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p(u, \Omega) := (1 - s)\mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx.$$

The potential W will be taken to satisfy the degenerate condition in (12.5). Moreover, we assume that for all $-1 \leq r \leq t \leq -1 + q$

$$(12.8) \quad W(t) - W(r) \geq c_1(t - r) |1 + r|^{m-1} + c_1(t - r)^k$$

for some $q \in (0, 1)$ and $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$, where

$$k := \begin{cases} m & \text{if } m \in \mathbb{N} \\ [m] + 1 & \text{if } m \in (1, +\infty) \setminus \mathbb{N}. \end{cases}$$

Also, we introduce the new class of state parameters, which includes all minimizers of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$:

Definition 12.5 (ε -minimizer). If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is bounded, given $\varepsilon \in [0, +\infty)$, we say that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is an ε -minimizer for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$ if, for every $v \in X_u^{s,p}(\Omega)$,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p(u, \Omega) \leq \varepsilon + \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p(v, \Omega).$$

If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is unbounded, we say that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is an ε -minimizer for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega)$ if for any $\Omega' \subset\subset \Omega$ it is a minimizer of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega')$.

Then, the main result of Chapter 14 is the following:

Theorem 12.6 (Theorem 14.4 & 14.7 in Chapter 14). *Let $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, 1)$ and u be such that*

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) > c_0,$$

for some $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$.

Then, there exists $\delta := \delta_{s,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_1,\theta_2,q,c_0} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, if $\varepsilon \in [0, \delta)$ and u is an ε -minimizer for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$, the following holds true:

There exist $R^* := R_{s,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_1,\theta_2,q,r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_1,\theta_2,q,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ and $c := c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for any $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{3r} \subset \Omega$,

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) > \tilde{c}r^n.$$

As aforementioned, this result represents an extension of the density estimates stated in Theorem 12.4, which were obtained only for $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$.

Indeed, for $\varepsilon = 0$, in Theorem 12.6 we obtain density estimates for minimizers of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$ (and therefore also for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p) when $s \in [\frac{1}{p}, 1)$.

It is also important to observe that if $\varepsilon > 0$, then Theorem 14.4 is new for every $s \in (0, 1)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$.

We notice that the structural constants δ , R^* and \tilde{c} in Theorem 12.6 depend on s . In Chapter 14, we show that under some additional regularity assumptions on the ε -minimizers, the density estimates are stable for s close to 1.

To be more precise, in Theorem 14.5, for $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ and $s \in [s_0, 1)$, we show that density estimates hold with structural constants which can be chosen independently from s , but depending on s_0 . The proof of this result relies on the additional regularity assumption that the ε -minimizer is Hölder continuous.

We also mention that from Theorem 14.5 one can establish density estimates for minimizers of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$ that are stable as $s \rightarrow 1$ and do not require any additional assumption on the regularity of the minimizer. Indeed, it is well known that minimizers for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$ are Hölder continuous, see for instance [IMS16; BLS18; Coz17] and the references therein. In particular in [Coz17], using fractional De Giorgi classes, M. Cozzi proved Hölder estimates for minimizers of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$ that do not depend on s whenever $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $s \in [s_0, 1)$ and $n \geq 2$, see Theorem 6.4 and Proposition 7.5 in [Coz17]. In particular we have the following:

Theorem 12.7 (Corollary 14.8 in Chapter 14). *Let $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, 1)$, $n \geq 2$, $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ and $s \in [s_0, 1)$. Also, let $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ be a minimizer for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$. Moreover, let $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ be such that $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$*

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) > c_0,$$

Then, there exists $R^ := R_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1, \theta_1, \theta_2, q, r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$ and $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s_0, n, p, m, \Lambda, c_1, \theta_1, \theta_2, q, r_0, c_0} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for any $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$*

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) > \tilde{c}r^n.$$

As we have already mentioned, in Chapter 14 we also address the problem of the optimality of the condition in (12.4). To do so, we consider the energy

$$\mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{K_{n,p}}{2p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^p dx + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx$$

for a suitable $K_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$, and a degenerate potential W satisfying (12.5) and (12.8). We observe that with such conditions \mathcal{E}_1^p takes the form (12.2)-(12.3).

Then, in Theorem 14.9 in Chapter 14, we show that the functional in (12.7) Γ -converges to \mathcal{E}_1^p for $s \rightarrow 1$. Making use of this result, together with the stable density estimates for ε -minimizers stated in Theorem 14.5, we manage to prove that the condition in (12.4) is not sharp, and as a matter of fact density estimates for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_1^p hold for every $n, p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$.

The statement of the result is the following:

Theorem 12.8 (Theorem 14.10 in Chapter 14 and Corollary 1.9 in [DFV18]). *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be open and bounded, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$ and $\theta \in (-1, 1)$. Moreover, we assume that u is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_1^p in $X^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and for some $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$*

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta\}) \geq c_0.$$

Then, for every $\Theta \in (-1, 1)$ there exist $R^ \geq r_0$ and $\tilde{c} \in (0, 1)$, possibly depending on $\lambda, \Lambda, \theta, \Theta, n, m, p, Q, r_0, c_0$ and c_1 , such that for every $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ for which $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,*

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \Theta\}) > \tilde{c}r^n$$

DENSITY ESTIMATES FOR A
NONLOCAL VARIATIONAL MODEL
WITH DEGENERATE DOUBLE-WELL
POTENTIAL VIA THE SOBOLEV
INEQUALITY

We provide density estimates for level sets of minimizers of the energy

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx$$

where $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$ and W is a double-well potential with polynomial growth $m \in [p, +\infty)$ from the minima.

These kinds of potentials are “degenerate”, since they detach “slowly” from the minima, therefore they provide additional difficulties if one wishes to determine the relative sizes of the “layers” and the “pure phases”. To overcome these challenges, we introduce new barriers allowing us to rely on the fractional Sobolev inequality and on a suitable iteration method.

The proofs presented here are robust enough to consider the case of quasilinear nonlocal equations driven by the fractional p -Laplacian, but our results are new even for the case $p = 2$.

13.1 Introduction

Phase coexistence models were introduced in physics to study the interfaces between regions associated with different values of a suitable state parameter, such as the density of a fluid in capillarity phenomena [Row79], the fraction of volume occupied by two different materials in a non homogeneous system [CH58], or the density of the superfluid component of helium [GP58]. Since these early works, phase coexistence models have been developed to describe a variety of physical systems characterized by the interaction of two or more components.

All these models are described by some region $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and a state parameter $u : \Omega \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, where the “pure phases” correspond in our setting to the values 1 and -1 , and the phase separation is induced by the minimization of a suitable energy functional.

The prototype of such an energy consists of a potential and an interaction term. The role of the potential term is to push the state parameter towards the pure phases, while the interaction term discourages the production of unneeded interfaces by suitably “shaping” the portions of the domain in which the value of the state parameter is either 1 or -1 (or is “sufficiently close” to these values).

In the local setting, the interaction energy is proportional to a gradient term of L^p -type with $p \in (1, +\infty)$, see for instance [AC81; ACF84; Bou90; PV05a; PV05b]. In order to capture long-range interactions, in the nonlocal framework the L^p -norm of the gradient has been replaced by the Gagliardo seminorm, see for instance [PSV13; AKS10; SV14]. For further references regarding local and nonlocal phase separation models we refer to the survey [DV23].

The potential energy is given by the L^1 -norm of a “double-well” function W whose absolute minima are the pure phases. More precisely, $W : [-1, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies

$$(13.1) \quad W(t) > 0 \quad \text{for every } t \in (-1, 1) \quad \text{and} \quad W(\pm 1) = 0.$$

In the study of phase coexistence models, it is often desirable to quantify the size of the transition layer with respect to that of the pure phases (or, more precisely, of the regions close to pure phases). This is important since, due to the complexity of the problem, it is often difficult, when not impossible, to have general descriptions of the interfaces and the best one can do is typically to describe the phase separation

“in a measure theoretic sense” and conclude that, at a large scale, most of the space is occupied by state parameters close to pure phases, separated by “thin” interfaces. In this spirit, the study of density estimates, namely of obtaining sharp quantifications of the measure of the interface, happens to be quite a cross-disciplinary topic, involving, under various perspectives, mathematical analysis, statistical mechanics, and materials sciences.

In the framework of density estimates a common hypothesis on the potential is that its growth from the minima is comparable to a polynomial of degree m , where $m \in (0, p]$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$ is the exponent of the interaction term, see for instance formula (1.10) in [PV05a] for the local case and formula (1.9) in [SV14] for the nonlocal one.

In the current chapter, we consider the energy functional

$$(13.2) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx$$

where W presents a polynomial growth from the minima -1 and 1 of degree $m \in [p, +\infty)$. We will refer to these potentials as “degenerate”, since they have a “slow” growth rate from their minima (in particular, slower than the homogeneity of the associated interaction energy).

In particular, we prove density estimates for every $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$, see Theorem 13.3 below. The precise hypothesis on W , the statement of Theorem 13.3 and its corollaries are all discussed in Section 13.1. In what follows, we introduce the concept of density estimate and we present in more detail the implications of the presence of a degenerate double-well potential.

Density estimates

To establish a conceptual framework in a model case, let us consider the prototype energy functional

$$(13.3) \quad \mathcal{E}(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^2 dx + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

with W satisfying the assumptions in (13.1) and “nondegenerate” (in the sense that W detaches at least quadratically from its minima). From one point of view,

as expected from the shape of the potential W , a minimizer for \mathcal{E} will be more likely to attain values close to the pure phases, to reduce the overall contribution of W in Ω . Yet, from another point of view, the interaction term penalizes “big jumps” of the state parameter. As a consequence of this simultaneous action, the minimizer will be pushed to attain values close to the pure phases but in such a way that at large scales the portion of the domain where the state parameter jumps from one pure phase to the other is negligible.

A common question in physics and mathematics is related to the geometrical features of these interfaces as we “zoom out”. So far, there have been two approaches to this question: one exploiting Γ -convergence and the other relying on density estimates.

On the one hand, the idea behind Γ -convergence is to analyse the limit functional obtained by suitably rescaling the minimizers of \mathcal{E} and deduce qualitative information regarding the interfaces at large scales. In particular, if u minimizes \mathcal{E} in Ω , then for $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ we consider the rescaled state parameter

$$u_\varepsilon(x) := u\left(\frac{x}{\varepsilon}\right).$$

In [MM77], and later in greater generality in [Bou90], it is proved that there exists some set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ such that as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ the minimizers u_ε converge, up to a subsequence, in $L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$ to¹ a step function $u_0 := \chi_E - \chi_{E^c}$. Interestingly, the interface ∂E is a minimal surface, namely a minimizer of the perimeter functional.

On the other hand, the purpose of density estimates is to provide lower bounds for the measure of the portion of the domain characterized by values of the minimizers of \mathcal{E} close to the pure phases. The first result in this direction is due to L. Caffarelli and A. Córdoba. In [CC95] they prove that if $u : \Omega \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ minimizes \mathcal{E} , then, for any $\theta \in (-1, 1)$ and $r \in (0, +\infty)$ sufficiently large, one has that $\{|u| > \theta\} \cap B_r$ is comparable to r^n (i.e., to the volume of the full ball B_r), while $\{|u| \leq \theta\} \cap B_r$ is bounded from above by a constant times r^{n-1} (corresponding, for example, to

¹As usual, we denote here by χ_A the characteristic function (or indicator function) of the set A , namely

$$\chi_A(a) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } a \in A, \\ 0 & \text{if } a \notin A. \end{cases}$$

the $(n - 1)$ -dimensional surface measure in B_r of a hyperplane passing through the origin). In other words, state parameters close to the pure phases occupy a considerable portion of the domain, while the interface is negligible in the sense of measure.

As a consequence, as the scale parameter $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ approaches zero, the set $\{|u_\varepsilon| \leq \theta\} \cap B_r$ converges in the Hausdorff distance to the hypersurface ∂E . More specifically, for any $\delta, R > 0$ there exists $\varepsilon_0 := \varepsilon_0(\delta, R) > 0$ such that, for any $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$,

$$\{|u_\varepsilon| \leq \theta\} \cap B_R \subset \bigcup_{x \in \partial E} B_\delta(x).$$

Since the pioneering work of L. Caffarelli and A. Córdoba, density estimates have been used to study the interface convergence of minimizers and quasiminimizers of a larger spectrum of energy functionals related to phase separation. In [PV05a] and [PV05b] gradient terms of L^p -type with $p \in (1, +\infty)$ are considered, together also with χ -shaped potentials W , namely $W(x) := \chi_{(-1,1)}(x)Q(x)$ with Q uniformly bounded away from zero. This type of potentials are related to models for fluid jets and capillarity phenomena; see also [Val01] for the elliptic case. In [FV08] density estimates are also proved under the weaker assumption of quasiminimality.

As already mentioned, nonlocal counterparts of (13.3) have been dealt with in the literature. A consolidated choice consists in replacing the L^2 -norm of the gradient with the Gagliardo seminorm. In [SV12] and [SV14], for $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, nonlocal phase separation was examined for the energy

$$(13.4) \quad \mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^2(u, \Omega) := \varepsilon^{2s} \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dx dy \right) + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx.$$

More precisely, in [SV12] it is proved that, by suitably scaling the energy in (13.4) by some factor depending on ε and s , as ε vanishes, the minimizers are compact and the rescaled energy Γ -converges (to a functional of geometric flavor which we discuss below). Such a gauge is proved to be ε^{-2s} , $\varepsilon^{-1}|\log(\varepsilon)|$ and ε^{-1} respectively for the cases $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, $s = \frac{1}{2}$ and $s \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$.

Interestingly, in Theorem 1.4 of [SV12], it is established that if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, then $\varepsilon^{-2s} \mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^2$ Γ -converges as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ to the nonlocal perimeter $\text{Per}_s(\cdot, \Omega)$ in Ω , defined for every measurable set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Per}_s(E, \Omega) := & \int_{E \cap \Omega} \int_{E^c \cap \Omega} \frac{dx dy}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} + \int_{E \cap \Omega^c} \int_{E^c \cap \Omega} \frac{dx dy}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} \\ & + \int_{E \cap \Omega} \int_{E^c \cap \Omega^c} \frac{dx dy}{|x - y|^{n+2s}}. \end{aligned}$$

Additionally, in [SV12] it is proved that if $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ the Γ -limit coincides with the classical perimeter. Surprisingly, this means that in the regime $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ and at large scales the effect of the Gagliardo seminorm on the interfaces is similar to the one of the L^2 -norm of the gradient and the phase separation resembles the classical one.

In this sense, the case $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ (when $p = 2$, or, more generally, the case $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ when $p \in (1, +\infty)$) is considered as “genuinely nonlocal”, since the problem retains its nonlocal features at every scale.

For what concerns density estimates, the cases $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ and $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ can be treated separately. As a matter of fact, in [AKS10] density estimates are proved for the functional in (13.4) for every $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ using the Sobolev inequality. This approach fails when $s \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ and in [SV14] a fine measure theoretic result is established, namely Theorem 1.6 in [SV14], to obtain density estimates for every $s \in (0, 1)$, see Theorem 1.4 in [SV14].

The Sobolev inequality will be employed also in the current chapter to obtain density estimates for the energy in (13.2). Analogously to the case $p = 2$ dealt with in [AKS10] and [SV14], this approach only works if $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$. The case $s \in [\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ will be treated in Chapter 14.

Degenerate double-well potentials

An interesting problem surrounding the topic of density estimates is how the growth from the minima of the double-well potential W might affect phase separation. For example, a slow growth might induce, in some cases, the formation of “intermediate phases”. To picture this, we may consider the extreme situation where, for some $a \in$

$(0, 1)$ and every $x \in (-1, 1)$, the potential is given by

$$(13.5) \quad W(x) := \chi_{[-a, a]}(x),$$

see Figure 13.1. In this case, the minimizer will occupy values close to $-a$ and a to reduce the interaction, whether this is prompted by a nonlocal or local type of interaction term, while the state parameters with value in $(-1, -a)$ and $(a, 1)$ become empty, violating density estimates. In particular, this shows that to obtain density estimates some assumptions on W are necessary.

As already mentioned, a common hypothesis on the potential is that if $p \in (1, +\infty)$ is the exponent of the interaction term, then, for some $m \in (0, p]$, $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and $\Lambda \in [1, +\infty)$, and every $x \in (-1, 1)$,

$$(13.6) \quad \lambda(1 - x^2)^m \leq W(x) \leq \Lambda(1 - x^2)^m.$$

This corresponds, in the framework of this chapter, to a nondegenerate double-well potential, since the growth from the potential's minima is not larger than the homogeneity of the interaction term. In particular, in the classical case of a gradient term of L^2 -type this translates into a (sub)quadratic growth, see [CC95]. In such a case, a common double-well potential in the literature is

$$(13.7) \quad W(x) := \frac{(1 - x^2)^2}{4}.$$

In view of (13.6) and (13.7), for $m \in [p, +\infty)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$ it is natural to define

$$(13.8) \quad W(x) := \frac{(1 - x^2)^m}{2m}$$

as a prototype of a degenerate double-well potential. See Figure 13.1 for a comparison with the potential in (13.7).

Of course, the conditions in (13.6) may be too restrictive, and density estimates may still hold for double-well potentials with a flatter profile close to the minima. This problem has been first addressed in the local setting in [DFV18], where the authors prove density estimates for quasiminimizers of a phase transition energy driven by the L^p -norm of the gradient and with a degenerate double-well potential

Figure 13.1: Plots of $\chi_{[-1/2, 1/2]}(x)$, $(1-x^2)^2$ and $(1-x^2)^8$ respectively in green, blue and red.

of the type (13.8), as far as some condition on n , m and p are met, see equation (1.7) in [DFV18].

The aim of this chapter is to obtain density estimates for minimizers of the energy in (13.2), when the potential W presents a polynomial growth from the minima comparable to the one of the degenerate potential in (13.8).

In the following section we introduce all the necessary mathematical notation, state precisely the main results and provide the structure of the chapter.

Mathematical framework and main results

In what follows $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is open, $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right)$. We consider $W \in C^1([-1, 1], \mathbb{R}^+)$ such that for some $\theta \in (-1, 1)$, $\lambda \in (0, 1]$, $\Lambda \in [1, +\infty)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$, for every $x \in [-1, 1]$,

$$(13.9) \quad \lambda \chi_{(-\infty, \theta]}(x) |1+x|^m \leq W(x) \leq \Lambda |1+x|^m.$$

Moreover, we assume that, for some $q \in (0, \theta + 1] \cap (0, 1)$ and $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$, for every $x \in (-1, -1+q)$,

$$(13.10) \quad c_1 |1+x|^{m-1} \leq W'(x).$$

Note that the prototype of a degenerate double-well potential in (13.8) satisfies (13.9) and (13.10).

Also, for every measurable function $u : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we define

$$(13.11) \quad \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy$$

and rewrite the energy in (13.2) as

$$(13.12) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx.$$

Furthermore, in analogy with [SV12], for every $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, we consider the rescaled energy

$$(13.13) \quad \mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p(u, \Omega) := \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) + \varepsilon^{-sp} \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx.$$

A convenient function space to study \mathcal{K}_s^p is

$$\widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega) := \{u : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ measurable s.t. } \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) < +\infty\}.$$

Note that $W^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^n) \subset \widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega)$. Since W is defined in the interval $[-1, 1]$, we consider the subspace of all those functions $u \in \widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega)$ such that $|u| \leq 1$ a.e., namely

$$(13.14) \quad X^{s,p}(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in \widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } \|u\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq 1 \right\}.$$

With these choices we have the following definition:

Definition 13.1 (Minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p and $\mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p$). If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is bounded, we say that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is a minimizer for $\mathcal{E}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega)$ in $X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ if

$$\mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) \leq \mathcal{E}_s^p(v, \Omega)$$

for any $v \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ such that $v \equiv u$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega$.

If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is unbounded, we say that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is a minimizer for $\mathcal{E}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega)$ in $X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ if it minimizes $\mathcal{E}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega')$ in $X^{s,p}(\Omega')$ for every bounded and open set $\Omega' \Subset \Omega$.

Similarly, one also defines a minimizer for $\mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p$.

Remark 13.2. Note that if u minimizes \mathcal{E}_s^p (or $\mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p$) in an open and bounded set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, then it minimizes \mathcal{E}_s^p (or $\mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p$) in every measurable subset $\Omega' \subset \Omega$.

The main result of this chapter is the following density estimate:

Theorem 13.3 (Density estimates). *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right)$ and $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, \theta]$.*

Let also

$$(13.15) \quad \theta_* := \min \{ \theta_1, \theta_2, -1 + q \} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta^* := \max \{ \theta_1, \theta_2, -1 + q \}.$$

Assume that u is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p in Ω and that, for some $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$,

$$(13.16) \quad \mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) > c_0.$$

Then, there exist $R^* := R_{s,n,p,m,\theta_*,r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$, and $c := c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$, such that, for any $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ with $B_{\frac{3r}{2}} \subset \Omega$,

$$(13.17) \quad c \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) \geq \tilde{c} r^n.$$

Here above and in the rest of the chapter, $\mathcal{L}^n(E)$ denotes the Lebesgue measure of a set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$.

The proof of the density estimates in Theorem 13.3 relies on the construction of a suitable barrier (see Theorem 13.10 below) that is inspired by Lemma 3.1 in [SV14], where a barrier is built in the case $p = 2$ and $m = 2$. The extension to the cases $p \neq 2$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$ that we provide in this chapter is nontrivial, due to the nonlinearity of the operator and the presence of a degenerate potential. In the case of the classical p -Laplacian, barriers have been built in [VSS06] in a different context. The case $p = 2$ in the nonlocal setting with a degenerate potential has been also considered in [DP+].

The presence of the first term in the left-hand side of (14.14) is a consequence of the weak lower bound in (13.9). More precisely, under some additional assumptions on the lower bound for W (see (13.19) below) it is possible to reabsorb such term in the right hand-side of the inequality, obtaining the “full density estimates”. This is made possible thanks to the following upper bound on the energy \mathcal{E}_s^p . Its proof is contained in Chapter 14.

Theorem 13.4 (Theorem 14.7 in Chapter 14). *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$ and u be a minimizer of \mathcal{E}_s^p in $X^{s,p}(B_{R+2})$ with $R \geq 2$. Then, there exists $\bar{C} > 0$, depending only on s, n, p, m and Λ , such that*

$$(13.18) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, B_R) \leq \bar{C} R^{n-sp}.$$

From Theorems 13.3 and 13.4 we obtain the following density estimate:

Corollary 13.5. *Let $\tilde{\theta}_1, \tilde{\theta}_2 \in (-1, 1)$ and u be as in the statement of Theorem 13.3.*

Assume that, for every $\mu \in (-1, 1)$, there exists $\lambda_\mu \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $x \in (-1, 1)$,

$$(13.19) \quad \lambda_\mu \chi_{(-\infty, \mu]}(x) |1 + x|^m \leq W(x).$$

Moreover, let θ_ and θ^* be as in (14.12).*

Then, there exist $\tilde{R} := \tilde{R}_{s,n,p,m,\theta_,r_0,\lambda_{\theta^*}} \in [r_0, +\infty)$ and $\hat{c} := \hat{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ such that, for any $r \in [\tilde{R}, +\infty)$ with $B_{\frac{3r}{2}} \subset \Omega$,*

$$(13.20) \quad \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) \geq \hat{c} r^n.$$

As already mentioned, an important consequence of the density estimates is the uniform convergence of the interface of the minimizers of the rescaled energy functional to a hypersurface. To prove this result we require an additional condition on the potential W . In particular, we assume that there exists some $c_2 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for every $x \in (-1, 1)$

$$(13.21) \quad W(x) \geq c_2(1 - x^2)^m.$$

Theorem 13.6 (Compactness). *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$ and W satisfy (13.21). Assume that the sequence $\{u_\varepsilon\}_\varepsilon \subset X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ satisfies*

$$(13.22) \quad \sup_{\varepsilon \in (0,1)} \mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p(u_\varepsilon, \Omega) < +\infty.$$

Then, there exists a measurable set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ such that, up to a subsequence,

$$(13.23) \quad u_\varepsilon \rightarrow u^* := \chi_E - \chi_{E^c} \quad \text{in} \quad L_{loc}^1(\Omega).$$

This compactness result is a consequence of the scaling chosen for $\mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p$. Indeed, it follows from (13.13) and (13.22) that the Gagliardo seminorm of u_ε is bounded on all compact subsets of Ω . Then, it is enough to use compact embeddings of $W^{s,p}$ to conclude.

As a byproduct of the density estimates in (13.20) and the compactness in Theorem 13.6 we obtain the Hausdorff convergence for the interfaces:

Corollary 13.7 (Hausdorff convergence). *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right)$, $c_3 \in (0, +\infty)$ and W satisfy (13.21) and $W(x) \leq c_3(1 - x^2)^m$ for every $x \in (-1, 1)$. For $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ let $\{u_\varepsilon\}_\varepsilon \subset X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ be such that u_ε is a minimizer of $\mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p$ in Ω and (13.22) holds. Moreover, let $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be as in the statement of Theorem 13.6.*

Then, for every $\Theta \in (0, 1)$, $\delta \in (0, +\infty)$, and $R \in (0, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_R \Subset \Omega$, there exists $\varepsilon_0 := \varepsilon_0(\Theta, \delta, R) > 0$ such that, if $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$,

$$\{|u_\varepsilon| < \Theta\} \cap B_R \subset \bigcup_{x \in \partial E} B_\delta(x).$$

We remark that the results presented in this chapter are stated and proved for all $p \in (1, +\infty)$, but they are new even for the case $p = 2$.

The rest of this chapter is structured as follows. In Section 13.2 we recall some known results that will be used in the proofs of the main statements. In Section 13.3 we construct a suitable barrier, see Theorem 13.10 below, which will be used to prove Theorem 13.3. The construction of this barrier relies also on some technical results that are collected in Appendix 13.6.

The proofs of Theorem 13.3 and Corollary 13.5 are contained in Section 13.4. Finally, in Section 13.5 we prove Theorem 13.6 and Corollary 13.7.

13.2 Some auxiliary results

In this section we recall some auxiliary results that will be used throughout the proofs of our main theorems.

A general estimate

The following statement is provided in Lemma 3.2. in [SV14]. We point out that by a careful inspection of the proof presented in [SV14] one can check that the dependence of the constants \tilde{c} and R_* is as claimed here below (this will be important in Chapter 14).

Lemma 13.8 (Lemma 3.2. in [SV14]). *Let $\sigma, R_0 \in (0, +\infty)$, $\nu \in (\sigma, +\infty)$ and $\gamma, \mu, C \in (1, +\infty)$.*

Let $V : (0, +\infty) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ be a nondecreasing function. For any $r \in [R_0, +\infty)$, let

$$\alpha(r) := \min \left\{ 1, \frac{\log(V(r))}{\log(r)} \right\}.$$

Also, suppose that

$$(13.24) \quad V(R_0) \geq \mu$$

and that, for any $r \in [R_0, +\infty)$,

$$(13.25) \quad r^\sigma \alpha(r) (V(r))^{\frac{\nu-\sigma}{\nu}} \leq C V(\gamma r).$$

Then, there exist $\tilde{c} \in (0, 1)$, depending on $C, \sigma, \mu, \gamma, \nu$ and R_0 , and $R_* \in [R_0, +\infty)$, depending on R_0 and γ , such that, for any $r \in [R_*, +\infty)$,

$$(13.26) \quad V(r) \geq \tilde{c} r^\nu.$$

Hölder regularity for minimizers

In what follows, we let $F \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$. Also, for every $u \in \widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega)$ we consider the renormalized energy

$$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_s^p(u, \Omega) := (1 - s) \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) + \int_\Omega F(u(x)) dx.$$

As customary, given some open set $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\beta \in (0, 1)$, we denote the Hölder seminorm of a function $f : B \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by

$$[f]_{C^\beta(B)} := \sup_{x,y \in B} \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|}{|x - y|^\beta}.$$

If $\beta = 1$, we denote the Lipschitz seminorm of $f : B \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by

$$[f]_{C^{0,1}(B)} := \sup_{x,y \in B} \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|}{|x - y|}.$$

Also, given $x_0 \in \Omega$ and $R \in (0, \text{dist}(x_0, \partial\Omega))$, we set

$$\text{Tail}(u, x_0, R) := \left[(1 - s) R^{sp} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R(x_0)} \frac{|u(y)|^{p-1}}{|y - x_0|^{n+sp}} \right]^{\frac{1}{p-1}}.$$

With this notation, we now recall the following result on the Hölder regularity for the minimizers of $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$. Such result is contained in [Coz17], where the Hölder regularity is established using fractional De Giorgi classes.

Theorem 13.9 (Theorem 6.4 and Proposition 7.5 in [Coz17]). *Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $s \in [s_0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$. Let $u \in \widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega)$ be a minimizer for $\widehat{\mathcal{E}}_s^p$ in Ω .*

Then, $u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$ for some $\alpha \in (0, 1)$.

Moreover, for any $x_0 \in \Omega$ and $R \in \left(0, \frac{\text{dist}(x_0, \partial\Omega)}{8}\right)$,

$$[u]_{C^\alpha(B_R(x_0))} \leq \frac{C}{R^\alpha} \left(\|u\|_{L^\infty(B_{4R}(x_0))} + \text{Tail}(u; x_0, 4R) + R^s \|F(u)\|_{L^\infty(B_{8R}(x_0))}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right)$$

for some $C \geq 1$.

The constants α and C depend only on n , p , s_0 when $n \geq 2$, and also on s when $n = 1$.

13.3 Construction of a suitable barrier

The following Theorem 13.10 is the extension to the cases $p \neq 2$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$ of Lemma 3.1 in [SV14].

We point out that, in our construction, the dependence of the constants with respect to s is explicit. In this way, as it will be discussed in detail in Chapter 14, it is possible to obtain density estimates that are stable as $s \rightarrow 1^-$, recovering local density estimates from the nonlocal ones.

In what follows, for every $t \in \mathbb{R}$ we denote by $[t]$ the integer part of t . Also, for every $z : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ measurable and $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, we denote its p -fractional Laplacian at $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ as

$$(-\Delta)_p^s z(x) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{(z(x) - z(y)) |z(x) - z(y)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy.$$

Throughout this section we will also make use of some technical results collected in Appendix 13.6.

Theorem 13.10. *For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\tau \in (0, +\infty)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$ there exists $\widehat{C}_{n,p,m} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if we define*

$$(13.27) \quad \bar{R} = \bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m} := \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{n,p,m}}{s(1-s)\tau} \right)^{\frac{1}{ps}}$$

the following statement holds true.

For every $R \in [\bar{R}, +\infty)$ there exists a rotationally symmetric function $w \in C(\mathbb{R}^n, (-1, 1])$ such that

$$(13.28) \quad w \equiv 1 \quad \text{in} \quad \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R$$

and, for every $x \in B_R$,

$$(13.29) \quad -(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) \leq \tau(1 + w(x))^{m-1}.$$

Also, if we set $q := \frac{p}{m-1}$ and

$$(13.30) \quad C_{s,\tau,n,p,m} := 2^{q+1} \max \{1, \bar{R}^{qs}\},$$

then, for every $x \in B_R$,

$$(13.31) \quad 1 + w(x) \leq \frac{C_{s,\tau,n,p,m}}{(1 + R - |x|)^{qs}}.$$

The proof of Theorem 13.10 will be based on the following construction. We take a large $r \in [1, +\infty)$, to be conveniently chosen with respect to R and τ here below (see formula (13.67)).

We consider the integer quantity

$$(13.32) \quad k = k(s, p) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } p \in (1, 2) \text{ and } s \in \left(0, \frac{p-1}{2p}\right), \\ \left\lfloor \frac{sp}{p-1} \right\rfloor + 1 & \text{if } p \in (1, 2) \text{ and } s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{2p}, 1\right), \\ 1 & \text{if } p \in [2, +\infty) \text{ and } s \in (0, 1). \end{cases}$$

We set $q := \frac{p}{m-1}$ and we define, for every $t \in (0, r)$,

$$(13.33) \quad \begin{aligned} g(t) &:= t^{-qs} \\ \text{and } f(t) &:= g(r-t) + \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{i+1}}{i!} g^{(i)}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right) \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^i. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we also define the functions

$$(13.34) \quad h(t) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \in (0, r/2], \\ \min \{f(t), 1\} & \text{if } t \in (r/2, r), \\ 1 & \text{if } t \in [r, +\infty) \end{cases}$$

$$\text{and } v(x) := h(|x|) \quad \text{for every } x \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

We provide the following estimate for the function h :

Proposition 13.11. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$ and $q := \frac{p}{m-1}$. Let $h : (0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be as in (13.34).*

Then, there exists $\bar{c}_{k,q,s} \in (1, +\infty)$ such that, for every $t \in (0, +\infty)$,

$$(13.35) \quad \min \{1, (r - t)^{-ps}\} \leq (h(t) + \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs})^{m-1}.$$

Proof. We observe that if $t \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$ and $h(t) < 1$, then

$$(13.36) \quad \begin{aligned} h(t) &= f(t) \\ &= g(r - t) + \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{i+1}}{i!} g^{(i)}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right) \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^i \\ &\geq (r - t)^{-qs} - \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{|g^{(i)}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right)|}{i!} \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^i \\ &\geq (r - t)^{-qs} - \sum_{i=0}^k c_{q,s,i} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-i} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^i \\ &= (r - t)^{-qs} - c_{k,q,s} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(13.37) \quad c_{q,s,i} := \frac{\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (qs + j)}{i!} \quad \text{and} \quad c_{k,q,s} := \sum_{i=0}^k c_{q,s,i}.$$

On this account, if $t \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$ and $h(t) < 1$ and we adopt the notation

$$(13.38) \quad \tilde{c}_{k,q,s} := 2^{qs} c_{k,q,s},$$

we can use (13.36) to deduce that

$$(13.39) \quad (h(t) + \tilde{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs})^{\frac{p}{q}} \geq ((r - t)^{-qs})^{\frac{p}{q}} = (r - t)^{-ps} \geq \min \{1, (r - t)^{-ps}\}.$$

Moreover, if $h(t) = 1$, then we have that

$$(13.40) \quad (h(t) + \tilde{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs})^{m-1} = (1 + \tilde{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs})^{m-1} \geq 1 \geq \min \{1, (r - t)^{-ps}\}.$$

Finally, if $t \in (0, \frac{r}{2}]$,

$$(13.41) \quad (h(t) + 2^{qs} r^{-qs})^{m-1} = (2^{qs} r^{-qs})^{\frac{p}{q}} = 2^{ps} r^{-ps} \geq (r - t)^{-ps} \geq \min \{1, (r - t)^{-ps}\}.$$

Gathering these pieces of information, we obtain the estimate in (13.35), as desired.

In particular, from (13.39), (13.40) and (13.41) we evince that (13.35) holds true with $\bar{c}_{k,q,s}$ given by

$$(13.42) \quad \bar{c}_{k,q,s} := \max \{2^{qs}, \tilde{c}_{k,q,s}\}.$$

This completes the proof of Proposition 13.11. □

The next observation provides a uniform bound in s for $\bar{c}_{k,q,s}^{\frac{1}{qs}}$. For this, we define the constant

$$(13.43) \quad \hat{c}_{p,m} := 2e^{c_{p,m}^{(1)}},$$

where

$$(13.44) \quad c_{p,m}^{(1)} := \left(\left[\frac{p}{p-1} \right] + 2 \right) \prod_{j=1}^{\left[\frac{p}{p-1} \right] + 1} \left(\frac{p}{m-1} + j \right).$$

Lemma 13.12. *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$ and $q := \frac{p}{m-1}$. Let $\bar{c}_{k,q,s}$ be given by Proposition 13.11.*

Then, for every $s \in (0, 1)$,

$$\bar{c}_{k,q,s}^{\frac{1}{qs}} \leq \hat{c}_{p,m}.$$

Proof. To show this, from (13.42) (and recalling also (13.37) and (13.38)), we evince that

$$(13.45) \quad \bar{c}_{k,q,s} = \max \{2^{qs}, \tilde{c}_{k,q,s}\} = 2^{qs} \max \{1, c_{k,q,s}\} \leq 2^{qs} (1 + c_{k,q,s}).$$

Moreover, we notice that, by (13.32),

$$k \leq \left[\frac{sp}{p-1} \right] + 1.$$

Therefore, recalling (13.37), we see that

$$(13.46) \quad \begin{aligned} c_{k,q,s} &\leq (k+1) \prod_{j=0}^k (qs + j) \\ &\leq qs \left(\left[\frac{p}{p-1} \right] + 2 \right) \prod_{j=1}^{\left[\frac{p}{p-1} \right] + 1} \left(\frac{p}{m-1} + j \right) \\ &= qsc_{p,m}^{(1)}. \end{aligned}$$

From this and (13.45) we obtain that, for every $s \in (0, 1)$,

$$(13.47) \quad \bar{c}_{k,q,s}^{\frac{1}{qs}} \leq 2(1 + c_{k,q,s})^{\frac{1}{qs}} \leq 2(1 + qsc_{p,m}^{(1)})^{\frac{1}{qs}}.$$

Now, we define the function $z : (0, 1) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ as

$$z(s) := (1 + qsc_{p,m}^{(1)})^{\frac{1}{qs}}$$

and we notice that z is decreasing in $(0, 1)$. Therefore, from (13.47), we find that

$$\bar{c}_{k,q,s}^{\frac{1}{qs}} \leq 2z(s) \leq 2 \limsup_{s \rightarrow 0^+} z(s) = 2e^{c_{p,m}^{(1)}},$$

which, together with (13.43), gives the desired result. □

The barrier w in Theorem 13.10 will be built by suitably rescaling and translating the function v in (13.34). Thus, as a preliminary step in this direction, we now estimate the p -fractional Laplacian of v , according to the following statement:

Proposition 13.13. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$, $q := \frac{p}{m-1}$ and $r \in [1, +\infty)$. Let $v : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be as in (13.34).*

Then, there exists $\tilde{C} \in (0, +\infty)$ depending only on n , m and p such that, for every $x \in B_r$,

$$(13.48) \quad -(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) \leq \frac{\tilde{C}}{s(1-s)} (v(x) + \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs})^{m-1},$$

where $\bar{c}_{k,q,s}$ is given in (13.42).

Proof. In order to prove (13.48), we show that there exists $\bar{C} \in (0, +\infty)$, depending only on n , m and p , such that, for every $x \in B_r$,

$$(13.49) \quad -(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) \leq \frac{\bar{C}}{s(1-s)} \left((r - |x|)^{-qs(p-1)-ps} + (r - |x|)^{-ps} \right),$$

and also

$$(13.50) \quad -(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) \leq \frac{\bar{C}}{s(1-s)}.$$

If equations (13.49) and (13.50) hold true, then using them together with the estimate in (13.35) we obtain that, for every $x \in B_r$,

$$\begin{aligned} -(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) &\leq \frac{\bar{C}}{s(1-s)} \min \left\{ 1, (r - |x|)^{-qs(p-1)-ps} + (r - |x|)^{-ps} \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{2\bar{C}}{s(1-s)} \min \left\{ 1, (r - |x|)^{-ps} \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{2\bar{C}}{s(1-s)} \left(h(|x|) + \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs} \right)^{m-1} \\ &= \frac{2\bar{C}}{s(1-s)} \left(v(x) + \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs} \right)^{m-1}, \end{aligned}$$

and therefore (13.48) holds true with $\tilde{C} := 2\bar{C}$.

Hence, from now on, we focus on the proof of (13.49) and (13.50). To accomplish this, in what follows we denote by $C \in (0, +\infty)$ a constant depending only on p, m and n and possibly changing from line to line.

If $p \in (1, 2)$ and $s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{2p}, 1 \right)$, we write that

$$\begin{aligned} -(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) &\leq \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\quad + 2^{p-1} \|v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\rho(x)} \frac{dy}{|x - y|^{n+sp}}. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, applying Lemma 13.19 with $\rho := \frac{r-|x|}{2}$ we find that

$$\begin{aligned} -(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) &\leq \frac{C_{n,p,m}}{1-s} \rho^{-qs(p-1)-ps} + \frac{C_{n,p}}{s} \rho^{-ps} \\ &\leq \frac{C}{s(1-s)} \left((r - |x|)^{-qs(p-1)-ps} + (r - |x|)^{-ps} \right), \end{aligned}$$

which establishes (13.49), while making use of Corollary 13.21 with $\rho = \mu := 1$ we obtain that

$$-(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) \leq \frac{C_{1,p,m,n}}{p-sp} + \frac{c_{n,p}}{s} \leq \frac{C}{s(1-s)},$$

which proves (13.50) in the case $p \in (1, 2)$ and $s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{2p}, 1 \right)$.

Now we let $p \in (1, 2)$ and $s \in (0, \frac{p-1}{2p})$. In this setting, recalling (13.32) and (13.34), we have that $k = 0$ and

$$v(y) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ (r - |y|)^{-qs} - \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs} & \text{if } y \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ 1 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \overline{B_{\hat{r}}}, \end{cases}$$

where $\hat{r} \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$ is defined as

$$(13.51) \quad \hat{r} := \min \left\{ t \in \left(\frac{r}{2}, r\right) \text{ s.t. } f(t) \geq 1 \right\}.$$

Accordingly,

$$(13.52) \quad \nabla v(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in B_{\frac{r}{2}}, \\ qs(r - |y|)^{-qs-1} \frac{y}{|y|} & \text{if } y \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \overline{B_{\hat{r}}}, \end{cases}$$

As a consequence, for a.e. $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(13.53) \quad |\nabla v(y)| \leq qs |r - |y||^{-qs-1} \chi_{B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}}.$$

Also, if $y \in B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x)$ then

$$|y| \leq |y - x| + |x| \leq \frac{r - |x|}{2} + |x| \leq \frac{r + |x|}{2} < r,$$

and thus

$$(13.54) \quad |r - |y|| = r - |y| \geq \frac{r - |x|}{2}.$$

Hence, using (13.53) and (13.54) we obtain that, if $y \in B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x)$,

$$|\nabla v(y)| \leq qs 2^{qs+1} (r - |x|)^{-qs-1},$$

and therefore

$$(13.55) \quad \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x))} < q 2^{q+1} (r - |x|)^{-qs-1}.$$

We thus apply Lemma 13.15 with

$$\widehat{K} := \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty\left(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}\right)} \quad \text{and} \quad \rho := \frac{r-|x|}{2}$$

and, thanks to (13.55), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} |(-\Delta)_p^s v(x)| &\leq \frac{c_{n,p}}{s(p-1-ps)} \left(\|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty\left(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}\right)}^{p-1} \left(\frac{r-|x|}{2}\right)^{-ps+p-1} + \left(\frac{r-|x|}{2}\right)^{-ps} \right) \\ &\leq \frac{C}{s(1-s)} \left((r-|x|)^{-qs(p-1)-ps} + (r-|x|)^{-ps} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (13.49) for the case $p \in (1, 2)$ and $s \in \left(0, \frac{p-1}{2p}\right)$.

Furthermore, from (13.53) and Proposition 13.20 we evince that, for every $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$|\nabla v(y)| \leq qs(r-\hat{r})^{-qs-1} \leq q\widehat{C}_{p,m}^{-qs-1} \leq C,$$

and so $\|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq C$. This allows us to use Lemma 13.15 with $\widehat{K} := \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}$ and $\rho := 1$, obtaining that, for every $x \in B_r$,

$$-(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) \leq \frac{C}{s(1-s)}.$$

This concludes the proof of (13.50) for the case $p \in (1, 2)$ and $s \in \left(0, \frac{p-1}{2p}\right)$.

Now, we let $p \in [2, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. In this case, recalling (13.32), we have that $k = 1$ and

$$v(y) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ (r-|y|)^{-qs} - \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs} - qs \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-1} \left(|y| - \frac{r}{2}\right) & \text{if } y \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ 1 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \overline{B_{\hat{r}}}, \end{cases}$$

where \hat{r} has been defined in (13.51). We can thereby compute that

$$(13.56) \quad \nabla v(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ \frac{y}{|y|} \left(qs(r-|y|)^{-qs-1} - qs \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-1} \right) & \text{if } y \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\hat{r}}. \end{cases}$$

Consequently, for every $y \in B_r$,

$$(13.57) \quad |\nabla v(y)| \leq qs \left((r - |y|)^{-qs-1} - \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-1} \right) \chi_{B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}} \leq C (r - |y|)^{-qs-1} \chi_{B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}}.$$

From this and (13.54) we infer that

$$(13.58) \quad \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x))} \leq C (r - |x|)^{-qs-1}.$$

Also, (13.57) and Proposition 13.20 give that

$$(13.59) \quad \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq C (r - \hat{r})^{-qs-1} \leq C.$$

Moreover, for every $y \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2}}$ and $\mu, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$,

$$D_{j,\mu}^2 v(y) = qs \left(\frac{\delta_{\mu,j}}{|y|} - \frac{y_\mu y_j}{|y|^3} \right) \left((r - |y|)^{-qs-1} - \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-1} \right) + \frac{y_\mu y_j}{|y|^2} qs (qs + 1) (r - |y|)^{-qs-2},$$

and thus, for every $y \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$,

$$(13.60) \quad |D^2 v(y)| \leq C \left(\frac{(r - |y|)^{-qs-1}}{|y|} + (r - |y|)^{-qs-2} \right) \leq C (r - |y|)^{-qs-2}.$$

Accordingly, making use of this and (13.54),

$$(13.61) \quad \|D^2 v\|_{L^\infty(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x) \cap B_{\hat{r}})} \leq C (r - |x|)^{-qs-2}.$$

In addition, we deduce from (13.60) and Proposition 13.20 that

$$(13.62) \quad \|D^2 v\|_{L^\infty(B_{\hat{r}})} \leq C (r - \hat{r})^{-qs-2} \leq C.$$

Now, we set

$$\Sigma(y) := \begin{cases} \nabla v(y) & \text{if } y \in B_{\hat{r}}, \\ 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\hat{r}} \end{cases}$$

and we claim that there exists $C \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $y \in B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x)$,

$$(13.63) \quad v(y) - v(x) - \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x) \leq C (r - |x|)^{-qs-2} |x - y|^2$$

and, for every $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(13.64) \quad v(y) - v(x) - \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x) \leq C |x - y|^2.$$

To check (13.63) and (13.64) we proceed as follows. If $x \in B_r \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$, the left-hand sides of both (13.63) and (13.64) are non positive, so the inequalities trivially hold. If instead $x, y \in B_{\hat{r}}$ the inequality in (13.64) follows from (13.62). Analogously, if $x \in B_{\hat{r}}$ and $y \in B_{\hat{r}} \cap B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x)$ the inequality in (13.63) follows from (13.61).

Now we consider a radial smooth extension \bar{v} of v outside $B_{\hat{r}}$ such that $1 \leq \bar{v} \leq 2$ and $D^2\bar{v}(y) \leq C$ for every $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$. Then, from (13.62), we have that if $x \in B_{\hat{r}}$, for every $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} v(y) - v(x) - \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x) &= 1 - \bar{v}(x) - \nabla\bar{v}(x) \cdot (y - x) \\ &\leq \bar{v}(y) - \bar{v}(x) - \nabla\bar{v}(x) \cdot (y - x) \\ &\leq C |x - y|^2. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (13.64).

Similarly, if we define the extension

$$\hat{v}(y) := \begin{cases} v(y) & \text{if } y \in B_{\hat{r}}, \\ f(|y|) & \text{if } y \in B_r \setminus B_{\hat{r}}, \\ 1 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_r, \end{cases}$$

we notice that, by (13.61) and the definition of f in (13.33), if $x \in B_{\hat{r}}$,

$$\|D^2\hat{v}\|_{L^\infty(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x))} \leq C (r - |x|)^{-qs-2}.$$

Then, for every $y \in B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x) \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} v(y) - v(x) - \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x) &= 1 - \hat{v}(x) - \nabla\hat{v}(x) \cdot (y - x) \\ &\leq \hat{v}(y) - \hat{v}(x) - \nabla\hat{v}(x) \cdot (y - x) \\ &\leq C (r - |x|)^{-qs-2} |x - y|^2. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (13.63).

Now, we apply Lemma 13.16 with

$$\rho := \frac{r - |x|}{2}, \quad \widehat{K} := \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x))} \quad \text{and} \quad \widetilde{C} := C (r - |x|)^{-qs-2}$$

and obtain, thanks to (13.58) and (13.63), that, if $x \in B_r$,

$$\begin{aligned} & -(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) \\ & \leq \frac{c_{n,p}}{s(1-s)} \left(\tilde{C} \max \left\{ \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty\left(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x)\right)}, |\Sigma(x)| \right\}^{p-2} (r-|x|)^{-sp+p-qs-2} + (r-|x|)^{-sp} \right) \\ & \leq \frac{c_{n,p}}{1-s} \left(\tilde{C} \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty\left(B_{\frac{r-|x|}{2}}(x)\right)}^{p-2} (r-|x|)^{-sp+p-qs-2} + (r-|x|)^{-sp} \right) \\ & \leq \frac{C}{1-s} \left((r-|x|)^{-(qs+1)(p-2)-sp+p-qs-2} + (r-|x|)^{-sp} \right) \\ & = \frac{C}{1-s} \left((r-|x|)^{-qs(p-1)-sp} + (r-|x|)^{-sp} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (13.49) when $p \in [2, +\infty)$ and $s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{p}, 1\right)$.

Finally, applying Lemma 13.16 with

$$\rho := 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{K} := \|\nabla v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)},$$

and recalling also equations (13.59) and (13.64), we obtain that, if $x \in B_r$,

$$-(-\Delta)_p^s v(x) \leq \frac{C}{1-s}.$$

This concludes the proof of (13.50) when $p \in [2, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$. □

With the work done so far, we can now complete the construction of the barrier in Theorem 13.10.

Proof of Theorem 13.10. Let $\bar{c}_{k,q,s}$ and \tilde{C} be as in Propositions 13.11 and 13.13 respectively. We define the constants

$$(13.65) \quad C_0 := \left(\frac{\tilde{C}}{s(1-s)\tau} \right)^{\frac{1}{ps}} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta := 2\bar{c}_{k,q,s}r^{-qs}.$$

Also, we rescale and translate v as follows

$$(13.66) \quad w(x) := (2-\beta)v\left(\frac{x}{C_0}\right) + \beta - 1.$$

Moreover, we set

$$(13.67) \quad r := \frac{R}{C_0}$$

and we define the constants

$$(13.68) \quad \widehat{C}_{n,p,m} := \widehat{c}_{p,m}^p \widetilde{C} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m} := \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{n,p,m}}{s(1-s)\tau} \right)^{\frac{1}{ps}},$$

where $\widehat{c}_{p,m} \in (1, +\infty)$ is provided in (13.43).

We prove that w , as defined in (13.66), satisfies the properties listed in the statement of Theorem 13.10.

We first observe that, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m}, +\infty)$, if $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R$ then

$$\frac{|x|}{C_0} \geq \frac{R}{C_0} = r$$

and so, recalling the definition of v in (13.34), we have that

$$w(x) = (2 - \beta)v\left(\frac{x}{C_0}\right) + \beta - 1 = 2 - \beta + \beta - 1 = 1.$$

This establishes (13.28).

We now check that (13.31) holds true for every $R \in [\bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m}, +\infty)$. For this, we make use of Lemma 13.12 (recall also that $\widehat{c}_{p,m} > 1$ thanks to (13.43)) to deduce that

$$R \geq \bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m} = C_0 \widehat{c}_{p,m}^{\frac{1}{s}} \geq C_0 \widehat{c}_{p,m} \geq C_0 \bar{c}_{k,q,s}^{\frac{1}{qs}}.$$

In light of this, (13.65) and (13.67) we obtain that

$$\beta = 2\bar{c}_{k,q,s} \left(\frac{C_0}{R} \right)^{qs} \leq 2.$$

From this and (13.66) we infer that

$$(13.69) \quad -1 < w \leq 1.$$

Moreover, recalling the definitions in (13.33) and (13.34), for every $t \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
 h(t) &\leq f(t) \\
 &= g(r-t) + \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(-1)^{i+1}}{i!} g^{(i)}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right) \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^i \\
 &\leq (r-t)^{-qs} + \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{|g^{(i)}(r/2)|}{i!} \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^i \\
 &\leq (r-t)^{-qs} + \sum_{i=0}^k c_{q,s,i} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-i} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^i \\
 &= (r-t)^{-qs} + \tilde{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs},
 \end{aligned}$$

where $c_{q,s,i}$ and $\tilde{c}_{k,q,s}$ have been defined respectively in (13.37) and (13.38).

From this we deduce that, for every $x \in B_r$,

$$v(x) \leq (r - |x|)^{-qs} + \tilde{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs}.$$

For this reason, for any $x \in B_R$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (13.70) \quad 1 + w(x) &\leq 2v\left(\frac{x}{C_0}\right) + \beta \leq 2C_0^{qs}(R - |x|)^{-qs} + 2\tilde{c}_{k,q,s}r^{-qs} + \beta \\
 &= 2C_0^{qs}(R - |x|)^{-qs} + 2\tilde{c}_{k,q,s}r^{-qs} + 2\bar{c}_{k,q,s}r^{-qs}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$r = \frac{R}{C_0} \geq \frac{R - |x|}{C_0},$$

we obtain from (13.70) that, for all $x \in B_R$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (13.71) \quad 1 + w(x) &\leq 2C_0^{qs}(R - |x|)^{-qs} + 2\tilde{c}_{k,q,s}C_0^{qs}(R - |x|)^{-qs} + 2\bar{c}_{k,q,s}C_0^{qs}(R - |x|)^{-qs} \\
 &\leq C_1(R - |x|)^{-qs},
 \end{aligned}$$

where $C_1 := 2C_0^{qs} \max\{1, \tilde{c}_{k,q,s}, \bar{c}_{k,q,s}\} = 2C_0^{qs} \bar{c}_{k,q,s}$, in light of (13.42).

Now, if $x \in B_{R-1}$ then $R - |x| \geq \frac{1+R-|x|}{2}$. Thus, by (13.71),

$$(13.72) \quad 1 + w(x) \leq 2^{qs+1} C_0^{qs} \bar{c}_{k,q,s} (1 + R - |x|)^{-qs}.$$

Additionally, if $x \in B_R \setminus B_{R-1}$, then $R + 1 - |x| \leq 2$. Thus, by (13.69),

$$(13.73) \quad 1 + w(x) \leq 2 = 2^{qs+1} 2^{-qs} \leq 2^{qs+1} (1 + R - |x|)^{-qs}.$$

From (13.72) and (13.73), and recalling Lemma 13.12, we see that, for every $x \in B_R$,

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + w(x) &\leq 2^{qs+1} \max \{1, C_0^{qs} \bar{c}_{k,q,s}\} (1 + R - |x|)^{-qs} \\ &\leq 2^{q+1} \max \{1, C_0^{qs} \hat{c}_{p,m}^{qs}\} (1 + R - |x|)^{-qs} \\ &\leq 2^{q+1} \max \{1, C_0^{qs} \hat{c}_{p,m}^q\} (1 + R - |x|)^{-qs} \\ &= 2^{q+1} \max \{1, \bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m}^{qs}\} (1 + R - |x|)^{-qs}, \end{aligned}$$

which proves (13.31).

Now we prove (13.29). For this, we use Lemma 13.13 and equation (13.65) and we see that, for every $x \in B_R$,

$$\begin{aligned} -(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) &= -(2 - \beta)^{p-1} C_0^{-sp} (-\Delta)_p^s v \left(\frac{x}{C_0} \right) \\ &\leq (2 - \beta)^{p-1} C_0^{-sp} \frac{\tilde{C}}{s(1-s)} \left(v \left(\frac{x}{C_0} \right) + \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs} \right)^{m-1} \\ &= \tau (2 - \beta)^{p-1} \left(v \left(\frac{x}{C_0} \right) + \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs} \right)^{m-1} \\ &\leq \tau (2 - \beta)^{m-1} \left(v \left(\frac{x}{C_0} \right) + \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs} \right)^{m-1} \\ &\leq \tau \left((2 - \beta) v \left(\frac{x}{C_0} \right) + (2 - \beta) \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs} \right)^{m-1} \\ &\leq \tau \left((2 - \beta) v \left(\frac{x}{C_0} \right) + 2 \bar{c}_{k,q,s} r^{-qs} \right)^{m-1} \\ &= \tau (1 + w(x))^{m-1}. \end{aligned}$$

This establishes the claim in (13.29) and completes the proof of Theorem 13.10. \square

13.4 Proofs of Theorem 13.3 and Corollary 13.5

In the section we prove the density estimates in Theorem 13.3 and Corollary 13.5.

We begin with the following observation:

Remark 13.14. We notice that in (14.13) we can assume, without loss of generality, that $c_0 \in (1, +\infty)$. Indeed, if $c_0 \in (0, 1]$, we can choose some $\tilde{c}_0 \in (1, +\infty)$ and for $t := (c_0/\tilde{c}_0)^{\frac{1}{n}}$ we can consider the rescaled function

$$\tilde{u}(x) := u(tx).$$

Then, if we define $\tilde{r}_0 := r_0/t$, by scaling we obtain that

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{\tilde{r}_0} \cap \{\tilde{u} > \theta_1\}) = \frac{1}{t^n} \mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) > \frac{c_0}{t^n} = \tilde{c}_0.$$

As a consequence, being \tilde{u} a minimizer² for $\mathcal{E}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega_{1/t})$ with potential $\widetilde{W} := t^{sp}W$, according to (14.14) we obtain the existence of some R^* and \tilde{c} , depending only on $n, s, p, c_0, W, r_0, \theta_1, \theta_2$ and \tilde{c}_0 , such that, for any $r \geq R^*$ satisfying $B_{\frac{3}{2}r} \subset \Omega_{1/t}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{c}r^n &< c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < \tilde{u} \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + \tilde{u}(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\tilde{u} > \theta_2\}) \\ &= \frac{c_{m,\theta_*}}{t^n} \int_{B_{tr} \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \frac{1}{t^n} \mathcal{L}^n(B_{tr} \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) \end{aligned}$$

thus proving the density estimates for u with constants R^*t and \tilde{c} .

Proof of Theorem 13.3. Thanks to Remark 13.14, we can assume, without loss of generality, that

$$(13.74) \quad c_0 \in (1, +\infty).$$

Let $R \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$ and $w \in C(\mathbb{R}^n, (-1, 1])$ such that $w \equiv 1$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R$. A more specific choice of w will be made later on in the proof (namely w will be the barrier constructed in Theorem 13.10 with a suitable choice of the parameter τ).

Moreover, we define

$$v := \min \{u, w\}$$

and we observe that

$$(13.75) \quad v = u \quad \text{in} \quad \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R.$$

²In this chapter, for any $r > 0$, we use the notation

$$\Omega_r := r\Omega := \{rx \text{ with } x \in \Omega\}.$$

To ease notation, we also set

$$D := (\mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n) \setminus ((\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R) \times (\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R)).$$

In this way, recalling the definition of the interaction energy \mathcal{K}_s^p in (13.11), we see that, for every $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$,

$$(13.76) \quad \mathcal{K}_s^p(f, B_R) = \frac{1}{2} \int_D \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy.$$

Now we introduce the following exponents

$$(13.77) \quad \hat{p} := \max \{2, p\} \quad \text{and} \quad l := \min \{2, p\}.$$

We claim that, for $\tau := \frac{c_1}{p}$, $\bar{R}_\tau := \bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m} \in (0, +\infty)$ given in (13.27) and $w \in C(\mathbb{R}^n, (-1, 1])$ given by Theorem 13.10, there exists $\hat{c}_p \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\tau, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_R \subset \Omega$,

$$(13.78) \quad \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u - v, B_R) \leq \frac{\Lambda + 2c_1}{\hat{c}_p} \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx.$$

Here above, Λ is given in (13.9) and c_1 in (13.10).

To prove this, if $p \in [2, +\infty)$ we use formula (4.3) in [Lin90] to deduce that, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(13.79) \quad \frac{1}{2^{p-1} - 1} |(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y)|^p + |v(x) - v(y)|^p - |u(x) - u(y)|^p \leq p(v(x) - v(y)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2} (v(x) - v(y) - (u(x) - u(y))),$$

while if $p \in (1, 2)$ we use formula (4.4) in [Lin90] to obtain that, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\frac{3p(p-1)}{4^2} \frac{|(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y)|^2}{(|v(x) - v(y)| + |u(x) - u(y)|)^{2-p}} + |v(x) - v(y)|^p - |u(x) - u(y)|^p \leq p(v(x) - v(y)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2} (v(x) - v(y) - (u(x) - u(y))).$$

Since $\|v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}, \|u\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq 1$, from the last equation we obtain that, for every $p \in (1, 2)$ and $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(13.80) \quad \frac{3p(p-1)}{4^{4-p}} |(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y)|^2 + |v(x) - v(y)|^p - |u(x) - u(y)|^p \leq p(v(x) - v(y)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2} (v(x) - v(y) - (u(x) - u(y))).$$

Therefore, we define the constant

$$\hat{c}_p := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} & \text{if } p \in [2, +\infty), \\ \frac{3p(p-1)}{4^{4-p}} & \text{if } p \in (1, 2) \end{cases}$$

and we infer from (13.79) and (13.80) that, for every $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and for every $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(13.81) \quad \hat{c}_p |(u-v)(x) - (u-v)(y)|^{\hat{p}} + |v(x) - v(y)|^p - |u(x) - u(y)|^p \\ \leq p(v(x) - v(y)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2} (v(x) - v(y) - (u(x) - u(y))).$$

Now, recalling (13.76), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} & \hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u-v, B_R) + \mathcal{K}_s^p(v, B_R) - \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) \\ = & \frac{\hat{c}_p}{2} \int_D \frac{|(u-v)(x) - (u-v)(y)|^{\hat{p}}}{|x-y|^{n+\hat{p}\frac{sl}{2}}} dx dy \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \int_D \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy - \frac{1}{2} \int_D \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

We remark that, in light of (14.31),

$$\hat{p}\frac{sl}{2} = \frac{2sp}{2} = sp,$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} & \hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u-v, B_R) + \mathcal{K}_s^p(v, B_R) - \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) \\ = & \frac{\hat{c}_p}{2} \int_D \frac{|(u-v)(x) - (u-v)(y)|^{\hat{p}}}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \int_D \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy - \frac{1}{2} \int_D \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy. \end{aligned}$$

Employing (13.81) and then recalling (14.37) we thereby obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} & \hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u-v, B_R) + \mathcal{K}_s^p(v, B_R) - \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) \\ \leq & \frac{p}{2} \int_D \frac{(v(x) - v(y)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2} (v(x) - v(y) - (u(x) - u(y)))}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{p}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n} \frac{(v(x) - v(y)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2} (v(x) - v(y) - (u(x) - u(y)))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \\
 &= p \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2} (u(x) - v(x))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

As a result, making again use of (14.37) and of the fact that $w \equiv 1$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R$,

(13.82)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u - v, B_R) + \mathcal{K}_s^p(v, B_R) - \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) \\
 &\leq p \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left((u(x) - v(x)) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(x) - v(y)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \right) dx \\
 &= p \int_{\{u > v = w\}} \left((u(x) - v(x)) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{(v(y) - w(x)) |w(x) - v(y)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \right) dx \\
 &= p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} \left((u(x) - v(x)) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{(v(y) - w(x)) |w(x) - v(y)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \right) dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we define the function $\phi_p(t) := t|t|^{p-2}$ and we observe that ϕ_p is nondecreasing, since

$$\phi_p'(t) = |t|^{p-2} + t(p-2)|t|^{p-4}t = |t|^{p-2} + (p-2)|t|^{p-2} = (p-1)|t|^{p-2} \geq 0.$$

As a consequence, since $v(y) \leq w(y)$, we see that

$$\phi_p(v(y) - w(x)) \leq \phi_p(w(y) - w(x)).$$

Plugging this information into (13.82), we thus find that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u - v, B_R) + \mathcal{K}_s^p(v, B_R) - \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) \\
 &\leq p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} \left((u(x) - v(x)) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{(w(y) - w(x)) |w(x) - w(y)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \right) dx \\
 &= -p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} (u(x) - v(x)) (-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

From this and the definition of the energy in (13.12) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u - v, B_R) &\leq \mathcal{E}(u, B_R) - \mathcal{E}(v, B_R) + \int_{B_R} W(v(x)) - W(u(x)) dx \\
 &\quad - p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} (u(x) - v(x)) (-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the minimality of u in B_R and (14.37) give that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (13.83) \quad & \hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u - v, B_R) \\
 & \leq \int_{B_R} W(v(x)) - W(u(x)) \, dx - p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} (u(x) - v(x)) (-\Delta)_p^s w(x) \, dx \\
 & = \int_{B_R \cap \{u > w\}} W(w(x)) - W(u(x)) \, dx - p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} (u(x) - v(x)) (-\Delta)_p^s w(x) \, dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we observe that, thanks to (13.10), if $x \in \{u > w\}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 W(u(x)) - W(w(x)) &= \int_{w(x)}^{u(x)} W'(\xi) \, d\xi \geq c_1 \int_{w(x)}^{u(x)} |1 + \xi|^{m-1} \, d\xi \\
 &\geq c_1 |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} (u(x) - w(x)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, using also (13.9),

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{B_R \cap \{u > w\}} W(w(x)) - W(u(x)) \, dx \\
 = & \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} W(w(x)) - W(u(x)) \, dx + \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} W(w(x)) - W(u(x)) \, dx \\
 \leq & -c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} (u(x) - w(x)) \, dx \\
 & \quad + \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^m \, dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, using this fact into (13.83),

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u - v, B_R) \\
 \leq & -c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} (u(x) - w(x)) dx \\
 & + \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx \\
 & - p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} (u(x) - v(x)) (-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx \\
 = & -c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{u > w\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} (u(x) - w(x)) dx \\
 & + c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{w, \theta_*\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} (u(x) - w(x)) dx \\
 & + \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx \\
 & - p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} (u(x) - v(x)) (-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

The computations done so far hold true for any function $w \in C(\mathbb{R}^n, (-1, 1])$ such that $w \equiv 1$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R$. We now choose w as in Theorem 13.10 with $\tau := \frac{c_1}{p}$. Then, if $\bar{R}_\tau := \bar{R}_{s, \tau, n, p, m} \in (0, +\infty)$ is given as in (13.27), thanks to Theorem 13.10 we

obtain that, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\tau, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \hat{c}_p \mathcal{K}_{\frac{sl}{2}}^{\hat{p}}(u - v, B_R) \\
& \leq -c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{u > w\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} (u(x) - w(x)) dx \\
& \quad + c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{w, \theta_*\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} (u(x) - w(x)) dx \\
& \quad + \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx \\
& \quad + c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v = w\}} (u(x) - v(x)) |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx \\
& = \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx \\
& \quad + c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{w, \theta_*\}\}} (u(x) - v(x)) |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx \\
& \leq (\Lambda + 2c_1) \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w(x)|^{m-1} dx.
\end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of the claim in (13.78).

Now, let $C_\tau = C_{s,\tau,n,p,m}$ be as in (13.30) with $\tau = \frac{c_1}{p}$, and define

$$k_0 := \left(\frac{2C_\tau}{1 + \theta_*} \right)^{\frac{m-1}{ps}} - 1.$$

Note that by the definitions of C_τ and θ_* we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
(13.84) \quad k_0 & \geq C_\tau^{\frac{m-1}{ps}} - 1 = \left(2^{\frac{p}{m-1}+1} \max \left\{ 1, \bar{R}_\tau^{\frac{ps}{m-1}} \right\} \right)^{\frac{m-1}{ps}} - 1 \\
& = 2^{\frac{1}{s} + \frac{m-1}{ps}} \max \{ 1, \bar{R}_\tau \} - 1 \geq \max \{ 1, \bar{R}_\tau \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thanks to this and (13.31), we have that if $R \in (k_0, +\infty)$ and $k \in (k_0, R)$, for all $x \in B_{R-k}$,

$$w(x) \leq -1 + \frac{C_\tau}{(1 + R - |x|)^{\frac{ps}{m-1}}} \leq -1 + \frac{C_\tau}{(1 + k)^{\frac{ps}{m-1}}} \leq -1 + \frac{1 + \theta_*}{2}.$$

This gives that, for all $x \in B_{R-k} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}$,

$$(13.85) \quad |u(x) - v(x)| = u(x) - v(x) \geq u(x) - w(x) \geq \frac{1 + \theta_*}{2}.$$

Now, for every $t \in (0, +\infty)$ we denote by

$$(13.86) \quad V(t) := \mathcal{L}^n(B_t \cap \{u > \theta_*\}).$$

With this notation, using (13.85), we have that, for every $R \in (k_0, +\infty)$ and $k \in (k_0, R)$ satisfying $B_R \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} (V(R-k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} &= \left(\int_{B_{R-k} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}} dx \right)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \left(\int_{B_{R-k} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}} |u(x) - v(x)|^{\frac{n\hat{p}}{n-sp}} dx \right)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}}, \end{aligned}$$

where \hat{p} has been defined in (14.31).

We also denote by $s' := \frac{sl}{2}$, with l given in (14.31), and we observe that

$$sp = \frac{2sp}{2} = \frac{\hat{p}sl}{2} = \hat{p}s'.$$

Hence, we can write that

$$\begin{aligned} (13.87) \quad (V(R-k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} &\leq \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \left(\int_{B_{R-k} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}} |u(x) - v(x)|^{\frac{n\hat{p}}{n-\hat{p}s'}} dx \right)^{\frac{n-\hat{p}s'}{n}} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |u(x) - v(x)|^{\frac{n\hat{p}}{n-\hat{p}s'}} dx \right)^{\frac{n-\hat{p}s'}{n}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we recall the Sobolev inequality of Theorem 1 in [MS02], according to which there exists $c_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $f \in W_0^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^n)$,

$$\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |f(x)|^{\frac{pn}{n-sp}} dx \right)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \leq c_{n,p} \frac{s(1-s)}{(n-sp)^{p-1}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy.$$

From this inequality (used with $f := u - v$) and (13.87), we deduce that

$$(V(R-k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \leq c_{n,\hat{p}} \frac{s'(1-s')}{(n-s'\hat{p})^{\hat{p}-1}} \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|(u-v)(x) - (u-v)(y)|^{\hat{p}}}{|x-y|^{n+s'\hat{p}}} dy dx.$$

Thus, making use of (14.37),

$$(V(R-k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \leq c_{n,\hat{p}} \frac{s'(1-s')}{(n-sp)^{\hat{p}-1}} \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \int_D \frac{|(u-v)(x) - (u-v)(y)|^{\hat{p}}}{|x-y|^{n+s'\hat{p}}} dy dx$$

$$= c_{n,\hat{p}} \frac{s'(1-s')}{(n-sp)^{\hat{p}-1}} \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \mathcal{K}_{s'}^{\hat{p}}(u-v, B_R).$$

This and (13.78) give that

$$\begin{aligned} & (V(R-k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \\ & \leq c_{n,\hat{p}} \frac{s'(1-s')}{(n-sp)^{\hat{p}-1}} \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \frac{\Lambda + 2c_1}{\hat{c}_p} \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1+w(x)|^{m-1} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, in light of (13.31),

$$\begin{aligned} & (V(R-k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \\ & \leq c_{n,\hat{p}} \frac{s'(1-s')}{(n-sp)^{\hat{p}-1}} \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \frac{\Lambda + 2c_1}{\hat{c}_p} C_\tau^{m-1} \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} (1+R-|x|)^{-ps} dx \\ & \leq c_{n,\hat{p}} \frac{s'(1-s')}{(n-sp)^{\hat{p}-1}} \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \frac{\Lambda + 2c_1}{\hat{c}_p} C_{\frac{c_1}{p}}^{m-1} \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \theta_*\}} (1+R-|x|)^{-ps} dx. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, using the coarea formula and setting

$$c = c_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*} := c_{n,\hat{p}} \frac{s'(1-s')}{(n-sp)^{\hat{p}-1}} \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right)^{\hat{p}} \frac{\Lambda + 2c_1}{\hat{c}_p} C_{\frac{c_1}{p}}^{m-1},$$

we conclude that, for every $R \in (k_0, +\infty)$ and $k \in (k_0, R)$ satisfying $B_R \subset \Omega$,

$$(13.88) \quad (V(R-k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \leq c \int_0^R (1+R-|t|)^{-ps} V'(t) dt.$$

Now we integrate (13.88) in $R \in [\rho, \frac{3}{2}\rho]$ with $\rho \geq 4k$ and $B_{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \subset \Omega$. Also, we use

the fact that $s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right)$ together with (13.84) and obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\rho}{2}(V(\rho - k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} &\leq \int_{\rho}^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} (V(R - k))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} dR \\ &\leq c \int_{\rho}^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \left(\int_0^R (1 + R - |t|)^{-sp} V'(t) dt \right) dR \\ &\leq c \int_0^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \left(V'(t) \int_t^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} (1 + R - |t|)^{-sp} dR \right) dt \\ &= \frac{c}{1-sp} \int_0^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} V'(t) \left[\left(1 + \frac{3}{2}\rho - |t|\right)^{1-sp} - 1 \right] dt \\ &\leq \frac{c}{1-sp} 2^{1-sp} \rho^{1-sp} \int_0^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} V'(t) dt \\ &\leq \frac{2c}{1-sp} \rho^{1-sp} V\left(\frac{3}{2}\rho\right). \end{aligned}$$

In particular, setting $r := \rho - k$ and recalling that $\rho \geq 4k$ we deduce that

$$(13.89) \quad r^{sp} (V(r))^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \leq \hat{c} V(2r),$$

with

$$\hat{c} = \hat{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*} := \frac{4c}{1-sp}.$$

From now $k > k_0$ is fixed once and for all.

From (14.13), (13.74) and (13.89) we see that (13.24) and (13.25) in Lemma 13.8 hold true with V as in (13.86) and with the following choices

$$\sigma := sp, \quad \nu := n, \quad \gamma := 2, \quad \mu := c_0, \quad R_0 := \max\{3k, r_0\} \quad \text{and} \quad C := \hat{c},$$

as far as $R \in [R_0, +\infty)$ is such that $B_{\frac{3R}{2}} \subset \Omega$.

Therefore, in virtue of (13.26) in Lemma 13.8, we obtain that there exist $\tilde{c} \in (0, 1)$, depending only on $s, n, p, m, \Lambda, c_1, \theta_*, c_0, R_0$ and k , and $R_* \in [R_0, +\infty)$, depending only on R_0 , such that, for every $r \in [R_*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{\frac{3r}{2}} \subset \Omega$,

$$V(r) \geq \tilde{c} r^n.$$

As a result, for any $r \in [R_*, +\infty)$ such that $B_{\frac{3r}{2}} \subset \Omega$,

$$(13.90) \quad \tilde{c} r^n \leq \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_*\}) = \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta^*\}) + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}).$$

Now we observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}) &= \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} dx \\ &\leq (1 + \theta_*)^{-m} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it follows from this and (14.82) that, for every $r \in [R_*, +\infty)$ such that $B_{\frac{3r}{2}} \subset \Omega$,

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta^*\}) \geq cr^n - (1 + \theta_*)^{-m} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx.$$

This entails the desired result in (14.14). \square

Proof of Corollary 13.5. Thanks to the claim (13.18) in Theorem 13.4 and the assumption in (13.19), we have that, for every $r \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{r+2} \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} (13.91) \quad \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx &\leq \lambda_{\theta^*}^{-1} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} W(u(x)) dx \\ &\leq \lambda_{\theta^*}^{-1} \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, B_r) \leq \lambda_{\theta^*}^{-1} \bar{C} r^{n-sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Also, we observe that for every $r \geq 4$ it holds that $\frac{3}{2}r \geq r + 2$. Hence, from (13.91) and (14.14) we deduce that, for every $r \geq \max\{4, R^*\}$ such that $B_{\frac{3}{2}r} \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{c}r^n &\leq c_{m, \theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) \\ &\leq \lambda_{\theta^*}^{-1} c_{m, \theta_*} \bar{C} r^{n-sp} + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}). \end{aligned}$$

From this, the claim in (13.20) readily follows. \square

13.5 Proofs of Theorem 13.6 and Corollary 13.7

We begin this section by establishing the compactness result for sequences of functions $\{u_\varepsilon\}_\varepsilon \subset X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ satisfying the boundedness assumption (13.22), as stated in Theorem 13.6. As already mentioned in the introduction, the convergence is a straightforward consequence of the scaling of $\mathcal{F}_{s,\varepsilon}^p$, the uniform bound in (13.22) and the compact embedding of $W^{s,p}(\Omega')$ into $L^1(\Omega')$ for $\Omega' \Subset \Omega$. The details of the proof are as follows.

Proof of Theorem 13.6. As a consequence of (13.22), for every open and bounded set $\Omega' \Subset \Omega$, we have that

$$(13.92) \quad \sup_{\varepsilon \in (0,1)} \int_{\Omega'} \int_{\Omega'} \frac{|u_\varepsilon(x) - u_\varepsilon(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy < +\infty.$$

Moreover, since $u_\varepsilon \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$, we find that, for every $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$,

$$(13.93) \quad \|u_\varepsilon\|_{L^p(\Omega')} \leq |\Omega'|^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Thus, it follows from (13.92), (13.93) and Theorem 7.1 in [DNPV12] that there exists some $u_0 \in L^1(\Omega')$ such that, up to a subsequence, u_ε converges to u_0 in $L^1(\Omega')$ and pointwise a.e. in Ω' , as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

Furthermore, using (13.21), (13.22) and Fatou's Lemma, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \varepsilon^{sp} \mathcal{F}_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon, \Omega') \\ &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \varepsilon^{sp} \mathcal{K}_s^p(u_\varepsilon, \Omega') + \int_{\Omega'} W(u_\varepsilon(x)) dx \\ &\geq c_2 \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{\Omega'} (1 - u_\varepsilon^2(x))^m dx \\ &\geq c_2 \int_{\Omega'} (1 - u_0^2(x))^m dx. \end{aligned}$$

This yields that u_0 must be equal to -1 and 1 a.e. in Ω' . Accordingly, if we denote by

$$E := \{x \in \Omega' \text{ s.t. } u_0(x) = 1\}$$

we obtain that $u_0|_{\Omega'} = \chi_E - \chi_{E^c}$. The proof of Theorem 13.6 is thereby complete. \square

In what follows we prove the Hausdorff convergence of the interface stated in Corollary 13.7. This result follows from the density estimates in Corollary 13.5 together with the Hölder regularity result for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p that we have recalled in Section 13.2.

Proof of Corollary 13.7. We argue by contradiction, and we assume that there exist $\Theta \in (0, 1)$, $\delta \in (0, +\infty)$, $R \in (0, +\infty)$ and a sequence $x_k \in \{|u_{\varepsilon_k}| < \Theta\} \cap B_R$ such that either $B_\delta(x_k) \subset E$ or $B_\delta(x_k) \subset E^c$. Without loss of generality, we assume that for every k it holds that $B_\delta(x_k) \subset E^c$.

Then, according to Theorem 13.6, up to a subsequence we have that

$$(13.94) \quad \begin{aligned} 0 &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_\delta(x_k) \cap \Omega} |u_{\varepsilon_k}(x) - \chi_E(x) + \chi_{E^c}(x)| \, dx \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_\delta(x_k) \cap \Omega} |u_{\varepsilon_k}(x) + 1| \, dx. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we define the rescaled set

$$\Omega_k := \left\{ \frac{x - x_k}{\varepsilon_k} \text{ s.t. } x \in \Omega \right\},$$

and the sequence of functions

$$w_k(x) := u_{\varepsilon_k}(x\varepsilon_k + x_k).$$

In this way, w_k is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p in Ω_k . Moreover,

$$(13.95) \quad w_k(0) = u_{\varepsilon_k}(x_k) > -\Theta.$$

Now, we apply Theorem 13.9 to w_k with the choice $F(t) := (1 - s)W(t)$ and we obtain that $w_k \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega_k)$ for some $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, depending only on n, s and p , and there exists $C \geq 1$, depending only on n, s and p , such that, for every $R_0 \in \left(0, \frac{\text{dist}(0, \partial\Omega_k)}{8}\right)$,

$$(13.96) \quad \begin{aligned} & [w_k]_{C^\alpha(B_{R_0})} \\ & \leq \frac{C}{R_0^\alpha} \left[\|w_k\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} + \text{Tail}(w_k; 0, 4R_0) + R_0^s (1 - s)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|W\|_{L^\infty((-1,1))}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{C}{R_0^\alpha} \left[1 + \left((1 - s)(4R_0)^{sp} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{4R_0}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp}} \right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}} + R_0^s (1 - s)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|W\|_{L^\infty((-1,1))}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right] \\ & = \frac{C}{R_0^\alpha} \left[1 + \left((1 - s) \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{sp} \right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}} + R_0^s (1 - s)^{\frac{1}{p}} \|W\|_{L^\infty((-1,1))}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, if we set $R_0 := \frac{\text{dist}(\partial B_R, \partial\Omega)}{8} \in (0, +\infty)$, then $R_0 \in \left(0, \frac{\text{dist}(0, \partial\Omega_k)}{8}\right)$ for every k . From this, (13.95) and (13.96), it follows that there exists r_0 such that $w_k(x) > -\Theta$ for every $x \in B_{r_0}$.

Therefore, we conclude that

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{w_k > -\Theta\}) \geq \mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0}) =: c_0.$$

We can thereby apply Corollary 13.5 and obtain that for any $\theta \in (-1, 1)$ there exist $\tilde{R} := \tilde{R}_{s,n,p,m,\theta_*,r_0,c_2} \in [r_0, +\infty)$ and $\hat{c} := \hat{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ such that, for every $r \in [\tilde{R}, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{\frac{3r}{2}} \subset \Omega_k$,

$$(13.97) \quad \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{w_k > \theta\}) \geq \hat{c} r^n.$$

Now, we choose $\theta := -\frac{1}{2}$ and $\delta_0 \in (0, \delta]$ such that $B_{\frac{3}{2}\delta_0}(x_k) \subset \Omega$, and we obtain from (13.94) and (13.97) that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_\delta(x_k)} |1 + u_{\varepsilon_k}(x)| \, dx \\ &\geq \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_{\delta_0}(x_k)} |1 + u_{\varepsilon_k}(x)| \, dx \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \varepsilon_k^n \int_{B_{\frac{\delta_0}{\varepsilon_k}}} |1 + u_{\varepsilon_k}(x\varepsilon_k + x_k)| \, dx \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \varepsilon_k^n \int_{B_{\frac{\delta_0}{\varepsilon_k}}} |1 + w_k(x)| \, dx \\ &\geq \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \varepsilon_k^n \int_{B_{\frac{\delta_0}{\varepsilon_k}} \cap \{w_k > \theta\}} |1 + w_k(x)| \, dx \\ &\geq \frac{\hat{c}}{2} \delta_0^n, \end{aligned}$$

thus providing a contradiction. □

13.6 Appendix

Some technical results towards the proof of Theorem 13.10

In this section we collect some technical results that are used throughout Section 13.3 in order to prove Theorem 13.10.

We start with two estimates for the fractional p -Laplacian of a bounded and locally Lipschitz function.

Lemma 13.15. Let $\rho \in (0, +\infty)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in \left(0, \frac{p-1}{p}\right)$ and $\psi \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$.

Let $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and assume that there exists $\widehat{K} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $y \in B_\rho(x)$,

$$|\psi(y) - \psi(x)| \leq \widehat{K} |y - x|.$$

Then, there exists $c_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(13.98) \quad |(-\Delta)_p^s \psi(x)| \leq \frac{c_{n,p}}{s(p-1-sp)} \left(\widehat{K}^{p-1} \rho^{-sp+p-1} + \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \rho^{-sp} \right).$$

Proof. We compute

$$\begin{aligned} & |(-\Delta)_p^s \psi(x)| \\ &= \left| \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(\psi(y) - \psi(x)) |\psi(y) - \psi(x)|^{p-2}}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dy \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\rho(x)} \frac{(\psi(y) - \psi(x)) |\psi(y) - \psi(x)|^{p-2}}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dy \right| \\ &\leq \widehat{K}^{p-1} \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+sp-p+1}} + 2^{p-1} \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\rho(x)} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} \\ &= \frac{\widehat{K}^{p-1} \omega_{n-1}}{p-1-sp} \rho^{-sp+p-1} + 2^{p-1} \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{sp} \rho^{-sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Now since $sp < p-1$ we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} |(-\Delta)_p^s \psi(x)| &\leq \frac{(p-1)\widehat{K}^{p-1}\omega_{n-1}}{sp(p-1-sp)} \rho^{-sp+p-1} + 2^{p-1} \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \frac{(p-1)\omega_{n-1}}{sp(p-1-sp)} \rho^{-sp} \\ &\leq \frac{c_{n,p}}{s(p-1-sp)} \left(\widehat{K}^{p-1} \rho^{-sp+p-1} + \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \rho^{-sp} \right), \end{aligned}$$

which is the desired result. \square

Lemma 13.16. Let $\rho \in (0, +\infty)$, $p \in [2, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\psi \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n) \cap C(\mathbb{R}^n)$.

Let $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and assume that there exist $\widehat{K}, \widetilde{C} \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\Sigma(x) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that, for every $y \in B_\rho(x)$,

$$(13.99) \quad |\psi(x) - \psi(y)| \leq \widehat{K} |x - y| \quad \text{and} \quad \psi(y) - \psi(x) - \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x) \leq \widetilde{C} |x - y|^2.$$

Then, there exists $c_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$-(-\Delta)_p^s \psi(x) \leq \frac{c_{n,p}}{s(1-s)} \left(\widetilde{C} \max \{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \}^{p-2} \rho^{-sp+p} + \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \rho^{-sp} \right).$$

Proof. We define the affine approximation of ψ at x as

$$\ell(y) := \psi(x) + \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x).$$

Then, denoting $\phi_p(t) := t|t|^{p-2}$, we obtain that

$$P.V. \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{\phi_p(\ell(y) - \ell(x))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy = 0.$$

Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\phi_p(\psi(y) - \psi(x))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{\phi_p(\psi(y) - \psi(x))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\rho(x)} \frac{\phi_p(\psi(y) - \psi(x))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{\phi_p(\psi(y) - \psi(x)) - \phi_p(\ell(y) - \ell(x))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\rho(x)} \frac{\phi_p(\psi(y) - \psi(x))}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &=: I + II. \end{aligned}$$

To estimate I , for every $y \in B_\rho(x)$ we denote by

(13.100)

$$m := \min \{\psi(y) - \psi(x), \ell(y) - \ell(x)\} \quad \text{and} \quad M := \max \{\psi(y) - \psi(x), \ell(y) - \ell(x)\}.$$

Then, thanks to the Mean Value Theorem and (13.99), we obtain that there exists some $\xi \in [m, M]$ such that

(13.101)

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_p(\psi(y) - \psi(x)) - \phi_p(\ell(y) - \ell(x)) &= \phi_p'(\xi)(\psi(y) - \psi(x) - \ell(y) + \ell(x)) \\ &= \phi_p'(\xi)(\psi(y) - \ell(y)) \\ &= \phi_p'(\xi)(\psi(y) - \psi(x) - \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x)) \\ &= (p-1) |\xi|^{p-2} (\psi(y) - \psi(x) - \Sigma(x) \cdot (y - x)) \\ &\leq \tilde{C}(p-1) |\xi|^{p-2} |x - y|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Also, according to (13.99) and (13.100),

$$|\xi| \leq \max \left\{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \right\} |x - y|,$$

and employing (13.101) we obtain that

$$\phi_p(\psi(y) - \psi(x)) - \phi_p(\ell(y) - \ell(x)) \leq \tilde{C}(p-1) \max \left\{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \right\}^{p-2} |x - y|^p.$$

On this account, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} I &\leq \tilde{C}(p-1) \max \left\{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \right\}^{p-2} \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+sp-p}} \\ &= \tilde{C}(p-1) \max \left\{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \right\}^{p-2} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{p-sp} \rho^{-sp+p}. \end{aligned}$$

We now estimate II , as follows

$$II \leq 2^{p-2} \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} = 2^{p-2} \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{sp} \rho^{-sp}.$$

We thus conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} &-(-\Delta)_p^s \psi(x) \\ &\leq \tilde{C}(p-1) \max \left\{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \right\}^{p-2} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{p-sp} \rho^{-sp+p} + 2^{p-1} \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{sp} \rho^{-sp} \\ &= \tilde{C}_s(p-1) \max \left\{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \right\}^{p-2} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{sp(1-s)} \rho^{-sp+p} \\ &\quad + 2^{p-1}(1-s) \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{sp(1-s)} \rho^{-sp} \\ &\leq \frac{C_{n,p}}{s(1-s)} \left(\tilde{C} \max \left\{ |\Sigma(x)|, \widehat{K} \right\}^{p-2} \rho^{-sp+p} + \|\psi\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-1} \rho^{-sp} \right), \end{aligned}$$

as desired. \square

We now focus on the specific construction of the barrier in Theorem 13.10. We recall the setting in (13.32), (13.33) and (13.34) and we show the following:

Proposition 13.17. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$. Let k and f be respectively as in (13.32) and (13.33).*

Then, for every $i \in \{0, \dots, k+1\}$ there exists $\tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, if $\rho_0 \in (0, \frac{r}{2})$ and $t \in (\frac{r}{2}, r - \rho_0)$,

$$(13.102) \quad \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k+1-i} \leq f^{(i)}(t) \leq \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} \rho_0^{-qs-k-1} \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k+1-i}.$$

Also, for every $i \in \{0, \dots, k+1\}$ there exists $C_{i,q,s} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, if $x \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$ and $\rho \in (0, x - \frac{r}{2})$,

$$(13.103) \quad \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} (r-x+\rho)^{-qs-k-1} \rho^{k+1-i} \leq f^{(i)}(x) \leq C_{i,q,s} (r-x)^{-qs-i}.$$

Proof. In order to prove (13.102) and (13.103), we notice that, owing to (13.33),

$$(13.104) \quad \begin{cases} f^{(i)}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right) = 0 & \text{for all } i \in \{0, 1, \dots, k\} \\ f^{(k+1)}(\eta) = (-1)^{(k+1)}g^{(k+1)}(r - \eta) & \text{for all } \eta \in \left(\frac{r}{2}, r\right]. \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, for every $\eta \in (0, +\infty)$ we have that

$$g^{(k+1)}(\eta) = (-1)^{k+1} \prod_{i=0}^k (qs + i) \eta^{-qs-k-1}.$$

From this, it follows that, given $0 < \rho_0 < \rho_1$, for all $\eta \in (\rho_0, \rho_1)$,

$$(13.105) \quad C_{q,s,k} \rho_1^{-qs-k-1} \leq (-1)^{(k+1)}g^{(k+1)}(\eta) \leq C_{q,s,k} \rho_0^{-qs-k-1}$$

where

$$(13.106) \quad C_{q,s,k} := \prod_{i=0}^k (qs + i).$$

Gathering these pieces of information, we deduce that, for every $t \in \left(\frac{r}{2}, r - \rho_0\right)$,

$$C_{q,s,k} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \leq f^{(k+1)}(t) \leq C_{q,s,k} \rho_0^{-qs-k-1}.$$

From this we obtain that, for every $i \in \{0, \dots, k\}$ and $y \in \left(\frac{r}{2}, r - \rho_0\right)$,

$$\begin{aligned} f^{(i)}(y) &= \int_{\frac{r}{2}}^y f^{(i+1)}(t_1) dt_1 \\ &= \int_{\frac{r}{2}}^y \int_{\frac{r}{2}}^{t_1} f^{(i+2)}(t_2) dt_2 dt_1 \\ &= \int_{\frac{r}{2}}^y \int_{\frac{r}{2}}^{t_1} \dots \int_{\frac{r}{2}}^{t_{k-i}} f^{(k+1)}(t_{k+1-i}) dt_{k+1-i} \dots dt_2 dt_1 \\ &\geq \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \left(y - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k+1-i}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(13.107) \quad \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} := \frac{C_{q,s,k}}{(k+1-i)!}.$$

Similarly, one can show that for every $i \in \{0, \dots, k\}$ and $y \in (\frac{r}{2}, r - \rho_0)$

$$f^{(i)}(y) \leq \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} \rho_0^{-qs-k-1} \left(y - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k+1-i}.$$

This concludes the proof of (13.102).

Now we prove (13.103). To do so, we make use of (13.104) and (13.105) to see that, for every $x \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$ and $\rho \in (0, x - \frac{r}{2})$,

$$C_{q,s,k}(r - x + \rho)^{-qs-k-1} \leq f^{(k+1)}(x) \leq C_{q,s,k}(r - x)^{-qs-k-1}.$$

Moreover, we point out that $f^{(i)}(x - \rho) \geq 0$ for all $i \in \{0, \dots, k\}$. Therefore, for every $i \in \{0, \dots, k\}$,

$$\begin{aligned} f^{(i)}(x) &\geq \int_{x-\rho}^x f^{(i+1)}(t_1) dt_1 \\ &\geq \int_{x-\rho}^x \int_{x-\rho}^{t_1} f^{(i+2)}(t_2) dt_2 dt_1 \\ &\geq \int_{x-\rho}^x \int_{x-\rho}^{t_1} \dots \int_{x-\rho}^{t_{k-i}} f^{(k+1)}(r - t_{k-i+1}) dt_{k-i+1} \dots dt_2 dt_1 \\ &\geq \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} (r - x + \rho)^{-qs-k-1} \rho^{k+1-i}. \end{aligned}$$

This gives the lower bound in (13.103).

Additionally, recalling (13.33), we find that, for every $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, k\}$ and $x \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$,

$$\begin{aligned} f^{(i)}(x) &= (-1)^i g^{(i)}(r - x) - (-1)^i g^{(i)}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right) + \sum_{j=i+1}^k \frac{(-1)^{j+1}}{(j-2)!} g^{(j)}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right) \left(x - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{j-2} \\ &\leq (-1)^i g^{(i)}(r - x) \\ &= \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (qs + j) (r - x)^{-qs-i}. \end{aligned}$$

This gives the upper bound in (13.103) with

$$(13.108) \quad C_{i,q,s} := \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (qs + j),$$

as desired. □

Remark 13.18. We notice that if $p \in (1, 2)$, $s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{2p}, 1\right)$ and $q := \frac{p}{m-1}$ it follows from (13.32) that

$$1 \leq k \leq \left\lceil \frac{p}{p-1} \right\rceil + 1.$$

Hence, if we recall (13.106) and we define

$$(13.109) \quad C_{p,m} := \prod_{i=0}^{\lceil \frac{p}{p-1} \rceil + 1} \left(\frac{p}{m-1} + i \right),$$

we see that

$$(13.110) \quad \frac{p-1}{2(m-1)} \left(\frac{p-1}{2(m-1)} + 1 \right) \leq C_{q,s,k} \leq C_{p,m}.$$

Thus, recalling also (13.107), for every $i \in \{0, \dots, k+1\}$, we evince that

$$c_{p,m} := \frac{\frac{p-1}{2(m-1)} \left(\frac{p-1}{2(m-1)} + 1 \right)}{\left(\left\lceil \frac{p}{p-1} \right\rceil + 2 \right)!} \leq \tilde{C}_{q,s,k,i} \leq C_{p,m}.$$

Hence, using also (13.102), we deduce that for every $i \in \{0, \dots, k+1\}$, $\rho_0 \in (0, \frac{r}{2})$ and $t \in (\frac{r}{2}, r - \rho_0)$

$$(13.111) \quad c_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k+1-i} \leq f^{(i)}(t) \leq C_{p,m} \rho_0^{-qs-k-1} \left(t - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k+1-i}.$$

Now we notice that, by (13.108) and (13.110),

$$(13.112) \quad C_{i,q,s} \leq C_{q,s,k} \leq C_{p,m}.$$

We infer from this and (13.103) that for every $x \in (\frac{2}{3}r, r)$, $\rho := \frac{r-x}{2}$ and $i \in \{0, \dots, k+1\}$

$$c_{p,m} 3^{-qs-k-1} \rho^{-qs-i} \leq f^{(i)}(x) \leq C_{p,m} 2^{-qs-i} \rho^{-qs-i}.$$

Thus, if we define the constant

$$(13.113) \quad \tilde{c}_{p,m} := c_{p,m} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{p}{m-1} + \lceil \frac{p}{p-1} \rceil + 2},$$

we see that, for every $x \in (\frac{2}{3}r, r)$ and $i \in \{0, \dots, k+1\}$,

$$(13.114) \quad \tilde{c}_{p,m} \rho^{-qs-i} \leq f^{(i)}(x) \leq C_{p,m} \rho^{-qs-i},$$

where $\rho := \frac{r-x}{2}$.

Thanks to these observations, we now provide some auxiliary results that allow us to estimate the fractional p -Laplacian of the function v in (13.34), as stated in Proposition 13.13.

Lemma 13.19. *Let $p \in (1, 2)$, $s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{2p}, 1\right)$ and $r \in (1, +\infty)$. Let $v : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be as in (13.34). Let $x \in B_r$ and*

$$(13.115) \quad \rho := \frac{r - |x|}{2}.$$

Then, there exists $C_{n,p,m} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(13.116) \quad \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \leq \frac{C_{n,p,m}}{1-s} \rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}.$$

Proof. In what follows, for simplicity of notation, if $A, B \in (0, +\infty)$ we adopt the notation

$$A \lesssim B \quad \text{if} \quad A \leq C_{n,p,m} B$$

for some $C_{n,p,m} \in (0, +\infty)$ depending at most on n, p and m .

Moreover, for every $p \in (1, 2)$, $s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{2p}, 1\right)$ and k as in (13.32), we have that

$$(13.117) \quad (k+1)(p-1) - sp \geq (1-s)(p-1).$$

Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned} (k+1)(p-1) - sp - (1-s)(p-1) &= k(p-1) - s \\ &= \left(\left[\frac{sp}{p-1} \right] + 1 \right) (p-1) - s \geq \frac{sp}{p-1} (p-1) - s = s(p-1) \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

as desired.

Now, we complete the proof of (13.116), which is based on a long and tedious computation, that we provide here below for the facility of the reader. We will deal separately with the cases $x \in \overline{B}_{\frac{r}{2}}$, $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B}_{\frac{r}{2}}$ and $x \in B_r \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$, where \hat{r} has been defined in (13.51).

(i) Case $x \in \overline{B}_{\frac{r}{2}}$. In this case, for every $y \in B_\rho(x)$ it holds that

$$|y| \leq \rho + |x| = \frac{r - |x|}{2} + |x| = \frac{r + |x|}{2} \leq \frac{3}{4}r.$$

Hence, recalling (13.34), if $y \in B_\rho(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} (v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2} &= (h(|y|) - h(|x|)) |h(|y|) - h(|x|)|^{p-2} \\ &= h(|y|) |h(|y|)|^{p-2} \leq |f(|y|)|^{p-1} \chi_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2}}}(y). \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence,

$$\int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \leq \int_{B_\rho(x) \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2}}} \frac{|f(|y|)|^{p-1}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy.$$

We now use (13.111) with $\rho_0 := r/4$ and $i := 0$ and we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\leq C_{p,m}^{p-1} \left(\frac{r}{4}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \int_{B_\rho(x) \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2}}} \frac{(|y| - \frac{r}{2})^{(p-1)(k+1)}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, changing variable gives that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\leq C_{p,m}^{p-1} \left(\frac{r}{4}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \int_{B_\rho \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2}}(-x)} \frac{(|y + x| - \frac{r}{2})^{(k+1)(p-1)}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\leq C_{p,m}^{p-1} \left(\frac{r}{4}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \int_{B_\rho \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2}}(-x)} \frac{(|y| + |x| - \frac{r}{2})^{(k+1)(p-1)}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Since $|x| \leq r/2$, from this we find that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ (13.118) \quad &\leq C_{p,m}^{p-1} \left(\frac{r}{4}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \int_{B_\rho} \frac{|y|^{(k+1)(p-1)}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \frac{C_{p,m}^{p-1} \omega_{n-1}}{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} \left(\frac{r}{4}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \rho^{(k+1)(p-1) - sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Also, in light of (13.115) we have that $\rho \leq r/2$, and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} r^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \rho^{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} &\leq (2\rho)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \rho^{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} \\ &= 2^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} \rho^{-qs(p-1) - sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Using this into (13.118) and recalling (13.117), we see that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy &\leq \frac{C_{p,m}^{p-1} \omega_{n-1} 2^{(qs+k+1)(p-1)}}{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} \rho^{-qs(p-1) - sp} \\ &\leq \frac{C_{p,m}^{p-1} \omega_{n-1} 2^{(qs+k+1)(p-1)}}{(1-s)(p-1)} \rho^{-qs(p-1) - sp}, \end{aligned}$$

which gives the desired estimate in (13.116).

(ii) **Case** $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{\hat{r}}{2}}}$. If we denote by

$$\begin{aligned} B_\rho^+ &:= \{y \in B_\rho \text{ s.t. } y \cdot x \geq 0\} \\ \text{and } B_\rho^- &:= \{y \in B_\rho \text{ s.t. } y \cdot x < 0\}, \end{aligned}$$

we have that

$$(13.119) \quad |y + x| \geq |x| \text{ for every } y \in B_\rho^+.$$

Now, we write

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x)) |v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\rho} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x)) |v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\rho} \frac{(v(x-y) - v(x)) |v(x-y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x)) |v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(v(x-y) - v(x)) |v(x-y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\rho^-} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x)) |v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\rho^-} \frac{(v(x-y) - v(x)) |v(x-y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Since v is a radial function, changing variable in the last integral, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_\rho^-} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x))|v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \quad + \int_{B_\rho^-} \frac{(v(x-y) - v(x))|v(x-y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x))|v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \quad + \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(v(x-y) - v(x))|v(x-y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy, \end{aligned}$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_\rho} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x))|v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x))|v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \quad + \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(v(x-y) - v(x))|v(x-y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)) |h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \quad + \int_{B_\rho^+} \frac{(h(|x-y|) - h(|x|)) |h(|x-y|) - h(|x|)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, thanks to (13.119) and the fact that h is a non decreasing function,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_\rho} \frac{(v(y+x) - v(x)) |v(y+x) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= \int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{\rho}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ (13.120) \quad & + \int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{\rho}{2}}(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & + \int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} + |h(|x-y|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we claim that

$$(13.121) \quad \int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{\rho}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s},$$

(13.122)

$$\int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}$$

and

(13.123)

$$\int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} + |h(|x-y|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}.$$

We point out that if the claims in (13.121), (13.122) and (13.123) hold true, then from (13.120) the estimate in (13.116) for the case $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$ readily follows.

Hence, from now on, we focus on the proofs of the claims in (13.121), (13.122) and (13.123).

Proof of (13.121): For this, we recall (13.34) and we use Proposition 13.17 to find that, for every $y \in B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} h(|x+y|) - h(|x|) &\leq f(|x+y|) - f(|x|) = \int_{|x|}^{|x+y|} f'(t) dt \\ &= \int_{|x|}^{|x+y|} \left(f'(|x|) + \int_{|x|}^t f''(\xi) d\xi \right) dt \\ (13.124) \quad &\leq f'(|x|) (|y+x| - |x|) + f''(|x+y|) \int_{|x|}^{|x+y|} \left(\int_{|x|}^t d\xi \right) dt \\ &= f'(|x|) (|y+x| - |x|) + f''(|x+y|) \frac{(|x+y| - |x|)^2}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Also, for every $y \in B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)$, we have that $|x-y| \in (\frac{r}{2}, \hat{r})$, and so

$$\begin{aligned} h(|x|) - h(|x-y|) &= f(|x|) - f(|x-y|) = \int_{|x-y|}^{|x|} f'(t) dt \\ &= \int_{|x-y|}^{|x|} \left(f'(|x|) - \int_t^{|x|} f''(\xi) d\xi \right) dt \\ (13.125) \quad &\geq f'(|x|) (|x| - |x-y|) - f''(|x|) \int_{|x-y|}^{|x|} \left(\int_t^{|x|} d\xi \right) dt \\ &= f'(|x|) (|x| - |x-y|) - f''(|x|) \frac{(|x| - |x-y|)^2}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we define

$$(13.126) \quad u(x) := 2 \frac{f'(|x|)}{f''(|x|)}$$

and we notice that, for every $y \in B_{u(x)}$,

$$f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{(|x| - |x - y|)}{2} \geq f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \geq 0.$$

From this, (13.124) and (13.125) we deduce that, for every $y \in B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{\rho}{2}}^c(x) \cap B_{u(x)}$,

$$(13.127) \quad \begin{aligned} & |h(|y + x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x - y|)|^{p-1} \\ \leq & (|x + y| - |x|)^{p-1} \left| f'(|x|) + f''(|x + y|) \frac{|x + y| - |x|}{2} \right|^{p-1} \\ & - (|x| - |x - y|)^{p-1} \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{(|x| - |x - y|)}{2} \right|^{p-1} \\ = & (|x + y| - |x|)^{p-1} \\ & \times \left(\left| f'(|x|) + f''(|x + y|) \frac{|x + y| - |x|}{2} \right|^{p-1} - \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{(|x| - |x - y|)}{2} \right|^{p-1} \right) \\ & + ((|x + y| - |x|)^{p-1} - (|x| - |x - y|)^{p-1}) \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{(|x| - |x - y|)}{2} \right|^{p-1} \\ \leq & |y|^{p-1} \left(\left| f'(|x|) + f''(|x + y|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-1} - \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-1} \right) \\ & + ((|x + y| - |x|)^{p-1} - (|x| - |x - y|)^{p-1}) |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Taylor's Theorem with the Lagrange remainder we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| f'(|x|) + f''(|x+y|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-1} \\
 &= |f'(|x|)|^{p-1} + (p-1) |f'(|x|)|^{p-2} f''(|x+y|) \frac{|y|}{2} \\
 &\quad + \frac{(p-1)(p-2)}{8} |f'(|x|) + b|^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 |y|^2 \\
 (13.128) \quad &\leq |f'(|x|)|^{p-1} + (p-1) |f'(|x|)|^{p-2} f''(|x+y|) \frac{|y|}{2} \\
 &\quad + \frac{(p-1)(2-p)}{8} |f'(|x|) + b|^{p-3} (f''(|x+y|))^2 |y|^2 \\
 &\leq |f'(|x|)|^{p-1} + (p-1) |f'(|x|)|^{p-2} f''(|x+y|) \frac{|y|}{2} \\
 &\quad + \frac{(p-1)(2-p)}{8} |f'(|x|)|^{p-3} (f''(|x+y|))^2 |y|^2,
 \end{aligned}$$

for some $b \in \left(0, f''(|x+y|) \frac{|y|}{2}\right)$.

Also, for every $\xi \in \left(0, f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2}\right)$,

$$|f'(|x|) - \xi| \geq |f'(|x|)| - \xi \geq f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \geq 0.$$

Hence, thanks to Taylor's Theorem we find that, for some $a \in \left(0, f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2}\right)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-1} \\
 &= |f'(|x|)|^{p-1} - (p-1) |f'(|x|)|^{p-2} f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \\
 &\quad + \frac{(p-1)(p-2)}{8} |f'(|x|) - a|^{p-3} (f''(|x|))^2 |y|^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

From this, (13.127) and (13.128) we conclude that, for every $y \in B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x) \cap B_{u(x)}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1} \\
 &\leq \frac{p-1}{2} |y|^p |f'(|x|)|^{p-2} (f''(|x+y|) + f''(|x|)) \\
 &\quad + \frac{(p-1)(2-p)}{8} |y|^{p+1} \left(f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 + \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2 \right) \\
 &\quad + ((|x+y| - |x|)^{p-1} - (|x| - |x-y|)^{p-1}) |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we deduce that, for every $w \in (0, u(x)) \cap (0, |x| - \frac{r}{2}) \cap (0, \rho)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (13.129) \quad & \int_{B_{\rho}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
 & \leq \frac{p-1}{2} \int_{B_w^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|f'(|x|)|^{p-2} (f''(|x+y|) + f''(|x|))}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \\
 & \quad + \frac{(p-1)(2-p)}{8} \int_{B_w^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy \\
 & \quad + \frac{(p-1)(2-p)}{8} \int_{B_w^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|f'(|x|) - f''(|x|)\frac{|y|}{2}|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy \\
 & \quad + \int_{B_w^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{((|x+y| - |x|)^{p-1} - (|x| - |x-y|)^{p-1}) |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
 & \quad + \int_{(B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_w^+) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we adopt the notation

$$(13.130) \quad \tilde{x} := |x| - \frac{r}{2}.$$

Also, we assume that $\hat{r} \in (\frac{2}{3}r, +\infty)$, the other case being similar. We notice that

$$(13.131) \quad \tilde{x} < \rho \quad \text{if } x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$$

$$(13.132) \quad \text{and } \tilde{x} \geq \rho \quad \text{if } x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{2}{3}r}.$$

Moreover, we define

$$\alpha_{p,m} := \frac{\tilde{c}_{p,m}}{C_{p,m}}$$

and the function

$$(13.133) \quad w(x) := \begin{cases} \alpha_{p,m} \tilde{x} & \text{for } x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}, \\ \alpha_{p,m} \rho & \text{for } x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{2}{3}r}, \end{cases}$$

where $\tilde{c}_{p,m}$ and $C_{p,m}$ are given respectively in (13.113) and (13.109).

We notice that $\alpha_{p,m} \leq 1$, thanks to (13.114). Moreover, recalling (13.126) and making use of (13.114),

$$u(x) = 2 \frac{f'(|x|)}{f''(|x|)} \geq 2 \frac{\tilde{C}_{p,m} \left(\frac{r-|x|}{2}\right)^{-qs-1}}{C_{p,m} \left(\frac{r-|x|}{2}\right)^{-qs-2}} = \alpha_{p,m}(r - |x|) = \alpha_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2} - \tilde{x}\right) \geq w(x).$$

Therefore, using also (13.131) and (13.132), we have that, if $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B}_{\frac{r}{2}}$,

$$(13.134) \quad w(x) \leq \min \{u(x), \tilde{x}, \rho\}.$$

Accordingly, we can exploit (13.129) with $w := w(x)$.

In this way, we deduce that, in order to show (13.121), it is enough to prove that, if $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{r}{2}}$,

$$(13.135) \quad \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|f'(|x|)|^{p-2} (f''(|x+y|) + f''(|x|))}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s},$$

(13.136)

$$\int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 + \left|f'(|x|) - f''(|x|)\frac{|y|}{2}\right|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s},$$

$$(13.137) \quad \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{((|x+y| - |x|)^{p-1} - (|x| - |x-y|)^{p-1}) |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}$$

and

(13.138)

$$\int_{(B_{\hat{r}}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}.$$

Hence, from now on we focus on the proofs of these claims.

We first prove (13.135). To do so, if $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$, we observe that, in light of (13.111),

$$\begin{aligned} & |f'(|x|)|^{p-2} (f''(|x+y|) + f''(|x|)) \\ \leq & C_{p,m}^{p-2} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-2)} \left(|x| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k(p-2)} C_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{6}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \\ & \times \left(\left(|x+y| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k-1} + \left(|x| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k-1} \right) \\ \leq & C_{p,m}^{p-2} C_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-2)} \left(\frac{r}{6}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^{k(p-2)} ((\tilde{x} + |y|)^{k-1} + \tilde{x}^{k-1}). \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|f'(|x|)|^{p-2} (f''(|x+y|) + f''(|x|))}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \\ \leq & C_{p,m}^{p-2} C_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-2)} \left(\frac{r}{6}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \\ & \times \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{\tilde{x}^{k(p-2)} ((\tilde{x} + |y|)^{k-1} + \tilde{x}^{k-1})}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \\ \lesssim & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \int_{B_{w(x)}} \frac{\tilde{x}^{k(p-2)} ((\tilde{x} + |y|)^{k-1} + \tilde{x}^{k-1})}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, changing variable $z := y/\tilde{x}$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|f'(|x|)|^{p-2} (f''(|x+y|) + f''(|x|))}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \\ \lesssim & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{w(x)/\tilde{x}}} \frac{((1+|z|)^{k-1} + 1)}{|z|^{n+sp-p}} dz \\ \lesssim & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{\alpha_{p,m}}} \frac{((1+|z|)^{k-1} + 1)}{|z|^{n+sp-p}} dz \\ \lesssim & \frac{r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)}}{p-sp} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we observe that $(k+1)(p-1) - sp \geq 0$ thanks to (13.117), and therefore we deduce from (13.131) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|f'(|x|)|^{p-2} (f''(|x+y|) + f''(|x|))}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \\ \lesssim & \frac{r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)}}{1-s} \rho^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \leq \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves (13.135) when $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$.

If instead $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{2}{3}r}}$, we exploit (13.114) to obtain the estimate

$$(13.139) \quad \begin{aligned} & |f'(x)|^{p-2} (f''(x+y) + f''(x)) \\ & \leq \tilde{c}_{p,m}^{p-2} \left(\frac{r-|x|}{2} \right)^{(qs+1)(2-p)} C_{p,m} \left(\left(\frac{r-|x+y|}{2} \right)^{-qs-2} + \left(\frac{r-|x|}{2} \right)^{-qs-2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Also, if $y \in B_{w(x)}$ then $|x+y| \leq |x| + |y| \leq |x| + w(x) \leq |x| + \rho$, thanks to (13.134). Consequently,

$$(13.140) \quad \frac{r-|x+y|}{2} \geq \frac{r-|x|-\rho}{2} = \rho - \frac{\rho}{2} = \frac{\rho}{2}.$$

From this and (13.139), we infer that

$$|f'(x)|^{p-2} (f''(x+y) + f''(x)) \lesssim \rho^{(qs+1)(2-p)} \rho^{-qs-2} = \rho^{-qs(p-1)-p}.$$

As a result,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|f'(x)|^{p-2} (f''(x+y) + f''(x))}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \lesssim \rho^{-qs(p-1)-p} \int_{B_{w(x)}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} \\ & \leq \rho^{-qs(p-1)-p} \int_{B_\rho} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (13.135).

Next, we show that (13.136) holds true. For this, we observe that, as a consequence of (13.111) and (13.113), if $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$ and $y \in B_{w(x)}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} & \geq c_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k - C_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{6} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^{k-1} \frac{|y|}{2} \\ & \geq c_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k - C_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{6} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^{k-1} \frac{w(x)}{2} \\ & \geq c_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k - \frac{\tilde{c}_{p,m}}{2} \left(\frac{r}{6} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k \\ & = c_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k - \frac{c_{p,m}}{2} \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{q+\lceil \frac{p}{p-1} \rceil + 1} \left(\frac{r}{6} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k \\ & \geq c_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k - \frac{c_{p,m}}{2} \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{qs+k+1} \left(\frac{r}{6} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k \\ & = \frac{c_{p,m}}{2} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs-k-1} \tilde{x}^k. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, making again use of (13.111),

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 + \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2 \\
 \leq & C_{p,m}^{p-3} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-3)} \left(|x| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k(p-3)} C_{p,m}^2 \left(\frac{r}{6}\right)^{-2(qs+k+1)} \left(|x+y| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{2(k-1)} \\
 & + \frac{C_{p,m}^{p-3}}{2^{p-3}} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-(qs+k+1)(p-3)} \tilde{x}^{k(p-3)} C_{p,m}^2 \left(\frac{r}{6}\right)^{-2(qs+k+1)} \left(|x| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{2(k-1)} \\
 \lesssim & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{k(p-3)} \left(\left(|x+y| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{2(k-1)} + \tilde{x}^{2(k-1)} \right) \\
 \leq & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{k(p-3)} \left((\tilde{x} + |y|)^{2(k-1)} + \tilde{x}^{2(k-1)} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence, using also (13.131), we infer that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x)} \frac{f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 + \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy \\
 \lesssim & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{k(p-3)} \left(\int_{B_{w(x)}} \frac{(\tilde{x} + |y|)^{2(k-1)}}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy + \int_{B_{w(x)}} \frac{\tilde{x}^{2(k-1)}}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy \right) \\
 \leq & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \left(\int_{B_{\alpha_{p,m}}} \frac{(1 + |y|)^{2(k-1)}}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy + \int_{B_{\alpha_{p,m}}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} \right) \\
 \leq & r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \rho^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{\alpha_{p,m}}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} \\
 \lesssim & \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1 + p - sp} \\
 \leq & \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1 - s},
 \end{aligned}$$

which establishes (13.136) when $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$,

Similarly, using (13.114), we find that, for all $x \in B_{\tilde{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{2}{3}r}$ and $y \in B_{w(x)}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} & \geq f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{w(x)}{2} \\
 & = f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{\alpha_{p,m} \rho}{2} \\
 & \geq \tilde{c}_{p,m} \rho^{-qs-1} - C_{p,m} \rho^{-qs-1} \frac{\alpha_{p,m}}{2} \\
 & = \rho^{-qs-1} \frac{\tilde{c}_{p,m}}{2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This and (13.114) give that

$$\begin{aligned} & f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 + \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2 \\ \leq & \tilde{C}_{p,m}^{p-3} \rho^{-(qs+1)(p-3)} C_{p,m}^2 \left(\frac{r - |x+y|}{2} \right)^{-2(qs+2)} + \rho^{-(qs+1)(p-3)} \frac{\tilde{C}_{p,m}^{p-3}}{2^{p-3}} C_{p,m}^2 \rho^{-2(qs+2)} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, recalling (13.140),

$$f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 + \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2 \lesssim \rho^{-(qs+1)(p-3)-2(qs+2)}.$$

From this we thereby find that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{f'(|x|)^{p-3} f''(|x+y|)^2 + \left| f'(|x|) - f''(|x|) \frac{|y|}{2} \right|^{p-3} f''(|x|)^2}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy \\ & \lesssim \rho^{(qs+1)(1-p)} \int_{B_{w(x)}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} \\ & = \rho^{(qs+1)(1-p)} \rho^{-sp+p-1} \int_{B_{\alpha_{p,m}}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p-1}} \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1+p-sp} \leq \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the proof of (13.136) is complete.

Now we prove (13.137). To accomplish this goal, we prove first that there exists $C_p \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $x \in B_{\tilde{r}}$ and $y \in B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)$,

$$(13.141) \quad \left(\left| \frac{x}{|x|} + y \right| - 1 \right)^{p-1} - \left(1 - \left| y - \frac{x}{|x|} \right| \right)^{p-1} \leq C_p |y|^p.$$

To show the claim in (13.141), we assume without loss of generality that $x = |x| e_n$.

Then, if we write $y = (y', y_n)$ with $y' := (y_1, \dots, y_{n-1})$, we have that

$$\frac{d}{dy_n} \left| \frac{x}{|x|} + y \right| = \frac{d}{dy_n} \sqrt{|y'|^2 + y_n^2 + 2y_n + 1} = \frac{1 + y_n}{\sqrt{|y'|^2 + y_n^2 + 2y_n + 1}}$$

and similarly

$$\begin{aligned} (13.142) \quad \frac{d^2}{dy_n^2} \left| \frac{x}{|x|} + y \right| &= \frac{(|y'|^2 + y_n^2 + 2y_n + 1) - (1 + y_n)^2}{(|y'|^2 + y_n^2 + 2y_n + 1)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &= \frac{|y'|^2}{(|y'|^2 + y_n^2 + 2y_n + 1)^{\frac{3}{2}}}. \end{aligned}$$

We also compute that

$$\frac{d}{dy_n} \left| y - \frac{x}{|x|} \right| = \frac{d}{dy_n} \sqrt{|y'|^2 + y_n^2 - 2y_n + 1} = \frac{y_n - 1}{\sqrt{|y'|^2 + y_n^2 - 2y_n + 1}}$$

and

$$(13.143) \quad \frac{d^2}{dy_n^2} \left| y - \frac{x}{|x|} \right| = \frac{|y'|^2}{(|y'|^2 + y_n^2 - 2y_n + 1)^{\frac{3}{2}}}.$$

Now we denote by $\pi_n : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the projection along the n -th axis and we set

$$A := \pi_n \left(B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|) \right).$$

Then, in light of (13.142) and (13.143),

$$\sup_{y_n \in A} \left| \frac{d^2}{dy_n^2} \left| \frac{x}{|x|} + y \right| \right| \leq \frac{|y'|^2}{(|y'|^2 + 1)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \leq 1.$$

Also, since $x \in B_{\hat{r}}$,

$$\sup_{y_n \in A} \left| \frac{d^2}{dy_n^2} \left| y - \frac{x}{|x|} \right| \right| \leq \frac{1}{(|y'|^2 + y_n^2 - 2y_n + 1)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \leq \frac{2|x|}{r} \leq \frac{2\hat{r}}{r} \leq 2.$$

By Taylor's Theorem we thereby deduce that

$$(13.144) \quad \left| \frac{x}{|x|} + y \right| - 1 = y_n + \frac{y_n^2}{2} \frac{d^2}{d\xi^2} \left| \frac{x}{|x|} - (y', \xi) \right| \leq y_n + \frac{1}{2} y_n^2$$

and that

$$(13.145) \quad 1 - \left| y - \frac{x}{|x|} \right| = y_n - \frac{y_n^2}{2} \frac{d^2}{d\eta^2} \left| (y', \eta) - \frac{x}{|x|} \right| \geq y_n - y_n^2,$$

for some $\eta, \xi \in (0, y_n)$.

Furthermore, by (13.134), we have that, for every $y \in B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)$,

$$(13.146) \quad (1 - y_n) \geq (1 - |y|) \geq \left(1 - \frac{w(x)}{|x|} \right) \geq \left(1 - \frac{\min\{\tilde{x}, \rho\}}{|x|} \right) \geq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Therefore, thanks to (13.144), (13.145) and (13.146), and applying Taylor's Theorem once again, we infer that, for every $y \in B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)$, there exist some $\xi, \eta \in (0, y_n)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\left| \frac{x}{|x|} + y \right| - 1 \right)^{p-1} - \left(1 - \left| \frac{x}{|x|} - y \right| \right)^{p-1} \\
&= \left(\sqrt{|y'|^2 + y_n^2 + 2y_n + 1} - 1 \right)^{p-1} - \left(1 - \sqrt{|y'|^2 + y_n^2 - 2y_n + 1} \right)^{p-1} \\
&\leq y_n^{p-1} \left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{2}y_n \right)^{p-1} - (1 - y_n)^{p-1} \right) \\
&\leq y_n^{p-1} \left(1 + \frac{p-1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2}\xi \right)^{p-2} y_n - 1 + (p-1)(1-\eta)^{p-2} y_n \right) \\
&\leq y_n^{p-1} \left(\frac{p-1}{2} y_n + (p-1)(1-y_n)^{p-2} y_n \right) \\
&\leq y_n^{p-1} \left(\frac{p-1}{2} y_n + (p-1)2^{2-p} y_n \right) \\
&\leq C_p y_n^p \\
&\leq C_p |y|^p
\end{aligned}$$

where we have defined $C_p := (p-1)(2^{-1} + 2^{2-p})$. This concludes the proof of (13.141).

As a consequence of a change of variable and (13.141), if $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{(|x+y|-|x|)^{p-1} - (|x|-|x-y|)^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} |f'(|x|)|^{p-1} dy \\
&= |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)} \frac{(|x/|x|+y|-1)^{p-1} |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
&\quad - |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)} \frac{(1-|x/|x|-y|)^{p-1} |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
&\leq C_p |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)} \frac{|f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy.
\end{aligned}$$

From this and (13.111) we thus find that

$$\int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{(|x+y|-|x|)^{p-1} - (|x|-|x-y|)^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} |f'(|x|)|^{p-1} dy$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq C_p C_{p,m}^{p-1} |x|^{p-1-sp} \left(\frac{r}{6}\right)^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \left(|x| - \frac{r}{2}\right)^{k(p-1)} \\ &\quad \times \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} \\ &\lesssim |x|^{p-1-sp} r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{k(p-1)} \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we observe that $w(x) \leq \tilde{x} \leq |x|$, thanks to (13.130) and (13.134). Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{((|x+y| - |x|)^{p-1} - (|x| - |x-y|)^{p-1}) |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim |x|^{p-1-sp} r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{k(p-1)} \int_{B_1} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} \\ &\lesssim \frac{|x|^{p-1-sp} r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{k(p-1)}}{p-sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, recalling also (13.131),

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{((|x+y| - |x|)^{p-1} - (|x| - |x-y|)^{p-1}) |f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim \frac{r^{-sp-(p-1)(qs+k)} \rho^{k(p-1)}}{p-sp} \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}, \end{aligned}$$

which proves (13.137) when $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$.

If $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{2}{3}r}$, we argue in a similar way, exploiting a change of variable and (13.141), but using now (13.114) to estimate $|f'(|x|)|$ and (13.132) to see

that $w(x) \leq \rho$. In this way, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_{w(x)}^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{(|x+y|-|x|)^{p-1} - (|x|-|x-y|)^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} |f'(|x|)|^{p-1} dy \\ & \lesssim |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1(x/|x|) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2|x|}}^c(x/|x|)} \frac{|f'(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} dy \\ & \leq C_{p,m}^{p-1} |x|^{p-1-sp} \rho^{-(qs+1)(p-1)} \int_{B_{\frac{w(x)}{|x|}}^+} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p}} \\ & \lesssim |x|^{p-1-sp} \rho^{-(qs+1)(p-1)} \frac{\rho^{p-sp}}{|x|^{p-sp}} \frac{1}{p-sp} \\ & \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the claim in (13.137) holds true for every $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$.

In order to complete the proof of (13.121) it is only left to show (13.138). To do so, we observe that, for every $t > 0$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_t$,

$$(13.147) \quad (1 + |y|)^{k-1} - 1 \leq (1 + |y|)^{k+1} \leq (t^{-1} + 1)^{k+1} |y|^{k+1}.$$

Moreover, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} (13.148) \quad & \int_{(B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \leq \int_{(B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \leq \int_{B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \leq \int_{B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+} \frac{|f(|y+x|) - f(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Now, if $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$ and $y \in B_{\rho}$, we have that $(\tilde{x} + \frac{r}{2}, \tilde{x} + \frac{r}{2} + |y|) \subset (\frac{r}{2}, \frac{5r}{6})$.

Therefore, we employ (13.111) with $\rho_0 := r/6$ and we obtain that

(13.149)

$$\begin{aligned} |f(|y+x|) - f(|x|)| &\leq \left| f\left(|y| + \tilde{x} + \frac{r}{2}\right) - f\left(\tilde{x} + \frac{r}{2}\right) \right| = \int_{\tilde{x}}^{\tilde{x}+|y|} f'(t + \frac{r}{2}) dt \\ &\leq C_{p,m} \left(\frac{r}{6}\right)^{-qs-k-1} \int_{\tilde{x}}^{\tilde{x}+|y|} t^k dt \lesssim r^{-qs-k-1} ((\tilde{x} + |y|)^{k+1} - \tilde{x}^{k+1}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$, we employ a change of variable to deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{(B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \int_{B_{\rho} \setminus B_{w(x)}} \frac{((\tilde{x} + |y|)^{k+1} - \tilde{x}^{k+1})^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{\rho/\tilde{x}} \setminus B_{\alpha_{p,m}}} \frac{((1 + |y|)^{k+1} - 1)^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Now, formula (13.147) (used here with $t := \alpha_{p,m}$) gives that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{(B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{\rho/\tilde{x}} \setminus B_{\alpha_{p,m}}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-(k+1)(p-1)}} \\ &\leq r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{\rho/\tilde{x}}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-(k+1)(p-1)}} \\ &\lesssim \frac{r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)}}{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} \rho^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, recalling (13.117),

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{(B_{\rho}^+ \setminus B_{w(x)}^+) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} \leq \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}, \end{aligned}$$

which is (13.138) when $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$.

Analogously, if $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{2}{3}\hat{r}}$ we use (13.114) into (13.148) to obtain that

$$\int_{(B_{\rho^+} \setminus B_{w(x)^+}) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy$$

$$\leq C_{p,m}^{p-1} \int_{B_{\rho^+} \setminus B_{w(x)^+}} \frac{\rho^{-(qs+1)(p-1)}}{|y|^{n+sp-p+1}} dy.$$

Hence, changing variable and recalling (13.133),

$$\int_{(B_{\rho^+} \setminus B_{w(x)^+}) \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy$$

$$= C_{p,m}^{p-1} \rho^{-(qs+1)(p-1)-sp+p-1} \int_{B_1^+ \setminus B_{\alpha_{p,m}^+}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p+1}}$$

$$\lesssim \rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp} \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha_{p,m}^{p-sp-1} - 1}{1+sp-p} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{p-1}{p}, 1\right), \\ |\ln(\alpha_{p,m})| & \text{if } s = \frac{p-1}{p}, \\ \frac{1 - \alpha_{p,m}^{p-sp-1}}{p-1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{p-1}{2p}, \frac{p-1}{p}\right) \end{cases}$$

$$\lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}.$$

This concludes the proof of (13.138) and thus of the claim in (13.121).

Proof of (13.122): Toward this objective, we use the notation for \tilde{x} in (13.130) and we observe that, for every $y \in B_{\frac{r}{2\tilde{x}}}\left(\frac{x}{\tilde{x}}\right)$,

$$(13.150) \quad (|y| + 1)^{k+1} - 1 \leq (|y| + 1)^{k+1} \leq 2^{k+1} |y|^{k+1}.$$

Indeed, the first inequality is obvious. For the second one, we use the triangular inequality to obtain that, if $y \in B_{\frac{r}{2\tilde{x}}}\left(\frac{x}{\tilde{x}}\right)$,

$$\frac{|x|}{\tilde{x}} - |y| \leq \left|y - \frac{x}{\tilde{x}}\right| \leq \frac{r}{2\tilde{x}},$$

from which it follows that

$$|y| \geq \left(|x| - \frac{r}{2}\right) \frac{1}{\tilde{x}} = 1,$$

and therefore the proof of (13.150) is complete.

Moreover, if $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$ and $y \in B_\rho$, we recall (13.149) and we see that

$$\begin{aligned} |h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1} &\leq |h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} \\ &\leq |f(|y+x|) - f(|x|)|^{p-1} \lesssim r^{-(qs+k+1)(p-1)} ((\tilde{x} + |y|)^{k+1} - \tilde{x}^{k+1})^{p-1}, \end{aligned}$$

and thus a change of variable gives that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x)} \frac{((|y| + \tilde{x})^{k+1} - \tilde{x}^{k+1})^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &= r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{\rho}{\tilde{x}}}^+ \cap B_{\frac{r}{2\tilde{x}}}(\frac{x}{\tilde{x}})} \frac{((|y| + 1)^{k+1} - 1)^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

From this, and using also (13.117), (13.133) and (13.150) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)} \tilde{x}^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{\rho}{\tilde{x}}}^+} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-(k+1)(p-1)}} dy \\ &\lesssim \frac{r^{-(p-1)(qs+k+1)}}{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} \rho^{(k+1)(p-1)-sp} \\ &\lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{(k+1)(p-1) - sp} \\ &\leq \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}. \end{aligned}$$

This establishes (13.122) if $x \in B_{\frac{2}{3}r} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$.

If instead $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus B_{\frac{2}{3}r}$ we argue as follows. We notice that

$$(13.151) \quad B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x) \subset \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\tilde{x}},$$

since, if $y \in B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x)$ then, recalling (13.130),

$$|y| \geq |x| - |y-x| = \tilde{x} + \frac{r}{2} - |y-x| \geq \tilde{x}.$$

Thus, according to (13.132) and (13.151), we have that

$$B_\rho^+ \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x) \subset B_\rho^+ \cap B_{\tilde{x}}^c = \emptyset.$$

As a consequence,

$$\int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}(x) \cap B_{\frac{r}{2}}(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} - |h(|x|) - h(|x-y|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy = 0.$$

This concludes the proof of claim (13.122).

Proof of (13.123): Making use of (13.103) we see that, for every $y \in B_\rho$,

$$\begin{aligned} |h(|y \pm x|) - h(|x|)| &\leq |f(|x \pm y|) - f(|x|)| \leq \int_{|x|}^{|x|+|y|} f'(t) dt \leq f'(|x| + |y|)|y| \\ &\lesssim (r - |x| - |y|)^{-qs-1} |y| = (2\rho - |y|)^{-qs-1} |y| \leq \rho^{-qs-1} |y|. \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to this, and also changing variable, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} + |h(|x-y|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} \int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}^c(x)} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p+1}} \\ &= \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{\rho}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1^c(\frac{x}{|x|})} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp-p+1}} \\ &\leq \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{\rho}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1^c(\frac{x}{|x|})} \frac{dy}{|y'|^{n+sp-p+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

We suppose, without loss of generality, that $x = |x|e_n$, and so

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} + |h(|x-y|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\lesssim \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{B_{\frac{\rho}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1^c(e_n)} \frac{dy}{|y'|^{n+sp-p+1}} \end{aligned}$$

Now, we remark that, if $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{r}{2}}}$,

$$\frac{\rho}{|x|} = \frac{r}{2|x|} - \frac{1}{2} \leq 1 - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

As a consequence, denoting by $y = (y', y_n) \in \mathbb{R}^{n-1} \times \mathbb{R}$, we have that

$$B_{\frac{\rho}{|x|}}^+ \cap B_1^c(e_n) \subset \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ s.t. } |y'| \leq \frac{\rho}{|x|} \text{ and } y_n \in \left(0, 1 - \sqrt{1 - |y'|^2} \right) \right\},$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{B_\rho^+ \cap B_{|x|}^c(x)} \frac{|h(|y+x|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1} + |h(|x-y|) - h(|x|)|^{p-1}}{|y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
 & \lesssim \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{\{|y'| \leq \frac{\rho}{|x|}\}} \frac{1}{|y'|^{n+sp-p+1}} \left(\int_0^{1-\sqrt{1-|y'|^2}} dy_n \right) dy' \\
 & = \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{\{|y'| \leq \frac{\rho}{|x|}\}} \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - |y'|^2}}{|y'|^{n+sp-p+1}} dy' \\
 & \leq \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} |x|^{p-1-sp} \int_{\{|y'| \leq \frac{\rho}{|x|}\}} \frac{2}{\sqrt{3} |y'|^{n+sp-p-1}} dy' \\
 & \lesssim \rho^{-(p-1)(qs+1)} |x|^{p-1-sp} \frac{\rho^{p-sp}}{|x|^{p-sp}} \frac{1}{p-sp} \\
 & \lesssim \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{1-s}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of claim (13.123).

(iii) **Case** $x \in B_r \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$. In this case, for every $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ it holds that

$$v(y) - v(x) = v(y) - 1 \leq 0.$$

From this, we deduce that

$$\int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dy \leq 0,$$

and (13.116) trivially follows. □

We now provide an estimate on $r - \hat{r}$, where \hat{r} has been defined in (13.51).

Proposition 13.20. *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $r \in (1, +\infty)$.*

Let f and \hat{r} be defined respectively as in (13.34) and (13.51).

Then, there exists $\hat{C}_{p,m} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$r - \hat{r} > \hat{C}_{p,m}.$$

Proof. From the computations in (13.36), we see that, for every $t \in (\frac{r}{2}, r)$,

$$f(t) \geq (r-t)^{-qs} - c_{k,q,s} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{-qs},$$

where $c_{k,q,s}$ is given in (13.37).

Thus, if we define

$$(13.152) \quad r_0 := r - \left(c_{k,q,s} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs} + 1 \right)^{-\frac{1}{qs}},$$

we obtain that $f(t) \geq 1$ for every $t \in (r_0, r)$.

Therefore, owing to (13.51), we obtain that $\hat{r} < r_0$. This gives that

$$r - \hat{r} \geq \left(c_{k,q,s} \left(\frac{r}{2} \right)^{-qs} + 1 \right)^{-\frac{1}{qs}} \geq (c_{k,q,s} 2^{qs} + 1)^{-\frac{1}{qs}} =: C_{q,s,k}.$$

Hence, in order to complete the proof of Lemma 13.20, it is only left to show that there exists $\widehat{C}_{p,m} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(13.153) \quad C_{q,s,k} \geq \widehat{C}_{p,m}.$$

To prove (13.153), we make use of (13.46) and we obtain that

$$(13.154) \quad C_{q,s,k} \geq (qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q + 1)^{-\frac{1}{qs}} = \left(1 - \frac{qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q}{qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q + 1} \right)^{\frac{1}{qs}}.$$

Now we consider the continuous function $l : (0, 1] \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ defined by

$$l(s) := \left(1 - \frac{qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q}{qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q + 1} \right)^{\frac{1}{qs}}.$$

We set $s_0 := \min \left\{ 1, \frac{1}{q2^{q+1}c_{p,m}^{(1)}} \right\}$ and we observe that, for every $s \in (0, s_0)$,

$$1 - \frac{qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q}{qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q + 1} \geq \frac{1}{2}$$

and therefore

$$l(s) \geq (1 - qsc_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q)^{\frac{1}{qs}}.$$

Taking the liminf as $s \rightarrow 0$, we obtain that

$$\liminf_{s \rightarrow 0} l(s) \geq e^{-c_{p,m}^{(1)} 2^q}.$$

From this, the fact that $l \in C((0, 1], (0, +\infty))$ and (13.154), we obtain (13.153), as desired. \square

Corollary 13.21. *Let $p \in (1, 2)$, $s \in \left[\frac{p-1}{2p}, 1\right)$, $r \in (1, +\infty)$ and $\mu \in (0, +\infty)$. Let $v : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be defined as in (13.34).*

Then, there exists $C_{\mu,n,p,m} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $x \in B_r$,

$$(13.155) \quad \int_{B_\mu(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \leq \frac{C_{\mu,n,p,m}}{1 - s}.$$

Proof. We recall that, if \hat{r} is given as in (13.51), then, for every $x \in B_r \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$ and every $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$v(y) - v(x) = v(y) - 1 \leq 0.$$

Consequently, for every $x \in B_r \setminus B_{\hat{r}}$ and $\mu \in (0, +\infty)$,

$$\int_{B_\mu(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \leq 0,$$

and (13.155) plainly follows.

Furthermore, in virtue of (13.116) and Lemma 13.20, if $\rho := \frac{r-|x|}{2}$ we have that, for every $x \in B_{\hat{r}} \setminus \overline{B_{\frac{\hat{r}}{2}}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy &\leq C_{n,p,m} \frac{\rho^{-qs(p-1)-sp}}{p - sp} \\ &\leq \frac{C_{n,p,m}}{p - sp} \left(\frac{r - \hat{r}}{2}\right)^{-qs(p-1)-sp} \leq \frac{C_{n,p,m}}{p - sp} \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{p,m}}{2}\right)^{-qs(p-1)-sp}. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, if $\mu \in [\rho, +\infty)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_\mu(x) \setminus B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy &\leq \int_{B_\mu(x) \setminus B_\rho(x)} \frac{dy}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \\ &\leq \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{sp} \rho^{-sp} \leq \frac{1}{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{p-sp} \rho^{-sp} \leq \frac{1}{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{p-sp} \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{p,m}}{2}\right)^{-sp}. \end{aligned}$$

From the last two displays we thus obtain that, if $\mu \in [\rho, +\infty)$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_\mu(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ &\leq \frac{C_{n,m,p}}{p - sp} \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{p,m}}{2}\right)^{-qs(p-1)-sp} + \frac{1}{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{p-sp} \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{p,m}}{2}\right)^{-sp} \end{aligned}$$

which gives the desired estimate.

Similarly, if $\mu \in (0, \rho)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{B_\mu(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
= & \int_{B_\rho(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
& - \int_{B_\rho(x) \setminus B_\mu(x)} \frac{(v(y) - v(x)) |v(y) - v(x)|^{p-2}}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\
\leq & \frac{C_{n,m,p}}{p - sp} \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{p,m}}{2} \right)^{-qs(p-1)-sp} + 2^{p-1} \int_{B_\rho(x) \setminus B_\mu(x)} \frac{dy}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \\
\leq & \frac{C_{n,m,p}}{p - sp} \left(\frac{\widehat{C}_{p,m}}{2} \right)^{-qs(p-1)-sp} + \frac{2^{p-1}}{p-1} \frac{\omega_{n-1}}{p - sp} \mu^{-sp},
\end{aligned}$$

as desired. □

DENSITY ESTIMATES FOR A
(NON)LOCAL VARIATIONAL MODEL
WITH DEGENERATE DOUBLE-WELL
POTENTIAL

In this chapter we provide density estimates for a class of functions which includes all the minimizers of the energy

$$\mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := (1 - s) \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \right) + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

where $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and W is a double-well potential with polynomial growth $m \in [p, +\infty)$ from the minima.

Moreover, making use of a Γ -convergence result for \mathcal{E}_s^p as $s \rightarrow 1$, we obtain density estimates for the minimizers of the limit energy functional, which takes the form

$$\mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{K_{n,p}}{2p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^p + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

for a suitable $K_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$.

14.1 Introduction

Phase separation is a cross-disciplinary field, which attracts researchers from physics [Web+19; TH13; Row79; Gur85; GP58; CH58; AC72], biology [Bra09; Alb17; Mit16] and social sciences [Har20; Cas09]. This model is used to describe a broad variety of systems characterized by the interaction of two (or more) components, which are associated to different values of a suitable state parameter. Such a parameter is often expressed by a function $u : \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, where the pure phases are given by -1 and 1 .

In the classical framework, a prototype of energy for phase separation is given by the non-scaled energy functional

$$(14.1) \quad \mathcal{E}^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^p dx + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

where $p \in (1, +\infty)$. The function $W : [-1, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a double-well potential satisfying

$$W(t) > 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in (-1, 1) \quad \text{and} \quad W(\pm 1) = 0.$$

In this framework, phase separation is induced by the minimization of \mathcal{E}^p . More precisely, on the one hand, the action of the potential W pushes the minimizers of \mathcal{E}^p to attain values as close as possible to its zeros, namely the pure phases ± 1 . Furthermore, the presence of the gradient term of L^p -type discourages the formation of subregions of Ω where the state parameter jumps from one pure phase to the other. These regions, which are characterized by intermediate values of the state parameter, are known as “interfaces”.

A common matter of investigation in physics, biology, mathematical physics and analysis is the description of these interfaces. An interesting approach to this problem is provided by density estimates.

The aim of density estimates is to establish lower bounds for the measure of the portion of the domain where the state parameter attains values close to the pure phases. The first result in this direction was obtained by L. Caffarelli and A. Córdoba. In [CC95] they proved that if $u : \Omega \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}^2 , then for every $\theta \in (-1, 1)$ and $r \in (0, +\infty)$ large enough it holds that $\{|u| > \theta\} \cap B_r$ is comparable to r^n . On the other hand, they showed that the measure of the interface $\{|u| \leq \theta\} \cap B_r$ behaves like r^{n-1} .

Since the pioneering work of L. Caffarelli and A. Córdoba, density estimates have been established for minimizers and quasiminimizers of a larger class of energy functionals associated to phenomena of phase separation. In [PV05b] and [PV05a] density estimates have been proved for minimizers of \mathcal{E}^p with $p \in (1, +\infty)$. Also, χ -shaped potentials (i.e., piecewise constant potentials) are considered, which are associated to models for fluid jets. In [FV08] density estimates are proved for the same energies but under the weaker assumption of quasiminimality.

Nonlocal counterparts of the energies studied in [CC95; PV05b; PV05a; FV08] have already been considered in the literature. A common approach to generalize phase separation in a nonlocal framework is to replace the gradient term of L^p -type with the Gagliardo seminorm. With such a choice, the energy used to describe nonlocal phase separation becomes

$$(14.2) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx,$$

where $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$.

Density estimates for the energy functional in (14.2) with $p = 2$ were proved in [SV11] for every $s \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$, making use of the Sobolev inequality. Moreover, in [SV14], the same authors generalized the result for every $s \in (0, 1)$.

In all the aforementioned papers on density estimates, the potential W is taken such that its growth from the minima is comparable to a polynomial of degree m , where $m \in (1, p]$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$ is the homogeneity of the gradient term. Potentials W that detach from their minima with $m \geq p$ are known as *degenerate potentials*, and to the best of our knowledge these have been previously studied in the framework of density estimates only in two others research articles, namely [DFV18] and Chapter 13.

In the local setting, see [DFV18], density estimates for degenerate double-well potentials have been proved for quasiminimizers of \mathcal{E}^p . For our purposes, it is also important to recall that such a result came with an additional restriction on the growth of the potential with respect to its wells. Indeed, in Theorem 1.1 of [DFV18],

density estimates are showed as far as $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$ and n satisfy

$$(14.3) \quad \frac{pm}{m-p} > n,$$

see (1.7) in [DFV18].

In the nonlocal setting, see Chapter 13, density estimates for degenerate double-well potentials have been proved for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p for every $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$. This result was obtained through the Sobolev inequality, with an approach similar to the one used by E. Valdinoci and O. Savin in [SV11]. Nevertheless, the presence of a degenerate double-well potential together with a homogeneity $p \neq 2$ required the introduction of a new barrier bespoke for the specifics of the problem under consideration, see Theorem 13.10.

In this chapter, we consider the renormalized non-scaled free energy

$$(14.4) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := (1-s) & \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \right) \\ & + \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx, \end{aligned}$$

with W being a degenerate double-well potential. In particular, we complete the work begun in Chapter 13, and establish, for every $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$, density estimates for a class of state parameters which includes all minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p , see Theorems 14.4 and 14.5 below.

The presence of $(1-s)$ in front of the kinetic term is needed to guarantee that as $s \rightarrow 1$ the energy \mathcal{E}_s^p Γ -converges to an energy proportional to the one in (14.1), see Theorem 14.9 below. From this we will be able to obtain density estimates for minimizers of (14.1) starting from the nonlocal density estimates obtained in Theorem 14.5. As a byproduct, we are able to show that the condition in (14.3) for minimizers is not sharp, and density estimates hold for the local and degenerate case for every $n \geq 2$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$, see Theorem 14.10. The optimality of condition (14.3) for quasiminimizers will remain as an open problem.

The precise hypotheses on W , the statement of Theorems 14.4, 14.5, 14.9 and 14.10 and their corollaries are all discussed in the following section.

14.2 Mathematical framework and main results

In what follows we let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ open, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$. We consider a potential $W : [-1, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ such that

$$(14.5) \quad W \text{ is lower semicontinuous.}$$

Also, we suppose that, for every $x \in [-1, 1]$,

$$(14.6) \quad \lambda \chi_{(-\infty, \theta]}(x) |1 + x|^m \leq W(x) \leq \Lambda |1 + x|^m,$$

for some $\lambda \in (0, 1]$, $\Lambda \in [1, +\infty)$, $\theta \in (-1, 1)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$.

Moreover, we assume that, for all $-1 \leq r \leq t \leq -1 + q$,

$$(14.7) \quad W(t) - W(r) \geq c_1(t - r) |1 + r|^{m-1} + c_1(t - r)^k,$$

for some $q \in (0, 1)$ and $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$, where

$$(14.8) \quad k := \begin{cases} m & \text{if } m \in \mathbb{N} \\ [m] + 1 & \text{if } m \in (1, +\infty) \setminus \mathbb{N}. \end{cases}$$

Given $m \in (1, +\infty)$, the prototype of double-well potential that we have in mind has the form

$$W_m(x) := \frac{(1 - x^2)^m}{2m},$$

since one can show the validity of condition (14.7) for this model case (see In Proposition 14.16).

For every measurable $u : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we define

$$\mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy$$

and rewrite the energy in (14.4) as

$$\mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) := (1 - s)\mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) + \int_{\Omega} W(u) dx.$$

The normalizing constant $(1 - s)$ in front of \mathcal{K}_s^p is needed to obtain stable estimates as $s \rightarrow 1$ and recover density estimates for the local energy in (14.1) starting from the nonlocal ones. We will achieve such a result, see Theorem 14.10, by proving first

that \mathcal{E}_s^p Γ -converges as $s \rightarrow 1$ to an energy proportional to the one in (14.1), see Theorem 14.9. This point will be discussed more in detail in Section 14.2.

A suitable function space to study \mathcal{K}_s^p is

$$(14.9) \quad \widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega) := \{u : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ measurable s.t. } \mathcal{K}_s^p(u, \Omega) < +\infty\}.$$

Since the potential W is defined in the interval $[-1, 1]$, the suitable subspace of $\widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega)$ needed to study \mathcal{E}_s^p is

$$X^{s,p}(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in \widehat{H}^{s,p}(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } \|u\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq 1 \right\}.$$

Moreover, it will be useful to consider the subspace of $X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ of functions with a prescribed trace. Hence, given any measurable $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ we denote the subspace of $X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ with trace f , i.e.

$$X_f^{s,p}(\Omega) := \{u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } u = f \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega\}.$$

Then, we have the following definition:

Definition 14.1 (ε -minimizer). If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is bounded, given $\varepsilon \in [0, +\infty)$, we say that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is an ε -minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p if, for every $v \in X_u^{s,p}(\Omega)$,

$$\mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) \leq \varepsilon + \mathcal{E}_s^p(v, \Omega).$$

If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is unbounded, we say that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is an ε -minimizer for $\mathcal{E}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega)$ if for any $\Omega' \subset\subset \Omega$ it is a minimizer of $\mathcal{E}_s^p(\cdot, \Omega')$.

We observe that for $\varepsilon = 0$ one recovers the definition of minimizer of \mathcal{E}_s^p , see for e.g. Definition 13.1 in Chapter 13.

Remark 14.2. Note that if u is an ε -minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p in $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ open and bounded, then u ε -minimizes \mathcal{E}_s^p in every measurable subdomain $\Omega' \subset \Omega$.

For every $u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$, we define the quantity

$$(14.10) \quad [u]_{B,\alpha} := \sup \left\{ [u]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \text{ s.t. } x_0 \in B_R \text{ and } B_{R+2} \subset \Omega \right\}$$

and we consider the subspace of $C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$ given by

$$C_B^\alpha(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } [u]_{B,\alpha} < +\infty \right\}.$$

Note that for every $\Omega \neq \mathbb{R}^n$ we have that $C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega) = C_B^\alpha(\Omega)$.

Now we introduce the mathematical setting necessary to study the local contribution to the energy functional in (14.1). To do so, we let

$$K_{n,p} := \int_{\partial B_1} |\omega \cdot e_1|^p dH_\omega^{n-1}$$

and, for every $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$,

$$\mathcal{K}_1^p(u, \Omega) := \frac{K_{n,p}}{2p} \int_\Omega |\nabla u(x)|^p dx.$$

Furthermore, we define

$$X^{1,p}(\Omega) := \left\{ u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega) \text{ s.t. } \|u\|_{L^\infty(\Omega)} \leq 1 \right\}$$

and, for every $u \in X^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we consider the energy functional

$$(14.11) \quad \mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) := \mathcal{K}_1^p(u, \Omega) + \int_\Omega W(u(x)) dx.$$

Also, as customary we denote by $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ the closure of $C_c^\infty(\Omega)$ with respect to the $\|\cdot\|_{W^{1,p}(\Omega)}$ -norm and we recall the definition of minimizer for \mathcal{E}_1^p :

Definition 14.3 (Minimizer for \mathcal{E}_1^p). If $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is open and bounded, we say that $u \in X^{1,p}(\Omega)$ is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_1^p in $X^{1,p}(\Omega)$ if for every $w \in X^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that $u - w \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$

$$\mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) \leq \mathcal{E}_1^p(w, \Omega).$$

Nonlocal density estimates

We are now ready to state the main result of this chapter:

Theorem 14.4 (Density estimates for ε -minimizers). *Let $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, \theta]$ and*

$$(14.12) \quad \theta_* := \min \{ \theta_1, \theta_2, -1 + q \} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta^* := \max \{ \theta_1, \theta_2, -1 + q \}.$$

Also, let $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ be such that

$$(14.13) \quad \mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) > c_0,$$

for some $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$.

Then, there exists $\delta := \delta_{s,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_*,c_0} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, if $\varepsilon \in [0, \delta)$ and u is an ε -minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p , the following holds true:

There exist $R^* := R_{s,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_*,r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ and $c := c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for any $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{3r} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.14) \quad c \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) > \tilde{c}r^n.$$

Here above and in the rest of the chapter, $\mathcal{L}^n(E)$ denotes the Lebesgue measure of a set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$. We observe that if $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, \frac{1}{p})$ and $\varepsilon = 0$ then Theorem 14.4 coincides with Theorem 13.3. However, if $p \neq 2$ and $m \geq p$ or $p = 2$ and $m > 2$, even the cases $\varepsilon = 0$ and $s \in [\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ are new in the literature. Moreover, if $\varepsilon > 0$, then Theorem 14.4 is new for every $s \in (0, 1)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$.

In the following result, we establish density estimates for ε -minimizers that are stable with respect to $s \rightarrow 1$. To be more precise, for $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ and $s \in [s_0, 1)$, we show that density estimates hold with structural constants which can be chosen independently from s , but depending on s_0 . The proof of this result relies on the additional regularity assumption that the ε -minimizer is Hölder continuous. The precise statement of the result is the following:

Theorem 14.5 (Stable density estimates for ε -minimizers). *Let $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{p}, 1)$, $s \in [s_0, 1)$, $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, \theta]$ and θ_*, θ^* be defined as in (14.12). Also, let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $u \in C_B^\alpha(\Omega) \cap X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ such that there exist $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$ and (14.13).*

Then, there exists $\delta := \delta_{s_0,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_*,c_0,\alpha,[u]_{B,\alpha}} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, if $\varepsilon \in [0, \delta)$ and u is an ε -minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p the following holds true:

There exist $R^* := R_{s_0,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_*,r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s_0,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0,\alpha,[u]_{B,\alpha}} \in (0, 1)$ and $c := c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for any $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.15) \quad c \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) > \tilde{c}r^n.$$

From Theorem 14.5, one can establish density estimates for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p that are stable as $s \rightarrow 1$ and do not require any additional assumption on the regularity of the minimizer.

Indeed, it is well known that minimizers for \mathcal{E}_s^p are Hölder continuous, see for instance [IMS16; BLS18; Coz17] and the references therein. In particular in [Coz17], using fractional De Giorgi classes, M. Cozzi proved Hölder estimates for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p that do not depend on s whenever $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $s \in [s_0, 1)$ and $n \geq 2$, see Theorem 6.4 and Proposition 7.5 in [Coz17] or Theorem 13.9 in Chapter 13. Therefore, as a byproduct of Theorem 14.5, we obtain the stability of density estimates for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p as $s \rightarrow 1$. The precise statement of this result goes as follows:

Corollary 14.6 (Stable density estimates for minimizers). *Let $n \geq 2$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ and $s \in [s_0, 1)$. Also, let $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, \theta]$ and θ_*, θ^* be defined as in (14.12).*

Moreover, we assume that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p and that there exist $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$ and (14.13) is satisfied.

Then, there exist $R^ := R_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1, \theta_*, r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s_0, n, p, m, \Lambda, c_1, \theta_*, r_0, c_0} \in (0, 1)$ and $c := c_{m, \theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for any $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,*

$$(14.16) \quad c_{m, \theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) > \tilde{c}r^n.$$

The presence of the first term in the left-hand side of (14.14), (14.15) and (14.16) is a consequence of the lower bound in (14.6). To be more precise, under some additional assumptions on the lower bound for W (see (14.18) below) it is possible to reabsorb such term into the right-hand side of the inequality, obtaining the “full density estimates”. This is made possible thanks to the following upper bound for the energy \mathcal{E}_s^p .

Theorem 14.7. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$ and u be a minimizer of \mathcal{E}_s^p in $X^{s,p}(B_{R+2})$ with $R \geq 2$. Then, there exists $\bar{C} := \bar{C}_{n, p, m, \Lambda} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that*

$$(14.17) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, B_R) \leq \frac{\bar{C}}{s} \begin{cases} \frac{R^{n-sp}}{1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ R^{n-1} \log(R) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{R^{n-1}}{sp-1} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

This result was originally proved in [SV14] for $p = 2$ and without the explicit dependence of the constant with respect to s .

From Theorem 14.4, Corollary 14.6 and Theorem 14.7 we obtain the following density estimate:

Corollary 14.8. *Let $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, 1)$, θ_* , θ^* as in (14.12) and $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ be a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p . Moreover, let $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ be such that $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$ and (14.13) is satisfied.*

Also, we assume that for every $\mu \in (-1, 1)$ there exists $\lambda_\mu \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $x \in (-1, 1)$,

$$(14.18) \quad \lambda_\mu \chi_{(-\infty, \mu]}(x) |1 + x|^m \leq W(x).$$

Then, there exist $R^ := R_{s,n,m,p,c_1,\theta_*,r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$ and $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ such that, for any $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,*

$$(14.19) \quad \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) > \tilde{c}r^n.$$

Furthermore, if $n \geq 2$, $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{p}, 1)$ and $s \in [s_0, 1)$, the quantities R^ and \tilde{c} do not depend on s , namely*

$$(14.20) \quad R^* := R_{s_0,n,m,p,c_1,\theta_*,r_0}^* \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s_0,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0}.$$

Local density estimates

In this section we state the main result concerning density estimates for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_1^p . To do so, we first need to state the following Γ -convergence result. In particular, we show that \mathcal{E}_s^p Γ -converges to \mathcal{E}_1^p as $s \rightarrow 1$. This result will be employed to prove density estimates for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_1^p (see Theorem 14.10 below), starting from the density estimates for ε -minimizers of \mathcal{E}_s^p discussed in Theorem 14.5.

Theorem 14.9 (Γ -convergence of \mathcal{E}_s^p). *Let $\{s_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subset (0, 1)$ such that $s_k \rightarrow 1$. Also, let $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be open, bounded and Lipschitz. Then, we have the following:*

(i) *Let $\{u_{s_k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X^{s_k,p}(\Omega)$ and $M \in (0, +\infty)$ be such that*

$$(14.21) \quad \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} (1 - s_k) \mathcal{K}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega) \leq M.$$

Then, up to a subsequence, $u_{s_k} \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\Omega)$ for some $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

Moreover, if $u_{s_k} \in X_0^{s_k,p}(\Omega)$ for every k , we obtain that $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

(ii) For any $u \in L^p(\Omega)$ and $\{u_{s_k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X^{s_k,p}(\Omega)$ such that $u_{s_k} \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\Omega)$ it holds that

$$(14.22) \quad \mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega).$$

(iii) For any $u \in L^p(\Omega)$ satisfying $|u| \leq 1$ a.e. in Ω there exists $\{u_{s_k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X^{s_k,p}(\Omega)$ such that $u_{s_k} \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\Omega)$ and

$$\mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) \geq \limsup_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega).$$

Furthermore, if $u \in X^{1,p}(\Omega)$, there exists $v \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ for every $s \in (0, 1)$ such that $u \equiv v$ in Ω and

$$(14.23) \quad \mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) = \limsup_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(v, \Omega).$$

As aforementioned, making use of Theorem 14.5 and Theorem 14.9 we can establish density estimates for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_1^p . The statement of the result is the following:

Theorem 14.10. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be open and bounded, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $m \in [p, +\infty)$ and $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, \theta]$. Also, we set θ_* and θ^* as in (14.12). Moreover, we assume that u is a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_1^p in $X^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and for some $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$*

$$(14.24) \quad \mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) \geq c_0.$$

Then, there exist $R^ := R_{n,m,p,c_1,\theta_*,c_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ and $c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ for which $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,*

$$c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) > \tilde{c}r^n$$

We recall that such a result was already proved in [DFV18] for quasiminimizers (and therefore also for minimizers) under a suitable constraint on n, p and m . More precisely, in Theorem 1.1 in [DFV18], it is stated that density estimates hold for quasiminimizers of \mathcal{E}_1^p if n, p and m satisfy

$$(14.25) \quad \frac{pm}{m-p} > n.$$

As stated in Remark 1.7 in [DFV18], it is not known whether the condition in (14.25) is sharp or not. The novelty in Theorem 14.10 is to prove that (14.25) is not sharp. Indeed, we show that density estimates hold for minimizers of \mathcal{E}_1^p for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $m \in [p, +\infty)$. The case of quasiminimizers is still an open problem.

The rest of the chapter is structured as follows. In Section 14.3 we prove Theorems 14.4, 14.5 and Corollaries 14.6, 14.8. These results are a consequence of a preliminary estimate, Lemma 14.13 in Section 14.3, which holds true for every ε -minimizer of \mathcal{E}_s^p with $\varepsilon \in (0, +\infty)$ and satisfying (14.13). The proofs of Theorems 14.4 and 14.5 are contained in Section 14.3. Section 14.3 is devoted to the proofs of Corollaries 14.6 and 14.8. The proofs of Theorems 14.9 and 14.10 are provided in Section 14.4. Finally, in Section 14.5 we prove Theorem 14.7.

14.3 Proof of Theorems 14.4 & 14.5 and Corollaries 14.6 & 14.8

In this section we prove Theorems 14.4 & 14.5 and Corollaries 14.6 & 14.8. These proofs are based on a preliminary estimate, which holds true for any ε -minimizer $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ satisfying equation (14.13). Such an estimate is the content of Lemma 14.13 in Section 14.3 below. In Section 14.3, we use the inequality stated in Lemma 14.13 to prove the main results, namely Theorem 14.4 and Theorem 14.5. Finally, in Section 14.3 we provide the proofs of Corollaries 14.6 and 14.8.

Remark 14.11. We notice that in (14.13) we can assume without loss of generality that $c_0 \in (1, +\infty)$. More precisely, we show that if the results in either Theorem 14.4 or Theorem 14.5 hold true with $c_0 \in (1, +\infty)$, then they hold true also with $c_0 \in (0, 1]$.

Therefore, in what follows we assume that

$$(14.26) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Theorem 14.4 and Theorem 14.5 hold true} \\ \text{under the additional assumption that } c_0 \in (1, +\infty). \end{array}$$

Then, let $c_0 \in (0, 1]$ (and note that we are now not entitled in principle to use Theorem 14.4 and Theorem 14.5 for this c_0). Let also $\tilde{c}_0 \in (1, +\infty)$ and define

$$r := \left(\frac{c_0}{\tilde{c}_0}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}}.$$

Also, if $f \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ we consider its rescaling $f_r \in X^{s,p}\left(\Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}\right)$ given by

$$f_r(x) := f(rx).$$

Thus, let $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ satisfy (14.13) and define $\tilde{r}_0 := \frac{r_0}{r}$.

In this way,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^n(B_{\tilde{r}_0} \cap \{u_r > \theta_1\}) &= \frac{1}{r^n} \mathcal{L}^n(B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}) \\ (14.27) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\geq \frac{c_0}{r^n} \\ &= \tilde{c}_0. \end{aligned}$$

Also, for all $\varepsilon \in (0, +\infty)$,

$$\tilde{W} := r^{sp}W, \quad \tilde{\varepsilon} := \varepsilon r^{sp-n} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p\left(\cdot, \Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}\right) := (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^p\left(\cdot, \Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}\right) + \|\tilde{W}(\cdot)\|_{L^1\left(\Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}\right)}.$$

If $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is an ε -minimizer, then, for every $w_r \in X_{u_r}^{s,p}\left(\Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}\right)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p(w_r, \Omega) + \tilde{\varepsilon} &= r^{sp-n}(\mathcal{E}_s^p(w, \Omega) + \varepsilon) \\ (14.28) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\geq r^{sp-n}\mathcal{E}_s^p(u, \Omega) \\ &= \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p\left(u_r, \Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

In particular, we obtain that u_r is a $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ -minimizer for $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_s^p\left(\cdot, \Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}\right)$.

Then, as a consequence of (14.26), (14.27), (14.28) and Theorem 14.4 we obtain that there exists $\delta := \delta_{s,n,m,p,c_1,\theta_*,\tilde{c}_0} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that if $\tilde{\varepsilon} \in [0, \delta)$ then there exist $R^* := R_{s,n,m,p,r^{sp}c_1,\theta_*,\tilde{r}_0}^* \in [\tilde{r}_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s,n,p,m,r^{sp}\Lambda,r^{sp}c_1,\theta_*,\tilde{r}_0,\tilde{c}_0} \in (0, 1)$ and $c := c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $t \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{3t} \subset \Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}$,

$$(14.29) \qquad \tilde{c}t^n < \mathcal{L}^n(B_t \cap \{u_r > \theta_2\}) + c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_t \cap \{\theta_* < u_r \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u_r(x)|^m dx$$

Now, we define

$$\delta^{(1)} := r^{n-sp}\delta \quad \text{and} \quad R^{(1)} := rR^*$$

Hence, by scaling, we obtain from (14.29) that if $\varepsilon \in [0, \delta^{(1)})$, then, for every $t \in [R^{(1)}, +\infty)$ such that $B_{3t} \subset \Omega$,

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_t \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) + c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_t \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx \geq \tilde{c}t^n.$$

Therefore, we have showed that if Theorem 14.4 holds true with $c_0 \in (1, +\infty)$, then it holds true with $c_0 \in (0, 1]$.

Now, we assume that $s_0 \in (\frac{1}{p}, 1)$, $s \in [s_0, 1)$ and also $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega) \cap C_B^\alpha(\Omega)$.

Then, as a consequence of (14.26), (14.27), (14.28) and Theorem 14.5 we obtain that there exists $\delta := \delta_{s_0,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_*,\tilde{c}_0,\alpha,[u]_{B,\alpha}} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, if $\tilde{\varepsilon} \in [0, \delta)$, then there exist $R^* := R^*_{s_0,n,p,m,c_1,\theta_*,\tilde{r}_0} \in [\tilde{r}_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s_0,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,\tilde{r}_0,\tilde{c}_0,\alpha,[u]_{B,\alpha}} \in (0, 1)$ and $c := c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for any $t \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{4t} \subset \Omega_{\frac{1}{r}}$,

$$(14.30) \quad \tilde{c}t^n < \mathcal{L}^n(B_t \cap \{u_r > \theta_2\}) + c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_t \cap \{\theta_* < u_r \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u_r(x)|^m dx.$$

Now we define

$$\delta^{(2)} := \delta \min_{s \in [s_0, 1]} r^{n-sp} \quad \text{and} \quad R^{(2)} := rR^*.$$

Therefore, by scaling, we obtain from (14.30) that if $\varepsilon \in [0, \delta^{(2)})$, then, for every $t \in [R^{(2)}, +\infty)$ such that $B_{4t} \subset \Omega$,

$$\mathcal{L}^n(B_t \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) + c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_t \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx \geq \tilde{c}t^n.$$

Hence, we have showed that if Theorem 14.5 holds true with $c_0 \in (1, +\infty)$, then it holds true with $c_0 \in (0, 1]$.

A preliminary estimate

In this section we state and prove a preliminary estimate for ε -minimizers $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$. This result will be employed in the proof of both Theorems 14.4 and 14.5. Before stating and commenting such a result, we first need to set some notation.

First, given any $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $s \in (0, 1)$ we let

$$(14.31) \quad \bar{p} := \max \{2, p\}, \quad l := \min \{2, p\} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{s} := \frac{sl}{2}.$$

Moreover, for every $\tau \in (0, +\infty)$ we recall the quantities

$$(14.32) \quad C_\tau := C_{s,\tau,n,p,m} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{R}_\tau := \bar{R}_{s,\tau,n,p,m}$$

defined respectively in (13.30) and (13.27). Also, from now on we introduce the quantity

$$(14.33) \quad \mu := \frac{c_1}{(1-s)p}$$

where $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$ is the structural constant in (14.7), and we choose the barrier $w \in C((-1, 1], \mathbb{R}^n)$ as in Theorem 13.10 with $\tau = \mu$. Furthermore, we define the constant

$$K_0 := \left[C_\mu \left(\frac{2}{1+\theta_*} \right) \right]^{\frac{m-1}{ps}} - 1,$$

and we notice that, according to (13.30),

$$(14.34) \quad K_0 \geq C_\mu^{\frac{m-1}{ps}} \geq \max \left\{ 1, \bar{R}_\mu^{\frac{ps}{m-1}} \right\}^{\frac{m-1}{ps}} \geq \bar{R}_\mu.$$

For later convenience, we also observe that, thanks to (13.31) in Theorem 13.10, for all $R \in (K_0, +\infty)$, all $K \in (K_0, R)$ and all $x \in B_{R-K}$,

$$(14.35) \quad w(x) \leq -1 + C_\mu(K+1)^{-\frac{ps}{m-1}} < -1 + \frac{1+\theta_*}{2}.$$

Now, given $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ and $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$, we define

$$(14.36) \quad v := \min \{u, w\}.$$

We notice that, as a consequence of (13.28),

$$(14.37) \quad v \equiv u \quad \text{in} \quad \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R.$$

Then, we define

$$(14.38) \quad a_R := \left\{ u - v \geq \frac{1+\theta_*}{4} \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad b_R := \left\{ \frac{1+\theta_*}{8} < u - v < \frac{1+\theta_*}{4} \right\}$$

and, using (14.35) and (14.38), we conclude that, for every $R \in (K_0, +\infty)$ and $K \in (K_0, R)$,

$$(14.39) \quad a_R \supset B_{R-K} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}.$$

Also, according to equation (14.37), the function $u - v$ has compact support. In particular, the symmetric decreasing rearrangement of $u - v$, denoted by $(u - v)^*$, is well defined. Hence, we can define

$$(14.40) \quad a_R^* := \left\{ (u - v)^* \geq \frac{1 + \theta_*}{4} \right\}, \quad b_R^* := \left\{ \frac{1 + \theta_*}{8} < (u - v)^* < \frac{1 + \theta_*}{4} \right\}$$

and $d_R^* := \mathbb{R}^n \setminus (a_R^* \cup b_R^*)$.

Now we state and prove the following facts regarding a_R^* , b_R^* and d_R^* .

Proposition 14.12. *Let $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, \theta]$ and θ_*, θ^* be defined as in (14.12). Moreover, we let $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ and $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$ and (14.13) is satisfied.*

Then, for every $R \in (K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$,

$$(14.41) \quad |a_R^*| \geq c_0$$

and there exist $r_2 \in (0, +\infty)$ and $r_1 \in [0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(14.42) \quad a_R^* = B_{r_2}, \quad b_R^* = B_{r_1+r_2} \setminus B_{r_2} \quad \text{and} \quad d_R^* = \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r_2+r_1}.$$

Proof. First, from (14.13) and (14.39) we infer that, for every $R \in (K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ and $K \in (K_0, R - r_0)$,

$$\begin{aligned} |a_R^*| &= |a_R| \\ &\geq |B_{R-K} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}| \\ &\geq |B_{R-K} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}| \\ &\geq |B_{r_0} \cap \{u > \theta_1\}| \\ &\geq c_0. \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (14.41).

Now we recall that the superlevel sets of the symmetric decreasing rearrangement of a function are balls in \mathbb{R}^n . Thus, there exist $r_2, r_1 \in [0, +\infty)$ such that

$$a_R^* = B_{r_2}, \quad b_R^* = B_{r_1+r_2} \setminus B_{r_2} \quad \text{and} \quad d_R^* = \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r_2+r_1}.$$

Moreover, thanks to (14.41) we obtain that $r_2 > (\omega_n c_0)^{\frac{1}{n}}$, which completes the proof of (14.42). \square

We now set

$$(14.43) \quad \hat{c}_p := \begin{cases} 2^{1-p} & \text{if } p \in [2, +\infty) \\ \frac{3p(p-1)}{4^{4-p}} & \text{if } p \in (1, 2). \end{cases}$$

Also, given any $K \in (0, +\infty)$, we define the following constants

$$(14.44) \quad \begin{aligned} c_2 &:= c_1 \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{8} \right)^k, & c_3 &:= c_2(1 + K)^p \\ \bar{c}_4 &:= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{8} \right)^{\bar{p}} & \text{and } c_5 &:= C_\mu^{m-1} \frac{2c_1 + \Lambda}{\hat{c}_p} + \frac{c_3}{\hat{c}_p}, \end{aligned}$$

where k has been introduced in (14.8).

Moreover, for every $t \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $B_t \subset \Omega$, we let

$$(14.45) \quad V(t) := \mathcal{L}^n(B_t \cap \{u > \theta_*\}).$$

Finally, given any measurable subsets $A, D \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ we set

$$(14.46) \quad L(A, D) := \int_A \int_D \frac{dx dy}{|x - y|^{n+sp}}.$$

With this, we are ready to state the main result of this section:

Lemma 14.13. *Let $\varepsilon \in [0, +\infty)$, $\theta_1, \theta_2 \in (-1, \theta]$ and θ_*, θ^* be defined as in (14.12). Also, let $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ be an ε -minimizer for \mathcal{E}_s^p and $c_0, r_0 \in (0, +\infty)$ be such that $B_{r_0} \subset \Omega$ and (14.13) is satisfied.*

Then, for every $R \in (K_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$ and $K \in (K_0, R)$,

$$(14.47) \quad (1 - s)\bar{c}_4 L(a_R^*, d_R^*) + \frac{c_2}{\hat{c}_p} |b_R^*| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{\hat{c}_p} + c_5 \int_0^R (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt.$$

As aforementioned at the beginning of Section 14.3, Lemma 14.13 is used to prove both Theorem 14.4 and 14.5. Indeed, we observe that any ε -minimizer satisfying the hypothesis of either Theorem 14.4 or 14.5 satisfies automatically all the conditions required to apply Lemma 14.13.

Proof of Lemma 14.13. For every $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$, we set

$$(14.48) \quad A_k(R) := c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} (u - w)^k dx.$$

We claim that, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_R \subset \Omega$,

(14.49)

$$\hat{c}_p(1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) \leq \varepsilon + C_\mu^{m-1}(2c_1 + \Lambda) \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \theta_*\}} (R - |x| + 1)^{-sp} dx - A_k(R).$$

In order to show (14.49), we recall equation (13.34), according to which, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} (1-s)\hat{c}_p\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) & \leq (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) - (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^p(v, B_R) \\ & \quad - (1-s)p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v\}} (u(x) - v(x))(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

From this, we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} (1-s)\hat{c}_p\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) & \leq (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) - (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^p(v, B_R) + \int_{B_R} W(u) - W(v) dx \\ & \quad + \int_{B_R} W(v) - W(u) dx - (1-s)p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v\}} (u(x) - v(x))(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx \\ & = \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, B_R) - \mathcal{E}_s^p(v, B_R) + \int_{B_R} W(v) - W(u) dx \\ & \quad - (1-s)p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v\}} (u(x) - v(x))(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, recalling the ε -minimality of u and (14.37) we gather that

(14.50)

$$\begin{aligned} (1-s)\hat{c}_p\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) & \leq \varepsilon + \int_{B_R} W(v) - W(u) dx - (1-s)p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v\}} (u(x) - v(x))(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx \\ & = \varepsilon + \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v\}} W(v) - W(u) dx - (1-s)p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > v\}} (u(x) - v(x))(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Now, using (14.6) and (14.7) we obtain that, for $k \in \mathbb{N}$ as in (14.8),

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{B_R \cap \{u > w\}} W(w) - W(u) \, dx \\
 (14.51) \quad &= \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} W(w) - W(u) \, dx + \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{w, \theta_*\}\}} W(w) - W(u) \, dx \\
 &\leq -c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} |1 + w|^{m-1} (u - w) \, dx - c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} (u - w)^k \, dx \\
 &\quad + \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w|^m \, dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, we infer from (14.50) and (14.51) that, for all $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \hat{c}_p(1 - s)\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u - v, B_R) \\
 &\leq \varepsilon - c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} |1 + w|^{m-1} (u - w) \, dx + \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w|^{m-1} \, dx \\
 &\quad - (1 - s)p \int_{B_R \cap \{u > w\}} (u(x) - v(x))(-\Delta)_p^s w(x) \, dx - c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} (u - w)^k \, dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Making use of this inequality, (14.48) and (13.29), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \hat{c}_p(1 - s)\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u - v, B_R) \\
 &\leq \varepsilon - c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} |1 + w|^{m-1} (u - w) \, dx + \Lambda \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w|^{m-1} \, dx \\
 &\quad + c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} (u(x) - v(x)) |1 + w|^{m-1} \, dx \\
 &\quad \quad + c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} (u(x) - v(x)) |1 + w|^{m-1} \, dx \\
 &\quad - c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} (u - w)^k \, dx \\
 &\leq \varepsilon + (2c_1 + \Lambda) \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w|^{m-1} \, dx - c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} (u - w)^k \, dx \\
 &= \varepsilon + (2c_1 + \Lambda) \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \max\{\theta_*, w\}\}} |1 + w|^{m-1} \, dx - A_k(R).
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, thanks to (13.31),

$$\hat{c}_p(1 - s)\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u - v, B_R) \leq \varepsilon + C_\mu^{m-1}(2c_1 + \Lambda) \int_{B_R \cap \{u > \theta_*\}} (R - |x| + 1)^{-sp} \, dx - A_k(R).$$

This concludes the proof of claim (14.49).

From (14.49) and the coarea formula, we infer that, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{A_k(R)}{\hat{c}_p} + (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) \\
 (14.52) \quad & \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{\hat{c}_p} + C_\mu^{m-1} \frac{2c_1 + \Lambda}{\hat{c}_p} \int_0^R (R - |x| + 1)^{-sp} \int_{\partial B_t} \chi_{\{u > \theta_*\}}(x) dH_x^{n-1} dt \\
 & = \frac{\varepsilon}{\hat{c}_p} + C_\mu^{m-1} \frac{2c_1 + \Lambda}{\hat{c}_p} \int_0^R (R - |x| + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, from (13.27) and (14.12),

$$(14.53) \quad K_0 \geq \left[2^{\frac{p}{m-1}+1} \right]^{\frac{m-1}{ps}} - 1 \geq 2^{\frac{1}{s}} - 1 \geq 1.$$

We now claim that, for every $R \in (K_0, +\infty)$ and $K \in (K_0, R)$,

$$(14.54) \quad A_k(R) \geq c_2 |b_R^*| - c_3 \int_0^R (R + 1 - t)^{-ps} V'(t) dt,$$

and, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$,

$$(14.55) \quad 2\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) \geq \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{8} \right)^{\bar{p}} L(a_R^*, d_R^*).$$

We observe that if claims (14.54) and (14.55) hold true, then from (14.54), (14.55), (14.52) and (14.34) it follows that, for every $R \in (K_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$ and $K \in (K_0, R)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{(1-s)}{2} \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{8} \right)^{\bar{p}} L(a_R^*, d_R^*) + \frac{c_2}{\hat{c}_p} |b_R^*| - \frac{c_3}{\hat{c}_p} \int_0^R (R + 1 - t)^{-sp} V'(t) dt \\
 & \leq (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) + \frac{A_k(R)}{\hat{c}_p} \\
 & \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{\hat{c}_p} + C_\mu^{m-1} \frac{2c_1 + \Lambda}{\hat{c}_p} \int_0^R (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt,
 \end{aligned}$$

which shows (14.47). Hence, in order to conclude the proof of Lemma 14.13 it is only left to show claims (14.54) and (14.55).

To prove (14.54) we first observe that

$$b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\} \subset B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.56) \quad A_k(R) &= c_1 \int_{B_R \cap \{w < u \leq \theta_*\}} (u - w)^k dx \geq c_1 \int_{b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}} (u - w)^k dx \\
 &\geq c_1 \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{8}\right)^k |b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}|.
 \end{aligned}$$

In addition, we notice that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.57) \quad V(R) - V(R - K) &= \int_{R-K}^R V'(t) dt \\
 &\leq (1 + K)^{ps} \int_{R-K}^R (R + 1 - t)^{-ps} V'(t) dt \\
 &\leq (1 + K)^{ps} \int_0^R (R + 1 - t)^{-ps} V'(t) dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, from (14.35) we evince that

$$(14.58) \quad b_R \cap B_{R-K} \subset B_{R-K} \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}.$$

From (14.57) and (14.58) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.59) \quad |b_R| &= |b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}| + |b_R \cap \{u > \theta_*\}| \\
 &= |b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}| + |(b_R \setminus B_{R-K}) \cap \{u > \theta_*\}| \\
 &\leq |b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}| + |(B_R \setminus B_{R-K}) \cap \{u > \theta_*\}| \\
 &= |b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}| + V(R) - V(R - K) \\
 &\leq |b_R \cap \{u \leq \theta_*\}| + (1 + K)^{ps} \int_0^R (R + 1 - t)^{-ps} V'(t) dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, from (14.56) and (14.59) we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.60) \quad A_k(R) &\geq c_1 \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{8}\right)^k \left(|b_R| - (1 + K)^{ps} \int_0^R (R + 1 - t)^{-ps} V'(t) dt \right) \\
 &= c_2 |b_R| - c_3 \int_0^R (R + 1 - t)^{-ps} V'(t) dt \\
 &= c_2 |b_R^*| - c_3 \int_0^R (R + 1 - t)^{-ps} V'(t) dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of claim (14.54).

It is only left to prove (14.55). To show this, we observe that if $x \in a_R^*$ and $y \in d_R^*$

$$\begin{aligned}
 |(u-v)^*(x) - (u-v)^*(y)| &\geq (u-v)^*(x) - (u-v)^*(y) \\
 (14.61) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\geq \frac{1+\theta_*}{4} - \frac{1+\theta_*}{8} \\
 &= \frac{1+\theta_*}{8}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, making use of Theorem 9.2 in [AL89] and (14.61) here, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 2\mathcal{K}_s^{\bar{p}}(u-v, B_R) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|(u-v)(x) - (u-v)(y)|^{\bar{p}}}{|x-y|^{n+\bar{s}\bar{p}}} dy dx \\
 &\geq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|(u-v)^*(x) - (u-v)^*(y)|^{\bar{p}}}{|x-y|^{n+\bar{s}\bar{p}}} dy dx \\
 &\geq \left(\frac{1+\theta_*}{8}\right)^{\bar{p}} \int_{a_R^*} \int_{d_R^*} \frac{dy dx}{|x-y|^{n+s\bar{p}}} \\
 &= \left(\frac{1+\theta_*}{8}\right)^{\bar{p}} L(a_R^*, d_R^*).
 \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (14.55). \square

Proof of Theorem 14.4 & 14.5

In this section we prove Theorems 14.4 and 14.5.

The first step is to suitably estimate from below the left-hand side of (14.47). To do so, we need two different approaches for Theorems 14.4 and 14.5, due to the presence of the multiplicative term $(1-s)$ in front of $L(a_R^*, d_R^*)$.

Indeed, when we show Theorem 14.4, we can treat $(1-s)$ as any constant, being the aim of the result to show density estimates at any fixed $s \in (0, 1)$.

However, in Theorem 14.5, we want to obtain density estimates whose structural constants do not depend on $s \in [s_0, 1)$ where $s_0 \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right)$. To achieve this, when estimating the left-hand side of (14.47), we need to consider the fact that $(1-s)$ vanishes as $s \rightarrow 1$. As a consequence of this, it is not possible to utilize the same result that we use to prove Theorem 14.4 also to obtain a lower bound for the left-hand side of (14.47).

We begin by proving Theorem 14.4. The result employed to estimate the left-hand side of (14.47) is the following:

Proposition 14.14. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $r_1, r_2 \in [0, +\infty)$ such that $|B_{r_2}| \geq \kappa$ for some $\kappa \in (0, +\infty)$. Also, let*

$$(14.62) \quad l(B_{r_2}) := \begin{cases} |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{1-sp}{n}} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ |\ln(|B_{r_2}|)| & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ 1 & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

Then, there exists $\hat{c} := \hat{c}_{\kappa, n, p} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(14.63) \quad L(B_{r_2}, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r_2+r_1}) + |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| \geq \hat{c} |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} l(B_{r_2}).$$

Proposition 14.14 is a direct consequence of the following result:

Theorem 14.15. *Let $s \in (0, 1)$, $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $\delta := \min\{2^{-n}, 2^{-n+2-p}\}$, $R \in (0, +\infty)$ and $r \in (0, \delta R)$. Then,*

$$(14.64) \quad L(B_R, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+r}) \geq \begin{cases} \delta R^{n-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \delta R^{n-1} \log\left(\frac{R}{r}\right) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \delta R^{n-sp} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

The proof of Theorem 14.15 can be found in Appendix 14.6.

We observe that a lower bound in the spirit of Theorem 14.15 was also established, with different (and more complicated) methods, in Theorem 1.6 of [SV14] for $L(A, D)$, where $A, D \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are two generic measurable sets satisfying $A \cap D = \emptyset$ and not necessarily a ball B_R and the complement of a ball $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+r}$. Although it is possible to prove such a general result also for $p \neq 2$, for the purpose of this chapter this further generality is not necessary: we can thereby restrict our attention to balls and complement of balls, which provides a significant technical simplification, allowing the use of rearrangement techniques. Indeed, using the continuity of the Gagliardo seminorm with respect to the symmetric decreasing rearrangement in the proof of Lemma 14.13, we managed to obtain in the left-hand side of (14.47) the function L computed on the level sets a_R^* and d_R^* of the symmetric decreasing rearrangement $(u - v)^*$.

Proof of Proposition 14.14. We begin by setting

$$\delta := \min \{2^{-n}, 2^{-n+2-p}\}$$

and we study separately the case $r_1 \in (0, \delta r_2)$ and $r_1 \in [r_2 \delta, +\infty)$.

(i) **Case** $r_1 \in [\delta r_2, +\infty)$. In this case, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned} |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| &= \omega_n ((r_2 + r_1)^n - r_2^n) \\ &= \omega_n r_2^n \left(\left(1 + \frac{r_1}{r_2}\right)^n - 1 \right) \\ (14.65) \quad &\geq \omega_n r_2^n ((1 + \delta)^n - 1) \\ &= |B_{r_2}| ((1 + \delta)^n - 1) \\ &= c_\delta |B_{r_2}|, \end{aligned}$$

where $c_\delta := (1 + \delta)^n - 1$.

Thus, we consider the map $\Psi : [\kappa, +\infty) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ defined by

$$\Psi(t) := \frac{t^{\frac{1}{n}}}{1 + |\ln(t)|}.$$

Also, we notice that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \Psi(t) = +\infty$$

and therefore

$$(14.66) \quad i_\kappa := \inf_{t \in [\kappa, +\infty)} \psi(t) \in (0, +\infty).$$

Then, if we set

$$c_2 := c_\delta \min \left\{ \kappa^{\frac{1}{n}}, 1, i_\kappa \right\},$$

making use (14.66) and (14.65) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} &L(B_{r_2}, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r_2+r_1}) + |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| \\ &\geq |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| \\ &\geq c_\delta |B_{r_2}| \\ &= \begin{cases} c_\delta |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{sp}{n}} |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \geq c_\delta \kappa^{\frac{sp}{n}} |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ c_\delta |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{1}{n}} |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \geq c_\delta i_\kappa (1 + |\ln(|B_{r_2}|)|) |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} & \text{if } s \in \left[\frac{1}{p}, 1\right) \end{cases} \\ &\geq c_2 |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} l(B_{r_2}). \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (14.63) for the case $r_1 \in [r_2\delta, +\infty)$.

(ii) **Case** $r_1 \in [0, \delta r_2)$. For $s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right)$ we define $z : (0, +\infty) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ as

$$z(t) := t^{1-sp} + t.$$

Then, we observe that $t_0 := (sp - 1)^{\frac{1}{sp}}$ is a global minimizer for z , and henceforth

$$(14.67) \quad \inf_{t \in (0, +\infty)} z(t) = z(t_0) = sp(sp - 1)^{\frac{1-sp}{sp}}.$$

Similarly, if $\alpha \in (0, +\infty)$ we introduce the map $g : (0, \alpha] \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ given by

$$g(t) := \ln\left(\frac{\alpha}{t}\right) + t.$$

Then, we have that $t_\alpha := \min\{1, \alpha\}$ is a global minimizer for g , and consequently

$$(14.68) \quad \inf_{t \in (0, \alpha]} g(t) = g(t_1) = \begin{cases} \ln(\alpha) + 1 & \text{if } \alpha \in (1, +\infty) \\ \alpha & \text{if } \alpha \in (0, 1]. \end{cases}$$

Notice that

$$(14.69) \quad \begin{aligned} |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| &= \omega_n ((r_2 + r_1)^n - r_2^n) \\ &= \omega_n \left(\sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} r_1^j r_2^{n-j} - r_2^n \right) \\ &\geq n\omega_n r_1 r_2^{n-1} \\ &= |\partial B_1| r_1 r_2^{n-1} \\ &\geq r_1 r_2^{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we use (14.64), (14.67), (14.68), (14.69) and the fact that $|B_{r_2}| \geq \kappa$ to obtain

(14.70)

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\delta} L(B_{r_2}, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r_2+r_1}) + |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| \\ & \geq \begin{cases} r_2^{n-sp} + |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ r_2^{n-1} \log\left(\frac{r_2}{r_1}\right) + |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ r_2^{n-1} r_1^{1-sp} + |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right) \end{cases} \\ & \geq \begin{cases} r_2^{n-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ r_2^{n-1} \left(\ln\left(\frac{r_2}{r_1}\right) + r_1\right) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ r_2^{n-1} (r_1^{1-sp} + r_1) & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right) \end{cases} \\ & \geq \begin{cases} r_2^{n-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ r_2^{n-1} g(t_{r_2}) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ r_2^{n-1} sp(sp-1)^{\frac{1-sp}{sp}} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

In particular, there exists a constant $c_{n,\kappa,p} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$\frac{1}{\delta} L(B_{r_2}, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r_2+r_1}) + |B_{r_2+r_1} \setminus B_{r_2}| \geq c_{n,\kappa,p} |B_{r_2}|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} l(B_{r_2}).$$

This concludes the proof of (14.63) for the case $r_1 \in (0, \delta r_2)$. \square

Now, thanks to Lemma 14.13 and Proposition 14.14, we are ready to prove Theorem 14.4.

Proof of Theorem 14.4. First, according to Remark 14.11, we can assume without loss of generality that

$$c_0 \in (1, +\infty).$$

We introduce the constant

$$(14.71) \quad c_4 := \min \left\{ \frac{c_2}{\hat{c}_p}, (1-s)\bar{c}_4 \right\},$$

where c_2 and \bar{c}_4 are provided in (14.44).

We notice that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ satisfies all the hypothesis of Lemma 14.13. Therefore, thanks to (14.47), for every $R \in (K_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$ and $K \in (K_0, R)$

$$(14.72) \quad L(a_R^*, d_R^*) + |b_R^*| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{c_4 \hat{c}_p} + \frac{c_5}{c_4} \int_0^R (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt.$$

Moreover, we notice that $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ satisfies all the assumptions of Proposition 14.12. Hence, from (14.41) and (14.42) we deduce that all the conditions in order to apply Proposition 14.14 are met with the choice $\kappa = c_0$.

Accordingly, making use of (14.63) in Proposition 14.14 we obtain that

$$L(a_R^*, d_R^*) + |b_R^*| \geq \hat{c} |a_R^*|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} l(a_R^*),$$

where l is provided in (14.62) and $\hat{c} := \hat{c}_{c_0, n, p} \in (0, +\infty)$.

From this inequality, (14.39) and (14.45), we obtain that for all $R \in (K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ and $K \in (K_0, R - r_0)$,

$$(14.73) \quad \begin{aligned} L(a_R^*, d_R^*) + |b_R^*| &\geq \hat{c} |a_R^*|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} l(a_R^*) \\ &\geq \hat{c} |B_{R-K} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}| l(B_{R-K} \cap \{u > \theta_*\}) \\ &= \hat{c} V(R - K)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} l_{R-K}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$l_R := l(B_R \cap \{u > \theta_*\}).$$

Note also that

$$(14.74) \quad \text{the map } R \mapsto l_R \text{ is non decreasing.}$$

Now, from equation (14.73) and (14.72) we deduce that, for all $R \in (K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$ and $K \in (K_0, R - r_0)$,

$$(14.75) \quad V(R - K)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} l_{R-K} \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{c_4 \hat{c}_p} + \frac{c_5}{c_4 \hat{c}} \int_0^R (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt.$$

Also, if $\rho \geq 1$ then

$$(14.76) \quad \int_t^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} (R + 1 - t)^{-sp} dR \leq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1 - sp} \left(\frac{5}{2}\rho\right)^{1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \log\left(\frac{5}{2}\rho\right) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{1}{sp - 1} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

Moreover, integrating both sides of (14.75) in $R \in [\rho, \frac{3}{2}\rho]$, with $\rho \in (K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$, $B_{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \subset \Omega$ and $K \in (K_0, \min\{\rho - r_0, \frac{\rho}{2}\})$, we infer that

$$(14.77) \quad \int_{\rho}^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} l_{R-K} V(R-K)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} dR \leq \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\varepsilon}{c_4 \hat{c} \hat{c}_p} + \frac{c_5}{c_4 \hat{c}} \int_{\rho}^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \int_0^R (R-t+1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt dR \\ \leq \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\varepsilon}{c_4 \hat{c} \hat{c}_p} + \frac{c_5}{c_4 \hat{c}} \int_0^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \int_t^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} (R-t+1)^{-sp} V'(t) dR dt.$$

Thus, making use of (14.76), (14.74) and (14.77), we obtain that, for all $\rho \in (K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \subset \Omega$ and all $K \in (K_0, \min\{\rho - r_0, \frac{\rho}{2}\})$,

$$(14.78) \quad \rho l_{\rho-K} V(\rho-K)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \leq \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\varepsilon}{c_4 \hat{c} \hat{c}_p} + \frac{c_5}{c_4 \hat{c}} \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1-sp} \left(\frac{5}{2}\rho\right)^{1-sp} V\left(\frac{3}{2}\rho\right) & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \log\left(\frac{5}{2}\rho\right) V\left(\frac{3}{2}\rho\right) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{1}{sp-1} V\left(\frac{3}{2}\rho\right) & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

Now, we introduce the constants

$$C_{s,p}^{(1)} := \frac{5c_5}{c_4 \hat{c} (1-sp)}, \quad C_{s,p}^{(2)} := \frac{2c_5}{c_4 \hat{c}}, \quad C_{s,p}^{(3)} := \frac{c_5}{(sp-1)c_4 \hat{c}} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{s,p}^{(4)} := \frac{1}{c_4 \hat{c} \hat{c}_p}.$$

Then, if we denote $r := \frac{\rho}{2}$ and we assume that $r \geq 5$, we notice that $\rho - K \geq r$ and therefore, owing to (14.78),

$$\begin{cases} 2r^{sp} V(r)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \leq r^{sp} \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)} + C_{s,p}^{(1)} V(3r) & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ 2r \frac{\log(V(r))}{\log(r)} V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \leq \frac{r}{\log(r)} \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)} + C_{s,p}^{(2)} V(3r) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ 2r V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \leq r \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)} + C_{s,p}^{(3)} V(3r) & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

We can rewrite these inequalities as

$$(14.79) \quad \begin{cases} r^{sp} \left(2V(r)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} - \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)}\right) \leq C_{s,p}^{(1)} V(3r) & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \frac{r}{\log(r)} \left(2 \log(V(r)) V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)}\right) \leq C_{s,p}^{(2)} V(3r) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ r \left(2V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)}\right) \leq C_{s,p}^{(3)} V(3r) & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

We also observe that, for every $r \in (r_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_r \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.80) \quad \begin{cases} \text{if } \varepsilon \leq \frac{c_0^{\frac{n-sp}{n}}}{C_{s,p}^{(4)}} & \text{then } 2V(r)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} - \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)} \geq V(r)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \\ \text{if } \varepsilon \leq \frac{\log(c_0)c_0^{\frac{n-1}{n}}}{C_{s,p}^{(4)}} & \text{then } 2\log(V(r))V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)} \geq \log(V(r))V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \\ \text{if } \varepsilon \leq \frac{c_0^{\frac{n-1}{n}}}{C_{s,p}^{(4)}} & \text{then } 2V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - \varepsilon C_{s,p}^{(4)} \geq \log(V(r))V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}. \end{cases}$$

We set

$$\delta := \min \left\{ \frac{c_0^{\frac{n-sp}{n}}}{C_{s,p}^{(4)}}, \frac{\log(c_0)c_0^{\frac{n-1}{n}}}{C_{s,p}^{(4)}}, \frac{c_0^{\frac{n-1}{n}}}{C_{s,p}^{(4)}} \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad R_0 := \max \left\{ r_0, 5, \frac{K_0 + r_0}{2} \right\}.$$

In this way, we deduce from (14.79) and (14.80) that, for every $\varepsilon \in (0, \delta)$ and every $r \in [R_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{3r} \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{cases} r^{sp}V(r)^{\frac{n-sp}{n}} \leq C_{s,p}^{(1)}V(3r) & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ r \frac{\log(V(r))}{\log(r)} V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \leq C_{s,p}^{(2)}V(3r) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ rV(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \leq C_{s,p}^{(3)}V(3r) & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

From now on K is fixed once and for all. Thanks to this and (14.13) we notice that (13.24) and (13.24) in Lemma 13.8 hold true with the following choices:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma = sp, \nu = n, C = C_{s,p}^{(1)}, \gamma = 3, \mu = c_0 & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \sigma = 1, \nu = n, C = C_{s,p}^{(2)}, \gamma = 3, \mu = c_0 & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \sigma = 1, \nu = n, C = C_{s,p}^{(3)}, \gamma = 3, \mu = c_0 & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

Therefore, in virtue of (13.26) in Lemma 13.8, we obtain that, for every $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{3r} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.81) \quad V(r) \geq \tilde{c}r^n,$$

for a suitable $\tilde{c} \in (0, 1)$, depending only on $C, \sigma, \mu, \gamma, \nu$ and R_0 , and a suitable $R^* \in [R_0, +\infty)$, depending only on R_0 and γ .

In particular, from (14.81) we deduce that, when $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ and $B_{3r} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.82) \quad \tilde{c}r^n \leq \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_*\}) = \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta^*\}) + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}).$$

We also set $c_{m,\theta_*} := (1 + \theta_*)^{-m}$ and observe that

$$(14.83) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}) &= \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} dx \\ &\leq c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we deduce from (14.82) and (14.83) that, for every $r \geq R_*$ such that $B_{3r} \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta^*\}) &\geq \tilde{c}r^n - \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}) \\ &\geq \tilde{c}r^n - c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Now we prove Theorem 14.5. As aforementioned, in this case, to estimate the left-hand side of (14.47), it is not possible to use Proposition 14.14. Hence, to obtain a suitable lower bound for the left-hand side of (14.47), we make use of the additional Hölder regularity assumption on the ε -minimizer $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$.

Proof of Theorem 14.5. First, we notice that, according to Remark 14.11, we can assume without loss of generality that

$$c_0 \in (1, +\infty).$$

Also, it follows from (14.42) that, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$,

$$(14.84) \quad |b_R^*| \geq n\omega_n r_2^{n-1} r_1.$$

Then, we claim that there exists a constant $\tilde{C} := \tilde{C}_{\alpha, s_0, n, m, p, c_1, [u]_{B, \alpha}} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, when $R \in [K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ and $B_{R+2} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.85) \quad r_1 > \tilde{C},$$

where $[u]_{B, \alpha}$ has been defined in (14.10).

To show (14.85), we begin by setting the following notation. For every function $f \in C_c(\mathbb{R}^n)$ we denote by ω_f its modulus of continuity, namely, for every $\delta > 0$,

$$\omega_f(\delta) := \sup \{|f(x) - f(y)| \text{ s.t. } |x - y| < \delta\}.$$

It is well known, see for instance Corollary 6.1 in [BS00], that for every $\delta > 0$ and $f \in C_c(\mathbb{R}^n)$,

$$f^* \in C_c(\mathbb{R}^n) \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_{f^*}(\delta) \leq \omega_f(\delta).$$

Since $u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$, it follows from Proposition 14.19 that $u - v \in C_c^\alpha(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and therefore

$$(14.86) \quad (u - v)^* \in C_c^\alpha(\mathbb{R}^n) \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_{(u-v)^*}(\delta) \leq \omega_{u-v}(\delta).$$

From this, (14.41) and the Mean Value Theorem, we obtain that for every $R \in (K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ there exists $x_0 \in b_R^*$ such that

$$(14.87) \quad (u - v)^*(x_0) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{4} + \frac{1 + \theta_*}{8} \right) = \frac{3}{16} (1 + \theta_*).$$

Now, for every $t \in (0, +\infty)$ we define the annulus

$$\mathcal{C}_{x_0}^t := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ s.t. } ||x| - |x_0|| \leq t\}$$

Then, we claim that there exists $d := d_{\alpha, s_0, n, m, p, c_1, [u]_{B, \alpha}} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(14.88) \quad \mathcal{C}_{x_0}^d \subset b_R^*.$$

In particular, if claim (14.88) holds true, then

$$r_1 \geq 2d,$$

proving (14.85).

For this reason, it only remains to check the validity of (14.88). To do so, we notice that, according to (14.173), there exists $C^{(0)} := C_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1}^{(0)} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $\delta \in (0, 2)$,

$$(14.89) \quad \omega_{u-v}(\delta) \leq \left[2C^{(0)} + 4[u]_{B, \alpha} \right] \delta^\alpha.$$

We also denote

$$C^{(1)} := 2C^{(0)} + 4[u]_{B,\alpha}.$$

Moreover, by construction, the function $(u - v)^*$ is rotationally symmetric. In particular, for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(u - v)^*(x) = (u - v)^*\left(|x| \frac{x_0}{|x_0|}\right).$$

Hence, keeping in mind (14.86) and (14.89), we obtain that, for every $\delta \in (0, 2)$ and $x \in \mathcal{C}_{x_0}^\delta$,

$$\begin{aligned} |(u - v)^*(x) - (u - v)^*(x_0)| &= \left| (u - v)^*\left(|x| \frac{x_0}{|x_0|}\right) - (u - v)^*(x_0) \right| \\ (14.90) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\leq \omega_{(u-v)^*}(\delta) \\ &\leq \omega_{(u-v)}(\delta) \\ &\leq C^{(1)}\delta^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if we define

$$d := \left(\frac{1 + \theta_*}{16 C^{(1)}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}},$$

making use of (14.87) and (14.90) we evince that, for every $R \in [K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{R+2} \subset \Omega$,

$$\mathcal{C}_{x_0}^d \subset b_R^*,$$

proving claim (14.88) and thus (14.85).

Now, thanks to (14.45), (14.39), (14.84), (14.42) and (14.85) we evince that, for every $R \in [K_0 + r_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{R+2} \subset \Omega$ and for every $K \in (K_0, R - r_0)$,

$$(14.91) \qquad |b_R^*| \geq n\omega_n 2dr_2^{n-1} = n\omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d |a_R^*|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} = n\omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d |a_R|^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \geq n\omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2dV(R - K)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}.$$

Also, according to (14.47), for every $R \in (K_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_R \subset \Omega$ and for every $K \in (K_0, R)$,

$$(14.92) \qquad |b_R^*| \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{c_2} + C^{(2)} \int_0^R (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt,$$

where we have defined

$$(14.93) \quad C^{(2)} := \frac{c_3 + C_\mu^{m-1}(2c_1 + \Lambda)}{c_2}.$$

We recall that the constants c_2 and c_3 are defined in (14.44). Note also that c_3 depends on K .

Now, from (13.27), (13.29) and (14.33), it is immediate to verify that

$$(14.94) \quad \bar{R}_{s_0} := \sup_{s \in [s_0, 1)} \bar{R}_\mu \in (0, +\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad C_{s_0} := \sup_{s \in [s_0, 1)} C_\mu \in (0, +\infty).$$

Then, recalling (14.53), we define the constant

$$K_{s_0} := \left[C_{s_0} \left(\frac{2}{1 + \theta_*} \right) \right]^{\frac{m-1}{ps_0}} - 1.$$

Moreover, making use of (14.93) for every $K \in (K_{s_0}, R - r_0)$ we set

$$C^{(3)} := \frac{C_{s_0}^{m-1}(2c_1 + \Lambda) + c_3}{c_2}.$$

Finally, in light of (14.91), (14.92) and (14.94), we deduce that, when $R \in (K_{s_0} + r_0, +\infty)$, $B_{R+4} \subset \Omega$ and $K \in (K_{s_0}, R - r_0)$,

$$V(R - K)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{c_2 n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} + \frac{C^{(3)}}{n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} \int_0^R (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt.$$

Now, we integrate both sides of this inequality in $R \in [\rho, \frac{3}{2}\rho]$, with $\rho \in (K_{s_0} + r_0, +\infty)$, $B_{\frac{3}{2}\rho+4}$ and $K \in (K_{s_0}, \min\{\rho - r_0, \frac{\rho}{2}\})$ and conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_\rho^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} V(R - K)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} dR &\leq \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\varepsilon}{c_2 n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} + \frac{C^{(3)}}{n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} \int_\rho^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \int_0^R (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dt dR \\ &\leq \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\varepsilon}{c_2 n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} + \frac{C^{(3)}}{n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} \int_0^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} \int_t^{\frac{3}{2}\rho} (R - t + 1)^{-sp} V'(t) dR dt. \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, recalling (14.76),

$$(14.95) \quad \begin{aligned} \rho V(\rho - K) &\leq \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\varepsilon}{c_2 n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} + \frac{C^{(3)}}{n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d(sp - 1)} V\left(\frac{3}{2}\rho\right) \\ &\leq \frac{\rho}{2} \frac{\varepsilon}{c_2 n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d} + \frac{C^{(3)}}{n \omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d(s_0 p - 1)} V\left(\frac{3}{2}\rho\right). \end{aligned}$$

Now, we introduce the constants

$$(14.96) \quad C^{(4)} := \frac{C^{(3)}}{n\omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d(s_0p - 1)} \quad \text{and} \quad C^{(5)} := \frac{1}{c_2 n\omega_n^{\frac{1}{n}} 2d}.$$

Then, if $r := \frac{\rho}{2}$, we assume that $r \in [5, +\infty)$ and we notice that $\rho - K \geq r$. It thereby follows from (14.95) and (14.96) that

$$(14.97) \quad r \left(2V(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - \varepsilon C^{(5)} \right) \leq C^{(4)} V(3r).$$

In particular, if we choose

$$\delta := \frac{c_0^{\frac{n-1}{n}}}{C^{(5)}} \quad \text{and} \quad R_0 := \max \left\{ r_0, 5, \frac{K_{s_0} + r_0}{2} \right\}$$

we deduce from (14.13) and (14.97) that, for every $\varepsilon \in (0, \delta)$ and $r \in [R_0, +\infty)$ such that $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$rV(r)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \leq C^{(4)} V(3r).$$

From now on K is fixed once and for all. Thanks to the above inequality and (14.13) we find that (13.24) and (13.25) in Lemma 13.8 hold true with the following choices:

$$\sigma = 1, \quad \nu = n, \quad C = C^{(0)}, \quad \gamma = 3 \quad \text{and} \quad \mu = c_0.$$

Therefore, in virtue of (13.26) in Lemma 13.8, we obtain that, for every $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ such that $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.98) \quad V(r) \geq \tilde{c}r^n,$$

for a suitable $\tilde{c} \in (0, 1)$, depending only on $C, \sigma, \mu, \gamma, \nu$ and R_0 , and a suitable $R^* \in [R_0, +\infty)$, depending only on R_0 and γ .

In particular, for all $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ such that $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.99) \quad \tilde{c}r^n \leq \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_*\}) = \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta^*\}) + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}).$$

Now we set $c_{m,\theta_*} := (1 + \theta_*)^{-m}$ and we see that

$$(14.100) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}) &= \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} dx \\ &\leq c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, from (14.99) and (14.100) we deduce that, for every $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ such that $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta^*\}) &\geq \tilde{c}r^n - \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}) \\ &\geq \tilde{c}r^n - c_{m,\theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Proof of Corollaries 14.6 & 14.8

In this section we prove Corollary 14.6 and 14.8. We begin with Corollary 14.6.

Proof of Corollary 14.6. Since $u \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ is a minimizer of \mathcal{E}_s^p we can apply Theorem 13.9 and obtain that $u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$, where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ depends only on n, p and s_0 .

Furthermore, there exists a constant $C_{s_0,n,p}$ such that, for every $x_0 \in B_R$,

$$(14.101) \quad [u]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \leq C_{s_0,n,p} \left(\|u\|_{L^\infty(B_4(x_0))} + \text{Tail}(u, x_0, 4) + \|W\|_{L^\infty(B_8(x_0))}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right).$$

Using the fact that $\|u\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq 1$ we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tail}(u, x_0, 2) &\leq \left[(1-s)2^{sp} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_2(x_0)} \frac{dy}{|y-x_0|^{n+sp}} \right]^{\frac{1}{p-1}} \\ &= \left[\frac{(1-s)}{sp} \omega_{n-1} \right]^{\frac{1}{p-1}} \\ &\leq \tilde{C}_{s_0,n,p}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, it follows from (14.6) and (14.101) that

$$[u]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \leq C_{s_0,n,p} \left(1 + \tilde{C}_{s_0,n,p} + 2^{\frac{m}{p}} \Lambda^{\frac{1}{p}} \right) \leq C_{n,s_0,p,m,\Lambda}.$$

In particular, bearing in mind (14.10), we have that

$$[u]_{B,\alpha} \leq C_{n,s_0,p,m,\Lambda}.$$

Thanks to this last estimate and Theorem 14.5 we conclude. □

Now we prove Corollary 14.8.

Proof of Corollary 14.8. For simplicity of notation, for every $r \in [2, +\infty)$ we denote

$$(14.102) \quad F(r) := \frac{\bar{C}}{s} \begin{cases} \frac{r^{n-sp}}{1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ r^{n-1} \log(r) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{r^{n-1}}{sp-1} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right), \end{cases}$$

where $\bar{C} := \bar{C}_{n,p,m,\Lambda} \in (0, +\infty)$ is the constant introduced in (14.17).

Thanks to (14.18) and (14.17) we have that, for every $r \in [2, +\infty)$ such that $B_{r+2} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.103) \quad \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx \leq \lambda_{\theta_*}^{-1} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} W(u(x)) dx \leq \lambda_{\theta_*}^{-1} \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, B_r) \leq \lambda_{\theta_*}^{-1} F(r).$$

Also, for every $r \geq 2$,

$$(14.104) \quad 4r \geq r + 2.$$

Thus, applying Theorem 14.4 to u with $\varepsilon = 0$ and making use of (14.103) and (14.104), we obtain that there exist $R^* := R_{s,n,m,p,c_1,\theta_*,r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$ and $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s,n,m,p,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ such that, for every $r \geq \max\{2, R^*\}$ satisfying $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{c}r^n &\leq c \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) \\ &\leq \lambda_{\theta_*}^{-1} cF(r) + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}). \end{aligned}$$

From this and equation (14.102), the claim in (14.19) readily follows.

Now, if $n \geq 2$, $s_0 \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right)$ and $s \in [s_0, 1)$ we can apply Corollary 14.6 to u . Therefore, making use of (14.16), (14.102), (14.103) and (14.104), we deduce that there exist $R^* := R_{s_0,n,m,p,c_1,\theta_*,r_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$, $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s_0,n,p,m,\Lambda,c_1,\theta_*,r_0,c_0} \in (0, 1)$ and $c := c_{m,\theta_*} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $r \geq \max\{2, R^*\}$ satisfying $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{c}r^n &\leq c \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < u \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + u(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}) \\ &\leq \lambda_{\theta_*}^{-1} c \frac{\bar{C}r^{n-1}}{s_0(s_0p-1)} + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{u > \theta_2\}). \end{aligned}$$

From this equation, claim (14.20) plainly follows. □

14.4 Proof of Theorems 14.9 & 14.10

The proof of Theorem 14.9 relies the Γ -convergence of the Gagliardo seminorm, which has already been discussed in [Pon04] and [Cri+23]. In particular, we follow the proof of Theorem 2.1 in [Cri+23], where the Γ -convergence of \mathcal{K}_s^2 is showed for traceless functions. Here minor adjustments are needed due to the different homogeneity $p \in (1, +\infty)$ of the seminorm and the relaxed condition on the trace.

In what follows we will adopt the following notation. For any $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ we define

$$d(x, A) := \inf_{y \in A} |x - y|.$$

Furthermore, for any $\varepsilon \in (0, +\infty)$ we set

(14.105)

$$\Omega_\varepsilon^+ := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ s.t. } d(x, \Omega) \leq \varepsilon\} \quad \text{and} \quad \Omega_\varepsilon^- := \{x \in \Omega \text{ s.t. } d(x, \partial\Omega) \geq \varepsilon\}.$$

Note that Ω_ε^- might be empty for large values of ε . Furthermore, given any measurable $g : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we adopt the following notation for its zero extension in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega$

$$\bar{g}(x) := \begin{cases} g(x) & \text{if } x \in \Omega \\ 0 & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega. \end{cases}$$

Moreover, for every $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ measurable we consider the translation operator defined by

$$\tau_h f(\cdot) := f(\cdot + h).$$

We are now ready for the proof of Theorem 14.9, which will be divided into its specific parts.

Proof of Theorem 14.9(i). We make use of Proposition 14.22 and obtain that, for

every $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

(14.106)

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tau_h u_{s_k} - u_{s_k}\|_{L^p(\Omega_{|h|}^-)}^p &= \int_{\Omega_{|h|}^-} |u_{s_k}(h+y) - u_{s_k}(y)|^p dy \\ &\leq \bar{C}_{n,p} |h|^{s_k p} (1-s_k) \int_{B_{|h|}} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u_{s_k}(x+y) - u_{s_k}(x)|^p}{|y|^{n+s_k p}} dx dy \\ &\leq \bar{C}_{n,p} |h|^{s_k p} (1-s_k) \int_{\Omega_{|h|}^+} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|u_{s_k}(y) - u_{s_k}(x)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+s_k p}} dx dy \\ &\leq \bar{C}_{n,p} |h|^{s_k p} 2M, \end{aligned}$$

where $\bar{C}_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$ is a constant depending only on n and p .

As a result,

(14.107)

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tau_h \bar{u}_{s_k} - \bar{u}_{s_k}\|_{L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |\bar{u}_{s_k}(h+y) - \bar{u}_{s_k}(y)|^p dy \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega_{|h|}^-} |u_{s_k}(h+y) - u_{s_k}(y)|^p dy + 2^p \int_{\Omega_{|h|}^+ \setminus \Omega_{|h|}^-} \|u_{s_k}\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p dy \\ &\leq \bar{C}_{n,p} |h|^{s_k p} 2M + 2^p |\Omega_{|h|}^+ \setminus \Omega_{|h|}^-|. \end{aligned}$$

Also, we notice that, as a consequence of the Dominated Convergence Theorem,

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} |\Omega_{|h|}^+ \setminus \Omega_{|h|}^-| = 0.$$

Thanks to this and (14.107), we can apply the Fréchet-Kolmogorov to \bar{u}_{s_k} , see for instance Theorem 4.26 in [Bre11], and obtain that there exists $u \in L^p(\Omega)$ such that, up to a subsequence,

(14.108)
$$\lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \|u_{s_k} - u\|_{L^p(\Omega)} = 0.$$

Therefore, taking the limit as $k \rightarrow +\infty$ in (14.106), it follows from (14.108) that, for every $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\|\tau_h u - u\|_{L^p(\Omega_{|h|}^-)} \leq (2M \bar{C}_{n,p})^{\frac{1}{p}} |h|.$$

In particular, employing Proposition 9.3 in [Bre11] we deduce that $Du \in L^p(\Omega)$ and therefore $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

Now we assume that $u_{s_k} \in X_0^{s_k,p}(\Omega)$ for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, $u_{s_k} \equiv \bar{u}_{s_k}$. In particular, we obtain that

$$\mathcal{K}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega) = \frac{1}{2} [u_{s_k}]_{W^{s_k,p}(\Omega)}^p.$$

It follows from this, (14.21) and Proposition 14.22 that, for every open and bounded $\Omega' \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(14.109) \quad \|\tau_h u_{s_k} - u_{s_k}\|_{L^p(\Omega')} \leq (2\bar{C}_{n,p}M)^{\frac{1}{p}} |h|^{s_k}.$$

Consequently, by Theorem 4.26 in [Bre11] it holds that $u_{s_k} \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$, where $u \equiv 0$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega$. By taking the limit as $k \rightarrow +\infty$ in (14.109), we obtain that

$$\|\tau_h u - u\|_{L^p(\Omega')} \leq (2\bar{C}_{n,p}M)^{\frac{1}{p}} |h|.$$

From this and Proposition 9.3 in [Bre11] it follows that $Du \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$. Since $u \equiv 0$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega$ and $\partial\Omega$ is Lipschitz, we find that $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. This concludes the proof of Theorem 14.9(i). □

Proof of Theorem 14.9(ii). Since $W \in L^\infty((-1,1))$, with no loss of generality we can suppose that there exists $M_1 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(14.110) \quad \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (1 - s_k) \mathcal{K}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega) \leq M_1.$$

In particular, up to a subsequence, we can assume that (14.21) holds true. Hence, it follows from Theorem 14.9(i) that $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

Now, let $v \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and $\eta \in C_c^\infty(B_1)$ be a standard mollifier such that

$$\eta \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{B_1} \eta(x) \, dx = 1.$$

Also, for $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ we consider $\eta_\varepsilon(\cdot) := \eta(\frac{\cdot}{\varepsilon})$ and we define the convolution $v_\varepsilon := v * \eta_\varepsilon$.

Then, we make the following claims. For every $s \in (0, 1)$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$,

$$(14.111) \quad \mathcal{K}_s^p(v, \Omega) \geq \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|v_\varepsilon(x) - v_\varepsilon(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \, dy \, dx$$

and

$$(14.112) \quad \frac{|\partial B_1|}{p} \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x)|^p dx \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (1-s_k) \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+s_k p}} dx dy.$$

Suppose for the moment that claims (14.111) and (14.112) hold true. Then, we obtain that

$$(14.113) \quad \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (1 - s_k) \mathcal{K}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega) \geq \frac{|\partial B_1|}{2p} \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}|^p dx.$$

Also, we observe that $u_{s_k, \varepsilon} \rightarrow u_\varepsilon := u * \eta_\varepsilon$ in $L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)$. Now, according to (14.110) and (14.113), we obtain that up to a subsequence $u_{s_k, \varepsilon}$ is uniformly bounded in $W^{1,p}(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)$ with respect to k .

For this reason, again up to a subsequence, we see that

$$(14.114) \quad u_{s_k, \varepsilon} \rightharpoonup u_\varepsilon \quad \text{weakly in } W^{1,p}(\Omega_\varepsilon^-).$$

Hence, we infer from (14.113) and (14.114) that

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{K}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega) \geq \frac{|\partial B_1|}{2p} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} |\nabla u_\varepsilon|^p dx.$$

Since $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$, taking the limit with respect to $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ we obtain that

$$(14.115) \quad \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (1 - s_k) \mathcal{K}_{s_k}^p(u_{s_k}, \Omega) \geq \frac{|\partial B_1|}{2p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u(x)|^p dx = \mathcal{K}_1^p(u, \Omega).$$

We also notice that since $u_{s_k} \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\Omega)$, then, up to a subsequence, $u_{s_k} \rightarrow u$ a.e. in Ω . Since $|u_{s_k}| \leq 1$ a.e. in Ω it follows that $|u| \leq 1$ a.e. in Ω . Besides, making use of Fatou's Lemma and of the lower semicontinuity of W (see equation (14.5)) we obtain that

$$(14.116) \quad \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} W(u_{s_k}(x)) dx \geq \int_{\Omega} \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} W(u_{s_k}(x)) dx \geq \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx.$$

Finally, from (14.115) and (14.116) we obtain (14.22).

Hence, it is only left to show claims (14.111) and (14.112).

To prove (14.111) we argue as follows. Using Jensen inequality we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|v_\varepsilon(x) - v_\varepsilon(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (v(x - z) - v(y - z)) \eta_\varepsilon(z) dz|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|v(x - z) - v(y - z)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \eta_\varepsilon(z) dz dx dy \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\varepsilon} \int_{-z + \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \eta_\varepsilon(z) dx dy dz \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_\varepsilon} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \eta_\varepsilon(z) dx dy dz \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\leq \mathcal{K}_s^p(v, \Omega).
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof of (14.111) is thereby complete and we now turn to the proof of (14.112). For this, let $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $|x - y| < 1$. Using Taylor's Theorem with the Lagrange remainder, we obtain that, for some $\xi \in B_1(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.117) \quad |u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p &= |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y) + D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^p \\
 &\geq \left| |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)| - |D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2| \right|^p.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we distinguish between the cases

$$(14.118) \quad |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)| \leq |D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|$$

and

$$(14.119) \quad |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)| \geq |D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|.$$

When (14.118) holds true, making use of the convexity of $\mathbb{R}^+ \ni t \rightarrow t^p$ and (14.117) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 |u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p &\geq |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^p - |D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^p \\
 &\geq \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p - \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^2(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p |x - y|^{2p}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, since $\|u_{s_k}\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq 1$, we obtain that

$$(14.120) \quad \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^2(\mathbb{R}^n)} \leq \|\eta_\varepsilon\|_{W^{2,1}(\mathbb{R}^n)}.$$

As a result, if $|\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)| \leq |D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|$ we obtain that

$$(14.121) \quad \begin{aligned} |u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p &\geq \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p - \|\eta_\varepsilon\|_{W^{2,1}(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p |x - y|^{2p} \\ &\geq \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p - \|\eta_\varepsilon\|_{W^{2,1}(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p |x - y|^{p+1}, \end{aligned}$$

as desired.

If instead (14.119) holds true, we use equation (14.196) to estimate

$$(14.122) \quad |u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p \geq \sum_{j=0}^{+\infty} \binom{p}{j} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} |-D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j.$$

Consequently,

$$(14.123) \quad \begin{aligned} &\sum_{j=0}^{+\infty} \binom{p}{j} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} |-D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j \\ &\geq \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p \\ &\quad - \sum_{j=1}^{[p]} \binom{p}{j} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} |-D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j \\ &\quad - \sum_{j=[p]+1}^{+\infty} \binom{p}{j} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} |-D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{j=1}^{[p]} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right| |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} |-D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j \\
 & \leq \sum_{j=1}^{[p]} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right| |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^2(\mathbb{R}^n)}^j |x - y|^{2j} \\
 (14.124) \quad & \leq \sum_{j=1}^{[p]} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right| \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^1(\mathbb{R}^n)}^{p-j} \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^2(\mathbb{R}^n)}^j |x - y|^{p+j} \\
 & \leq \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^2(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p |x - y|^{p+1} \sum_{j=1}^{[p]} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{j=[p]+1}^{+\infty} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right| |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} |D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j \\
 (14.125) \quad & \leq \sum_{j=[p]+1}^{+\infty} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right| |D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j \\
 & \leq \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^2(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p |x - y|^{2p} \sum_{j=[p]+1}^{+\infty} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if we set

$$C_p := \max \left\{ \sum_{j=[p]+1}^{+\infty} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right|, \sum_{j=1}^{[p]} \left| \binom{p}{j} \right| \right\} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{p, \varepsilon} := 2C_p \|\eta_\varepsilon\|_{W^{2,1}(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p,$$

making use of (14.120), (14.123), (14.124) and (14.125) we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{j=0}^{+\infty} \binom{p}{j} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot (x - y)|^{p-j} |-D^2 u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(\xi) \cdot (x - y)^2|^j \\
 & \geq \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p - C_p \|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}\|_{C^2(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p (|x - y|^{p+1} + |x - y|^{2p}) \\
 & \geq \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p - 2C_p \|\eta_\varepsilon\|_{W^{2,1}(\mathbb{R}^n)}^p |x - y|^{p+1} \\
 & = \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p - C_{p, \varepsilon} |x - y|^{p+1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, as a consequence of (14.121), (14.122) and the fact that $C_p \geq 1$, we have that, for every $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $|x - y| < 1$,

$$|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p \geq \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^p - C_{p, \varepsilon} |x - y|^{p+1}.$$

Therefore, for every $x \in \Omega_\varepsilon^-$,

$$\begin{aligned} & (1 - s_k) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+s_k p}} dy \\ & \geq (1 - s_k) \int_{B_1(x)} \frac{|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+s_k p}} dy \\ & \geq (1 - s_k) \int_{B_1(x)} \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^{p(1-s_k)-n} dy \\ & \quad - (1 - s_k) C_{p, \varepsilon} \int_{B_1(x)} \frac{dy}{|x - y|^{n+s_k p - p - 1}}. \end{aligned}$$

We notice that, for every $z \in \partial B_1$,

$$\int_{\partial B_1} |z \cdot \omega|^p dH_\omega^{n-1} = |z|^p \int_{\partial B_1} |\omega_1|^p dH_\omega^{n-1} = |z|^p K_{n,p}.$$

We thereby deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_1(x)} \left| \nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \frac{(x - y)}{|x - y|} \right|^p |x - y|^{p(1-s_k)-n} dy \\ & = \int_0^1 \int_{\partial B_1} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) \cdot \omega|^p t^{p(1-s_k)-1} dH_\omega^{n-1} dt \\ & = K_{n,p} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x)|^p \int_0^1 t^{p(1-s_k)-1} dt \\ & = \frac{K_{n,p}}{p(1 - s_k)} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x)|^p. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for every $x \in \Omega_\varepsilon^-$,

$$(1 - s_k) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+s_k p}} dy \geq \frac{K_{n,p}}{p} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x)|^p - (1 - s_k) C_{p, \varepsilon} \frac{|\partial B_1|}{p - s_k p + 1}.$$

We thus integrate both sides of the inequality in $x \in \Omega_\varepsilon^-$ and we take the liminf to obtain

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (1 - s_k) \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x) - u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+s_k p}} dy dx \geq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{K_{n,p}}{p} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} |\nabla u_{s_k, \varepsilon}(x)|^p dx$$

and this concludes the proof of (14.112). □

Proof of Theorem 14.9(iii). We assume with no loss of generality that $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Being Ω Lipschitz, we extend u to a function $\tilde{u} \in W^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^n)$ such that $\tilde{u} = 0$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{\frac{R}{3}}$ where $R \in (0, +\infty)$ is chosen such that $\Omega \subset B_{\frac{R}{3}}$. Then, we define

$$v := \min \{ \max \{ \tilde{u}, -1 \}, 1 \}.$$

Notice that, by Stampacchia's Theorem, $v \in W^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^n)$. Also, $v = 0$ in $B_{\frac{R}{3}}$. Then, v satisfies all the assumptions of Proposition 14.20. Furthermore, we have that $v \in X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ for every $s \in (0, 1)$.

Therefore, we can choose $u_{s_k} \equiv v$ and, thanks to Proposition 14.20, we obtain that

$$(14.126) \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (1 - s_k) \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+s_k p}} dy dx = \frac{K_{n,p}}{p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v(x)|^p dx.$$

Furthermore, since $u_{s_k} \equiv u$ in Ω for every k , we obtain

$$(14.127) \quad \int_{\Omega} W(u_{s_k}(x)) dx = \int_{\Omega} W(u(x)) dx.$$

From (14.126) and (14.127) we conclude the proof of Theorem 14.9(iii). □

As a consequence of the density estimates in Theorem 14.4 and the Γ -convergence of the functional \mathcal{E}_s^p to the free energy \mathcal{E}_1^p , we obtain density estimates for \mathcal{E}_1^p as precisely stated in Theorem 14.10.

Proof of Theorem 14.10. According to Theorem 14.9(iii), there exists an extension $v : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ belonging to $X^{s,p}(\Omega)$ for every $s \in (0, 1)$, such that

$$(14.128) \quad v \equiv u \quad \text{in} \quad \Omega$$

and for every $\{s_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subset (0, 1)$ such that $s_k \rightarrow 1$ it holds that

$$(14.129) \quad \mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) = \limsup_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(v, \Omega).$$

From now on we let $\{s_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subset (0, 1)$ satisfying $s_k \rightarrow 1$ be fixed. Moreover, up to a subsequence, we can assume that $\{s_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is increasing.

Then, we claim that for every $\varepsilon \in (0, +\infty)$ there exists a subsequence of $\{s_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$, which will not be renamed, such that, for every $h \in X_v^{s_k,p}$,

$$(14.130) \quad \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(v, \Omega) \leq \varepsilon + \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(h, \Omega).$$

To show (14.130), given $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we consider $w_{s_k} \in X_v^{s_k,p}(\Omega)$ such that, for every $h \in X_v^{s_k,p}(\Omega)$,

$$(14.131) \quad \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(w_{s_k}, \Omega) \leq \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(h, \Omega).$$

The existence of w_{s_k} follows from the direct method. In particular, from this and (14.129) it follows that

$$(14.132) \quad \mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) \geq \limsup_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(w_{s_k}, \Omega).$$

From this last inequality and Theorem 14.9(i) and (ii) we deduce that there exists $w \in X^{1,p}(\Omega)$ such that $w_{s_k} \rightarrow w$ in $L^p(\Omega)$ and

$$(14.133) \quad \mathcal{E}_1^p(w, \Omega) \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(w_{s_k}, \Omega).$$

Now, employing (14.132) and (14.133) we deduce that

$$(14.134) \quad \mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) \geq \mathcal{E}_1^p(w, \Omega).$$

Also, as a consequence of Theorem 14.9(i), we infer that

$$(14.135) \quad u - w \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

From (14.135), (14.134) and the minimality of u we obtain that

$$\mathcal{E}_1^p(u, \Omega) = \mathcal{E}_1^p(w, \Omega).$$

Making use of this identity, (14.129) and (14.133) we obtain that

$$\limsup_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(v, \Omega) \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{E}_{s_k}^p(w_{s_k}, \Omega).$$

As a consequence, bearing in mind (14.131), we deduce that (14.130) holds true and this concludes the proof of claim (14.130).

Now, being u a minimizer for \mathcal{E}_1^p in $X^{1,p}(\Omega)$, we can apply Theorem 13.10 in [GG82] and Theorem 6.1 in [LU68] and obtain that

$$(14.136) \quad u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega),$$

for some $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ depending only on n , p and m .

Since $\Omega \neq \mathbb{R}^n$, we have that $C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega) = C_B^\alpha(\Omega)$. From this, (14.136) and (14.128) we obtain that

$$(14.137) \quad v \in C_B^\alpha(\Omega) \quad \text{with } \alpha \in (0, 1) \text{ depending only on } n, p \text{ and } m.$$

Given $s_0 \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right)$, we set

$$k_0 := \min \{k \in \mathbb{N} \text{ s.t. } s_k > s_0\}.$$

Notice that being $\{s_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ increasing, we have that $s_k > s_0$ for every $k \geq k_0$. Then, we choose a subsequence of $\{s_k\}_{k \geq k_0}$ such that (14.130) is satisfied for $\varepsilon := \frac{\delta}{2}$, where $\delta := \delta_{s_0, n, p, m, c_1, \theta_*, c_0, \alpha, [v]_{C_B^\alpha(\Omega)}} \in (0, +\infty)$ is the constant in equation (14.20).

Therefore, by (14.24), (14.128), (14.137), (14.130) and the choice of ε and δ , we obtain that all the hypothesis to apply Theorem 14.5 are satisfied. In virtue of (14.15) we obtain that there exist $\tilde{c} := \tilde{c}_{s_0, n, p, m, \Lambda, c_1, \theta_*, r_0, c_0, \alpha, [u]_{B, \alpha}} \in (0, 1)$ and $R^* := R_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1, \theta_*, c_0}^* \in [r_0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $r \in [R^*, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{4r} \subset \Omega$,

$$(14.138) \quad c_{m, \theta_*} \int_{B_r \cap \{\theta_* < v \leq \theta^*\}} |1 + v(x)|^m dx + \mathcal{L}^n(B_r \cap \{v > \theta_2\}) \geq \tilde{c}r^n.$$

To conclude, we also notice that, since α depends only on n, p and m ,

$$[v]_{C_B^\alpha(\Omega)} \quad \text{depends only on } n, p, m \text{ and } \Omega.$$

On this account, recalling (14.137), we can rewrite δ and \tilde{c} as

$$\delta = \delta_{s_0, n, p, m, c_1, \theta_*, c_0} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{c} = \tilde{c}_{s_0, n, p, m, \Lambda, c_1, \theta_*, r_0, c_0}.$$

Hence, owing to (14.138) and the fact that the choice of $s_0 \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right)$ is arbitrary, we conclude the proof of Theorem 14.10. \square

14.5 Proof of Theorem 14.7

The following result is based on Theorem 1.3 in [SV14]. The main difference is that here we consider the case $p \neq 2$ and we write explicitly the dependence of the constants with respect to $s \in (0, 1)$, which will be important to obtain stable estimates as $s \rightarrow 1$. Also, for every $t \in \mathbb{R}$ we denote $t^+ := \max\{t, 0\}$.

Proof of Theorem 14.7. In what follows, given $A, B \in (0, +\infty)$, we adopt the notation

$$A \lesssim B \quad \text{if} \quad A \leq C_{n,p,m,\Lambda} B$$

for a suitable constant $C_{n,p,m,\Lambda} \in (0, +\infty)$.

Moreover, for every measurable sets $E, F \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and every function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we set

$$f(E, F) := \int_E \int_F \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy.$$

We also define the barrier

$$(14.139) \quad \psi(x) := -1 + 2 \min \{ (|x| - R - 1)^+, 1 \}$$

and the function

$$(14.140) \quad d(x) := \max \{ R - |x|, 1 \}.$$

Then, we claim that

$$(14.141) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(\psi, B_{R+2}) \lesssim \begin{cases} \frac{R^{n-sp}}{s(1-sp)} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \frac{R^{n-1} \log(R)}{s} & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{R^{n-1}}{s(sp-1)} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

The proof of the claim is postponed for the moment, and we show first that if (14.141) holds true then (14.17) follows. To do so, we consider

$$v := \min \{ u, \psi \}.$$

We notice that if we define $A := \{v = \psi\} \cap B_{R+2}$ then we have that $B_{R+1} \subset A$. Also, it clearly holds that $u = v$ in A^c . Hence, we use the minimality of u in B_{R+2} and henceforth in A to obtain that

$$(14.142) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, A) &= (1-s) \left(\frac{1}{2} u(A, A) + u(A, A^c) \right) + \int_A W(u) dx \\ &\leq (1-s) \left(\frac{1}{2} v(A, A) + v(A, A^c) \right) + \int_A W(v) dx \\ &= \mathcal{E}_s^p(v, A). \end{aligned}$$

Now, if $x \in A$ and $y \in A^c$ then $v(x) = \psi(x) \leq u(x)$ and $v(y) = u(y) \leq \psi(y)$, and thus

$$|v(x) - v(y)| \leq \max \{|u(x) - u(y)|, |\psi(x) - \psi(y)|\}.$$

On this account, we find that

$$v(A, A^c) \leq u(A, A^c) + \psi(A, A^c).$$

Thus, making use of (14.142), we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} (14.143) \quad (1-s)\frac{1}{2}u(A, A) + \int_A W(u) dx &\leq (1-s) \left(\frac{1}{2}\psi(A, A) + \psi(A, A^c) \right) + \int_A W(\psi) dx \\ &= \mathcal{E}_s^p(\psi, A) \\ &\leq \mathcal{E}_s^p(\psi, B_{R+2}). \end{aligned}$$

In particular, since $B_{R+1} \subset A \subset B_{R+2}$, using (14.143) we infer that

$$\begin{aligned} (14.144) \quad \mathcal{E}_s^p(u, B_R) &= (1-s)\mathcal{K}_s^p(u, B_R) + \int_{B_R} W(u) dx \\ &\leq (1-s) \left(\frac{1}{2}u(B_{R+1}, B_{R+1}) + u(B_R, B_{R+1}^c) \right) + \int_{B_R} W(u) dx \\ &\leq (1-s) \left(\frac{1}{2}u(A, A) + u(B_R, B_{R+1}^c) \right) + \int_A W(u) dx \\ &\leq \mathcal{E}_s^p(\psi, B_{R+2}) + (1-s)u(B_R, B_{R+1}^c). \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we notice that

$$(14.145) \quad \int_0^{R-1} t^{n-1}(R-t)^{-sp} \leq \begin{cases} \frac{R^{n-1}}{1-sp} (R^{1-sp} - 1) & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ R^{n-1} (\log(R) - \log(1)) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{R^{n-1}}{sp-1} (1 - R^{1-sp}) & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}$$

As a result, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
& (1-s)u(B_R, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+1}) \\
&= (1-s) \int_{B_R} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+1}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\
&\leq 2^p(1-s) \int_{B_R} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+1}(x)} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp}} dx \\
&\leq 2^p(1-s) \int_{B_R} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{d(x)}} \frac{dy}{|y|^{n+sp}} dx \\
&= 2^p(1-s)\omega_{n-1} \int_{B_R} d(x)^{-sp} dx \\
&= 2^p(1-s)\omega_{n-1}^2 \left(\int_0^{R-1} t^{n-1} (R-t)^{-sp} dt + \int_{R-1}^R t^{n-1} dt \right) \\
&\leq 2^p(1-s)\omega_{n-1}^2 \begin{cases} \frac{R^{n-1}}{1-sp} (R^{1-sp} - 1) + R^{n-1} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ R^{n-1} (\log(R) - \log(1)) + R^{n-1} & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{R^{n-1}}{sp-1} (1 - R^{1-sp}) + R^{n-1} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right) \end{cases} \\
&\leq C(1-s) \begin{cases} \frac{R^{n-sp}}{1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ R^{n-1} \log(R) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \frac{R^{n-1}}{sp-1} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right). \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

Making use of this, (14.144) and claim (14.141) we conclude the proof of (14.17).

It remains however to check claim (14.141). To this end, we first show that

$$(14.146) \quad |\psi(x) - \psi(y)| \leq \begin{cases} 2d(x)^{-1}|x-y| & \text{if } |x-y| < d(x) \\ 2 & \text{if } |x-y| \geq d(x). \end{cases}$$

To prove this, we notice that, for every $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(14.147) \quad |\psi(x) - \psi(y)| = 2 \left| \min \{(|x| - R - 1)^+, 1\} - \min \{(|y| - R - 1)^+, 1\} \right|.$$

Also,

$$(14.148) \quad \min \{(|x| - R - 1)^+, 1\} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in B_{R+1} \\ |x| - R - 1 & \text{if } x \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 1 & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+2}. \end{cases}$$

Now, to prove (14.146), we distinguish between the cases

$$(14.149) \quad |x - y| < d(x)$$

and

$$(14.150) \quad |x - y| \geq d(x).$$

Suppose first that (14.149) holds true. Thus, if $x \in B_{R-1}$ we deduce from (14.140) that $d(x) = R - |x|$ and accordingly $|x - y| < R - |x|$, which in turn gives that $y \in B_R$.

From this, (14.148) and (14.147) it follows that

$$(14.151) \quad |\psi(x) - \psi(y)| = 0.$$

Also, when $x \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_{R-1}$ we infer from (14.140) that $d(x) = 1$ and thus $|x - y| < 1$. It thereby follows that $y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R-1}$ and then, in light of (14.147) and (14.148),

$$(14.152) \quad \begin{aligned} |\psi(x) - \psi(y)| &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_{R-1} \\ 2(|y| - R - 1) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \end{cases} \\ &\leq \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_{R-1} \\ 2(|y| - |x|) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \end{cases} \\ &\leq \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_{R-1} \\ 2|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_{R-1} \\ 2d^{-1}(x)|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1}. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

When instead $x \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1}$, we infer from (14.140) that $d(x) = 1$ and thus $|x - y| < 1$. This yields that $y \in B_{R+3} \setminus B_R$. Then, by virtue of (14.147)

and (14.148), we see that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.153) \quad |\psi(x) - \psi(y)| &= \begin{cases} 2(|x| - R - 1) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_R \\ 2||x| - |y|| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 2||x| - R - 2| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+3} \setminus B_{R+2} \end{cases} \\
 &\leq \begin{cases} 2(|x| - |y|) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_R \\ 2|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 2(R + 2 - |x|) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+3} \setminus B_{R+2} \end{cases} \\
 &\leq \begin{cases} 2|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_R \\ 2d^{-1}(x)|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 2(|y| - |x|) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+3} \setminus B_{R+2} \end{cases} \\
 &= \begin{cases} 2d^{-1}(x)|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+1} \setminus B_R \\ 2d^{-1}(x)|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 2d^{-1}(x)|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+3} \setminus B_{R+2}. \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

If instead $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+2}$, we use that $|x - y| < d(x) = 1$ and accordingly $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+1}$. From this, we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\psi(x) - \psi(y)| &= \begin{cases} 2(R + 2 - |y|) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+2} \end{cases} \\
 &\leq \begin{cases} 2(|x| - |y|) & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+2} \end{cases} \\
 &\leq \begin{cases} 2|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+2} \end{cases} \\
 &= \begin{cases} 2d^{-1}(x)|x - y| & \text{if } y \in B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1} \\ 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+2}. \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

By combining the latter estimate with (14.151), (14.152) and (14.153), we deduce that (14.146) holds true in this case.

We now focus on the case given by (14.149). In this situation, it follows from (14.147) that

$$|\psi(x) - \psi(y)| \leq 2$$

and this concludes the proof of (14.146).

Now, using (14.146), given $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ we see that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|\psi(x) - \psi(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy \\ & \lesssim \left(\int_{B_{d(x)}(x)} \frac{d(x)^{-p}}{|x - y|^{n+sp-p}} dy + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{d(x)}(x)} \frac{dy}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \right) \\ & \lesssim \left(d(x)^{-p} \int_0^{d(x)} r^{-1-p+sp} dr + \int_{d(x)}^{+\infty} r^{-1-sp} dr \right) \\ & = \frac{d(x)^{-sp}}{p - sp} + \frac{d(x)^{-sp}}{sp} \\ & = \frac{d(x)^{-sp}}{sp(1 - s)}, \end{aligned}$$

From this, integrating with respect to $x \in B_{R+2}$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_s^p(\psi, B_{R+2}) & \leq \int_{B_{R+2}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|\psi(x) - \psi(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\ & \lesssim \frac{1}{s(1 - s)} \int_{B_{R+2}} d(x)^{-sp} dx \\ & = \frac{1}{s(1 - s)} \left(|B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R-1}| + \int_{B_{R-1}} (R - |x|)^{-sp} dx \right) \\ & \lesssim \frac{1}{s(1 - s)} \left(R^{n-1} + \int_0^{R-1} t^{n-1} (R - t)^{-sp} dt \right). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, recalling (14.145), we conclude that, for every $R \geq 2$,

$$(14.154) \quad \mathcal{K}_s^p(\psi, B_{R+2}) \lesssim \frac{1}{s(1 - s)} \begin{cases} \frac{R^{n-1}}{1 - sp} (R^{1-sp} - 1) & \text{if } s \in (0, 1/p) \\ R^{n-1} (\log(R) - \log(1)) & \text{if } s = 1/p \\ \frac{R^{n-1}}{sp - 1} (1 - R^{1-sp}) & \text{if } s \in (1/p, 1). \end{cases}$$

Finally, using (14.6), (14.139) and (14.148) we obtain that

$$(14.155) \quad \begin{aligned} \int_{B_{R+2}} W(\psi(x)) dx & = \int_{B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1}} W(\psi(x)) dx \\ & \lesssim \int_{B_{R+2} \setminus B_{R+1}} |1 + \psi(x)|^m dx \\ & \lesssim R^{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, from (14.154) and (14.155) we obtain (14.141), as desired. \square

14.6 Appendix

A recursive formula

For $x \in [-1, 1]$, $m \in (1, +\infty)$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, [m]\}$ we define the polynomials

$$\begin{cases} P_m^1(x) := -2xm \\ P_m^k(x) := P_{m-k+1}^1(x)P_m^{k-1}(x) + (1-x^2)P_m^{k-1}'(x). \end{cases}$$

Then, we have the following result:

Proposition 14.16. *Let $m \in (1, +\infty)$ and $W_m(x) := (1-x^2)^m$ with $x \in [-1, 1]$. Then, for every $k \in \{1, \dots, [m]\}$,*

$$(14.156) \quad W_m^{(k)}(x) = W_{m-k}(x)P_m^k(x).$$

Also, for every $m \in (1, +\infty)$ and $c \in (0, 1)$ there exists $\hat{q}_{m,c} \in (0, 1)$ such that, for every $k \in \{1, \dots, [m]\}$ and $x \in [-1, -1 + \hat{q}_{m,c}]$,

$$(14.157) \quad P_m^k(x) \geq c.$$

In particular, $W_m(x)$ satisfies (14.7) for some $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$ and $q \in (0, 1)$.

Proof. We notice that, for every $m \in (1, +\infty)$,

$$(14.158) \quad W_m'(x) = -2xm(1-x^2)^{m-1} = P_m^1(x)W_{m-1}(x).$$

Let us now proceed recursively and assume that $m \in [2, +\infty)$ and that (14.156) holds for every $j \leq k-1 < [m]$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} W_m^{(k)}(x) &= (W_m^{(k-1)}(x))' \\ &= (W_{m-k+1}(x)P_m^{k-1}(x))' \\ &= W_{m-k+1}'(x)P_m^{k-1}(x) + W_{m-k+1}(x)P_m^{k-1}'(x) \\ &= P_{m-k+1}^1(x)W_{m-k}(x)P_m^{k-1}(x) + W_{m-k+1}(x)P_m^{k-1}'(x) \\ &= W_{m-k}(x) \left(P_{m-k+1}^1(x)P_m^{k-1}(x) + (1-x^2)P_m^{k-1}'(x) \right) \\ &= W_{m-k}(x)P_m^k(x). \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of (14.156).

Now we prove (14.157). For this, we consider $0 < q_{[m]} \leq \dots \leq q_1 < 1$ which will be chosen as follows.

For any $m \in (1, +\infty)$, we choose $q_1 := 1 - \frac{c}{2m}$, from which it follows that, for every $x \in [-1, -1 + q_1]$,

$$P_m^1(x) = -2xm \geq -2m(-1 + q_1) = 2m(1 - q_1) = c.$$

Now we assume that $P_m^j(x) \geq c$ for every $j \leq k - 1 < [m]$ and $x \in [-1, -1 + q_j]$. We need to show that there exists $q_k \in (0, q_{k-1})$ such that $P_m^k(x) \geq c$ for every $x \in [-1, -1 + q_k]$. In order to do so, we let

$$(14.159) \quad q_k := \min \left\{ q_{k-1}, \frac{2c(m - k + 1) - c}{2c(m - k + 1) + 2 \|P_m^{k-1'}\|_{L^\infty([-1,0])}} \right\}$$

and, for every $x \in [-1, -1 + q_k] \subset [-1, -1 + q_{k-1}]$,

$$\begin{aligned} P_m^k(x) &= P_{m-k+1}^1(x)P_m^{k-1}(x) + (1 - x^2)P_m^{k-1'}(x) \\ &\geq P_{m-k+1}^1(x)P_m^{k-1}(x) - (1 - x^2) \|P_m^{k-1'}\|_{L^\infty([-1,0])} \\ &\geq 2c(1 - q_k)(m - k + 1) - 2q_k \|P_m^{k-1'}\|_{L^\infty([-1,0])} \\ &\geq c. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, by choosing $\hat{q}_{c,m} := q_{[m]}$ we establish the validity of (14.157), as desired.

Thus, as a consequence of (14.156) and (14.157), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} W_m(t) - W_m(r) &= \int_r^t W_m'(\xi) d\xi \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{W_m^{(j)}(r)}{j!} (t - r)^j + \int_r^t \dots \int_r^l W_m^{(k)}(z) dz \dots d\xi \\ &\geq W_m^{(1)}(r)(t - r) + \frac{c}{k!} (t - r)^k \\ &= (1 - r^2)^{m-1} P_1^m(r)(t - r) + \frac{c}{k!} (t - r)^k \\ &\geq c(1 - r)^{m-1} (1 + r)^{m-1} (t - r) + \frac{c}{k!} (t - r)^k \\ &\geq c(2 - \hat{q}_{c,m})^{m-1} (1 + r)^{m-1} (t - r) + \frac{c}{k!} (t - r)^k, \end{aligned}$$

as long as $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $c \in (0, 1)$, $-1 \leq r \leq t \leq -1 + \hat{q}_{c,m}$ and $k = m$.

This shows that $W_m(x)$ satisfies (14.7) for every $m \in \mathbb{N}$ with $q := \hat{q}_{c,m}$ and

$$(14.160) \quad c_1 := \min \left\{ c(2-q)^{m-1}, \frac{c}{k!} \right\}.$$

Additionally, if $m \in (1, +\infty) \setminus \mathbb{N}$ and $c \in (0, 1)$ we define $q_1 \in (0, 1)$ as the unique solution to

$$2c(1-q_1)(m-[m])(2q_1)^{m-[m]-1} = c + (2q_1)^{m-[m]} \left\| P_m^{[m]'} \right\|_{L^\infty([-1,0])}.$$

We observe that, for every $t \in (0, q_1)$,

$$(14.161) \quad 2c(1-t)(m-[m])(2t)^{m-[m]-1} > c + (2t)^{m-[m]} \left\| P_m^{[m]'} \right\|_{L^\infty([-1,0])}.$$

Then, we set

$$(14.162) \quad q := \min \{ \hat{q}_{c,m}, q_1 \}$$

and we deduce from (14.161), (14.156) and (14.157) that, when $k = [m] + 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} W_m^{(k)}(x) &= (W_m^{([m])}(x))' \\ &= ((1-x^2)^{m-[m]} P_m^{[m]}(x))' \\ &= -2x(m-[m]) (1-x^2)^{m-[m]-1} P_m^{[m]}(x) + (1-x^2)^{m-[m]} P_m^{[m]'}(x) \\ &\geq 2c(1-\tilde{q})(m-[m])(2\tilde{q})^{m-[m]-1} - (2\tilde{q})^{m-[m]} \left\| P_m^{[m]'} \right\|_{L^\infty([-1,0])} \\ &\geq c, \end{aligned}$$

for every $x \in [-1, -1+q]$

Because of this, we have that, for every $-1 \leq r \leq t \leq -1+q$,

$$\begin{aligned} W_m(t) - W_m(r) &= \int_r^t W_m'(\xi) d\xi \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{W_m^{(j)}(r)}{j!} (t-r)^j + \int_r^t \dots \int_r^l W_m^{(k)}(z) dz \dots d\xi \\ &\geq W_m^{(1)}(r)(t-r) + \frac{c}{k!} (t-r)^k \\ &= (1-r^2)^{m-1} P_1^m(r)(t-r) \frac{c}{k!} (t-r)^k \\ &\geq c(1-r)^{m-1} (1+r)^{m-1} (t-r) + \frac{c}{k!} (t-r)^k \\ &\geq c(2-q)^{m-1} (1+r)^{m-1} (t-r) + \frac{c}{k!} (t-r)^k. \end{aligned}$$

This proves that W_m satisfies (14.7) for every $m \in (1, +\infty) \setminus \mathbb{N}$ with c_1 and q respectively as in (14.160) and (14.162). \square

Proof of Theorem 14.15

In this section we prove Theorem 14.15. The estimate in Theorem 14.15 is actually a consequence of the following integral inequality:

Proposition 14.17. *Let $R, \sigma \in (0, +\infty)$. Then, there exists a constant $c_{n,\sigma} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $x \in B_R$,*

$$(14.163) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+\sigma}} \geq \frac{c_{n,\sigma}}{\sigma} (R-|x|)^{-\sigma}.$$

Furthermore, if $\sigma \in (0, M)$ for some $M \in (0, +\infty)$, it holds that $c_{n,\sigma} \geq c_{n,M}$.

Proof. To show (14.163), we begin by observing that, for every $x \in B_R$,

$$(14.164) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+\sigma}} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \frac{dy}{||x|e_1 - y|^{n+\sigma}}.$$

Also, given $m > 0$, we define

$$(14.165) \quad T_m(|x|) := \{z \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid z_1 \in (R, +\infty), |z_i| \leq m(z_1 - |x|) \text{ for all } i = 2, \dots, n\},$$

and we notice that

$$(14.166) \quad T_m(|x|) \subset \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R.$$

Accordingly, thanks to (14.164), (14.165) and (14.166) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+\sigma}} &\geq \int_{T_m(|x|)} \frac{dz}{|e_1|x| - z|^{n+\sigma}} \\ &= \int_R^{+\infty} \int_{-m(z_1-|x|)}^{m(z_1-|x|)} \dots \int_{-m(z_1-|x|)}^{m(z_1-|x|)} \frac{dz_n \dots dz_2}{||x|e_1 - z|^{n+\sigma}} dz_1. \end{aligned}$$

Besides, we observe that, for every $z \in T_m(|x|)$,

$$(14.167) \quad \begin{aligned} ||x|e_1 - z|^2 &= (|x| - z_1)^2 + z_2^2 \dots + z_n^2 \\ &\leq (|x| - z_1)^2 + m^2 (z_1 - |x|)^2 + \dots + m^2 (1 - z_1)^2 \\ &= ((n-1)m^2 + 1) (z_1 - |x|)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, making use of (14.166) and (14.167) we evince that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+\sigma}} \\
 & \geq \frac{1}{((n-1)m^2+1)^{\frac{n+\sigma}{2}}} \int_R^{+\infty} \int_{-m(z_1-|x|)}^{m(z_1-|x|)} \cdots \int_{-m(z_1-|x|)}^{m(z_1-|x|)} \frac{dz_n \dots dz_2}{|z_1-|x||^{n+\sigma}} dz_1 \\
 (14.168) \quad & = \frac{(2m)^{n-1}}{((n-1)m^2+1)^{\frac{n+1+s}{2}}} \int_R^{+\infty} \frac{(z_1-|x|)^{n-1}}{|z_1-|x||^{n+\sigma}} dz_1 \\
 & = \frac{2^n m^n}{(nm^2+1)^{\frac{n+1+s}{2}}} \int_R^{+\infty} \frac{dz_1}{|z_1-|x||^{1+\sigma}} dz_1 \\
 & = \frac{(2m)^{n-1}}{\sigma((n-1)m^2+1)^{\frac{n+\sigma}{2}}} (R-|x|)^{-s} \\
 & \geq \frac{c_{n,\sigma}}{\sigma} (R-|x|)^{-s}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, we notice that if $\sigma \in (0, M)$ for some $M \in (0, +\infty)$, then $c_{n,\sigma} \geq c_{n,M}$. □

Making use of Proposition 14.17, we now state and prove a lower bound for $L(B_1, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{1+r})$ when $r \in (0, +\infty)$ is small enough. Then, Theorem 14.15 will follow by scaling from Lemma 14.18.

Lemma 14.18. *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $\delta := \min \{2^{-n}, 2^{-n+2-p}\}$.*

Then, for every $r \in (0, \delta)$,

$$L(B_1, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r+1}) \geq \begin{cases} \delta & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \delta \ln \left(\frac{1}{r}\right) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \delta r^{1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right) \end{cases}$$

Proof. By (14.163), we have that, for every $x \in B_1$,

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{r+1}} \frac{dy}{|x-y|^{n+sp}} \geq \frac{c_{n,p}}{s} (r+1-|x|)^{-sp}.$$

Hence, integrating both sides of the above inequality in B_1 we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.169) \quad L(B_1, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{1+r}) &= \int_{B_1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{1+r}} \frac{dy \, dx}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} \\
 &\geq \frac{c_{n,p}}{s} \int_{B_1} (r + 1 - |x|)^{-sp} \, dx \\
 &= |\partial B_1| \frac{c_{n,p}}{s} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{n-1}}{(r + 1 - t)^{sp}} \, dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we need to distinguish the following three cases:

$$(14.170) \quad sp \in (0, 1),$$

$$(14.171) \quad sp = 1$$

and

$$(14.172) \quad sp \in (1, p).$$

When (14.170) holds true, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^1 t^{n-1} (r + 1 - t)^{-sp} \, dt &\geq \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 t^{n-1} (r + 1 - t)^{-sp} \, dt \\
 &\geq \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 (r + 1 - t)^{-sp} \, dt \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \frac{1}{sp - 1} (r + 1 - t)^{-sp+1} \Big|_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \frac{1}{1 - sp} \left[\left(r + \frac{1}{2}\right)^{1-sp} - r^{1-sp} \right] \\
 &\geq \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \frac{1}{1 - sp} \left[1 - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{1-sp} \right] \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \frac{1 - 2^{-(1-sp)}}{1 - sp} \\
 &\geq \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Instead, when (14.171) holds true, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^1 t^{n-1}(r+1-t)^{-1} dt &\geq \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 t^{n-1}(r+1-t)^{-1} dt \\
&\geq \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 (r+1-t)^{-1} dt \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \left| \ln(r+1-t) \right|_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} [|\ln(r)| - |\ln(r+1/2)|] \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n 2 \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{2r}\right) \\
&\geq \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n \ln \left(\frac{1}{r}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, in case (14.172),

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^1 t^{n-1}(r+1-t)^{-sp} dt &\geq \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 t^{n-1}(r+1-t)^{-sp} dt \\
&\geq \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 (r+1-t)^{-sp} dt \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \frac{1}{sp-1} (r+1-t)^{-sp+1} \Big|_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \frac{1}{sp-1} \left[\frac{1}{r^{sp-1}} - \frac{1}{(r+1/2)^{sp-1}} \right] \\
&\geq \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{n-1} \frac{1}{sp-1} \left[\frac{1}{r^{sp-1}} - \frac{1}{(2r)^{sp-1}} \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{2^{sp+n-2}} \left(\frac{2^{sp-1}-1}{sp-1} \right) r^{1-sp} \\
&\geq \frac{1}{2^{p+n-2}} r^{1-sp}.
\end{aligned}$$

These three cases complete the proof of the desired result. \square

With this preliminary work, we are in a position to complete the proof of Theorem 14.15.

Proof of Theorem 14.15. To prove (14.64) it is enough to rescale $L(B_R, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+r})$. By doing so, we can apply Lemma 14.18 as follows:

$$L(B_R, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R+r}) = R^{n-sp} L(B_1, \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{1+\frac{r}{R}}) \geq \begin{cases} \delta R^{n-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(0, \frac{1}{p}\right) \\ \delta R^{n-1} \ln\left(\frac{R}{r}\right) & \text{if } s = \frac{1}{p} \\ \delta R^{n-sp} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{1-sp} & \text{if } s \in \left(\frac{1}{p}, 1\right), \end{cases}$$

yielding the desired result. □

Some regularity results

In what follows we consider w as given in Theorem 13.10 with $\tau := \mu$, where μ has been defined in equation (14.33). Also, we let \bar{R}_μ be as in (14.32). Moreover, given any $f \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$, $K \subset\subset \Omega$ such that $\bigcup_{x_0 \in K} B_2(x_0) \subset \Omega$ we denote

$$\sup_{x_0 \in K} [f]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} := [f]_{K,\alpha}.$$

Then, with these choices we have the following result:

Proposition 14.19. *Let $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $s \in [s_0, 1)$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$. Moreover, we let v be defined in (14.36) and $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ satisfying $B_{R+2} \subset \Omega$. Then, $u - v \in C_c^\alpha(\Omega)$ and there exists $C := C_{s_0,n,m,p,c_1} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for every $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$,*

$$(14.173) \quad [u - v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \leq 4 [u]_{K,\alpha} + 2C.$$

Proof. First, we claim that there exists $C_{s_0,n,m,p,c_1} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that, for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(14.174) \quad |\nabla w(x)| \leq C_{s_0,n,m,p,c_1}.$$

To show (14.174), we recall that according to (13.66), we have that

$$(14.175) \quad w(x) = (2 - \beta)h\left(\frac{|x|}{C_0}\right) + \beta - 1,$$

where the function h and the constants C_0 and β are given respectively in (13.34) and (13.65). Also, for every $R \in [\bar{R}_\mu, +\infty)$ according to (13.65) and (13.67) it holds that

$$(14.176) \quad \beta \leq 2.$$

Furthermore, according to (13.65) there exists a constant $c_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that

$$(14.177) \quad c_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1} \leq C_0.$$

Also, if $\hat{r}, r \in (0, +\infty)$ are given respectively as in (13.51) and (13.67), then, for every $t \in (0, \frac{r}{2}] \cup (\hat{r}, +\infty)$,

$$(14.178) \quad h'(t) = 0.$$

Moreover, according to equations (13.34), (13.51), (13.111) and Proposition 13.17, it holds that, for every $t \in (\frac{r}{2}, \hat{r})$,

$$(14.179) \quad h'(t) \leq C_{p, m} (r - t)^{-qs-1} \leq C_{p, m} (r - \hat{r})^{-qs-1} \leq C_{p, m} \left(\hat{C}_{p, m} \right)^{-qs-1} \leq \tilde{C}_{p, m}.$$

Therefore, putting together (14.175), (14.176), (14.177), (14.178) and (14.179), we deduce that, for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$|\nabla w(x)| = \frac{2 - \beta}{C_0} \left| h' \left(\frac{|x|}{C_0} \right) \right| \leq \frac{4}{c_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1}} \tilde{C}_{p, m} =: C_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1}.$$

This concludes the proof of claim (14.174).

Furthermore, since $u \in C_{loc}^\alpha(\Omega)$ and $B_{R+2} \subset \Omega$, we have that, for every $x_0 \in \bar{B}_R$,

$$(14.180) \quad [u]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \leq [u]_{C^\alpha(B_{R+\frac{3}{2}})}.$$

Also, we recall that $v := \min\{u, w\}$ and it is easy to verify that

$$|v(x) - v(y)| \leq \max\{|u(x) - u(y)|, |w(x) - w(y)|\}.$$

From this and (14.174) it follows that, for every $x_0 \in \bar{B}_R$,

$$(14.181) \quad [v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \leq \max \left\{ [u]_{C^\alpha(B_{R+\frac{3}{2}})}, C_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1} \right\}.$$

Hence, recalling (14.181), we obtain that, for every $x_0 \in \overline{B}_R$,

$$(14.182) \quad [u - v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \leq [u]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} + [v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \leq 2 [u]_{C^\alpha(B_{R+\frac{3}{2}})} + C_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1}.$$

Now, for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R$ we use the notation $x' := \frac{x}{|x|}R$. Also, in what follows we take $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \overline{B}_R$. Then, employing (14.180), (14.181), (14.182) and recalling that the support of $u - v$ is contained in B_R , we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} & [u - v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x_0))} \\ := & \sup_{x, y \in B_1(x_0)} \frac{|(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y)|}{|x - y|^\alpha} \\ \leq & \sup_{x, y \in B_R \cap B_1(x_0)} \frac{|(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y)|}{|x - y|^\alpha} + \sup_{\substack{x \in B_R \cap B_1(x_0) \\ y \in B_1(x_0) \setminus B_R}} \frac{|(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y)|}{|x - y|^\alpha} \\ \leq & \sup_{x, y \in B_R \cap B_1(x_0)} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|}{|x - y|^\alpha} + \sup_{x, y \in B_R \cap B_1(x_0)} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|}{|x - y|^\alpha} \\ & + \sup_{\substack{x \in B_R \cap B_1(x_0) \\ y \in B_1(x_0) \setminus B_R}} \frac{|(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y)|}{|x - y|^\alpha} \\ \leq & [u]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x'_0))} + [v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x'_0))} + \sup_{\substack{x \in B_R \cap B_1(x_0) \\ y \in B_1(x_0) \setminus B_R}} \frac{|(u - v)(x) - (u - v)(y')|}{|x - y'|^\alpha} \\ \leq & [u]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x'_0))} + [v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x'_0))} + [u - v]_{C^\alpha(B_1(x'_0))} \\ \leq & 4 [u]_{C^\alpha(B_{R+\frac{3}{2}})} + 2C_{s_0, n, m, p, c_1}. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Technical results

Here we collect some technical results that will be used in the proof of the Γ -convergence stated in Theorem 14.9.

First we point out a useful variation of a celebrated result in [BBM01].

Proposition 14.20. *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$ and $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded, open and smooth. Also, let $R \in (0, +\infty)$ be such that $\Omega \subset B_{\frac{R}{3}}$.*

Then, for every $v \in W^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R) \cap L^p(B_R)$,

$$(14.183) \quad \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (1 - s) \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx = \frac{K_{n,p}}{p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v(x)|^p dx.$$

Proof. For any $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ small enough we define the sets Ω_ε^- and Ω_ε^+ as in (14.105). Also, without loss of generality we assume that $0 \in \Omega$.

According to Corollary 2 in [BBM01], we have that, for every $u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega)$,

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \int_{\Omega} \int_{\Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx = \frac{K_{n,p}}{p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^p dx.$$

As a consequence, in order to prove (14.183) it is only left to show that

$$(14.184) \quad \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} (1 - s) \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx = 0.$$

To show (14.184), we first observe that

$$(14.185) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\ &= \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx + \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\ &= \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx + \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\ &+ \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx + \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx. \end{aligned}$$

Now we define

$$\begin{aligned} A &:= \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx, & B &:= \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx, \\ C &:= \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx, & D &:= \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx. \end{aligned}$$

Then, if $R \in (0, +\infty)$ is such that $\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \subset B_{\frac{R}{2}}$, we see that, for every $x \in \Omega_\varepsilon^-$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R$,

$$|x - y|^{n+sp} \geq (|y| - |x|)^{n+sp} \geq \left(\frac{|y|}{2}\right)^{n+sp}.$$

Hence, we obtain the existence of a constant $C_{n,p}$ such that

(14.186)

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|y/2|^{n+sp}} dx dy + \int_{B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{(2\varepsilon)^{n+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\leq 2^{p-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \frac{|v(x)|^p + |v(y)|^p}{|y/2|^{n+sp}} dx dy + 2^{p-1} \int_{B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^-} \frac{|v(x)|^p + |v(y)|^p}{(2\varepsilon)^{n+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\leq 2^{p-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R} \frac{\|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R)}^p}{|y/2|^{n+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\quad + 2^{p-1} \int_{B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+} \frac{\|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| |v(y)|^p}{(2\varepsilon)^{n+sp}} dy \\
 &\leq C_{n,p} \left(\|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R)}^p \right) \frac{R^{-sp}}{sp} \\
 &\quad + C_{n,p} \varepsilon^{-n-sp} \left(|B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^p(B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+)}^p \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$(14.187) \quad B \leq C_{n,p} \varepsilon^{-n-sp} \left(|\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} + |\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)} \right).$$

Also, we can estimate C as

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.188) \quad C &\leq C_{n,p} \left(\|v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R)}^p \right) \frac{R^{-sp}}{sp} \\
 &\quad + C_{n,p} \varepsilon^{-n-sp} \left(|B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^p(B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+)}^p \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we estimate D . To do so, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (14.189) \quad D &= \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\
 &= \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\
 &\quad + \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1^c(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, for a.e. $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ it holds that

$$\frac{|v(x) - v(y)|}{|x - y|} \leq \int_0^1 |\nabla v(y + t(x - y))| dt$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\
&= \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^p} \frac{1}{|x - y|^{n+sp-p}} dy dx \\
&\leq \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \left(\int_0^1 |\nabla v(y + t(x - y))| dt \right)^p \frac{1}{|x - y|^{n+sp-p}} dy dx \\
&\leq \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \int_0^1 \frac{|\nabla v(y + t(x - y))|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp-p}} dt dy dx \\
(14.190) \quad &\leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{B_1} \int_0^1 \frac{|\nabla v(x + (1-t)z)|^p}{|z|^{n+sp-p}} \chi_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-}(x) dt dz dx \\
&= \int_{B_1} \int_0^1 \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|\nabla v(x)|^p}{|z|^{n+sp-p}} \chi_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-}(x - (1-t)z) dx dt dz \\
&= \int_{B_1} \int_0^1 \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{|\nabla v(x)|^p}{|z|^{n+sp-p}} \chi_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + (1-t)z}(x) dx dt dz \\
&= \int_{B_1} \int_0^1 \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\|\nabla v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + (1-t)z)}^p}{|z|^{n+sp-p}} dt dz.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the function $f : \overline{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$f(q) := \|\nabla v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + q)}^p$$

is continuous and therefore there exists $\tilde{q}_\varepsilon \in \overline{B}_1$ such that, for every $t \in (0, 1)$ and $z \in B_1$,

$$\|\nabla v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + (1-t)z)}^p \leq f(\tilde{q}_\varepsilon).$$

Hence, it follows from (14.190) that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\
(14.191) \quad &\leq \int_{B_1} \frac{\|\nabla v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + \tilde{q}_\varepsilon)}^p}{|z|^{n+sp-p}} dz \\
&= \frac{|\partial B_1|}{p - sp} \|\nabla v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + \tilde{q}_\varepsilon)}^p
\end{aligned}$$

We also observe that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1^c(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\ & \leq \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-} \int_{B_1^c(x) \cap (\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} |v(x) - v(y)|^p dy dx \\ & \leq C_{n,p} \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^+)} , \end{aligned}$$

for a suitable constant $C_{n,p}$.

Consequently, taking into account (14.185), (14.186), (14.187), (14.188), (14.189) and (14.191), we infer that

$$\begin{aligned} & (1-s) \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \\ & \leq (1-s) C_{n,p} \left(\|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R)}^p \right) \frac{R^{-sp}}{sp} \\ & \quad + (1-s) C_{n,p} \varepsilon^{-n-sp} \left(|B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^p(B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+)}^p \right) \\ & \quad + (1-s) C_{n,p} \varepsilon^{-n-sp} \left(|\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega)} + |\Omega_\varepsilon^+ \setminus \Omega| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^-)} \right) \\ & \quad + (1-s) C_{n,p} \left(\|v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_R)}^p \right) \frac{R^{-sp}}{sp} \\ & \quad + (1-s) C_{n,p} \varepsilon^{-n-sp} \left(|B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+| \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-)}^p + |\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^-| \|v\|_{L^p(B_R \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^+)}^p \right) \\ & \quad + (1-s) \frac{|\partial B_1|}{p(1-s)} \|\nabla v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + \tilde{q}_\varepsilon)}^p \\ & \quad + (1-s) C_{n,p} \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega_\varepsilon^+)} . \end{aligned}$$

In particular, we deduce that

$$\limsup_{s \rightarrow 1} (1-s) \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{n+sp}} dy dx \leq \frac{|\partial B_1|}{p} \|\nabla v\|_{L^p(\Omega \setminus \Omega_\varepsilon^- + \tilde{q}_\varepsilon)}^p .$$

Finally, we notice that the right-hand side is small with ε , which concludes the proof of Proposition 14.20. \square

The following result has been proved for $L^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$ in [ADPM11] and for $L^2(\mathbb{R}^n)$ in [Cri+23]. We provide here a proof for $L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$ for every $p \in (1, +\infty)$.

Proposition 14.21. *Let $p \in (1, +\infty)$. Then, there exists $C_{n,p} \in (0, 1)$ such that, for every $v \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$, every $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$, every open bounded set $\Omega' \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and every $\rho \in (0, |h|]$,*

$$(14.192) \quad \|\tau_h v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega')} \leq C_{n,p} \frac{|h|^p}{\rho^{n+p}} \int_{B_\rho} \|\tau_h v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega'_{|h|})} dy.$$

Proof. Let $\phi \in C_c^1(B_1)$ be such that

$$\phi \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{B_1} \phi(x) dx = 1.$$

For every $\rho \in (0, +\infty)$ we define the following two functions

$$U_\rho(x) := \frac{1}{\rho^n} \int_{B_\rho} v(x+y) \phi\left(\frac{y}{\rho}\right) dy \quad \text{and} \quad V_\rho(x) := \frac{1}{\rho^n} \int_{B_\rho} (v(x) - v(x+y)) \phi\left(\frac{y}{\rho}\right) dy.$$

We notice that

$$v(x) = U_\rho(x) + V_\rho(x).$$

We also have that

$$(14.193) \quad \begin{aligned} |\tau_h v(x) - v(x)|^p &= |U_\rho(x+h) + V_\rho(x+h) - U_\rho(x) - V_\rho(x)|^p \\ &\leq C_p (|U_\rho(x+h) - U_\rho(x)|^p + |V_\rho(x+h)|^p + |V_\rho(x)|^p), \end{aligned}$$

for a suitable constant $C_p > 0$.

By the Jensen inequality, for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$(14.194) \quad |V_\rho(x)|^p \leq \frac{\|\phi\|_{L^\infty(B_1)}}{\rho^n} \int_{B_\rho} |v(x) - v(x+y)|^p dy.$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla U_\rho(x) &= \frac{\nabla}{\rho^n} \int_{B_\rho} v(x+y) \phi\left(\frac{y}{\rho}\right) dy \\ &= \frac{\nabla}{\rho^n} \int_{B_\rho} v(z) \phi\left(\frac{z-x}{\rho}\right) dy \\ &= -\frac{1}{\rho^{n+1}} \int_{B_\rho} (v(z) - v(x)) \nabla \phi\left(\frac{z-x}{\rho}\right) dy \\ &= -\frac{1}{\rho^{n+1}} \int_{B_\rho} (v(x+y) - v(x)) \nabla \phi\left(\frac{y}{\rho}\right) dy. \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, using the fundamental Theorem of Calculus and the Jensen inequality we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} |U_\rho(x+h) - U_\rho(x)|^p &= \left| \int_0^1 \nabla U_\rho(x+th) \cdot h \, dt \right|^p \\ &\leq |h|^p \int_0^1 |\nabla U_\rho(x+th)|^p \, dt \\ &\leq \omega_n^p \frac{|h|^p}{\rho^{n+p}} \|\nabla \phi\|_{L^\infty(B_1)}^p \int_0^1 \int_{B_\rho} |\tau_y v(x+th) - v(x+th)|^p \, dy \, dt \end{aligned}$$

On this account, using (14.193) and (14.194), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} |\tau_h v(x) - v(x)|^p &\leq C_p \left(\omega_n^p \frac{|h|^p}{\rho^{n+p}} \|\nabla \phi\|_{L^\infty(B_1)}^p \int_0^1 \int_{B_\rho} |\tau_y v(x+th) - v(x+th)|^p \, dy \, dt \right. \\ &\quad + \frac{\|\phi\|_{L^\infty(B_1)}}{\rho^n} \int_{B_\rho} |v(x) - v(x+y)|^p \, dy \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\|\phi\|_{L^\infty(B_1)}}{\rho^n} \int_{B_\rho} |v(x+h) - v(x+h+y)|^p \, dy \right). \end{aligned}$$

Integrating both sides in Ω' and taking $\rho \leq |h|$ we conclude. □

As a consequence of this result and Lemma 2.5 in [Cri+23] we obtain the following result.

Proposition 14.22. *There exists a constant $\bar{C}_{n,p} \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for every $v \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$, every bounded open set $\Omega' \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, every $s \in (0, 1)$ and every $h \in \mathbb{R}^n$,*

$$\|\tau_h v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega')}^p \leq \bar{C}_{n,p} |h|^{sp} (1-s) \int_{B_{|h|}} \frac{\|\tau_y v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega'_{|h|})}^p}{|y|^{n+sp}} \, dy.$$

Proof. For every fixed $v \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^n)$, we define the function $g_v : [0, |h|] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as

$$g_v(t) := \int_{\partial B_t} \|\tau_y v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega'_{|h|})}^p \, dH_y^{n-1}.$$

In particular, writing formula (14.192) in polar coordinates we obtain that

$$(14.195) \quad \|\tau_h v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega')}^p \leq C_{n,p} \frac{|h|^p}{\rho^{n+p}} \int_0^\rho g_v(t) \, dt.$$

We multiply both sides of (14.195) by ρ^{p-sp-1} and integrate in the interval $[0, |h|]$. In this way, we find that

$$\|\tau_h v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega')}^p \leq p(1-s)C_{n,p} \int_0^{|h|} \frac{|h|^{sp}}{\rho^{n+sp+1}} \int_0^\rho g_v(t) dt d\rho$$

Then, applying Lemma 2.5 in [Cri+23], we arrive at

$$\|\tau_h v - v\|_{L^p(\Omega')}^p \leq p(1-s)C_{n,p} |h|^{sp} \int_0^{|h|} \frac{g_v(t)}{t^{n+sp}} dt.$$

Recalling the definition of g_v , the desired result plainly follows. \square

In the proof of Theorem 14.9 we will also make use of the following binomial Theorem.

Proposition 14.23 (Newton's generalized binomial Theorem). *Let $a > b > 0$ and $p \in (1, +\infty)$. Then, we have that*

$$(14.196) \quad (a-b)^p = \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \binom{p}{k} a^{p-k} (-b)^k.$$

PART IV

FRACTIONAL MALMHEDEN THEOREM

INTRODUCTION TO PART IV

In this part we prove a geometrical algorithm to write explicitly s -harmonic maps in the open ball B knowing their value on the boundary ∂B . This result can be considered as the nonlocal counterpart of the classical Malmheden Theorem.

15.1 Classical Malmheden Theorem

In 1934, Harry William Malmheden [Mal34] proved an algorithm to compute the value of a harmonic function at a point of B_1 , knowing its value on ∂B_1 .

To state the Malmheden Theorem precisely we need to introduce the following notation.

First, given a function $f : K \subset \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, two distinct points $a, b \in K$, and a point x on the segment L joining a and b , we denote by $\mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(x)$ the affine function on L such that $\mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(a) = f(a)$ and $\mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(b) = f(b)$, see equation (16.1) in Chapter 16 for an explicit expression.

Moreover, for any given a point $x \in B_1$ and a direction $e \in \partial B_1$ we consider the intersections $Q_+^x(e)$ and $Q_-^x(e)$ of ∂B_1 with the straight line passing through $x \in B_1$ with direction e , with the convention that $Q_+^x(e) - Q_-^x(e)$ has the same orientation of e , see Figure 15.1. Also, for an explicit analytical expression for $Q_\pm^x(e)$ see equation (16.2) in Chapter 16.

Then, with this notation, the statement of the Malmheden Theorem is the following:

Figure 15.1: The projections $Q_{\pm}^x(e)$ used in the Malmheden Theorem.

Theorem 15.1 ([Mal34]). *Let $n \geq 2$ and $f : \partial B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous. Then*

$$u_f(x) := \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_f^{Q_-^x(e), Q_+^x(e)}(x) dH_e^{n-1}$$

is the harmonic function in B_1 with boundary datum f .

We observe that Theorem 15.1 contains the Mean Value Theorem for harmonic functions as a special case, as it can be easily checked by taking $x = 0$ in (15.1), see equation (16.7) in Chapter 16.

Moreover, from Theorem 15.1 it is possible to deduce directly Schwarz Theorem (Theorem 16.2 in Chapter 16), see e.g. [DV24] for a presentation of this argument.

Finally, we conclude by observing that such an elegant result is specific for balls and cannot be extended in general to other domains, as pointed out in [AKS10].

15.2 Fractional Malmheden Theorem

In Chapter 16 we provide a fractional counterpart of Theorem 15.1. More precisely, we consider the problem

$$(15.1) \quad \begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u = f & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \end{cases}$$

where $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ for some $R > 1$ and

$$L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) := \left\{ f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ measurable} : \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|f(x)|}{|x|^{n+2s}} dx < \infty \right\}.$$

Then, we aim at building a geometrical algorithm, in the spirit of the classical Malmheden Theorem, to determine the unique solution to (15.1).

In order to account for the nonlocality of the problem, we need to introduce the following tools.

First, given $\rho > 0$ and $f \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, then for all $x \in \partial B_1$ we set $f_\rho(x) := f(\rho x)$ and also

$$\mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) := \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho}^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right).$$

Moreover, to detect the long-range effect of the fractional Laplacian, it is also useful to consider the kernel

$$(15.2) \quad B_1 \times (1, +\infty) \ni (x, \rho) \longmapsto \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) := c(n, s) \frac{\rho(1 - |x|^2)^s}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s (\rho^2 - |x|^2)},$$

where $c(n, s)$ is the constant in (16.14).

Then, the the main result of Chapter 16 is the following representation formula for fractional harmonic maps:

Theorem 15.2 (Theorem 16.4 in Chapter 16, Fractional Malmheden Theorem). *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$.*

Then, the unique solution (up to a zero measure subset of $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$) to the problem in (15.1), can be written, for each $x \in B_1$, as

$$u_f^{(s)}(x) := \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

We notice that Theorem 15.2 can be regarded as the natural fractional counterpart of Theorem 15.1. Indeed, one can “recover” Theorem 15.1 in the limit as $s \nearrow 1$, according to the following proposition:

Proposition 15.3 (Proposition in Chapter 16). *Let $n \geq 2$, $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in C(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ for each $s \in (s_0, 1]$. Then, for each $x \in B_1$, it holds that*

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} u_f^{(s)}(x) = u_f(x),$$

where $u_f^{(s)}$ and u_f are defined in (16.17) and (16.6), respectively.

Moreover, analogously to the classical case, we point out that Theorem 16.4 entails as a straightforward consequence the Mean Value Formula for s -harmonics functions, see equation (16.18) in Chapter 16.

Furthermore, from the classical Malmheden Theorem (Theorem 15.1) and its fractional formulation (Theorem 15.2) we deduce the following result:

Theorem 15.4 (Theorem 16.6 in Chapter 16, an s -harmonic function is the superposition of classical harmonic functions). *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$. For each $\rho > 1$ we define u_{f_ρ} as the unique solution to the Dirichlet problem*

$$\begin{cases} \Delta u = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u|_{\partial B_1} = f_\rho|_{\partial B_1}. \end{cases}$$

Then, the unique solution $u_f^{(s)}$ to (16.16) can be written as

$$u_f^{(s)}(x) = |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho.$$

The interest of Theorem 15.4 is that it allows us to write an s -harmonic function in B_1 as a weighted integral of classical harmonic functions, where the weight coincide with $\mathcal{E}(x, \rho)$. Besides being interesting in itself, this result is very useful to deduce properties of s -harmonic functions, as the Harnack inequality, starting from their local counterpart.

As a matter of fact, as a consequence of Theorem 16.6 one obtains a new proof of the Harnack inequality for s -harmonic functions in B_1 . The result goes as follows:

Theorem 15.5 (Theorem 16.7 in Chapter 16, Harnack inequality). *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and u be non negative, s -harmonic in B_1 and such that $u \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$.*

Then, for each $r \in (0, 1)$ and $x \in B_r$,

$$\frac{(1-r^2)^s}{(1+r)^n} u(0) \leq u(x) \leq \frac{(1-r^2)^s}{(1-r)^n} u(0).$$

The constants in (16.21) are optimal, and for $s \nearrow 1$ they converge to the optimal constants of the classical Harnack inequality in B_r for harmonic functions in B_1 .

For different proofs of the fractional Harnack inequality see [Km01; CS07; Kas11] and the references therein.

To conclude, we also mention that analogously to the classical Malmheden Theorem, the its fractional formulation contains as a special case the Fractional Schwarz Theorem, see Theorem 16.8 in Chapter 16.

THE FRACTIONAL MALMHEDEN THEOREM

We provide a fractional counterpart of the classical results by Schwarz and Malmheden on harmonic functions. From that we obtain a representation formula for s -harmonic functions as a linear superposition of weighted classical harmonic functions which also entails a new proof of the fractional Harnack inequality. This proof also leads to optimal constants for the fractional Harnack inequality in the ball.

16.1 Introduction

In 1934, Harry William Malmheden [Mal34] proved a simple algorithm to compute the value of a harmonic function at a point of B_1 , knowing its value on the boundary.

The Malmheden Theorem makes use of two fundamental geometric ingredients:

1. the notion of affine interpolation between the values of a given function at two different points of the space,
2. the projections of a point inside a ball to the boundary in a given direction.

Hence, to state the Malmheden Theorem explicitly, we now formalize these two notions into a precise mathematical setting. We start by introducing a notation for the affine interpolation between the values of some given function. That is, given a set $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, a function $f : K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, two distinct points $a, b \in K$, and a point x

on the segment L joining a and b , we define $\mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(x)$ as the affine function on L such that $\mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(a) = f(a)$ and $\mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(b) = f(b)$.

Of course, one can write this affine function explicitly by using the analytic expression

$$(16.1) \quad \mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(x) = \frac{(x-a) \cdot e}{|b-a|} f(b) + \frac{(b-x) \cdot e}{|b-a|} f(a), \quad \text{where } e := \frac{b-a}{|b-a|}.$$

One can call $\mathcal{L}_f^{a,b}(x)$ the “affine function of f with extrema a and b evaluated at the point x ”.

Figure 16.1: The projections $Q_{\pm}^x(e)$ used in the Malmheden Theorem.

Now we discuss the notation regarding the projections of a point inside a ball to the boundary of the ball in a given direction. For this, given a point $x \in B_1$ and a direction $e \in \partial B_1$ we consider the intersections $Q_+^x(e)$ and $Q_-^x(e)$ of ∂B_1 with the straight line passing through $x \in B_1$ with direction e , with the convention that $Q_+^x(e) - Q_-^x(e)$ has the same orientation of e , see Figure 16.1.

Clearly, from the analytic point of view, one can write explicitly these projections in the form

$$(16.2) \quad \begin{aligned} Q_+^x(e) &:= x + r_+^x(e)e \\ \text{and} \quad Q_-^x(e) &:= x + r_-^x(e)e, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(16.3) \quad \begin{aligned} r_+^x(e) &= -x \cdot e + \sqrt{(x \cdot e)^2 - |x|^2 + 1} \\ \text{and} \quad r_-^x(e) &= -x \cdot e - \sqrt{(x \cdot e)^2 - |x|^2 + 1}. \end{aligned}$$

We note from equations (16.2) and (16.3) that $Q_{\pm}^x(e)$ are continuous functions in $(x, e) \in B_1 \times \partial B_1$. Moreover,

$$(16.4) \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} Q_{\pm}^x(e) = \pm e$$

for each $e \in \partial B_1$. This tells us that the maps Q_{\pm}^x simply reduce to $\pm id_{\partial B_1}$ when $x = 0$.

Given a boundary datum $f : \partial B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the core of the Malmheden Theorem is thus to consider, for every point $x \in B_1$ and every direction $e \in \partial B_1$, the affine function of f with extrema $Q_-^x(e)$ and $Q_+^x(e)$, namely the function

$$(16.5) \quad \mathcal{L}_f^{Q_-^x(e), Q_+^x(e)}(x)$$

and then to average in all directions e .

The remarkable result by Malmheden is that this averaging procedure of linear interpolations produces precisely the solution of the classical Dirichlet problem in B_1 with boundary datum f , according to the following classical statement (see [Mal34]):

Theorem 16.1 (Malmheden Theorem). *Let $n \geq 2$ and $f : \partial B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous. Then*

$$(16.6) \quad u_f(x) := \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_f^{Q_-^x(e), Q_+^x(e)}(x) dH_e^{n-1}$$

is the harmonic function in B_1 with boundary datum f .

As usual, here above and in the rest of this chapter, we denoted by H^{n-1} the $(n-1)$ -Hausdorff measure (hence, the integral on the right hand side of (16.6) is simply the spherical integral along ∂B_1 ; we kept the explicit notation with the Hausdorff measure to have a typographical evidence of the surface integrals, to be distinguished by the classical volume ones).

We remark that Theorem 16.1 contains the Mean Value Theorem for harmonic functions as a particular case: indeed, in light of (16.1) and (16.4), if we take $x := 0$ then (16.6) reduces to

$$(16.7) \quad u_f(0) = \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_f^{-e, e}(0) dH_e^{n-1} = \int_{\partial B_1} \left(\frac{f(e)}{2} + \frac{f(-e)}{2} \right) dH_e^{n-1} = \int_{\partial B_1} f(e) dH_e^{n-1},$$

which is the content of the Mean Value Theorem.

We also stress that an elegant result such as Theorem 16.1 is specific for balls and cannot be extended in general to other domains, as pointed out in [AKS10].

Interestingly, Theorem 16.1 contains as a particular case a classical result due to Hermann Amandus Schwarz [Sch72] about the Dirichlet problem in the plane and related to conformal mappings in the complex framework.

Figure 16.2: The reflection $Q^x(\omega)$ used in the Schwarz Theorem.

To state Schwarz result it is convenient to introduce the reflection of a point $\omega \in \partial B_1$ through a point $x \in B_1$, see Figure 16.2. More precisely, given $x \in B_1$ and $\omega \in \partial B_1$ we define

$$(16.8) \quad Q^x(\omega) := \omega - 2 \frac{(x - \omega) \cdot \omega}{|x - \omega|^2} (x - \omega).$$

Comparing with (16.2), one sees that if $e := \frac{\omega - x}{|\omega - x|}$ then $Q_+^x(e) = \omega$ and $Q_-^x(e) = Q^x(\omega)$.

In this setting, the result by Schwarz is that the average of the boundary datum composed with the above reflection returns the solution of the Dirichlet problem in the ball. More explicitly:

Theorem 16.2 (Schwarz Theorem). *Let $n = 2$ and $f : \partial B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous. Then*

$$(16.9) \quad u_f(x) := \int_{\partial B_1} f(Q^x(e)) dH_e^{n-1}$$

is the harmonic function in B_1 with external datum f .

Theorem 16.2 can be proved in several ways using either complex or real analysis (see e.g. [Neu84; Duf57; Nee94]), but it is also a direct consequence of Theorem 16.1, see e.g. [DV24] for a detailed presentation of this classical argument.

Example 16.3. A very neat application of Theorem 16.2 (see e.g. [Nee97]) consists in the determination of the stationary temperature u at a point x in a plate (say B_1) when the temperature along the boundary of the plate is 1 along some arc Σ and 0 outside. In this case, the reflection in (16.8) sends Σ into an arc Σ' (the symmetric of Σ through x , see Figure 16.3) and it therefore follows from Theorem 16.2 that

$$u(x) = \frac{|\Sigma'|}{2\pi},$$

where $|\Sigma'|$ is the length of the arc Σ' , thus providing an elementary geometric construction to solve a problem of physical relevance.

Figure 16.3: The geometric construction to detect the temperature of a plate at the point x .

The objective of this chapter is to obtain a fractional counterpart for the Malmheden and Schwarz Theorems.

We will thus replace the notion of harmonic functions in B_1 with that of s -harmonic functions, namely functions whose fractional Laplacian vanishes in B_1 , that is, for all $x \in B_1$,

$$(16.10) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{u(x) - u(y)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy = 0,$$

where the integral above is intended in the principal value sense. Here above and throughout the chapter the fractional parameter $s \in (0, 1)$.

Rather than a boundary value along ∂B_1 , as usual in the nonlocal setting, we complement (16.10) with an external condition of the type $u = f$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$.

We recall that in general s -harmonic functions behave way more wildly than their classical counterparts, see e.g. [DSV17]. Therefore, in principle one cannot easily expect that a “simple formulation” such as the one in Theorems 16.1 and 16.2 accounts for all the complex situations arising in the fractional setting.

However, we will prove that a counterpart of Theorems 16.1 and 16.2 carries over to the case of the fractional Laplacian, considering the following structural modifications:

1. the classical spherical averages are replaced by suitable weighted averages on spheres of radius larger than 1,
2. the geometric transformations in (16.2) and (16.8) are scaled in dependence of the radius of each of these spheres.

To clarify these points, and thus reconsider (16.5) in a nonlocal setting, given $\rho > 1$ and $f : \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, for all $x \in \partial B_1$ we define

$$(16.11) \quad f_\rho(x) := f(\rho x).$$

Hence, in the notation of (16.1), we define

$$(16.12) \quad \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) := \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho}^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right).$$

Notice that when $\rho = 1$ the above setting reduces to (16.5), otherwise one is considering here a similar framework but for a rescaled version of the function f and rescaled points.

To detect the long-range effect of the fractional Laplacian, it is also useful to consider the kernel

$$(16.13) \quad B_1 \times (1, +\infty) \ni (x, \rho) \mapsto \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) := c(n, s) \frac{\rho(1 - |x|^2)^s}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s (\rho^2 - |x|^2)},$$

where

$$(16.14) \quad c(n, s) := \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) \sin(\pi s)}{\pi^{\frac{n}{2}+1}}.$$

For our purposes, the kernel \mathcal{E} will play the role of a suitable spherical average¹ of a Fractional Poisson Kernel and the constant $c(n, s)$ is merely needed for normalization purposes.

We also define the space

$$(16.15) \quad L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) := \left\{ f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ measurable} : \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|f(x)|}{|x|^{n+2s}} dx < \infty \right\}.$$

With this, we can state the main result of this chapter as follows:

Theorem 16.4 (Fractional Malmheden Theorem). *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$.*

Then, the unique solution (up to a zero measure subset of $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$) to the problem

$$(16.16) \quad \begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u = f & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \end{cases}$$

can be written, for each $x \in B_1$, as

$$(16.17) \quad u_f^{(s)}(x) := \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f, e, \rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

As a fractional counterpart of the observation in (16.7), we point out that Theorem 16.4 entails as a straightforward consequence the Mean Value Formula for s -

¹More precisely, the intuition behind \mathcal{E} is that it satisfies, for each $x \in B_1$ and $\rho \in (1, +\infty)$,

$$\mathcal{E}(x, \rho) = \rho^{n-1} \int_{\partial B_\rho} P(x, y) dH_y^{n-1},$$

where P is the Fractional Poisson Kernel.

This relation can be obtained as a consequence of our Fractional Malmheden Theorem. Though our approach does not pass explicitly through this identity, for the sake of completeness we provide an independent proof in Appendix 16.5.

harmonics functions. Indeed, by the changes of variable $e := \omega/|\omega|$ and $y := \rho\omega/|\omega|$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_f^{(s)}(0) &= \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(0, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f, e, \rho}(0) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 &= c(n, s) \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{1}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho}^{-e, e}(0) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 &= c(n, s) \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{1}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\frac{f(\rho e)}{2} + \frac{f(-\rho e)}{2} \right) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 (16.18) \quad &= c(n, s) \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_\rho} \frac{1}{\rho^n(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\frac{f(\omega)}{2} + \frac{f(-\omega)}{2} \right) dH_\omega^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 &= c(n, s) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{1}{|y|^n(|y|^2 - 1)^s} \left(\frac{f(y)}{2} + \frac{f(-y)}{2} \right) dy \\
 &= c(n, s) \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{f(y)}{|y|^n(|y|^2 - 1)^s} dy,
 \end{aligned}$$

which is the Mean Value Formula for s -harmonic functions, see e.g. formula (1.3) in [BDV20].

We consider Theorem 16.4 as the natural fractional counterpart of Theorem 16.1 and we mention that indeed one can “recover” Theorem 16.1 in the limit as $s \nearrow 1$, according to the following result:

Proposition 16.5. *Let $n \geq 2$, $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in C(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ for each $s \in (s_0, 1]$. Then, for each $x \in B_1$, it holds that*

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} u_f^{(s)}(x) = u_f(x),$$

where $u_f^{(s)}$ and u_f are defined in (16.17) and (16.6), respectively.

As a straightforward consequence of the classical Malmheden Theorem (Theorem 16.1) and its fractional formulation Theorem (Theorem 16.4), we deduce the following result.

Theorem 16.6 (An s -harmonic function is the superposition of classical harmonic functions). *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$. For each $\rho > 1$ we define u_{f_ρ} as the unique solution to the Dirichlet problem*

$$(16.19) \quad \begin{cases} \Delta u = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u|_{\partial B_1} = f_\rho|_{\partial B_1}, \end{cases}$$

where f_ρ is defined in (16.11).

Then the unique solution $u_f^{(s)}$ to (16.16) can be written as

$$(16.20) \quad u_f^{(s)}(x) = |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho.$$

The interest of Theorem 16.6 is that it allows us to write an s -harmonic function in B_1 as a weighted integral of classical harmonic functions, where the weight coincide with $\mathcal{E}(x, \rho)$. Besides being interesting in itself, this result is very useful to deduce properties of s -harmonic functions, as the Harnack inequality (see Section 16.4), starting from their local counterpart.

As a matter of fact, as a consequence of Theorem 16.6 one obtains a new proof of the Harnack inequality for s -harmonic functions in B_1 . The result goes as follows:

Theorem 16.7 (Harnack inequality). *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and u be non negative, s -harmonic in B_1 and such that $u \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$.*

Then, for each $r \in (0, 1)$ and $x \in B_r$,

$$(16.21) \quad \frac{(1-r^2)^s}{(1+r)^n} u(0) \leq u(x) \leq \frac{(1-r^2)^s}{(1-r)^n} u(0).$$

The constants in (16.21) are optimal, and for $s \nearrow 1$ they converge to the optimal constants of the classical Harnack inequality in B_r for harmonic functions in B_1 .

For different proofs of the fractional Harnack inequality see [Km01; CS07; Kas11] and the references therein.

Another consequence of Theorem 16.4 is the fractional version of Schwarz result:

Theorem 16.8 (Fractional Schwarz Theorem). *Let $n = 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1)$. Then, the unique solution (up to a zero measure subset of $\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1$) to the problem*

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u = f & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1 \end{cases}$$

can be written, for each $x \in B_1$, as

$$(16.22) \quad u_f^{(s)}(x) := \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) f_\rho(Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^1 \right) d\rho.$$

This is a fractional counterpart of Theorem 16.2, in the sense of Proposition 16.9 below. Proposition 16.9 is a straightforward consequence of Theorems 16.2 and 16.8 and Proposition 16.5.

Proposition 16.9. *Let $n = 2$, $s_0 \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in C(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1)$ for each $s \in (s_0, 1]$. Then, for each $x \in B_1$, it holds that*

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} u_f^{(s)}(x) = u_f(x)$$

where $u_f^{(s)}$, u_f are defined in (16.22) and (16.9), respectively.

Remark 16.10. It is worth pointing out that from Theorem 16.4 we can evince the identity

$$(16.23) \quad \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) d\rho = \frac{1}{|\partial B_1|},$$

for each $x \in B_1$. Indeed, if we consider as external data $f = 1$ in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$, then the unique solution to the problem (16.16) is $u = 1$ in \mathbb{R}^n . Therefore, according to (16.17) and the fact that in this case the linear interpolation $\mathcal{L}_{1,e,\rho}(x) = 1$ for each $x \in B_1$, we obtain that

$$1 = \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{1,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho = \int_1^\infty |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) d\rho,$$

which gives (16.23).

As an application of Theorem 16.8, we have:

Example 16.11. Let $n = 2$ and take an arc $\Sigma \subset \partial B_1$. Consider the function defined on $\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1$ as

$$(16.24) \quad \tilde{\chi}_\Sigma(y) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \frac{y}{|y|} \in \Sigma, \\ 0 & \text{if } \frac{y}{|y|} \in \partial B_1 \setminus \Sigma. \end{cases}$$

It is clear that $\tilde{\chi}_\Sigma$ is positively homogeneous of degree zero, and furthermore $\tilde{\chi}_\Sigma \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1) \subset L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1)$. Then by Theorem 16.8 we get that for each $x \in B_1$

$$(16.25) \quad u_{\tilde{\chi}_\Sigma}^{(s)}(x) = \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) |\Sigma'_{x/\rho}| d\rho$$

where $\Sigma'_{x/\rho}$ is the projected arc of Σ on ∂B_1 through the focal point x/ρ , as constructed in Example 16.3. We denoted with $|\Sigma'_{x/\rho}|$ its length.

This gives a simple geometrical procedure to compute the solution of

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u = \tilde{\chi}_\Sigma & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1 \end{cases}$$

at a point x of the two dimensional disc when the non local boundary condition is given by (16.24). Note that as ρ is getting larger, the measure of $\Sigma'_{x/\rho}$ reaches the one of Σ , or more precisely

$$\lim_{\rho \rightarrow \infty} |\Sigma'_{x/\rho}| = |\Sigma|.$$

If $x = 0$, formula (16.25) boils down to

$$(16.26) \quad u_{\tilde{\chi}_\Sigma}^{(s)}(0) = c(n, s)|\Sigma| \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} d\rho = \frac{|\Sigma|}{2\pi},$$

where we have applied identity (16.23). This example can be seen as the fractional counterpart of Example 16.3.

This chapter is organized as follows. In Section 16.2 we give some preliminary results on the s -harmonic function written as a convolution with the Fractional Poisson Kernel.

Section 16.3 is devoted to the proofs of the fractional Malmheden and Schwarz results, that is Theorems 16.4 and 16.8, and of the convergence result in Proposition 16.5.

In Section 16.4 we use these results to provide a proof of the well-known Harnack inequality for s -harmonic functions under some regularity assumptions on the external datum $f : \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, that is we prove Theorem 16.7.

16.2 Preliminary results on the Fractional Poisson Kernel

In this section, we revisit the well-established result according to which fractional harmonic functions can be represented as an integral of the datum outside the

domain against a suitable Poisson Kernel. For completeness, we extend this result to the case in which the datum is not necessarily continuous, so to be able to present the results of this chapter in a suitable generality. Notice that the extension to functions that are not necessarily continuous is also useful for us to comprise situations as in Example 16.11.

The framework that we consider is the following. For $n \geq 2$ and $s \in (0, 1)$, we consider the space $L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ as defined in (16.15). Given $f \in L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$, we denote the norm on $L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ by

$$\|f\|_{L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)} := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|f(x)|}{|x|^{n+2s}} dx.$$

Furthermore, we define the following *Fractional Poisson Kernel* in the unit ball

$$(16.27) \quad P(x, y) := c(n, s) \left(\frac{1 - |x|^2}{|y|^2 - 1} \right)^s \frac{1}{|x - y|^n}$$

for $x \in B_1$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$, and $c(n, s)$ is the normalizing constant in (16.14).

As customary, the role of the constant $c(n, s)$ is to normalize the Poisson Kernel, namely we have that

$$(16.28) \quad \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} P(x, y) dy = 1,$$

see e.g. formula (1.14) and Lemma A.5 in [Buc16].

We also remark that

$$P(\cdot, y) \in C^\infty(B_1)$$

and, for every $\rho \in (0, 1)$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}^n$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$,

$$(16.29) \quad \sup_{x \in B_\rho} |D_x^\alpha P(x, y)| \leq \frac{C_\rho}{(|y| - 1)^s |y|^{n+s+|\alpha|}},$$

where $C_\rho > 0$ depends only on ρ , n and s and, as usual, we have denoted the length of the multi-index α as $|\alpha| := \alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_n$.

Then, we define

$$(16.30) \quad u_f^{(s)}(x) := \begin{cases} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} P(x, y) f(y) dy & \text{if } x \in B_1, \\ f(x) & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1, \end{cases}$$

and we have the following result on the representation of s -harmonic functions:

Theorem 16.12. *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$ and $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$. Then the function in (16.30) is the unique pointwise continuous solution to the problem*

$$(16.31) \quad \begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u_f^{(s)} = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u_f^{(s)} = f & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1. \end{cases}$$

For a proof of Theorem 16.12 see e.g. Theorem 2.10 in [Buc16].

We now generalize Theorem 16.12 by allowing external data that are not necessarily continuous:

Proposition 16.13. *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$. Then the function defined in (16.30) is the unique solution (up to a zero measure subset of $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$) to the problem in (16.31).*

Proof. We argue by approximation, owing to Theorem 16.12. The gist is indeed to take a sequence of continuous functions f_k approaching f as $k \rightarrow +\infty$, use Theorem 16.12 and then pass to the limit. To implement this idea, one needs to take care of some regularity issues.

The details of this technical argument go as follows. By (16.29), for each $x \in B_1$ and multi-index α we have that

$$D_x^\alpha P(x, \cdot) f(\cdot) \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus \overline{B_1}).$$

As a consequence, we obtain that $u_f^{(s)}(x)$ in (16.30) is well defined and smooth inside B_1 .

To complete the proof of Proposition 16.13, we need to show that $u_f^{(s)}$, as defined in (16.30), is the unique solution of (16.31). To do so, we start by checking that $u_f^{(s)}$ is s -harmonic in B_1 . We consider a sequence $\{f_k\}_k \subset C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$, such that

$$(16.32) \quad f_k \rightarrow f \text{ in } L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \text{ as } k \rightarrow +\infty.$$

More specifically, we take $f_k := (\chi_{B_k} \tilde{f}) * \eta_{\frac{1}{k}}$ with $k \geq 2$, where \tilde{f} is defined as

$$\tilde{f}(x) := \begin{cases} f(x) & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \in B_1, \end{cases}$$

and $\eta_{\frac{1}{k}}$ is a mollifier of radius $\frac{1}{k}$, while χ_{B_k} is the characteristic function of B_k . We also let $u_{f_k}^{(s)}$ be the unique pointwise continuous solution to the problem (16.31), according to Theorem 16.12.

Then we have that for each multi-index α

$$(16.33) \quad \|D^\alpha u_{f_k}^{(s)} - D^\alpha u_f^{(s)}\|_{L^\infty_{\text{loc}}(B_1)} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Indeed for each multi-index α and $g \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ one finds that

$$D^\alpha u_g(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} D_x^\alpha P(x, y) g(y) dy$$

for each $x \in B_1$, and therefore, choosing $R_0 \in (1, R)$, we see that, for every $x \in B'$ with $B' \Subset B_1$,

$$(16.34) \quad \begin{aligned} & |D^\alpha u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - D^\alpha u_f^{(s)}(x)| \\ & \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} |D_x^\alpha P(x, y)| |f_k(y) - f(y)| dy + \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} |D_x^\alpha P(x, y)| |f_k(y) - f(y)| dy \\ & \leq c \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{|f_k(y) - f(y)|}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy + \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} |D_x^\alpha P(x, y)| |f_k(y) - f(y)| dy, \end{aligned}$$

where c is a positive constant depending on α , R_0 , n , s and B' . The first term in the third line in (16.34) converges to zero as $k \rightarrow +\infty$, thanks to (16.32). We also observe that, if $y \in B_{R_0} \setminus B_1$, then $|f_k(y) - f(y)| \leq 2\|f\|_{L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1)}$, and therefore, by the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we have that also the second term in the third line in (16.34) converges to zero as $k \rightarrow +\infty$. These considerations prove (16.33).

Furthermore note that if $\alpha = 0$, taking $R_0 \in (1, R)$ and using also (16.28), we have that, for all $x \in B_1$,

$$(16.35) \quad \begin{aligned} |u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x)| & \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} |P(x, y)| |f_k(y)| dy + \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} |P(x, y)| |f_k(y)| dy \\ & \leq C \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{|f_k(y)|}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy + \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} |P(x, y)| |f_k(y)| dy \\ & \leq C \|f_k\|_{L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)} + \|f\|_{L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1)}, \end{aligned}$$

where C is a positive constant depending on R_0 , n and s . Now, we observe that the sequence $\|f_k\|_{L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)}$ is uniformly bounded, thanks to (16.32). Accordingly,

from (16.35) we see that

$$(16.36) \quad u_{f_k}^{(s)} \text{ is uniformly bounded in } B_1.$$

Now, if $x \in B_1$, taking $\delta \in (0, 1 - |x|)$, we have that

$$(16.37) \quad \begin{aligned} (-\Delta)^s u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - (-\Delta)^s u_f^{(s)}(x) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - u_{f_k}^{(s)}(y) - u_f^{(s)}(x) + u_f^{(s)}(y)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy \\ &= A + B + C + D + E + F, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A &:= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - u_f^{(s)}(x)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy, & B &:= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{u_{f_k}^{(s)}(y) - u_f^{(s)}(y)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy, \\ C &:= \int_{B_\delta(x)} \frac{u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - u_{f_k}^{(s)}(y)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy, & D &:= \int_{B_\delta(x)} \frac{u_f^{(s)}(y) - u_f^{(s)}(x)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy, \\ E &:= \int_{B_1 \setminus B_\delta(x)} \frac{u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - u_f^{(s)}(x)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy \quad \text{and} & F &:= \int_{B_1 \setminus B_\delta(x)} \frac{u_f^{(s)}(y) - u_{f_k}^{(s)}(y)}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} |A + E| &\leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\delta(x)} \frac{|u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - u_f^{(s)}(x)|}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy \leq |u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - u_f^{(s)}(x)| \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\delta} \frac{dz}{|z|^{n+2s}} \\ &\leq \frac{C}{\delta^{2s}} |u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) - u_f^{(s)}(x)|, \end{aligned}$$

which converges to zero as $k \rightarrow +\infty$, thanks to (16.33).

Furthermore, we observe that if $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$ then

$$|x - y| \geq |y| - |x| = \delta|y| + (1 - \delta)|y| - |x| \geq \delta|y| + 1 - \delta - |x| \geq \delta|y|,$$

and thus

$$|B| \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|f_k(y) - f(y)|}{|x - y|^{n+2s}} dy \leq \frac{1}{\delta^{n+2s}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|f_k(y) - f(y)|}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy$$

which, in light of (16.32), converges to zero as $k \rightarrow +\infty$.

Moreover, from (16.33) and the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we see that the quantity $C + D$ converges to zero as $k \rightarrow +\infty$.

Finally, recalling (16.36) and making again use of the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we have that F converges to zero as $k \rightarrow +\infty$.

These considerations and (16.37) give that $(-\Delta)^s u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x)$ converges to $(-\Delta)^s u_f^{(s)}(x)$ as $k \rightarrow +\infty$ for every $x \in B_1$. Since, by Theorem 16.12, we know that $(-\Delta)^s u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) = 0$ for each $x \in B_1$, we conclude that $(-\Delta)^s u_f^{(s)}(x) = 0$. This proves that $u_f^{(s)}$ solves (16.31).

It is only left to show the uniqueness statement. Suppose that there exists $u_1 : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u_1 = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u_1 = f & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1. \end{cases}$$

Then both $v := u_f^{(s)} - u_1$ and $-v = u_1 - u_f^{(s)}$ are solutions to

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = 0 & \text{in } B_1, \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1, \end{cases}$$

and therefore by the maximum principle for the fractional Laplacian (see e.g. Theorem 2.3.2. in [BV16]) we have that $v = 0$ in B_1 , leading to uniqueness. \square

16.3 Proof of the Fractional Malmheden and Schwarz Theorems

In this section we provide the proofs of the Fractional Malmheden and Schwarz results, as stated in Theorems 16.4 and 16.8, and of the convergence result in Proposition 16.5.

We start with the main argument to prove Theorem 16.4. For this, we employ the following change of variable result (see Lemma 2.13.3 in [DV24] for the proof of it):

Lemma 16.14. *Let $n \geq 2$, $x \in B_1$ and Q_{\pm}^x and r_{\pm}^x be defined as in (16.2) and (16.3), respectively. Then for each $e \in \partial B_1$ it holds that*

$$|\det DQ_{\pm}^x(e)| = \frac{(\pm r_{\pm}^x(e))^n}{1 - |x|^2 - r_{\pm}^x(e)x \cdot e},$$

and for each continuous $f : \partial B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we have that

$$\int_{\partial B_1} f(e) dH_e^{n-1} = \int_{\partial B_1} f(Q_{\pm}^x(e)) \frac{(\pm r_{\pm}^x(e))^n}{1 - |x|^2 - r_{\pm}^x(e)x \cdot e} dH_e^{n-1}.$$

With this notation, Theorem 16.4 will be a consequence of the following statement.

Theorem 16.15. *Let $n \geq 2$, $s \in (0, 1)$, $R > 1$ and $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$. Let $u_f^{(s)}$ be as in (16.30).*

Then, for each $x \in B_1$,

$$(16.38) \quad u_f^{(s)}(x) = \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho,$$

where the notation in (16.12) and (16.13) has been used.

Furthermore, if f is positively homogeneous of degree γ for some $\gamma \geq 0$, then we have that

$$(16.39) \quad u_f^{(s)}(x) = \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \rho^\gamma \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f,e,1} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

Proof. We first suppose that $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$. Let $x \in B_1$, then, using polar coordinates, from (16.27) and (16.30) we get that

$$\begin{aligned} (16.40) \quad & u_f^{(s)}(x) \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} P(x, y) f(y) dy \\ &= c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{1}{(|y|^2 - 1)^s} \frac{f(y)}{|x - y|^n} dy \\ &= c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_\rho} \frac{f(\omega)}{|x - \omega|^n} dH_\omega^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho^{n-1}}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{f(\rho e)}{|x - \rho e|^n} dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{f(\rho e)}{\left| \frac{x}{\rho} - e \right|^n} dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{f(\rho e)}{\left| \frac{x}{\rho} - e \right|^n} \left(1 - \frac{|x|^2}{\rho^2} \right) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &=: \mathcal{I}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, defining

$$g(e) := \frac{f(\rho e)}{\left|\frac{x}{\rho} - e\right|^n} \left(1 - \frac{|x|^2}{\rho^2}\right)$$

and applying Lemma 16.14 we obtain that

$$(16.41) \quad \begin{aligned} & \frac{\mathcal{I}}{c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s} \\ &= \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} g(e) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} g(Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) \frac{(-r_-^{x/\rho}(e))^n}{1 - |x/\rho|^2 - (x/\rho \cdot e)r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e))}{\left|\frac{x}{\rho} - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)\right|^n} \frac{(1 - |x/\rho|^2)(-r_-^{x/\rho}(e))^n}{1 - |x/\rho|^2 - (x/\rho \cdot e)r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho. \end{aligned}$$

From equations (16.2) and (16.3) we deduce that

$$\left| \frac{x}{\rho} - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e) \right| = |r_-^{x/\rho}(e)| = -r_-^{x/\rho}(e),$$

and also (see formula (2.13.25) in [DV24])

$$\frac{1 - |x/\rho|^2}{1 - |x/\rho|^2 - (x/\rho \cdot e)r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} = \frac{2r_+^{x/\rho}(e)}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)}$$

which, together with (16.41), gives that

$$(16.42) \quad \mathcal{I} = c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{2r_+^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e))}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

We now observe that

$$(16.43) \quad \begin{aligned} & \int_{\partial B_1} \frac{2r_+^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e))}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1} \\ &= \int_{\partial B_1} \frac{r_+^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e))}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1} - \int_{\partial B_1} \frac{r_-^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_+^{x/\rho}(e))}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1} \\ &= \int_{\partial B_1} \frac{r_+^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_+^{x/\rho}(e))}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

From (16.2), (16.3), (16.11) and (16.12) we also deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{r_+^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_+^{x/\rho}(e))}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} \\
 = & \frac{r_+^{x/\rho}(e)f_\rho(Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)f_\rho(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e))}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} \\
 = & \frac{\left(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - \frac{x}{\rho}\right) \cdot e f_\rho(Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) + \left(\frac{x}{\rho} - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)\right) \cdot e f_\rho(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e))}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} \\
 = & \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho}^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) \\
 = & \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x).
 \end{aligned}$$

Plugging this information into (16.43) we find that

$$\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{2r_+^{x/\rho}(e)f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e))}{r_+^{x/\rho}(e) - r_-^{x/\rho}(e)} dH_e^{n-1} = \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1},$$

which in turn, together with (16.42), gives that

$$\mathcal{I} = c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

Thus, recalling (16.13), this and (16.40) establish the desired result in (16.38) under the additional assumption that f is continuous in $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$.

Now we remove the continuity assumption on f by an approximation argument. Given $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$, we consider a sequence of functions $\{f_k\}_k \subset C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ as in (16.32) and we let $u_{f_k}^{(s)}$ be the unique pointwise continuous solution to the problem (16.31), according to Theorem 16.12.

By (16.33),

$$(16.44) \quad \|u_{f_k}^{(s)} - u_f^{(s)}\|_{L^\infty_{\text{loc}}(B_1)} \rightarrow 0.$$

Therefore we have that, for each $x \in B_1$,

$$u_f^{(s)}(x) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f_k, e, \rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

From this, we claim that there exists a subsequence $\{f_{k_j}\}_j$, such that

$$(16.45) \quad \begin{aligned} u_f^{(s)}(x) &= \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f_{k_j}, e, \rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f, e, \rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho. \end{aligned}$$

For the convenience of the reader, the technical proof of (16.45) can be found in Appendix 16.5.

The claim in (16.45) establishes the desired result in (16.38) also for non continuous functions.

To prove the claim in (16.39), we use (16.1) and (16.12) to see that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{f, e, \rho}(x) &= \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho}^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{x}{\rho} - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e) \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} f_\rho(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)) + \frac{\left(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - \frac{x}{\rho} \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} f_\rho(Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{x}{\rho} - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e) \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} f(\rho Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)) + \frac{\left(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - \frac{x}{\rho} \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} f(\rho Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) \\ &= \rho^\gamma \left[\frac{\left(\frac{x}{\rho} - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e) \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} f(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)) + \frac{\left(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - \frac{x}{\rho} \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} f(Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) \right] \\ &= \rho^\gamma \mathcal{L}_f^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) \\ &= \rho^\gamma \mathcal{L}_{f, e, 1} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right). \end{aligned}$$

The claim in (16.39) then follows from this and (16.38). This concludes the proof of Theorem 16.15. \square

Proof of Theorem 16.4. From Proposition 16.13, we know that, under the hypotheses of Theorem 16.4, the function defined in (16.30) is the unique solution (up to a zero measure subset of $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$) to the problem (16.16). Then, the desired result in Theorem 16.4 follows from this and Theorem 16.15. \square

We now give the proof of the Schwarz result in Theorem 16.8.

Proof of Theorem 16.8. We first suppose that $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1)$. Under these assumptions we can apply Theorem 16.6 in dimension 2 and get

$$u_f^{(s)}(x) = 2\pi \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \tilde{u}_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho,$$

where \tilde{u}_{f_ρ} has been defined in the statement of Theorem 16.6. Therefore, when $n = 2$ we can apply Theorem 16.2 to \tilde{u}_{f_ρ} and get

$$\tilde{u}_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\partial B_1} f_\rho(Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1},$$

which leads to (16.22) in the case in which $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1)$.

Suppose now that $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1)$, and consider a sequence of functions $\{f_k\}_k \subset C(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_1)$ as in (16.32). We let $u_{f_k}^{(s)}$ be the unique pointwise continuous solution to the problem (16.31), according to Theorem 16.12. From the previous step, we have that, for each $x \in B_1$,

$$u_{f_k}^{(s)}(x) = \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(\int_{\partial B_1} f_k(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

By this and (16.44), we have that, for each $x \in B_1$,

$$u_f^{(s)}(x) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) f_k(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

From this, one sees that there exists a subsequence $\{f_{k_j}\}_j$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (16.46) \quad u_f^{(s)}(x) &= \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) f_{k_j}(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) f(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho. \end{aligned}$$

For the facility of the reader, a detailed proof of (16.46) is given in Appendix 16.5.

We observe that the proof of Theorem 16.8 is completed, thanks to (16.46). \square

We now deal with the convergence result in Proposition 16.5.

Proof of Proposition 16.5. Let $f \in C(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$, for each $s \in (s_0, 1]$. Furthermore let $u_f^{(s)}$ and u_f as in the statement of Proposition 16.5. Then, Theorem 16.1 implies that the following identity holds for each $\rho \in (1, R)$

$$(16.47) \quad u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) = \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho}^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) dH_e^{n-1} = \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f, e, \rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1},$$

thanks to (16.12), where u_{f_ρ} is the unique solution to the classical Dirichlet problem (16.19).

In particular, we have that

$$(16.48) \quad u_f\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) = \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_f^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) dH_e^{n-1} = \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f,e,1}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) dH_e^{n-1}.$$

Now, using (16.17), (16.23) and (16.47) we obtain for each $x \in B_1$ and $R_0 \in (1, R)$ the following identity

$$(16.49) \quad \begin{aligned} & u_f^{(s)}(x) - u_f(x) \\ &= \int_1^\infty |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} - u_f(x) \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_1^{R_0} |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(u_{f_\rho}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - u_f(x) \right) d\rho \\ &\quad + \int_{R_0}^\infty |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} - u_f(x) \right) d\rho. \end{aligned}$$

By the continuity of u_f and f , we have that for each $\delta > 0$ there exists some $R_0 \in (1, R)$ such that for each $\rho \in (1, R_0)$

$$(16.50) \quad \begin{aligned} & \left| u_f\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - u_f(x) \right| \leq \delta \quad \text{for all } x \in B_1 \\ & \text{and} \quad \|f_\rho - f\|_{L^\infty(\partial B_1)} \leq \delta. \end{aligned}$$

Also, we point out that

$$\mathcal{L}_{f_\rho, e, 1}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) = \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho}^{Q_-^{x/\rho}(e), Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) = \mathcal{L}_{f, e, \rho}(x),$$

thanks to (16.12).

Therefore, from this, (16.47), (16.48), and (16.50), for all $x \in B_1$, we deduce that, if $\rho \in (1, R_0)$,

$$(16.51) \quad \begin{aligned} & \left| u_{f_\rho}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - u_f(x) \right| \leq \left| u_{f_\rho}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - u_f\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) \right| + \left| u_f\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - u_f(x) \right| \\ &= \left| \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho, e, 1}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - \mathcal{L}_{f, e, 1}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) dH_e^{n-1} \right| + \left| u_f\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - u_f(x) \right| \\ &= \left| \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho - f, e, 1}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) dH_e^{n-1} \right| + \left| u_f\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) - u_f(x) \right| \\ &\leq \int_{\partial B_1} \left| \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho - f, e, 1}\left(\frac{x}{\rho}\right) \right| dH_e^{n-1} + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

Now, if $x \in B_1$ and $\rho \in (1, R_0)$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (16.52) \quad |Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)| &= 2\sqrt{\left(\frac{x \cdot e}{\rho}\right)^2 - \frac{|x|^2}{\rho^2} + 1} \geq 2\sqrt{1 - \frac{|x|^2}{\rho^2}} \\
 &= \frac{2}{\rho}\sqrt{\rho^2 - |x|^2} \geq \frac{2}{R_0}\sqrt{1 - |x|^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

and thus, according to (16.1),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (16.53) \quad & \left| \mathcal{L}_{f_\rho - f, e, 1} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) \right| \\
 &= \left| \frac{\left(\frac{x}{\rho} - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e) \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} (f_\rho - f)(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e)) + \frac{\left(Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - \frac{x}{\rho} \right) \cdot e}{|Q_+^{x/\rho}(e) - Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)|} (f_\rho - f)(Q_-^{x/\rho}(e)) \right| \\
 &\leq 4 \frac{R_0}{2\sqrt{1 - |x|^2}} \|f_\rho - f\|_{L^\infty(\partial B_1)} \\
 &\leq \frac{2R_0 \delta}{\sqrt{1 - |x|^2}},
 \end{aligned}$$

and therefore, plugging this information into (16.51), we obtain that, if $x \in B_1$ and $\rho \in (1, R_0)$,

$$(16.54) \quad \left| u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) - u_f(x) \right| \leq \left(\frac{2R_0}{\sqrt{1 - |x|^2}} + 1 \right) \delta.$$

Furthermore, employing the change of variable $e := \omega/|\omega|$ and recalling (16.13),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (16.55) \quad & \int_{R_0}^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f, e, \rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} - |\partial B_1| u_f(x) \right) d\rho \\
 &= \int_{R_0}^\infty \frac{\mathcal{E}(x, \rho)}{\rho^{n-1}} \left(\int_{\partial B_\rho} \mathcal{L}_{f, \omega/|\omega|, |\omega|}(x) dH_\omega^{n-1} - |\partial B_1| u_f(x) \right) d\rho \\
 &= c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{|y|^2}{(|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2) |y|^n} (\mathcal{L}_{f, y/|y|, |y|}(x) - |\partial B_1| u_f(x)) dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

We also deduce from (16.1) the following pointwise estimate

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \mathcal{L}_{f,y/|y|,|y|}(x) \right| \\
 = & \left| \frac{\left(\frac{x}{|y|} - Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \cdot \frac{y}{|y|}}{\left| Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) - Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right|} f_{|y|} \left(Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right. \\
 (16.56) \quad & \left. + \frac{\left(Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) - \frac{x}{|y|} \right) \cdot \frac{y}{|y|}}{\left| Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) - Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right|} f_{|y|} \left(Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-|x|^2}} \left(\left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| + \left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

We claim that

$$(16.57) \quad \text{the right hand side in (16.56) is } L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \text{ for each } s \in (s_0, 1].$$

Indeed, if we define the following function

$$\begin{aligned}
 (16.58) \quad & F_{\pm} : \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1 \\
 & y \mapsto |y| Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|),
 \end{aligned}$$

we see that it is C^1 and invertible. Note that, recalling also the limits in (16.4), one finds that

$$(16.59) \quad \|\det(DF_{\pm}^{-1}(z))\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)} \leq C,$$

for some positive constant C , depending on x . Therefore by applying Theorem 2 in Section 3.3.3 of [Eva18], we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (16.60) \quad & \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{\left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|) \right) \right|}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{\left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|) \right) \right|}{\left| |y| Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|) \right|^{n+2s}} dy \\
 & = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|f(z)|}{|z|^{n+2s}} |\det(DF_{\pm}^{-1}(z))| dz \leq C \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|f(z)|}{|z|^{n+2s}} dz.
 \end{aligned}$$

This and the fact that $f \in L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ for each $s \in (s_0, 1]$ entail that (16.57) holds true.

As a consequence of (16.56) and (16.57) we have that the integrals in (16.55) are finite and bounded in s .

Using this information and (16.54), we deduce from (16.49) that for each $\delta > 0$ there exists some $R_0 \in (1, R)$ such that for each $\rho \in (1, R_0)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |u_f^{(s)}(x) - u_f(x)| \\ & \leq \int_1^{R_0} |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left| u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) - u_f(x) \right| d\rho \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{R_0}^\infty |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} - u_f(x) \right) d\rho \right| \\ & \leq \int_1^{R_0} |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(\frac{2R_0}{\sqrt{1-|x|^2}} + 1 \right) \delta d\rho \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{R_0}^\infty |\partial B_1| \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} - u_f(x) \right) d\rho \right| \\ & \leq C(x, R)\delta + c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \\ & \quad \times \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{|y|^2}{(|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2) |y|^n} (\mathcal{L}_{f,y/|y|,|y|}(x) - |\partial B_1| u_f(x)) dy \\ & \leq C(x, R)\delta + c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{|y|^2}{(|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2) |y|^n} \\ & \quad \times \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - |x|^2}} \left(\left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| + \left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| \right) - |\partial B_1| u_f(x) \right) dy \end{aligned}$$

where $C(x, R_0)$ depends only on x and R_0 . By taking the limit as $s \nearrow 1$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{s \nearrow 1} c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{|y|^2}{(|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2) |y|^n} \\ & \times \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - |x|^2}} \left(\left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| + \left| f_{|y|} \left(Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| \right) - |\partial B_1| u_f(x) \right) dy \\ & = 0 \end{aligned}$$

since $c(n, s) \rightarrow 0$ for $s \nearrow 1$ by (16.14). As a consequence

$$\lim_{s \nearrow 1} |u_f^{(s)}(x) - u_f(x)| \leq C(x, R)\delta.$$

This and the arbitrariness of δ give the desired claim in Proposition 16.5. \square

16.4 Harnack inequality

In this section we provide a new proof of the Harnack inequality for s -harmonic functions as stated in Theorem 16.7. Our strategy is to use the Fractional Malmheden Theorem to show that this result can be directly inferred from the classical Harnack inequality for harmonic functions.

Proof of Theorem 16.7. For convenience we call $u|_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} = f$. Let us first assume that $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$. Under this assumption, we can apply Theorem 16.6 and obtain that

$$u(x) = |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho,$$

for each $x \in B_1$, where u_{f_ρ} has been defined in the statement of Theorem 16.6. Therefore, we have that

$$(16.61) \quad u(0) = c(n, s) |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \frac{u_{f_\rho}(0)}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} d\rho.$$

Now we fix $r \in (0, 1)$ and we consider $x \in B_r$. Applying the Harnack inequality for classical harmonic functions to u_{f_ρ} , we have that

$$u_{f_\rho}(0) \leq \frac{(1 + |x|/\rho)^{n-1}}{1 - |x|/\rho} u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right).$$

From this, (16.13) and (16.61) we obtain that

$$(16.62) \quad \begin{aligned} u(0) &\leq c(n, s) |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \frac{(1 + |x|/\rho)^{n-1}}{1 - |x|/\rho} u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho \\ &= |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \frac{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)}{\rho^2 (1 - |x|^2)^s} \frac{(\rho + |x|)^{n-1}}{\rho^{n-2}(\rho - |x|)} u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho \\ &= |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \frac{(\rho + |x|)^n}{\rho^n (1 - |x|^2)^s} u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho \\ &= |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) g(\rho, t) u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho, \end{aligned}$$

where for convenience we have called $t := |x|$ in the last line and defined

$$g(\rho, t) := \frac{(\rho + t)^n}{\rho^n (1 - t^2)^s},$$

with $(\rho, t) \in [1, \infty) \times [0, r]$.

Since $g(\rho, t)$ is decreasing in ρ and increasing in t , we have that

$$\frac{(1+r)^n}{(1-r^2)^s} = \sup_{(\rho,t) \in [1,\infty) \times [0,r]} g(\rho, t).$$

Therefore, from this, (16.20) and (16.62) we obtain that

$$u(0) \leq |\partial B_1| \frac{(1+r)^n}{(1-r^2)^s} \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho = \frac{(1+r)^n}{(1-r^2)^s} u(x),$$

which establishes the first inequality in (16.21).

To prove the second inequality in (16.21), we make use of the Harnack inequality for harmonic functions, thus obtaining that

$$u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) \leq \frac{1 + |x|/\rho}{(1 - |x|/\rho)^{n-1}} u_{f_\rho}(0).$$

Using this and (16.13) into (16.61), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} u(0) &= c(n, s) |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \frac{u_{f_\rho}(0)}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} d\rho \\ &\geq c(n, s) |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{\rho(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \frac{(1 - |x|/\rho)^{n-1}}{1 + |x|/\rho} u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho \\ &= c(n, s) |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \frac{(\rho - |x|)^{n-1}}{\rho^{n-1}(\rho^2 - 1)^s(\rho + |x|)} u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho \\ &= |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \frac{(\rho - |x|)^n}{\rho^n(1 - |x|^2)^s} u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho. \end{aligned}$$

Using again the notation $t := |x|$, we define the following function

$$(16.63) \quad g_1(\rho, t) := \frac{(\rho - t)^n}{\rho^n(1 - t^2)^s},$$

with $(\rho, t) \in [1, \infty) \times [0, r]$, and we see that

$$(16.64) \quad u(0) \geq |\partial B_1| \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) g_1(\rho, t) u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho.$$

Since g_1 is increasing in ρ , we have that, for all $(\rho, t) \in [1, \infty) \times [0, r]$,

$$g_1(\rho, t) \geq g_1(1, t) = \frac{(1 - t)^n}{(1 - t^2)^s} = \frac{(1 - t)^{n-s}}{(1 + t)^s} =: g_2(t).$$

Notice also that g_2 is decreasing, and therefore, for all $(\rho, t) \in [1, \infty) \times [0, r]$,

$$g_1(\rho, t) \geq g_2(r) = \frac{(1-r)^{n-s}}{(1+r)^s} = \frac{(1-r)^n}{(1-r^2)^s}.$$

Plugging this information into (16.64) and recalling (16.20), we get

$$u(0) \geq |\partial B_1| \frac{(1-r)^n}{(1-r^2)^s} \int_1^\infty \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) u_{f_\rho} \left(\frac{x}{\rho} \right) d\rho \geq \frac{(1-r)^n}{(1-r^2)^s} u(x),$$

which completes the proof of (16.21) under the additional continuity assumption on f .

To deal with the general case, we perform an approximation argument, whose details go as follows. If $f \in L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$, we take a sequence $\{f_k\}_k \subset C(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1) \cap L_s^1(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ as in (16.32). Then for $u_{f_k}^{(s)}$ the two-sided inequality in (16.21) holds true, thanks to the previous step. Also, by (16.44), we have the local uniform convergence

$$\|u_{f_k}^{(s)} - u\|_{L_{loc}^\infty(B_1)} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty,$$

and therefore we deduce the two sided inequality (16.21) also in this case.

It is only left to prove that the constants provided in equation (16.21) are optimal. To show this let us fix some direction $e \in \partial B_1$, a constant $\varepsilon > 0$ and the function

$$f_\varepsilon(y) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_\varepsilon((1+\varepsilon)e), \\ (|y|^2 - 1)^s & \text{if } y \in B_\varepsilon((1+\varepsilon)e). \end{cases}$$

Then the function

$$u_{f_\varepsilon}^{(s)}(x) := c(n, s) \int_{B_\varepsilon((\varepsilon+1)e)} \frac{(1-|x|^2)^s}{|y-x|^n} dy$$

is s -harmonic in B_1 , as a consequence of Proposition 16.13. Therefore, if we fix $x = -re$ for $r \in (0, 1)$, we have that

$$\frac{u_{f_\varepsilon}^{(s)}(0)}{u_{f_\varepsilon}^{(s)}(-re)} = \frac{\int_{B_\varepsilon((\varepsilon+1)e)} \frac{dy}{|y|^n}}{\int_{B_\varepsilon((\varepsilon+1)e)} \frac{(1-r^2)^s}{|y+re|^n} dy},$$

and thus, by Lebesgue Differentiation Theorem, we conclude that

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{u_{f_\varepsilon}^{(s)}(0)}{u_{f_\varepsilon}^{(s)}(-re)} = \frac{(1+r)^n}{(1-r^2)^s}.$$

This proves that the constant on the left hand side inequality in (16.21) is optimal.

Similarly, taking $x = re$, one sees that

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{u_{f_\varepsilon}^{(s)}(re)}{u_{f_\varepsilon}^{(s)}(0)} = \frac{(1-r^2)^s}{(1-r)^n},$$

which shows that the constant on the right hand side inequality in (16.21) is also optimal. This concludes the proof of Theorem 16.7. \square

16.5 Appendices

Averaging the Fractional Poisson Kernel

Here we give a direct proof of the identity pointed out in footnote 1 on page 635. Namely, we establish that, if $x \in B_1$ and $\rho > 1$,

$$(16.65) \quad \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) = \rho^{n-1} \int_{\partial B_\rho} P(x, y) dH_y^{n-1},$$

being P the Fractional Poisson Kernel in (16.27).

The identity in (16.65) has its own interest and it can be deduced from our Fractional Malmheden Theorem, by taking a datum f concentrating along a given sphere ∂B_ρ . For the sake of completeness however, we provide here an independent proof, only based on elementary computations and standard integral formulas.

More specifically, we aim at showing that

$$(16.66) \quad \int_{\partial B_1} \frac{dH_\omega^{n-1}}{|x - \rho\omega|^n} = \frac{\rho^{2-n}}{\rho^2 - |x|^2}.$$

Indeed, once (16.66) is established, we deduce from it, (16.13) and (16.27) that

$$\int_{\partial B_\rho} P(x, y) dH_y^{n-1} = c(n, s) (1 - |x|^2)^s \int_{\partial B_\rho} \frac{dH_y^{n-1}}{(|y|^2 - 1)^s |x - y|^n}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{c(n, s) (1 - |x|^2)^s}{|\partial B_1| \rho^{n-1}} \int_{\partial B_1} \frac{\rho^{n-1} dH_\omega^{n-1}}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s |x - \rho\omega|^n} \\
&= \frac{c(n, s) (1 - |x|^2)^s}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \int_{\partial B_1} \frac{dH_\omega^{n-1}}{|x - \rho\omega|^n} = c(n, s) \frac{\rho^{2-n} (1 - |x|^2)^s}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s (\rho^2 - |x|^2)} \\
&= \rho^{1-n} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho)
\end{aligned}$$

and this would complete the proof of (16.65).

Hence, we focus now on proving (16.66). To this end, we use spherical coordinates on ∂B_1 , with $\theta, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n-3} \in [0, \pi]$ and $\theta_{n-2} \in [0, 2\pi)$, see e.g. equation (A.23) in [Buc16] or pages 60-61 in [Mik65], which correspond to $\omega = \omega(\theta)$ of the form

$$\begin{cases} \omega_1 = \sin \theta \sin \theta_1 \dots \sin \theta_{n-3} \sin \theta_{n-2}, \\ \omega_2 = \sin \theta \sin \theta_1 \dots \sin \theta_{n-3} \cos \theta_{n-2}, \\ \omega_3 = \sin \theta \sin \theta_1 \dots \cos \theta_{n-3}, \\ \vdots \\ \omega_n = \cos \theta \end{cases}$$

and produce a surface element of the form

$$\sin^{n-2} \theta \sin^{n-3} \theta_1 \dots \sin^2 \theta_{n-4} \sin \theta_{n-3} d\theta d\theta_1 \dots d\theta_{n-2}.$$

Also, up to a rotation, to prove (16.66) we can assume that $x = (0, \dots, 0, |x|)$. In this way, we find that

$$|x - \rho\omega|^2 = |x|^2 + \rho^2 - 2\rho x \cdot \omega = |x|^2 + \rho^2 - 2\rho|x|\omega_n = |x|^2 + \rho^2 - 2\rho|x| \cos \theta,$$

whence it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{dH_\omega^{n-1}}{|x - \rho\omega|^n} \\
&= \int_{\substack{\theta, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n-3} \in [0, \pi] \\ \theta_{n-2} \in [0, 2\pi)}} \frac{\sin^{n-2} \theta \sin^{n-3} \theta_1 \dots \sin^2 \theta_{n-4} \sin \theta_{n-3} d\theta d\theta_1 \dots d\theta_{n-2}}{(|x|^2 + \rho^2 - 2\rho|x| \cos \theta)^{\frac{n}{2}}} \\
&= 2\pi \left(\prod_{j=1}^{n-3} \int_0^\pi \sin^{n-j-2} \theta_j d\theta_j \right) \int_{\theta \in [0, \pi]} \frac{\sin^{n-2} \theta d\theta}{(|x|^2 + \rho^2 - 2\rho|x| \cos \theta)^{\frac{n}{2}}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we use the notation $\tau := \frac{\rho}{|x|} \in (1, +\infty)$ and, by Proposition A.9 in [Buc16], we deduce that

$$\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{dH_\omega^{n-1}}{|x - \rho\omega|^n} = \frac{2\pi}{|x|^n} \left(\prod_{k=1}^{n-3} \int_0^\pi \sin^k \vartheta d\vartheta \right) \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin^{n-2} \theta d\theta}{(\tau^2 + 1 - 2\tau \cos \theta)^{\frac{n}{2}}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{2\pi}{|x|^n \tau^{n-2}(\tau^2 - 1)} \left(\prod_{k=1}^{n-3} \int_0^\pi \sin^k \vartheta \, d\vartheta \right) \int_0^\pi \sin^{n-2} \alpha \, d\alpha \\
 &= \frac{2\pi}{|x|^n \tau^{n-2}(\tau^2 - 1)} \left(\prod_{k=1}^{n-2} \int_0^\pi \sin^k \vartheta \, d\vartheta \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

This and Proposition A.10 in [Buc16] yield that

$$\int_{\partial B_1} \frac{dH_\omega^{n-1}}{|x - \rho\omega|^n} = \frac{2\pi^{\frac{n}{2}}}{|x|^n \tau^{n-2}(\tau^2 - 1) \Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)} = \frac{|\partial B_1|}{|x|^n \tau^{n-2}(\tau^2 - 1)} = \frac{|\partial B_1| \rho^{2-n}}{\rho^2 - |x|^2}.$$

The proof of (16.66) is thereby complete.

Proof of (16.45)

We recall (16.13) and we employ the change of variable $e := \omega/|\omega|$ to see that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f_k, e, \rho}(x) \, dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 (16.67) \quad &= \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - 1)^s (\rho^2 - |x|^2)} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{L}_{f_k, e, \rho}(x) \, dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 &= \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho^2}{\rho^n (\rho^2 - 1)^s (\rho^2 - |x|^2)} \left(\int_{\partial B_\rho} \mathcal{L}_{f_k, \omega/|\omega|, |\omega|}(x) \, dH_\omega^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{|y|^2}{|y|^n (|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2)} \mathcal{L}_{f_k, y/|y|, |y|}(x) \, dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

It also follows from (16.32) that, for a.e. $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$,

$$(16.68) \quad \mathcal{L}_{f_k, y/|y|, |y|}(x) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_{f, y/|y|, |y|}(x) \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Now we take $R_0 \in (1, R)$ and we deduce from (16.67) that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{c(n, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f_k, e, \rho}(x) \, dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\
 (16.69) \quad &= \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} \frac{|y|^2}{|y|^n (|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2)} \mathcal{L}_{f_k, y/|y|, |y|}(x) \, dy \\
 &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{|y|^2}{|y|^n (|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2)} \mathcal{L}_{f_k, y/|y|, |y|}(x) \, dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

Recalling the computation in (16.53), for k large enough we have that

$$\|\mathcal{L}_{f_k, y/|y|, |y|}(x)\|_{L^\infty(B_{R_0} \setminus B_1)} \leq \frac{2R_0}{\sqrt{1-|x|^2}} \|f\|_{L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1)}.$$

Consequently, using this, (16.68) and the Dominated Convergence Theorem,

$$(16.70) \quad \begin{aligned} & \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} \frac{|y|^2}{|y|^n (|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2)} \mathcal{L}_{f_k, y/|y|, |y|}(x) dy \\ &= \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} \frac{|y|^2}{|y|^n (|y|^2 - 1)^s (|y|^2 - |x|^2)} \mathcal{L}_{f, y/|y|, |y|}(x) dy. \end{aligned}$$

Also, we claim that there exists a subsequence $\{f_{k_j}\}_j$ such that

$$(16.71) \quad \|\mathcal{L}_{f_{k_j}, y/|y|, |y|}(x) - \mathcal{L}_{f, y/|y|, |y|}(x)\|_{L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0})} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } j \rightarrow +\infty.$$

To show (16.71), we recall (16.52) and we observe that, for every $x \in B_1$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}$,

$$(16.72) \quad \begin{aligned} & \left| \mathcal{L}_{f_{k_j}, y/|y|, |y|}(x) \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{\left(\frac{x}{|y|} - Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \cdot \frac{y}{|y|}}{\left| Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) - Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right|} f_{k_j} \left(|y| Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{\left(Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) - \frac{x}{|y|} \right) \cdot \frac{y}{|y|}}{\left| Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) - Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right|} f_{k_j} \left(Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{R_0}{\sqrt{1-|x|^2}} \left[\left| f_{k_j} \left(|y| Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| + \left| f_{k_j} \left(|y| Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right| \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, by (16.32) there exists a subsequence $\{f_{k_j}\}_j$ and a function $h \in L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ such that $|f_{k_j}(y)| \leq h(y)$ for a.e. $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$ (see for instance Theorem 4.9 in [Bre11]). Therefore, using this information into (16.72), we have

$$(16.73) \quad \left| \mathcal{L}_{f_{k_j}, y/|y|, |y|}(x) \right| \leq \frac{R_0}{\sqrt{1-|x|^2}} \left[h \left(|y| Q_-^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) + h \left(|y| Q_+^{x/|y|} \left(\frac{y}{|y|} \right) \right) \right]$$

for a.e. $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}$.

Now we recall the map F_{\pm} defined in (16.58), which is C^1 and invertible, and therefore, by Theorem 2 in Section 3.3.3 of [Eva18] and (16.59), we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h\left(|y|Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)\right)}{|y|^{n+2s}} dy &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h\left(|y|Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)\right)}{\left||y|Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)\right|^{n+2s}} dy \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h(z)}{|z|^{n+2s}} |\det(DF_{\pm}^{-1}(z))| dz \leq C \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h(z)}{|z|^{n+2s}} dz. \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, we deduce that

$$h\left(|y|Q_{\pm}^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)\right) \in L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}).$$

This, the bound in (16.73), the pointwise convergence in (16.68) and the Dominated Convergence Theorem lead to (16.71), as desired.

Hence, putting together (16.69), (16.70) and (16.71), we obtain that

$$u_f(x) = \int_1^\infty \int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) \mathcal{L}_{f,e,\rho}(x) dH_e^{n-1} d\rho$$

for each $x \in B_1$, which completes the proof of (16.45). □

Proof of (16.46)

The proof of (16.46) is similar to the one of (16.45). We provide here the details for the convenience of the reader.

From (16.13) with $n = 2$ and the change of variable $e := \omega/|\omega|$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{c(2,s)(1-|x|^2)^s} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) f_k(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ (16.74) \quad &= \int_1^\infty \frac{\rho}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_1} f_k(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{(\rho^2 - |x|^2)(\rho^2 - 1)^s} \left(\int_{\partial B_\rho} f_k(|\omega|Q^{x/|\omega|}(\omega/|\omega|)) dH_\omega^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1} \frac{1}{(|y|^2 - |x|^2)(|y|^2 - 1)^s} f_k(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) dy \end{aligned}$$

By (16.32), we have that, for a.e. $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1$,

$$(16.75) \quad f_k(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) \rightarrow f(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Now we take $R_0 \in (1, R)$ and we get from (16.74) that

$$(16.76) \quad \begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{c(2, s)(1 - |x|^2)^s} \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) f_k(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho \\ &= \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} \frac{1}{(|y|^2 - |x|^2)(|y|^2 - 1)^s} f_k(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) dy \\ & \quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{1}{(|y|^2 - |x|^2)(|y|^2 - 1)^s} f_k(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) dy \end{aligned}$$

Notice that, for k large enough,

$$\|f_k\|_{L^\infty(B_{R_0} \setminus B_1)} \leq \|f\|_{L^\infty(B_R \setminus B_1)}.$$

As a consequence,

$$(16.77) \quad \begin{aligned} & \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} \frac{1}{(|y|^2 - |x|^2)(|y|^2 - 1)^s} f_k(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) dy \\ &= \int_{B_{R_0} \setminus B_1} \frac{1}{(|y|^2 - |x|^2)(|y|^2 - 1)^s} f(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) dy \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, recalling (16.32) (see also Theorem 4.9 in [Bre11]) we deduce the existence of a subsequence $\{f_{k_j}\}_j$ and of a function $h \in L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_1)$ such that

$$(16.78) \quad |f_{k_j}(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|))| \leq h(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|))$$

for a.e. $y \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}$.

Furthermore, we claim that

$$(16.79) \quad h(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) \text{ belongs to } L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}).$$

Indeed, the function

$$\begin{aligned} F : \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0} &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0} \\ y &\mapsto |y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|) \end{aligned}$$

is C^1 and invertible. Moreover, since

$$\lim_{|y| \rightarrow \infty} Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|) = id_{\partial B_1},$$

we find that

$$\|\det(DF^{-1}(z))\|_{L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0})} \leq \tilde{C},$$

for some positive constant $\tilde{C} > 0$.

From this and Theorem 2 in Section 3.3.3 of [Eva18] we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|))}{|y|^{2+2s}} dy &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|))}{||y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)|^{2+2s}} dy \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h(z)}{|z|^{2+2s}} |\det(DF^{-1}(z))| dz \leq \tilde{C} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0}} \frac{h(z)}{|z|^{2+2s}} dz, \end{aligned}$$

which establishes (16.79).

From (16.75), (16.78) and (16.79) and the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we deduce that

$$\|f_{k_j}(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|)) - f(|y|Q^{x/|y|}(y/|y|))\|_{L^1_s(\mathbb{R}^n \setminus B_{R_0})} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } j \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Gathering together this, (16.76) and (16.77), we conclude that

$$u_f^{(s)}(x) = \int_1^\infty \left(\int_{\partial B_1} \mathcal{E}(x, \rho) f(\rho Q^{x/\rho}(e)) dH_e^{n-1} \right) d\rho.$$

This finishes the proof of (16.46). □

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